

HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.1.2

STATUS-QUO ANALYSIS OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICIES IN 8 EU COUNTRIES

PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

NATIONAL REPORT FOR BELGIUM

AUGUST 2015

Partner: *University of Antwerp*

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

OXFORD
BROOKES
UNIVERSITY

Universiteit
Antwerpen

Wuppertal Institute
for Climate, Environment
and Energy

SEI

STOCKHOLM
ENVIRONMENT
INSTITUTE

Institution: University of Antwerp

Steering Committee member ⁽¹⁾: Prof. Aviel Verbruggen

Prepared by: Johan Couder

⁽¹⁾ The Steering Committee member has the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the report.

HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACRONYMS	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL	8
1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE BUILDINGS SECTOR.....	8
1.1.1 Regulatory Policy Instruments	8
1.1.2 Dissemination and awareness instruments / Informative policy Instruments	22
1.1.3 Economic Policy Instruments	29
1.1.4 Capacity Building and Networking	41
1.1.5 Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services	44
1.1.6 Policy Instruments for Research and Development and Best available Technology (BAT) Promotion.....	45
1.1.7 Summary Table for the Buildings Sector in BELGIUM	49
1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR.....	52
1.2.1 Planning Instruments	52
1.2.2 Regulatory Policy Instruments	53
1.2.3 Financial Policy Instruments	56
1.2.4 Dissemination and awareness instruments	64
1.2.5 Policy Instruments for Research and Development	65
1.2.6 Summary Table for the Transport Sector in #country#.....	68
2. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE REGIONAL / LOCAL LEVEL	70
2.1 CASE STUDY: THE CITY OF GHENT	70
2.1.1 Ghent	70
2.1.2 Energy Efficiency Policy / Action	70
2.1.3 Energy Efficiency instruments / measures per sector	73
2.1.4 Interaction between national and local policies:	75
2.1.5 Contact person and contact details.	76
REFERENCES	77

ACRONYMS

ANB	Agency for Nature and Forest (Agentschap voor Natuur en Bos)
AEE	Energy Employment Alliance (Alliance Emploi-Environnement)
AWAC	Walloon Air and Climate Agency (Agence wallonne de l'Air et du Climat)
BatEx	Model (“Exemplary”) Building (Bâtiment Exemplaire)
BAU	Business As Usual
BBRI	Belgian Building Research Institute
BGL	Brussels Green Loan
CDM	Clean Development Mechanism
CELINE	Cellule Interrégionale de l’Environnement
CHP	Combined Heat and Power, cogeneration
CO	carbon monoxide
CO ₂	carbon dioxide
COBRACE	Brussels Code for Air, Climate and Energy management (Code Bruxellois de l’air, du climat et de la maîtrise de l’énergie)
CONCERE/ENOVER	Energy Consultation Group (Concertation Etat-Régions pour l’Energie”/Energieoverleg)
DIV	Department for Registration of Vehicles (Dienst Inschrijvingen Voertuigen)
DG	Directorate General
EE	Energy Efficiency
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive (Directive 2012/27/EU)
EP	Energy Performance
EPB	Energy Performane of Buildings
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (Directive 2010/31/ZU)
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
ESD	Energy Services Directive (Directive 2006/32/EC)
ETS	Energy Trading Scheme
EU	European Union
Fedesco	Federal Energy Services Company
FPS	Federal Public Service
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
GHG	Greenhouse Gases
GWh	Gigawatt hour
HC	Hydrocarbons
IBGE/BIM	Brussels Environment

IEE	Intelligent Energy Europe
INBO	Research Institute for Nature and Forest (Instituut voor Natuur en Bosonderzoek)
IRCEL/CELINE	Interregional Environmental Agency
IRCEL	Intergewestelijke Cel voor het Leefmilieu
LNE	Environment, Nature and Energy Department (Leefmilieu, Natuur en Energie)
LNG	Liquid Natural Gas
MAM	Maximum Authorised Mass
MEPS	Mandatory Energy Performance Standard
MIVB/STIB	public transport operator of Brussels
MIVB	Maatschappij voor het Intercommunaal Vervoer te Brussel
MMD	Monitoring Mechanism Decision
MMR	Monitoring Mechanism Regulation
Mtoe	Million tons of oil equivalent
MW	Megawatt
NEEAP	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan
NMBS/SNCB	national (Belgian) railway operator
NMBS	Nationale Maatschappij van de Belgische Spoorwegen
NOx	Nitrogen Oxides
NRP	National Reform Programme
nZEB	nearly Zero-Energy Building
PACE	Air-Climate-Energy Plan (Plan Air Climat Energie)
PAM	Policies And Measures
PEB	Energy Performance of Buildings (performance énergétique des bâtiments)
PM	Particulate Matter
PIT	Personal Income Tax
PIVERT	Green Investments Plan (Plan d'Investissements Verts)
pkm	passenger kilometre
PAEE	Action Plan on Energy Efficiency (Plan d'Action en Efficacité Energétique)
PACE	Air Climate Energy Plan (Plan Air Climat Energie)
PLAGE	Local Action Plan for the Use of Energy (Plan local d'actions de gestion de l'énergie)
PMR	Persons with Reduced Mobility (Personnes à Mobilité Réduite)
PSO	Public Service Obligations
PV	Photovoltaic
RES	Renewable Energy Sources

R&D	Research & Development
SDRB	Brussels Regional Development Agency (Société de Développement pour la Région de Bruxelles-Capitale)
SLRB	Brussels Regional Housing Authority (Société du Logement de la Région de Bruxelles-Capital)
REHA	Rehabilitation premium for owners (prime à la Réhabilitation en faveur des propriétaires)
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
ReTiBo	Registration Ticket On-board computer
SERV	Flanders Social and Economic Council (Sociaal Economische Raad Vlaanderen)
SISP	Public Service Housing Company
SME	Small and Medium Enterprises
SPW	Walloon Public Service (Service Public de Wallonie)
SRWT	Walloon Regional Transport Company (Société régionale wallonne du Transport)
SWL	Walloon Housing Corporation (Société Wallonne du Logement)
TEC	Walloon public transport operator (Transport En Commun)
TEP	Tradable Emissions Permit
TWh	Terawatt hour
UNFCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
URE	Rational Use of Energy (Utilisation Rationnelle de l'Energie)
UREBA	Rational Use of Energy in Public Buildings (Utilisation Rationnelle de l'Énergie dans les Bâtiments publics et Assimilés)
VEA	Flemish Energy Agency (Vlaams Energieagentschap)
VAP	Flemish Adaptation Plan (Vlaams adaptatieplan)
VMP	Flemish Mitigation Plan (Vlaams mitigatieplan)
VITO	Flemish Institute for Technological Research (Vlaame Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek)
VMSW	Flemish Association for Social Housing (Vlaamse Maatschappij voor Sociaal Wonen)
VORA	Progress Report (Vooruitgangsrapport)
WTCB	Belgian Building Research Institute (Wetenschappelijk & Technisch Centrum voor het Bouwbedrijf)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The competences of the Federal Government in the areas of energy and climate policies are limited. Its most important competence relates to “products” (Ecodesign, energy labelling). As far as buildings are concerned, the federal responsibility is limited to its own buildings, although it does provide a forum for coordination between the Regions regarding their implementation of the EPB Directive. Concerning transport, its most relevant remaining competence is the national railway operator NMBS/SNCB. The federal level helps the Regions accomplish a modal shift by promoting home-work rail travel.

All three Regions in Belgium focus on buildings, both residential and non-residential. They expect significant final energy savings by imposing mandatory energy building performance standards (MEPS), including the gradual introduction of near Zero Energy Buildings. This is not a surprise, given the low energetic quality of the housing stock in Belgium. However, the Flemish Region and the Brussels-Capital Region do not give a quantitative 2020 energy savings target for this particular measure. The Walloon Region expects a fairly modest 673 GWh final energy savings in 2020. The renovation of the existing building stock is encouraged by numerous subsidies (often called “premiums” or “bonuses”) in all three Regions and / or soft loans in the Walloon and Brussels-Capital Region. The Flemish Region is unique in that it relies on the Public Service Obligation (PSO) of the Distribution System Operators (DSOs) or “electricity grid managers”. This policy instrument is the only one the Flemish Region gives a clear target for, namely 14630 GWh final energy savings in 2020. All three regions pay particular attention to “vulnerable households”, who often get additional aid in the form of subsidies, soft loans and / or energy audits. Also striking in the Walloon Region and the Brussels-Capital Region is the combination of energy and climate policies with social policies, whereby the authorities vigorously try to stimulate “green jobs” in the construction sector. Informative and awareness raising initiatives are to be found at all levels (Federal, Regional), although in the Brussels-Capital Region and certainly in the Walloon Region those measures seem to be very fragmented.

Energy efficiency policies and measures for transport are weak, if not very weak. Basically, transport policies are limited to either agreements with the Regional public transport operators on improving vehicle fleet efficiencies and interconnectivity; or informative measures combined with financial / fiscal instruments to promote purchasing cars that emit less CO₂. In the Flemish Region and the Walloon Region ambitious mobility plans are still in the making.

In the case study of the City of Ghent, we encounter energy and climate policies that mirror those of the Flemish Region, with a focus on renovation of dwellings and promoting the nZEB standard for new-builds. Instruments are implementing strict “renovation standards”, aided by subsidies and awareness raising; whereby vulnerable households are targeted specifically. The local authorities however deeply regret that most of the policies and measures are a Regional competence, making it difficult for them to impose stricter rules, unless the City of Ghent is involved as owner. Their budget is also limited. In spite of significant competences in the area of urban planning, mobility policies in the City similarly seem to be lagging behind, and concentrates on making the city more biker and pedestrian friendly.

1. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE BUILDINGS SECTOR

1.1.1 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS

1.1.1.1 Implementation of the Ecodesign Directive

	Federal
General information	Belgium has implemented the Ecodesign Directive in its entirety and transposed it into Belgian law. To that end chapter V bis was added to the law on product standards (amendment of May 11, 2007). Stakeholders are invited to play a constructive role in the preparatory legislative process, in particular consultations around the specific eco-design product groups.
Type of policy instruments	Regulatory
Objectives	Improving energy and environmental performance of products on the internal (EU) market. Contribution towards global objectives of the European Union.
Target groups	Energy related products (ErP) excluding means of transport. To date 24 ecodesign implementing regulations have been put in place. Products covered range from household appliances, such as fridges, lamps and vacuum cleaners, to professional and industrial equipment, such as electric motors, power transformers and fans.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Market surveillance involves visual spot checks, examination of technical documentation and measurements in laboratories. The supervisors check whether the CE marking on the product has been applied and whether there is a declaration of conformity. The requirements concerning product information and technical documentation are also examined. Quantitative requirements are verified by measurements in laboratories. The procedures for sampling are laid down in the Ecodesign implementing measures. When the Ecodesign requirements are violated, the sanctions included a prison sentence (8 days to 3 years) and / or a fine (up to 4 160 million euros, not indexed).
Implementation network	The Ecodesign Directive comes under the jurisdiction of the federal public service FPS Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment ; but there is close cooperation with the FPS Economy, S.M.E.s, Self-employed and Energy, Directorate-general Energy , which is responsible for the Energy Labelling Directive. The Belgian stakeholders in the consultation groups are members of the Permanent Representative Working Group Energy (Enover); members of the group Sustainable production and consumption (CCIM); technical experts in administrations; members of the 'Federal Council for Sustainable Development' (FCSD); and identified experts for specific lots representing industry.
Outcome	The impact of the implementation of the Ecodesign directive is very significant. For the detailed quantitative evaluation please see D1.2 Table 3.

Legal reference Directive 2009/125/EC, formerly Directive 2005/32/EC.

Legal reference 21 DECEMBER 1998. [Law on product standards to promote sustainable production and consumption patterns and to protect the environment and public health](#)

Legal reference 11 MAY 2007 [Law amending the Law of December 21, 1998 on product standards to promote sustainable production and consumption patterns and to protect the environment and human health](#).

Contact person Belgium: FPS health, food chain safety and environment, product policy Maya De Groot: Maya.DeGroot@health.fgov.be
VITO & ECONOTEC (2015)

The implementation of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) is the responsibility of the regions. Therefore, there are three (3) different EPB regulations in Belgium.

1.1.1.2 Energy performance regulation (EPB) – Flemish Region

	Flemish Region.
General information	All buildings in Flanders for which an application for a building permit is made must meet certain minimum energy performance standards called EPB requirements, where EPB stands for ‘Energy Performance and Indoor Climate’ (“Energie Prestatie en Binnenklimaat”). For new construction (or equivalent) EPB requirements are related to thermal insulation (the so-called K-level or global thermal insulation of the building, and the U and R values); energy (the so-called E-performance level or “E-peil”, the net energy demand for heating, and the minimum share of renewable energy); and the indoor climate (ventilation and reduction of the risk of overheating). For renovation and for changing the function of the building there are also EPB requirements for thermal insulation, energy, indoor climate and from 2015 for technical installations. The EPB requirements are not the same for all buildings. Which EPB requirements apply for a construction project, depends on the function of the building (e.g. dwellings are subject to different requirements than offices, schools, industrial buildings, hospitals, restaurants, shops ...); the nature of the work (new construction has different requirements than for example deep renovation); and the year in which the planning permission was applied for. Every few years, the EPB requirements become stricter. When a building permit or notification for a dwelling, school or office dates from 2014 a minimum amount of energy has to come from renewable sources. From 2015 renovations or changes of function have to meet EPB requirements for the technical installations as well. By 2021, all new buildings in Flanders must be nearly zero energy buildings.
Type of policy instruments	Regulatory
Objectives	The agreed stricter energy efficiency performance standards for new buildings are an important step for attaining an energy neutral stock of new buildings by 2021. There are no quantitative objectives defined.
Target groups	The regulations apply to work on all buildings that are heated or cooled and for which a planning permission was applied for or a notification was made from January 1, 2006. Every new or renovated building thus falls under the regulation, except buildings where a specific exemption applies, and industrial buildings if at the time of the license application or notification it is certain that no air conditioning system will be installed. Exemptions are possible for agricultural buildings (depending on type of agricultural building), and for existing and new buildings for which meeting the requirements is technically, functionally or economically not

	feasible. There are also derogations from certain EPB requirements for tennis halls made of sailcloth.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	<p>During the building process, there are obligations for the notifiable (i.e. the client or owner of the construction project), for the architect and for the EPB reporter (“EPB verslaggever”). Prior to the start of the works the notifiable has to appoint a reporter. The reporter can be the designer or architect of the building, but also a different architect or engineer. The reporter must make an advance calculation to verify that the EPB requirements will be met. The reporter performs this calculation based on the design, the specifications, tenders, etc. For this calculation, he has to use the software package provided by the government. The prior calculation or “start statement” (“startverklaring”) has to be submitted electronically to the Flemish Energy Agency (VEA). VEA sends a reminder if the deadline for the prior calculation (“startverklaring”) is not met before the start of the works. If the pre-calculation shows that the requirements are not met on the basis of the design, the reporter has to make a proposal to ensure that the requirements will as yet be reached. The notifiable decides whether or not to carry out this proposal and to change certain building materials and installations in order to meet the requirements. The electronic “start statement” indicates the start date of the work and is also proof that a reporter has been appointed. During the execution of the works everything that affects thermal insulation, energy performance and indoor climate of the building is accurately tracked. In this phase, the notifiable retains the right to change the choices for certain materials or installations. If the architect notices that (e.g. due to a poor choice of materials or installations) the EPB requirements may not be met, he must report this to the notifiable and the reporter. The notifiable has to prove that the building meets the EPB requirements. The reporter makes a calculation (the EPB declaration) based on his findings, estimates, invoices, ... For this calculation, he used the software package provided by the government. The EPB declaration (“EPB-aangifte”) must be submitted in time to the Flemish Energy Agency (VEA). After the EPB declaration is submitted to the VEA, the reporter delivers the compulsory energy performance certificate for new construction. This certificate exists only for buildings for which an E-level requirement applies (i.e. for new builds, not for building conversions). The declarant may incur an administrative penalty if the so-called “start statement” is not submitted in time; if the EPB declaration is not submitted or not submitted in time (after formal notice), or if one or more of the EPB requirements are not satisfied. The larger the violation, the higher the penalty. The reporter can be fined if it appears that the EPB declaration does not correspond to the materials and the techniques effectively used. Administrative fines for non-compliance with the procedure are as follows, 1) no or late submission of the start statement: 250 euro effectively imposed on the notifiable; and 2) no or late submission of the EPB declaration: 1,000 euro plus 1 euro per cubic meter new building volume, effectively imposed on the notifiable. The declaration must always be submitted, even if a fine has already been</p>

	<p>paid. This is enforced by an amount of 10 euros for each day that the declaration has not been submitted. Fines for non-compliance with the EPB requirements are as follows. The fine depends on the severity of the offense. The penalty is 60 euro per deviation of 1 W/K on the level of the thermal insulation of the construction elements and the K-level; 24 eurocent per deviation of 1 MJ/year in terms of the overall energy performance; 48 eurocent per 1000 Kh and per m³ deviation in terms of the risk of overheating; and 4 euros per deviation of 1 m³/h in the area of the ventilation system. The fine is effectively imposed on the notifiable if the fine is 250 euro or more, which is generally the case. Fines under 250 euros are not collected, but are mentioned on the EPB certificate. The Flemish Energy Agency organizes a hearing where the notifiable has the opportunity to present either in writing or orally his arguments. The Flemish Energy Agency has no appreciation authority on whether or not to implement the fines. If the EPB requirements were not met, the agency is obliged to collect the administrative fine. In 2006, the number of EPB fines (from 250 euro or higher) equalled 10% of the number of submitted EPB declarations. Since 2009, this number still hovers around 4%. Some 84% of all fines are related to ventilation offences. The average fine is 800 euro. In a dwelling where a ventilation system is completely absent the fine can amount to up to 3000 euro. The proceeds of the administrative fines go to the Energy Fund. This fund is used to finance extra initiatives to reduce energy consumption in buildings.</p>
Implementation network	<p>The Flemish Energy Agency (VEA) and the Ministry of Environment, Nature and Energy (LNE) are responsible for the implementation of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD). The agency (VEA) collects the EPB penalties in case of violation. The reporter is the designer or architect of the building, but may also be an external architect or building engineer.</p>
Outcome	<p>No evaluation available</p>

Legal references <http://www.energiesparen.be/epb/besluiten>

1.1.1.3 Energy performance of buildings (PEB) – Walloon Region

	<p>Walloon Region.</p>
General information	<p>In the Walloon Region, the regulation to promote the Energy Performance of Buildings (PEB or “Performance Energétique des Bâtiments”) came into force on 1 September 2008. The principle is to calculate the energy consumption for heating, hot water, auxiliary equipment and optional cooling while assuming a standardized usage of the building. The calculation is made based on the technical characteristics of the building and its equipment, using PEB software available free of charge to the authors of the building project. The calculation results are expressed by two indicators: the Ew level and the specific consumption Es. Ew stands for the primary energy consumption of the building. Es stands for the specific energy consumption of the building. Other indicators to assess the energy characteristics of the building are the K-level and the U values which are a function of the degree of insulation; as well as the risk of overheating S. The regulation</p>

	imposes a maximum value for each of these indicators. In addition, it sets ventilation requirements (V) for different spaces. The PEB requirements vary depending on the type of work and the purpose of the building. The procedure depends on whether the license application relates to a new building, a major renovation or a simple renovation.
Type of policy instruments	Regulatory.
Objectives	The goal is to consume less primary energy to ensure the indoor comfort of buildings.
Target groups	The regulation applies to all buildings (with the exception of exemptions explicitly specified by the regulation) for all construction, reconstruction and transformation works for which obtaining a planning permission is required. Examples of exemptions are buildings with a useful floor area of less than 50 m ² , unless they are intended for housing; a provisional construction which will last a maximum of 2 years; a place of worship; an industrial site, workshop or non-residential agricultural building which is unheated and/or has no air-conditioning or with a low energy demand. In the latter case, only the heat emitters for the comfort of the occupants have to be considered.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	<p>The PEB registrant (“déclarant PEB”) is the person or entity required to comply with the PEB requirements. This is either the client or the purchaser of a building sold on plan or under construction. For new buildings and major renovations, a PEB manager (“responsable PEB”) must be appointed to ensure that the project meets the energy requirements. The PEB manager oversees the compliance requirements. He records, using the PEB software, all data characterizing the energy performance of the building. He prepares various PEB documents which have to be submitted to the Walloon administration (DGO4), namely the original report and the final declaration. The EPB certificate indicates the degree of energy performance of a building. The certificate is drawn up by the PEB manager based on the PEB final declaration. In the case of a simple renovation and/or a change of function, a simplified PEB declaration is sufficient to meet the legal requirements, and a PEB manager does not have to be appointed.</p> <p>The following shortcomings are sanctioned with an administrative fine: the failure to designate an author of the feasibility study or a PEB manager when this is required: a fine of 2 euros per m³ of volume built with a minimum of 250 euros and a maximum of 25,000 euros; 2) the failure to respect the procedures: a fine of 2 euros per m³ of volume built with a minimum of 250 euros and a maximum of 25,000 euros; the failure to comply with the PEB requirements: 60 euros per 1W/K gap for U and R values; 60 euros per 1 W/K gap for the K-level; 0.24 euros per 1MJ gap for the energy performance level E_w; 0.85 euros per 1000 k.h.m³ gap for overheating and 4 euros per 1m³/h gap for ventilation.</p>
Implementation network	The development authority is the Operational Directorate General for Spatial Planning, Housing, Heritage and Energy of the Walloon Public Service. The implementation authority is Department for Energy and Sustainable Building. All documents relating to PEB procedures and requirements have to be addressed to the Department for Energy and

	Sustainable building.
Outcome	No evaluation available.

Legal references: energie.wallonie.be/fr/textes-reglementaires

Link to PEB Wallonia energie.wallonie.be/fr/appliquer-la-reglementation-wallonne-peb.

Ew: Niveau de performance énergétique globale du bâtiment comparé à un bâtiment de référence

Es : Consommation théorique annuelle d'énergie primaire pour le bâtiment en [kWh/m²an]

1.1.1.4 Energy performance of building (PEB) – Brussels-Capital Region

	Brussels-Capital Region.
General information	<p>Since July 2nd, 2008, the PEB regulation (with certain exceptions) affects all construction or renovation works for which an application for a planning permission is required. The PEB requirements are related to the design, the thermal insulation, the technical characteristics of the installations, the energy production, ventilation, etc. The EPB requirements depend on the nature of the work and the function of the building. A PEB unit is a set of adjacent premises located in the same building, which could be sold or leased separately. The regulation applies to 1) new units, i.e. newly built or rebuilt units; 2) units equated to new units, i.e. when construction work exceeds 75% of the building envelope and all technical facilities are replaced; 3) deeply renovated units, i.e. the construction work exceeds 50% of the building envelope and work is carried out on the technical installations; and 4) simply renovated units. The filing date of the planning permission also influences the PEB requirements of the project. On 01.01.2015 the Brussels code on air, climate and energy management or CoBrACE (“Code bruxellois de l'air, du climat et de la maîtrise de l'énergie”) came into force, which replaces the existing PEB regulation. For buildings whose application for a planning permit dates from 1.1.2015 and whose designated function is individual dwellings, offices and services or schools, new EPB requirements were introduced which are added to the requirements in existence prior to 2015, with the exception of requirements concerning the E-level and K-level, which are discontinued since 2015.</p>
Type of policy instruments	Regulatory.
Objectives	The requirements envisage a high energy efficiency and a healthy indoor climate. No quantitative objectives
Target groups	All construction or renovation works of buildings for which an application for a planning permission is required. From 1.1.2015, there is a possibility to request an exception for a new unit when the total or partial compliance requirements are technically, functionally or economically unfeasible. Before 1.1.2015, only renovation projects could possibly benefit from such derogation. Other exemptions include places dedicated to a recognized religious cult and secular morality; places with local industrial or artisanal activities; workshops; agricultural premises; funeral centres, standalone buildings with an area less than 50 m ² unless they contain a dwelling; temporary buildings with a permitted lifetime of two years or less; and residential buildings used or intended to be used less than four months a year and outside the winter season.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	For new projects (or major renovations or works equated with new construction works) a PEB adviser (“conseiller PEB”) must be appointed

	<p>by the project owner to monitor the PEB requirements and to follow up the PEB procedures. For simple renovations, the designation of a PEB adviser is optional, and the architect or even the registrant may assume this role. For projects whose planning permission was filed from 01.01.2015, the appointment of the PEB adviser must be made before the filing of the application for planning permission. The PEB adviser has to inform the designer about the requirements that the project will be submitted to as well as on the consequences in terms of energy performance implied by the proposed architectural choices. If the appointment of a PEB adviser is mandatory, he has to write the PEB proposal (“proposition EPB”) which has to be attached to the application for planning permission. He notifies the start of work to the authorizing authority or to Brussels Environment. The PEB adviser takes note of and evaluates the measures taken to comply with the EPB requirements mentioned in the proposal; he simulates the energy performance and (thermal) comfort of the building and determines if the results meet the required levels; he informs the project owner and architect if it turns out during construction that the project deviates from the required levels; and he calculates the final PEB requirements, that is those of the building as constructed or renovated. He establishes the PEB statement (“déclaration PEB”) at the end of the project. The PEB statement determines whether the PEB requirements are met, or in the case of a renovation without an architect, describes the steps taken to meet the requirements. In the case of a new unit for housing, education or office, an EPB certificate is issued by Brussels Environment. The non-compliance with the EPB procedure is punishable by criminal penalties (with imprisonment from eight days to two years and a fine of 50 to 100,000 euro, or only one of these penalties). The non-compliance of the EPB requirements is punishable by administrative fines. The administrative fines are imposed by Brussels Environment. Brussels Environment can impose on the registrant up to five years after submitting the PEB statement, an administrative fine amounting to 60 euro per 1 W/K difference in the field of thermal insulation of the building elements and the K-level; 0.24 euro per 1 MJ/year deviation in the area of the overall energy performance; 4 euro per 1 m³/h difference in the area of ventilation equipment; and 0.48 euro per 1,000 Kh per m³ difference in the area of overheating.</p>
Implementation network	Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM).
Outcome	No evaluation available

Legal references www.environnement.brussels/thematiques/batiment/la-peb/construction-et-renovation/legislation

Link to PEB Brussels <http://www.environnement.brussels/thematiques/batiment/la-peb>

The decree on the energy certification of buildings (rules and rating method) was issued by the Belgian government in April 2008. Different certification procedures are defined depending on the following parameters: new or existing building; residential, non-residential or public building. The (practical) implementation is the responsibility of the three regions. The certification procedures and the status of the legislation also vary from one region to another.

1.1.1.5 Energy Performance Certificates (EPC) - Flemish Region

	Flemish Region.
General information	<p>An Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) is mandatory for all dwellings that are for sale from November 1, 2008; and for all dwellings that are leased from January 1, 2009. For new buildings, the EP-certificate is based on the EPB-declaration and is established at the same time as the EPB-declaration.</p> <p>An energy performance certificate (EPC) shows how energy efficient a building is. It is mandatory for sale or lease of dwellings and for certain public buildings. An EPC is required per dwelling unit (apartment, studio, house, accommodation, etc.) when selling the unit in full ownership; or when leasing the unit. It is also required when leasing real estate.</p> <p>An energy performance certificate (EPC) is mandatory for (public) buildings housing public organizations who provide services to a large number of persons and are often visited by the public.</p> <p>The energy performance certificate is valid for 10 years.</p>
Type of policy instruments	Regulatory. Information and Education
Objectives	No quantitative objectives
Target groups	<p>Dwellings and certain public buildings. An EPC is not mandatory for dwellings without heating, houseboats, or a house used exclusively as an office, shop, or other non-residential function.</p> <p>Public buildings include buildings of the federal, regional (Flemish), provincial and municipal authorities; public enterprises, educational institutions, welfare and health facilities. Initially, the EPC was only mandatory for large public buildings with a useful floor area of 1,000 m² or more. Since January 1, 2013 the requirement applies to buildings with a useful floor area above 500 m². As of January 1, 2015 the EPC is also mandatory for buildings with a useful floor area above 250 m². Some public buildings do not require an EPC: premises of youth associations; religious buildings such as churches, buildings which are not frequently visited by the public, for example, a building used exclusively for sorting mail or storage of goods; hotels; private offices and banks; buildings or parts of buildings which do not consume energy for the benefit of people, such as warehouses, hangars; fire stations; or service flats.</p>
Rules and influencing mechanisms	<p>An EPC must be present from the moment a housing unit is offered for sale or for lease. When selling or leasing a dwelling an EPC is drawn up by a recognized energy expert type A.</p> <p>The owner can hand over certain documents (e.g. valid invoices of work on the property) to the expert at the latest during the latter's visit on site. Without such pieces of evidence, the expert uses default values based on the year of construction of the building. The energy expert type A inspects the property (roof, walls, floor, windows, doors, insulation materials, heating system, etc.) following a certain inspection protocol. The expert has to use the certification software made available by the Flemish Energy Agency (VEA). The use of a specific fixed inspection method and software increases the reproducibility of the result.</p> <p>The EPC has to be transferred to the new owner or has to be added to the lease. The owner who wants to sell or lease his property remains</p>

	<p>responsible at all times.</p> <p>Anyone who sells or leases a dwelling must mention certain elements of the EPC in advertisements and publications in which the dwelling is offered for sale or for lease., namely the specific energy consumption (kWh/m²), the full address of the dwelling; and the unique code of the EPC. This is not required for small “for sale/for rent” window posters or small panels attached to the house that refer to the real estate office.</p> <p>The Flemish Energy Agency (VEA) does random checks to verify that dwellings for sale or for rent have a valid EPC. Notaries have a reporting obligation in the absence of an EPC. This is done through the e-notary (electronic notary). Anyone can report the lack of an EPC to the VEA (but anonymous or incomplete messages are not accepted).</p> <p>An owner who does not have a valid EPC (in time) is invited by the VEA to submit his written arguments. The lack of an EPC does not mean that the property can not be sold or leased. The owner risks a fine of 500 euro to 5000 euro.</p> <p>The VEA also carries out spot checks on the performance, qualifications and the additional requirements of the recognized energy expert; as well as on the accuracy of the EPC. In case of abuse or manifest incompetence, the VEA may withdraw the recognition of the energy expert. If an EPC is of insufficient quality, the VEA may revoke the energy performance certificate in question. The VEA can impose a fine on the expert of 500 to 5,000 euro if the EPC does not match reality.</p> <p>For failure to comply with the ad obligation the VEA can impose a fine of 500 to 5,000 euro on the owner, the real estate agent or the notary who put up the property for sale or rent.</p> <p>An EPC for public buildings is drawn up by a recognized energy expert type C or an internal energy expert and is based on the measured (actual) annual consumption of the public building. A recognized energy expert type C has completed an approved training after passing a national examination. An internal energy expert is an employee of the public body who has at least two years experience within the organization in the field of energy management. The EPC has to be on public display. The VEA carries out spot checks on the presence and accuracy of the EPC for public buildings. If the public organization (i.e. the user of the building) does not have a valid EPC, the VEA can impose an administrative fine of minimum 500 euros and maximum 5,000 euros on the public organisation. If the inspection reveals that the EPC does not correspond to reality, VEA can impose a fine of between 500 and 5,000 euros on the. In case of abuse of manifest incompetence the VEA may withdraw the recognition of the expert and / or revoke the EPCs in question. The user of the public building and the energy expert has to provide the VEA with all the necessary information.</p>
Implementation network	<p>The Flemish Energy Agency (VEA). VEA makes available the certification software. VEA carries out random spot checks on the presence and accuracy of the EPC and the ad obligation. The VEA is always available to answer questions, comments and complaints made by citizens or professionals.</p>

Outcome	No evaluation available.
Legal references www.energiesparen.be/epcparticulier/documenten Link to VEA EPC www.energiesparen.be/energieprestatiecertificaten	

1.1.1.6 Energy Performance Certificates (EPC) - Walloon Region

	Walloon Region.
General information	<p>In Wallonia, the energy performance certificate (EPC) is mandatory for all single-family home sales since 1 January 2011 and compulsory for sales and rentals of any house and apartment from 1 June 2011.</p> <p>The PEB (“Performance Énergétique des Bâtiments”) certificate assesses the energy performance of buildings, under standardized conditions of use and outdoor climate. The calculation method evaluates the performance of the building envelope (insulation) and systems (heating, domestic hot water and ventilation). The PEB certificate also contains recommendations for improvement. The PEB certificate is required only in case of sale and lease. There is one exception: when the building is acquired by the buyer to be demolished. In that case, the acknowledgment of receipt of the request for a demolition permit must be attached to the sale agreement. The PEB certificate must be issued before the sale or lease; and must be handed over to the buyer (original certificate) or tenant (copy of certificate) <i>before</i> signing the sale or lease agreement.</p> <p>Since 1 January 2015, the PEB indicators have to be mentioned in the sales and rental advertisements. Those indicators include the unique code of the PEB certificate; the total primary energy consumption in kWh per year; the specific primary energy consumption in kWh/m² per year; and the energy class (or “label”).</p> <p>The energy performance certificate is valid for 10 years.</p>
Type of policy instruments	Regulatory. Information and Education.
Objectives	No quantitative objectives.
Target groups	Only new or existing <i>residential</i> buildings (single-family houses, apartments & other dwelling units) have to be certified. The Walloon Region is currently developing the tools required for certification of other new or existing buildings (offices, services, shops, etc.).
Rules and influencing mechanisms	<p>The PEB certificate is drawn up according to different methods and by different actors for different types of buildings (and also depending on the date of the application for a planning permission).</p> <p>The PEB certificate is issued by an approved PEB certifier (“certificateur PEB agréé”) designated by the owner. The PEB certifier collects, as part of a tour of the building, the necessary data (insulation of the building envelope; efficiency of the heating, domestic hot water and ventilation systems). The PEB certifier has to use the software and the data collection protocol made available by the Walloon administration (DGO4). The owner may provide acceptable evidence (documents) relating to the energy performance of the building which otherwise cannot be obtained without special procedures (e.g. destructive tests to check the thermal insulation of a wall). Otherwise, the PEB certifier has to apply default values</p>

	The penalties are 1) for the absence of a PEB certificate valid at the time of the sale or lease a fixed administrative fine to the amount of 1,000 euro; 2) for non-compliance with the advertisement obligation a fixed administrative fine of 500 euro; and 3) for failure to observe the requirement relating to handing over the PEB certificate a fixed administrative fine of 500 euro.
Implementation network	The Department for Energy and Sustainable Building of DGO4 is responsible for the development and implementation. In the case of the construction of a new building, the EPB certificate is issued by the Regional authorities. In other cases, it is issued by an EPB certifying officer.
Outcome	No evaluation available.

Legal references: energie.wallonie.be/fr/textes-reglementaires

Link to EPC Wallonia energie.wallonie.be/fr/acheter-vendre-louer-le-certificat-peb

1.1.1.7 Energy Performance Certificates (EPC) – Brussels-Capital Region

	Brussels-Capital Region.
General information	<p>Regulation in force on 1 May, 2011 for sale of an individual dwelling or of “offices and services buildings” with a surface area of more than 500 m²; and on 1 November 2011 for leasing an individual dwelling or “offices and services buildings” with a surface area of more than 500 m².</p> <p>As part of a real estate transaction (sale or lease, leasing of real estate) of a property situated in the Brussels-Capital Region, the owner or the intermediary appointed by the owner (real estate agency, notary) must have a PEB certificate from the moment he places the property on the market. Depending on the assignment of the property, there are PEB certificates for individual dwellings; and for tertiary units (currently only for offices with a surface area of more than 500 m²).</p> <p>The PEB certificate presents the energy performance of the property on a scale from A (very efficient) to G (energy-intensive). The energy performance is established based on the energy characteristics of the property (heat loss surface, insulation, type of boiler, ventilation, etc.), collected on site and encoded in software by the EPB certifier; taking into account several calculation assumptions such as a standard behaviour of the occupants and average outdoor climate. The EPB certificate also includes a series of recommendations for energy savings by implementing energy efficiency improvement works. The person who puts the property for sale or lease must include in all publicity (internet, classifieds, public display ...) the energy class and the level of CO₂ emission indicated on the PEB certificate. The PEB certificate is valid for 10 years provided that it has not been revoked by Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM), and provided that there are no changes to the building such that the PEB certificate no longer reflects the energy characteristics as identified by the PEB certifier when visiting the property. For all newly constructed buildings (dwellings, offices or educational buildings) with a planning permit from July 2, 2008, a PEB certificate "new building" is issued by Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM) on the basis of the PEB statement introduced by the PEB consultant. This PEB certificate is very</p>

	similar to the one established by a PEB certifier. It has the same validity period and can also be used as part of a real estate transaction.
Type of policy instruments	Regulatory. Information and Education.
Objectives	The PEB certificate informs the potential buyer or tenant of the energy quality of the property, and allows him to compare the different properties he visits in terms of their theoretical energy consumption (in kWh/m ² per year) and their annual CO ₂ emissions.
Target groups	Existing Individual dwellings. Offices with a surface area of more than 500 m ² . For new dwellings, offices and educational buildings we refer to the EPB regulation in the Brussels-Capital Region. Under certain conditions, A PEB certificate is not required on the sale date for residential property in poor condition, of which the technical facilities are lacking or incomplete, or the construction or renovation is unfinished.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	The PEB certifier ("PEB certificateur") issues the PEB certificate using the software and applying the protocol made available by Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM). The rules for the approval and recognition of training are listed in the decree of the Government of the Brussels-Capital Region of 17 February 2011. The list of certifiers is published on the website of Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM). Homeowners who do not respect the obligation to produce a PEB certificate are punishable by criminal penalties, which can be converted into administrative fines levied by Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM).
Implementation network	The Government of the Brussels-Capital Region is responsible for the development. Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM) is responsible for the implementation. When a new building is constructed, the EPB certificate is issued by Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM), in other cases by the EPB certifying officer.
Outcome	No evaluation available.

Legal reference: 19 June 2008 - [Order of the Brussels-Capital Government concerning the energy performance certificate for new buildings that are dedicated to housing, offices and services, and education](#) Moniteur belge/Belgisch Staatsblad, 4th of July 2008
Link to PEB Bruxelles <http://www.pebruxelles.com>

The implementation of the mandatory energy audit requirements of art. 8 of Directive 2012/27/EC on Energy Efficiency (the Energy Efficiency Directive or EED) is regulated in Belgium by the three regions. The Flemish and Walloon regions have not yet (fully) implemented these requirements.

1.1.1.8 Mandatory energy audit requirement in the Flemish Region

	Flemish Region
General information	The Energy Act states that the Flemish Government shall impose mandatory energy audits on companies, public entities and non-profit organisations. To date, no executing decree has been adopted by the Flemish Government.
Type of policy instruments	Regulatory. Auditing.
Objectives	As audits are not currently mandatory, there are no objectives.
Target groups	Non-residential buildings, in particular companies, public entities and non-profit organisations.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	As audits are not currently mandatory, there are no sanctions
Implementation network	As audits are not currently mandatory, there is no implementation

	network.
Outcome	As audits are not currently mandatory, there is no outcome.

Legal reference [08-05-2009 Decree concerning general provisions relating to energy policy \[quote inscription: "the Energy Act"\]](#).

1.1.1.9 Mandatory energy audit requirement in the Walloon Region

	Walloon Region
General information	The Decree AMURE provides that private entities can benefit from public subsidies in order to conduct energy audits. This Decree does not impose mandatory energy audits, but only provides for incentives in order for companies to carry out an audit. The Decree UREBA applies to public entities and non-profit organisations.
Type of policy instruments	Regulatory. Auditing
Objectives	As audits are not currently mandatory, there are no objectives.
Target groups	Non-residential buildings, in particular companies (legal persons from the private sector), public entities (municipality, public social action centre, province, intermunicipal local police zone) and non-profit organisations (schools, hospitals, swimming pools, other services to the community, NGOs and unincorporated associations with philanthropic, scientific, technical or teaching purposes, in the fields of energy, environmental protection or fight against social exclusion).
Rules and influencing mechanisms	As audits are not currently mandatory, there are no sanctions.
Implementation network	As audits are not currently mandatory, there is no implementation network.
Outcome	As audits are not currently mandatory, there is no outcome.

Legal reference: The Ministerial Decree of the Walloon Government of 27/02/2014 "on the granting of subsidies to companies and organizations representative of enterprises to improve energy efficiency and promote a more rational use of energy in the private sector" (AMURE). <https://wallex.wallonie.be/index.php?doc=27662&rev=29039-19348>

Legal reference: The Decree of the Walloon Government of 28/03/2013 "on the granting of subsidies to public entities and non-commercial organizations for studies and work to improve the energy efficiency and the rational use of energy in buildings" (UREBA)

1.1.1.10 Mandatory energy audit requirement in the Brussels-Capital Region

	Brussels-Capital Region.
General information	First qualification date 30/07/2012. Energy audits must be carried out by operators applying for environmental permits
Type of policy instruments	Regulatory.
Objectives	
Target groups	Operators applying for environmental permits
Rules and influencing mechanisms	If an operator does not comply with the obligation to conduct an energy audit, the environmental permit, or its renewal, will be refused. The audit must be carried out by an approved auditor at the request of the applicant and under the applicant's responsibility, within the 12 months before the deposit of the application for the environmental permit. The energy audit is part of the environmental permit application, extension or renewal file. The permit applicant shall countersign the energy audit and accept the measures and action plan. All measures arising from the energy audit which have a return time of less than five years must be implemented by the establishment within four years following the issuance of the environmental permit. An energy audit

	<p>must be carried out for environmental permit applications of class 1A or 1B and environmental permit applications of class 2 by public companies or concerning acts and public works, as well as for permit applications for the renewal or the extension of establishments with one or more buildings with a non-domestic floor area of more than 3,500 m².</p> <p>The Decree allows certain exemptions for the application of environmental permits when: 1) it is subjected to a EPB (energy performance of buildings) proposal for new buildings or major renovations according to the Decree of 07/05/2007 on the energy performance and indoor climate of buildings; 2) it concerns an undertaking within the exchange gas emission allowance trading scheme for greenhouse gas as defined in the order of 31/01/2008 establishing a system for the exchange of gas emission quotas for greenhouses and on the Kyoto Protocol's flexible mechanisms; 3) it concerns a building whose energy consumption per m² of surface area of the protected volume is below the limits specified in the annex of standard climate and of normal occupation.</p>
Implementation network	Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM)
Outcome	No evaluation available.

Legal reference [The Decree of the Government of Brussels-Capital Region of 15 December 2011 "relating to energy audits for large consumers of energy facilities"](#).

Legal reference The Decree of Brussels-Capital Region of 02/05/2013 concerning the Brussels Code of Air, Climate and Energy Management provides that the Regional Government can take measures to impose energy audits on owners of certain buildings according to their size and their purposes. However, to date, no executing decree has been adopted by the Government. The Brussels Code of Air, Climate and Energy Management can be downloaded [here](#).

1.1.1.11 Inspection, maintenance and heating audit of heating equipment

	Flemish Region.
General information	<p>Date effective 1 June 2007. Recent update 3 May 2013. It is obligatory to have heating systems regularly serviced to guarantee the safety of the system and to promote energy efficiency. Maintenance must be carried out once a year for liquid fuel systems and every two years for gas fuel systems. It is also obligatory to carry out a heating audit for heating appliances with an output of 20 to 100 kW. This audit must be carried out on its first maintenance after the appliance is five years old, and every five years thereafter, either by a liquid fuel or a gaseous fuel engineer. The heating audit for heating appliances with an output of more than 100 kW must be carried out every two years (liquid fuels) or every four years (gaseous fuels) by a heating audit engineer. These three types of engineer are accredited for a period of five years, after which they must undergo further training to renew the accreditation.</p>
Type of policy instruments	Regulatory. Auditing.
Objectives	The objectives are to save energy (and energy costs); to reduce emissions of pollutants including greenhouse gases; to guarantee a safe heating of the building; and to avoid high repair costs as a regularly maintained heating systems last longer.
Target groups	The provisions of the Decree concerning the maintenance and inspection of heating appliances apply to <i>central</i> heating devices that are used primarily for heating buildings and optional for the production of

	domestic hot water.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Failure to meet the obligations under Article 8 (operation and maintenance of a central heating unit) and Article 10 (removal of defects) is regarded as an environmental offense. The prosecutor must decide within 180 days whether there will be criminal prosecution (criminal fine or imprisonment) or not. In the latter case an alternative administrative fine may be imposed (capped at 250,000 EUR).
Implementation network	Ministry of Environment, Nature and Energy (LNE).
Outcome	No evaluation available.

Legal reference [Decision of the Flemish Government of 8 December 2006 concerning the maintenance and inspection of heating appliances for heating of buildings or for the production of hot water consumption.](#)

Legal reference [Decision of the Flemish Government amending the VLAREL and amending various other decisions regarding recognitions relating to the environment \(BS23 / 04/2013\)](#)

1.1.2 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS / INFORMATIVE POLICY INSTRUMENTS

1.1.2.1 Energy labelling

	Federal.
General information	Date effective 2004. Amended in 2010, 2011, 2012, 2013, 2014. The developments are in synergy with Framework Directive 2009/125/EC on "Ecodesign" and with its related implementation measures (regulations and voluntary agreements). Belgium is one of the few Member States that have adopted a market surveillance under the new regulations and delegated regulations from 2009. The labels must convey the specific models established for each group of appliances. Typical for Belgium is that the contents of the label must be at least in the official language of the region where the product is commercialised, i.e. French for the Walloon region, Dutch for the Flemish region, French and Dutch for the Brussels region and German for the Eupen-Malmedy area.
Type of policy instruments	Information and Education. Performance Label
Objectives	Energy labelling gives potential buyers the opportunity to avoid the most energy-consuming appliances, by informing and sensitizing them.
Target groups	Twelve (12) implementing measures of Directive 2010/30/EU are already published, namely on refrigerators, dishwashers, washing machines, air-conditioning, tumble dryers, lamps, luminaires & lightbulbs (2012), televisions, vacuum cleaners, space and water heaters, ovens, range hoods and residential ventilation. The replacement of the last directive on washers/dryers by a delegated regulation is under evaluation. Additional delegated regulations are expected in 2015 and 2016.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Suppliers putting devices on the market that are subject to the energy labelling scheme have to provide the labels and records and compile the technical documentation. Manufacturers, importers, distributors and retailers are obliged to put the correct labels on the devices. At the federal level, the Directorate-General (DG) Energy writes the legal texts and verifies the compliance of the information given on the labels and markers with the technical files and the measures implemented on the

	<p>devices. The federal Regulation and Control Policy Division regularly organizes campaigns to verify the presence, the formal compliance and the correct display of the labels at the distributors and retailers.</p> <p>The DG Energy that has to test whether the mandatory energy label of a device corresponds to the actual power consumption does not have enough staff and money. Because of this, the number of tests is limited, and some types of devices are rarely tested or not tested at all. Between 2009 and 2014 only a few hundred devices (refrigerators, dishwashers, dryers, televisions, energy-saving lamps and microwave ovens (**)) were tested. On several occasions, the labels did not appear to be very reliable. Washing machines, air-conditioners, motors and transformers were rarely tested during that period (*). Two particular problems were reported in the implementation of the market surveillance. Firstly, for various categories of devices the Belgian laboratories do not have the necessary equipment to perform the tests and without the certainty that a minimum number of tests will be carried out, they are not always willing to invest in the purchase of that equipment. Secondly, producers often use the provided tolerances to improve the energy class of their appliances. In addition, there were the high cost of inspections by foreign laboratories equipped for the types of devices that cannot be tested by Belgian laboratories. Because of the budgetary and personnel constraints for market surveillance, it was necessary to limit the number of tests, as a result of which some categories of devices were rarely tested or not tested at all. Regarding the monitoring of the presence of the labels and their visual conformity, the FPS Economy regularly undertakes campaigns. In 2010, more than 200 stores were checked for a total of more than 9,000 "large electrical household appliances" (refrigerators, washing machines, dishwashers, dryers and washer dryers). More than 30% were not compliant (especially the ovens). During the campaign of 2013, the checks were limited to "major electrical household appliances" and television sets (more than 15,000). 20% of the devices were not compliant.</p>
Implementation network	The Federal Public Service (FPS) Economy, S.M.E.s, Self-employed and Energy - Directorate General for Quality and Safety - Regulation and Control Policy Division. The Federal Public Service for the Economy, SME, Middle Class and Energy - Directorate-General for Energy.
Outcome	

Legal reference 1 JULY 2004. - [Ministerial Decree amending the Ministerial Decree of November 20th 1996 on the application of the Royal Decree of November 10, 1996 on the indication of energy consumption and consumption of other resources by labelling and standard product information for household appliances](#) .

Link to FPS economie.fgov.be/nl/consument/Energie/Duurzame_ontwikkeling/Energie-efficiëntie/Labelling

(*) Article in Knack 17 July 2015. www.knack.be/nieuws/belgie/energielabels-op-huishoudtoestellen-worden-nauwelijks-gecontroleerd

Article Federation of Electricity and Electronics FEE 29 July 2015 www.feebel.be/nl/energielabels

Source: second federal environmental report Part 2 Other aspects of the federal environmental policy. This report can be downloaded [here](#) from the FEE website.

(**) The FPS mentions microwave oven, although there are no energy labels for microwave ovens, only for other types of ovens.

[VITO & ECONOTEC \(2015\)](#)

1.1.2.2 The “energy guzzlers” website

	Federal.
General information	A website called “energy guzzlers” to evaluate the energy performance of

	household appliances (washers, dryers, dishwashers, refrigerators, freezers, TVs, lighting, windows, roof insulation, wall insulation and cars). An internet-based CO ₂ calculator allows: 1) to evaluate the energy performance of existing appliances/products at home, giving personalized advice on replacement or better use; 2) to make a “wise” personal selection of new appliances/products amongst all products available on the Belgian market. For new appliances/products, the calculator calculates the CO ₂ emissions and financial cost, as well as the yearly savings and the payback time. It even allows accounting for personal selection criteria, personal behaviour, specific parameters (energy price, mean outside temperature of the region...) and existing fiscal incentives and subsidies. The website has been promoted by a campaign with strong, humoristic images and has won many national and international awards (3 golden Belgian awards, the "Bronze World Medal" + "UNDPI-Gold" at the New York Advertising Festival (2007) and was shortlisted at the international Publicity Festival in Cannes 2008).
Type of policy instruments	Information and Education
Objectives	No quantitative objectives
Target groups	Washers, dryers, dishwashers, refrigerators, freezers, TVs, lighting, windows, roof insulation, wall insulation and cars.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Awareness raising
Implementation network	The Federal Public Service Health, Food chain Safety and Environment; Directorate-general for Environment (DG5) - Climate Change Section, department of Product Management and Chemicals and the thematic service “climate change” developed the website and maintain it.
Outcome	The official “evaluation” only refers to the “awards” the site has won or for which it has been nominated. No quantitative evaluation of results.

Link to the website www.energievreters.be (Dutch) or www.energivores.be (French)

More information [here](#).

1.1.2.3 The “energy savings” website

	Flemish Region
General information	The “energy savings” website of the Flemish Energy Agency (VEA) purports to be the reference website on energy efficiency for Flanders. The so-called ‘energy profit calculators’ provide customised advice on a number of energy saving investments, such as roof insulation, wall insulation, replacement of single glazing, replacement of old central heating boilers, installation of a solar boiler or photovoltaic solar panels. The “subsidy search module” includes all the subsidies at the federal, Flemish, provincial as well as municipal level. The 'test your EPC' tool allows comparing the EPC of a particular house (terraced, semi-detached or detached) or apartment with the average EPC reference value in a certain municipality, province or Flanders as a whole. Information is provided through a range of brochures about energy efficiency (e.g. EPB, EPC, subsidies, ...) which are available at the website. All information campaigns (e.g. “New energy grants 2014 – Make your nest 100% warm” are mentioned at the website. Energy saving tips can be found at the website.
Type of policy instruments	Information and Education

Objectives	No quantitative objectives
Target groups	General public. Information for all citizens of Flanders on all types of buildings, heating systems, solar boilers for domestic hot water and photovoltaics (PV).
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Awareness raising.
Implementation network	The Flemish Energy Agency (VEA).
Outcome	The site welcomes some 1.2 million visitors per year.

Link to the website www.energiesparen.be;

Link to the energy profit calculators www.energiesparen.be/energiewinst

1.1.2.4 Energy consultants

	Flemish Region.
General information	Date effective 2011. The Flemish support programme for energy consultants was launched end of 2010, for a three year period 2011-2013. The aim is to raise awareness about the rational use of energy (RUE) and environment-friendly energy production via information campaigns and consultancy. Energy consultants receiving government support are assigned to a range of target groups: households, owners of heritage buildings, operators of tourism businesses and accommodations, SMEs, building sector professionals, and farmers. As announced on 2 October 2013, the programme will enter into a second project phase from 2014 until 2016. In total 1.2 million EUR are foreseen for project phase 2 (2014-2016) with a maximum of 175,000 EUR per project. The programme is directed towards households with special attention to low-income households; construction companies and agricultural companies.
Type of policy instruments	Information and Education – Advice / Aid in Implementation. Economic – Subsidies
Objectives	No quantitative objectives
Target groups	Households (with special attention to low income households); owners of heritage buildings; operators of tourism businesses and accommodations; SMEs; building sector professionals; and farmers.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Each energy consultancy project is monitored by a supervisory committee established by the Flemish Energy Agency (VEA). The monitoring and reporting agreements included in the subsidy agreements allow regular and adequately detailed monitoring of the achievement of the targets.
Implementation network	The Flemish Energy Agency (VEA) is responsible for issuing the subsidies (to the projects). VEA also establishes the committee that supervises and monitors the projects. Other actors include for the target group households “ Samenlevingsopbouw ” (underprivileged people); “ Gezinsbond ” (households) and “ Komosie ” (thrift stores); for the target group building professionals “ NAV ” (architects). “ Bouwunie ” (contractors) and “ Vlaamse Confederatie Bouw ” (contractors); and for the target group farmers “ Boerenbond Consult ”.
Outcome	No evaluation available

Legal reference: [Decision of the Flemish Government laying down general provisions on energy policy \(cited as the Energy Act\)](#)

Link to the website energiesparen.be/energieconsulenten

Link to the website

There are various measures in Wallonia providing information, such as an energy portal website (“Site portail de l’énergie”); the green phone of Wallonia (“Téléphone vert de la Wallonie”); energy information desks (“Guichets Énergie Wallonie”); energy facilitators (“Facilitateurs énergie”); energy advisers in the municipalities (“Conseillers énergie dans les communes”); ‘energy ferryman’ (“Écopasseurs”); and Energie+.

1.1.2.5 Energy information desks (“guichets énergie”)

	Walloon region
General information	The energy information desks (“guichets énergie”) are 16 information desks or “counters” distributed throughout the Walloon region. Forty (40) consultants welcome and guide citizens seeking to save energy through thermal insulation of their dwelling, more efficient heating systems, solar boilers for domestic hot water, lighting, electric appliances, etc. They provide personalized technical advice, free of charge, and they also inform citizens on the regulations in force and the financial and other (government) support available in Wallonia.
Type of policy instruments	Information and Education.
Objectives	No quantitative objectives.
Target groups	General public. Citizens of the Walloon region (either tenant or owner). Households. Residential buildings - dwellings (all energy efficiency related measures such as thermal insulation, heating systems, solar boilers, lighting, appliances, ...).
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Awareness raising.
Implementation network	The Department for Energy and Sustainable Building of DGO4. The consultants are experts in the service of the Walloon Region (i.e. they are ‘civil servants’ of the Department for Energy and Sustainable Building).
Outcome	No evaluation available

Legal reference

Link to the website [guichets-energie-wallonie](http://guichets-energie-wallonie.be)

Link to the energy portal website: energie.wallonie.be

1.1.2.6 The Energy House

	Brussels-Capital Region.
General information	The Energy House offers all citizens of Brussels free of charge coaching (dissemination of information, home visits, assistance in making decisions, realization of small interventions, and assistance in finding the necessary funding) by a team of (energy) experts. The Energy House is an initiative of the Brussels Capital Region. It consists of a coordination structure which is housed at Brussels Environment and local offices that provide the field work and are responsible for direct contact with the households within the region. Brussels Environment coordinates the assignments of the Energy House and is responsible for the framework, the funding (through subsidies) and the overall organization of the local branches. The local branches are themselves independent and separately managed associations. The six existing associations are active in each one of the six geographical areas in which the Brussels-Capital Region is

	divided and cover all 19 municipalities.
Type of policy instruments	Information and Education – Advice / Aid in implementation
Objectives	No quantitative objectives
Target groups	All citizens of Brussels-Capital Region. Households. Residential buildings - dwellings.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	The services offered by the Energy House are available free of charge to all citizens of Brussels who freely decide whether or not to make use of those services.
Implementation network	Brussels Environment. The coordination structure is housed at Brussels Environment. Local independent offices provide the field work. Brussels Environment coordinates the assignments of the Energy House and is responsible for the framework, the funding (through subsidies) and the overall organization of the local branches.
Outcome	Evaluation – please see D1.1 Table 6.

Legal reference. Not relevant.

Link to the website , <http://www.maisonenergiehuis.be>

1.1.2.7 Local Action Plans for Demand-side Management (P.L.A.G.E.)

	Brussels-Capital Region
General information	<p>The first round of Local Action Plans for Energy Management (P.L.A.G.E.) projects was launched in 2006. The P.L.A.G.E. programs are specifically targeted at organisations managing large building stocks in the private and public sector. The underlying premise is that energy performance of certain buildings can be improved by 20-30% even without major investments. The objective are 1) to provide information on energy efficiency; 2) to organize internal management around energy-efficient maintenance of facilities; 3) to identify the potential energy savings and the priority actions, in particular through building audits; 4) to raise awareness amongst occupants of how to behave; 5) to involve energy efficiency in investment choices (new construction, renovation and refurbishment); and 6) to ensure transparency of information through the publication and promotion of a regular summary of results. P.L.A.G.E. funds energy reduction measures and training of building administrators in the passive standard. The Brussels-Capital Region covers 50% to 100% of the expenses incurred for up to 3 years. The phases of a P.L.A.G.E. projects are creating an energy consumption cadastre of the building complex; establishing a concrete action plan for those buildings that are considered top priority; carrying out the action plan; and following up with the regional authorities by reporting on progress in project implementation. In addition, an energy consultants („Responsible Energie“) helps with the project implementation. Brussels Environment has created a P.L.A.G.E. manual for building managers, as well as another one for energy consultants. The success of the scheme has been such that the regional parliament has decided that, from 2015, it will become mandatory for private owners of more than 100 000 m² of building stock and public owners of more than 50 000 m² to adopt a P.L.A.G.E. action plan.</p>
Type of policy instruments	Information and Education – Advice / Aid in Implementation. Voluntary

	Approaches. From 2015 Regulatory (for specific building stocks).
Objectives	No quantitative objectives. It is assumed that the energy performance of certain (large) buildings can be improved by 20-30% even without major investments.
Target groups	Organisations managing large building stocks in the private and public sector. Buildings – residential and non-residential. Private and public buildings. Hospitals, schools, public and social housing communities. For the non-voluntary part: private owners with a building stock of more than 100 000 m ² of building stock and public owners with a building stock of more than 50 000 m ²
Rules and influencing mechanisms	For the non-voluntary part of P.L.A.G.E., the rules of the “Order to the Brussels Code of Air, Climate and Energy Management” apply, namely the penalty provided in Article 31, § 1 of the Code of inspection, prevention, recognition and enforcement of environmental violations and environmental responsibility.
Implementation network	Brussels Environment. Brussels Environment covers 50% to 100% of the expenses incurred for up to 3 years. . Brussels Environment has created a P.L.A.G.E. manual for building managers, as well as another one for energy consultants.
Outcome	P.L.A.G.E. has since its introduction been implemented in 1380 buildings representing 4.5 million m ² , leading to an average 16% cut in heating costs and an annual reduction of 10,000 tonnes of carbon dioxide emissions. Please also see D1.1 Table 6.

Legal reference. [2 May 2013 - Order to the Brussels Code of Air, Climate and Energy Management](#) .

Link to the website themas/energie/bespaar-energie/plage

1.1.2.8 Sustainable building facilitator network

	Brussels-Capital Region.
General information	Since 2008, the Brussels-Capital Region has provided a network of support specialists (“facilitators”). Since 2011, the specialist network service has been centralized under Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM) under a new name: Sustainable Building Facilitator Network (“Facilitateur Bâtiment durable”). Facilitators are energy efficiency experts who provide free-of-charge, independent and impartial advice on rational use of energy (RUE) and renewable energy. The professionals provide guidance and recommendations in all areas related to energy management, renovation, or the construction of passive buildings. The network service is aimed at two main categories: managers of multi-family dwellings and the tertiary sector (office buildings, schools, hospitals, ...). The mandate of the Green Building Facilitator is to promote the green building tools developed by Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM); to provide information on and raise awareness of green buildings; to analyse obstacles to the development of green building; and to suggest solutions.
Type of policy instruments	Information and Education – Advice / Aid in Implementation.
Objectives	No quantitative objectives
Target groups	Professional builder; architect; engineer or engineering firm; building promoter; building manager or managing agent; technical supervisor;

	installer or other professional in the construction industry. Residential and non-residential buildings. Corporate bodies and institutions. Multifamily dwellings and the tertiary sector (including industrial facilities).
Rules and influencing mechanisms	The services offered by the Sustainable building facilitator network are available free of charge to all building professionals of Brussels who freely decide whether or not to make use of those services. Owners or tenants of buildings with fewer than six apartments should make use of the services offered by the Energy House.
Implementation network	Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM).
Outcome	No evaluation available

Legal reference. Not relevant.

Link to the website [themas/energie/energiepremie-en-steun/facilitator-duurzame-gebouwen](https://themas.energie.be/energiepremie-en-steun/facilitator-duurzame-gebouwen)

1.1.3 ECONOMIC POLICY INSTRUMENTS

1.1.3.1 Fund for the Reduction of the Global cost of Energy (FRGE)

In 2006 the Belgian government established the Fund for the Reduction of the Global cost of Energy (FRGE). The fund supported cheap loans for structural energy savings investments, providing assistance to the most disadvantaged (vulnerable) households as defined in the [Royal Decree establishing the statutes of the "Fund for the reduction of overall energy costs of March 9, 2006](#). Those households were supported by entities appointed by the Public Social Welfare Centres in identifying, organizing and implementing appropriate works. A total of 100 million EUR was available for the period 2006-2014. Funds were distributed via 33 local entities covering 333 cities (VITO, 2015). Due to the Sixth State Reform, the FRGE was abolished on 1 January 2015. The FRGE will therefore not be discussed any further. It is only briefly mentioned here because it is still considered a "measure" in the Belgian NEEAP (2014).

1.1.3.2 Tax deduction for investments in roof insulation of dwellings

Since end of 2004 the Federal Government offered tax deductions to all households who improved the energy efficiency of their existing house via investments in for instance roof, wall and floor insulation; condensing boiler, solar boiler; or PV installation. The eligible technologies and the maximum deductible amounts varied from year to year. Moreover, the regional authorities offered subsidies or other financial incentives for the same technologies. From income year (i.e. expenses made in) 2012 (tax year or assessment year 2013), the federal tax incentives for energy savings have been abolished, due to overlap with the regional incentives. There is one exception. The tax deduction for roof insulation was retained for income year (i.e. expenses made in) 2013. As a result of the Sixth State Reform, from 1 January 2015, the regions are responsible for the tax credit, and can decide independently to continue, change or stop this incentive. For income year (i.e. expenses actually paid in) 2014, or tax year 2015, the regions decided to keep the tax credit for roof insulation expenses. Due to the (extremely) complex internal workings of the Belgian federal state, individual or personal income taxes (PIT) are still collected by the Federal Public Service (SPF) Finances, even though the tax credit for roof insulation expenses is set by the regions. We discuss this policy instrument in detail, although it is (still) unclear whether or not the regions will decide to keep it.

	Federal level (tax credit for expenses paid in 2013). Regions (tax credit for expenses paid in 2014). The Federal Public Service Finances remains responsible for collecting the Personal Income Tax (PIT).
General information	The Federal Government still granted a tax deduction for roof insulation

	<p>investment expenditures made in 2013, but the former maximum deductible amount of 40% of the investment expenditures was reduced to 30%; and the deduction could no longer be spread over several years. At the start of the works, the dwelling had to be occupied for at least five years. The roof insulation works had to be carried out by a contractor. In tax year or assessment year 2014 (expenses paid in 2013), the maximum allowed tax deduction was 3,010 EUR. The tax credit could not be granted concurrently with tax credits for expenses for the renovation of low-rent dwelling houses; expenses for burglary protection and fire protection; and expenses for the maintenance and renovation of classified monuments and sites.</p> <p>In tax year 2015 (expenses actually paid in 2014) the regions decided to retain the tax credit and under the same conditions, except that the maximum allowed tax deduction was 3,040 EUR per taxable period and per dwelling.</p>
Type of policy instruments	Economic – tax deduction or tax credit.
Objectives	No quantitative objectives.
Target groups	All residents of Belgium who own their dwelling and have to pay Belgian (individual) income taxes. Residential buildings – own dwellings (in 2013 and 2014 roof insulation only). In future, if one or more regions decide to abolish the tax credit, it would no longer apply to the residents of that region. Also, Belgians who do not pay personal income tax because their income is too low, by definition cannot profit from the tax credit.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	It is up to the personal income tax paying dwelling owner of Belgium to decide freely whether or not he wants to take advantage of the tax deduction while filling out his personal income tax (PIT) return. Failure to fill out the proper codes and/or to produce the necessary documents (invoices of the contractor) would simply mean not receiving the tax deduction.
Implementation network	The Federal Public Service (FPS) Finance collects the Personal Income Tax (PIT). Tax deductions or tax credits are set by the federal authority or by the regional authorities, for matters under their material competences. From 1 January 2015, tax credits for expenses related to energy saving measures (including roof insulation of dwellings) are a regional competence. It is still unclear whether or not in future the regional authorities will keep the tax credit for expenses related to roof insulation of dwellings.
Outcome	No quantitative evaluation. The impact of this federal measure (tax credit for expenses paid in 2013) has not been assessed separately, to avoid double counting with the existing regional financial and other incentives for the same technology. Obviously, at the time of writing (2015), there is no evaluation of the regional tax credit for expenses paid in 2014, as FPS Finances is still processing the tax returns.

Legal reference. For a mere 220.14 EUR one can buy the complete Belgian Income Tax Code 2015 in every decent Belgian bookstore.

Link to the website FPS Finance on tax credits financien.belgium.be/nl/particulieren/belastingvoordelen

VITO & ECONOTEC (2015)

1.1.3.3 Promotion of rational use of energy (RUE) by electricity distribution service operators as part of their Public Service Obligation (PSO)

	Flemish Region.
General information	<p>Effective 2003. The Flemish Region has opted for a single rational use of energy (RUE) action obligation on the electricity distribution system operators (DSOs). The Flemish DSOs or grid operators have a legal obligation to promote and stimulate energy saving measures for the existing residential and non-residential buildings of their customers. The grid operators do so mainly by financially supporting investments in roof or loft insulation, external or cavity wall insulation, cellar or floor insulation, and high-efficiency glazing. These financial incentives are commonly known as “(energy) premiums”. For new dwellings the grid operator grants a “premium” if the energy performance level (the so-called “E-peil”) is substantially lower than legally required. For non-residential buildings connected to the electricity distribution grid there is an additional RUE support granted after performing an energy audit. For buildings connected to the local transmission grid there is also an additional investment aid.</p> <p>Customers have to send their application form for an “energy premium” to their DSO within 12 months after the invoices or bills for their energy saving measures have been issued. The grid operator has to pay the premium to his customer at the latest 6 months after receiving the application form. A premium is paid only once during a period of 12 months for the same type of investment.</p> <p>The grid operators must pay specific attention to their “vulnerable customers” (low income households), by increasing the premium with 50% for existing dwellings and with 20% for new dwellings; by providing a discount voucher when purchasing an energy efficient refrigerator or washing machine; by granting a premium of 800 EUR for the installation of a condensing boiler; by performing a free “energy scan” of the dwelling; by guiding and executing roof insulation in private rental housing (the so-called “social roof insulation projects”); and by organizing specific information sessions on RUE.</p> <p>The grid operators have the obligation to support local authorities in their local energy policy, for instance through setting up energy accounting systems or energy management systems; performing energy audits; and providing third party financing or other funding mechanisms for the implementation of energy-saving investments.</p> <p>The costs for the support schemes are covered by the competent grid operator. The general principle is that the costs of the RUE public service obligations imposed on the distribution system operators are passed on to the electricity tariffs via the network tariffs.</p>
Type of policy instruments	Regulatory – Public Service Obligations. Economic – financial incentives. Information and Education.
Objectives	No quantitative objectives
Target groups	Customers of electricity distribution service operators (DSOs) in Flanders. Existing residential and non-residential buildings (thermal insulation including glazing). New dwellings (energy performance). Non-residential

	buildings connected to the distribution grid. Buildings connected to the local transmission grid. Special attention to “vulnerable” customers (with additional measures concerning energy efficient refrigerators, washing machines and condensing boilers).
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Customers apply for a “premium” within 12 months after the invoice for energy saving measure(s) was issued. The electricity distribution service operator (DSO) grants the premium for the energy saving measure(s) at the latest 6 months after receiving the application from his customer. Customers who do not apply for a premium obviously do not receive a premium. Customers are made aware of the existence of the premiums by information campaigns initiated by the DSOs.
Implementation network	The Flemish Energy Agency (VEA) VEA imposes, monitors and evaluates the Public Service Obligation.(PSO) of the DSOs. The Flemish electricity distribution system operators (DSOs) or grid operators pay the “premiums” to their customers. The grid operators recover the costs by increasing the electricity tariffs.
Outcome	Please see D1.1 Table 4.

Legal reference: Article 7.5.1 of the Energy Decree and Title VI, Chapter IV of the [Energy Decree of November 19, 2010](#).

Link to website: www.energiesparen.be/reg-openbaardienstverplichtingen

1.1.3.4 Property tax reduction

	Flemish Region
General information	<p>Since tax year 2009 the Flemish Government rewards energy-efficient builders with a reduction in the property tax. A levy known as "immovable withholding tax" (“Onroerende Voorheffing”) is imposed on the deemed income from immovable property located in Belgium. The tax rate is 2.5% for the Flemish region. Municipal surcharges increase the effective rate to between 18% and 50% or more, depending on the municipality where the property is located. The energy performance level (or “E-peil”) of a building is a measure of the energy performance of the building and the fixed installations in standard conditions. The Flemish Government implements a reduction in property tax for new energy-efficient builds. For building applications up and till 2012 new residential buildings with an energy performance level (or “E-peil”) of maximum E60 receive a 20 % property tax reduction for a period of 10 years. New residential buildings with an E-level of maximum E40 receive a 40 % property tax reduction From 1 January 2013 residential buildings with an E-level of maximum E50 (maximum E40 in 2014) receive a reduction of 50% for a period of 5 years; and buildings with an E-level of maximum E30 or nearly Zero Energy Buildings receive a 100% reduction for 5 years</p> <p>For newly built non-residential buildings the following rules apply. For building applications before 1 January 2013 buildings with an E-level of maximum E70 receive a 20% property tax reduction for a period of 10 years. From 1 January 2013 new non-residential buildings with an E-level of maximum E50 receive a 50% tax reduction; and those with an E-level of maximum E30 receive a 100% property tax reduction; in both cases for a period of 5 years. From 1 January 2014 new non-residential buildings</p>

	with an E-level of maximum E40 receive a 50% property tax reduction; and those with an E-level of maximum E30 receive a 100% property tax reduction, in both instances for a period of 5 years.
Type of policy instruments	Economic – tax reduction.
Objectives	No quantitative objectives
Target groups	The owners of newly built energy efficient dwellings. The owner does not have to be domiciled in the home. The tax reduction also applies for a second home. The owners of newly built energy efficient commercial buildings.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	This tax reduction is automatically assigned by the Flemish Tax Authority. The owner of the building does not have to take any action.
Implementation network	The Flemish Government decides on the property tax reduction. The Flemish Tax Agency automatically assigns the tax reduction.
Outcome	No evaluation available.

Legal reference: [Decree for the Flemish Codex Tax \(official title: "Flemish Tax Codex of December 13, 2013"\)](#)

Link to website: [vermindering-van-de-onroerende-voorheffing](#) [korting-op-onroerende-voorheffing](#)

Link to website of Flemish Tax Authority: [belastingen.vlaanderen.be](#)

1.1.3.5 Home improvement grant

	Flemish Region.
General information	The Flemish home improvement grant for specific improvements to the property or for renovation work applies to work carried out on the dwelling (roof, façade, windows, heating system, humidity control, plumbing and extension works); on the condition that the dwelling is at least 25 years old and that the household has an income of maximum 29,030 EUR (+1,510 EUR per dependent).
Type of policy instruments	Economic – subsidy.
Objectives	The aim is to provide financial help to anyone who wants to improve or extend their house because it no longer meets the standards.
Target groups	Any resident (occupier or lessor) of the Flemish Region who wants to improve or extend his house because it no longer meets the standards and whose annual income does not exceed 29,020 EUR. Existing (at least 25 years old) residential buildings (dwellings).
Rules and influencing mechanisms	The applicant can either be occupier or lessor. The occupier is the person and, possibly, the person with whom he or she is cohabiting or to whom he or she is married; and who occupies the house on the application date on the basis of a right in rem or of a rental agreement for minimum three years. The lessor is the person and, possibly, the person with whom he or she is cohabiting or to whom he or she is married; and who is who is letting the house on the application date to a social letting agency for at least nine years. Whether or not the applicant will receive a home improvement grant depends on his income, his house and the invoice. Within a period of ten years, the applicant can apply for a home improvement or home adaptation grant for a maximum of three times. The applicant must make sure that each new application pertains to another category of works. The applicant can only apply for the home improvement grant after completion of the works. He has to append all the invoices, as well as the tax notice of the personal income tax of the income year from three

	<p>years ago, to his application.</p> <p>The applicant can apply for the home improvement grant in two ways: by means of a paper application form or by means of a digital application form. Both forms are available from the website bouwenenwonen.be. The applicant can also apply for the paper application form with Wonen-Vlaanderen (Housing Agency-Flanders); or order it for free by telephone on the number 1700.</p> <p>A decision will be taken within three months, provided the application is accurate and complete. The grant will be paid within three months after this decision.</p>
Implementation network	The Housing Agency-Flanders (“Wonen-Vlaanderen”), more in particular the Housing department, is responsible for implementation, monitoring and evaluation.
Outcome	No evaluation available.

Legal reference: [Decision of the Flemish Government of December 18, 1992 establishing a premium adjustment and improved premium for homes](#) ; [Ministerial decree implementing the decision of the Flemish Government of December 18, 1992 establishing a premium adjustment and improved premium for homes](#)

Most information is available in English at the moving-and-housing/home-improvement-grant

Link to website www.bouwenenwonen.be

1.1.3.6 ÉCOPACK

	Walloon Region
General information	<p>On 1 May 2012, the Walloon Government launched a support instrument called “ÉCOPACK” aiming at stimulating energy efficiency upgrades in housing. It applies to owners of dwellings completed before 1 December 1996. Households willing to improve the energy performance of their houses may benefit from a zero-percent interest loan for the realisation of several refurbishment works. Certain renewable energy technologies are also eligible for the loan. The Ecopack was introduced in order to compensate the suspension of income tax reduction at the federal level. The programme granted interest-free loans and energy subsidies, provided the household in question carries out at least two energy efficiency improvements. Eligible improvements include amongst others installing roof insulation, wall or floor insulation (if approved by an energy audit), double glazing, a condensing boiler, a biomass boiler or a heat pump, combined with the installation of thermostatic valves, the insulation of piping systems or the replacement of flooring for instance. The actual costs of the improvements shall range between €2,500 and €30,000 including VAT. Due to a reform of the energy subsidies (“primes énergie”) support mechanism in Wallonia, applicants from 1 January 2015 are only entitled to the zero-percent interest loan without additional subsidy.</p>
Type of policy instruments	Economic – soft loan.
Objectives	No quantitative objectives
Target groups	The beneficiary of ÉCOPACK has to be the owner-occupant, owner-lessor or tenant of the dwelling, with a taxable income of less than 93,000 EUR in 2013, have a stable income and sufficient financial capacity to repay the credit. Dwellings in Wallonia, completed before 1 December 1996, in

	good condition with a compliant electrical installation, and occupied by the applicant or leased at the time of application (second homes are excluded).
Rules and influencing mechanisms	The applicant verifies at the site of the Social Credit Society (SWCS) or at the site of the Housing Fund for large families in Wallonia (FLW) whether or not he is eligible for the loan; contacts the call centre; collects quotes related to the work and all other necessary documents; signs the ÉCOPACK loan contract; starts the work; and sends the invoices as work progresses to SWCS or FLW who pay the contractor or the building material supplier.
Implementation network	The Ecopack support is directly financed by the budget of the Walloon Region. The Social Credit Society (“la Société wallonne du crédit social”, SWCS) and the Housing Fund for large families in Wallonia (“le Fonds du logement des familles nombreuses de Wallonie”, FLW) are the two organisations in charge of allocating the zero-percent-interest rate loan.
Outcome	Please see D.1.1 Table 5

Legal reference: [26 January 2012 - Order of the Walloon Government laying down the conditions for granting écopacks by the Housing Fund of the Large Families in Wallonia](#)

Information brochure on Ecopack can be downloaded [here](#) (in French).

Link to website of Housing Funds for large families in Wallonia www.flw.be/swcs.be

Link to website of [DGO4](#)

1.1.3.7 Energy premiums (“primes énergie”) in Wallonia

Several energy subsidies are provided by the Walloon Region. The energy subsidies a.k.a. “energy premiums” are directly financed by the budget of the Walloon region. On 21 October 2014, the Minister of Energy announced that the Walloon Region will reform its energy subsidies in order to simplify and harmonize the support mechanism for housing and renewable energies. As a result, most energy subsidies were suspended during the first quarter of 2015. Thanks to the reform, the Walloon government hopes to place greater emphasis on low-interest loans in order to limit windfall effects observed with the allocation of subsidies. On 1 April 2015 the Walloon government restored the “prime énergie” mechanism.

	Walloon Region.
General information	The energy premium (“prime Énergie”) is a package of financial support granted by the Walloon Region for the execution of works intended to improve the energy performance of dwellings. Energy premiums are granted for thermal roof, wall and floor insulation; heating and/or domestic hot water systems; or for energy audits. Applications for premiums for the same type of investment in the same dwelling have to be at least six years apart.
Type of policy instruments	Economic – subsidies.
Objectives	No quantitative objectives
Target groups	An applicant must be 18 years of age, have a real interest in the dwelling (owner, usufructuary, etc.); have an overall taxable income lower than or equal to 93,000 EUR; and commit oneself to meet (no later than 12 months after the settlement date of the premium) one of the following requirements: 1) to occupy the home as the principal resident for a minimum of 5 years, or 2) to make the dwelling available to a social housing agency or public social housing society, or 3) to make the

	<p>dwelling available free of charge to family members or relatives to the second degree for a minimum period of one year.</p> <p>The dwelling must be located in Wallonia and having been occupied as a dwelling for the first time at least 20 years before the application date.</p>
Rules and influencing mechanisms	<p>The applicant first sends the appropriate form to the Department of Energy and Sustainable Building of DGO4. The administration sends a notice. The applicant performs the work or has the work carried out by a contractor. The invoices (contractor and/or building materials) has to be dated after the date of receiving the notice sent by the administration. Next, the completed and signed premium application is sent to the administration within four months after the date that the final invoice was issued.</p>
Implementation network	<p>The energy subsidies are directly financed by the budget of the Walloon Region. The Department of Energy and Sustainable Building of DGO4 implements, monitors and evaluates the policy instrument.</p>
Outcome	<p>Please see D1.1 Table 5</p>

Legal reference: [March 26, 2015 Order of the Walloon Government establishing a system of premiums for individuals promoting energy saving and renovation of housing](#)

Link to website energie.wallonie.be/fr/primes-energie-2015

1.1.3.8 PIVERT (green investments program)

	<p>Walloon Region</p>
General information	<p>The PIVERT program was initiated by the Walloon Minister of Housing in 2012. It is part of the “Marshall Plan 2.Green” of the Walloon Government.</p> <p>The aim is the thermal renovation of up to 12,000 social dwellings amongst the least energy efficient of the Walloon housing stock. The works mainly cover the thermal insulation of dwellings, the replacement of windows as well as the replacement of heating and/or domestic hot water systems and ventilation systems. The technical and financial eligibility criteria in the PIVERT programme are very stringent. The targeted energy performance of rehabilitated buildings is greater than that set by the Energy Performance of Buildings (EPB) Standard, and is in some cases even comparable to the passive house standard.</p> <p>The first of four phases of the PIVERT program concerned the renovation of 3,860 dwellings for a total amount of 97.5 million EUR. For the second phase the total amounts to 300.28 million EUR.</p>
Type of policy instruments	<p>Economic – green investment programme.</p>
Objectives	<p>The thermal renovation of up to 12,212 social dwellings in Wallonia. Reducing the energy bill and fuel poverty of the target group (social tenants with insecure or low incomes).</p>
Target groups	<p>Tenants with insecure or low-income living in public social housing in the Walloon Region of Belgium.</p>
Rules and influencing mechanisms	<p>All public social housing societies in Wallonia obtained funding to carry out work under the PIVERT Green Investment Plan. The social dwellings to be renovated are selected through a call for proposals to all Public Service Housing Societies (SLSP). The projects are selected based on the current energy performance; the expected energy savings and the speed</p>

	with which the energy efficiency measures can be implemented. The invested amount per dwelling is minimum 10,000 EUR and maximum 60,000 EUR.
Implementation network	<p>Société Wallonne du Logement (SWL). SWL is a public interest organisation and the main institutional operator of the public social housing policy in Wallonia. It ensures, on behalf of the Walloon Government, guardianship of and provides advice and assistance to 64 public social housing societies. It coordinates the development and rental management of 101,000 social dwellings.</p> <p>A funding of 400,000 EUR is dedicated to the PIVERT program, spread over a period of 4 years. This amount is made up of 300 million EUR alternative funding from the Marshall 2.Green plan; and a loan of 100 million EUR consented to the SWL by the Council of Europe Development Bank.</p>
Outcome	Energy efficiency measures resulted in an average 60% reduction in energy consumption in about 8,500 dwellings renovated in the first two phases of the PIVERT programme. On the basis of an annual energy consumption of 90 kWh/m ² or 9 litres of heating fuel oil/m ² , the PIVERT programme consistently reduced the overall carbon footprint by 30,000 tons of CO ₂ per year. Environmental impact is expected to increase in the two subsequent phases of the programme. Please also see D1.1. Table 5.

Legal reference: PIVERT is part of the Marshall Plan 2.Green. Documents can be downloaded [here](#).

Link to code-du-logement-et-de-l-habitat-durable.html

Link to website SWL www.wallonie.be/fr/guide/guide-services

1.1.3.9 UREBA (Subsidies to Improve the energy efficiency of public buildings)

	Walloon Region.
General information	<p>Date effective 2000. Updated in 2013. The Walloon region provides UREBA subsidies, which aim at supporting public bodies in their initiatives to reduce the energy consumption of their buildings. The UREBA subsidies are directly financed by the budget of the Walloon region. The UREBA subsidies are available only for the retrofit of <i>existing</i> buildings. The subsidies for Rational Use of Energy (RUE) in public buildings range from audits, setting up an energy management system, investment feasibility studies to investments in building shell elements or systems. The main works taken into account by these subsidies include the thermal insulation of building walls, the replacement or upgrading of the heating system, the improvement of the lighting system, or the implementation of district heating. The subsidy varies according to the type of public building and type of rational use of energy (RUE) action. In addition to the regular annual call for projects, there are specific calls (e.g. in 2007, 2008 and 2013) with higher subsidy rates for specifically targeted types of public buildings (e.g. schools).</p>
Type of policy instruments	Economic – subsidies
Objectives	No quantitative objectives.
Target groups	Persons of public law and non-commercial organisations, such as municipalities, provinces, public centres for social welfare (CPAS), police zones, schools, hospitals, swimming pools and non-profit associations pursuing philanthropic, scientific, technical or educational purposes in

	the field of energy, environmental protection or the fight against social exclusion. The UREBA subsidies are only available for renovation of existing non-residential, non-commercial buildings and public buildings older than 10 years.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	The application for a subsidy must be submitted in the conventional manner to the Department of Energy and Sustainable Building of DGO4, It must clearly show the cost of the equipment to be installed and the financial burden of third-party funding. The latter may not be included in the amount to be subsidized.
Implementation network	The UREBA subsidies are directly financed by the budget of the Walloon Region. The department of Energy and Sustainable Building of DGO4 implements, monitors and evaluates the policy instrument.
Outcome	Please see D1.1 Table 5

Legal reference: [March 28, 2013 Order of the Walloon Government on the granting of subsidies to public law persons and non-commercial organizations for studies and work to improve energy efficiency and the rational use of energy in buildings \(UREBA\)](#)

Link to [subventions-ureba](#)

1.1.3.10 Energy premiums (“primes énergie”) in Brussels

	Brussels-Capital Region
General information	The Brussels Capital region provides energy subsidies (“primes énergie”) for residential and non-residential buildings as well as industrial buildings located in the Brussels region. The energy subsidies are directly financed by the budget of the Brussels-Capital region. The “primes énergie” are subsidies granted to natural or legal persons for several categories of building refurbishments. Categories include for instance roof, wall or floor insulation, super-insulating glazing, efficient mechanical ventilation, efficient heating systems and controls, or renewables (solar boiler or PV), district heating, and energy efficient appliances (A++ refrigerators and freezers, A electric tumble dryer). Energy premiums are also allocated for energy audits or feasibility studies. The energy subsidies are defined each year and apply from 1 January to 31 December. The amount is calculated according to the income level of the applicant. Social real estate agencies, public service real estate agencies as well as the Housing fund of the Brussels region benefit of the subsidies of the low income category (< 30,000 EUR for singles and < 45,000 EUR for couples in 2014). Service sector buildings as well as industrial buildings benefit from the subsidies of the base income category (> 60,000 EUR for singles and > 75,000 EUR for couples in 2014). The subsidy is increased by 10 % for residential buildings situated within a Housing and Renovation Development Area (“Espace de Développement Renforcé du Logement et de la Rénovation” EDRLR).
Type of policy instruments	Economic – subsidies.
Objectives	No quantitative objectives.
Target groups	Natural persons (households) and legal entities (associations, building syndics, businesses). Existing residential and non-residential (including industrial) buildings. New extensions to buildings are not eligible for the energy premiums.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Applications and additional documents may be sent only to Brussels Environment by e-mail or by registered letter. The application must be

	submitted after the work and within four months from the date of the final invoice. The application will be processed by Brussels Environment within 60 days of receipt. If the dossier is incomplete, Brussels Environment will indicate which elements are missing. The applicant has 60 days to complete the dossier. To establish the level of income the applicant has to provide proof of the composition of the family, which is issued by the local authority, as well as a copy of the tax assessment for the year for which the income is requested. If these two items are not provided, the amount of the grant is automatically calculated using the basic category. The applicant cannot appeal against this. All applications where the premium is less than 50 EUR will be automatically rejected. The total amount of aid may not exceed 100% of the amount of the investment or work. Brussels Environment closely examines the evidence of the payments made for the work for which an application for a premium was submitted. If the dossier is complete and admissible, the applicant receives a message that the dossier has been approved. The payment will be made within a week of sending the notice of approval. If the dossier is not admissible, the applicant receives a refusal.
Implementation network	The energy subsidies are directly financed by the budget of the Brussels-Capital region. Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM) implements, monitors and evaluates the policy instrument.
Outcome	Please see D1.1 Table 6

Legal reference: 11/12/2014 Decree of the Brussels Capital Region of December 11th, 2014 approving the implementation concerning the granting of financial support in the field of energy (the legal reference could **not** be located).

Link to [energiepremies-en-steun](#)

1.1.3.11 The Brussels green loan (BGL)

	Brussels-Capital Region.
General information	The Brussels Green Loan was launched in 2008, although it was initially called “The Social Green Loan” and renamed in 2012. The green loan is a zero-rate energy loan for low (or medium) income households to retrofit their dwelling while increasing its energy efficiency. The loans are financed by CRÉDAL (an alternative credit cooperative). The Region brings its guarantee (regional warranty in case of no repayment), covers the operating cost and the interest subsidy. The eligible energy efficiency improvements include roof, wall and floor insulation, super insulating glazing, controlled mechanical ventilation, gas condensing boiler and thermostatic controls. The loan covers the costs of the technologies / materials and the installation (labour) costs. For each property in the Brussels Region, the Brussels green loan is offered to resident owners; owners who lease their premises (subject to certain conditions); beneficiaries of a right in rem (usufruct, bare owners); and tenants (on condition that the owner agrees). To benefit from the green loan the professional income must be below certain limits. The amount of the Brussels green loan is calculated based on the nature of the work(s) described in the estimate(s) and the repayment capacity of the applicant. The green loan is linked to the regional “energy premiums”.
Type of policy instruments	Economic – soft loan. Combination of loan, subsidy and guarantee funds.
Objectives	To retrofit dwellings while increasing their energy efficiency. The initial

	objective was to disburse 500 loans per year. This objective has not been achieved as between 2008 and 2013 (6 years) only 523 loans were disbursed.
Target groups	Brussels' residents – private housing owners and/or tenants. Citizens with low or medium income; or who have difficult access to credit. The aim is to give <i>all</i> inhabitants of the Region access to the Brussels Green Loan. Residential buildings (retrofit of dwellings).
Rules and influencing mechanisms	The applicant has to check first if he is eligible by contacting the Energy House. If so, he contacts CRÉDAL to make an appointment, where he has to bring with him the necessary paperwork (including the estimate(s) of the works). CRÉDAL hands over the estimate of the works to Brussels Environment. Brussels Environment calculates the amount that the applicant may claim in terms of energy premiums and the Brussels green loan. This calculation is made by Brussels Environment based on the submitted estimate(s). Another calculation is made by CRÉDAL in the framework of the credit analysis of the applicant. The microcredit advisor of CRÉDAL analyses the budget, determines the repayment capacity and offers the applicant the most suitable green loan formula. The amount of the eligible works must exceed 500 EUR, but a Brussels green Loan (BGL) is in no case granted for an amount higher than 20,000 EUR. To obtain a green loan the works may not yet have been started. It is CRÉDAL who makes the decision on whether the green loan is provided or not. The applicant returns the completed forms to CRÉDAL, signs the Brussels green loan (BGL) agreement, and starts the works. Once the works are completed, the final invoice is examined by Brussels Environment to ensure that the executed works comply with the works specified in the initial estimate(s). The applicant sends the completed forms of the green loan settlement to CRÉDAL, who pays the contractor.
Implementation network	The Brussels green loan is a partnership between Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM) who is the manager of the Regional Energy Fund and the Regional Budget; and the banking institution CRÉDAL (an alternative credit cooperation). Brussels Environment manages the scheme and the subsidies (one person from the 'Energy Department - Unit of Support to private individuals' is responsible). CRÉDAL is a cooperative society which provides loans to social economy actors and microcredits to small enterprises. The "Energy House" acts as a front office for the applicants.
Outcome	466 loans for a total amount of 4,524,848 EUR granted between 2008 and June 2013. Out of 523 loans disbursed between 2008 and 2013 only 1 loan has not been repaid. No other evaluation available.

Legal reference: Not found.

Detailed information in English (spring 2014) can be downloaded [here](#).

Link to [de-brusselse-groene-lening](#)

Link to green loan brochure ([French](#)) ([Dutch](#))

Link to CRÉDAL www.credal.be/prevertbruxellois

1.1.4 CAPACITY BUILDING AND NETWORKING

1.1.4.1 Build Up Skills Belgium (BUSB)

	Flemish Region. Walloon Region.
General information	<p>Start November 2011. End April 2013. BUILD UP Skills was a strategic initiative under the Intelligent Energy Europe (IEE) programme to boost continuing or further education and training of craftsmen and other on-site construction workers and systems installers in the building sector. Build Up Skills Belgium was a consortium consisting of the Belgian construction industry training fund (fvb-ffc Constructiv), the Scientific and Technical Centre for the Building industry (BBRI), the Flemish Energy Agency (VEA) and the Public Service of Wallonia (DGO4), Department of Energy and Sustainable Building.</p> <p>The project consisted of three phases: 1) detailed analysis of the national status quo to assess and quantify supply and demand in the building sector until 2020 and beyond, and to identify specific skills shortages by craft occupation as well as key barriers; 2) the creation of a national platform of stakeholders including public and private organisations in the field of Vocational Education and Training (VET), public bodies that develop policies in the field of energy efficiency and renewable energy sources, and social partners (who are seen as key partners); and 3) the development of a “national roadmap”. The analysis of the status quo is the basis for broad discussions with public and private stakeholders about current gaps, future needs and priorities, leading to the elaboration and endorsement of a national roadmap of priority measures to up-skill the qualification of craftsmen, other on-site workers and system installers of buildings. The identified measures should aim at reaching the 2020 targets in the building sector.</p>
Type of policy instruments	Capacity building.
Objectives	The final aim is to increase the number of qualified workers to deliver renovations offering a high energy performance as well as new, nearly zero-energy buildings.
Target groups	<p>Craftsmen and other on-site construction workers and systems installers</p> <p>The initiative addresses skills in relation to energy efficiency and renewables in all types of buildings, including residential and non-residential buildings.</p>
Rules and influencing mechanisms	<p>BUILD UP Skills was a strategic initiative under the Intelligent Energy Europe (IEE) programme. Throughout the duration of the research project, regular exchange activities were organised at EU level to underline the European dimension and to foster the learning among countries. In addition to the three plenary meetings of the BUSB platform, nine thematic workshops were organised between November 2012 and March 2013, with two sessions per theme. BUILD UP Skills Belgium used working group sessions, in which seven technological and two cross-profession themes were addressed. The themes were defined based on the results of a questionnaire about priority technologies with regard to renewable energy sources and energy efficiency. The questionnaire was addressed to all Belgian stakeholders.</p>

Implementation network	The consortium partners were the Belgian construction industry training fund (fvb-ffc Constructiv); the Scientific and Technical Centre for the Building industry (BBRI); the Flemish Energy Agency (VEA) and the Public Service of Wallonia (DGO4), Department of Energy and Sustainable Building. During the research project, all relevant Belgian stakeholders were consulted. The stakeholders also provided data.
Outcome	A report on the analysis of the status quo was published in 2012. The national roadmap was published in 2013. The national roadmap contains sixteen (16) measures that BUILD UP Skills Belgium proposed and that are meant to enable a higher-quality execution of techniques and technologies with regard to renewable energy sources and energy efficiency. The follow-up however is very unclear, and it seems that the partnership ended with the project.

Links to [fvb-ffc Constructiv](#) and [BBRI](#).

The Analysis of the national status quo can be downloaded [here](#).

The Roadmap BUILD UP Skills Belgium (in English) can be downloaded [here](#).

Link to Build Up Skills Belgium website: belgium.buildupskills.eu European website www.buildupskills.eu

1.1.4.2 Employment-Environment Alliance (AEE) in Wallonia

	Walloon Region.
General information	The idea behind the development of the so-called ‘Employment-Environment’ Alliances in the Walloon region and the Brussels-Capital regions is that policies accompanying the green transition of economic sectors can create new jobs and maintain these sectors’ long-term viability. The initiative was launched in Wallonia in 2012. The Alliance focuses on the potential of energy and environmental improvements in buildings to generate jobs, create economic opportunities and increase training especially in the field of sustainable construction jobs. The Walloon Alliance brings together various public and private decision makers, as well as concerned social partners and field actors, with the aim of stimulating demand for sustainable renovation and construction of private and public buildings; increasing the availability and capacity of the construction sector; and developing skills through an extensive “green training” programme. Special emphasis is placed on energy efficiency in buildings. Concrete measures include training schemes, exchanges of good practice, the funding of schemes for individuals as well as small and medium-sized enterprises, research programmes and the provision of technical support. In February 2012, 41 multi-sectorial contracts had been signed with partners for the first Employment-Environment Alliance.
Type of policy instruments	Multisectorial contracts between the Walloon Government and various partners.
Objectives	To turn the improvement of the environment into a source of economic opportunities and job creation. Stimulate demand for renovation and sustainable construction of private and public buildings; strengthen the capacity of the construction sector; and develop skills through a comprehensive programs of “green training”.
Target groups	Building sector. Federations of construction companies, public interest

	and services organizations, unions, training operators, as well as groups and associations involved in sustainable development and construction. Residential and non-residential buildings.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Tainting schemes, exchanges of good practice, the funding of schemes for individuals as well as small and medium-sized enterprises, research programmes and the provision of technical support.
Implementation network	The Walloon Government, in 2012 represented by the Walloon Prime Minister, the Minister of Sustainable Development; the Minister of Employment and Training; and the Minister of Economy (after the elections of 2014, the names of the ministries have change). The (then) Ministry of Sustainable Development was entrusted with the EEA coordination.
Outcome	The EEA measures put in place during the first EEA reduced CO ₂ emissions by 590,000 tons in 2014. Energy savings costs are estimated at 215 million EUR in 2014. The final evaluation report (March 2014) can be downloaded here (in French). A synthesis of the evaluation report can be downloaded here (in French); and a (very short) executive summary in English here . These evaluation reports contain very little to no information in terms of energy savings.

A description (in French) of the first Employment-Environment Alliance can be found [here](#). This report also contains (in Annex 2) a list of the partners.

1.1.4.3 Employment-Environment Alliance (AEE) in Brussels

	Brussels-Capital Region.
General information	The initiative was launched in Brussels in 2011. AEE arose as a response to the exploding demand for eco-construction in the Brussels-Capital Region. It acts on two levels: one intended to stimulate demand, the other intended to support the development of supply. Sustainable construction is one of the four major work axes of the Alliance, together with Water; Resources and waste; and Sustainable supply of food. The objective of the “Green construction” axis is to “stimulate and accompany the Brussels actors in the construction sector so that they develop a competitive supply in terms of green construction and renovation. One of the main goals is quality job creation in sustainable construction, mainly for masons, chapistes, façade builders, roofers, carpenters, glaziers, heating and sanitation specialists (installation and maintenance), electricians, architects, and technical engineers. The EEA multiannual plan engages 44 partners who signed the multi-sectorial contracts.
Type of policy instruments	Multisectorial contracts between the Brussels-Capital Government and various partners. Voluntary.
Objectives	The goals are the organization of 30,000 training hours and the creation of 2,500 new jobs to stimulate sustainable construction.
Target groups	The Brussels actors in the construction industry. Masons, chapistes, façade builders, roofers, carpenters, glaziers, heating and sanitation specialists (installation and maintenance), electricians, architects, and technical engineers. Residential and non-residential buildings.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	The AEE operates on the basis of a participatory approach. The members

	draft open collaboration proposals while sharing information and best practices. The Alliance allows the different actors in vocational training and sustainable development such as sector funds, training organisations and organizations of socio-professional integration to unite four or five times a year. 110 actors (administrators, public interest organisations, professional federations, sector representatives and social partners) discuss, propose and implement various actions to achieve the shared objective of creating green jobs. The actors first identified the obstacles that prevent businesses from moving towards sustainable construction. All the actors involved in the dialogue then came up with 44 concrete actions which aim to confront the challenges concerning education, training, integration, technical references, research, support for businesses, financing, certification, etc.
Implementation network	The Employment-Environment Alliance is an initiative of the government of the Brussels-Capital Region. The ministers, the social partners and the relevant public, non-profit and private-sector actors in the field are united.
Outcome	No evaluation available The Thematic Report 2014 Sustainable Construction contains useful information.

The Thematic Report 2014 Sustainable Construction can be downloaded [here](#) (Dutch) or [here](#) (French)

A list of partners and organisations can be found here www.aee-rbc.be/partenaires

A list of actions can be found here www.aee-rbc.be/actions

Link to AEE <http://www.aee-rbc.be/>.

1.1.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR THE PROMOTION OF ENERGY SERVICES

1.1.5.1 FEDESCO (Federal Energy Service Company)

	Federal level.
General information	<p>Fedesco was created in 2005 by the Belgian Federal Investment Company as a public limited company to finance energy efficiency measures in 1,800 federal government buildings. It is a public / private funded energy service company with the objectives to promote energy efficiency and to remove obstacles to energy saving investments in the federal public buildings. Fedesco sponsors and funds energy audits to identify potential energy efficiency measures and provides the financing needed for their implementation, including investments in the building envelope and technical installations. Through Fedesco, energy efficiency investments in the federal public buildings are made and may be reimbursed based on the generated energy savings on a "first out" basis. Fedesco is financed by the Federal government and invests in projects to increase energy efficiency via e.g. energy performance contracts, energy monitoring systems and PV panels.</p> <p>Fedesco played a pioneering role in Belgium in the field of third party financing (TPF) and Energy Performance Contracts (EPC) in government buildings, concessions for photovoltaic (PV) solar panels on the rooftops of government buildings and a global approach to energy monitoring, accounting and authentication.</p>
Type of policy instruments	Promotion of energy services.
Objectives	Promote energy efficiency and remove obstacles to energy efficiency

	investments in the federal public buildings. The National Climate Plan mentions an objective of FEDESCO to decrease CO ₂ emissions from public buildings with 22% in 2014 compared to 2007.
Target groups	The ±1,800 public buildings used by the Federal government (administrations, prisons, courthouses, museums, archives, etc.).
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Fedesco studies, evaluates, finances and has energy efficiency measures implemented for all the public buildings of the Federal Public Services (FPS) and other federal government agencies. The reimbursements to FEDESCO are based on future savings. These repayments cover the investment costs, operating costs and interests incurred by Fedesco.
Implementation network	Fedesco is a public / private funded energy service company. Fedesco acts autonomously, but carries out its tasks in close collaboration with the Belgian Buildings Agency, which is responsible for the daily management of the federal public buildings. By the end of 2015, Fedesco will be abolished, and the Belgian Buildings Agency will take over the tasks and staff of Fedesco.
Outcome	In a report dated 2012 FEDESCO reports to have invested 2,496,733 EUR resulting in an annual energy saving of 19,883 MWh. It is therefore estimated that each k€ invested by FEDESCO results in an annual energy saving of 8 MWh. See also VITO & ECONOTEC (2015) , p. 72-32 for the effect on CO ₂ emission reductions.

Legal reference: [11 MARCH 2005 - Royal Decree amending the Royal Decree of December 27, 2004 that the Federal Investment mission entrusted under Article 2 § 3 of the Act of April 2, 1962 on the Federal Investment and the regional investment companies.](#); [27 DECEMBER 2004. - Royal decree that the Federal Investment mission entrusted under Article 2 § 3 of the Act of April 2, 1962 on the Federal Investment and the regional investment companies.](#)

Link [knowledgecenter by Fedesco](#);

Link to Belgian Buildings Agency www.buildingsagency.be .

[VITO & ECONOTEC \(2015\)](#)

1.1.6 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT AND BEST AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGY (BAT) PROMOTION

1.1.6.1 The Guide for sustainable procurement

	Federal
General information	<p>The Belgian Federal government subscribes to the goal of the European Council and the European commission of 50% sustainable procurement procedures for all federal public procurements. Sustainable procurement procedures are compliant with the instructions given in the federal circulars concerning sustainable public procurement.</p> <p>Publicprocurement.be is the procurement portal website of the Public Procurement Agency of the Federal Public Service Personnel and Organisation in collaboration with the Public Procurement Agency of the Chancellery of the Prime Minister. This portal website has a webpage dedicated to sustainable public procurement , where one can download the guide for sustainable procurements (in three parts). The web-based user's guide outlines the technical sustainability criteria to be included in specifications for the purchase of supplies and services. The portal website also links to the website "guide for sustainable procurement", where extensive information can be found on all types of sustainable</p>

	products guidedesachatsdurables.be
Type of policy instruments	Promotion of best available technologies (BAT)
Objectives	The contracting authorities of the federal government have a main responsibility in the area of sustainable development. Their role is twofold: 1) to integrate sustainable development in the assignments they give to improve the overall score in this area; and 2) to launch an increasing range of sustainable products and services to the subscribers.
Target groups	The Federal Public Services and other federal government agencies. Other Belgian public bodies also make use of the guide for sustainable procurement.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	The instructions for sustainable procurement are detailed in the federal circular of 16 May 2014. The circular of May 16, 2014 aims to implement a sustainable procurement by the federal government, to promote the integration of social clauses and to make the contracts awarded by the federal contracting services more accessible to SMEs. A practical help for “green procurement under socially responsible conditions” is the website guidedesachatsdurables.be
Implementation network	The Public Procurement Agency of the Federal Public Service Personnel. The Public Procurement Agency of the Chancellery of the Prime Minister. Support is given by the Federal Institute for Sustainable Development (FRDO/DFDD). The FRDO/CFDD continuously updates the Sustainable Procurement Guide and advises on the correct interpretation of technical specifications and other clauses contained within it. The FRDO/DFDD also conducts studies on issues such as life-cycle costing. The Procurement Advice and Policy Cell or CPA encourages federal purchasing units to incorporate sustainability clauses into contract specifications. It also advises on the incorporation of sustainability clauses into contract specifications, through its templates and through customised advice. The consultation network (channels of dialogue and communication) and the Interdepartmental Commission on Sustainable Development (CIDD) are in charge of monitoring.
Outcome	<p>The CPA and the FRDO/CFDD, have noted that the technical specifications featured in the Sustainable Procurement Guide are increasingly being used by the federal purchasing units as well as by the purchasing units of other Belgian public bodies.</p> <p>An OECD (2015) report mentions Belgium as best practice with regard to the professionalization of the approach of sustainable public procurement at the federal, regional and local level. The approach within the legal and technical networks for buyers; the dialogue between companies and buyers to provide criteria for green products; the support from the Federal Institute for Sustainable Development (FIDO) and in particular the development of the Guide to Sustainable Procurement are praised.</p> <p>VITO & ECONOTEC (2015), p. 66, did not quantify this measure because the website on the purchase of products which are environmentally friendly and produced in socially accepted circumstances does not focus on CO₂ emissions.</p>

The circular of 16 May 2014 concerning sustainable procurement can be downloaded [here](#).

The Guide for sustainable public procurement (2013) can be downloaded [here](#) (part I), [here](#) (part II) and [here](#) (part III).

Link to publicprocurement.be . [www.publicprocurement.be duurzame-overheidopdrachten](http://www.publicprocurement.be/duurzame-overheidopdrachten)

Link to the [OECD Smart Procurement](#) (2015) report. The OECD report gives a more detailed description.

Link to the Federal Institute for Sustainable Development (FRDO/CFDD). <http://www.frdo-cfdd.be/en>

Link to the Interdepartmental Commission on Sustainable Development (CIDD) <http://www.cidd.belgium.be/nl>

VITO & ECONOTEC (2015)

1.1.6.2 BatEx - The ‘Exemplary Buildings’ call for proposals (“Bâtiments exemplaires”)

	Brussels-Capital Region.
General information	Date effective May 2007. The Brussels-Capital Region supports the design of energy-efficient buildings. It launches annual contests for the design and construction or renovation of buildings meeting high energy and environmental standards. The four requirements for the model buildings or so-called “Exemplary Buildings” (“bâtiments exemplaires” or BatEx) are: 1) be aimed at minimizing primary energy needs with a minimal use of conventional energy carriers (gas, oil or electricity) and striving for zero CO ₂ emissions; 2) be based on eco-design principles to minimize the impact on humans and the environment; 3) have high architectural quality (with attention to comfort, aesthetics and clever use of materials) and with high integration in the public space; and 4) be a combination of existing technologies and innovative solutions so that the project remains technically and financially accessible. The Brussels-Capital Region provides subsidies for the conception and the realisation of exemplary buildings; technical support to help project designers reach the quality objectives; and public visibility for the buildings and their designers.
Type of policy instruments	Information and Education – Advice / Aid in Implementation. Economic – Subsidies. Project Demonstration and Dissemination.
Objectives	The goal is to show that, even with limited financial resources, excellent energy and environmental performance can be achieved. No quantitative objectives.
Target groups	Households, public authorities, NGOs, enterprises, project developers, ... for new constructions, reconstructions, renovations of combinations thereof in the Brussels-Capital Region. Single family and multi-family residential buildings Non-residential buildings including public services (schools, hospitals, nurseries, youth centres, sports accommodations, etc.); offices and commercial or industrial buildings.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Each project beneficiary makes a declaration of honour to respect the contract signed. A follow-up of the projects is conducted, including the verification of the specified energy performance. Data of the buildings’ energy consumption are collected over a period of five years.
Implementation network	Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM). The activities are also supported by the Public Service Housing Associations [“Sociétés Immobilières de Service Public”, SISP], the Brussels Regional Development Agency (SDRB) and the municipalities through Sustainable Neighbourhood contracts.
Outcome	In the 2007-2009 period 177 projects were selected; 18.6 million EUR subsidies were allocated, allowing 81,000 m ² to be built following the Passive standard. In 2012, the Brussels-Capital region allocated a budget of 5 million EUR to the development of 37 selected projects representing a total area of 148,000 m ² . Between 2007 and 2013 193 projects were

	selected, representing a total floor area of 522,000 m ² ; and 29 million EUR of financial support was allocated. Please also see D1.1 Table 6.
--	--

Link to BatEx [voorbeeldgebouwen](#)

1.1.7 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR IN BELGIUM

Type of policy instrument		Name	Final Energy savings 2020	Target group	Rules & Influencing mechanisms	Implementation network
Regulatory	Bel	Ecodesign Directive	See D1.1	Products	Sanctions	The Federal Public Service (FPS) Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment-Policy Division of Products and Chemicals.
Regulatory	Fla	EPB - MEPS	not defined	Buildings - Residential & Non-residential	Penalties for non-compliance	The Flemish Energy Agency (VEA) and the Ministry of Environment, Nature and Energy (LNE) are responsible for the implementation of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD)
Regulatory	Wal	EPB - MEPS	673 GWh	Buildings - Residential & Non-residential	Penalties for non-compliance	The development authority is the Operational Directorate General for Spatial Planning, Housing, Heritage and Energy of the Walloon Public Service. The implementation authority is Department of Energy and Sustainable Building
Regulatory	Bru	EPB - MEPS	not defined	Buildings - Residential & Non-residential	Penalties for non-compliance	Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM)
Regulatory	Fla	EPB - EPC	not defined	Buildings - Residential & Non-residential	Penalties for non-compliance	The Flemish Energy Agency (VEA) and the Ministry for Environment, Nature and Energy are responsible for the implementation
Regulatory	Wal	EPB - EPC	not defined	Buildings - Residential & Non-residential	Penalties for non-compliance	The Department for Energy and Sustainable Building of the Walloon Region (SPW - DGO4) and the Ministry of Environment are responsible for the development and implementation. In the case of the construction of a new building, the EPB certificate is issued by the Regional authorities. In other cases, it is issued by an EPB certifying officer.
Regulatory	Bru	EPB - EPC	not defined	Buildings - Residential & Non-residential	Penalties for non-compliance	The Government of the Brussels-Capital Region is responsible for the development. Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM) is responsible for the implementation. When a new building is constructed, the EPB certificate is issued by the Brussels Environmental Authority (IBGE), in other cases by the EPB certifying officer.
Regulatory	Fla	mandatory Energy Audit	n.r.	Buildings - Non-residential	not yet implemented	..
Regulatory	Wal	mandatory Energy Audit	n.r.	Buildings - Non-residential	not yet implemented	..
Regulatory	Bru	mandatory Energy Audit	not defined	Buildings - Non-residential	Sanction (no permit granted)	Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM)
Regulatory	Fla	Heating audit	not defined	Buildings - Heating systems	Sanctions	Ministry of Environment, Nature and Energy (LNE)
Dissemination - Informative	Bel	Energy labelling	not defined	Products	Awareness raising	The Federal Public Service (FPS) Economy, S.M.E.s, Self-employed and Energy - Directorate General for Quality and Safety - Regulation and Control Policy Division. The Federal Public Service for the Economy, SME, Middle Class and Energy - Directorate-General for Energy.
Dissemination - Informative	Bel	Energy guzzlers website	not defined	Products	Awareness raising	Federal Public Service Health, Food chain Safety and Environment; Directorate-general for Environment (DG5) - Climate Change Section. Department of Product Policy and Chemical Substances.
Dissemination - Informative	Fla	Energy savings website	not defined	Multi-sectoral	Awareness raising	The Flemish Energy Agency (VEA).

Dissemination - Informative	Fla	Energy consultants	not defined	Multi-sectoral	Aid in implementation + subsidies	Flemish Energy Agency (VEA). NAV (architecten). Bouwunie (aannemers). Vlaamse Confederatie Bouw (aannemers). Samenlevingsopbouw (kansarmen). Gezinsbond. Komosie. Boerenbond Consult
Dissemination - Informative	Wal	Dissemination measures	not defined	Multi-sectoral	Aid in Implementation	Public Service of Wallonia - Department of Energy and Sustainable Building (DG04) - Department for Energy and Sustainable Building
Dissemination - Informative	Bru	Energy House	not defined	Buildings - Residential (households)	Aid in implementation	Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM)
Dissemination - Informative	Bru	P.L.A.G.E.	not defined	Buildings - Residential & Non-residential	Aid in implementation	Bussels Environment (BIM/IBGE). Minister of Energy. Secretary of state for housing. Brussels Regional Housing Authority (SLRB).
Dissemination - Informative	Bru	Sustainable Building facilitator network	not defined	Buildings - Residential & Non-residential	Aid in implementation	Brussels Environmen((IBGE/BIM)
Economic	Bel	Tax deductions	not defined	Households (tax payers)	Incentive - fiscal	Federal Public Service (FPS) of Finance
Economic	Bel	FRGE	not defined	Buildings - Residential (low income households)	Incentive - soft loan	Belgian Government. "Fund for the Reduction of the Global Cost of Energy"
Economic	Fla	Public Service Obligations DSOs	14630 GWh	Households & Companies . Focus low-income	Incentive - financial	The Flemish Energy Agency (VEA). The competent authority are the electricity distribution system (grid) operators (DSOs) in the Flemish region.
Economic	Fla	Property Tax Reduction	not defined	Buildings - Residential (households)	Incentive - subsidies	Flemish Tax Agency
Economic	Fla	Home improvement Grant	not defined	Buildings - Residential (households)	Incentive - subsidies	Housing Agency-Flanders ("Wonen-Vlaanderen"), more in particular the Housing department,
Economic	Wal	Ecopack	267,GWh	Buildings - Residential (households)	Incentive - subsidies + soft loan	The Social Credit Society ("la Société wallonne du crédit social", SWCS) and the Housing Fund for large families in Wallonia ("le Fonds du logement des familles nombreuses de Wallonie", FLW)
Economic	Wal	Energy premiums	3349 GWh	Buildings - Residential (households)	Incentive - subsidies	Public Service of Wallonia - Department of Energy and Sustainable Building (DG04).
Economic	Wal	PIVERT	173 GWh	Buildings - Residential (low income households)	Incentive - financial	The Walloon Housing Corporaton or "Société Wallonne du Logement" (SWL)
Economic	Wal	UREBA	74 GWh	Buildings - Non-residential	Incentive - subsidies	Public Service of Wallonia - Department of Energy and Sustainable Building (DG04).
Economic	Bru	Energy premiums	not defined	Buildings - Residential & Non-residential	Incentive - subsidies	Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM)
Economic	Bru	The Brussels Green Loan (BGL)	not defined	Buildings - Residential (households)	Incentive - soft loan	Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM) who is the manager of the Regional Energy Fund and the Regional Budget; and the banking institution CRÉDAL (an alternative credit cooperation)
Capacity building Networking	FWB	Build Up Skills BUSB	not defined	Building sector (professionals)	Voluntary	The Belgian construction industry training fund (fvb-ffc Constructiv). The Scientific and Technical Centre for the Building industry (BBRI). The Flemish Energy Agency (VEA). the Public Service of Wallonia - Department of Energy and Sustainable Building (DG04).
Capacity building Networking	Wal	Employment-Environment Alliance	not defined	Multi-sectoral (building sector + all buildings)	Incentive - financial	The Walloon Government, in 2012 represented by the Walloon Prime Minister, the Minister of Sustainable Development; the Minister of Employment and Training; and the Minister of Economy (after the elections of 2014, the names of the ministries have change). The (then) Ministry of

						Sustainable Development was entrusted with the EEA coordination.
Capacity building Networking	Bru	Employment-Environment Alliance	not defined	Multi-sectoral (building sector + all buildings)	Incentive - financial	The Employment-Environment Alliance is an initiative of the government of the Brussels-Capital Region. The ministers, the social partners and the relevant public, non-profit and private-sector actors in the field are united.
Promotion of Energy Services	Bel	FEDESCO	not defined	Buildings of the Federal Government	Incentive - financial	Belgian Buildings Agency. Fedesco is (was) a Belgian public / private funded energy service company. . By the end of 2015, Fedesco will be abolished, and the Belgian Buildings Agency will take over the tasks and staff of Fedesco.
Promotion R&D	Bel	Sustainable procurement	not defined	Federal Government	Promotion of BAT	The Public Procurement Agency of the Federal Public Service Personnel. The Public Procurement Agency of the Chancellery of the Prime Minister. Support is given by the Federal Institute for Sustainable Development (FRDO/DFDD).
Promotion R&D	Bru	Model Buildings BatEx	not defined	Buildings - Residential & Non-Residential	Promotion of BAT + Subsidies	(Bruxelles environnement (IBGE/BIM) : Administration de l'environnement et de l'énergie de la Région de Bruxelles-Capitale). Ministry of Energy and Environment. The activities are also supported by the Public Service Housing Associations [Sociétés Immobilières de Service Public, SISP], the Brussels Regional Development Agency (SDRB) and the municipalities through Sustainable Neighbourhood contracts.

Bel = Belgium. Fla = Flemish Region. Wal = Walloon Region. Bru = Brussels-Capital Region.

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

1.2.1 PLANNING INSTRUMENTS

Territory planning is a regional competence. The policies and measures of the regions concerning “planning” are mostly “work in progress”. The policies and measures of the Regions are in fact so vague, that the Flemish Region and the Brussels-Capital Region just provide one energy saving target for the whole transport sector in the NEEAP (see D1.1). The Walloon Region provides four targets in the NEEAP, but it is not entirely clear how Wallonia intends to achieve them (see regulatory instruments).

1.2.1.1 Mobility Plan in the Flemish Region

- Flemish Region
- The Flemish Mobility plan is not expected until 2016, and will be implemented in conjunction with policy plans concerning spatial planning and living environment.

1.2.1.2 Mobility Plan in the Walloon Region

- Walloon Region
- The Walloon Region is working on a global approach reconciling accessibility, environment and energy efficiency.

1.2.1.3 Plan Iris 2

	Brussels-Capital Region.
General information	On September 9, 2010, the Brussels government adopted the final version of the Iris 2 mobility plan. This strategic plan sets out the main guidelines for mobility in the Brussels-Capital Region by 2015-2020. The intended measures to reach this goal include – amongst many others – the increase of pedestrian zones, the improvement of cycling infrastructures, provide separate lanes for trams and buses, and the automation and expansion of the metro network. Other intended measures are promoting the rational use of cars, improve parking policy, protecting residential areas, taxing car use, etc.
Type of policy instruments	Planning instrument. Modal shift. Travel efficiency.
Objectives	The overall goal of the Iris 2 mobility plan is to reduce car traffic by 20% by 2018 compared to 2001. Other goals are to improve the accessibility of the Brussels-Capital Region; and to promote the quality of life of the inhabitants of the region.
Target groups	All citizens of the Brussels-Capital Regions and everyone else who makes use of the transport system of the region.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	The Iris 2 Mobility plan has 9 priorities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To promote soft transport modes such as cycling and walking as an alternative to the car, especially for short trips - To provide everyone with a modern and diverse range of first class public transport; - To encourage rational use of cars and promote innovative applications such as car sharing and collective taxis; - To offer a hierarchical road system which optimizes the safety

	<p>for everyone and optimizes the regulation of traffic in order to create space for other modes of transport;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To pursue a coordinated and regulated parking policy; - To link the mobility plan with urban planning ; - To make available a modern system with real-time information on mobility so that users can take this information into account during their daily movements; - To optimize the logistics and distribution of freight; - To improve the „governance“ in order to create the optimal circumstances for the Iris 2 mobility plan to succeed. <p>In the context of those priorities, the Iris 2 mobility plan provides concrete proposals. Chapter 4 of the plan describes each of those actions in more detail.</p>
Implementation network	Brussels Mobility, Policy Directorate.
Outcome	No evaluation available

Link to website of Brussels Mobility www.mobielbrussel.irisnet.be

Link to Iris-2 mobility plan website de-mobiliteit-van-morgen

Link to the [Iris 2-mobiliteitsplan](#) (2011) (146 pp) (Dutch) or [Plan Iris 2](#) (French).

1.2.2 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS

1.2.2.1 Eco-driving

	Federal.
General information	The measure on eco-driving corresponds to the application of directive 2003/59/EC, on the initial qualification and periodic training of drivers of driver licence categories C (trucks) and D (buses). The latter has been transposed by a Royal Decree of 4 May 2007. It consists in the inclusion of optimisation of fuel consumption in the list of subjects of the qualification tests and periodic training for the Certificate of Professional Competence (CPC).
Type of policy instruments	Regulatory.
Objectives	
Target groups	Truck drivers and bus drivers. Freight transport and passenger public transport.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Truck drivers and bus drivers who obtained their (driver) license before September 2009, should no later than September 2016 follow 35 lessons (35 credits) on eco-driving. Truck drivers and bus drivers who obtained their (driver) license after September 2009 had to follow 35 lessons on eco-driving at the earliest by 2014. The training modules of the training centres have to be recognized by the Federal Public Service Mobility and Transport. A failure to follow the lessons means that the (driver) license will not be renewed.
Implementation network	The Federal Public Service Mobility and Transport. FPS Mobility and Transport recognizes the training modules of the training centres.
Outcome	The impact of training is a 5% to 7% savings on energy consumption of trucks and buses. The effect is reduced to 1% because only 40% of drivers were concerned by 2012; 60% of traffic on highways use cruise control

	(no effect) and foreign drivers are not concerned. It is estimated that the federal policy of promoting ecodriving will reduce CO ₂ emissions by 40 kt CO ₂ -eq. In 2020.
--	---

Legal reference. [4 May 2007 - \[Royal Decree on driving licenses, the skills and the training of drivers of vehicles in categories C1, C1 + E, C, C + E, D1, D1 + E, D and D + E\] <Inscriptions replaced by KB 2011-04-28 / 01, art. 85 009 Effective date: 01-05-2013>](#)

VITO & ECONOTEC (2015)

1.2.2.2 Energy savings in the public transport sector in Wallonia

	Walloon Region.
General information	On 18 November 2013, the Walloon Government renewed the public service contract with the Walloon Regional Transport Company SRWT (“Société Régionale Wallonne du Transport”) and the Public Transport Companies (TEC). The transport company SRWT commits itself to further modernize its fleet in order to improve the energy efficiency of its vehicles and to decrease their emissions of greenhouse gases (GHG) and other pollutants. The Walloon Region Transport Company also has to improve interconnectivity and interoperability of tickets; and promote car-sharing systems such as CAMBIO. TEC have to participate in the promotion of bicycle use; develop and monitor mobility plans; assist and advise the Walloon Region in matters of regional mobility strategy, collaborate with other Belgian transport companies; and represent the sector in other national and international public transport organisations. Outside the public service contract with SRWT - TEC, the Walloon Region intends to promote public transport by encouraging telework for some of its officials and by promoting the use of rail passenger transport.
Type of policy instruments	Regulatory (public service contract). Vehicle efficiency. Modal shift.
Objectives	The objectives for SRWT-TEC are 1.9 GWh final energy savings by 2020 through improved vehicle performance of the SRWT-TEC fleet. The other objectives are 4.5 GWh final energy savings by 2020 via car sharing schemes and improved interconnectivity; 216 GWh final energy savings by 2020 through promotion of public transport; and 0.17 GWh final energy savings through the promotion of telework for certain civil servants of Wallonia.
Target groups	All users of public transport in the Walloon region. Civil servants (“officials”) of the Walloon Region.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	A public service contract between on the one hand the Prime Minister of the Walloon Government; the Minister of the Environment, Spatial Planning and Mobility; the Minister of Budget, Finance, Employment, Training, Sport and Airport policy; and on the other hand the Walloon Regional Transport Company (SRWT). The Walloon Regional Transport Company (SRWT) is a legal entity of public law. Its competences are described in more detail in D1.1 Governance framework of Belgium. TEC are associations of public law whose acts are deemed commercial.
Implementation network	The Walloon Regional Transport Company (SRWT). The five (5) Walloon Public Transport Companies, abbreviated TEC.
Outcome	There are (obviously) only results available for the previous management contract, namely final energy savings of about 6 GWh in 2012 as reported in the NEEAP

Link to [Walloon Regional Transport Company](#) (SRWT)

Link to TEC www.infotec.be

The Management contract 2013-2017 between Wallonia and TEC can be downloaded [here](#) (in French)

Link to car sharing scheme CAMBO www.cambio.be

1.2.2.3 Company Transport Plan (“bedrijfsvervoerplan BVP”) (“Plan de déplacements entreprises PDE”)

	Brussels-Capital Region.
General information	In force since 2004. Amended 30 June 2011. Since 2004, (private or public) companies with more than 200 employees on a single site are required to develop a “Company Transport Plan”, to promote more sustainable modes of transport and to improve air quality. In 2011, the threshold was lowered to 100 employees and certain measures were made mandatory, such as bicycle parking facilities for employees and visitors, a multimodal access map, awareness-raising campaigns, promotion of public transport, the choice of vehicles with a higher Ecoscore, and an action plan in the event of pollution spikes. Some 600 companies fall under the obligation, representing one-third of all employment in Brussels.
Type of policy instruments	Regulatory. Modal shift.
Objectives	The aim of the Company Transport Plan is twofold: 1) to reduce the environmental impact of the traffic generated by a company in Brussels (improvement of air quality) and 2) to reduce traffic and congestion on the roads in the Brussels-Capital Region (improving mobility). This means that a company has to take actions to encourage a shift from motorized trips to more sustainable transport modes (modal shift).
Target groups	Some 294,000 employees working in the Brussels-Capital Region. Each institution of private and public law with more than 100 employees in one and the same location in the Brussels-Capital Region. Private companies, government departments or other regional or local authorities, etc.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Each company in the region must submit a plan with the following components: general information about the company (address, contact person., etc.); a diagnosis of how the company currently deals with mobility; and a concrete action plan (including the obligatory measures) and also specifying the objectives to be achieved. Every three years, the diagnosis has to be re-done and the action plan has to be reviewed and updated. This information has to be sent through the use of the appropriate electronic form (“Irsibox”) to Brussels Environment. The companies have updated their plans in 2014, the next update is expected in 2017.
Implementation network	Brussels Environment is responsible for the overall administrative and methodological support in connection with the implementation of the Company Transport Plan. The portal website of Brussels Environment contains all legal documents and practical information to develop a Company Transport Plan. Brussels Environment also regularly issues a newsletter related to the Company Transport Plans at its portal website. Brussels Mobility, Policy Directorate (see D1.1 for a complete description of its responsibilities). Brussels Mobility is the link between the companies and the institutions responsible for car sharing, public

	transport and cycling, and also the social partners. Brussels Mobility is not directly involved in the Company Transport Plans, but indirectly through its policies, e.g. information and awareness campaigns.
Outcome	In the 2004-2011 period 270 Company Transport Plans were submitted, related to 233,000 employees. The proportion of car use for home-work travel fell from 45% in 2004 to 27% in 2011. Currently, the number of Company Transport Plans is 585, related to 294,000 employees, or 42% of the total number of employees working in the Brussels-Capital region. A very detailed analysis can be downloaded at the Brussels Environment portal website (in Dutch or French only).

Legal references [2 MAY 2013 - Ordinance amending the Brussels Code Air, Climate and Energy Management](#) Title 2; chapter 1, pages 20 - 29. [7 APRIL 2011 - Decree of the Brussels Capital Region concerning the transport plans](#)

Link to Brussels Environment Company Transport Plan [bedrijfsvervoerplannen](#)

Link to Brussels Mobility Company Transport plan [bedrijfsvervoerplan](#)

Link to electronic form IRISbox [irisbox.irisnet.be](#)

The evaluation report Balans 2011: Bedrijfsvervoerplannen can be downloaded [here](#) (Dutch) or [here](#) (French)

1.2.3 FINANCIAL POLICY INSTRUMENTS

1.2.3.1 Tax deduction for environmentally friendly private cars

	Federal.
General information	<p>From 1 January 2005 to 30 June 2007 a tax deduction of 3% of the purchase price of cars with CO₂ emissions less than 115 g/km; and 15% (with a maximum of 3,280 EUR) of the purchase price of cars with a CO₂ emission less than 105 g/km. From July 2007 to 2012 the tax reduction was replaced by an immediate discount of the invoice, for the same amounts. Since 2007, a tax reduction of 15 EUR for new diesel cars equipped with a particulate filter, a CO₂ emission of less than 130 g/km and particulate emission of less than 0,005 g/km. From 2010 to 2012, a 30% tax reduction of the purchase price of electric vehicles (with a price ceiling of 9,190 EUR) and 40 % tax deduction of the purchase price or an electricity reload terminal (with a price ceiling of 250 EUR).</p> <p>In 2014 (i.e. tax year or assessment year 2015, income year 2014), there was still a federal tax credit for purchases (in 2014) of new motorcycles, tricycles and quadricycles, exclusively powered by an electric motor and suitable for the transport of two persons at least. The tax credit amounted to 15% of the purchase price with a maximum of 4,940 euro for quadricycles and 3,010 euro for motorcycles or tricycles. The tax credit for electric cars had already been abolished in 2013 (i.e. the year in which the expenses were paid or income year 2013; tax year 2014).</p>
Type of policy instruments	Economic – Fiscal / Financial incentives.
Objectives	No longer relevant.
Target groups	Everyone who pays Belgian personal income tax and purchased a private car in the period 2007-2012; or an electric motorcycle, tricycle or quadricycle in 2013 and 2014.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	<p>Belgian Law on Personal Income Tax (PIT).</p> <p>No longer relevant. The tax credit for electric vehicles remains a federal competence, but was abolished by the Federal government. The regions therefore have not taken over this policy instrument. However, the</p>

	regions have changed or intend to change the various traffic taxes for which they are responsible (e.g. vehicle registration tax).
Implementation network	Federal Public Service (FPS) Finance. (see D1.1 Governance framework in Belgium)
Outcome	See VITO & ECONOTEC (2015) , p. 61 for the effect on CO ₂ emission reductions.

Legal reference. No longer relevant.

[VITO & ECONOTEC \(2015\)](#)

1.2.3.2 Free public (rail) transport for commuters

	Federal.
General information	<p>Since 2004, all federal civil servants benefit from free public transport to and from work. This system of free commuting by federal employees was permanently extended by a Royal Decree of 3 May 2007.</p> <p>In 2005, the Federal government introduced the 80/20 system for private sector employees. In this system, if 80% of the train subscription is paid by the private sector employer and a contract has been signed between the employer and the national railway company NMBS/SNCB, the Federal government pays the remaining 20%. In that case, the home work travel is free for the private sector commuter. In 2008, the Federal government prolonged the 80/20 system for private employees until 2012. In 2013, this was again prolonged for the 2013-2014 period.</p>
Type of policy instruments	Regulatory. Financial incentive.
Objectives	Modal shift. Promoting passenger (public) transport by railway.
Target groups	Civil servants of the Federal government. Employees of private companies who commute (home-work travel) by train.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	<p>Management contracts between the Federal government and the national (Belgian) railway operator NMBS/SNCB.</p> <p>A (private) company signs a contract (Third Payer Agreement or TPA) with the national (Belgian) railway company NMBS/SNCB. A TPA is an agreement between the NMBS/SNCB and the employer whereby the employer's contribution to public transportation is directly invoiced to the employer. The (private) employer commits himself to pay 80% of the subscription fee of his employers who commute by train. In return, the Federal government pays the remaining 20%. The commuter thus pays 0%.</p>
Implementation network	The Federal government. The Federal Public Service (FPS) Mobility and Transport has the custody over the Belgian (national) railway company, in particular the NMBS/SNCB. The NMBS/SNCB is a limited liability company of public law.
Outcome	A decrease in car use by about 2.1% between 2005 and 2008 and an increase of 2.0% in other modes of transportation (public transport and cycling). The modal shift is a result of several policy instruments at the federal and regional level. It is estimated that the federal policy of free public transport for commuters will reduce CO ₂ emissions by 80 kt CO ₂ -eq. In 2020.

Legal reference [3 MAY 2007 Royal Decree concerning taking charge of the costs related to public transport for home-work travel of federal employees by the state and by certain federal public institutions..](#)

Legal reference.. [29 JUNE 2008 - Royal Decree approving the management contract between the State and the limited liability company of public law, National Railway Company of Belgium](#)

VITO & ECONOTEC (2015)

Legal reference [29 JUNE 2008 - Royal Decree approving the management contract between the State and the limited liability company of public law, SNCB Holding](#) .

1.2.3.3 Tax deduction for home work travel by bicycle

	Federal.
General information	In place 2001. Employers can pay a cycling allowance for home-work travel of currently 0.22 EUR/km free of taxes and social security contributions. Furthermore, they can provide their employees with a company bicycle. For the employee, this is not counted as a taxable advantage. For the company, 120% of the costs are deductible from taxable profits. This means that there is not only a tax exemption, but actually a subsidy. This is also valid for installations which make it easier for employees to go to work by bike, e.g. bike parking spaces or showers and changing rooms. VAT paid for company bikes is entirely deductible as input tax.
Type of policy instruments	Economic. Fiscal incentives.
Objectives	Modal shift (from car to bicycle).
Target groups	Employees of private companies who commute (home-work travel) by bicycle and who pay Belgian personal income tax (PIT). Private companies (employers) who promote the use of home-work travel by bicycle.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Belgian Law on Personal Income Tax (PIT) or Income Tax Code 2015. Commuting expenses have to be borne by the employee. They are deductible as professional expenses. However, if the expenses are refunded by the employer, they are in principle a taxable income. This can be exempted, e.g. for bicycle commuting (where the allowance is exempted up to 0.22 EUR/km). There is a deduction up to 120% of some expenses incurred to encourage the use of the bicycle by employees for commuting, namely the expenses incurred by the employer to acquire, construct or convert a real estate intended for bicycle storage during working hours, or to put a changing room or sanitation facilities at the staff's disposal. It also concerns expenses incurred by the employer to acquire, maintain or repair bicycles and their accessories.
Implementation network	The Federal government. Each year the Belgian Parliament votes a new Personal Income Tax Code. The Federal Public Service (FPS) Finance is responsible for taxation and collects the Personal Income Tax (PIT).
Outcome	A decrease in car use by about 2.1% between 2005 and 2008 and an increase of 2.0% in other modes of transportation (public transport and cycling). The modal shift is a result of several policy instruments at both the federal and regional levels. It is estimated that the federal policy of promoting the use of bicycles will reduce CO ₂ emissions by 7.5 kt CO ₂ -eq. In 2020. This impact would also be related to The Royal Decree of 13 June 2010, granting compensation for using bicycles to staff members of the federal public administration.

Legal reference. For a mere 220.14 EUR one can buy the complete the Belgian Income Tax Code 2015 in every decent Belgian bookstore.

VITO & ECONOTEC (2015)

1.2.3.4 Blue-bike

	Flemish Region. Belgium.
General information	Since May 2011. Blue-bike is an initiative of Blue-mobility, a collaboration between the national railway operator NBMS/SNCB Holding and FIETS&WERK. Blue-bike makes share bikes available at more than 40 railway stations in Belgium and other mobile points throughout Belgium (Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels). The aim is to provide people who use public transport a solution for the last leg of their trip. They can also use a blue-bike to explore a city or to arrive at a meeting in time. Blue-bike is particularly interesting for those who wish to use a bike for the whole day; or for those who wish to visit one of the smaller cities in Belgium by train.
Type of policy instruments	Economic – subsidies.
Objectives	Promote co-modality.
Target groups	Users of public transport who wish to use a bike for the last leg of their (city) trip.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Membership of Blue-bike is required through online registration. After receipt of payment (10 EUR for one year) Blue-bike sends a Blue-bike (membership) card. One can borrow a Blue-bike either at the “key automaton” (24/24) or at the “bike point” (during business hours). Borrowing a bike is fully automatic with the use of the Blue-bike card without paying or filling out forms. The standard rate for using a Blue-bike is 3 EUR per 24 hours. In several (currently more than 20) cities or municipalities borrowing a Blue-bike is free of charge or just 1 EUR for the first 24 hours. Through Third Party Agreements (TPAs), for each EUR that a Flemish city pays for a 24 hour blue-bike ride, the Flemish government gives a one EUR subsidy to the city; and the user of Blue-bike only has to pay one EUR. Alternatively, if the city pays 2 EUR for each 24 hour blue-bike ride, the Flemish government pays 1 EUR; and the Blue-bike user can borrow a blue-bike free of charge.
Implementation network	Blue-mobility, a collaboration between the national railway operator NBMS/SNCB Holding and FIETS&WERK. FIETS&WERK is an umbrella (membership) organization for bicycle companies in the social economy. FIETS&WERK operates the so-called “bike points” near the Belgian railway stations. Blue-mobility receives support from the Federal Government (Federal Public Service Mobility and Transport) and the Flemish Government (Department of Mobility and Public Works). Blue-mobility also receives support from the National Lottery, the mutual insurance company Ethics and its shareholders; the Flemish public transport company “de Limn”; and the Walloon Regional Transport Company SRWT-TEC.. As an example of the kind of support given, “De Limn” subscribers get 2 free rides with Blue-bike. In 2014, “De Limn” decided to invest 340,000 EUR to install 6 new Blue-bike stations near its stops.
Outcome	No evaluation available.

Legal reference. For a mere 220.14 EUR one can buy the complete Belgian Income Tax Code 2015 in every decent Belgian bookstore.

Link to Blue-bike website www.blue-bike.be/en

Link to Blue-mobility www.blue-mobility.be

Link to FIETSenWERK www.fietsenwerk.be

Link to mobielvlaanderen mobienvlaanderen.be

Link to Blue-bike De Lijn blue-bike

1.2.3.5 Green car registration tax (BIV) (“Groene belasting op de inverkeerstelling”)

	Flemish Region.
General information	<p>On 1 March 2012, the Flemish government reformed the vehicle registration tax (BIV) for natural persons and corporations. The so-called “green registration tax” in Flanders is based on CO₂ emissions as well as exhaust emissions standards, fuel type and age. Previously, the car’s engine power was the only consideration. The Decree of 1 March 2012 also promotes the acquisition of cars running on natural gas (CNG) and LPG. Electric and plug-in hybrid vehicles are exempt from registration tax in Flanders.</p> <p>A simulation tool at the tax portal website of Flanders (“Belastingportaal Vlaanderen”) allows taxpayers to calculate the different traffic taxes in Flanders, including the car registration tax. The tool is also available as an app for iOS or Android.</p>
Type of policy instruments	Economic – Fiscal.
Objectives	<p>Promote the use of more environmentally friendly cars.</p> <p>Improve air quality.</p> <p>Stimulate new and clean technologies.</p>
Target groups	All residents (natural persons and corporations) in Flanders acquiring a new vehicle or a second hand vehicle (which is registered by the new owner for the first time).
Rules and influencing mechanisms	<p>The car registration tax is collected by the Flemish Tax Authority. Since the tax liability for the car registration tax (BIV) "automatically" arises from the registration of the vehicle at the DIV (Department for Registration of Vehicles of the Federal Public Service Mobility and Transport), the Flemish taxpayer automatically receives a tax bill from the Flemish Tax Authority. The tax bill must be paid within two months after receiving the notice of assessment.</p> <p>An exemption of the BIV is granted in some cases, for instance for vehicles exclusively used for the transport of sick or injured persons and (in the case of road vehicles) registered as ambulances</p>
Implementation network	<p>The Flemish Tax Authority, Department collection and regulations.</p> <p>The DIV is the Department for Registration of Vehicles of the Federal Public Service Mobility and Transport.</p>
Outcome	No evaluation available.

Legal reference. [17.02.2012 Decree for the amendment of various provisions of the Code of the taxes equivalent to income taxes concerning the registration tax on the basis of environmental characteristics](#)

Link to the tax portal website [simulatieVerkeersbelasting](#)

Link to Flemish Tax Authority [belastingen.vlaanderen.be](#)

Link to the DIV <http://www.mobilit.belgium.be/nl/wegverkeer/inschrijving/>

1.2.3.6 Ecomalus (éco-malus”)

	Walloon Region.
General information	Since 1 January 2008, the Walloon region applies a CO ₂ -based ecobonus/ecomalus scheme when registering a new vehicle or a second

	<p>hand vehicle which is registered by the new owner for the first time (company cars were initially excluded). The ecobonus and ecomalus system was tightened in 2012. From 1 January 2012, cars emitting less than 81 g CO₂/km received a premium (ecobonus) of 500 EUR to 3,500 EUR. Cars emitting more than 146 g CO₂/km paid a penalty (ecomalus) of up to 2,500 EUR. On 1 January 2014, the Walloon government abolished the ecobonus. From 1 January 2014, the ecomalus also applies to certain company cars.</p> <p>The vehicle registration tax is based on the power of the engine expressed in fiscal horsepower or kilowatts. The ecomalus however is an additional component of the vehicle registration tax. Vehicles that emit more than 146 CO₂/km have to pay a penalty (the ecomalus) that varies from 100 EUR to 2,500 EUR. Owners of vehicles running on LPG can benefit from a reduction of the ecomalus. Large families can also benefit from a reduction.</p>
Type of policy instruments	Economic – Fiscal (tax)
Objectives	To help reduce the emissions of greenhouse gases, especially CO ₂ emissions, in accordance with the Kyoto targets.
Target groups	All residents of Wallonia acquiring a new or second hand vehicle. The tax applies to all types of vehicles (cars, motorcycles, airplanes, airships, etc.), new or used.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	After having registered a new or second hand vehicle at the DIV (Department for Registration of Vehicles of the Federal Public Service Mobility and Transport), the taxpayer will automatically receive an invitation from the Walloon Department of Taxation of Vehicles to pay the registration tax as well as the ecomalus component. In principle, the taxpayer will receive the invitation to pay within two months following the month of registration. The payment deadline is indicated in the document. The registration tax is non-refundable.
Implementation network	The Department of Taxation of Vehicles of the Operational Directorate General (DGO7) of Taxation is responsible for collecting the registration tax, including the ecomalus component. The DIV is the Department for Registration of Vehicles of the Federal Public Service Mobility and Transport.
Outcome	No evaluation available. See also D1.1 Table 8.

Legal reference. [5 MARCH 2008 Decree establishing a ecomalus on CO₂ emissions from vehicles of individuals in the Code of taxes assimilated to income taxes](#)

Link to Walloon vehicle registration tax <http://www.wallonie.be/fr/taxe-de-mise-en-circulation>

Link to the DIV <http://www.mobilit.belgium.be/nl/wegverkeer/inschrijving>

1.2.3.7 BRUXEL'AIR premium (« La prime Bruxell 'air »)

	Brussels-Capital Region.
General information	Since 1 October 2006, the Brussels-Capital Region provides incentives to car owners deregistering their licence plate. The purpose of the premium is to encourage motorists to give up their car in favour of more environmentally friendly modes of travel: public transport, cycling, walking and / or the Cambio car sharing system. Car owners giving up their car and returning their licence plate receive either a one year public

	transport season ticket and a one year car sharing subscription (Cambio Start); or a bicycle bonus and a one year car sharing subscription (Cambio Start) – or a bicycle bonus. Car owners who also have their vehicle scrapped receive either a two year public transport season ticket and a two year car sharing subscription; or a one year public transport season ticket, a two year car sharing subscription and a bicycle bonus; or a two year car sharing subscription and a double bicycle bonus.
Type of policy instruments	Economic – Financial.
Objectives	Modal shift. Encourage motorists to give up their car in favour of more environmentally friendly modes of travel: public transport, cycling, walking and / or the Cambio car sharing system
Target groups	Every resident (natural person) of the Brussels-Capital Region and car-owner who has his car deregistered (and/or scrapped).
Rules and influencing mechanisms	The BRUXEL'AIR premium can only be requested by mail and the application letter has to be addressed to the MIVB/STIB. The appropriate request form is available at the website of brusselair-premie.be ; at the BOOTIKs of the MIVB/STIB; or at the counters of Brussels Environment. Other documents include a copy of the notification of the deregistration by the DIV (Department for Registration of Vehicles), a copy of the original registration, a copy of the id, etc. The MIVB/STIB will shortly thereafter notify whether the application was accepted, incomplete or refused. If the application is accepted, one will receive a letter or letters which one has to send to Cambio (car sharing) to receive the car sharing bonus; and/or to Pro Velo to receive the bicycle bonus. A very detailed description of the procedures is given at the dedicated website brusselair-premie.be .
Implementation network	MIVB/STIB, Distance selling – Bruxel'Air. MIVB/STIB is the transport company that operates the local public transport system in the Brussels-Capital Region. The DIV is the Department for Registration of Vehicles of the Federal Public Service Mobility and Transport. Cambio is the name of the first car-sharing system in Belgium. It is a cooperation of – amongst others – the MIVB/STIB, De Lijn, the Flemish Automobile Association (VAB) and the German car sharing organization with the same name. Pro Velo is a non-profit organization that promotes the use of bicycles as a daily means of transport.
Outcome	No evaluation available.

Legal reference. Not found.

Link to [brusselair-premie](http://www.brusselair-premie.be) www.brusselair-premie.be

Link to Brussels Mobility de-brusselair-premie

Link to MIVB/STIB <http://www.stib-mivb.be>

Link to Cambio carsharing

Link to Pro Velo <http://www.provelo.org/nl>

Link to the DIV <http://www.mobilit.belgium.be/nl/wegverkeer/inschrijving/>

1.2.3.8 Commuter Fund (“Pendelfonds”) and Mobility points (“Provinciale mobiliteitspunten”)

	Flemish Region.
General information	Implemented 30 June 2006. In force 5 February 2007. In 2006, the

	<p>Flemish Region created a Commuter Fund (“Pendelfonds”). The aim is to support companies in achieving a modal shift in work-related journeys. Since 2007, companies and non-profit organisations can obtain a subsidy of maximum 50% of the investment costs during four years for sustainable mobility solutions such as shuttle buses, bicycle infrastructure or promotion of carpooling. The Flemish Region also created provincial mobility points (“provinciale mobiliteitspunten”) in each of the Flemish provinces, to support companies in the development of small mobility plans and to assist companies in preparing proposals for the Commuter Fund.</p>
Type of policy instruments	Economic – Subsidy. Information and education
Objectives	Modal shift.
Target groups	Individual companies; group of companies; local or provincial governments, in collaboration with a private partner; other private organizations or partnerships between private and public organizations.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	<p>The applicant must request a file number via an electronic form. Next the applicant contacts the Provincial Mobility Point in his province. The contact details are in the e-mail the applicant receives after submitting the application form. The Provincial Mobility Point delivers a submission form, which has to be filled out by the applicant. The Mobility Point can assist the applicant and provide further information. Once the application form is complete, the applicant logs in to his online file (the login details are in the e-mail received after requesting the file number). The final submission form and corresponding attachments can subsequently be uploaded.</p> <p>An application is admissible only if it is submitted in time and if the project contains measures that at least meet the following conditions: 1) they were drawn up after consultations at the project level between employers and employees; 2) they must assume a shared responsibility of all partners involved in the project, both organisationally and financially; and 3) they must regularly provide a narrative and financial follow-up, allowing to either steer or stop the project.</p> <p>The grant is paid in three instalments. The first 40% is paid within one month after the submission of proof that the project has started. The project applicant has to provide evidence to the Department of Mobility and Traffic Safety Administration of the Department of Mobility and Public Works. The second instalment of 40% is paid after the decision for further funding by the Flemish Minister responsible for mobility policy. That decision will be made based on the first follow-up report. This report must be submitted no later than 12 months after the start of the project (via the website). The last instalment of 20% is paid after the Flemish minister responsible for mobility policy decides to continue subsidizing the project. The decision is taken based on the latest monitoring report and a comprehensive financial report.</p>
Implementation network	The Provincial Mobility Points are a collaboration between the provinces and the Flemish Region. There is a “mobility point” in each Flemish province. They initiate and facilitate potential projects. They also play a guiding role in the coordination, the elaboration, the implementation and

	<p>the monitoring of the projects.</p> <p>The supervisory committee is composed of a chairman appointed by the Flemish minister responsible for mobility policy; two representatives of the Flemish Government; an equal number of representatives of employers' and workers' organizations in the Social and Economic Council of Flanders (SERV), nominated by the SERV and appointed by the Flemish minister responsible for mobility policy; and a representation of the Policy Division of the Department of Mobility and Road Transport and Public Works (Flemish Ministry of Mobility and Public Works), appointed by the Secretary-General of the Department. The Steering Committee is established at the office of the SERV. All correspondence with the Supervisory Committee has to be sent to that address.</p>
Outcome	No evaluation available.

Legal reference. the [Decree of June 30, 2006 containing provisions to accompany the adaptation of the 2006 budget](#) (Articles 51 to 62). the [Decree of the Flemish Government of November 24](#)

Link to pendelfonds www.pendelfonds.be

Link to SERV supervisory committee <http://www.serv.be/pendelfonds>

1.2.4 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS

1.2.4.1 CO₂ car guide and the “energy guzzlers” website.

	Federal.
General information	<p>From 2006 to 2012, the Federal government published the annual publication “CO₂ car guide”. The guide provided objective information on and allowed comparisons of all car models available on the Belgian market with respect to CO₂ emissions, fuel type, fuel consumption and existing tax incentives. The last guide was published in 2012 and has been replaced by a web application called “energy guzzlers” since 2013. The website allows visitors to quickly find the CO₂-emissions, the CO₂-category, and the fuel consumption or the power in kW of all new models available on the market. The website provides several search functions (by make/model, car type, fuel type, max. CO₂-emission,) or simply lists the 20 ‘best choices’.</p>
Type of policy instruments	Information and Education
Objectives	See “energy guzzlers”
Target groups	Potential buyers in Belgium of new cars. Passenger road transport.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Awareness raising
Implementation network	The Federal Public Service Health, Food chain Safety and Environment; Directorate-general for Environment (DG5) - Climate Change Section, department of Product Management and Chemicals and the thematic service “climate change” developed the website and maintain it.
Outcome	No evaluation available

Legal reference. Not found.

Link to the website www.energievreters.be (Dutch) or www.energivores.be (French)

VITO & ECONOTEC (2015)

1.2.4.2 Ecoscore

	Flemish Region. Brussels-Capital Region. Walloon Region.
--	--

General information	A website (www.ecoscore.be) provides information on the energy efficiency and environmental features of cars to encourage consumers and companies to choose an energy-efficient and eco-friendly car. The site helps find and compare the “ecoscore” of a vehicle. The ecoscore evaluates the environmental performance of a vehicle by taking into account the most important environmental impact factors. Those factors are the emissions of greenhouse gases (global warming); the emissions of pollutants (e.g. particulate matter, nitrogen oxides) that have a direct negative impact on human health and on ecosystems; and noise. The ecoscore is a number between 0 and 100. The closer to 100, the more eco-friendly.
Type of policy instruments	Information and Education
Objectives	The website is meant to inform end users on the environmental performance of all passenger cars available on the Belgian market (new and used).
Target groups	Potential buyers in Belgium of new and second hand cars, motorcycles, vans, trucks, etc. Passenger and freight road transport.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	Ecoscore was developed by Vito , the VUB and ULB . More information about the methodology that underlies the Ecoscore, can be found in their research report, that can be downloaded in full.
Implementation network	The website is sponsored by the Environment, Nature and Energy (LNE) Department; the Walloon Air and Climate Agency (AWAC) and Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM). It is maintained by VITO and VUB/ULB. The Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO). VITO is a research centre that performs contract research and develops products and processes in the fields of energy, environment and materials, both for the public sector and the private sector. ULB is the Free University of Brussels, French-speaking and VUB Dutch-speaking. The data are obtained from the Department for Registration of Vehicles (DIV) of the Federal Public Service Mobility and Transport; the Belgian Federation of Automobile and Cycle Industries FEBIAC and from documented studies. The information on emissions is based on the information provided by the importers, but not all importers have given the information.
Outcome	A report (VUB, Clean Vehicles Europe versus ECOSCORE, 2011) that evaluates the value of the Ecoscore website in the framework of the new European Clean Vehicle Portal (CVP) can be downloaded here .

The research report on the ecoscore can be downloaded [here](#)

Link to www.ecoscore.be

Link to LNE ecoscore ecoscore-en-euronormen/ecoscore

1.2.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

1.2.5.1 Registration and Ticket System with on-Board computer (ReTiBo)

	Flemish Region. Brussels-Capital Region. Walloon Region.
General information	Start 2011. End 2016. ReTiBo stands for “Registration and Ticket System with ON-board computer. As a means to stimulate a more efficient and sustainable public transportation system, the four Belgian transport

	operators (De Lijn, MIVB/STIB and TEC, NMBS/SNCB) agreed to integrate their registration, ticketing and board computer systems.
Type of policy instruments	Research and Development.
Objectives	Travel efficiency. ReTiBo makes it possible to chart travel streams in an objective way, and to better coordinate supply and demand.
Target groups	All users of public transport in Flanders, Brussels and Wallonia. Passenger public transport.
Rules and influencing mechanisms	<p>The research project implementation is divided into 2 phases. The first phase was completed and the new system is gradually being installed. In a second phase (during 2016), the old system shall be completely removed.</p> <p>The ReTiBo on-board computer collects passenger data (boarding location, time and trip number) and forwards it to the backend reporting systems of the public transport operators. The driver can still create magnetic tickets using the old system. In a pilot project it was shown that the on-board computer coupled to a radio system may affect traffic lights based on the vehicle position (without the need of ground loops). The following software releases will be implemented in 2015 and 2016. The driver will dynamically be kept informed of delays, roadblocks, detours etc. The on-board computer will visualize the ride (such as on a GPS system). The computer continuously displays the location of the vehicle so that passengers receive timely and accurate information on the stop signs.</p>
Implementation network	<p>Federal Government, all three Regional Governments and all public transport operators (De Lijn, TEC, MIVB/STIB, NMBS/SNCB).</p> <p>The consortium THV Prodata Systems - Prodata Mobility Systems - Fabricom GDF Suez.</p> <p>For "De Lijn" the temporary Trading Association (THD) Profa was commissioned to assist in the installation of equipment for the MOBIB card in the vehicles of "De Lijn", the vending machines, the development of the accompanying software and the necessary training of the personnel. It involves 4,500 on-board computers; 4,500 touch screens for the drivers; 12,000 contactless validators (card readers) for the passengers and 65 vending machines. Additionally, all travellers using "De Lijn" must get a new MOBIB card.</p>
Outcome	No evaluation available

Eurotransportmagazine 30.08.2011 [prodata-mobility-systems-wins-the-de-lijn-retibo-97-million-euro-contract](#)

1.2.6 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR IN #COUNTRY#

Type of instrument		Instrument	Ojbjective	Target group	Rules & Influencing mechanism	Implementation network
Planning	Fla	Mobility Plan expected 2016	reduce / avoid travel	not yet implemented	not yet implemented	not yet implemented
Planning	Wal	Integrated approach - in progress	reduce / avoid travel	Passenger - public	not yet implemented	not yet implemented
Planning	Bru	Plan Iris 2	reduce / avoid travel - reduce car traffic by 20% by 2018 compared to 2001	Passenger - car	Aid in implementation	Brussels Mobility. Policy Directorate.
Regulatory	FBW	Ecodriving	travel efficiency	Passenger – public road vehicles Freight - trucks	Sanction	The Federal Public Service Mobility and Transport.
Regulatory	Wal	Management contract with regional transport company SRWT	vehicle efficiency + modal shift. Final energy savings by 2020 around 6 GWh	Passenger - public	Sanction	The Walloon Regional Transport Company (SRWT). The five (5) Walloon Public Transport Companies, abbreviated TEC.
Regulatory	Bru	Company Transport Plan	modal shift	Passenger - car - commuters	Sanction	Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM). Brussels Mobility, Policy Directorate
Regulatory	Bem	Tax deduction for environmentally friendly cars	Vehicle efficiency	Passenger car	Incentve - fiscal	Federal government. Federal Public Service (FPS) Finance.
Economic	Bel	Free transport for commuters	travel efficiency	Commuters	Incentive - financial	The Federal government. The Federal Public Service (FPS) Mobility and Transport. The Belgian (national) railway company, in particular the NMBS/SNCB.
Economic	Bel	Tax deduction for home-work travel by bicycle	travel efficiency	Commuters	Incentive - financial	Federal Government Federal Public Service Finance
Economic	Bel + Fla	Blue-bike	travel efficiency	Passenger - public - commuters	Aid in implementation	Flemish and federal government, the National Lottery, Ethias and its shareholders NMBS (Belgian Rail), de Lijn (public transport in Flanders), SRWT/TEC (public transport in Wallonia) and FIETSenWERK.
Economic	Fla	Green car registration tax	vehicle efficiency	Passenger - car	Incentive - fiscal	The Flemish Tax Authority, Department collection and regulations. The DIV is the Department for Registration of Vehicles of the Federal Public Service Mobility and Transport
Economic	Wal	Eco-malus	vehicle efficiency	Passenger - car	Incentive - fiscal	The Department of Taxation of Vehicles of the Operational Directorate General (DGO7) of Taxation. The DIV is the Department for Registration of Vehicles of the Federal Public Service Mobility and Transport.
Economic	Bru	Bruxell'air bonus	travel efficiency	Passenger - car - car owners	Incentive - financial	MIVB/STIB, Distance selling. DIV, the Department for Registration of Vehicles of the Federal Public Service Mobility and Transport. Cambio, car-sharing system. ProVelo, non-profit organisation.

Economic	Fla	Commuter Fund	travel efficiency	Passenger - car - commuters	Incentive - subsidies	The Provincial Mobility Points , a collaboration between the provinces and the Flemish Region. The Social and Economic Council of Flanders (SERV). The Policy Division of the Department of Mobility and Road Transport and Public Works
Dissemination - Informative	Bel	CO ₂ car guide & energy guzzlers website	vehicle efficiency	Passenger - car	Awareness raising	Federal Public Service Health, Food chain Safety and Environment Directorate-general for Environment (DG5) - Climate Change Section + Department of Product Policy and Chemical Substances.
Dissemination - Informative	Fla Wal Bru	Eco-score	vehicle efficiency	Passenger - car	Awareness raising	the Environment, Nature and Energy (LNE) Department; the Walloon Air and Climate Agency (AWAC) and Brussels Environment (IBGE/BIM). Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO). Free University of Brussels (BUV). The Department for Registration of Vehicles (DIV)
R&D	Bel Fla Wal Bru	ReTiBo	travel efficiency	Passenger – public road and rail transport	Aid in implementation	Federal Government, all three Regional Governments and all public transport operators (De Lijn, TEC, MIVB/STIB, NMBS/SNCB). The consortium THV Prodata Systems - Prodata Mobility Systems - Fabricom GDF Suez.

2. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE REGIONAL / LOCAL LEVEL

2.1 CASE STUDY: THE CITY OF GHENT

2.1.1 GHENT

The City of Ghent in the Flemish Region has 251,133 inhabitants, 56 squares and 74 parks, 35 hotels and 450 restaurants, 650 pubs, 10 museums and 10 theatres, 15 monasteries and abbeys, 300 schools, 100 km roads, 380 km bicycle paths, and last but not least, a Port of Ghent with 17,500 ships, 47.7 million ton goods transferred and 60,000 workers. Ghent also has a large presence of industrial companies covered by the European Emission Trading system (ETS).

To European standards Ghent is a small city. This has to be seen in the wider context of a very urbanized Flemish landscape of metropolitan areas and regional urbanized areas. The city centre is a fairly dense built area, mostly composed of the historic centre, surrounded by a problematic 19th century blue collar neighbourhood. It is connected to international railways, national and European motorways, and to the sea by a river and canal.

The City of Ghent is a frontrunner in addressing environmental issues. In 2008 it produced its first Local Climate Plan (2008-2010) setting out 105 actions. In January 2009 the City of Ghent was the first Flemish city to sign the Covenant of Mayors (CoM). In the current Climate Plan 2014-2019, the City of Ghent makes the following (short-term) commitments:

- A reduction of CO₂ emissions of 20% in 2019 compared to reference year 2007 (1,274 ktonnes CO₂ emissions in 2019);
- A reduction of energy consumption of 20% in 2019 compared to reference year 2007 (energy consumption of 5,409 GWh in 2019);
- A share of 15% of domestic energy demand is locally produced by renewable energy sources (RES) in 2019;
- An annual reduction of 3% of energy consumption in city buildings and public lighting (15% over the entire legislature) compared to consumption in 2012.

The long-term commitment is to become a *climate neutral* city by 2050.

2.1.2 ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY / ACTION

2.1.2.1 RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS

Ghent has about 115,000 households. More than half of them (53%) are home-owners. The other households live in a private rented house (34%), or they rent from either a social housing company or from the Belgium public social welfare centre (OCMW) (13%). Almost two thirds (64%) of the households live in single family dwellings, the remaining third (36%) in either multi-family dwellings (mainly apartments, and to a lesser extent “studios”), student housing (Ghent has the largest proportion of higher education students in Flanders) or other non-specified residences. 44% of the dwellings are occupied by single person households. 70% of private rented housing is rented out by Senior Citizens.

The energy efficiency policies and measures for residential buildings make a distinction between existing dwellings and new-build dwellings.

2.1.2.1.1 Existing dwellings.

For existing buildings the aim is to at least double the refurbishment rate in Ghent from 1,500 refurbishments to 3,500 refurbishments per year. The retrofits should conform to very strict energy performance levels:

- The „new standard“ for renovations. At least 80% of the retrofits should achieve an annual energy consumption level of 70 kWh/m², which is set as a the so-called „new standard“ for refurbishments. This can be achieved by installing sufficient roof, façade and floor insulation where feasible, replacing inefficient glazing with high-efficiency glazing, and installing an energy efficient heating system;
- The „new future standard“ for renovations. The remaining 20% should achieve an annual consumption level of 30 kWh/m², which should become the so-called „new future standard“ for refurbishments. This can be achieved by more profound measures, including a higher level of insulation and the use of renewable energy.

The major theme in the Ghent Climate Plan is to lower or remove the thresholds („barriers“) to the implementation of the above mentioned „standards“. The Ghent Climate Plan strategy to that end addresses the *motivations* of families to invest in homes that are more energy efficient and less dependent on fossil fuels. The action plan for existing residential dwellings is thus based on three (3) actions:

- **Action 1: Inspiring the households** in Ghent to implement a phased refurbishment of their residence to 70kWh/m² or possibly even 30 kWh/m². The City of Ghent wishes to instil a passion amongst its Citizens for energy-saving refurbishments through *raising awareness, building knowledge, and setting good examples*. Policy instruments include *„developing and providing online information on energy-efficient refurbishments via websites“*; *„developing an online-decision tree to obtain a tailored to-do list“*; an *„awareness campaign called „the New Standard“*; a *„complete package offered by the non-profit organization REGent to guide vulnerable households“*; and *„the development of an interactive digital platform on energy efficient construction and housing in Ghent“*;
- **Action 2: Making it easy** for the households to implement the refurbishments. The City of Ghent offers support both before and during the execution of the works. The Citizens of Ghent can, upon request, obtain tailored (technical) advice and guidance for drawing up specifications, searching and contacting contractors, comparing quotations, organizing as well as inspecting the works. Policy instruments are various *services offered by the City of Ghent itself*. These services include advice given at the „Woonwinkel (a housing centre), the non-profit organisation REGent or at the „Milieuadvieswinkel“ (environmental advice centre), but also advice delivered „at the doorstep“. This action is inspired by the fact that research has shown that financial incentives alone are not sufficient to activate people.
- **Action 3: Making the refurbishments affordable** for the households. Policy instruments such as *premiums and cheap loans* should ensure that deep retrofits are affordable for every resident of Ghent.

2.1.2.1.2 New-build dwellings.

The plan makes a distinction between:

- Urban development projects that only involve the local authorities, i.e. the City of Ghent, the public social welfare centre (OCMW) and urban development company „sogent“. As land

owners these authorities can impose the strict non-Zero Energy Building (nZEB) standard, that supersedes the current building standard set by the Flemish Government (which will not come into full force until 2021);

- Large urban development projects on land owned by Gent, the OCMW and sogent, but developed via a public-private partnership (PPP). For these projects, the „Sustainability Meter“ is used as a guide. This policy instrument allows the public authorities to select private project developers who pledge to adhere to the strict sustainability standards set by the City of Ghent, including climate neutrality.
- Urban development projects on land not owned by the City of Ghent. In this case , the City of Ghent can only hope that the private developers who are or were also involved in the above mentioned projects will be inspired and motivated by the example set by the City of Ghent. (role model).

2.1.2.2 BUILDINGS IN THE TERTIARY SECTOR

The City of Ghent focuses on SMEs, companies and services not covered by an agreement with a higher policy level. Higher policy levels include the European ETS system, but also the Energy Policy Agreement (EPA) with the Flemish government. The energy policy agreement (EPA) seeks to push energy-intensive companies to become and remain leaders in the field of energy efficiency, without undermining their competitiveness. Energy policy agreements are agreements between sectors and the Flemish government, which individual companies with an energy consumption greater than 1 PJ can join.

The City of Ghent wishes to create a local framework to structurally anchor “sustainability” in the operations of the Ghent enterprises. For entrepreneurs it is essential that the range of policies and measures is harmonized among the various levels of government, and that they remain stable for an extended period of time. This will decrease uncertainty and stimulate sustainable investments. The actions of the entrepreneurs also need to reinforce each other. The climate workgroup “Energy efficiency in industry” is therefore the ideal soundboard for evaluating and refining the approaches suggested by the City of Ghent. The climate workgroup was founded in 2009 within the Ghent Climate Alliance. The members represent various regional economic players, amongst others, the Department of Economy of the City of Ghent, the Ghent Port Company, the Flemish Enterprise Agency, the Flemish employers organizations VOKA and Unizo, the consultation platform for energy experts OVED, the service company for the realization of a sustainable waste and materials management IVAGO, the provincial development corporation POM East Flanders, the Flemish Institute for Technology and Research VITO, the grid manager Eandis, workers associations and individual companies.

The Ghent approach is based on an integrated package of harmonized policy instruments:

- coaching regarding energy management for individual (existing) companies through tailored guidance in the execution of energy efficiency measures and renewable energy investments, the so-called unburdening of companies;
- rendering new business areas more sustainable via the issuance policy;
- rendering existing business areas more sustainable, in conjunction with the business area associations;
- stimulating the ESCO market;
- stimulating sustainable refurbishments of commercial buildings;
- stimulating heat exchange among companies and/or residential areas;

- setting up test beds, such as living lab experiments;
- networks, communication, and awareness raising via 'Ghent Climate City'

2.1.2.3 MOBILITY

The City of Ghent makes two clear commitments:

- to decrease the number of vehicle kilometres;
- to decrease the share of motorized transport while increasing the shares of more environmentally friendly transport modes.

To decrease the number of vehicle kilometres, the following targets are set:

- by 2030: a reduction of vehicle-kilometres by 9.5% for passenger transport and 5.35% for heavy goods freight transport;
- by 2050 (additionally compared to 2030): a reduction of vehicle-kilometres by 3.7% for passenger transport and 2.14% for heavy goods freight transport.

To realize a model shift, the City has to be designed in such a way that that it offers more people more options for clean modes of transportation, such as public transportation, bicycles, and travelling on foot.

To achieve the above mentioned commitments, as well as to reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions from transport, the mobility policy of the City of Ghent focuses on the following actions:

- **Action 1. Lowering the number of required trips.** This can be done by ensuring proximity. New urban developments should bring functions together ("economy of proximity") and interconnect them ("functional interconnectivity"), in such a way that these functions can be combined in a single trip. Other ways to limit trips may include the allocation of enrolments in childcare centres and schools whereby distances from and to home are taken into account;
- **Action 2. Enhancing steps, stairs, and public transportation.** The shift toward more sustainable modes such as public transportation, cycling or walking can be accomplished by introducing a sustainable parking policy, clever densification, stimulating Park & Rides (P&Rs), introducing a regional public transportation network focusing on „tramification“, an integral bicycle policy (e.g. investing in bicycle infrastructure and bicycle parking facilities), and setting up a sustainable distribution centre;
- **Action 3. Greening modes of transportation.** The first two actions focus on reducing trips and model shift. The third and last action aims to stimulate the use of electric vehicles and CNG powered vehicles. Policy instruments and measures include premiums, tax reductions at CNG pumps and the development of charging infrastructure for electric vehicles and CNG filling options for CNG powered cars.

2.1.3 ENERGY EFFICIENCY INSTRUMENTS / MEASURES PER SECTOR

2.1.3.1 BUILDINGS

The City of Ghent provides "premiums" (subsidies) and cheap loans to make the deep retrofits of existing dwelling "affordable" for its citizens.

Financial incentives for the refurbishment of existing dwellings.

The City of Ghent provides energy premiums, in addition to the existing energy subsidies of the Flemish Government. The motivation is that the City of Ghent requires higher energy performance levels for renovated dwellings than those currently implied by the policies of the Flemish Region.

The energy premiums are subsidies for investments in attic / roof insulation, exterior wall insulation, floor insulation, high-efficiency glazing, heat pumps, and low temperature heating systems. There is also a premium for OCMW apprenticeships.

The amount of the premium depends on the net taxable income of the applicant.

- Lower income households, the so-called “vulnerable families”, have access to a premium of maximum 4600 EUR for all types of investments;
- Medium-income households have – depending on their income – access to a premium of maximum 1,500 EUR or maximum 2,500 Euros for investment in energy-efficiency improvements, also for all types of investments;
- Higher income households only have access to a premium of maximum 1,000 EUR, and only for attic or roof insulation.

Figure 1 Premiums for refurbishments of existing dwellings

Joint net taxable income of the applicant (and possible partner) lower than or equal to		Maximum total premium sum	Type of works
Singles (without dependant)	Single with dependant/cohabitants/ married couples		
€28,941.88 + 1,504 per dependant + index Or an owner renting out his property to a Social Rental Housing Agency (SRHA)		€4600	Under roof/roof insulation Roof refurbishment Façade insulation Floor insulation Low-emission glass Heat pump Floor heating Apprenticeships OCMW ²³
€34,338 + index	€45,128 + 3,241.49 per dependant (as of 2nd dependant for singles) + index	€2500	Under roof/roof insulation Façade insulation Floor insulation Low-emission glass Heat pump Floor heating
€40,518.64 +index	€57,883.77 + 3,241.49 per dependant (as of 2nd dependant for singles) + index	€1500	Under roof/roof insulation Façade insulation Floor insulation Low-emission glass Heat pump Floor heating
Higher taxable income or multiple properties		€1000	Under roof/roof insulation
social housing companies, co-ownership associations and certified local associations		€1000	Under roof/roof insulation

The City of Ghent also provides cheap loans via REGent. REGent is an arm’s-length agency incorporated as a non-profit organisation. The “Fund to Reduce the Overall Cost of Energy” or FROCE aims to remove the barrier where in particular lower income households cannot advance the money for the refurbishment of their dwelling. FROCE is a rolling fund. The loan is a (pre-)financing of investments in energy efficiency improvements. The credit provision works very smoothly, in part because of the close cooperation with the public social welfare centre OCMW and because of the personal guidance the applicants receive from REGent.

2.1.3.2 MOBILITY

Investments for promoting the use of bicycles

The City of Ghent invests heavily in facilitating a modal shift from car to bicycle. Measures include:

- Investing in bicycle infrastructure. There is a continued but intensified development of the bicycle route network in Ghent. Examples are the layout of cycling infrastructure and a bicycle underpass at the „Gasmeterlaan/Nieuwevaart“, a bicycle tunnel under the railroad at „Dampoortstation“, bicycle connections at the „Franse vaart“, „Parkbos“ bridges and an underpass at the „Rozemarijn“ bridge;
- Home of the Bicycle („Huis van de Fiets“). The City of Ghent invests in the reorganization and housing of various bicycle service providers for the purpose of providing optimal services to cyclists;
- Investing in bicycle parking facilities. The City of Ghent invests significantly in all manners of bicycle parking facilities, including the expansion of the underground bicycle parking facility at „Gent-Sint-Pieters“ station from 6,800 to 10,000 spaces, a new bicycle parking facility at the „Waalse Krook“, and bicycle parking spaces in the streets of Ghent.

2.1.4 INTERACTION BETWEEN NATIONAL AND LOCAL POLICIES:

Since the fifth State Reform of 2001 the Regions in Belgium (and not the Federal Level) are responsible for the organisation of local and provincial government. The current Flemish Government is still debating a shift of competences between the different government levels, a reform of municipal finances and the promotion of voluntary mergers between municipalities. In other words, the Flemish Region is elaborating its own „internal state reform“. At present, the municipalities are responsible for matters delegated to them by the higher state levels and for all matters *with a municipal interest*. The local authorities have an extensive (open) list of competences such as town planning, education, culture and sports (museums, infrastructure), environmental issues, infrastructure (roads), tourism, health, social welfare, etc. [Ceuninck & Reynert, 2011, p. 1023]. Flemish municipalities have financial autonomy, and can tax anything they want, as long as the local councils agree with the tax [id., ibid., p. 1029].

In the Flemish Region, the Covenant of Mayors (CoM) is to a certain extent the successor of the so-called „Covenant“, an agreement between the Flemish Government and the Association of Flemish Cities and Municipalities (VVSG). If municipalities undertake environmental actions (encompassing energy, mobility water, waste, sustainable procurement, etc.) the Flemish Region subsidizes them. There was no legal obligation for municipalities to have an energy plan, but some of them had one, „often in implementation of the above mentioned ‘environmental covenant’“ [VVSG, 2012, p. 3]. After more than 20 years, the so-called „Covenants“ were discontinued in 2014.

Some of the initial perceptions of the CoM by Flemish mayors in general were that the „central“, i.e. Regional or Flemish Government should provide more technical support for the baseline emission inventories (BEI) and/or SEAP. Data often have to come from the Regional Agencies. The Flemish Government decided to provide this support for the cities that signed the covenant of mayors. The Flemish Institute for Technological Research (VITO) standardized the method for the drafting of a CO₂ monitor and as of 2014 ensures the annual supply of data available at the Flemish level. The Ghent CO₂ monitor for the years 2007 and 2009 was thus recalculated according to the VITO method.

In a recent study, VITO revealed that when funding is concerned, the Flemish companion cities of Ghent (Antwerp, Genk, Hasselt, Leuven, Mechelen, Ostend) „regret the fact that implementation of policies developed at a higher level in many domains comes down to the city level, increasing the cities’ political responsibilities without an increase of city budget.“ [Cuypers, 2014, p. 7].

The City of Ghent points out the very strong impact of the energy and climate policies and measures at the Regional Level. We quote from the Ghent Climate Plan:

„Flemish policy has a strong impact on just about all climate themes. The Flemish authorities are not only in control when it comes to legislation (e.g. energy performance regulations for residences), but a multitude of areas directly impacting CO₂ emissions in Ghent are also part of Flemish competences. Investments in social housing construction, regional roads and highways, public transport, green energy certificates, school buildings, refurbishment premiums, energy policy agreements with companies, etc. ensure that the Flemish authorities will have a big hand in whether or not Ghent will achieve the objective of the Covenant of Mayors.“ [Ghent Climate Plan 2014-2019, p.]

From that perspective, all the City of Ghent can do is *„provide an added value CO₂ reduction, alongside Flemish policy.“* This certainly applies in the case of the *„refurbishment premiums“*, where the City of Ghent provides *additional* premiums, with an eye to ensuring that higher energy performance levels are achieved than those currently implied by the energy and climate policies of the Flemish Government.

Furthermore, the City of Ghent calls its targeted energy performance levels for the refurbishment of dwellings *„standards“*, but strictly speaking legal building standards and codes are an exclusive competence of the Regions in Belgium. In the same vein, the City of Ghent regrets that it cannot impose the nZEB standard on new-builds, unless the projects only involve the local authorities.

These findings also apply to the Flemish companion cities of Ghent. *„ For the measures which require involvement from other parties than the city administration itself, cities rely mainly upon broad awareness raising and facilitation actions. In many cases the listed initiatives for the residential sector are accompanying measures for the European, Belgian and Flemish legislation and their subsidy schemes.“ [Cuyppers, 2014, p. 14].*

For transport emissions, cities depend upon the regulations at federal and EU level to increase the environmental performance of these vehicles. Cities do have a big influence on passenger and freight traffic *within* their city or city centre.

2.1.5 CONTACT PERSON AND CONTACT DETAILS.

Tine Heyse, Deputy mayor for the Environment, Climate, Energy and North-South

<http://tineheyse.be/>

www.gentklimaatstad.be

REFERENCES

NEEAP BELGIUM (2014)

Ghent climate plan 2014-2019 Ghent climate city working overtime. www.gentklimaatstad.be

Vandevyvere H. (2014), Climate neutral city initiatives: wishful thinking or thoughtful wish? Onderzoekspapers 7, Steunpunt TRADO, Mol. Contact: han.vandevyverer@vito.be

Cuypers, D. (2014), Learning network of cities in Flanders – State of sustainable city planning and implementation, key issues and priorities, VITO, Mol. Contact: dieter.cuypers@vito.be

De Ceuninck K. and Reynert H. (2011), Flanders Heading Towards Its Own State Reform, HKJU – CCPA, god. 11. (2011), br. 4, str. 1017-1039.

VITO & ECONOTEC (2015), Evaluation of the impact of policy instruments and measures implemented in the context of the Federal climate policy, Final report, Study commissioned by the Belgian Federal Public Service of Public Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment. 4 March 2015, VITO, Mol.

VVSG (2013), Feedback from the ground on the Covenant of Mayors implementation in Flanders (Belgium), prepared by VVSG, June 2013. Contact: alex.verhoeven@vsg.be

HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.1.2

STATUS-QUO ANALYSIS OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICIES IN 8 EU COUNTRIES

D 1.2.

**PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY
POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS
AND TRANSPORT**

NATIONAL REPORT FOR BULGARIA

July 2015

Partner: Black Sea Energy Research Centre

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

OXFORD
BROOKES
UNIVERSITY

Universiteit
Antwerpen

Wuppertal Institute
for Climate, Environment
and Energy

SEI

STOCKHOLM
ENVIRONMENT
INSTITUTE

Institution: Black Sea Energy Research Centre

Steering Committee member ⁽¹⁾: Lulin Radulov

Prepared by: Valentin Vassilev and Cvetoslava Spassova

⁽¹⁾ ***The Steering Committee member has the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the report.***

HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

CONTENTS

ACRONYMS	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL	6
1.1.1 Policy instruments in the building sector. Regulatory policy instruments	6
1.1.2 Dissemination and awareness instruments / Informative policy Instruments	9
1.1.3 Economic Policy Instruments	10
1.1.4 Capacity Building and Networking	13
1.1.5 Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services	14
1.1.6 Policy Instruments for Research and Development and Best Available Technology (BAT) Promotion	15
1.1.7 Summary Table for the Buildings Sector in Bulgaria	17
1.2 Policy instruments in the transport sector	19
1.2.1 Planning Instruments	19
1.2.2 Regulatory Policy Instruments	20
1.2.3 Financial Policy Instruments	21
1.2.4 Dissemination and awareness instruments	23
1.2.5 Policy Instruments for Research and Development	24
1.2.6 Summary Table for the Transport Sector in Bulgaria	26
2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE REGIONAL / LOCAL LEVEL	27
2.1 Presentation of the Case Study “Strategy for sustainable energy development of the municipality of Burgas 2011 - 2020”	27
2.1.1 Introduction	27
2.1.2 Energy Consumption	27
REFERENCES	30

ACRONYMS

BAT	Best Available Technology
BGN	Bulgarian lev (national currency)
EC	European communities
EE	Energy Efficiency
EEA	Energy Efficiency Act
EEC	European Economic Community
EU	European Union
EWRC	Energy and Water Regulatory Commission
GWh	Gigawatt hour
kW	kilowatt
m ² K	Square meter per degree Kelvin
ME	Ministry of Energy
MEET	Ministry of Economy and Energy
MRDPW	Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works
NEEAP	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan
NZEB	Nearly Zero Energy Building
OP	Operational Programme
OPRD	Operational Programme Regional Development
OPT	Operational Programme Transport
PJ	Peta joule
REECL	Residential Energy Efficiency Credit Line
SEDA	Sustainable Energy Development Agency
VTMIS	Vessel Traffic Management Information System
W	Watt
Y	year

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Buildings

The experience and analysis of the already implemented policy instruments show that the most significant is the effect of the regulatory measures such as requirements for minimal insulation of new buildings, mandatory audits and certification, individual energy saving targets for public buildings, mandatory inspection of water heating boilers and air-conditioning systems.

The individual billing and payment of energy costs for heating in multifamily residential buildings connected to district heating formally is an informative policy instrument with high impact, but the influencing mechanism of this measure is similar to that of the regulatory instruments. If devices for heat share distribution are not installed by the consumers, the energy for heating is calculated on the basis of the installed capacity of the radiators multiplied by the maximum specific consumption of the building, and is 2-3 times higher. Practically all consumers were obliged to install distribution devices and regulation valves.

From the financial instruments, the Residential Energy Efficiency Credit Line (REECL 2015) was successful, but the great expectations are linked with the “National Programme for Energy Efficiency of Residential Buildings” (MRDPW 2015b) which will be the main mechanism for supporting the energy efficiency in households in the near future and provides 100% grants for multifamily buildings’ renovation.

The national definition of NZEB has been introduced with the new Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015). All new buildings in the country constructed after 2020 shall meet the NZEB requirements.

Transport

The primary objective of the regulatory policy instruments in transport sector - mandatory speed limits and periodical or roadside technical inspections of the vehicles - is the safety of travel, but the energy savings from these measures is substantial.

The development of railroad and urban metro infrastructure are financed by the Structural and the Cohesion Funds of the EU through the Operational Programme “Transport” 2007-2013 (OPT 2015).

Research and development activities in the field of new technologies and innovations are supported by the National Action Plan for Promotion of the Production and Accelerated Penetration of Ecological Vehicles, including Electric Mobility 2012-2014 (Council of Ministers 2012). The Plan proposes introduction of financial instruments (tax exemptions, subsidies for purchase) for the take-off of the efficient vehicles.

General conclusion

The typical problems, not addressed adequately in the national and local energy efficiency policy, are:

- Increased electricity consumption in public buildings per employed person;
- Increased share of and fuel consumption by private cars which are the biggest consumer in the transport sector;
- Insufficient financing for renovation of residential buildings and increased use of firewood in inefficient old stoves.

1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL

In comparison to D1.1 where policy packages are in the focus of analysis, this chapter presents single energy efficiency policy instruments implemented in the eight considered countries. Additionally, case studies for eight provinces or cities, focussing on the vertical integration of local actions into the national energy efficiency framework and vice versa, will be presented.

1.1.1 Policy instruments in the building sector. Regulatory policy instruments

1.1.1.1 Requirements for minimal values of U-factor of the walls, floors, roofs and windows

a) General information

Requirements for minimal values of thermal insulation of buildings have been introduced since 1964.

The values of the building envelope and its elements thermal performance, as well as the efficiency of the heating, cooling, ventilation and domestic hot water systems, are determined under the legal acts in operation at the time of the building's commissioning.

Table 1 in Appendix 4 to the Ordinance № RD-16-1057 of 10 December 2009 "On the indicators of energy consumption and energy performance in buildings" presents the maximum values of the thermal transmittance of building's elements under "Heat insulation in construction. Norms for design" of 1964, 1969 and 1977" (MEET & MRDPW 2009a).

With the enactment of Ordinance №7 of 2004 on energy efficiency, heat and energy savings in buildings (MRDPW 2015a), new requirements for improved thermal insulation of buildings have entered into force.

In order to implement them, a project entitled "Analysis, research and update regulations in support of OPRD 2014-2020" was launched in 2013 (MIP 2013). The beneficiary was the Department "Rules and regulations for the design and construction" of the Ministry of Investment Planning. The project included research, analysis, generation and evaluation of different solutions to determine the requirements for the national characteristics, leading to a reduction in energy costs in buildings through cost-effective solutions. On the basis of these analyses the following measures had been implemented:

- complementing national legal requirements for reference values of the heat transfer U-factor, W/m^2K of solid and glazed enclosure structures and elements types of buildings;
- benchmarking of total specific energy consumption, kWh/m^2 , heating, cooling, ventilation, hot water, lighting and appliances in different classes of energy and types of buildings: residential and non-residential - buildings for public services in the field of education, health, culture, trade and administrative buildings, taking into account the technical progress in the production of construction materials;
- setting national parameters (numerical reference indicators for annual energy consumption) to form a legal requirement for the energy performance of nearly zero energy consumption buildings;
- updating the national calculation methodology for annual energy consumption with new elements, including nearly zero energy consumption buildings;

- updating Ordinance №7 of 2004 on energy efficiency, heat and energy savings in buildings, Ordinance №15 of 2005 on technical regulations and standards for design, construction and operation of facilities for the generation, transmission and distribution of heat and Ordinance № RD 16-1058 from 10 December 2009 on the indicators for energy consumption and energy performance of buildings (MEET & MRDPW 2009b).

b) Type of policy instrument

Minimum energy performance standards

c) Objectives

The objectives of the instrument are:

- to regularly update the national legislative requirements for heat transfer U-factor, W/m^2K , referent values for glass and walls constructions and elements of the buildings, according to the technological progress at the production of construction materials and products.
- to determine requirements for the national characteristics of the thermal insulation leading to a reduction in energy costs in buildings through cost-effective solutions.

d) Target group

The target group includes all new residential and public buildings.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The rules for determination of the correspondence to the energy efficiency requirements and the scale for the energy consumption categories are regulated by Ordinance № RD 16-1058 (MEET & MRDPW 2009b). The Ordinance contains referent values of the heat technical indexes of the construction and building elements.

There is a methodology for calculation of minimum performance of insulation depending on the construction elements' type and characteristics – external walls, glazing, roofs, floors etc.

If a building does not comply with the requirements (including for heat insulation) it cannot be put into service according to Article 14 of the “Ordinance №2 from December 11, 2012 for commissioning of construction works in Bulgaria” (MRDPW 2012).

f) Implementation network

The Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works is responsible for the implementation of the requirements in all new buildings.

g) Outcomes

The evaluation is an expert assessment of the annually saved energy for space heating as a result of the new regulations for the introduced into exploitation new residential building areas during the period 2009 - 2013, as well as a forecast for the new residential area for the period until 2020.

Forecast of final energy savings:

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Requirements for minimal values of thermal insulation of buildings	0,598 PJ/a (2013)	1,506 PJ/a (2020)

1.1.1.2 Inspection of water heating boilers, heating and air-conditioning systems

a) General information

The mandatory energy efficiency control of water heating boilers, heating and air-conditioning systems is specified in the Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015).

The Act specifies the systems, which are subject to regular inspection, and the corresponding procedures. The systems include:

- Hot water boiler heating systems in buildings with over 20 kW effective rated output for heating premises;
- Air conditioning systems in buildings with electrical rated output over 12 kW.

b) Type of policy instrument

Mandatory energy audits

c) Objectives

The objective is to reduce energy consumption and costs by improving the efficiency of boilers and air-conditioning systems in residential and public buildings.

d) Target group

The target group comprises all residential and public buildings equipped with such boilers and air-conditioning systems.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Depending on the installed capacity and the type of the energy used, hot water boilers and heating systems shall be subject to mandatory periodical energy efficiency inspections once per:

- each 8 years - hot water boiler and heating systems for liquid or solid fuel of single rated output of 20 kW to 50 kW, and for natural gas with single rated output of more than 100 kW;
- each 4 years - hot water boiler and heating systems for liquid or solid fuel of single rated output of 50 kW to 100 kW;
- each 3 years - hot water boiler and heating systems for liquid or solid fuel of single rated output over 100 kW.

The inspections shall be carried out during the heating period while these systems are in operation.

The first inspection of the installed hot water boilers in new buildings shall be made within the scope of the energy efficiency audit of the building after its commissioning.

Air-conditioning systems of an effective rated electric output of more than 12 kW in public buildings shall likewise be subject to an inspection according to the procedure established by the Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015). Air-conditioning installations shall be subject to a mandatory energy efficiency inspection on a regular basis once every 4 years.

The inspections identify the energy efficiency actions to be implemented by the owners of boilers and air-conditioning systems.

f) Implementation network

The Bulgarian Sustainable Energy Development Agency (SEDA) creates and maintains a database of:

1. hot water boiler and heating systems;
2. air-conditioning systems.

Within six months after the date of commissioning of the facilities, their owners shall submit to the Agency a declaration completed in a standard form endorsed by the Executive Director of SEDA.

Table: Performed inspections of hot water boilers and air-conditioning systems in SEDA's database for the period 2011-2013 (SEDA 2014a):

	2011		2012		2013	
	Num	Installed capacity	Num	Installed capacity	Num	Installed capacity
		MW		MW		MW
Hot water boiler heating systems	219	88,6	530	340,8	189	98,4
Air-conditioning systems	39	4,6	96	8,9	112	10,5
Total	258	93,2	626	349,7	301	108,9

g) Outcomes

The evaluation of the final energy savings is cited from the “Report on the implementation of the second national action plan for energy efficiency 2011 – 2013” (SEDA 2014a) and bases on the performed inspections and expert assessment of the annually saved energy as a result of the implementation of the prescribed energy efficiency actions.

The evaluation of the final energy savings is based on the performed inspections (SEDA 2014a)	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Mandatory energy efficiency control for boilers, heating systems and air-conditioning systems in buildings	Boilers: 0,35 PJ/a Air-conditioners: 0,43 PJ/a	Not available

1.1.2 Dissemination and awareness instruments / Informative policy Instruments

1.1.2.1 Individual billing of heat energy in multifamily buildings

a) General information

The individual billing and payment of energy costs for heating in multifamily residential buildings connected to district heating network is stipulated in the following documents:

1. Energy Act from 2003 (EA 2015);
2. Ordinance on regulating the prices of heat supply since 25.06.2004 (EWRC 2004);
3. Ordinance № 16-334 since 06.04.2007 on district heating (MEE 2015).

The distribution of heat energy in multi-apartment buildings shall be carried out on the basis of share distribution system if the consumers have installed respective devices – individual allocators on the radiators.

As a result of the measure, regulation thermostatic valves and individual distributors for heat energy regulation have been installed on all heating radiators in the households.

b) Type of policy instrument

This measure is a combination of provision of information and energy management.

c) Objectives

The objectives are:

- To determine the real consumption and bill of the individual consumer.
- To promote regulation of heating and to reduce the energy consumption and costs in multifamily buildings connected to district heating.

d) Target group

The target group includes residential multifamily buildings connected to district heating with vertical pipe system.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

If devices for heat share distribution are not installed by the consumers, the bill for heat energy is calculated on the basis of the installed capacity of the radiators multiplied by the maximum specific consumption of the building, and in this case the bill for the consumer is 2-3 or more times higher. Practically all consumers were compelled to install distribution devices and regulation valves or not to use district heating.

f) Implementation network

District heating companies measure the heat energy for buildings by heat meters. Energy services companies install thermostatic valves and allocators on radiators and perform the calculation of the bills paid by the consumers to the district heating company.

g) Outcomes

The evaluations and data from district heating companies show no less than 15% energy savings due to improved efficiency, without worsening the heat comfort in the dwellings. On the basis of 3 698 GWh heat consumption in residential buildings with district heating systems in 2013 (NSI 2015), the achieved savings are evaluated at not less than 555 GWh/year or 2,0 PJ/year (SEDA 2014c).

Evaluation of final energy savings (SEDA 2011):

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
.....	2,0 PJ/a (2013)	2,5 PJ/a (2020)

1.1.3 Economic Policy Instruments**1.1.3.1 National energy efficiency program for multifamily residential buildings****a) General information**

On 02.02.2015, the Council of Ministers adopted with Decree №18 a “National Programme for Energy Efficiency of Residential Buildings, the terms and conditions for granting financial assistance under the program and to determine the bodies responsible for its implementation” (MRDPW 2015b). The program is aimed at the renovation of multifamily residential buildings through the implementation of energy efficiency measures.

The total budget of the program is 500 million EUR.

As of 24.07.2015, 301 applications for financing and implementation of energy efficiency measures have been approved (MRDPW 2015c).

b) Type of policy instrument

The program is an economic policy instrument and supports with 100% subsidy the costs for the energy audit and the implementation of the energy efficiency measures.

c) Objectives

The program is aimed at the renovation of multifamily residential buildings, as it seeks through the implementation of energy efficiency measures to ensure better living conditions for the citizens, thermal comfort and higher quality of living environment. It will contribute to:

- reaching higher level of energy efficiency and reduced energy costs;
- improving performance to extend the life-cycle of buildings;
- ensuring conditions of living environment in accordance with sustainability criteria.

d) Target group

The target group covers multifamily residential buildings with more than 32 dwellings.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The grants are received by owners' associations and amount to the full cost of renovation. Exemptions are the single family houses and buildings with less than 32 dwellings.

An Association of owners of a multifamily building may decide to sign a contract under which the Local Authority (Municipality) represents it for the exercise of rights and fulfilment of its obligations under the Programme. The Local Authority receives financing from the Bulgarian Development Bank. After the completion of renovation, the amounts of the grants are transferred to the Bulgarian Development Bank from the state budget (of the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works).

f) Implementation network

Coordinator of the programme is the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, which regulates the provision of grants, supports Local Authorities in implementing the program and in the budgetary procedure for the annual plans of the funds to be provided in the national budget.

The Mayors of municipalities are responsible for the overall technical and financial administration of the renovation of the buildings located on their territories and perform the following functions:

- negotiate all renovation activities;
- sign contracts for targeted funding with the Bulgarian Development Bank;
- conduct tendering procedures under the Public Procurement Act and the applicable regulations for the award of the activities for renovation.

g) Outcomes

The preliminary evaluation concerns only the first subsidy of 500 million EUR, which can be exhausted by the end of 2016. As a result of this financing, residential buildings with about 8,5 million sq. meters floor area will be renovated.

Evaluation of final energy savings:

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
.....		1,2 PJ/a (till 2016)

1.1.3.2 Residential Energy Efficiency Credit Line (REECL)

a) General information

To help the Bulgarian households to reduce their energy bills and consumption, the European Commission, the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development and the Bulgarian Energy Efficiency Agency have developed a €50 million Residential Energy Efficiency Credit Line (REECL), which provides credit lines to reputable Bulgarian banks to make loans to householders for specific energy efficiency measures including double-glazing; wall, floor, and roof insulation; installation of efficient biomass stoves and boilers; solar water heaters; efficient gas boilers; and heat pump systems. (REECL 2015)

b) Type of policy instrument

REECL is an economic policy instrument and supports with soft loans and 20 – 35% grant energy efficiency actions in households.

c) Objectives

The facility aims to give individual households or Associations of Homeowners across Bulgaria the benefits of energy efficiency improvement by providing them with loans and incentive grants through local participating banks.

d) Target group

The target group includes all individual households or Associations of Homeowners in residential single or multifamily buildings.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The following rules are in force (REECL 2015):

“Any household or Association of Homeowners, which takes a REECL loan, is entitled to receive an incentive grant of 20%, 30% or 35% respectively, toward the cost of the energy saving project, once it has been completed at their residence, subject to terms and conditions. Applicants shall use eligible products and materials to qualify for the incentive grants.

Loans and grants are given to the following energy efficiency installations:

- Energy efficient windows;
- Insulation of walls, roofs and floors;
- Gas boilers;
- Biomass fuelled room heaters, stoves and boiler systems;
- Solar thermal systems;
- Cooling and heating heat pump systems;
- Building-integrated photovoltaic systems;
- Heat-exchanger stations and building installations;
- Gasification installations;
- Balanced mechanical ventilation with heat recovery.”

f) Implementation network

REECL facility is established to provide credit lines to Bulgarian banks to make loans to householders and Associations of home owners. Each bank has different borrowing conditions and procedures.

The grant financing comes from the Kozloduy International Decommissioning Support Fund (KIDSF 2015), set up in 2000 with contributions from the European Commission, EU member countries, and

Switzerland. KIDSF financially supports the early decommissioning of units 1-4 of Kozloduy Nuclear Power Plant. KIDSF also supports energy sector initiatives associated with the decommissioning effort, such as improving energy efficiency in Bulgaria.

g) Outcomes

The evaluation of the achieved savings only from energy efficiency projects is based on completed investment projects or project applications as of the end of 2014 (RES projects are excluded). (REECL 2015).

Evaluation of final energy savings:

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
	0,44 PJ/a (to 2014)	

1.1.4 Capacity Building and Networking

1.1.4.1 Training of governmental and municipal employees on development, implementation and reporting the results of energy efficiency plans

a) General information

According to Article 11 of the Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015) the energy efficiency policy shall be implemented by the central government and local self-government bodies through elaboration of energy efficiency plans and programmes for their implementation for a certain period.

This measure foresees organization of training campaigns for the employees in the central government and local administrations for developing of EE plans and programs, managing energy efficiency in buildings and preparing annual reports on the implementation of the measures.

b) Type of policy instrument

Policy instrument for education and training.

c) Objectives

To improve the capacity of employees in the central government and local administrations for developing energy efficiency plans and programs, managing energy efficiency in buildings, and preparing annual reports on the implementation of the measures in the buildings.

d) Target group

The target group includes the employees in the central government and local administrations.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The plans and programmes shall be developed in compliance with the National Energy Efficiency Strategy (not yet adopted). Specific characteristics of the regional plans for development of the relevant regions and their perspectives for sustainable economic growth will be taken into account.

Central government and local self-government bodies shall submit annually to the Executive Director of SEDA reports on the plans' implementation.

These reports shall contain description of the activities and measures, shall point out the proportion of the achieved energy savings and shall be submitted not later than 31 March of the year, following the year of the implemented activities and measures. The reports shall be drafted on a sample, approved by the Agency's Executive Director and shall be a part of the report for the implementation of the relevant national action plan.

The owners of buildings with floor area more than 1000 m² (500 m² since 2013 and 250 m² in 2015) have obligation to perform energy audits and to manage the energy efficiency in their property.

This measure foresees training of the employees of the central government and local administrations on development of these plans and programs, managing energy efficiency in buildings and preparing the annual reports of the measures' implementation.

f) Implementation network

For the measure's implementation, in 2013 SEDA organized 6 seminars, which aim was to educate state and municipal administrations' experts in:

- elaboration of energy efficiency plans,
- annual reporting on the implementation of the EE measures executed by the administrations.

In addition to this, SEDA developed and sent to all 265 municipal administrations a questionnaire about the degree of implementation and the problems identified in the implementation of obligations under the Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015) and the Energy from Renewable Sources Act (ERSA 2015). The main idea was to identify the needs of the Local Administrations (financial, administrative, and educational) for the implementation of sustainable energy local policy, as well as the possibilities for SEDA to give any possible support to the obligated administrations.

The training is funded by the European Social Fund and the state budget of the Republic of Bulgaria through the Operational Programme "Administrative Capacity".

g) Outcomes

The measure has no direct energy saving impact. It supports the implementation of energy efficiency measures.

1.1.5 Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services

1.1.5.1 Individual targets for public buildings owners for energy savings under the Energy Efficiency Act

a) General information

The Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015) determines three groups of obliged persons – energy dealers, owners of public buildings and industrial enterprises with individual targets for energy savings till 2016. These targets are included in the NEEAPs.

b) Type of policy instrument

Policy instrument for promotion of energy services in public buildings.

c) Objectives

The measure's objectives include improvement of energy efficiency of public buildings, reduction of energy costs and promotion of energy services.

d) Target group

The obliged persons are owners of public buildings with total useful floor area over 250 m².

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

In Bulgaria the obliged building owners include 243 municipal, 28 regional and 15 central administrations. The total amount of their individual targets for energy savings till 2016 is 521 GWh/a, which is about 7% of the National Indicative Target, set under Directive 2006/32/EC.

According to Article 85 of the Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015) any retail energy sales company, owner of a building and owner of an industrial system, who fails to achieve the individual energy savings target allocated within the time limits provided for in the National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, shall be liable to a penalty from BGN 5 000 to BGN 500 000.

f) Implementation network

The control over the implementation of the individual energy savings targets is executed by SEDA.

The methods for proving the achieved energy savings are energy audits or specialized methods adopted by the Council of Ministers of the Republic of Bulgaria. These methods could be applied only by companies authorized by the Energy Efficiency Act (SEDA 2009).

g) Outcomes

According to Article 36 of the Energy Efficiency Act, buildings owners with individual targets submit to SEDA annual reports on energy efficiency management. These reports contain a description of the activities and measures and indicate the amount of the energy savings achieved, and shall be submitted not later than on the 31st day of March of the year following the year of implementation of the respective activities and measures. The evaluation of the achieved and expected savings was made on the basis of the reports submitted to SEDA (SEDA 2014a).

The energy savings for 2014 are cited from the “Annual report on the implementation of the NEEAP 2014-2020” (SEDA 2015).

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
	3,3 PJ/a	0,21 PJ/a (only in 2014)

1.1.6 Policy Instruments for Research and Development and Best Available Technology (BAT) Promotion

1.1.6.1 Development of pilot program for public buildings with nearly zero energy consumption

a) General information

The measure is part of the activities for determination of the national target for buildings with nearly zero energy consumption. In determining the national target, Bulgaria adheres to the EC proposed "two-step approach". In the first stage, which matches the period of the Second National Action Plan for Energy Efficiency 2011 – 2013 (SEDA 2014a), Bulgaria sets the basis for definition of parameters for national buildings with nearly zero energy consumption.

b) Type of policy instrument

Policy instrument for research and development of the best available technology in buildings sector.

c) Objectives

The objective is to formulate a national definition for buildings with nearly zero energy consumption in accordance with the basic principles of the NZEB definition at European level (BPIE 2011).

d) Target group

The different types of buildings are divided into 3 main groups:

- Group A – Single and multifamily buildings with total floor area more than 500 m².
- Group B - Residential and public buildings with total floor area 500 m² – 7 000 m².

- Group C - Residential and public buildings with total floor area more than 7 000 m².

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The definition takes into consideration three basic requirements:

- Primary energy consumption corresponding to the A class of the national scale. Under the current regulations, the annual energy consumption in Class A is less than half the consumption of the B class, and the latter regulates the mandatory requirement for commissioning of new buildings;
- Minimum share of RES in the energy balance of the building;
- Limiting the maximum share of electricity in total energy balance of the building. This restriction only applies to buildings with floor area more than 500 m².

The simple definition for “Nearly zero energy consumption building” was adopted with the new Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015):

“Nearly zero energy consumption building” is a building that meets both of the following conditions:

1. energy consumption of the building, defined as primary energy, corresponds to class A of the scale of energy classes for the given type of buildings;
2. not less than 55 percent of the energy consumed (supplied) for heating, cooling, ventilation, domestic hot water and lighting is energy from renewable sources, produced on-site at the building level or near the building.”

f) Implementation network

The Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works is responsible for the definition of national parameters for buildings with nearly zero energy consumption and for proposing national target for NZEB.

g) Outcomes

The achieved energy savings in 2014 are taken from the “Annual report on the implementation of the NEEAP 2014-2020”, (SEDA 2015)

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
		0,38 PJ/a (to 2016)

1.1.7 Summary Table for the Buildings Sector in Bulgaria

Table: Buildings policy instruments

Policy instruments	Short list of implemented policies and measures	Objective	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Implementation network
Regulatory policy instruments	Requirements for minimal insulation	Reduce energy cost and improve thermal comfort in residential and public buildings	All new residential and public buildings	The requirements for improved thermal insulation of buildings are set in Ordinance №7 of 2004 on energy efficiency, heat and energy savings in buildings	The Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works is responsible for the implementation of the requirements for all new buildings
Dissemination and awareness instruments/Informative policy instruments	Individual billing of heat energy in multifamily buildings	Promote the regulation of heating and reduce energy consumption and costs	Residential multifamily buildings connected to district heating with vertical pipe system	If devices for share distribution are not installed by the consumers, the bill for heat energy is calculated on the basis of the installed capacity of the radiators multiplied by the maximum specific consumption of the building	Energy services companies install thermostatic valves and distributors on radiators and perform calculation of the bills paid by the clients of the district heating company
Economic policy instruments	National energy efficiency program for multifamily residential buildings	Reduce costs and improve thermal comfort in multifamily residential buildings	Multifamily residential buildings with more than 32 dwellings in all municipalities	The grants are received by owners' associations and amount to the full cost of renovation. Exemptions are the single family houses and buildings with less than 32 dwellings	The Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works coordinates the program and supports the Local Administrations in the programme's implementation. The Mayors of municipalities are responsible for the overall technical and financial administration of the renovation of the buildings located on their territories

Policy instruments	Short list of implemented policies and measures	Objective	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Implementation network
Capacity building and networking	Training of state and municipal employees in development of energy efficiency plans	Improve the capacity of the employees in the central and local administrations	Employees in the central government and local administrations	The plans and programmes shall be elaborated in compliance with the regional plans for development	In 2013 SEDA organized 6 educational seminars for the experts from state and municipal administrations
Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services	Individual energy saving targets for owners of public buildings	Improve energy efficiency of public buildings, reduce energy costs and promote energy services	Owners of public buildings with total useful floor area over 1000 m ²	The obliged building owners are 243 municipal, 28 regional and 15 central administrations	The control over the implementation of the individual energy savings targets is executed by the Sustainable Energy Development Agency
Policy instruments for Research and Development and BAT promotion	Pilot program for public buildings with nearly zero energy consumption	Determine the national definition for buildings with nearly zero energy consumption	All public and residential buildings	Definition of NZEB a) energy consumption corresponds to class A; b) not less than 55 percent of the energy is from renewable sources produced on-site at the building level or near.	The Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works defines national parameters for buildings with nearly zero energy consumption and proposes national target for NZEB

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

1.2.1 Planning Instruments

1.2.1.1 Development of the railroad infrastructure, improvement of shipping in the internal waterways and metro-transport extension

a) General information

The Operational Programme “Transport” 2007-2013 (OPT 2015) is one of the seven operational programmes in the Republic of Bulgaria, which are financed by the Structural and the Cohesion Funds of the EU.

The goal of OPT is the development of railway, road and waterway infrastructure, as well as the promotion of development of intermodal transport in accordance with the transport policy of the European Union and the established requirements for development of the Trans-European transport network in order to achieve stability of the Bulgarian transport system.

The projects addressing the development of railroad infrastructure are set in Axis I of the OPT. Construction and development of key rail infrastructure links with national, trans-border and EU importance and improvement of interoperability on major rail routes are provided with about 29% of the budget of the OPT (provided investment: €580 million).

The progress of the major rail projects in 2013 was as follows:

- Rehabilitation of railway infrastructure sections of the railway line Plovdiv – Burgas;
- Electrification and reconstruction of railway line Svilengrad - Turkish border;
- Construction of a new border combined road/rail bridge across the Danube River at Vidin – Calafat;
- Modernization of the trans-European rail network in Bulgaria railway line Sofia – Plovdiv.

As of 31.12.2014, 9 projects had been contracted under the Program with a total budget of 1,4 billion BGN. The priority axis are verified expenses amounting to 892 438 655 BGN. The amount requested for recovery costs from the EC-axis is 717 165 342 BGN (€ 366 686 441) only European co-financing. (OPT 2015)

Inland waterways:

The European transport policy gives high priority to the development of water and inland waterway transport in the Community, two key components of intermodality as a tool to address the growing burden of road and rail transport infrastructure and to reduce air pollution.

The progress of the major projects related to water transport in 2013 was as follows:

- Establishment of River Information System in the Bulgarian part of the Danube River (BULRIS) - Phase 1;
- Vessel Traffic Management Information System - (VTMIS), phase 3;
- Improved navigation and topographic measurements on the Danube River.

Expansion of metro transport:

The construction of the Sofia subway is funded under the Priority Axis 3 - "Improving intermodality for passengers and cargo." In 2013 two projects related to the construction of the metro network were implemented and the progress achieved was as follows:

- Sofia Metro Extension Project - III stage, Lot 1 "Tsarigradsko shose - Sofia Airport", Lot 2 " Mladost 1 District - Business Park Mladost 4";
- Technical assistance for the preparation of an investment project for the third metro line " Knyazhevo District – Central City Region – Botevgrad road Blvd." for realization as a "light metro" type.

b) Type of policy instrument

Improvements of rail, waterborne and public transport infrastructure.

c) Objectives

The measure's objectives are:

- Promotion of modal shift from road to rail and other energy efficient modes of transport;
- Reduction of fuels consumption and air polluting emissions.

d) Target group

The target groups include rail, inland waterborne and metro transport.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

These projects are part of the Operational Programme "Transport 2007 - 2013" (OPT 2015) financed with EU funds, and comply with the rules applied to the EU financed programmes.

f) Implementation network

The responsible bodies are the Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications and the implementation network of the Operational Programme "Transport 2007 - 2013".

g) Outcomes

Evaluation of the achieved and expected savings is not available.

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020

1.2.2 Regulatory Policy Instruments

1.2.2.1 Mandatory speed limits

a) General information

In conformity with the Article 21 of the Road Transport Law (RTL 2015), drivers are obliged to limit the speed in order not to cause any danger for others and not to hinder or disturb the traffic. The determination of the speed limits takes into account fuel consumption too.

b) Type of policy instrument

Speed restrictions are a regulatory policy instrument.

c) Objectives

The primary objective of the measure is safety of travel. A secondary objective is the reduction of fuel consumption.

d) Target group

The target group includes all road transport vehicles.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

If no other speed is indicated on road signs, the speed limits are as follows (in km/h):

Table: Road transport speed limits in Bulgaria

Class of road vehicle	Populated area	Outside populated area	Highway
A	50	80	100
B	50	90	130
C, D	50	80	100
B+E			
C+E, D+E	50	70	100
T	50	50	-
M	45	45	-

Source: RTL 2015

Traffic police imposes fines on the offenders.

f) Implementation network

The Ministry of Interior is responsible for implementing this measure.

g) Outcomes

The evaluation of the achieved and expected savings is made on the basis of an expert assessment and the experience and research in other countries:

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
	2 PJ/a (2013)	2,4 PJ/a (2020)

1.2.3 Financial Policy Instruments

1.2.3.1 Programme for improvement of energy efficiency in the Transport sector 2012-2020

a) General information

The “Programme for improvement of energy efficiency in the transport sector 2012 - 2020” (MTITC 2012a) was developed by the Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications under the provisions of the Energy Efficiency Act (EEA 2015): “The energy efficiency policy is implemented also by ministries and local authorities by elaborating energy efficiency plans and programmes for their implementation for a specified period”.

The programme includes energy efficiency measures implemented by the companies under the MTITC and roadside inspections of commercial road vehicles.

The implemented energy efficiency projects only in 2013 by the companies under the Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications included in the programme are:

- Repair and reconstruction of cable lines, etc. - estimated amount of electricity saved in the MTITC institutions for one year - 10 MWh/year;

- Installation of "Remote reporting control static electricity in State Company "National Railroad Structure" - expected amount of electricity saved - 10 MWh/year;
- Rehabilitation of the pylon and ramp lighting - the estimated amount of electricity saved – 25 MWh/year;
- Construction of a new power supply of electrical railroad structure Danube Bridge - Ruse - expected electricity savings amount - 15 MWh/year;
- Reconstruction of key railway stations (replacement of windows, insulated walls, energy saving measures appliances for measuring, monitoring and control building systems and lighting) - expected energy savings - 145 MWh/year;
- Optimization of motion graphics and fast passenger trains on diesel fuel - expected energy savings - 1 174,43 MWh/year;
- Optimization of motion graphics and fast passenger trains (of electricity) - the estimated amount of electricity saved - 14,608 MWh/year;
- Improve efficiency of diesel locomotives by constant monitoring of their performance and regulation of fuel - expected energy savings - 348,84 MWh/year).

Roadside inspections of the commercial road vehicles

Under Directive 2000/30/EC of the European Parliament and the Council on the technical roadside inspections of commercial vehicles (EC 2000) the Executive Agency "Automobile Administration" (in the frame of MTITC) performs roadside inspections of commercial passenger and freight vehicles (MTITC 2012b). These inspections include check of the engine exhaust system, measuring emissions of pollutants in exhaust gases and check for leaking fuel and /or oil.

b) Type of policy instrument

The program is a regulatory, financial and planning policy instrument and supports with inspections and subsidies the implementation of energy efficiency measures and development of transport infrastructure.

c) Objectives

Reconstruction of electrical supply of the railroad infrastructure, renovation of key railroad stations, optimization of traffic of passenger trains, improvement of fuel efficiency of diesel locomotives.

d) Target group

The target group includes the rail transport and rail infrastructure companies under the Ministry of Transport, Information Technologies and Communications and all commercial passenger and freight vehicles.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The projects, which beneficiaries are companies under the MTITC, are included in the Operational Programme "Transport 2007 - 2013" (OPT 2015) financed by EU funds and comply with its rules.

If the inspections find non-compliance with the requirements, this can lead to temporary or permanent termination of the registration of the road vehicle.

f) Implementation network

The obligation to develop and implement this program belongs to the Ministry of Transport, Information Technologies and Communications. The programme's implementation is annually reported to the Executive Director of SEDA and the information is included in the National Report for the implementation of the NEEAP (SEDA 2015).

g) Outcomes

The evaluation of the achieved and expected savings was made on the basis of the submitted to SEDA information from the Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications.

The evaluation of the final energy savings is included in the Report on the implementation of the Second National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2011 – 2013 (SEDA 2014c).

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
1. Projects implemented in the companies under the Ministry of transport	0,06 PJ/a (2013)	
2. Roadside inspections of the commercial road vehicles	2,4 PJ/a (2013)	

1.2.4 Dissemination and awareness instruments

1.2.4.1 Training of drivers of motor vehicles in economical driving

a) General information

A Programme for training of drivers of motor vehicles in fuels saving driving has been designed.

The measure is included in the legislation with Ordinance №41/04.08.2008 (MTITC 2008). This Ordinance transposes Directive 2003/59/EC (EC 2003) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 July 2003 on the initial qualification and periodic training of drivers of certain road vehicles for the carriage of goods or passengers, amending Council Regulation (EEC) No 3820/85 and Council Directive 91/439/EEC and repealing Council Directive 76/914/EEC into the Bulgarian legislation.

b) Type of policy instrument

This policy instrument concerns training on fuels saving driving of individuals, truck and bus drivers.

c) Objectives

The objective is to improve the capacity of motor vehicle drivers for saving fuel. The other aim is to reduce the energy costs for travel.

d) Target group

The target group encompasses all new motor vehicle drivers, drivers in the logistic companies and in companies for passenger transport.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The training of motor vehicles' drivers on economical driving includes:

- training courses for new drivers in driving with fuel savings;
- training courses for drivers in logistic companies and in companies for passenger transport.

The approximate budget for this measure is about 9 million BGN.

f) Implementation network

The training can be conducted only by certified legal entities or professional schools. The organization work is controlled by the Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications.

g) Outcomes

The expert evaluation shows that driver training in economical driving can result in energy savings and reduction of emissions in the transport sector of not less than 0,6% per year or about 181 GWh/y based on the energy consumption of the sector in 2013:

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
	0,65 PJ/a (2013)	0,75 PJ/a (2020)

1.2.5 Policy Instruments for Research and Development

1.2.5.1 National action plan to promote production and accelerated entry of environmental vehicles including electrical mobility in Bulgaria 2012-2014

a) General information

The National Action Plan (Council of Ministers 2012) was adopted by decision № 862 of the Council of Ministers on 17.10.2012. The purpose of this Plan was to identify the key measures and activities to be implemented to stimulate production and purchase of environmentally friendly vehicles in the country.

b) Type of policy instrument

This is a dissemination and research instrument.

c) Objectives

The main objectives of the Plan are as follows:

- Stimulating the production of electric and other green vehicles in Bulgaria, including auxiliary equipment and parts;
- Stimulating research and development activities for the development of environmentally friendly vehicles and charging systems;
- Stimulating the demand for new ecological vehicles;
- Accelerating the development of charging infrastructure for electrical vehicles;
- Raising the awareness and the capacity of stakeholders and public about the nature, purpose and benefits of the sustainable mobility development;
- Promoting the development of sustainable urban mobility.

d) Target group

The environment friendly vehicles addressed by the Plan include:

- electric vehicles - that use electric motor with full power and do not have an internal combustion engine;
- hybrid cars - vehicles that use two or more power systems of different types - an electric motor and an internal combustion engine (petrol or diesel);
- vehicles - passenger cars emitting CO₂ emissions up to 120 g/km; vans - up to 175 g/km; buses - requirements EURO V.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The proposed approaches to promote efficient vehicles are:

- For electric vehicles - exemption from annual tax;
- Hybrid cars - exemption from annual tax (not less than 5 years);
- Introduction of preferential fees for initial registration of electric and hybrid cars;
- Release/relief of tolls for the use of road infrastructure;
- Providing a single grant / bonus for individuals and legal persons in the purchase of new electrical or hybrid car as follows: for new electrical car – 2500 EUR, for new hybrid car – 1250 EUR.

f) Implementation network

The implementation network includes – Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications, Ministry of Energy, Ministry of Economy, Ministry of Environment and Water, Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, municipalities.

g) Outcomes

As of the end of 2014, the number of electric cars was 497 and of hybrid cars 1031 (TLL Media 2015).

Evaluation of the energy savings is not available.

1.2.6 Summary Table for the Transport Sector in Bulgaria

Summary table: Transport					
	Short list of implemented policies and measures	Objective ¹ (improve system, travel or vehicle efficiency)	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Implementation network
Planning instruments	Development of the railroad infrastructure	Improve travel efficiency	Rail, waterborne and subway transport infrastructure	Financing by EU funds	Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications and the network of the Operational Programme "Transport"
Regulatory policy instruments	Mandatory speed limits	Improve vehicle efficiency	Road transport	The traffic police imposes fines on the offenders	The implementation of the measures is a responsibility of the Ministry of Interior
Financial policy instruments	Programme for energy efficiency in the transport sector 2012-2020	Improve travel and vehicle efficiency	Rail transport, railway stations and infrastructure	Financing by EU funds	The responsibility for the development and implementation of the Programme belongs to the Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications
Dissemination and awareness instruments	Training of drivers in economical driving	Improve vehicle efficiency	Drivers of cars, trucks and buses	Training courses for drivers	The training courses are controlled by the Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications
Policy instruments for Research and Development	National action plan to promote efficient vehicles	Improve vehicle efficiency	Road vehicles	Tax exemption, grants for purchase of electric cars	Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communication, Ministry of Energy, Ministry of Economy

¹ Energy efficiency in the transport sector can be divided into system efficiency (reduce or avoid travel or the need to travel), travel efficiency (shift to more energy efficient modes) and vehicle efficiency (improve the efficiency through vehicle technology).

2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE REGIONAL / LOCAL LEVEL

2.1 PRESENTATION OF THE CASE STUDY "STRATEGY FOR SUSTAINABLE ENERGY DEVELOPMENT OF THE MUNICIPALITY OF BURGAS 2011 - 2020"

2.1.1 Introduction

In terms of decentralization and expanding the powers of local government, the role of the municipalities is becoming more significant in the management of energy. Rational use of energy resources, production and supply of energy are major concerns of the municipal authorities.

Energy planning and ensuring energy independence become a major component of the policy for sustainable development of each municipality.

In 2008 the Burgas Municipality joined the initiative Covenant of Mayors.

The Local Authority committed to develop a local action plan to improve energy efficiency and utilize the renewable energy potential (Municipality of Burgas 2011). As a local authority, the Burgas Municipality has defined local sustainable energy policy.

Burgas is the largest municipality in Southeast Bulgaria, located on an area of 514 362 ha which represents 0,43% of the country's area. To the East the municipality borders the Black Sea, which is a prerequisite for the development of maritime and fishing industries, tourism and foreign trade.

The population of the municipality (data from the National Census 2011) is 212 902 residents, 198 971 or 94,9% of which, live in the city of Burgas.

2.1.2 Energy Consumption

The general trend is the increase of energy consumption from 1 300 000 MWh in 2005 to 1 500 000 MWh in 2010.

Highest is the consumption of households (46%), followed by sector "Industry" (37%) and sector "Transport" (14%). The lowest share belongs to the sector "Municipal activities, services and municipal buildings" (about 3%). The Greenhouse gases emissions in 2010 amounted to 647 679 tCO₂. The table below shows the expected achievements till 2020 (Municipality of Burgas 2011).

Energy Efficiency Policy / Action:

Energy targets	% till 2020
Reduction of CO ₂ emissions	25
Energy savings	27
Share of RES	26

The next table shows the expected contributions of the different subsectors to the achievement of the energy saving target.

Distribution of the target for annual energy savings till 2020, MWh/year

Renovation of municipal buildings	11 054
Energy management in municipal buildings	1 020
Street lighting	7 246
Energy efficiency in households	266 860

Reduction of losses in district heating	37 000
Energy efficiency in industry	30 000
Energy efficiency in public transport	4 899
Alternative modes of travel	749
Total energy savings (27,59%)	358 828

The expected investments are 507 million EUR, reduced energy cost – 53 million EUR/y, reduced CO₂ emissions – 158 300 tCO₂/y (25 %)

2.1.2.1 Energy efficiency measures included in the strategy by sectors

Buildings sector

Renovation of municipal buildings:

- Reconstruction and renovation of the existing municipal buildings and introduction of energy saving measures;
- Introduction and establishment of a system of standards for energy efficiency in the construction of new buildings owned by the Municipality;
- Improvement of control systems and monitoring of energy consumption of buildings owned by the Municipality.

Energy efficiency in residential buildings:

- Energy audits of all residential buildings;
- Energy efficiency measures with priority over multifamily residential buildings;
- Development of local financial scheme to support energy efficiency in residential buildings;
- Development and implementation of municipal program stimulating the creation of owners associations with a view to facilitate financing and implementation of energy efficiency projects and use of renewable energy in multifamily buildings.

Transport sector

Improving energy efficiency of public transport:

- Renewal of the bus and trolley fleet of public transport;
- Introduction of a system of rapid bus transport;
- Introduction of priority traffic lights for public transport;
- Optimization of the public transport network;
- Introduction of a system for monitoring and control of public transport.

Efficient traffic management:

- Introduction of an integrated traffic management;
- Improvement of existing and construction of new transport infrastructure;
- Optimization of the parking system and its integration with public transport system;
- Development and implementation of innovative solutions for freight urban transport;
- Development and implementation of a system of incentives to purchase and use of environmentally friendly transport technologies.

Alternative modes of travel and new urban mobility:

- Building a comprehensive system of bicycle routes;
- Introduction of a system for renting bicycles;
- Expansion of pedestrian routes and areas.
- Energy Efficiency instruments / measures per sector:

Municipal action plan 2011 – 2013

The strategy will be implemented through separate three-year municipal action plans.

The first of them is the Municipal action plan 2011 – 2013.

The principal energy efficiency measures included in the action plan by sectors are:

Buildings sector

Renovation of municipal buildings:

- Energy audits of municipal buildings –all municipal buildings with more than 1000 sq. meters floor area have been audited;
- Gradual implementation of the identified in the energy audits actions with priority to the education and social buildings – achieved energy savings – 11 053 MWh/y;
- Experimental introduction of energy monitoring in municipal buildings – Monitoring systems introduced in 5 municipal buildings and achieved energy savings amount to 189 MWh/y.

Transport sector

Improving energy efficiency of public transport:

- construction of speed transit bus lanes - 15 km;
- Introduction of a control system which provides traffic priority for buses at traffic lights;
- construction of new bike lanes – 20,2 km;
- introduction of 28 new diesel buses;
- introduction of 39 new buses on methane fuel.

The expected energy savings are 4800 MWh/y; the reduced greenhouse gas emissions – 1 507 tons CO₂/y.

The measures in the transport are included in the project “Integrated Urban Transport of Burgas Municipality” funded by EU funds through the Operational Program "Regional Development 2007 – 2103”, which is managed by the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works.

The cost for the project implementation amounts to €61 937 000 EUR, including 44 million EUR from the Operational Programme.

After an analysis of the measures included in the strategy, it can be recommended to put additional specific measures, addressing:

- Increased electricity consumption in public buildings per employed person;
- Energy efficiency in private cars which are the biggest fuel consumer in the transport sector;
- The financing of renovation of residential buildings and the increased use of firewood in inefficient old stoves.

REFERENCES

Building Performance Institute Europe, 2011, Principles for Nearly-Zero Energy Buildings, <http://www.institutebe.com/InstituteBE/media/Library/Resources/Existing%20Building%20Retrofits/BPIE-Report-Principles-for-Nearly-Zero-Energy-Buildings.pdf>

Council of Ministers, 2012, National Action Plan for the Promotion of the Production and Accelerated Penetration of Ecological Vehicles, including Electric Mobility 2012-2014, http://www3.moew.government.bg/files/file/POS/Strategic_documents/Nacionalen_plan_elektromobil_nost.pdf

Energy Act, 2015, amended, SG No. 17/06.03.2015, www.me.government.bg/library/index/download/lang/en/fileId/256

Energy and Water Regulatory Commission, 2014, Ordinance on regulating the prices of heat supply promulgated in State Gazette issue 55/25.06.2004 (last amendment SG 17/28.02.2014), http://www.dker.bg/files/DOWNLOAD/ordinance_heat_en.pdf

Energy Efficiency Act, 2015, last amendment 15.05.2015, <http://www.seea.government.bg/documents/ZEE.pdf>

Energy from Renewable Sources Act, 2015, promulgated 14.11.2008, last amendment 28.11.2014, <http://lex.bg/en/laws/ldoc/2135728864>

European Commission, 2000, Directive 2000/30/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 June 2000 on the technical roadside inspection of the roadworthiness of commercial vehicles circulating in the Community, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32000L0030>

European Commission, 2003, Directive 2003/59/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 15 July 2003 on the initial qualification and periodic training of drivers of certain road vehicles for the carriage of goods or passengers, amending Council Regulation (EEC) No 3820/85 and Council Directive 91/439/EEC and repealing Council Directive 76/914/EEC, <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32003L0059>

Kozloduy International Decommissioning Support Fund (KIDSF), 2015, <http://www.me.government.bg/en/themes/kozloduy-international-decommissioning-support-fund-kidsf-905-348.html>

Ministry of Economy and Energy, 2015, Ordinance № 16-334 /06.04.2007 for district heating (last amendment 9.06.2015), <http://lex.bg/laws/ldoc/2135550456>

Ministry of Economy, Energy and Tourism & Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, 2009a, Ordinance № RD-16-1057 of 10 December 2009 “On the indicators of energy consumption and energy performance in buildings”, Appendix № 4 to Art. 16, para. 1 Table 1, <http://www.seea.government.bg/documents/Naredba-RD-16-1058.pdf>.

Ministry of Economy, Energy and Tourism & Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, 2009b, Ordinance № RD 16-1058/10 December 2009 on the indicators for energy consumption and energy performance of buildings, <http://seea.government.bg/documents/Naredba-RD-16-1058.pdf>

Ministry of Energy (ME), 2015, Energy from Renewable Sources Act, promulgated 14.11.2008, last amendment 28.11.2014, <http://lex.bg/en/laws/ldoc/2135728864>

Ministry of Investment Planning, 2013, Project "Analysis, research and update regulations in support of OPRD 2014-2020", <http://www.mip.government.bg/bg/page/44>

Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, 2012, Ordinance № 2/11 December 2012 on commissioning of construction works in the Republic of Bulgaria and the minimum warranty periods for finished construction works, facilities and construction sites, <http://www.mrrb.government.bg/docs/76925617e5a55c4fbb744b01cd627045.doc>

Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, 2013, "Analysis, research and update regulations in support of OPRD 2014-2020",

<http://www.mrrb.government.bg/index.php?controller=news&id=4259>

Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, 2015a, Ordinance № 7 of 2004 on energy efficiency, heat and energy savings in buildings (last supplemented in State Gazette, issue 31/28.04.2015), <http://www.mrrb.government.bg/docs/aa67aabccae39161239855e0de2f39f3.pdf>

Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, 2015b, "National Programme for Energy Efficiency of Residential Buildings, the terms and conditions for granting financial assistance under the program and to determine the bodies responsible for its implementation" (SG. 10 of February 6, 2015), <http://www.mrrb.government.bg/index.php?controller=category&catid=117>

Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, 2015 c, Information about the progress of the project "Energy Renovation of Bulgarian Homes" as of 24 July 2015, http://mrrb.government.bg/files/Copy%20of%20EOD%2024_7_2015.pdf

Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications, 2008, Ordinance №41/04.08.2008 on the Terms and Conditions on Conducting a Training Course for Drivers of Vehicles for Transportation of Passengers and Cargo and Terms and Conditions for Conducting Tests for Obtaining Initial Qualification, http://www.rta.government.bg/images/Image/n_uredba/n41.pdf

Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications, 2012a, Program for improvement of energy efficiency in the Transport sector 2012-2020, http://www.measures-odysseumure.eu/public/mure_pdf/transport/BG1.PDF

Ministry of Transport, Information Technology and Communications, 2012b, Ordinance № H-14 of 27.08.2009 on the conduct, scope and organization of roadside control, http://www.rta.government.bg/images/Image/n_uredba/n14.pdf

Municipality of Burgas, 2011, Strategy for sustainable energy development of Burgas Municipality 2011- 2020, http://www.covenantofmayors.eu/about/signatories_en.html?city_id=10&seap

Operational Programme "Transport" 2007-2013 (OPT), 2015, <http://www.optransport.bg/en/>

Report on the implementation in 2013 of the National action plan to promote production and accelerated entry of environmental vehicles including electrical mobility in Bulgaria 2012 – 2014, <http://www.strategy.bg/FileHandler.ashx?fileId=4803>

Residential Energy Efficiency Credit Line (REECL), 2015, <http://www.reecl.org/indexen.php>

Road Transport Law, 2015, (last amendment 22.05.20015), <http://www.lex.bg/bg/laws/ldoc/2134649345>

Sustainable Energy Development Agency, 2009, Ordinance on Methodology for Determining the National Indicative Targets, the Order of Distribution of the targets by Individual Savings Targets Between Persons in Art. 10, para. 1 of the EEA, Eligible Energy Efficiency Measures, Assessment Methodology and Ways for Verification of Energy Savings, http://www.seea.government.bg/documents/Metodiki_10_04_2009.pdf

Sustainable Energy Development Agency, 2014a, Report on the implementation of the second national action plan for energy efficiency 2011 – 2013, http://www.seea.government.bg/documents/Otchet_VNPDEE_2011-2013.pdf

Sustainable Energy Development Agency (SEDA), 2014b, National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2014 – 2020, http://www.seea.government.bg/documents/2014_neeap_en_bulgaria.pdf

Sustainable Energy Development Agency, 2015, "ANNUAL REPORT ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE NATIONAL ENERGY EFFICIENCY ACTION PLAN 2014–2020", https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/BG_Annual%20Report%202015_en.pdf

TLL Media, 2015, Information on the number of new electric and hybrid cars from the Report on the implementation in 2014 of the National action plan to promote production and accelerated entry of

environmental vehicles including electrical mobility in Bulgaria 2012 – 2014, <http://renewables-bulgaria.com/article/1786-497-elektricheski-i-1031-hibridni-prevozni-sredstva-sa-registrirani-v-balgariia>

HERON (No:649690): Deliverable 1.2

STATUS-QUO ANALYSIS OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICIES IN 8 EU COUNTRIES

D 1.2.

PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

NATIONAL REPORT FOR ESTONIA

DATE 11.08.2015

Partner: *Stockholm Environment Institute Tallinn Centre*

HERON project

“Forward-looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries”

This project has received funding from the *European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme* under grant agreement No 649690

***Institution: Stockholm Environment Institute Tallinn Centre
Steering Committee member (1): Tiit Kallaste***

Prepared by: Kerli Kirsimaa, Mari Jüssi, Tiit Kallaste, Piret Kuldna

(1) The Steering Committee member has the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the report.

HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains

Contents

ACRONYMS	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL.....	6
1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE BUILDINGS SECTOR	6
1.1.1 Regulatory Policy Instruments	6
1.1.1.1 Energy labelling of buildings	6
1.1.2 Dissemination and awareness instruments\ information	8
1.1.2.1 Energy audit and advice, and assistance	8
1.1.3 Economic policy instruments.....	10
1.1.3.1 The Credit and Export Guarantee Fund (KredEx Fund)	10
1.1.4 Capacity building and networking	12
1.1.4.1 Energy Savings Competence Centre of KredEx	12
1.1.5 Promotion of energy services.....	14
1.1.5.1 Pilot projects of zero-energy buildings.....	14
1.1.6 Policy instruments for research and development and BAT promotion	16
1.1.6.1 State supported schemes implemented by the Environmental Investment Centre EIC	16
1.1.7 Summary Table for the Buildings Sector in Estonia.....	19
1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR	21
1.2.1 PLANNING INSTRUMENTS.....	21
1.2.1.1 Development of regional and local public transport connections.....	21
1.2.2 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	22
1.2.2.1 Maximum parking standard in Tallinn city centre	22
1.2.3 FINANCIAL POLICY INSTRUMENTS	23
1.2.3.1 Increasing fuel excise duty.....	23
1.2.4 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS	25
1.2.4.1 Energy labelling of passenger cars.....	25
1.2.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT	26
1.2.5.1 Smart City Cluster	26
1.2.6 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR IN ESTONIA	28
2. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE REGIONAL / LOCAL LEVEL.....	29
2.1 PRESENTATION OF THE CASE STUDY: PROJECT “FASSAADID KORDA”	29
REFERENCES.....	32

Table of Tables

Table 1. Energy savings in Estonian houses in 2013 after the implementation of KredEx renovation fund.....	12
Table 2. An overview of EIC payments in 2014 made for renewable energy and protection of ambient air projects.....	18
Table 3 Main policy instruments in building sector in Estonia	19
Summary table: Buildings	19
Table 4 Excise duty rates per 1,000 litres of liquid fuels	23
Table 5 Savings expected/ estimated due to increasing fuel excise duty	24
Table 6 Main policy instruments in transport sector in Estonia	28

ACRONYMS

- CHP - Combined heat and power
- EIB - European Investment Bank
- EIC - Environmental Investment Centre (Estonia)
- ENMAK - National Development Plan of the Energy Sector Until 2030 (Eesti Energiamajanduse Arengukava 2030+)
- EPBD - Energy Performance of Buildings (Directive)
- ERDF - European Regional Development Fund
- ESF - European Social Fund
- IEA - International Energy Agency
- KIKAS - Environmental Investment Centre Data System (SA Keskkonnainvesteeringute Keskuse andmesüsteem)
- Kredex - Export Credit and Guarantee Foundation (Ministry of Economy and Communication)
- MEAC - The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communication (Estonia)
- NZEB - nearly Zero-Energy-Buildings
- R & D - Research & Development
- RKAS - State Real estate company (Riigi Kinnisvara AS) (Estonia)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In comparison to D 1.1 where policy packages are in the focus of analysis, this chapter presents single energy efficiency policies implemented. Additionally, specific case study of a city, focussing on the vertical integration of local actions into the national energy efficiency framework and vice versa, is presented at the end of this national report.

The main six policy instruments in the building sector analysed hereof, are energy labelling of buildings; energy audit and advice and assistance; the credit and export guarantee fund (KredEx Fund); establishment of energy savings competence centre under KredEx; pilot projects implemented to test zero-energy buildings; and state support schemes implemented by the Environmental Investment Centre (EIC). The summary table for the building sector in terms of policy instruments, can be found within the same report in table 3. Perhaps the most influential policy instrument in Estonian building sector today is the energy labelling of buildings which is an obligatory action for all the new buildings built as of January 1st 2009 onward. Another important instrument is the establishment of Foundation KredEx in 2001 and its funds and services offered for the renovation of apartment blocks explicitly. The multi-level policy process in building sector described in this paper, is the Tallinn city project „Fassaadid korda“, offering self-financing support (in addition to KredEx funding) to the apartment associations in order to help them renovate their apartment buildings.

It is only since 2010 that energy efficiency policies are introduced in Estonian transport sector more explicitly. One of the key roles in the policy instruments have been EU structural funds that have enabled funding for national, regional and local public transport and cycling infrastructure development (new passenger trains on commuter and long-distance lines, partly new trams and tramline in Tallinn, new rolling stock for regional bus lines, investment scheme for developing multi-modal access to railway stations and cycling infrastructure in major cities) and R&D activities in the Smart City Cluster (developing mobile services for public transport management). In July 2015 increasing fuel excise duty by 10% annually over the next three years was decided by the Parliament, having an estimated 5-7% energy saving impact on the transport energy consumption. New cars registered in Estonia tend to rate as the least fuel efficient cars compared to other EU member countries – therefore Estonian Ministry of Environment is introducing an energy labelling system for passenger cars from 2016 onwards in order to raise awareness of consumers. As energy efficiency is not a primary goal for all of these policies and the energy saving impacts are either not thoroughly assessed or monitored for these policies, there is only very little data available for energy efficiency impacts of these transport policies.

1. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE BUILDINGS SECTOR

1.1.1 Regulatory Policy Instruments

In Estonia, there are a number of national laws and regulations set on buildings such as the new “2030 Energy Management Development Plan”, and various Acts (i.e. 01.07.2015 Building Act, 09.01.2013 Minimum Energy Performance Requirements) formed under the Minister of Economic Affairs and Communications, the latter being the main national body responsible when it comes to energy management in Estonia.

1.1.1.1 Energy labelling of buildings

a) General information

In Estonia, energy labelling of buildings could be considered as one of the most important policy instruments in further developing energy efficiency in buildings sector. In line with the EU Directive 2002/91/EC, all the buildings and its parts must be provided with an energy label. The legal basis for issuing the energy label was set by the Regulation No. 107 of 17 December 2008 “Form of Energy Performance Certificate and Issuing Procedure” of the Minister of Economic Affairs and Communications (MEAC) (Energiamärgise..., 2008¹). The overall responsibility to manage the requirements related to the energy labelling of buildings is the duty of MEAC set by its construction and housing programme. New stricter energy performance requirements for all the buildings have been in effect since 9 January 2013 (Estonia 2013..., 2013). Yet today, new regulation was put in force by the Minister of Economic Affairs and Communications since July 2015, “Requirements for certification for energy and the energy label” (Nõuded..., 2015²).

b) Type of policy instrument

The “energy labelling of buildings” belongs to the policy type “Regulatory”. It is a regulatory policy instrument which requirements are formed under the Building Act (Nõuded..., 2015). It is obligatory for all new buildings built from 2009 onward.

c) Objectives

Energy label or energy performance certificate is a document, the objective of which is to give an information about how much does a building with the assurance of internal climate consume energy in comparison with the average energy consumption of other equivalent buildings. Energy consumption includes the amount of energy that is needed for heating, cooling, hot water, ventilation and lighting of a building. The energy label gives the buildings energy efficiency class. The higher the energy efficiency class (from A, B, C ... to G) of the building is, the lower are the electricity and heat consumption per square metre of the building (ÅF-Consulting, 2015).

¹ Energiamärgise vorm ja väljastamise kord 17.12.2008 nr. 107, RTL 2008, 100, 1428 [The form of the energy label and its issuing procedure]. Accessible at: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/13094120> (30.07.2015).

² Nõuded energiamärgise andmisele ja energiamärgisele 30.04.2015 nr. 36 [Requirements for certification for energy and the energy label]. Accessible at: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/106052015002> (30.07.2015).

In comparison to other countries part of International Energy Agency (IEA), Estonia stands out as one of the biggest household energy users, residential sector contributing to 32.8% of total final energy consumption according to 2011 statistics (transport sector being the second largest consumer group) (Estonia, 2013). An energy label is thus an important tool for the flat owner in Estonia to know, what electricity- and heat bills there will be for him/her in the future. Thus, an energy label should promote the use and ownership of energy efficient homes. It helps to compare the energy use of different buildings, helping to choose the most energy efficient type of property.

d) Target groups

The issuing of energy labels is relevant for all the buildings (all the new buildings built from 2009 onward), except the buildings which have been recognized in accordance with the “Law on National Heritage”, and the buildings which character or appearance would change under the appliance of minimum energy requirements. The minimum energy performance requirement is also exempted from:

- a) The places of worship;
- b) buildings with a service life of up to two years;
- c) industrial buildings, workshops and a low-energy, non-residential agricultural buildings;
- d) the buildings used for housing in less than four months a year;
- e) buildings with usable area up to 50 m² (Energy..., 2015).

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

At present, new single-family dwellings need to achieve a 160 kilowatt hour per square metre (kWh/m²) total annual weighted energy consumption, and multi-apartment houses to achieve total weighted energy levels of 150 kWh/m² per year.

The energy label must be given to all buildings or its parts, including apartments which are to sold or rented after January 1st 2009. The landlord or the seller of the flat must be able to let the buyer or renter to familiarize him-/herself with the energy label of the building. In case the building is older than from 2009, the energy label must be issued from a local government. Thus it plays an important role on the housing market in general (Energy..., 2015).

f) Implementation network

The energy label of all the new buildings built from 2009 onward must be provided by that company or person who drew up the building project. The entrepreneur issuing the energy labels must have a corresponding legal relationship with a specialist who can prove his/her competence with a professional certificate. The awarding of qualifications for energy auditors and energy label publishers is done by the Union of Estonian Heating- and Ventilation Engineers³. The qualification is awarded after the successful completion of the vocational training (Energy..., 2015). Those trainings are provided by the Open University of Tallinn University of Technology. The buildings which are just to be designed or which are undergoing a major renovation are to be provided by the energy labels designated by the design contractors. In line with the building code, the entrepreneur who gives out the energy labels needs to enter the data to the national construction register available electronically. When doing so, the form of the energy label will be generated automatically (Energy...,

³ <http://www.ekvy.ee/index.php?lang=et>

2015). The overall duties related to the requirements issuing an energy label of the buildings falls under the tasks of MEAC.

g) Outcomes

An energy label of the building helps the tenant or buyer of the house\flat to be aware of the costs of the energy bills which the building may occur to, thus it in turn helps to further increase the energy awareness among the inhabitants in general. The more so as it is an obligatory action as from 2009 onward. Since energy label is to be given out by various companies eligible for it, it is hard to know the percentage of how many of the buildings out of the overall Estonian housing market are still lacking the energy label. No precise data is available about the exact figures of achieved energy efficiency after the implementation of the energy label regulation. Yet it is a positive approach towards increasing awareness and actual practical results to be seen.

1.1.2 Dissemination and awareness instruments\ information

1.1.2.1 Energy audit and advice, and assistance

a) General information

Energy audit is a procedure which explains how energy is being used, what the possible energy savings methods are and how energy can be used more sustainably on the object of the audit. Energy audit gives an overview about the technical situation of the building as well as the energy loss. Audit highlights the priorities of the renovation work together with the energy savings and feasibility study analysis. The requirements are laid down in a regulation of the Minister for Economic Affairs and Communications under „The formal requirements of energy audit of the residential buildings and its issuing procedure“, adopted in 04.03.2014⁴ (Elamu..., 2014).

b) Type of policy instrument

The “energy audit and advice, and assistance” belongs to the policy type “Energy information and advice”. By performing an energy audit of building, useful information in terms of how building can be made more energy-efficient, will be made available. It is a necessary step also towards another regulatory policy instrument “energy labelling of buildings” which is in turn an obligatory action from 2009 onward.

c) Objectives

The main objective of the energy audit is to analyse buildings in respect of its energy usage in order to provide and promote more energy efficient solutions. The technical and energy situation of the building is examined in order to draw out a long-term renovation plan. After successful completion of

⁴ Elamu energiaauditi aruande vorminõuded ja väljastamise kord 04.03.2014 nr. 16 [The formal requirements of energy audit of the residential buildings and its issuing procedure 04.03.2014 nr. 16], accessible at: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/111032014004> (28.07.2015).

the energy audit, energy label could be attributed to the building, as well as it helps to implement different measures necessary for making the building more energy efficient.

d) Target groups

Energy audit could be ordered by anyone who is need of:

- Evaluation of energy efficiency of building envelope and heating systems and planning of renovation measures;
- planning of energy savings measures for a building if renovation of building envelope is planned and necessary;
- applying a loan from the bank;
- issuing an energy certificate;
- when improving the technical condition of building and improving energy efficiency at the same time, then the building's certificate will be better and the value of real estate higher (Energiasäätü..., 2015).

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The received data will allow the auditor to perform calculations, based upon which he or she can offer renovation measures in order to reduce energy consumption. Since issuing an energy label is obligatory as of 2009 onward, ordering an energy audit is a necessary step as to first analyse an energy performance of a building, based on what an energy label can be given. In addition, an influencing mechanism for people to order an energy audit in general (as to renovate their homes), is their own financial interest to keep their energy costs low, the more so as the energy prices are currently increasing.

f) Implementation network

As set in the regulation Nr.16 04.03.2014⁵ set under § 38 of the Building Act, energy audit can be performed by any entrepreneur who has certain qualifications for it. The issuing of energy audit is led by specialist who complies with the rules set in paragraphs 1 and 2 of § 47 of the Building Act. All these rules have been set by MEAC who has the overall responsibility in managing the requirements and splitting the tasks related to issuing of an energy label.

g) Outcomes

Since energy audit is an evaluation made for the building to find out its current energy performance and the necessary steps which could be made in order to improve it, similarly to energy label it is hard to draw out any quantitative outcomes. Yet again it is a positive approach towards increasing awareness and actual practical results to be seen.

⁵ Elamu energiaauditi aruande vorminõuded ja väljastamise kord 04.03.2014 nr. 16 [The formal requirements of energy audit of the residential buildings and its issuing procedure 04.03.2014 nr. 16], accessible at: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/111032014004> (28.07.2015).

1.1.3 Economic policy instruments

Energy efficiency improvements in existing buildings are currently driven by funding programmes. The current renovation rate of funded energy efficiency programmes is 500 to 600 buildings per year at an average of 1 500 square metres per building. One well-functioning executive agency, The Credit and Export Guarantee Fund (KredEx Fund) develops and offers financial services aimed at energy efficiency and works with measures targeted to residential sector and electro-mobility (KredEx, 2015). KredEx provides grants for installing renewable energy generation installations for private households (solar panels, wind generators, heat pumps, etc.) and also, for energetic refurbishment, as well as guarantees for loans for reconstruction of multi-storey apartment houses to improve their energy efficiency.

Another agency in energy efficiency field is The Environmental Investment Centre (EIC) which funds larger-scale energy efficiency projects such as DH systems and both onshore and offshore wind parks, reconstructing or constructing combined heat and power (CHP) plant (EIC, 2015).

1.1.3.1 The Credit and Export Guarantee Fund (KredEx Fund)

a) General information

Foundation KredEx was founded in 2001 by merging Export Credit and Guarantee Foundation, Enterprise Credit Foundation and Foundation *Eesti Eluase*. KredEx⁶ is a financial institution which helps Estonian enterprises to develop faster and expand more safely to foreign markets. KredEx also helps to improve the living conditions of the inhabitants of Estonia, offering loan guarantees with state guarantee for purchasing homes, as well as loans, guarantees and grants for solutions aimed at energy efficiency (KredEx, 2015).

b) Type of policy instrument

The “credit and export guarantee fund KredEx” belongs to the policy type “Economic support mechanism”. It is a collection of funds to support the improvements in terms of energy efficiency in the Estonian housing market.

b) Objectives

The Credit and Export Guarantee Fund KredEx provides grants for installing renewable energy generation installations for private households (solar panels, wind generators, heat pumps, etc.) and also, for energetic refurbishment, as well as guarantees for loans for reconstruction of multi-storey apartment houses to improve their energy efficiency.

⁶ <http://www.kredex.ee/>

c) Target groups

Apartment blocks built during the Soviet era are currently considered as the most energy inefficient, being one of the main target groups for Kredex. Anyone wishing to renovate his\her home can apply for KredEx fund. Loans are guaranteed helping apartment associations to renovate buildings and young families and specialists to acquire a new home. Kredex have allocated the grants for reconstruction of apartment buildings to numerous apartment associations and local governments which had the possibility to receive support from the state for energetic refurbishment of apartment buildings and thus reduce energy expenses of flat owners.

d) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The reconstruction grant is designed for associations and communities wishing to reconstruct their apartment buildings. The grant may be combined with the renovation loan of KredEx to decrease the share of required self-financing, as well as with collected self-funds. Apartment buildings constructed since 1993 that do not belong in the renovation loan target group of KredEx may combine the grant with regular loan. The grant may be applied for in the amount of 15%, 25% and 35% of the total project cost depending on the level of integration in the reconstruction of the relevant apartment building. (KredEx, 2015) Having the opportunity to apply for the grant via the establishment of KredEx is already an important influencing mechanism in Estonia to increase the country's' energy efficiency. Yet, in order to be successful in his/her application, there are certain rules which one must apply. These rules have been described in the 2010 governmental regulation of conditions and procedures of "Support for the reconstruction of the apartment buildings" (Rohelise..., 2010).

e) Implementation network

To apply for the grant, a relevant application shall be submitted to the bank issuing the renovation loan. If an applicant has sufficient self-financing for the construction work and does not use the renovation loan, or the grant is necessary for the reconstruction of an apartment building completed after year 1993, the application shall be submitted to KredEx by mail. A prerequisite for applying for the grant is the existence of an energy audit (also an annex to the audit, if necessary) and building design(s). The grant shall be paid upon the completion of all construction tasks (Kredex, 2015).

g) Outcomes

Through the help of KredEx funding, about 1.1 m² of living area has been renovated since 2009. However, this is only 5% of the overall living area which needs to be renovated in Estonia. In order to achieve the EU 20/20/20 targets, the yearly amount of living space needed to be renovated should be about 700 000 – 1000 000 m², which makes it obvious that relying only on the EU Structural Funds is not sufficient enough and therefore an additional state funding schemes must be implemented. The study conducted for the implementation of the Estonian Energy Sector Development Plan 2030+ states, that in order to fulfil the yearly renovation targets, the investment necessary to be made to the building fond must be around 330 million Euros (ENMAK 2030+, 2015).

Information about the current energy savings achieved thanks to the help of KredEx can be accessed from their analysis report 2010-2014. The following table provides information about the energy efficiency achieved in 2013 throughout different Estonian counties, according to 314 houses renovated in total:

Table 1. Energy savings in Estonian houses in 2013 after the implementation of KredEx renovation fund

	Number of houses	2013 savings in kWh	Savings in euros
Tallinn	153	18 835 839	1 488 031
Tartu	31	4 367 870	279 544
Harjumaa	43	3 566 858	267 514
Tartumaa	19	1 667 597	125 070
Pärnumaa	20	1 288 205	96 615
Ida-Virumaa	6	998 427	74 882
Lääne-Virumaa	7	895 827	67 187
Raplamaa	10	638 517	47 889
Valgamaa	4	626 060	46 955
Viljandimaa	6	402 608	30 196
Jõgevamaa	5	246 233	18 467
Saaremaa	2	226 290	16 972
Läänemaa	3	197 523	14 814
Järvamaa	2	116 447	8 734
Põlvamaa	1	65 253	8 734
Võrumaa	1	45 793	3 434
Hiiumaa	1	22 453	1 684
Total	314	34 207 800	2 592 882

Source: Korterehamute renoveerimisturu..., 2014, pp 21-22.

1.1.4 Capacity building and networking

The environmental awareness of public (especially that in terms of energy efficiency) in Estonia is yet weak; however there are a number of training and education programmes given by the consultants of Tallinn University of Technology and Tartu University. Yet one of the biggest achievements in the awareness rising is gained by the Foundation KredEx, particularly by its Energy Savings Competence Centre.

1.1.4.1 Energy Savings Competence Centre of KredEx

a) General information

As of January 2006, a state financed Energy Efficiency Competence Centre operates under Kredex. The aim of the competence centre is to manage and provide information related with energy saving measures in high-rise residential buildings (KredEx, 2015).

b) Type of policy instrument

The “Energy Savings Competence Centre of KredEx” belongs to the policy type “Energy information, advice and awareness rising”. Although KredEx itself is mainly an economic support mechanism, its Energy Savings Competence Centre is an instrument which aims for knowledge increase and support of energy efficiency education.

c) Objectives

The main goals of the competence centre is to:

- Promote smart energy saving measures in apartment buildings;
- administer information concerning the energy saving topics for all apartment buildings;
- find common grounds between different parties related to the further use of energy consumption development in buildings in Estonia.

d) Target groups

The main target groups are:

- apartment associations
- apartment cooperatives
- communities of apartment owners
- housing maintenance managers
- private house owners

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Raising awareness of residents on energy efficiency measures in Estonia by KredEx Energy Savings Competence Centre is done through different courses, seminars and campaigns, as well as through wider channels such as media (radio, TV).

f) Implementation network

The awareness raising activities of KredEx fall under its Energy Savings Competence Centre which currently consists of 2 staff members.

g) Outcomes

The outcomes described under “Economic policy instruments” apply also as the same outcomes under this section. The KredEx Energy Savings Competence Centre is established in order to raise awareness, motivate more people to renovate their homes, teach them the benefits they can achieve by making their houses more energy efficient by using KredEx fund, etc.

In renovated apartment building, 45% of the heating costs could be saved, which makes it about half of the actual energy bill. The increasing energy costs and raised awareness have further helped Estonia to become more energy efficient. Yet, there is still a lot which is needed to be done (KredEx, 2015).

1.1.5 Promotion of energy services

The higher the potential in energy development and promotion activities, the higher the capabilities to implement changes in energy sector. In order to achieve the goals to become more energy efficient “Estonian Energy Technology Programme” was established in 2008 under the strategy of the “Knowledge based Estonia 2007-2013” (ENMAK 2030+, 2015). Today this document is not in use anymore, and the new energy development strategy directions and potentials have been studied for and implemented within the new Estonian Energy Development Plan 2030.

One of the things which was studied for the mentioned document, was the potential for nearly zero-energy buildings⁷ in Estonia (Eesti..., 2013). Directive [2010/31/EU](#) of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings requires all new buildings to be nearly zero-energy by the end of 2020. All new public buildings must be nearly zero-energy by the end of 2018. Its provisions cover energy needs for the heating of premises, the production of hot water, cooling, ventilation and lighting for new and existing buildings, whether they are residential or not (The European Parliament & The Council of the EU, 2010).

1.1.5.1 Pilot projects of zero-energy buildings

a) General information

In Estonia there are a quite a number of nearly zero energy pilot buildings already, the most recent one was built at the campus of Tallinn University of Technology in 2015. The first truly functioning “Smart house” has been designed by Smart House Competence Centre in Rakvere town (Rakvere Smart House Competence Centre, 2015) which was opened in May 2015. The capacity, knowledge, and lack of experience and experiments to achieve this ambitious EU target of nearly zero energy buildings in Estonia is however, not at the desirable level yet (Tuuleenergia..., 2014). Nevertheless, the relevant training courses for target groups have been started four-five years ago already. Still, there are a number of construction companies specialising on design and implementation of nearly zero energy buildings in private housing as well as in public buildings sector. Relevant market is rapidly developing and gaining high popularity for the people planning to build the private house.

b) Type of policy instrument

The “pilot projects of zero-energy buildings” belong to the policy type “policy instruments for the promotion of energy services”.

⁷ The definitions of nearly zero-energy-buildings differ by EU Member States as the building regulations and calculation methods may significantly differ from country to country. In the study “Overview of Member States information on NZEBs” by Ecofys Germany GmbH the Estonian definition is given as the following. A NZEB is a building which is characterised by sound engineering solutions, which is built according to the best possible construction practice, which employs energy efficiency and renewable energy technology solutions and whose energy performance indicator is greater than 0 kWh/m²/y but does not exceed the limit values established (Overview ..., 2014).

c) Objectives

The objective of the pilot projects is to understand and study the potential of fulfilling the goal of the European Union Directive [2010/31/EU](#). Nearly zero-energy buildings have very high energy performance and the low amount of energy that these buildings require comes mostly from renewable sources. All new buildings must be nearly zero-energy by the end of 2020 and all the new public buildings must be nearly zero-energy by 2018 (The European..., 2010).

d) Target groups

The target group for this task are all the EU member state countries who have formally established the requirements set in Directive [2010/31/EU](#). Yet, it is necessary to involve a great number of architects, construction experts, scientists, electrical engineers and other stakeholders involved in the decision making processes, who could start working for the implementation of achieving that EU goal in Estonia.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

In 2012, together with the State Real Estate Ltd (Riigi Kinnisvara AS) and Tallinn University of Technology, the instruction and guidance report for the establishment of the nearly zero-energy buildings was finalized. The aim of the guidance report is to bring out the differences in nearly zero-energy building solutions compared to conventional construction practices. Since the important choices are made in the initial stages of design, focusing on the preliminary design is an important step to ensure that energy efficiency in the nearly zero-energy buildings is achieved. The guideline is made for the architects, builders, project managers, contractors, energy efficiency and peripheral designers and all the others involved in the construction processes or decision making. The focus of the guidance report so far is mainly on the office buildings though, since this type of buildings are technically most demanding building types. However, the solutions can be applied also in other public buildings. (Real Estate Ltd, 2012)

Another guidance report was published by the order of KredEx also in 2012 with the focus on the residential buildings (Madalenergia- ..., 2012).

f) Implementation network

The implementation network equals with the target group.

g) Outcomes

As previously underlined, there are several pilot projects already in Estonia. However, in order to achieve the mass production of zero-energy buildings, even more pilot projects should be built as to further experiment the potential of achieving this EU target. The public sector should be the leading example for the residential sector. Some analysis could be however made on the example of the already existing pilot projects. The main worry so far seems to be the question whether achieving the EU goal is economically feasible or not. (Tuuleenergia ..., 2014) The research group of zero-energy buildings at Tallinn University of Technology (consisting of prof Jarek Kurnitsiki, prof Targo Kalamees, prof Hendrik Voll, PhD students Thalfeldt, Ergo Pikas, Erkki Seinre, Leena Paap, Mikk Maivel and MSc students) is thus yet very active in answering the most timely questions regarding the topic of zero-energy buildings in Estonia (Real Estate Ltd, 2015).

1.1.6 Policy instruments for research and development and BAT promotion

There are a number of services established in Estonia which promote research and development. In this respect, the Ministry of Economy and Communication is mainly working together with Foundation KredEx and Estonian Environment Investment Centre (EIC). In addition, active on the topics of energy efficiency are also bodies such as State Real Estate Company Ltd (RKAS) and Estonian Competition Authority (Konkurentsiamet). The completion of energy efficiency strategies and research on energy efficiency is also supported by the Estonian Development Fund (Eesti Arengufond). The ones directly dealing with buildings are Foundation KredEx and Riigi Kinnisvara AS (public buildings), whilst the other mentioned organizations are more of an indirect manners to promote energy efficiency in housing sector (Energy ..., 2015).

1.1.6.1 State supported schemes implemented by the Environmental Investment Centre EIC

a) General information

The foundation Environmental Investment Centre (EIC) was founded on 11 May 2000 by the Ministry of Finance. EIC performs as the implementing agency for the environmental projects funded by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), the European Social Fund (ESF) and the Cohesion Fund (CF). It also lends money for the implementation of environmental projects. From 2010 new financing measure was added to EIC's portfolio – the Green Investment Scheme, money which comes from the sale of the excess CO2 quota. Areas of financing will be decided by the buyers. The first funds channelled through EIC were for the renovation of the district heating networks, renovation of combined generation plants and more environmentally-sustainable boiler houses. Lately, the measures to support investments in the wind energy has joined the portfolio. In addition, the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) provided grants also for the renovation of combined generation plants, more environmentally-sustainable boiler houses and heating mainlines (EIC, 2015)

b) Type of policy instrument

The “state supported schemes implemented by the Environmental Investment Centre EIC” belongs to the policy type “Economic support mechanism”. It is a great source of funding for a wide range of environmental projects in Estonia. Promotion of sustainable energy services is one of the key areas of EIC. However, focus in terms of buildings energy efficiency under the mentioned scheme is still rather weak.

b) Objectives

The objectives of EIC include ensuring maximum efficiency for the benefit of the Estonian people, a healthy living environment, and resource-efficient development of the country. The environmental management programme of EIC supports all kinds of works to reduce the amount of emissions and pollutants coming from the energy industry and works towards the improvement of the ambient air quality. One of the objectives of the EIC is also to increase environmental awareness by supporting various activities aimed namely at increasing the awareness, educating and changing the attitudes of the people. Grants aimed at increasing environmental awareness are awarded from three sources: Environmental Programme, ERDF and ESF (EIC, 2015).

c) Target groups

The target group of EIC involves a wide range of applicants from all over Estonia who can enter their data to KIKAS database (SA Keskkonnainvesteeringute Keskuse andmebaas - Environmental Investment Centre Data System) in order to apply for the funding as to fulfil their environmental projects. There are about 2000 applications received a year. In 2014, majority of the funding was granted for the projects related to the water management, protection of atmospheric air and nature conservation. EIC helps to implement thousands of projects each year in order to improve and restore Estonian environmental condition, rectify environmental damage or reproduce natural resources (Yearbook 2014, 2015).

d) Rules and influencing mechanisms

EIC accepts applications twice a year. The applications must be submitted through electronic database KIKAS. The deadline for the applications is announced one month before the submission deadline and the process of decision making lasts for about 4-5 months (EIC, 2015).

e) Implementation network

EIC grants and loans are financed from four separate sources: the environmental fees of the Republic of Estonia, the European Union structural funds, part from the European Investment Bank's (EIB) loan to the Estonian State and the sale of Estonians' CO2 quotas (also known as Green Investment Scheme). The financing of the main activities has changed over the years – while in the early years grants were awarded mostly from the Estonian State funds, in recent years the volume of foreign aid projects has reached the same level (EIC, 2015).

d) Outcomes

Each year, EIC is giving out a report describing their annual successes, the projects which got funding and which have been implemented. The following table provides an overview of the payments made by EIC in 2014 for projects related to the renewable energy and protection of ambient air (yet no specific data is available on how much energy efficiency in housing sector particularly has been achieved due to the implementation of EIC funded projects):

Table 2. An overview of EIC payments in 2014 made for renewable energy and protection of ambient air projects

Payments for renewable energy and protection of ambient air projects		
2014	Projects	Payments EUR
Renewable energy	24	1,994,834
Ambient air	41	2,841,760
Co-financing	2	16,282
CF sustainable transportation development	1	15,385,184
ERDF extended use of renewable energy sources for the generation of energy	3	398,675
GIS extended use of renewable energy sources for the generation of energy and reconstruction of district heating networks	32	6,845,731
GIS supporting investments of the enterprises for the application of wind energy in electricity generation	1	1,455,875
GIS constructing energy-efficient street lightning	7	919,381
TOTAL	111	29,857,723

Source: Keskkonnauuringute Keskuse Aastaraamat 2014, pp 24.

1.1.7 Summary Table for the Buildings Sector in Estonia

Table 3 Main policy instruments in building sector in Estonia

Summary table: Buildings					
	Status quo	Objective	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Describe Implementation network
Regulation	Energy labelling of buildings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Be a tool for the flat owner to know, what electricity- and heat bills there will be. - To promote the use and ownership of energy efficient homes. 	From 2009 onward, the energy label must be given to all new buildings or its parts (except the buildings which have been recognized in accordance with the “Law on National Heritage”), including apartments which are to be sold or rented after January 1 st 2009.	The influencing mechanism of having an energy label on a building is quite rigid since it is an obligatory action from 2009 onward, thus non-compliance is not allowed. In addition, all the EU Directives and ambitions to reduce energy emissions sets further motivation for the government of Estonia and other local governments, to further implement and have control over energy labelling.	Energy label is given out by the entrepreneur issuing the energy labels who must have a corresponding legal relationship with a specialist who can prove his\her competence with a professional certificate. The awarding of qualifications for energy auditors and energy label publishers is done by the Union of Estonian Heating- and Ventilation Engineers. The qualification is awarded after the successful completion of the vocational training provided by the Open University of Tallinn University of Technology.
Transparency and information	Energy audit and advice and assistance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To provide technical and energy situation of the building, promote energy awareness - Assessment necessary for issuing of energy label 	Energy audit could be ordered by all kind of building\property owners who are interested in improving the energy efficiency of their building or who wants to know the technical situation of their property.	Issuing of an obligatory energy label might be a good motivation behind ordering an energy audit first. In addition, knowing what financial savings could be achieved, might as well be a good motivation to know what measures could improve one’s property.	Energy audit can be performed by any entrepreneur who has certain qualifications for it. The issuing of energy audit is led by specialist who complies with the rules set in paragraphs 1 and 2 of § 47 of the Building Act.
Incentives and financing	The Credit and Export Guarantee Fund (KredEx Fund).	To provide grants for installing renewable energy generation installations for private households (solar panels, wind generators, heat pumps, etc.) and also, for energetic refurbishment, as well as guarantees for loans for	Anyone wishing to renovate his\her home can apply for KredEx fund, however, apartment associations has been one of the main stakeholders.	The reconstruction grant is explicitly designed for associations and communities, as well as private households wishing to reconstruct their apartment buildings. In order to decrease the share of required self-financing, the grant may be combined with a KredEx loan. Aging housing	A prerequisite for applying for the grant is the existence of an energy audit, after what an application may be submitted to the bank or directly to Kredex (in case sufficient self-financing is there or loan is not needed).

		reconstruction of multi-storey apartment houses to improve their energy efficiency.		conditions and increasing energy prices most probably are the main influential factors for people to renovate their homes, and thus apply for the grant.	
Capacity building and networking	Energy Savings Competence Centre of KredEx	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote smart energy saving measures in apartment buildings; - administer information concerning the energy saving topics for all apartment buildings; - find common grounds between different parties related to the further use of energy consumption development in buildings in Estonia. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - apartment associations - apartment cooperatives - communities of apartment owners -housing maintenance managers 	Raising awareness of residents on energy efficiency measures in Estonia by KredEx Energy Savings Competence Centre is done through different courses, seminars and campaigns, as well as through wider channels such as media (radio, TV).	Energy Saving Competence Centre itself (created under Foundation KredEx) with its 2 staff members.
Promotion of energy services	Pilot projects of zero-energy buildings	To understand and study the potential of fulfilling the goal of the European Union Directive 2010/31/EU .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All the EU member state countries who have formally established the requirements set in Directive 2010/31/EU - Necessary to involve a high amount of architects, builders, scientists , electrical engineers, and other stakeholders involved in the decision making processes 	Obligations set by EU and different guidance reports.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - All the EU member state countries who have formally established the requirements set in Directive 2010/31/EU - Necessary to involve a high amount of architects, builders, scientists , electrical engineers, and other stakeholders involved in the decision making processes
RD&D and BAT promotion	State supported schemes implemented by the Environmental Investment Centre EIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure maximum efficiency for the benefit of the Estonian people, a healthy living environment, and resource-efficient development of the country - Increase environmental awareness 	The target group for EIC grants involves a wide range of applicants from all over Estonia who wish to apply for projects related to the environment.	EIC accepts applications twice a year, with the deadline for the applications announced one month before the submission.	EIC grants and loans are financed from four separate sources: the environmental fees of the Republic of Estonia, the European Union structural funds, part from the European Investment Bank's (EIB) loan to the Estonian State and the sale of Estonians' CO2 quotas (also known as Green Investment Scheme).

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

As energy efficiency is not a primary goal for most of the existing policies and the energy saving impacts are either not thoroughly assessed or monitored for these policies, there is only very little data available for energy efficiency impacts of the selected transport policy instruments. Yet some can be underlined.

1.2.1 PLANNING INSTRUMENTS

1.2.1.1 Development of regional and local public transport connections

a) General information

Within the framework of national implementation for EU structural funds 2014-2020, Estonia has set 3 different funding schemes for improvement of railway connections, public transport and pedestrian and cycling infrastructure (Ühtekuuluvuspoliitika..., 2015). These include support schemes for:

- improvement of rail connections and accessibility to railway stations
- sustainable development of urban areas
- sustainable development of Ida-Viru county cities
- increasing the competitiveness of the regions

During the previous EU funding period all rolling stock of commuter and long-distance passenger trains in Estonia were renewed.

b) Type of policy instrument

Planning, financial.

c) Objectives

Improve system efficiency by improving passenger rail, regional and local public transport connections and pedestrian and cycling facilities. The instrument targets energy efficiency implicitly and no concrete energy efficiency targets are set.

d) Target groups

10 major Estonian cities, municipalities with railway connection, rail company Elron. Multi-modal transport users (especially car) with a potential to cover part of their journey by train.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The projects have to be selected based on sustainable urban development strategies, 15% co-funding requirement, public procurement rules.

f) Implementation network

Ministry of Interior, Ministry of Economy and Communications, Enterprise Estonia, Environmental Investment Centre, Technical Regulatory Authority.

g) Outcomes

The schemes do not have explicit energy efficiency targets. As outputs the schemes have defined following targets:

- improvement of accessibility to at least 20 railway stations (outside Tallinn);
- improvement of consumer satisfaction among public transport users, pedestrians and cyclists (30 improved connections);
- 60 km of new cycling infrastructure;
- 3 new public transport improvement projects;
- new rolling stock for passenger train fleet.

1.2.2 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS

1.2.2.1 Maximum parking standard in Tallinn city centre

a) General information

Tallinn parking development plan sets parking standards, among different parking zones, Tallinn city centre developments are set a maximum parking provision standard that the developer is not allowed to exceed (Tallinna..., 2006).

b) Type of policy instrument:

Regulatory.

c) Objectives

Improve transport system efficiency by managing the supply side of car-based infrastructure.

d) Target groups

Real estate developers and property owners in Tallinn city centre. Car users and car owners.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The regulation sets parking standards for different zones in Tallinn city, including maximum standard for city centre.

f) Implementation network

Tallinn Transport Department⁸ is responsible for implementing the parking norm, on-street parking regulations and management of parking in general, Tallinn Urban Planning Department⁹ is responsible for implementing the parking norm in detailed planning processes and building permits.

g) Outcomes

No relevant studies have been carried out.

1.2.3 FINANCIAL POLICY INSTRUMENTS

1.2.3.1 Increasing fuel excise duty

a) General information

Fuel excise duty is imposed on different kinds of liquid fuel, solid fuel and natural gas. The current Alcohol, Tobacco, Fuel and Electricity Excise Duty Act, which was adopted on 4 December 2002, has been amended several times, most recently on 1 July 2015. The fuel excise has been raised on ten occasions in the last 15 years.

In June 2015, the Estonian parliament, *Riigikogu*, has decided to raise excise duty rate on petrol 10 percent each year from 2016–2019, and on diesel 14 percent in 2016, and 10 percent thereafter (4). The higher rate for diesel stemmed from the wish to tax diesel and petrol more equally. This should increase the state income from motor fuel excise from 59.3 million euros in 2016 to 85.3 million in 2018.

Table 4 Excise duty rates per 1,000 litres of liquid fuels

Excise duty rate per 1,000 litres of liquid fuel / Entry into force	1.01.2010	1.01.2016	1.01.2017	1.01.2018
Petrol, incl. unleaded petrol and aviation spirit (€)	422.77	+10% 465	+10% 512	+10% 563
Diesel fuel (€)	392.92	+14% 448	+10% 493	+10% 542

Alkoholi-, tubaka-, kütuse- ja elektriaktsiisi seadus. (2003). [Alcohol, Tobacco, Fuel and Electricity Excise Duty Act] Riigi Teataja I 2003, 2, 17. accessible at: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/ee/518062015016/consolide/current> (23.07.2015).

b) Type of policy instrument

Financial policy instrument, belonging to the policy type: tax increase.

⁸ <http://www.tallinn.ee/Parking-in-Tallinn>

⁹ <http://www.tallinn.ee/eng/Urban-Planning-Department>

c) Objectives

According to the explanatory report of the draft Act, the increase of excise rate aims at raising the state tax revenues and reducing fuel consumption.

d) Target group

Consumers of motor fuels (directly and indirectly), road transport.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The excise duty rates will be increased in 3 years as presented in **Fehler! Verweisquelle konnte nicht gefunden werden.**

f) Implementation network

The Ministry of Finance develops the tax policy and coordinates its implementation. The Tax and Customs Board, a government agency within the area of government of the Ministry of Finance, collects the state's tax revenues.

g) Outcomes

Although the primary instrument for influencing energy use in the transport sector has been excise duties, the households' response to motor fuel excise has been low and consumption of a taxed good has not decreased significantly over the past 15 years (Poltimäe, 2014). Energy consumption in transport has grown at the same rate as GDP and purchasing power has grown quicker than fuel excise duty (Jüssi et al., 2010). Depending on the development of fuel world market prices, the transport energy saving potential study commissioned during the elaboration of Estonian Energy Sector Development Plan 2030+, estimated that 15% increase in fuel excise duty (at constant fuel prices) will lead to a reduction of 2-3% (ca 900-1000 TJ/year) of transport fuel consumption (Jüssi et al., 2014). Based on these estimates, the likely impact on energy saving of this policy is ca 5-8% for diesel vehicles and 4-7% for petrol vehicles, resulting in the energy saving in the order of 1800-2000 TJ/year by 2020 (Table 5).

Table 5 Savings expected/ estimated due to increasing fuel excise duty

Policy instrument	Recorded Savings 2009-2013 (in PJ)	Expected/estimated Savings total 2014-2020 (in PJ)
Increasing fuel excise duty	Not recorded	1800-2000 TJ/year, estimated (based on Jüssi et al, 2014)

1.2.4 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS

1.2.4.1 Energy labelling of passenger cars

Currently there are no policy instruments in place that explicitly target transport energy efficiency. Ministry of Environment is currently drafting an act for energy labelling of passenger cars.

a) General information

“National regulation on the communication of fuel consumption and CO₂ emissions of new passenger cars” is currently redrafted to introduce energy labelling system for new passenger cars sold in Estonia. It is the direct outcome of one of the policy recommendations proposed by Sustainable Transport Report 2010 (Jüssi, et al., 2010) which highlighted the energy saving potential of passenger car fleet and lack of awareness raising measures similar to electric appliances. Labelling is compulsory for new cars and voluntary for second-hand cars.

b) Type of policy instrument

Regulatory

c) Objectives

Increase awareness about the energy consumption and options for consumers, to reduce energy consumption in transport.

d) Target groups whether the policy instrument

Consumers buying new cars, car retail companies.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Not specified in the regulation.

f) Implementation network

Road Administration is responsible for implementing the database of cars and their energy label/CO₂ emissions and designing the label. Car retail companies are responsible for updating the labels once a year and displaying the energy label at sales points.

g) Outcomes

The regulation and accompanying documents do not set any targets in terms of consumer awareness nor behaviour. During the writing of the transport energy saving potential study (Jüssi et al 2014) SEI-Tallinn carried out a literature survey on potential impacts on energy labelling of cars, however no relevant studies were found on the impacts of energy labelling of cars in the context of lacking fiscal measures (like vehicle taxation related to energy classes).

1.2.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

1.2.5.1 Smart City Cluster

a) General information

Smart City cluster (smartcitylab.eu) is part of the Estonian National Cluster Programme and is linked with 18 industrial cluster initiatives supported by the programme.

The cluster supports the fulfilment of the strategic development objectives set down in the sector strategy “Knowledge-Based Estonia. Estonian Research and Development and Innovation Strategy 2007-2013”. It is co-financed by the EU Structural funds (European Regional Development Fund), in the period of 1.08.2012 – 31.07.2015.

The cluster is designed to create an innovative environment in Tartu, the 2nd largest city in Estonia, by bringing together businesses, citizens, public authorities, R&D institutes and structures that support innovation.

b) Type of policy instrument

Policy instrument for Research and Development in the policy type: funding of public and private R&D for sustainable transport.

c) Objectives

Smart City e- and m-Services Cluster is aiming at development, delivery and export of smart ICT and mobile based services and products in the following priority areas: Transport, Energy and Environment, Tourism, Healthcare and Wellbeing, Governance and public services.

The solutions created will eventually be introduced in other towns and cities in Estonia and elsewhere around the world.

d) Target group

Cluster membership can be applied by all registered companies in Estonia and abroad, local governments, educational establishments and other sector specific NGOs and organisations. Covers all modes of transport.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Membership fee start from 10 000 euros per 3 years for larger companies and 3 000 euros for smaller companies and will be agreed on as a result of the negotiations with the board of the cluster. Benefits of the membership include participation in sector specific joint actions, in global network of contacts and new cooperation possibilities and in shaping the future of the sector.

f) Implementation network

As of July 2015, 17 organisations have become a member of the cluster.

Funding agency: The Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications. The members of the cluster pay the co-financing.

Administering agency: Enterprise Estonia

g) Outcomes

Completed pilot projects in transport:

- Needs assessment for developing an application of buying, selling and checking the public transport tickets,
- Study for developing a tool of participatory public transportation planning,
- Study and prototype of mobile application for public transportation information system.

Energy efficiency improvement assessment of the cluster has not been carried out.

1.2.6 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR IN ESTONIA

Table 6 Main policy instruments in transport sector in Estonia

	Short list of implemented policies and measures	Objective ¹⁰ (improve system, travel or vehicle efficiency)	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Implementation network
Planning instruments	Development of regional and local public transport connections	Improve system efficiency	Local municipalities, all transport users, railway stations	The projects have to be selected based on sustainable urban development strategies, 15% co-funding requirement, public procurement rules	Ministry of Interior, Ministry of Economy and Communications, Enterprise Estonia, Estonian Environmental Investment Fund, Technical Regulatory Authority, local municipalities
Regulatory policy instruments	Maximum parking standards in Tallinn centre	Improve system efficiency	Developers, property owners, car users and owners	Building permit depends on compliance with the regulation	Tallinn city government
Financial policy instruments	Fuel excise duty, annual increase by 10% 2016-2018	Improve system, travel and vehicle efficiency	Consumers of motor fuels: diesel and petrol, especially road transport	Gradual increase of fuel excise rate 2016-2018	Ministry of Finance, Tax and Customs Board
Dissemination and awareness instruments	Energy labelling of new cars	Improve vehicle efficiency	Consumers buying new cars, car retail companies	Not specified	Estonian Road Administration
Policy instruments for Research and Development	Smart City cluster	Improve system and travel efficiency	Companies, local governments, educational establishments, NGOs	Membership fee	Ministry of Economic Affairs, Enterprise Estonia, 17 member organisations

¹⁰ Energy efficiency in the transport sector can be divided into system efficiency (reduce or avoid travel or the need to travel), travel efficiency (shift to more energy efficient modes) and vehicle efficiency (improve the efficiency through vehicle technology).

2. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE REGIONAL / LOCAL LEVEL

The interaction between the different levels (national, regional, local) in energy efficiency policy making has already been covered in D.1.1. Next to national energy efficiency policies, many regions and cities have implemented own climate action plans, energy efficiency action plans, or are part of the Covenant of Mayors. Describing all existing policy instruments or energy efficiency measures, would be too voluminous to perform and is not possible in the frame of this project. Therefore, specific policy instrument on the regional / local level are exemplarily covered by a case study. In case of Estonia, a case study only on building sector has been drawn out. There is currently no example to give on a transport sector in terms of the vertical integration of local actions into the national energy efficiency framework and vice versa.

2.1 PRESENTATION OF THE CASE STUDY: PROJECT “FASSAADID KORDA”

- **City / Region:** Tallinn/ Harjumaa
- **Energy Efficiency Policy / Action:**

When it comes to energy efficiency policies, measures and instruments in Estonia, Tallinn is probably the front runner out of all the Estonian cities. Tallinn has joined the Covenant of Mayors on 15.02.2009 in order to implement measures given by EU climate-and energy package. By joining the Covenant of Mayors, Tallinn took the following commitments:

- To exceed the targets set by EU 20/20 Directive, reducing CO₂ emissions by at least 20% by implementing a Sustainable Energy Action Plan within their fields of competence ;
- to draw up the emissions inventory which provides the basis for the Sustainable Energy Action Plan;
- to submit a Sustainable Energy Action Plan one year after formally signing the Covenant of Mayors;
- to adapt city structures, including allocation of sufficient human resources in order to take the necessary measures;
- to create an implementation report in at least every two years after the submission of the Action Plan for the purpose of evaluation, monitoring and verification.
- to organize so called Energy Days or City Covenant Days in collaboration with European Commission and other stakeholders, allowing citizens to benefit directly from the opportunities and advantages what more intelligent use of energy could offer, and to regularly inform the local media on developments concerning the action plan;
- to participate every year on an annual conference organized by the Mayors of the EU, on sustainable energy and provide input. (Linnapeade..., 2015)

In the period following accession to the Covenant of Mayors, the Environment Agency started the implementation of the up-listed tasks. CO₂ emissions inventory was organized, as well as energy days and an action plan for Tallinn on sustainable energy was established (Linnapeade..., 2015).

In line with the Tallinn City Council Decision No. 27 of 10 March 2011, "Tallinn sustainable energy action plan for the period of 2011-2021" was introduced. To implement the objectives set in the aforementioned document, as well as for the implementation of the objectives, an implementation plan must be developed, which would set short-term operating prospects for the next three years of operation (Linnapeade..., 2015).

Tasks in the field of energy are divided by the Environment Agency, the city planning agency, neighbourhood councils, Municipal Services, Transportation Authority and Business Enterprise Agency. This makes controlling the implementation of "Tallinn sustainable energy action plan for the period of 2011-2021" a rather difficult task. In order to gather the information provided by different city authorities, Tallinn Energy Agency was established (Linnapeade..., 2015).

The specialists of Tallinn Energy Agency manage all the tasks which come from the obligations taken by joining the Covenant of Mayors and if possible, initiate and implement foreign-financed projects related to sustainable energy projects (Linnapeade..., 2015).

- **Energy Efficiency instrument / measure in building sector:**

Project "Fassaadid korda" ("Renovation of facades") is a project started by the City of Tallinn as of 1st of June 2009 onward, within the framework of the aid package to the city of Tallinn. The project "Fassaadid korda" is a co-operation project which works together with KredEx funding scheme. In order to receive KredEx funding, one must have the capability to provide his\her own self-funding to it. Thus, "Fassaadid korda" helps to cover the self-funding part of it. Within this project, necessary self-financing support is provided to the apartment associations in order to help them renovate their apartment buildings. Like that, the apartment associations` capability to get the financial grant and thus increase the energy efficiency of buildings as well as lower the heating costs during the winter. In addition, the appearance of houses will be improved. The target group for the renovation fund are the apartment blocks built before 1993 and which have an energy audit. The amount of the grant given depends on the amount of the renovation fund requested by the apartment association, as support will be given maximum of up to 10% of the requested amount (however not more than 19 173 euros per year) (Fassaadid..., 2015).

- **Interaction between national and local policies:**

"Fassaadid korda" is an initiative started directly by the city of Tallinn. Since the project works closely together with the funding provided by Foundation KredEx, started by the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communication (MEAC), there is a direct linkage in terms of co-operation between national (MEAC) and local (City of Tallinn) policies. The responsibilities of Tallinn City administration have been divided between 8 different city district councils. Thus also the overview of facades renovation has been divided between different councils which fall under the City of Tallinn.

- **Discussion / Recommendations:**

The project "Fassaadid korda" benefits the inhabitants of Tallinn only, being one of the reasons why majority of the KredEx applications have been done in Tallinn. Thus the barrier of the introduced case study is its overlay local character which is a pitfall for the other local Municipalities in Estonia and the overall Estonian energy efficiency in building sector in general. Another barrier might be the rules

(requirements for grant applicants and applications) and a rather long application procedure which one must go through in order to apply both for KredEx and grants provided by “Fassaadid korda” project. For instance, since the target group of the project are the buildings built before 1993, and most of them do not have the required energy audit, it is quite a long and motivation costly procedure for the applicant to apply for the funding. On the other hand, the benefit is that under the KredEx Foundation, free consultancy is offered for anyone who wants to apply for the renovation fund. Yet a set of requirements, such as an obligation for the applicant to be registered in the register of non-profit organization and foundations register at least six months prior to the application, makes it a time costly procedure for an applicant in case she or he is not yet fulfilling the requirements. Thus perhaps softer requirements could be implemented in the future.

- **Further information:**

The website of the described project is accessible at: <http://www.tallinn.ee/fassaadidkorda/>, and the general contact person is Mr. Peep Lass from Tallinn Municipal Services (e-mail: Peep.Lass@tallinnlv.ee).

REFERENCES

- ÅF-Consulting AS, <http://www.estivo.ee/en/> (30.07.2015).
- Alkoholi-, tubaka-, kütuse- ja elektriaktsiisi seadus. (2003). RT I 2007, 45, 319 [Alcohol, Tobacco, Fuel and Electricity Excise Duty Act] Riigi Teataja I 2003, 2, 17. Available online: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/en/eli/ee/518062015016/consolide/current> (23.07.2015).
- Allikmaa, A., Kalamees, T., Kurnitski, J., Kuusk, K., Pikas, E., Tark, T., Uutal, A. (2013). Eesti energiamajanduse arengukava ENMAKi uuendamise hoonete energiasäästupotentsiaali uuring, Elamu energiaauditi aruande vorminõuded ja väljastamise kord. (2014). RT I, 11.03.2014, 4 [The formal requirements of energy audit of the residential buildings and its issuing procedure] Riigi Teataja 04.03.2014 nr. 16. Available online: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/111032014004> (28.07.2015).
- Energiamärgise vorm ja väljastamise kord, RTL 2008, 100, 1428 [The form of the energy label and its issuing procedure] Riigi Teataja 17.12.2008 nr. 107. Available online: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/13094120> (30.07.2015).
- Energiasäästu Büroo, Energy audit. Available online: <http://www.energiaaudit.ee/services/energy-audit/?lang=en> (28.07.2015).
- Estonia 2013, Energy Policies beyond IEA Countries. (2013). OECD/IEA. Available online: https://www.iea.org/publications/freepublications/publication/Estonia2013_free.pdf (01.07.2015).
- European Parliament & European Council. (2010). Directive [2010/31/EU](http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:153:0013:0035:EN:PDF). Available online: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:153:0013:0035:EN:PDF> (30.07.2015).
- Fassaadid korda, Tallinna Linnavalitsus. Available online: <http://www.tallinn.ee/est/kesklinn/Fassaadid-korda> (03.08.2015).
- Foundation KredEx: Available online: <http://www.kredex.ee/en/> (30.07.2015).
- Hoonefondi energiatõhususe parandamine – energiasääst, ühikmaksumused ja mahud. Available online: http://www.energiatalgud.ee/img_auth.php/5/51/ENMAK_2030_Hoonete_energias%C3%A4%C3%A4stupotentsiaali_uuring.pdf (29.07.2015).
- Jüssi, M., Poltimäe, H., Orru, H., Metspalu, P. (2014). Energiamajanduse arengukava ENMAK 2030+ Eesti transpordi ja liikuvuse energiasäästupotentsiaali uuring. Available online: <http://www.seit.ee/et/publikatsioonid?id=4524> (01.08.2015).
- Kalamees, T., Tark, T. (2012). Madalenergia- ja liginullenergiahoone kavandamine, Juhend väikeelamu projekteerijale, ehitajale ja tellijale. Available online: http://kredex.ee/public/Uuringud/Madalenergia-ja_liginullenergiahoone_kavandamine_Vaikeelamu.pdf (30.07.2015).
- Keskkonnainvesteeringute Keskus [Environmental Investment Centre]. Available online: <http://www.kik.ee/en> (30.07.2015).
- Keskkonnauuringute Keskuse Aastaraamat 2014 [Environmental Investment Centre Yearbook 2014]. Available online: http://kik.ee/sites/default/files/kik_ar_2014_eng.pdf (29.07.2015).
- Korterelamute renoveerimisturu ülevaade ja perioodi 2010-2014 korterelamute rekonstrueerimistoetuste mõju analüüs. (2014). [An overview of renovations made in the apartment

building and analysis of the impacts of renovation funding during the period of 2010-2014], ordered by KredEx, page 21-22. Available online: http://kredex.ee/public/Uuringud/Korterelamute_analuus_030914.pdf (30.07.2015).

Linnapeade pakt, Tallinna Linnavalitsus. Available online: <http://www.tallinn.ee/est/energiaagentuur/Linnapeade-pakt> (03.08.2015).

Ministry of Economic Affairs and Communications, Energy Performance of Buildings. Available online: <https://www.mkm.ee/et/eesmargid-tegevused/ehitus-ja-elamumajandus/hoonete-energiatohusus> (28.07.2015).

Nõuded energiamärgise andmisele ja energiamärgisele RT I, 06.05.2015, 2 [Requirements for certification for energy and the energy label] Riigi Teataja 30.04.2015 nr. 36. Available online: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/106052015002> (30.07.2015).

Poltimäe, H. (2014). The distributional and behavioural effects of Estonian environmental taxes. Dissertationes Rerum Oeconomicarum Universitatis Tartuensis 49. University of Tartu Press. Available online: http://dspace.utlib.ee/dspace/bitstream/handle/10062/40552/poltimae_helen.pdf?sequence=1 (23.07.2015).

Rakvere Smart House Competence Centre. Available online: <http://www.rakveretarkmaja.ee/> (30.07.2015).

Rohelise investeerimisskeemi "Korterelamute rekonstrueerimise toetus" kasutamise tingimused ja kord RT I 2010, 58, 397 [Conditions and procedures for the support for the reconstruction of the apartment buildings] Riigi Teataja 17.08.2010 nr 52. Available online: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/13359879> (01.08.2015).

Smart City Lab. Available online: <http://smartcitylab.eu/> (24.07.2015).

State Real Estate Ltd [Riigi Kinnisvara AS]. Available online: <http://www.rkas.ee> (30.07.2015).

Tallinna parkimise arengukava aastateks 2006-2014. Available online: https://oigusaktid.tallinn.ee/?id=3001&aktid=106241#_Toc151543631 (30.07.2015).

Toetuse andmise tingimused investeringuteks raudteepeatuste ühendamiseks erinevate liikumisviisidega. (2014) RT I, 17.10.2014, 15 [The conditions for support for investment to connect the rail stops with different of transport modes] Riigi Teataja 15.10.2014 nr 88. Available online: <https://www.riigiteataja.ee/akt/117102014015> (01.08.2015).

Ühtekuuluvuspoliitika Fondide rakenduskava meetmete nimekiri koos jõustunud õigusaktide ja seletuskirjadega. (2015). Available online: <http://www.struktuurifondid.ee/struktuuritoetuse-seaduse-meetmepohised-oigusaktid-2/> (23.7.2015).

HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.1.2

STATUS-QUO ANALYSIS OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICIES IN 8 EU COUNTRIES

PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT

NATIONAL REPORT FOR GERMANY

JULY, 31ST 2015

Partner: *Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment, Energy*

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

OXFORD
BROOKES
UNIVERSITY

Universiteit
Antwerpen

Wuppertal Institute
for Climate, Environment
and Energy

SEI

STOCKHOLM
ENVIRONMENT
INSTITUTE

Institution: Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment, Energy

Steering Committee member ⁽¹⁾: Dr. Ralf Schüle

Prepared by: Thomas Adisorn, Carolin Schäfer-Sparenberg, Lena Tholen, Hanna Hüging, Dr. Ralf Schüle, Jonas Fischer, Jan Kaselofsky

⁽¹⁾ *The Steering Committee member has the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the report.*

HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	FEHLER! TEXTMARKE NICHT DEFINIERT.
GLOSSARY	FEHLER! TEXTMARKE NICHT DEFINIERT.
ACRONYMS	5
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL	7
1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE BUILDINGS SECTOR	7
1.1.1 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS	8
1.1.2 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS / INFORMATIVE POLICY INSTRUMENTS	14
1.1.3 ECONOMIC POLICY INSTRUMENTS	20
1.1.4 CAPACITY BUILDING AND NETWORKING	27
1.1.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR THE PROMOTION OF ENERGY SERVICES	33
1.1.6 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT AND BEST AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGY (BAT) PROMOTION	35
1.1.7 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR IN GERMANY	39
1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR	43
1.2.1 PLANNING INSTRUMENTS	44
1.2.2 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS	49
1.2.3 ECONOMIC INSTRUMENTS	51
1.2.4 INFORMATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS.....	57
1.2.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT	62
1.2.6 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR IN GERMANY	65
2. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE REGIONAL / LOCAL LEVEL	68
2.1 PRESENTATION OF THE CASE STUDY: THE CLIMATE ACTION PLAN OF THE CITY OF HAMBURG, GERMANY	68
2.1.1 OVERVIEW OF THE ENERGY EFFICIENCY ACTIONS OF THE CITY OF HAMBURG: THE CITY ACTION PLAN 2007-2012	68
2.1.2 ENERGY EFFICIENCY INSTRUMENTS: EXAMPLES FOR THE BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTOR	70
2.1.3 INTERACTION BETWEEN NATIONAL AND LOCAL POLICIES	73
2.1.4 DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	73
2.1.5 FURTHER INFORMATION	74
ANNEXES	FEHLER! TEXTMARKE NICHT DEFINIERT.
REFERENCES	75

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Development of building efficiency and regulations in Germany (kWh/m²a primary energy)	9
Figure 2: Example of an Dena Efficient House Quality Mark	19
Figure 3: Exemplary Fuel Efficiency Labelling of Passenger Cars	58
Figure 4: Hamburg's climate action plan: Number of measures and share in total funding by field of activity 69	

Table of Tables

Table 1: Overview of selected policy instruments in Germany	7
Table 2: Energy savings according to the NEEAP	10
Table 3: Energy savings according the German Federal Government	15

Table 4: Forecast of final energy saving according to Article 7	16
Table 5: Final energy savings according to the Article 7	17
Table 6: Efficiency classification of efficiency houses	19
Table 7: Efficiency house and available incentives through KfW	20
Table 8: Forecasts of final energy savings according to the third NEEAP.....	22
Table 9: Forecasts of final energy savings according to the third NEEAP:.....	23
Table 10: Forecast of final energy savings according to the third NEEAP	24
Table 11: Forecast of final energy savings of the MAP according to the third NEEAP	26
Table 12: Savings according to Article 7 notifications of the EED.....	27
Table 13: Forecast of final energy savings according to the NAPE	28
Table 14: Forecast of final energy savings according to the third NEEAP	30
Table 15: Overview of measures implemented in Germany	39
Table 16: Overview of selected policy instruments for the transport sector in Germany.....	43
Table 17: Estimated fuel and CO2 savings.....	52
Table 18: Assessment of energy savings by heavy goods vehicle toll charges.....	55
Table 19: Summary table for the German transport sector	65
Table 20: Subsidies available for individual measures.....	71
Table 21: Subsidies available for extensive refurbishments	71
Table 22: Subsidies available in the programme Energetische Modernisierung A	72

ACRONYMS

Dena – German Energy Agency, Deutsche Energieagentur

EnEV – Energy Saving Ordinance, Energieeinsparverordnung

KfW – Bank for Reconstruction, Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau

NAPE – National Action Plan on Energy Efficiency

NEEAP – National Energy Efficiency Action Plan

FTIP – Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan

NCP – National Cycling Plan

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In comparison to D 1.1 where policy packages are in the focus of analysis, this chapter presents single energy efficiency policy instruments implemented in Germany. For the buildings sector as well as for the transport sector most important policy instruments are described briefly.

The Germany **buildings sector** consumes a substantial amount (40%) of final energy in Germany. One of the reasons is that the majority of buildings was erected before the first minimum energy performance standard was established. Apart from that, less efficient building equipment or appliances contribute to excessive energy consumption. Through a package of policy instruments the Government seeks to drive down energy consumption of the German building stock.

In order to increase the energy efficiency in the **transport sector**, three different levels of energy efficiency connected with three basic strategies have to be taken into account, based on the Avoid-Shift-Improve (ASI) approach (e.g. Schipper and Marie-Liliu 1999, Dalkmann and Brannigan 2007, ADB 2009):

- Avoid travel or reduce travel-length in order to improve the system efficiency which concerns how transport is generated and how modes are chosen.
- Shift travel to more energy-efficient modes in order to improve the travel efficiency which covers the energy consumption of different transport modes.
- Improve the energy efficiency of vehicles and fuels in order to improve the vehicle efficiency which can be improved by reducing the vehicle's fuel consumption per kilometre.

For implementation, different instruments (planning, regulation, economic incentives, information and technology oriented measures) can be used.

For both sectors, summary tables of the described policy instruments are included.

The **interaction between the different levels** (national, regional, local) in energy efficiency policy making has already been covered in D.1.1. Next to national energy efficiency policies, many regions and cities have implemented own climate action plans, energy efficiency action plans, or are part of the Covenant of Mayors. Describing all existing policy instruments or energy efficiency measures, would be too much and is not possible in the framework of this project. Therefore, in this deliverable, specific policy instruments on the regional / local level are exemplarily covered by a case study of the **City of Hamburg**.

1. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL

Increasing energy efficiency has become one of the central pillar of Germany's energy and climate policy. In order to reduce the dependence on conventional fuels, enhance the security of energy supply and to mitigate global warming the Government established comprehensive policy packages in the building and transport sector.

In the following sections, this paper will initially focus on the buildings sector prior to moving on the transport sector. Both of these sections will give an overview of policy instruments implemented at the national level. More specifically, this includes some general background information, the type and objective of the policy instruments, its target groups, further rules or mechanisms affecting the policy as well as the implementation network and relevant results.

In the wake of this section, the interaction of different levels of energy efficiency policy making (national, regional, local) in Germany is presented.

An overview of "legislation governing Germany's energy supply system" can be found at: <http://www.bmwi.de/English/Redaktion/Pdf/gesetzeskarte,property=pdf,bereich=bmwi2012,sprache=en,rwb=true.pdf>.

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE BUILDINGS SECTOR

The Germany building sector consumes a substantial amount (40%) of final energy in Germany. One of the reason is that the majority of buildings was erected before the first minimum energy performance standard was established. Apart from that, less efficient building equipment or appliances contribute to excessive energy consumption. Through a package of policy instruments the Government seeks to drive down energy consumption of the German building stock.

The following table gives an overview of the measures presented in this paper.

Table 1: Overview of selected policy instruments in Germany

German policy instruments for the buildings sector	
Regulatory Policy Instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Saving Ordinance (EnEV) • Regular Inspection of boilers and (non-residential) air-conditioning • Heating Cost Regulation • Energy performance certificate
Dissemination and awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy checks • On-side energy consultation • Energy consultation for SMEs (KfW) • KfW construction monitoring • Dena Efficiency House Quality Mark
Economic policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KfW Energy-efficient Construction • KfW Energy Efficient Renovation • Energy tax and electricity tax • Market incentive programme • BAFA cross-cutting technologies
Capacity Building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy efficiency Networks Initiative LEEN • Promotion of energy management systems (EMS)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educational voucher for re-training towards energy advisors • Requirement guidelines for energy consultants and list of certified energy consultants • IPEEC (International Partnership for Energy Efficiency Cooperation)
Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centre of excellence - contracting for public buildings
Research and Development and BAT promotion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low energy buildings project (dena) and efficiency house Plus • Research initiative "Zukunft Bau" and Research for energy-optimised construction • Public procurement guidelines • 6. energy research programme

1.1.1 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS

The following section presents some of the most important regulatory policy instruments in Germany. Through the Energy Saving Ordinance (EnEV), the Government has established minimum energy performance standards for buildings, which are tightened regularly. This prevents very energy-inefficient buildings from entering the market. Moreover, by mandating regular inspections of boilers and of non-residential air-conditioning the Government also seeks to phase out very energy-inefficient building components. With respect to energy consumption, consumers receive regular feedback on space and water heating expenses, which is required by the Heating Cost Regulation. Since 2009, sellers or landlords are required to provide energy performance certificates to potential buyers or tenants of the respective building unit. Due to energy-related information buyers and tenants can assess the complete costs for a building unit. Putting it in a very rough nutshell, new energy wasting buildings are not allowed, inefficient building equipment is to be exchanged and building owners or tenants are made more aware of energy consumption and costs.

1.1.1.1 ENERGY SAVING ORDINANCE (ENEV)

a) General information

Through the EnEV¹, the German Government defines a minimum energy performance for both, newly erected buildings and existing buildings that undergo substantial renovations (BMWl 2014). Only a limited number of building types is beyond the scope of the EnEV such as churches or greenhouses (ASUE 2009).

The latest version of the EnEV, EnEV 2014, implemented the decisions taken by the German Federal Government on its Energy Concept and the energy transition, as well as transposed the provisions of Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and the Council on the energy performance of buildings.

The catalogue of criteria used in the EnEV refers to the building envelope as well as technical installations. For instance, considering the latest revision of the EnEV made in 2014, in new

¹ http://www.enev-online.com/enev_2014_volltext/enev_2014_verkuendung_bundesgesetzblatt_21.11.2013.pdf

residential and non-residential buildings erected after 01.01.2016 thermal insulation has to be enhanced by around 20% compared to buildings completed before that date. Moreover, according to EnEV 2014, certain types of boilers must be exchanged if their lifespan exceeds 30 years (dena 2015a) (see next chapter).

Technically speaking, EnEV was put into effect only in 2002. However, it has de facto been integrating preceding regulations determining the energy use of buildings such as the Thermal Insulation Ordinance (Germ. Wärmeschutzverordnung) already introduced in 1977. Generally, every few years criteria of the EnEV are updated and tightened. The next changes are scheduled for 2016.

Figure 1: Development of building efficiency and regulations in Germany (kWh/m²a primary energy)

Source: Fraunhofer IBP & BMWi as found in BMWi 2014, p. 26

b) Type of policy instrument

The Energy Saving Regulation is a regulatory policy instrument – buildings have to comply with performance requirements set.

c) Objective

Since the EnEV is frequently adjusted, the regulation directly aims at phasing out energy-inefficient buildings and, hence, to transform the building market, the market for building components and certain types of technologies (e.g. boilers). In doing so, the instrument strives, among other things, for lowering energy consumption in the building sector and for mitigating CO₂ emissions.

d) Target group

The target group consists of investors that seek to erect a new building or to undertake substantial renovations. Architects, construction companies and installation contractors meet the demands stated in the EnEV.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Through the EU's Directive on Energy Performance of Buildings (EPBD), member states have to safeguard that only nearly zero-energy-buildings will be erected from 2021 onwards. Germany's EnEV that is gradually tightened contributes to meeting this goal. For existing buildings undergoing substantial renovations, the Government offers financial incentives if the building complies with or exceeds a certain set of EnEV standards. New buildings may also receive financial support, but only if they significantly exceed EnEV standards. EnEV also mandates building owners to disclose energy performance certificates in case of selling or letting a buildings.

In the case of violation of EnEV rules, fines will be imposed. These fines range between EUR 5,000 and EUR 50,000 (http://www.enev-online.com/enev_praxishilfen/enev_2014_bussgeld_strafgeld_ordnungswidrigkeiten_uebersicht.htm).

f) Implementation network

The Federal Government (www.bundesregierung.de), the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy (www.bmwi.de), as well as the Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure (www.bmvi.de) have been responsible for setting up the EnEV. Information on the practical implementation is provided by www.eneve-online.de

Since 2009, craftsmen have been required to declare that new or exchanged building parts meet EnEV criteria. In particular, they have to fill in an entrepreneurial declaration, which is to be given to the building owner. Public building control agencies may request the declaration to check whether the building complies with the EnEV (Löschel et al. 2014, dena 2015d).

g) Outcomes

According to Schröder et al. (2011, p. 31), the EnEV is expected “to be responsible for nearly half of the reductions in energy consumption from the building sector in the years 1995 – 2016.” Hence, it can be considered to be the most valuable instruments of the German Government for reducing energy consumption in the buildings stock. The German National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP 2014) presumes that through the German building stock substantial energy savings can be realised. Results are shown below:

Table 2: Energy savings according to the NEEAP

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Energy Saving Regulation	338 PJ (stock) 144 PJ (new build)	270 PJ (stock) 44 PJ (new build)

1.1.1.2 REGULAR INSPECTION OF BOILERS AND (NON-RESIDENTIAL) AIR-CONDITIONING

a) General information

In Germany, mandatory inspections for boilers have been in place since 1978. However, initially such assessments carried out by chimney sweepers were mainly to minimise security risks. In the succeeding years, the “task [of chimney sweepers] has been gradually enlarged to energy efficiency checks, with a minimum extra-cost” (Antinucci 2008, p. 11). For air conditioning systems, checks, which are to be undertaken by adequately trained experts.

While annual boiler inspections are the rule (e.g. conventional oil- or gas-based boilers), the Government requires some systems to be inspected only every two years. With respect to air conditioning systems, checks are less regular. For instance, “every air conditioning unit with more than 12 kW rated thermal output has to undergo an inspection by a specialized engineer every 10 years. The engineer has to inspect the appliances with respect to proper dimensioning and state of the art. He has to provide recommendations for cost-effective improvements to the owner” (Schettler-Köhler 2008).

The Energy Saving Regulation (EnEV), described above, is the regulatory basis for regular inspections of boilers and air conditioning systems in Germany².

² http://www.enev-online.com/enev_2014_volltext/enev_2014_verkuendung_bundesgesetzblatt_21.11.2013.pdf

b) Type of policy instrument

Inspections for boilers and air conditioning systems are mandatory – hence, it is classified as a regulatory policy instruments. Alternatively, it may sound eligible to frame building-related equipment inspections also as an advisory or information tool.

c) Objective

Inspections aim at (i) phasing out the least energy-efficient boilers and air conditioning systems, (ii) create awareness among users with respect to the energy consumed through these appliances and (iii) to persuade users of exchanging rather inefficient technologies with newer and more efficient models.

d) Target group

The regulatory instruments primarily targets building owners or, in particular, operators of boilers and air conditioning systems. While boilers inspections are carried out by chimney sweepers, checks for air conditioning systems are to be carried out by an expert (Germ. “fachkundige Person”) that has gained hands-on experience in planning, constructing, operating or assessing air conditioning systems (Händel 2008).

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The European Union through the European Building Performance Directive (2010/31/EU EPBD) designed a system that also requires Member States to realise frequent checks of boilers and air conditioning systems. With respect to boilers, the Government found that its already existing system is more appropriate (Schettler-Köhler 2008). Apart from the interaction with the EU level, the Government introduced information tools (e.g. the website www.co2online.de) as well as financial support (e.g. KfW programmes; see more below) to drive awareness and uptake of more energy-efficient boilers. Due to climate conditions, the use of air conditioning systems is not prioritised by the Government.

If inspections are not carried out as stated in the EnEV, fines up to EUR 15,000 can be imposed (http://www.enev-online.com/enev_praxishilfen/enev_2014_bussgeld_strafgeld_ordnungswidrigkeiten_uebersicht.htm).

f) Implementation network

As noted above, chimney sweepers regularly carry out boiler inspections. According to Schettler-Köhler (2008), a “chimney sweeper keeps a register of all the boilers in the region. The operator of the boiler has to pay a fee, which is officially fixed according to the extent of work.”

g) Outcomes

Inspections are part of the EnEV, whose energy saving potential was given in the section above. Apparently, efforts to evaluate inspections only have not been made available yet. However, with respect to heating systems, energy savings can be assumed to be huge. Around one fourth of such systems were installed before 1990 and 71% are assumed to be insufficiently energy-efficient (Statista 2015)

1.1.1.3 HEATING COST REGULATION**a) General information**

The heating cost regulation (Verordnung über die verbrauchsabhängige Abrechnung der Heiz- und Warmwasserkosten (Verordnung über Heizkostenabrechnung – HeizkostenV)³ is part of the energy saving law/act. Since the 1980s, the regulation mandates the detailed compilation of heating consumption and water heating consumption. Moreover, through the regulation the consumption of space and water heating can be exactly allocated to the user. Hence, the individual costs for consumption can also be determined. The Government assesses whether the heating cost regulation can be optimized in order to offer further cost-effective benefits from energy saving perspective (Deutscher Bundestag 2014).

b) Type of policy instrument

The heating cost regulation is a mandatory measure.

c) Objective

The primary goal of the heating cost regulation is to incentivise final-energy users to use energy more rationally (Landtag Nordrhein-Westfalen 2015).

d) Target group

The heating cost regulation applies for residential buildings with central heating appliances used by multiple households.

e) Rules and influencing mechanism

As stated above, the heating cost regulation belongs to the energy saving law/act.

According to § 12 HeizkostenV, a tenant can reduce its rental fee, if the landlord does not bill consumption-dependent.

f) Implementation network

Information on space and water heating are to be submitted to energy providers.

g) Outcome

According to the German National Action Plan Plan for Energy Efficiency the heating cost regulation has resulted in energy demand reduction of around 15% on average.

1.1.1.4 ENERGY PERFORMANCE CERTIFICATE

a) General information

As required by the EU's EPBD Directive, Germany's Energy Performance Certificate (EPC, Energieausweis) for buildings has been mandatory for new buildings and for existing buildings if these have been sold or rented since July 1st 2009. With respect to new buildings, the architect or the construction company issues the EPC. Building experts (e.g. architects, energy consultants, construction engineers) who have completed a training course on energy saving for buildings can issue EPCs for existing buildings. While residential buildings do not yet have to publicly display their EPC, they will have to do so in the future following Germany's implementation of the requirement in the 2010 recast of the EU legislation of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD). Public institutions (e.g. town halls, university buildings, social services departments, schools) already have to make them visible. The EPC consists of five pages. First of all, basic information such as the

³ <http://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/bundesrecht/heizkostenv/gesamt.pdf>

building type (e.g. single- or multi-family house), the address, its year of completion and the buildings size is stated. Based on all the building information, both the final energy demand and the primary energy demand are given and visualised on a scale, with green signalling low energy demand and red indicating a rather high energy demand.

Apart from that, the EPC also gives refurbishment recommendations like the replacement of conventional double-glazed windows (U-value 3 W/m²/K) with low emissivity double or triple glazing windows (U-value 1.3 or 0.8 W/m²/K).

The EPC is also regulated in the EnEV⁴.

b) Type of policy instrument

The Energy Performance Certificate belongs to the policy type “Regulation” as it is a mandatory policy instrument to inform consumers about the energy performance of the building.

c) Objectives

EPCs enhance market transparency and can contribute to establishing energy performance as a relevant purchasing criterion and subsequently increasing the demand for energy-efficient buildings. In order to raise public awareness of the energy performance of buildings, every building owner who puts their building on the market for sale or rent is required to provide the energy performance certificate to prospective buyers and tenants. With the information provided, potential buyers or tenants will be able to take the energy performance into consideration before purchasing or renting. The consumer shall be provided with comprehensive information. A national quantitative objective was not defined.

d) Target groups

The policy concerns public, residential and industrial buildings. Concrete target groups are manufacturers, architects, engineering consultants, investors, users and energy consultants.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Building owners and issuers of energy certificates may be punished with monetary penalties of up to EUR 15.000 if the energy certificate is not available when required, illustrates the wrong data or if the certificate was not issued by an authorized person.

f) Implementation network

The Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy is responsible for the implementation of the EnEV, which is the legal basis of the energy performance certificate.

g) Outcomes

DIW Berlin (2011) analyzed the effectiveness of the energy performance certificate in Germany. 81% of the respondents were aware of the certificate and 78% use the instrument at some point during their information gathering about the energy performance of the building. Only 35% stated that they used the EPC for the final purchase decision.

⁴ http://www.enev-online.com/enev_2014_volltext/enev_2014_verkuendung_bundesgesetzblatt_21.11.2013.pdf

1.1.2 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS / INFORMATIVE POLICY INSTRUMENTS

Germany has a very comprehensive number of policies, which focus on information and awareness. For instance, energy checks, through which households can identify and realise energy saving potentials, are offered by consumer organisations or non-profit organisations. Similarly, but in a more holistic way, an on-site consultation programme is provided by the Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export Control (BAFA). For SMEs, energy advisory services are also available and are subsidised by the Government. Furthermore, the Government offers a non-repayable grant for the monitoring of building refurbishment. If a new or refurbished building has an outstandingly low energy demand, it will be eligible to receive the Efficient House Quality Mark through the German Energy Agency (dena). With the help of these instruments presented in more detail in the next sections, final energy users are enabled and motivated to spot opportunities to save energy and achieve energy and, ultimately, monetary savings.

1.1.2.1 ENERGY CHECKS

a) General information

On-site energy efficiency checks have been offered by the consumer organisation VZBV to private consumers and tenants for a contribution of EUR 10 to the full costs of the energy advice. The programme started in 2012 and is free of charge for low-income households. Homeowners can also have a building check carried out for a contribution of EUR 20 to the costs. Another add-on is a boiler heating system inspection for a contribution of EUR 30 of the costs.

A similar energy check programme is organised by Caritas. It also offers free energy efficiency checks with a focus on low-income households. Caritas works together with the Association of Energy and Climate Protection Agencies in Germany. The energy checks are performed by so called “energy-saving assistants”. Unemployed people are trained as energy-saving assistant and offer the energy saving checks to low-income households (German Federal Government 2012). With this training they do not only learn how to save energy and how to support other people to invest in energy efficient technologies. They also get new opportunities in the labour market (Caritas ND). The energy saving assistants distribute CFLs, automatic timers, water flow reducers and other products to save energy free of charge. In addition a detailed plan to save energy within a specific period of time is developed with concrete recommendations. The Germany Ministry of the Environment is funding the Electricity Saving Check project (<http://www.stromspar-check.de>).

b) Type of policy instrument

The energy checks belong to the policy instrument “energy advice” and “energy audits”.

c) Objectives

The objective was stated in the Climate Action Programme 2020: 0.04 million tonnes of CO₂ equivalent shall be reduced as a result of support for low-income households (2015-2020). Furthermore another aim is to help low-income households to achieve energy savings in their homes and to create jobs.

d) Target groups

Target groups are low-income households.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Only households which receive unemployment benefits or social assistance can participate in the programme.

f) Implementation network

The Federal Ministry of the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (BMUB) supports the programme. Caritas, the Energy Climate Protection Agencies and the consumer associations carry out the energy checks.

g) Outcomes

An evaluation comes to the result that an average household with 2.5 inhabitants and an annual power consumption of 2.928 kilowatt hours can save 397 kilowatt hours (15%) per year (Stromsparcheck.de). In 2012, 3000 unemployed people were trained as energy saving assistant. Data about cost-effectiveness is not available. According to the German Federal Government, energy savings are as follows:

Table 3: Energy savings according the German Federal Government

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Energy checks (vzbv)	0.2 PJ	0.8 PJ
Energy efficiency checks (Caritas)	1.6 PJ	1.2 PJ

Source: German Federal Government 2012

1.1.2.2 ON-SIDE ENERGY CONSULTATION

a) General information

Since 1998 expenses for specially trained and accredited Energy Advisors are partly covered by the On-site Energy Saving Advice programme (Germ.: Energieeinsparberatung vor Ort), operated by the Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export Control (BAFA, <http://www.bafa.de/bafa/de/energie/energiesparberatung/>), a superior federal authority subordinated to the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi, <http://www.bmwi.de/DE/Themen/Energie/Energieeffizienz/energieberatung-und-foerderung,did=9790.html>).

Within the On-Side energy consultation the performance of the building and its energy consumption are analysed. Trained and authorised advisors assess saving opportunities and recommend improvements. For this purpose the advisor prepares a renovation plan as well as an action roadmap. It includes an economic feasibility calculation and is explained personally. The reports deal with structural thermal insulation as well as heat generation and distribution including water heating and use of renewable energies.

The funding is granted as a part-financing package in the form of a non-repayable contribution which is paid to the applicant consultant. A maximum of EUR 800 for single-family or two-family house and EUR 1100 for buildings with more than two housing units is given directly to the energy advisor.

Bonuses are given for implemented measures such as the integration of electricity saving measures or for the utilisation of thermographical screening or a blower-door test. Funding cannot exceed more than 60% of the energy advisory service costs.

The legal foundation is a Directive. The last revision of the Directive was published on October, 29th 2014 by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BAnz AT 12.11.2014 B2 as found in BAFA 2014a).

b) Type of policy instrument

The On-Side Energy Saving Advice Programme belongs to the policy type “Energy information and advice”. It is a policy that combines information, motivation and advice.

c) Objectives

The energy advice programme aims to identify and understand solid energy savings options that are tailored to their needs and to realize available funding possibilities so that they can assess the related costs and benefits and prioritize options. The objective is to save a total of 6.5 PJ of energy by 2020.

d) Target group

Target groups are home and property owners, consumers, apartment associations and facilities for charitable purposes. According to the National Action Plan on Energy Efficiency (NAPE) “energy consulting helps consumers to take cost-effective and efficient measures, because energy efficiency improvements should begin with a review and the preparation of a renovation roadmap”.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Building owners are eligible for funding if the building application was approved before 31 January 2002.

The on-side consultation excludes all objects which have already received a subsidised funding in the last four years.

Technical proposals are developed after the analysis of the energy performance. Then packages of recommended cost-effective measures are proposed. These recommendations can also be used for the application of the KfW financial incentive programme.

f) Implementation network

The Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi) is responsible for the on-site energy consultation in cooperation with the Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export Control (BAFA).

g) Outcomes

In a study (IFEU 2008) the energy advisory service received positive feedback. In 2005 95% of those who utilised the service implemented recommended refurbishment measures. On average, every onsite consultation produced energy savings of 5,300 kWh/yr in single and two-family houses and 8,800 kWh/yr in multi-family houses each year. These numbers indicate energy savings of about 10% that can be attributed to the programme as compared to the previous energy demand (IFEU 2008, p. 4). Forecast of final energy savings according to the Article 7 notification of EED (2012/27/EU) are as follows:

Table 4: Forecast of final energy saving according to Article 7

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
On-site energy consultation	8.1 PJ	6.5 PJ

Source: German Federal Government 2012

1.1.2.3 ENERGY CONSULTATIONS FOR SMEs (KfW)

a) General information

The energy consultation for SMEs is an instrument to support small and medium enterprises (SMEs) to highlight weaknesses in the use of energy, to illustrate the potentials and to provide recommendations for energy efficiency improvements. At the end of the energy consultation the SME manager is given specific suggestions on economically viable energy saving measures in buildings and facilities as well as on consumer behaviour issues (Richtlinie über die Förderung von Energieberatern im Mittelstand 2014, <http://www.bmwi.de/BMWi/Redaktion/PDF/P-R/richtlinie-ueber-die-foerderung-von-energieberatungen-im-mittelstand,property=pdf,bereich=bmwi2012,sprache=de,rwb=true.pdf>). Consultations may qualify for subsidies of up to 80 % of the consultation costs. SMEs can receive funding for an initial consultation and/or a detailed consultation. Eligible applicants are small and medium sized enterprises with less than 250 employees and with an annual turnover that does not exceed EUR 50 million or an annual balance sheet that does not exceed EUR 43 million (BAFA 2015c).

The funding became even more attractive on 1 January 2015. A new funding regulation provides more funding for knowledgeable advice and professional assistance to increase the number of consultations and the amount of investments in energy efficient technologies. Small companies with less than EUR 10,000 in energy costs can receive up to EUR 800 in consultation subsidies. Companies with more than EUR 10,000 energy costs can receive up to EUR 8,000 (BMW 2015d, BMW 2014).

b) Type of policy instrument

The policy instrument belongs to the policy type energy consultation and energy advice.

c) Objectives

A clear objective was not formulated. From 2015 on, the German federal government provides EUR 5 million (BMW 2014).

d) Target groups

Target groups are small and medium-sized enterprises.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

To improve consulting quality, energy consultations will only qualify for funding if they meet the audit requirements set out in the EU Energy Efficiency Directive. Only certified and registered energy consultants may carry out the energy consultations (BAFA 2015c).

The help SMEs to implement the suggested measures, the KfW programme extends low-interest loans from its energy efficiency programme to businesses that invest in energy conservation (BMW 2015d).

f) Implementation network

The programme is organised by the KfW bank and financed by the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy.

g) Outcomes

Around 17,000 companies received consultations under this programme from 2008 to 2013. The consultations led to EUR 0.7 to 1.4 billion of investment and 1.5 to 2.7 terawatt-hours of energy savings. Every publicly financed euro generated EUR 16 to 29 in private investment (BMW 2015d). Final energy savings according to the Article 7 (EED 2012/27/EU) notification are as follows:

Table 5: Final energy savings according to the Article 7

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Energy consultations for SMEs	54 PJ	41 PJ

Source: German Federal Government 2012

Data about cost-effectiveness are not available.

1.1.2.4 KfW CONSTRUCTION MONITORING

a) General information

The KfW bank supports the construction monitoring during the refurbishment of inefficient buildings. 50% of the costs for the construction monitoring are covered with a maximum of EUR 4,000. Qualified experts accompany the process and offer:

- Planning of the energy concept of the building
- Support for the incoming proposals
- Monitoring of the whole refurbishment process
- Evaluation of the refurbishment (KfW 2015e)

The financial support is available, e.g. for wall insulation, roof insulation, replacement of inefficient heating systems and replacement of windows. The energy experts guarantee the compliance with minimum requirements and illustrate the benefits of energy efficient measures. Qualified and independent experts are listed at www.energie-effizienz-experten.de (<http://www.bmwi.de/DE/Presse/pressemitteilungen,did=646614.html>).

b) Type of policy instrument

This policy belongs to the policy type “Advice” and “Information”

c) Objectives

The programme aims to support building owners with the refurbishment of inefficient buildings. Owners can find high-quality assistance to guarantee that the work is done properly.

d) Target groups

Target group are home owners and energy consultants.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

- The financial support is only available in combination with other KfW programmes, a credit or an investment grant offered by KfW.
- Furthermore it is possible to combine the construction monitoring with the BAFA on-side consultation.
- The energy expert may not be the owner of the building nor be in a social or employment relationship to the building owner.

f) Implementation network

The Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy, BAFA and KfW have concluded in 2011 to initiate a national, consistent database of qualified energy efficiency experts in order to secure the quality of supported energy consultancies. The implementation and supervision is carried out by Deutsche Energie-Agentur (dena).

g) Outcomes

No information available.

1.1.2.5 DENA EFFICIENT HOUSE QUALITY MARK (EH)**a) General information****Figure 2: Example of an Dena Efficient House Quality Mark**

Source: Dena 2015e

Besides the mandatory energy performance certificate, Germany's energy agency, dena, has created the "Dena Efficient House Quality Mark" (Germ.: Gütesiegel Effizienzhaus). It is a voluntary certification scheme with the central goals to strengthen the market for energy efficient homes, to increase demand and to push bandwagon effects (dena 2013). The label shows buildings with a low energy demand. At the same time building contractors and refurbishers receive confirmation that the quality of the house is in the form of the quality mark (dena 2015). To receive the dena quality mark evidence of the low energy requirements must be provided. For this purpose dena developed a quality-assured procedure (dena 2015). The label compares the energy efficiency performance of the building with the legal maximum requirements for new buildings. If the energy demand of the building is as high as a standard new building, the building is rated with 100%. A building that is rated with 40% is much more energy efficient and uses only 40% of the energy demand of a standard new building. The lower the value, the better the energy efficiency rate. The next table illustrates the calculation method and the maximum energy performance requirements.

Table 6: Efficiency classification of efficiency houses

Efficiency Classification	Calculation method	Requirements primary energy demand
Efficiency House 40	Max. 40% (new and existing buildings)	Max. 30 kWh/(m2a)
Efficiency House 55	Max. 55% (new and existing buildings)	Max. 40 kWh/(m2a)
Efficiency House 70	Max. 70% (new and existing buildings)	Max. 50 kWh/(m2a)
Efficiency House 85	Max. 85% (existing buildings)	Max. 60 kWh/(m2a)
Efficiency House 100	Max. 100% (existing buildings)	Max. 70 kWh/(m2a)

Source: dena (2015)

A Quality Mark can be ordered at the energy agency to put it on the wall of the building. Furthermore the energy efficient building can be presented at the platform of the dena website (www.zukunft-haus.info/effizienzhaus) (dena n.d.).

b) Type of policy instrument

The instrument belongs to the policy type "voluntary labelling scheme" and "information".

c) Objectives

The objective is to increase the visibility of energy efficient buildings and to inform home owners about the energy demand of their building.

d) Target groups

Target group are home owners.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The Efficiency House Quality Mark goes hand in hand with the KfW incentive programme “energy efficient refurbishment”. The energy requirements are the same and building owners can easily identify the financial incentives for their building. The better the EH standard, i.e. energy performance of a building after the refurbishment/ construction process, the higher the financial incentives.

Table 7: Efficiency house and available incentives through KfW

	Dena Efficiency House Quality Mark available		KfW financial incentives available	
	New buildings	Existing buildings	New buildings	Existing buildings
Efficiency house 40	✓	✓	✓	✓
Efficiency house 55	✓	✓	✓	✓
Efficiency house 70	✓	✓	✓	✓
Efficiency house 85	—	✓	✓	✓
Efficiency house 100	—	✓	—	✓

Source: dena (2010)

The costs for the dena Efficiency House Quality Mark is EUR 95 for single family buildings and up to EUR 300 for multi-family buildings.

If the quality mark is wrong declared, for instance, if the energy demand is higher than indicated, the quality mark can be withdrawn.

f) Implementation network

The German Energy-Agency is responsible for the implementation of the Efficient House Quality Mark.

g) Outcomes

No information available.

1.1.3 ECONOMIC POLICY INSTRUMENTS

Economic policy instruments implemented in Germany deserve significant attention. In particular, the KfW programmes for households incentivising energy-efficient construction and energy-efficient refurbishment using a combination of loans and grants have become a cornerstone of Germany’s plans to achieve a low-carbon building stock. By taxing the consumption of energy and electricity end-users are to be disincentivised to use energy excessively. Moreover, the BAFA offers financial support to households and companies for the installation of energy saving building equipment. Hence, German economic policy instruments reward the implementation of certain energy saving measures and make excessive energy consumption costly.

1.1.3.1 KfW ENERGY EFFICIENT CONSTRUCTION

a) General information

The KfW Energy Efficient Construction programme⁵ makes available soft-loans to investors in new energy-efficient residential buildings including, for instance single- or two-family houses or retirement homes. The soft loan includes a total amount of up to EUR 50,000 available to investors,⁶ a relatively long contractual loan duration (up to 30 years), a fixed interest rate for the first ten years as well as a grace period of up to five years. Moreover, for very energy efficient buildings grants of up to EUR 5,000 (or 10% of the actual loan amount) are redeployed. In particular, the amount of the redeployed grant depends on the expected degree of energy efficiency. This is measured through an innovative system clustering buildings into differed energy efficiency “classes” or so-called “KfW Efficiency Houses” (KfW EH). The classification system takes into account a building’s annual primary energy demand as well as transmission heat loss and compares these values to those of a reference building designed in line with the German minimum energy performance standards. For example, the KfW EH 55 requires only 55% of primary energy demand of a reference building. There are three building classes applicable to new buildings. Hence, the more energy efficient a building (compared to the standard), the more preferential the loan (KfW 2015a, KfW 2015b).

b) Type of policy instrument

The KfW energy-efficient construction programme is an economic policy tool provided to investors in residential buildings.

c) Objective

Through the programme and the loan component, the German Government helps investors to close the higher demand for financing energy efficient buildings being more expensive, in general. Moreover, the redeployed grant reduces the overall debt sum and, hence, the overall costs for financing.

d) Target group

The instrument directly targets the uptake of energy-efficient and environment friendly construction of residential buildings. KfW facilitates loans via local banks to building owners. Apart from investors and local banks, other target groups such as construction companies and installation contractors may benefit from an increased demand of their services. Last but not least, the instruments requires investors to have an energy efficiency expert accompanying the construction process.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

With the state-owned KfW bank, the German Government has an important tool to promote energy efficiency in the building sector. As a AAA-rated financing institutions, KfW can raise money at capital markets at low costs. This money, in turn, is on-lend to investors in energy efficient buildings. Moreover, as stated above, the German minimum energy performance standards is used as a benchmark tool to assess the degree of energy efficiency of a building and, hence, to determine the preferences of the loan scheme.

⁵ From April 2016, the KfW Energy Efficient Construction scheme will change slightly. The following information presented refer to contemporary programme design. For the changes mentioned, please consult KfW (2015a)

⁶ Changes that will occur from April 2016 onwards will, among other things, result in a loan amount of up to EUR 100,000.

f) Implementation network

Construction companies and installation contractors have to carry out energy performance requirements. Moreover, if an investor seeks to make use of the KfW energy-efficient construction loan, an expert accompanying the realisation of the project is required. Such an expert can be chosen from an official list reducing search costs.⁷

g) Outcomes

The KfW has its programmes assessed annually. The latest evaluation is available for the year 2013. It was found that the programme covers 54% of new buildings in Germany. Final energy savings of buildings reached in 2013 amount to 336 GWh/a (Diefenbach et al. 2014). Forecasts of final energy savings according to the third NEEAP (2014) are as follows

Table 8: Forecasts of final energy savings according to the third NEEAP

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
KfW Energy Efficient Construction	27 PJ	22 PJ

1.1.3.2 KfW ENERGY EFFICIENT RENOVATION

a) General information

For residential building owners, the German Government through the KfW bank offers two financial support options under the KfW Energy Efficient Renovation scheme⁸.

First, the Renovation programme offers a credit line making available a soft-loan. Apart from other beneficial issues (e.g. grace period), the most important fact of the contract is that a grant is redeployed reducing the total loan amount and, thus, shortening the amortisation period. Very energy-efficient buildings can receive a grant of up to EUR 16,875 or 22,5% of the original loan amount. From August 2015, grant redeployment is also applicable to single measures (KfW 2015c).⁹ Second, building owners undertaking energy-efficient building refurbishment can also opt for a upfront grant. Again, if a building is expected to be classified as a highly energy-efficient building, the grant is highest amounting to EUR 30,000 or 30% of applicable costs. In contrast to the credit option, the grant option has already been offering support of up to EUR 5,000 for single measures (KfW 2015d).

Similarly to the KfW Energy Efficient Construction programme, this programme also makes use of the KfW Efficiency House scheme. The classification system takes into account a building's annual primary energy demand as well as transmission heat loss and compares these values to those of a reference building designed in line with the German minimum energy performance standards. The better the values compared to the standard, the better the financing arrangement under the credit or the grant option.

⁷ This list is available at www.energie-effizienz-experten.de.

⁸ The KfW Energy Efficiency Renovation programme will be undergoing some minor changes from August 2015. The information provided refer to the contemporary programme.

⁹ From a financing point of view, single measures were largely excluded from the KfW programmes in order to foster the uptake of comprehensive building refurbishment. This changes from August 2015 onwards.

b) Type of policy instrument

The KfW Energy Efficient Renovation scheme is a financing tool and, hence, according to our purposes defined as an economic policy instrument.

c) Objective

The loan component seeks to help investors in financing higher upfront costs typically associated with energy-efficient renovation (opposed to standard renovation). The component includes a grant redeployed later, which reduces the overall debt sum. The “grant-only” component assists investors in reducing the overall upfront costs. In both instances, investors are to be motivated to undertake energy-efficient renovations.

d) Target group

Grants facilitated by the programme are directly provided to investors. Loans are processed by local banks to building owners.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Obviously, like with the aforementioned Energy Efficient Construction programme, KfW plays a crucial role for raising money on capital markets at low costs. Moreover, the Renovation programme also uses the KfW Efficiency House scheme in order to determine the degree of energy efficiency, the German minimum energy performance standard affects the measure, as well.

f) Implementation network

In order to become applicable to the KfW financing scheme, investors in building refurbishment must assign an energy efficient expert from an official list.

g) Outcomes

According to Diefenbach et al. (2014), the programme approved 111,000 applications for 276,000 building units in 2013. In particular, building insulation measures exceed standards set in the EnEV, Germany’s minimum energy performance standard. In total, the authors expect that implemented measures result in final energy savings of 1,700 GWh/a as well as 650,000 tons of mitigated CO₂ emissions. Forecasts of final energy savings according to the third NEEAP (2014) are as follows:

Table 9: Forecasts of final energy savings according to the third NEEAP:

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
KfW Energy Efficient Renovation	219 PJ	175 PJ

1.1.3.3 ENERGY TAX AND ELECTRICITY TAX

a) General information

In 1999, the German Government introduced the so-called ecologic tax reform. The reform induced a tax increase of the so-called Mineral Oil Tax, today known as Energy Tax,¹⁰ including fuels for transportation and heating. Apart from that, through the 1999-reform the electricity tax was introduced, as well (NEEAP 2011). Both, the Energy Tax and the Electricity Tax are federal taxes. Tax revenues have to a large extent been subsidising the German pension system (MURE 2014).

¹⁰ The name of the Mineral Oil Tax changed to Energy Tax in 2006 (MURE 2014).

It should be noted that the taxation system in Germany allows large-scale energy consumers to claim for respective exemptions, if certain energy efficiency requirements are met (e.g. the installation of an energy management systems).

b) Type of policy instrument

The Energy Tax and Electricity Tax are commonly referred to as fiscal policy instruments. Given this study's cluster of policy instruments, it is classified as a economic policy instrument.

c) Objective

The objective of the Energy Tax and Electricity Tax is to increase the price of energy. In other words, the tax creates an incentive to use energy and electricity more rationally. In this respect, it is cross-cutting affecting very different fields of energy use. Even though hardly any information have been found, the tax may, for instance, positively affect the purchasing behaviour of end-users. In particular, due to higher costs for energy and electricity induced through the tax scheme, end-users may be more inclined to buy energy-efficient appliances. Moreover, as stated above, the tax revenues flow into the German pension system.

d) Target group

The policy instruments directly affect different sets of energy and electricity end-users. In an indirect way, the Energy Tax and the Electricity Tax may also bring manufacturers towards producing more energy-efficient goods due to increased demand in these types of products.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The collection of taxes requires adequately trained, staffed and financed fiscal authorities.

f) Implementation network

The Energy Tax and the Electricity Tax are administered by the Federal Ministry of Finance's main customs office.

g) Outcomes

According to Prognos (2013), both tax instruments will result in annual savings of 72 to 74 PJ between 2014 to 2020. Forecast of final energy savings according to the third NEEAP (2014) is as provided below:

Table 10: Forecast of final energy savings according to the third NEEAP

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Energy and electricity tax	0 PJ	551 PJ

1.1.3.4 MARKET INCENTIVE PROGRAMME (MARKTANREIZPROGRAMM MAP)

a) General information

The MAP actually consists of two components. The "investment grant" aims at facilitating rather small-scale equipment (< 100 kW) installed with private households, businesses and public institutions. The types of equipment eligible for funding include solar thermal collectors, pellet heating systems as well as efficient heat pumps. The component is managed by the Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export Control (BAFA¹¹), which also deals with grant applications.¹² With

¹¹ Germ.: Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle.

respect to the total grant amount, there is a “basic funding option,” which can be increased if the chosen product includes innovative characteristics and if it is combined with other selected technologies.¹³

b) Type of policy instrument

The market incentive programme is considered to be an economic policy tool or instrument.

c) Objective

In very narrow terms, the “investment grant” component of the MAP aims at reducing upfront costs for certain energy-efficient technologies in the heating and cooling domain. By reducing the price difference between, for instance, solar thermal collectors and conventional, energy-inefficient technologies, the grant is to motivate target groups to take up such more environment friendly technology options. In so doing, the programme component incentivises manufactures to produce such technologies. Eventually, the investment grant is a crucial element to promote sustainability in the heating sector and can also be seen as an instrument to spur investment, to create or maintain jobs in the sector and, ultimately, to contribute to the overall economic situation (Stuible et al. 2014).

d) Target group

The investment grant is made available to residential building owners, businesses and public institutions. Apart from that, energy contractors are also eligible to installed applicable technologies with aforementioned groups. Manufacturers serving the German market with eligible equipment and installation contractors are also targeted.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The German Government set the goal to increase the share of environment friendly technologies in the heating and cooling market to 14% by 2020. This creates planning and investment security among different types of investors including not only end-users but also equipment manufacturers.

f) Implementation network

In order to become eligible for funding, applicants must submit to BAFA several documents depending on the type of technology installed. One of the key documents is the so-called “entrepreneurial declaration”¹⁴, which includes several aspects of the installation and which has to be filled in by installation contractors (BAFA 2015a).

g) Outcomes

According to BAFA (2015b), MAP has helped to install around 1.7m climate friendly technology units. In 2014 alone, it facilitated the installation of close to 60,000 units. The applicants were primarily interested in biomass-based heating (29,000 applications) and solar thermal collectors (24,500 applications). Forecast of final energy savings of the MAP according to the third NEEAP (2014) is provided below:

¹² The second component of the MAP is called „grant towards loan-redemption,“ which is mainly made use of by commercial investors or local governments (BMWI 2015a).

¹³ The website www.CO2online.de provides a very good overview of the possible grant sum (co2online 2015).

¹⁴ Germ.: Unternehmererklärung

Table 11: Forecast of final energy savings of the MAP according to the third NEEAP

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Market incentive programme (BAFA portion)	48 PJ	24 PJ

1.1.3.5 BAFA CROSS CUTTING TECHNOLOGIES

a) General description

BAFA's cross-cutting technologies programme partly finances the installation of highly energy equipment with SMEs. Eligible equipment includes electrical pumps, electrical motors or LED-based lighting systems. These technologies have to be in mass production and can be installed in different sectors - they are cross-cutting. Several individual energy-efficiency criteria apply (see BAFA 2015f).

SMEs can chose between two options. Either they opt for "simply" exchanging old equipment with new, highly energy-efficient technologies or they chose the more comprehensive measure - the systemic optimization. The latter requires the employment of an energy advisor, who designs an energy (improvement) concept. Moreover, for systemic optimization some more technologies can be funded (e.g. metering technologies) in order to enhance energy savings as much as possible.

b) Type of policy instrument

The policy consists of non-refundable grants, which partly finance investment costs for cross-cutting technologies (BAFA 2014).

c) Objective

Through the policy instrument, BMWi and BAFA seek to realize energy efficiency potentials in the industry sector (BAFA 2014).

d) Target group

Especially small- and medium-sized enterprises are addressed by the funding programme for cross-cutting technologies. Energy services providers, which install and finance cross-cutting technologies with eligible SMEs, can also apply for the funding instrument.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The instrument was established, among other things, to achieve ambitious energy efficiency goals set in 2010 and 2011. As a result of these goals, the Government created the Energy Efficiency Fund for Promoting the Rational and Thrifty Use of Energy, which is the basis of BAFA's cross-cutting technologies programme (BAFA 2015f).

f) Implementation network

The Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export Control is in charge of processing applications.

g) Outcomes

In 2012, BAFA had to process less than 60 funding applications. Within two years only, the number of applications skyrocketed to more than 26,000. According to Article 7 notifications of the EED (2012/27/EU), savings amount to:

Table 12: Savings according to Article 7 notifications of the EED

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
BAFA Cross-cutting Technologies	4.8 PJ	19 PJ

1.1.4 CAPACITY BUILDING AND NETWORKING

Different types of policy instruments were implemented to enhance the capacities of different kinds of actors to promote energy efficiency. In energy efficiency networks a group of business representatives is trained on energy efficiency issues and exchanges information. Networks are partly subsidised. In addition, energy management systems enables businesses to reduce energy consumption systematically by compiling and assessing data. The installation of an EMS is funded by the Government. Due to increased demand for energy-related advisory services, the Government also supports (under certain circumstances) retraining activities as an energy consultant. As was shown above, several programmes exist, that indeed require an energy consultant. For energy advisors to become employed in these programmes, they must complete special training courses. Successful course participants can then become registered and found with an official online registry, which is easy to access for those looking for respective experts. In order to enhance capacities and knowledge on energy efficiency, the German Government participates in the International Partnership for Energy Efficiency Cooperation (IPEEC). Wrapping it up, the Government promotes capacity building on the national level with different actors and by participating in the IPEEC and networking internationally the Government also enhances its very own capacities.

1.1.4.1 ENERGY EFFICIENCY NETWORKS INITIATIVE (LERNENDE ENERGIE EFFIZIENZ NETZWERKE, LEEN)

a) General information

Learning Energy Efficiency Networks bring together 10 to 15 parties per network. Parties should be interested in saving energy. The focus of the instrument is on businesses. Through the energy efficiency network initiative (LEEN), the participating parties have to commit to a common energy saving target. The target is based on an energy assessment carried out by an appointed energy advisor, who analyses the energy consumption, assesses saving opportunities and recommends energy saving measures. In regular network meetings (every three to four months) participants exchange information regarding implemented actions and identify lessons learned. Such meetings are hosted by an assigned moderator. The moderator also invites external experts that may offer solutions to overcome certain problems.

b) Type of policy instrument

LEEN can be categorised as a capacity building measure. Through thoroughly exchanging and obtaining information on how to reduce energy consumption, LEEN participants are to be enabled to realise energy saving measures within their companies.

c) Objective

The overall and declared goal of the instrument is to establish 500 networks worldwide by 2020 (BWMI 2014).

d) Target group

As stated above, different types of LEEN exist. The main target groups are companies and municipalities.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The establishment and operation of a network is not without costs. However, for the initial phase of the policy instrument, the Government introduced several incentives. For instance, licensing fees do not apply for companies that will be participating in a network not later than 2017.¹⁵ Moreover, the first ten networks were supported with around EUR 4,000 for each participant. Apart from that, LEEN's website¹⁶ explicitly recommends to make use of further support instruments facilitated by the government. In particular, the moderator as well as the energy advisor should inform network participants on government support available.

f) Implementation network

A LEEN consists of a company initiating the network. The initiator seeks to mobilise like-minded companies that also wish to save energy and to engage in the network. Moreover, a moderator and an energy advisor have to be employed. The moderator manages the network and, for instance, sets the schedule and content for the meeting. Among other things, the advisor carries out an energy assessment with companies. Together, the moderator and the advisor can recommend external experts for network meetings. The coordination between the various networks rests with the Fraunhofer Institute for Systems ISI and Innovation Research and other organisations.

g) Outcomes

According to the Fraunhofer Institute (ND), the preceding project, "LEEN 100 Plus", which reached almost 400 businesses, has on average reduced CO₂ emissions by 1,000 tons and lowered energy costs by 10% within four years. This translates into costs savings of around EUR 200,000 annually. Forecast of final energy savings according to the NAPE (BMW_i 2014) are provided below:

Table 13: Forecast of final energy savings according to the NAPE

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2015 - 2020
Energy efficiency networks	-	74.5 PJ

1.1.4.2 PROMOTION OF ENERGY MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS (EMS)

a) General information

In 2010, the German Government introduced the so-called Energy and Climate Funds, which also includes financing for activities in the realm of energy efficiency. Since 2013 this financing pool makes available "Funding for Energy Management Systems" (EMS), administered by the BAFA.¹⁷ In

¹⁵ Licensing fees include costs working material.

¹⁶ <http://www.energie-effizienz-netzwerke.de>

¹⁷ The policy instrument was changed in 2015. The information provided refers to the updated version.

particular, the manufacturing industry can gain access to the mechanism covering some of the investments necessary for realising an EMS. For instance, the mechanism covers the costs (by up to 60% or up to EUR 6,000) for external advisory services for developing, implementing and operating an EMS. Apart from that, funding is also available for training staff, for acquiring necessary software and hardware and for completing a official certification according to DIN EN ISO 50001 (BAFA 2015d).

b) Type of policy instrument

In the long-term, the funding of energy management systems raises the capacities (and awareness) of final-energy users to reduce energy consumption, for instance, through training staff and acquiring software and hardware. Hence, it is defined as a capacity building instrument. In the very short-term, it surely overcomes the cost barrier associated with expenses for installing such a management system.

c) Objective

Through funding energy management systems the Government of Germany seeks to assist the industry in reducing the energy consumption and realising more environment friendly production processes (BMW 2015a). This is achieved, firstly, by reducing expenses associated with developing, installing and operating an EMS. Due to the operative EMS, companies are enabled to reduce energy consumption.

d) Target group

In general, large businesses mainly from the manufacturing sector are the core target group, even though there are certain exceptions.¹⁸

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The Government has identified energy management systems as a central to for raising the energy efficiency in the sectors industry, commerce, trade and services representing 43% of Germany's annual final energy consumption. The peak equalisation reducing the energy and electricity taxation for large energy consumers is a key tool for incentivising the uptake of energy management systems. The programme "Funding of Energy Management Systems" has been installed to incentivise even more companies (BMW 2015b). Apart from that, DIN EN ISO 50001 constitute the official norm according to which the system has to be installed.

f) Implementation network

The Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy is in charge for energy efficiency financing of the Energy and Climate Fund (BMW 2015a). The support programme "Funding for Energy Management Systems" is administered by the Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export Control (BAFA). For the realisation of an energy management system an energy advisor is required. The advisor has to be listed in an official registry for energy efficiency experts (BMW 2015a). Energy management system certification has to be carried out by an official certification organisation.

g) Outcomes

Overall results regarding achievements of the funding instrument have not been made available yet. According to UBA (2012), companies with a functioning EMS can save up to 10% of their energy costs in the initial years and investments may result in electricity savings of up to 50% with an amortisation period of two years. Forecast of final energy savings according to the third NEEAP (2014) is as follows:

¹⁸ For instance, companies that are supported through peak equalisation, which reduces energy and electricity taxation are not eligible for funding energy management systems (BAFA 2015d).

Table 14: Forecast of final energy savings according to the third NEEAP

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Funding of energy management systems through the Energy Efficiency Fund	0 PJ	1 PJ

1.1.4.3 EDUCATIONAL VOUCHER (GERM.: BILDUNGSGUTSCHEIN) FOR RE-TRAINING TOWARDS ENERGY ADVISORS

a) General information

In Germany, several policies exist, which require or recommend the assignment of an energy advisor.¹⁹ Generally, they help building owners or investors to reduce the energy consumption in buildings. The demand for such advisory services has been growing. In order to meet this demand, the German Government financially supports through the Job Centres re-training activities towards becoming an energy advisor.²⁰ People interested in re-training courses, which are offered at Chamber of Handicrafts or private education facilities, have to discuss with Job Centre staff the reasons for re-training. In general, people will have to have experience in the construction sector, be in a precarious work situation or have not been able to find a job. If the Job Centre staff is persuaded that re-training towards becoming an energy advisor enhances job opportunities for the applicant, then the so-called “educational voucher” can be facilitated.²¹ Issuing the “educational vouchers” depends on the Job Centre’s budget and cannot be claimed by applicants. Despite this uncertainty, the voucher may cover up to 100% of the costs for the course and course material, which may amount to EUR 2,000, and includes a monthly lump sums for travelling expenses, costs for out-of-town accommodation, catering as well as child care (Bundesagentur für Arbeit 2013, Arbeitsgemeinschaft Altersunabhängiges Lernen 2015a, 2015b). Once the educational measure is completed, newly trained energy advisors are eligible to register with the official list for energy efficiency experts.²²

b) Type of policy instrument

This policy tool can be categorised as a capacity building instrument, since it increases the number of people able to assess the energy consumption in buildings.

¹⁹ See, for instance, the sections on the Learning Energy Efficiency Networks or the KfW programmes described above.

²⁰ The educational voucher is not an instrument specifically designed to only support retraining for future energy advisors.

²¹ Financing support is based on case-decisions and far from being an automatic procedure. Moreover, it should be note that other requirements have also to be met. For instance, the applicant must be, at least, 18 years old.

²² <https://www.energie-effizienz-experten.de/>

c) Objective

Educational policy vouchers were introduced in 2003 in order to enhance the opportunities of interested parties to engage in retraining activities, for example. A quantitative objective of the policy is unknown.

d) Target group

People with experience in the construction sector and in precarious situation represent the direct target group of the policy as they receive re-training support towards becoming an energy advisors. The new advisors are eligible to carry out energy assessment in buildings, which is why building owners or investors can be regarded as the supplementary target group of the measure.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Energy advisors, which attended courses complying with BAFA guidelines, allow advisors to become registered in an official online list.²³ Moreover, only if experts are contracted that attended such courses and meet BAFA-guidelines, homeowners or investors in energy efficient buildings will be eligible to gain access to further financing tools (e.g. through the BAFA On-Site Visit programme).

f) Implementation network

The issuance of educational vouchers depends on case-by-case decisions of Job Centre staff. The courses financed by the voucher are offered by different types of organisations. For these training courses, the Federal Office for Economic Affairs and Export Control published guidelines (BAFA 2015).

g) Outcomes

So far, there have been no documents published regarding the effects of the educational voucher for re-training towards energy advisors.

1.1.4.4 REQUIREMENT GUIDELINES FOR ENERGY CONSULTANTS AND LIST OF CERTIFIED ENERGY CONSULTANTS

a) General information

In Germany, the KfW and the BAFA administer national programmes that are to reduce energy consumption in residential buildings. In order to receive funding through these programmes, building owners, who wish to refurbish their home, have to employ an energy efficiency expert, who can assess best the opportunities to save energy. However, such energy efficiency experts must meet be adequately trained before they can be assigned by homeowners. That is why the KfW and BAFA introduced training requirements for energy efficiency experts. For participation in BAFA's On-Site Visit programme, experts must complete the so-called "Consultation Module" and the "Planning and Realisation Module" is requested for participating in KfW programmes.²⁴ Once energy efficiency experts completed one or both of the modules, they can apply for registration with an official list for energy efficiency experts managed by dena (2015c). Registration includes an processing fee (EUR 50) and an annual fee (EUR 100).

²³ People in need of an energy advisor are more likely to rely on an expert registered with the official list.

²⁴ For further information on the requirements, please consult the guidebook published by the German Energy Agency (dena), BMWi, BAFA and KfW available in the German language only (dena et al. 2014b).

b) Type of policy instrument

The catalogue of requirements for energy advisors to perform certain tasks can be seen as a capacity building instrument. The official list of energy efficiency experts can be regarded as an additional incentive to meet the requirements.

c) Objective

The requirements for energy efficiency experts helps to safeguard that experts participating in the national energy efficiency programmes managed by KfW and BAFA are appropriately trained to carry out tasks responsibly. This is to increase the confidence of building owners in those experts and to reduce severe mistakes. Properly realising energy-efficient building also helps to enhance the image of energetic building in Germany, which is to some extent distorted through negative media broadcast. The list of experts helps building owners to reduce transaction costs for finding an eligible expert.

d) Target group

Obviously, the requirements set and the list of experts created have primarily been established to address energy efficiency experts – to train them accordingly.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

As stated before, the catalogue of requirements and the official lists for energy efficiency experts are linked to the KfW energy efficiency programmes for residential buildings as well as BAFA's On-Site energy consultation programme. These programmes require appropriately trained energy experts and increase the demand for energy advisory services.

f) Implementation network

KfW and BAFA have introduced different catalogues of criteria for building experts. Educational facilities carry out the training courses accordingly. Dena manages and maintains the list of experts.

g) Outcomes

Outcomes have not been made available yet.

1.1.4.5 IPEEC (INTERNATIONAL PARTNERSHIP FOR ENERGY EFFICIENCY COOPERATION)

a) General information

Germany participates in the IPEEC, an intergovernmental organization. Altogether it has around 16 members (e.g. Brazil, USA, China, EU). In order to improve energy efficiency in member states, the IPEEC has implemented a variety of measures across different sectors including buildings, appliances, transport etc.

Such measures include, for instance, the Super-efficient Equipment and Appliance Deployment initiative (SEAD), an award scheme for highly energy-efficient appliances, or the Global Superior Energy Performance Partnership (GSEP) that seeks to reduce energy consumption in industrial facilities and large buildings. Moreover, through the IPEEC information are shared and assessed, which could help to harmonize national energy efficiency policy landscapes.

b) Type of policy instrument

The IPEEC is an intergovernmental dialogue and networking forum that also implements initiatives in order to facilitate energy savings.

c) Objective

Again, since the IPEEC launched different types of measures, the objectives of these individual measures vary. In very general terms, it can be said that the IPEEC seeks to "assist its member countries to identify and share proven, innovative practices and data on energy efficiency to better inform decision makers" (IPEEC 2015). Hence, it seeks to enhance the capacities (through networking) of national government decision-makers.

d) Target group

The IPEEC brings together decision-makers of the G8-country group and of emerging economies in order to discuss energy efficiency issues. IPEEC's initiatives, in turn, are relatively comprehensive and are clustered into five areas including appliances, buildings and transport. Hence, the target group(s) of these different initiatives really depends on the type of measures passed.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The IPEEC is largely dependent on financial commitments made by its members.

f) Implementation network

Task Groups, funded by member states, are to design and implement technical work programmes and initiatives. Generally, other institutions including the private sector businesses can gain access and contribute to IPEEC's work.

g) Outcomes

Information on overall outcomes of the IPEEC and its initiatives is not available. Some initiatives were assessed to a limited extent.²⁵

1.1.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR THE PROMOTION OF ENERGY SERVICES

The following section focuses almost exclusively on the competence centre for public buildings. The Centre is comprised of several instruments (e.g. information dissemination, designing standardised contracts) in order to promote energy services, which is why it deserves special attention. Since they represent a relatively new policy tool, default guarantees for energy contractors are sketched only.

1.1.5.1 CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE – CONTRACTING FOR PUBLIC BUILDINGS (INCL. DEFAULT GUARANTEES)

a) General information

The Centre of Excellence for Contracting, established in 2010 by the German Energy Agency (dena), is located in Berlin. While it seeks to accelerate the cross-sectoral uptake of contracting solutions, it focuses on the situation in the public sector. On the one hand, the internet-based Centre via its website can be regarded as an informational one-stop shop, through which parties interested in contracting are provided with basic knowledge, references to further literature and ways to find contractors or financing support for advisory support, for example. However, the Centre is far from

²⁵ In Mexico, cool roofs were found to reduce energy consumption by 7% and 18% in commercial and residential buildings, respectively. This initiative was part of IPEEC's GSEP programme (Clean Energy Ministerial 2014).

being an online-information tool only. On the other hand, within the Centre's so-called "Circle of Experts," the Centre co-operates with experts from all over Germany. These experts are representatives from public institutions and regional energy agencies. They meet twice a year to discuss energy-contracting-related challenges and solutions (dena 2015d, Energy Agency NRW 2015). Through this expertise, the Centre designs standardised documents (e.g. guidebooks, standard contracts) easing the contractual situation between contracting parties, develops new contracting solutions²⁶ and it can also offer advanced advisory services for developing contracting projects. Innovative projects are accompanied by dena.

Apart from that, the Government seeks to establish default guarantees for energy contractors. In particular, small and medium sized contractors are in a difficult financial position to obtain sufficient financing in order to fulfil comprehensive contracting works. Through Government guarantees, private financial institutions become more willing to offer loans to SMEs.

b) Type of policy instrument

Through the online-platform and the "Circle of Experts," the dena via the Centre of Excellence for Contracting promotes energy services.

c) Objective

The overall objective of the Centre is to facilitate the uptake of contracting solutions. According to dena (2015d), it does so by (i) bundling know-how and expertise on contracting, (ii) enhancing the quality of contracting-tenders (iii) advancing contracting models and (iv) mediate interests between the supply side (contractors) and the demand side (public institutions from the national, regional and local level). Through default guarantees, the Government seeks to improve the situation for SME energy contractors to obtain financing by banks.

d) Target group

The Centre of Excellence aims at promoting contracting solutions with public buildings at the national, regional and local level (e.g. schools, universities, hospitals or buildings for administrative purposes). Therefore public institutions constitute one of the core target groups. Apart from public authorities, the Centre also seeks to engage with private building owners of residential and non-residential buildings. Energy contractors are also considered to be a target group (dena 2015b). Default guarantees are offered to small- and medium-sized energy contractors.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Both, the Centre of Excellence and default guarantees are interacting mechanisms that are to facilitate energy contracting.

f) Implementation network

The Centre of Excellence is administered by the German Energy Agency (dena). However, experts from all over Germany, which are representatives of public authorities, also participate in the Centre's works.

g) Outcomes

According to dena (2014), around 30 projects, that is federal properties, have been supported through dena resulting in energy cost savings (39%) and CO₂ emission reduction (37%). The introduction of default guarantees is only in the emerging stage.

²⁶ For instance, such solutions may embrace new technologies or methods to undertake contracting.

1.1.6 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT AND BEST AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGY (BAT) PROMOTION

The following section provides information the German tool-kit facilitating R&D and BAT. In particular, the section includes the low energy buildings project and the efficiency house plus project. These projects include research that accompanies and assesses the construction process of buildings with the most advanced technology available and energy-related living behaviour of occupants. The research initiative “Zukunft Bau”, the programme “research for energy-optimised construction” and the 6th Energy Research Programme rather focus on the development of new construction material, technologies and methods. On the other hand, public procurement guidelines target the promotion best available technologies in the appliance sector.

1.1.6.1 LOW ENERGY BUILDINGS PROJECT (DENA) AND EFFICIENCY HOUSE PLUS

a) General information

The Low Energy Buildings (LEB) project, initiated in 2003, is a national measure managed by dena. The project supports building owners in comprehensive energetic building refurbishment. While dena accompanies building projects, the state-owned KfW provides financing to realise refurbishment activities. Through the projects, dena gathers information on, for instance, energy savings and best-practices. Respective information is to be distributed to building experts (e.g. architects, planners). Through the demonstration of successful, energy saving refurbishment action and enhanced capacities of building experts, other building owners are to be attracted to follow the example of low energy buildings. The project was rolled out gradually initially including only residential buildings but later the programme also embraced non-residential buildings (e.g. schools) (dena 2005, 2008, 2009).

Apart from that, the Government launched the Efficiency House Plus (EHP) project. The research project supports the realisation of buildings that are net energy producers or – in other words – small-scale power plants (BBSR & Fraunhofer Institute 2015).

b) Type of policy instrument

The low energy buildings project as well as the efficiency house plus project can be seen as instruments to accelerate R&D and BAT.

c) Objective

Through the low energy buildings project, dena seeks to (i) reduce the energy consumption of buildings participating in the project, to (ii) raise the capacities of building experts and to (iii) incentivise others to follow the example of demonstration buildings. While the efficiency house Plus projects has similar goals, it is more oriented towards new buildings.

d) Target group

The immediate target group consists of building owners including property companies and private owners of single family houses. Further beneficiaries are experts that carry out energy efficient refurbishment (e.g. experts). Moreover, other building owners are addressed and expected to follow the lead of the demonstration buildings.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Traditionally, KfW has been supporting building owners in Germany. KfW is a AAA-rated bank and can raise money on capital markets at relatively low costs. Such capital is on-lend to building owners. Hence, it can be seen as an ideal instrument to facilitate energy efficiency in the German building sector.

f) Implementation network

In the LEB project, the dena is in charge of the management and KfW provides financing to selected building owners. The EHP project is co-operation project of the Federal Institute for Research on Building, Urban Affairs and Spatial Development as well as the Fraunhofer Institute. The latter also carries out project-accompanying research together with the Institute of Social Research.

g) Outcomes

Through the LEB the annual energy consumption of buildings was decreased by around 85% on average.

1.1.6.2 RESEARCH INITIATIVE “ZUKUNFT BAU” AND RESEARCH FOR ENERGY-OPTIMISED CONSTRUCTION

a) General information

The Research initiative “Zukunft Bau” supports building-related research. While research institutes and construction industry can apply for funding for their projects, which have to be of public interest, the Government can also tender particular research projects (BMUB 2014, 2015).

Research for energy-optimised construction focuses, among other things, on the development of new building materials and procedures as well as innovative technologies, systems and planning concept for buildings. These are tested in pilot projects, which are, in turn, accompanied by research (BMW 2014).

b) Type of policy instrument

By providing financing to the construction industry and research organisation, the Government promotes R&D.

c) Objective

The objective of the instruments is to facilitate incentivise R&D and to enhance the knowledge of building technologies and methods. Such knowledge is critical for optimising policy instruments.

d) Target group

Research institutions and the construction industry are target groups of the two instruments.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

One of the key influencing mechanisms that interacts with the discussed R&D promoting instruments is Germany’s energy performance standard (EnEV). In order to tighten the standards, which Government has frequently done in recent years, it has to pave the way for new technologies

f) Implementation network

The research initiative is a project is co-operation project of the Federal Institute for Research on Building, Urban Affairs and Spatial Development as well as the Fraunhofer Institute. The latter also carries out project-accompanying research together with the Institute of Social Research. The EnOB programme is funded through the Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy and implemented

by the Research Centre Jülich. The Centre also accompanies applicants, verifies project documents and monitors research results.

g) Outcomes

Between 2006 and 2014, the Government provided EUR 83 million for realising 750 projects.

1.1.6.3 PUBLIC PROCUREMENT GUIDELINES (VERGABEVERORDNUNG, VgV)

a) General information

When public authorities procure energy-consuming goods, they should seek to include energy consumption as a purchasing criterion, in particular, if the most economical bid is to be assessed. According to the German NEEAP (2014, p. 25), "the highest level of energy efficiency and, where available, the highest energy-efficiency class should be demanded when procuring goods that have a bearing on energy consumption." Moreover, national procurement guidelines require bidders to unveil the energy consumption of products and under certain circumstances, for instance, lifecycle costs can be requested.

b) Type of policy instrument

Public procurement is, generally, made effective through regulatory procedures mandating authorities to procure products that meet certain criteria.

c) Objective

In particular, by requesting authorities to procure the most energy-efficient energy consuming products, the Government of Germany promotes best available technologies. The instrument should have a positive impact on the product upfront costs, which is beneficial to other consumer groups (e.g. households).

d) Target group

The VgV is directly applicable to public procurement bodies. However, it also addresses manufacturers indirectly. If manufacturers know that there is a demand for very energy-efficient products, they are incentivized to put such products on the market.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Procurement authorities are guided by the Public Procurement Regulation. Labels ease the process of comparing energy consuming products enormously.

f) Implementation network

Procurement bodies are in charge of implementing energy efficiency criteria.

g) Outcomes

Information on the outcomes have not been available for this study. However, since the public sector is the largest buyer of goods and services, energy efficient procurement guidelines are expected to have a substantial impact on BAT-promotion and, ultimately, on energy savings (UBA 2014 as found in NEEAP 2014).

1.1.6.46. ENERGY RESEARCH PROGRAMME

a) General information

Through the 6th Energy Research Programme (ERP), the Government assists research institutions and businesses in developing future energy technologies, which is crucial for Germany's low carbon future and a successful energy transition. The focal areas include energy generation, transformation, transport, distribution and storage. For the period between 2013 and 2016, the Federal Government financed the ERP with EUR 3.5 billion. In 2014 only, the Government provided almost EUR 850 million. Renewable energy research and energy efficiency research were supported with EUR 300 million each, which makes these fields the most important cornerstones of the programme (BMW 2015c).

b) Type of policy instrument

The Energy Research Programme is a strategic document that stresses future focal areas in the realm of energy.

c) Objective

The most relevant objective of the Energy Research Programme is to support the energy and climate goals of the Federal Government. As the promotion of energy efficiency and renewable energies are core issues of the energy transition, the Programme is linked to these objectives. In particular, BMW (2011) states that it is important to reduce costs and accelerate market penetration. Second, the Programme seeks to enhance competitiveness of German companies in these sectors. Moreover, it seeks to capture technology options, which allow for a more flexible provision of energy.

d) Target group

In particular, the Programme aims at research institutions as well as construction companies.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

In Germany, the federal states also have non-nuclear energy research programmes - in 2013, the states provided a budget of around EUR 312 million.

f) Implementation network

The ERP has a variety of research areas, which are administered by different ministries. The focal area Energy in Buildings and Quarter is allotted to the BMWi. However, the processing of projects is carried out by the Research Centre Jülich.

g) Outcomes

In 2013, 218 projects were funded in the realm of energy efficiency in buildings.

1.1.7 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR IN GERMANY

Table 15: Overview of measures implemented in Germany

Summary table: Buildings					
Policy instruments	Short list of implemented policies and measures	Objective	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Implementation network
Regulatory policy instruments	Energy Saving Ordinance (EnEV)	Prevent market entrance of energy inefficient buildings	Mainly investors in new buildings; owners of old boilers	Among other things, financial support for new buildings if EnEV standards are exceeded substantially and funding for new energy-efficient heating systems in existing buildings	Construction companies and public authorities
	Regulator Inspection of Boilers and (non-residential) air-conditioning	Phase out inefficient building-related appliances	Operators of boilers and (non-residential) air-conditioning	Financial support for exchange of inefficient heating system through the Market Incentive Programme	Chimney sweepers for boilers and adequately trained experts for A/C systems
	Heating cost regulation	Provide detailed overview of monthly heating costs	Building occupants and owners	Increased costs for energy are an incentive to lower the excessive use of energy	Energy providers
	Energy Performance Certificate	Initiate dynamic market transformation towards a higher degree of energy efficiency in buildings	Building owners are required to hand over EPC to future owners or tenants	Penalties are established for not handing over an EPC to potential buyers or tenants	Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy

Dissemination and awareness instruments/Informative policy instruments	Energy checks	Promote the uptake of energy efficient appliances and behaviour	Households; especially low-income households are addressed by the energy check programme carried out by Caritas	Energy checks are available at very low to no costs; with the Caritas-managed programme, small-scale energy saving equipment is given free of charge	The consumer organisation <i>Verbraucherzentrale</i> Caritas
	On-side energy consultation	Identify energy saving options	Households, particularly building owners	Financial support incentivises one-side energy consultation	BAFA
	Energy consultation for SMEs (KfW)	Identify energy saving options	SMEs	Subsidies are offered	KfW bank and BMWi
	KfW Construction Monitoring	Support building owners with refurbishing energy-inefficient buildings	Building owners of energy-inefficient buildings	Construction monitoring is partly financed	BMWi, KfW bank
	Dena Efficiency House Quality Mark	Increase visibility of energy-efficient buildings and inform owners about energy demand	Home owners	KfW energy efficient renovation and construction programmes complement the Quality Mark	Dena
Economic policy instruments	KfW Energy-efficient construction	Support residential building investors with realising an energy-efficient home	Home owners	Financial support (soft-loans including grants) available; EnEV is used as a benchmarking tool to assess the amount of the support	KfW
	KfW Energy-efficient Renovation	Support residential building owners with realising the refurbishment towards an energy-efficient home	Home owners	Financial support (soft-loans including grants, grants) available; EnEV is used as a benchmarking tool to assess the amount of the support	KfW
	Energy tax	Facilitate the more rational use of	Cross-cutting	N/A	The main customs office of the Federal Ministry of

		energy			Finance's
	Market incentive programme	Reduce upfront costs for certain energy-efficient technologies and promote market breakthrough	Cross-cutting	Financial support available for taking up respective technology options	BAFA
	BAFA cross-cutting technologies	Reduce upfront costs for certain energy-efficient technologies and promote market breakthrough	SMEs and energy contractors assigned by SMEs	Financial support for installation of energy efficient technologies or for the systematic optimisation	BAFA
Capacity building and networking	Energy efficiency networks initiative	Promote voluntary energy saving targets and knowledge on how to achieve targets	SMEs	Financial incentives available for first-movers	Fraunhofer Institute for Systems ISI
	Promotion of energy management systems	Facilitate the uptake of an EMS	Mainly the manufacturing sector	Funding for EMS available	BAFA
	Educational vouchers for re-training towards energy advisors	Expand the supply of energy advisory services	Direct: people interested in becoming an energy advisors; indirect: home owners and occupants	The educational voucher subsidises retraining	Federal Employment Agency
	Requirement guidelines for energy consultants and list of certified energy consultants	Safeguard proper training for experts supporting the realisation of energy-efficient homes	Direct: energy efficiency experts; indirect: home owners	KfW and BAFA programmes require appropriate training of advisors	KfW, BAFA

	International Partnership for Energy Efficiency Cooperation	Improve policy-making	Direct: German Federal Government; indirect: cross-cutting	N/A	Members states
Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services	Centre of Excellence (incl. default guarantees)	Improve knowledge and procedures for the uptake of energy services Default guarantees support smaller companies to energy the energy services market	Energy services providers and public authorities	The Centre of Excellence and the default guarantees offered to smaller companies complement each other	Dena
Policy instruments for Research and Development and BAT promotion	Low energy buildings project and efficiency house Plus	Increase visibility of efficiency houses, and, primarily, promote BAT	Actors of the residential building sector	KfW offers financing support	dena
	Research initiative "Zukunft Bau" and Research for energy-optimised construction	Promote R&D	Research institutes and construction industry	Project financing available	Federal Institute for Research on Building, Urban Affairs and Spatial Development, Fraunhofer Institute, Institute for Social Research, Research Centre Jülich
	Public procurement guidelines	Promote BAT	Public procurement bodies	Particularly, building labels help public procurement authorities to identify energy-efficient technologies	BMW i
	6 th energy research programme	Promote R&D	Research institutions and construction companies	Financing is available	BMW i, Project Centre Jülic

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

In order to increase the energy efficiency in the transport sector, three different levels of energy efficiency connected with three basic strategies have to be taken into account, based on the Avoid-Shift-Improve (ASI) approach (e.g. Schipper and Marie-Liliu 1999, Dalkmann and Brannigan 2007, ADB 2009):

- Avoid travel or reduce travel-length in order to improve the system efficiency which concerns how transport is generated and how modes are chosen.
- Shift travel to more energy-efficient modes in order to improve the travel efficiency which covers the energy consumption of different transport modes.
- Improve the energy efficiency of vehicles and fuels in order to improve the vehicle efficiency which can be improved by reducing the vehicle's fuel consumption per kilometre.

For implementation, different instruments (planning, regulation, economic incentives, information and technology oriented measures) can be used.

The table below displays the most relevant policy instruments for energy efficiency in the transport sector currently in place in Germany, and must not be taken as an exhaustive list. Most of the policy instruments refer to the national level. Policy instruments which are mainly based on EU-directives or regulations are also mentioned, but not further explained as these instruments are not specific for Germany, but for all member states of the European Union. Additionally, there are also actions taken at the level of the Federal States and on local level.

Referring to the National Action Plan on Energy Efficiency (NAPE) (Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy 2014), the major measures taken so far for reducing energy consumption in transport are the European regulations on CO₂ reduction in passenger and light commercial vehicles, fuel taxation and heavy goods vehicle toll.

Table 16: Overview of selected policy instruments for the transport sector in Germany

German policy instruments for the transport sector	
Planning Instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federal transport infrastructure plan 2015: stronger emphasis on railways and waterways (freight) concerning budget • National cycling plan • Mobility and fuel strategy: introduction of alternative fuels and innovative drive technologies • <i>Improving bicycle infrastructure: investments in construction and maintenance of cycling tracks, and many individual projects at local level to further encourage bicycle traffic</i> • <i>Single European Sky: Improving flight paths in regard to environmental efficiency</i>
Regulatory instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Law on electric mobility (Elektromobilitätsgesetz) • Voluntary agreement with German National Railways: specific CO₂ reduction targets for the period 2006-2020 • <i>EU regulation: emission performance standards for new passenger cars (No. 443/200).</i> • <i>EU regulation: emission performance standards for new light</i>

	<p><i>commercial vehicles (No. 510/2011)</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Renewable Energy Directive (2009/28/EC) > national implementation: European Law Adaptation for Renewable Energies (Europarechtsanpassungsgesetz Erneuerbare Energien - EAG EE)</i> • <i>Fuel Quality Directive (2009/30/EC): fuel quality standards, biofuel quotas, biomass sustainability ordinance etc. > national implementation: Federal Emissions Protection Act (BimSchG) and Federal Emissions Protection Ordiances (BimSchV)</i>
Economic instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CO₂-related motor vehicle tax (German: Kraftfahrzeugsteuergesetz) • Ecological tax reform: eco tax on motor fuels, extension of tax reduction for natural gas in the transport sector • Heavy goods vehicle toll charges (German: Verordnung zur Erhebung, zum Nachweis der ordnungsgemäßen Entrichtung und zur Erstattung der Maut) • Fiscal allowances for work-related travel expenses, part of the income tax act (German: Einkommensteuergesetz, § 9) • Regionalisation act (German: Gesetz zur Regionalisierung des öffentlichen Personennahverkehr): financial aid for investments for improvement of the infrastructure and the transport of passenger in cities and municipalities • Levy on air traffic: “ecological” levy on air traffic at the national level for all flights from German airports • <i>Municipal transport financing act (German: Gesetz über Finanzhilfen des Bundes zur Verbesserung der Verkehrsverhältnisse der Gemeinden (GVFG))</i>: financial aid for investments for improvement of the infrastructure and the transport of passenger in cities and municipalities • <i>Investments in construction and maintenance of cycling tracks and many individual projects at local level to further encourage bicycle traffic</i>
Information and awareness instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Passenger car labelling: EU directive 1999/94/EC > national implementation: Verordnung über Verbraucherinformationen zu Kraftstoffverbrauch, CO₂-Emissionen und Stromverbrauch neuer Personenkraftwagen • Mobility management action programme • “me and my car” campaign • Federal procurement initiative for electric mobility • “new driving” campaign
Policy instruments for Research and Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government electro mobility programme • Funding programme for electro mobility in model regions Programme: Modellregionen Elektromobilität und Schaufensterregionen Elektromobilität) • National innovation programme for hydrogen and fuel cell technology

1.2.1 PLANNING INSTRUMENTS

Planning can reduce the need to travel through bringing people and activities they need to access closer together. Planning can also enable the implementation of new transport infrastructure (road, rail, other public transport, cycling and walking). Planning instruments include all measures that focus on „smarter“ planning of infrastructure.

There are planning instruments on all levels (national, federal states, regional, local). In the following, the Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan as well as the National Cycling Plan are further described as the main planning tools at the national level. Additionally, the Mobility and Fuel Strategy is further explained. Even if the Mobility and Fuel Strategy has no legally binding content by itself and is not an overarching mobility strategy, it is an initial, concrete contribution by the transport sector achieving the targets set out in the German government's Energy Concept for the transport sector (BMVBS 2012).

1.2.1.1 FEDERAL TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE PLAN 2015 (FTIP 2015)

a) General information

Under the basic law, the Federal Government has to take the responsibility to maintain, upgrade and construct the federal transport infrastructure (federal motorways, federal roads, federal waterways, railway lines for long-distance traffic and freight traffic). An efficient transport infrastructure is crucial for competitive economic activities and thus, economic growth and employment. The Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan, which is valid for about 10-15 years in general, reveals all the infrastructure projects that the Federal Government sought to implement the upcoming years. It covers three modes of transport, namely road, rail and maritime transport. Consecutive infrastructure plans are complementing each other through the identification of the need to invest in further infrastructure and an assessment of the viability of projects.

b) Type of policy instrument

The Federal Transport Plan is a planning tool and a framework investment plan.

c) Objective

Generally, the Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan aims "to provide people with safe and affordable mobility and create a reliable and competitive transport environment for the business sector" (BMVI 2015a). The enhancement of the German competitiveness in the global economy should create and secure employment. The plan seeks to follow an environmental friendly strategy as it aims to reduce the use of nature, the landscape and non-renewable resources. With regard to negative externalities, emissions of noise, pollutants and greenhouse gases should be diminished essentially. More specifically, the upcoming Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan 2015 is prepared: It aims to establish a new approach to plan infrastructure and to develop criteria for the prioritization of transport infrastructure investment. In times of financial constraints, the prioritization of investment represents the most important challenge. It means "policymakers should focus on meeting the most pressing needs." (BMVI 2015b) The Federal Transport Plan 2015 emphasizes that future transport policy will be based on safeguarding quality of existing networks through structural maintenance. Furthermore, a major contribution should be made by improving "links between ports/hub airports and their hinterland." (ibid). This upcoming plan will set a stronger emphasis on railways and waterways relatively to the Federal Transport Plan 2003.

The main transport policy objectives can be summarized as follows:

- enabling mobility in passenger transport (by maintenance of substance, improving traffic flow, improvements of accessibilities)
- ensuring the supply of goods, increasing competitiveness of enterprises (by maintenance of substance, improving traffic flow, reliability of transport, reduction in transport costs)
- increasing traffic safety (by maintenance of substance, shifting to safer transport modes)
- reducing greenhouse gases and pollutants (by improving traffic flow, shifting to more environmentally sound transport modes, maintenance of substance)

- limiting the use of nature and landscape (by limiting additional land usage, no further loss of non-fragmented areas/habitat corridors, maintenance of substance)
- Improving quality of life in towns and regions (by noise reduction, easing the burden of towns)

d) Target group

In the end, everybody who travels on federal roads, railways or motorways belongs to the target group as the FTIP is the mainly responsible for the development and the quality of the transport network.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

With regard to developing the federal transport infrastructure by the FTIP the following actors are involved: Proposals for maintaining, upgrading or construction of federal roads can only be submitted by Federal States, whereas there are no limitations by project proposals for federal railways. Besides the Federal States and railway infrastructure provider (DB Netz AG), also associations, initiatives and even citizens are allowed to submit proposals.

The most important task within the development of the FTIP is the development of criteria in order to prioritise the investments in federal transport infrastructure. There are three main steps how available investments are distributed:

Step 1: Firstly, the necessary financial resources for maintenance the substance of the existing traffic network will be determined by forecasts so that precedence is given to maintenance of substance.

Step 2: The remaining financial resources are distributed among the three transport carriers.

Step 3: Finally, the project proposals are classified into urgency categories within each transport carrier. Ongoing projects will be finalised as a matter of first priority. Additionally there are four more categories for new projects: priority needs plus, priority needs, further needs and further needs with planning regulations.

As financial resources are limited and therefore it is not possible to realise all project proposals, the benefit-cost-ratio is one crucial criteria for classifying into urgency categories. For the same reason, maintenance of substance and improving traffic flow (abolition of bottlenecks) are the objectives which are finally prioritised.

f) Implementation network

The Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure prepares and establishes the Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan. Finally, the federal government adopts the new plan. The Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan 2003 will expire in 2015. After revising the approach and methodology, FTIP 2015 will be implemented.

The FTIP forms the basis for the Federal Government's bill to amend the acts governing the upgrading of federal railway infrastructure and federal trunk roads with the related requirement plans. Based on the requirement plans, the Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure develops five-years-plans which illustrate the need for investment for the years ahead. IN 2006/2007, for the first time, the Ministry developed a cross-modal framework investment plan for federal transport infrastructure which includes information relating to the federal waterway projects (additionally to the federal railway infrastructure and federal trunk roads).

g) Outcomes

As the Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan 2015 is still in the formulation/ preparation phase, there are no documents on outcomes of the FTIP 2015 available. However, one could estimate outcomes by having a closer look at the recent FTIP. It was predicted "against the background of the rising

demand for transport, the regulatory and fiscal measures of the integration scenario plus the investment projects of the FTIP 2003 will result in a significant reduction in CO₂ emissions” (BMVI 2003). One could conclude that in the upcoming Plan measures to further diminish emissions will be introduced. Moreover, as the FTIP 2015 aims to emphasize railway and maritime transportation with regard to freight, the traffic volume will be split and balanced on each mode.

1.2.1.2 NATIONAL CYCLING PLAN (NCP)

a) General information

The Federal Government has adopted the National Cycling Plan as a regulatory framework to promote cycling purposes. Cycling as a facilitator to tackle current and future transport and social challenges entails a positive impact on the quality of life, environment and climate. Therefore, by establishing the National Cycling Plan, the Federal Government encourages the maintenance and additional construction of cycling infrastructure. Cycling is determined to be an essential part of a modern transport system in urban and rural areas (BMVI 2015c). It is “used to act as a promoter, catalyst, facilitator and coordinator.” (ibid) The current National Cycling Plan, which covers the period from 2013 to 2020 complements the original NCP (2002-2012). The former does not only aim to promote cycling, but also to strengthen the “ecomobility”, which encompasses local public transport, walking and cycling (ibid). It rather prefers a holistic approach relatively to its forerunner, the NCP 2013 as it emphasizes “the promotion of a challenge for society as a whole.” (ibid) Although Germany is already one of most developed European countries in terms of cycle use, the current NCP seeks to make use of Germany’s enormous potential.

The NCP 2020 uses nine action areas to identify the major actions required for evolving cycling and describes/recommends the specific steps that have to be taken by the Federal Government, federal states and local authorities, each within their own sphere of responsibility:

- planning and developing a cycling strategy
- infrastructure
- road safety
- communications
- cycle tourism
- electric mobility
- linkage with other means of transport
- mobility and road safety education
- create and safeguard qualities

b) Type of policy instrument

The National Cycling Plan belongs to several kinds of instruments. Firstly, it is a planning instrument as it summarizes the communal responsibilities of all tiers. Secondly, it is an information instrument, as it comprises guidelines and important action areas (incl. action required and problem-solving strategies and measures) in order to improve cycling conditions. Additionally, it is a policy instrument for research and development. As part of the implementation of the NCP, innovative projects and lighthouse projects (mainly not infrastructural projects with the exception of pilot projects as e.g. cycle superhighways or cycle parking facilities) are funded by the Federal Government.

Provided that funds are available the Federal Government is also responsible to determine appropriate funds to implement the measures prescribed in the NCP. Thus, it also can be seen as a financial tool.

c) Objective

By adopting the National Cycling Plan 2020, the existing regulatory framework should be improved to harness potential. As the national modal share of cycling was 10% in 2008, the share can be increased significantly until 2020. There is an adequate basis to promote cycling measures because of changes in the societal environment and the fact that journeys made by the public become shorter than five kilometres. (BMVI 2015c) Another objective is the complementation of the predecessor's vision "cycling as a system", which potential can only be exploited, when fields of activities are extended. Those should include intensive communication, public relations and the field of service. NCP 2020 aims that at all levels (local, city and national) policymakers should adopt this approach into their implementation plans. The promotion of cycling represents a major contribution by tackling societal problems with regard to health issues. Apart from strengthening public's health and safeguarding people's mobility, promoting cycling contributes to the prevention of greenhouse gases.

d) Target group

The National Cycling Plan is not only addressed to the Federal Government, but even more importantly to the federal states and local municipalities, because as part of the federal system they have the responsibility to implement the individual measures to promote cycling at local level. In addition to this, the successful implementation of cycling measures depends on the support from trade associations, businesses and the general public (BMVI 2015c).

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

In order to effectively promote cycling measures at local level, municipalities are categorized according to different stages of development (BMVI 2015c):

- Starters: municipalities are just starting to promote cycling
- Climbers: municipalities obtained an advanced level of cycling promotion
- Champions: municipalities reached a high level of cycling promotion.

f) Implementation network

A communal responsibility of all tiers of government is needed in order to promote cycling. The Federal Government contributes to a sustainable transport policy with regard to cycling by shaping the regulatory framework and providing funds within its area of responsibility. The Federal Government is responsible for ensuring a safe cycling infrastructure along federal highways. With the NCP, the government has also successfully assumed the function of promotor, facilitator, coordinator and catalyst by funding innovative and transferable schemes and pilot projects plus research and by disseminating examples of good practice.

The federal states play an active role as authorities responsible for construction and maintenance of their own roads as part of the devolution of Federal Government responsibilities as well as in their capacity as coordinators at federal state level. Additionally, the federal state can provide direct financial assistance to the promotion of cycling in municipalities.

The local authorities have central responsibility for implementing specific measures on the ground. They try to achieve their own objectives (expressed by the targeted modal cycling share of the total traffic volume) by implementing appropriately their individual cycling measures.

g) Outcomes

Promoting cycling measures could harness the potential and increase the cycling share of the traffic volume in Germany to 15%, which is a realistic scenario. However, local authorities have set their own objectives. For instance, "according to the information provided by Baden-Württemberg, the modal share of cycling in that state is to be doubled from 8% to 16% by 2015, with a target of 20% for

2020.” (BMVI 2015c) Furthermore, the National Cycling Plan 2020 suggests that the highest growth rates are among the municipalities, which are assessed as “starters”.

The NCP 2020 expects that cycling will play an essential role in the transport system of 2050. It contributes to a sustainable traffic development as cycling is environmentally friendly, improves the quality of life and is inexpensive for users and the public sector. (BMVI 2015c)

1.2.1.3 MOBILITY AND FUEL STRATEGY

a) General information

On the 12.06.2013, the German federal government introduced a “mobility and fuel strategy”. The main idea of the strategy was to develop goals and concepts in order to reduce energy consumption and CO₂ emissions in the transport sector. The strategy is based on the “fuel strategy” from 2004. After publishing the strategy in 2013, the strategy will be further developed in a dialogue process between actors from politics, companies and research as a so-called “learning strategy” (BMVBS 2013).

b) Type of policy instrument

Since the strategy formulates action recommendations for the government’s policies and it has no legally binding content by itself, the instrument can be characterized as voluntary. Specific laws and regulations are following the strategy though or have already set into action.

c) Objectives

The objective of the strategy is to foster the efforts for reducing energy consumption and CO₂ emissions. Specific objectives are for example the reduction of energy consumption in the transport sector by 40% until 2050 (BMVBS 2013).

d) Target groups

While the fuel strategy from 2004 focused on alternative fuelling concepts for the car sector, the new strategy is open to all kinds of technologies and targets all transport modes (BMVBS 2013).

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The strategy contains recommendations and describes options and potential measures to achieve the before mentioned goal. No sanctions are included though (BMVBS 2013).

f) Implementation network

The strategy, i.e. the included action recommendations is and will be implemented by various actors, first of all the federal government.

g) Outcomes

The government aims to reduce energy consumption in the transport sector by 40% until 2050 and 10% already until 2020. Whether these objectives can be achieved depends on the implementation and the success of the respective measures and regulations (BMVBS 2013).

1.2.2 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS

Regulatory policy instruments can be used to restrict the use of certain motorised vehicles, but also influences the types of vehicles used and standards that they should adhere to (both in terms of vehicle performance and road regulation). The regulatory instruments in the transport sector can be classified into four categories based on the purpose of the instruments: a) fuel economy standards, which aim at reducing fuel consumption and associated emissions, b) emission standards which are

directly aimed at the reduction of specific emissions released after fuel consumption, c) fuel quality standards to reduce or eliminate emissions causing elements before the combustion of fuel and d) other regulatory measures either discouraging vehicle utilization or encouraging high occupancy of the vehicles (Timilsina and Dulal 2009: 82). Referring to increase the energy-efficiency in the transport sector, fuel economy standards and other regulatory measures are of importance.

Many regulatory policy instruments in Germany are based on EU directives. These policy instruments are not further described as EU directives have to be implemented in all member states.

1.2.2.1 LAW ON ELECTRIC MOBILITY - ELEKTROMOBILITÄTSGESETZ (EMOG)

a) General information

The law on electric mobility came into force on 12th June 2015. This law should promote privileges for people using electrically powered vehicles (pure battery electric cars, plug-in hybrids and fuel cell vehicles). Those privileges include for instance parking priorities and the abolition of parking fees as well as use of bus lanes.

To encourage climate and environmental protection, the Federal Government set ambitious targets in 2009 by establishing the National Development Plan for Electric Mobility. These targets were further prepared and clearly defined as electric powered vehicles have many advantages compared to vehicles powered by conventional engines. They are much more efficient in the first place as they locally do not emit greenhouse gases and pollutants. Besides, they cause significantly less noise emissions. Therefore, electric mobility shapes a new environmental-friendly form of transportation. (Elektromobilitätsgesetz 2015)

b) Type of policy instrument

The law on electric mobility can be characterized as a regulatory policy instrument as it is a mandatory policy instrument to provide privileges for user of electrically powered vehicles.

c) Objective

This law contributes to the promotion of electric mobility by prescribing incentives to use electronically powered vehicles. It aims to boost the demand for electric vehicles. The Federal Government aims to increase the number of electronically powered vehicles from 125,000 to 1,000,000 by 2020.

d) Target group

Measures should be implemented at local level.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

In order to apply for the privileges prescribed in the law on electric mobility, eligible vehicles are clearly defined such as electric vehicles, fuel cell vehicles.

On the basis of this law, a directive should change traffic regulations in the future: The labelling of privileged vehicles, which are electrically powered, should represent a formal criterion to use the privileges. Additionally, by establishing such a directive, the federal states have the opportunity to adopt the privileges of electronically powered vehicles into the road traffic regulations.

f) Implementation network

The law was implemented by the German parliament and becomes valid after its publication.

g) Outcomes

No data available.

1.2.2.2 VOLUNTARY AGREEMENT WITH GERMAN NATIONAL RAILWAYS

a) General information

The German National Railways (Deutsche Bahn) has defined a specific CO₂ reduction target for the period 2006–2020, in relation to the traffic volume in 2006. The passenger transport, rail freight traffic and logistics business areas have their own subsumed energy and CO₂ reduction targets for this purpose (BMW_i 2011). All in all, the German National Railways planned to reduce their worldwide CO₂ emissions by 20% (Deutsche Bahn 2015).

b) Type of policy instrument

Since the target for CO₂ reduction is not binding, the instrument can be characterized as a voluntary instrument (BMW_i 2011).

c) Objectives

The objective of the agreement is to substantially reduce the worldwide CO₂ emissions of the German National Railways and its subsidiaries.

d) Target groups

The voluntary agreement is targeted at the German National Railways and its subsidiaries. It thus covers a large part of the German rail transport sector (BMW_i 2011).

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Since the agreement is voluntary, no sanctions or penalties for non-compliance have been implemented. Since the CO₂ emission reduction was planned to be achieved by an increase in energy efficiency and the saving of energy, the agreement provided financial incentives due to potentially lower energy cost (Deutsche Bahn 2015).

f) Implementation network

The different business areas of the German National Railways like the passenger transport, rail freight traffic and logistics business sector have their own subsumed energy and CO₂ reduction targets and the business areas themselves are responsible for definition and control of the measures (BMW_i 2011).

g) Outcomes

By 2020, the German National Railways aimed to reduce its specific CO₂ emissions from rail, road, air and ocean transportation by 20% compared to 2006 levels. In 2014 it has already reached this target six years earlier with 22.7% less specific CO₂ emissions (Deutsche Bahn 2015).

1.2.3 ECONOMIC INSTRUMENTS

Economic instruments can be used to discourage the use of motorised vehicles, which will encourage the use of alternative modes, or reduce the need to travel (de Haan et al. 2007). Instruments can also improve accessibility and mobility for those without a private vehicle, through investment in public transport, cycling, and walking infrastructure.

1.2.3.1 CO₂-RELATED MOTOR VEHICLE TAX

a) General information

Starting from 1st July 2009, the Federal government passed a new tax regulation regarding vehicles. The main novelty consists of a new charging system which taxes capacity (= base tax) as well as CO₂ emissions (CO₂ tax).

b) Type of policy instrument

Economic instrument

c) Objectives

Economic instruments like CO₂-related taxes not only generate revenues, but may induce behavioural change in producers and consumers. A major objective of the tax reform has been to reduce emission rates of new vehicles.

d) Target groups

The registered keeper of a vehicle is liable for the tax in Germany.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The base tax is 2 EUR per 100 cc (petrol) and 9.5 EUR (diesel) respectively. The CO₂ tax is linear at 2 EUR per g/km emitted above 95 g/km. Cars with CO₂ emissions below 95 g/km are exempt from the CO₂ tax component.

f) Implementation network

Before the reformation of the tax system in 2009, car taxes were a matter of the Federal states. Since the motor vehicle tax is also based on CO₂ emissions, it is a matter of national level.

g) Outcomes

The Öko-Institut et al. (2009) has estimated the fuel and CO₂ savings due to the CO₂ based vehicle tax in Germany ex-ante as follows:

Table 17: Estimated fuel and CO₂ savings

Policy Instrument	2010	2020
CO ₂ -related motor vehicle tax	Direct CO ₂ (kt): 2 Energy (PJ) (Fuels): 23.6	Direct CO ₂ (kt): 3 Energy (PJ) (Fuels): 43.1

Source: Öko-Institut/IFE-STE/DIV/Fraunhofer ISI/Ziesing (2009)

1.2.3.2 ECOLOGICAL TAX REFORM - ECO TAX ON MOTOR FUELS

a) General information

In the course of the so-called ecological tax reform, the tax burden on different forms of energy, like electricity or motor fuels has been significantly increased in Germany in 1999. Besides introducing a new tax on electricity, existing taxes like the petroleum tax have been increased during this reform. The Law Initiating the Ecological Tax Reform increased the price of energy from 1st April 1999 by

- motor fuels: 0.037 EUR/l
- fuel oil: 0.002 EUR/l
- gas: 0.016 EUR/kWh
- electricity: 0.01 EUR/kWh

In a second step in 2002, the tax rate on petroleum has been further increased. Totally, the petrol and diesel prices increased from 1999 to 2003 by 3.07 cents per liter and year (totalling an increase of 15.34 cents/l as of 2003).

b) Type of policy instrument

Economic instrument: By imposing a tax, financial incentives are given in order to regulate and reduce fuel consumption.

c) Objectives

With its ecological tax reform the German Government aimed to encourage energy saving and promote renewable energies, as well as to create jobs. (Parallel to the introduction of the eco-tax, contribution rates for statutory pensions insurance – and consequently the nonwage labour costs – were reduced.) The instrument aimed at internalising a part of the external costs and increasing energy efficiency in the transport sector (Wuppertal Institute 2012).

d) Target groups

The additional tax burden is imposed on different forms of energy like electricity, diesel and petroleum, making all consumers of these goods are potential targets of the tax. In their regulation, the government included several exemptions though, exempting for example the aviation sector from the ecological tax. Thus airplanes are not targeted, while cars and trains are.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Various exemptions and specific rules are implemented in the ecological tax regulation, including the before mentioned exemption for the aviation industry as well as exemptions from the tax on electricity for the renewable energy production. Additionally, taxation on fuels relies on ecological criteria, resulting in higher taxes on fuels that contain lead or high amounts of sulphur.

f) Implementation network

The ecological tax reform has been implemented by the government in 1999 and extended in 2002. The local customs offices, under supervision of the Federal Ministry of Finance, ensure the collection of the taxes.

g) Outcomes

The ecological tax reform had an effect on the motorised individual transport in Germany: The increase in petroleum prices results in a decrease of the kilometres driven by private households. According to a study from 2010, the effect is rather small though (DIW 2010) and is overcompensated by an increase in personal incomes. The ecological tax thus is able to influence mobility behaviour, while the effect on overall CO₂ emissions is rather small as well.

1.2.3.3 HEAVY GOODS VEHICLES TOLL CHARGES – HGV TOLLING SCHEME: FEDERAL TRUNK ROAD TOLL ACT

a) General information

In general, the Heavy Good Vehicle (HGV) toll is a charge, which is levied on heavy goods vehicles using federal motorways and certain federal highways. The amount of the levied toll depends on the number of kilometres driven. Users of all vehicles having a maximum permissible weight of at least 12 tonnes or more are obliged to pay the HGV toll. The Federal Trunk Road Toll Act, more specifically the Act on Levying of Distance-Related Charges for the Use of Federal Motorways and Federal Highways, entered into force on 19 July 2011. This new act superseded the Motorway Toll Act for Heavy Goods Vehicles and extended the HGV tolling scheme “to include federal highways which, by statutory instrument, were applied to 1,100 kilometers of federal highways for the first time on 1st August 2012.” (BMVI 2015d)

b) Type of policy instrument

The Federal Trunk Road Toll Act, which was implemented in 2011, can be assessed as an economic instrument.

c) Objectives

When the Federal Government introduced a system for the automatic distance-related charging of HGVs in the 1990s in Germany, it claimed the following reasons for its implementation: The transport infrastructure should be paid according to the “user pays” principle. In order to upgrade or construct transport infrastructure projects, the user should financially contribute. Besides, HGV tolls were introduced in order to improve the conditions of a competition on the roads, railways and waterways. With regard to global warming, tolls promote increasing environmental protection by means of emission category-based differentiation. This approach provides an incentive for companies to invest in environmental friendly vehicles. (HGV tolling scheme) Lastly, the HGV tolling scheme aims to promote innovative technologies.

d) Target groups

On the one hand, authorities and ministries are addressed at national level, as the HGV project concerns only federal motorways and highways. On the other hand, the Federal Trunk Road Toll Act is of particular importance for logistic or other service companies that are equipped with heavy good vehicles.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The obligation to pay refers to all vehicles, which have a maximum permissible weight of at least 12 tonnes or more. Particular vehicles such as buses and coaches, defence and security vehicles or maintenance vehicles are not required to pay the HGV tolling fee (BMVI 2015d).

f) Implementation network

The Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure has been responsible for the implementation of the HGV toll projects.

g) Outcomes

Broaddus and Gertz (2008) observed the immediate impacts of introduced truck tolls in Germany. People expected avoidance traffic as trucks might avoid toll roads by using parallel routes. But Broaddus and Gertz (2008) identified that the impact of avoidance traffic was minimal (ibid). Besides, “since introduction of the truck toll, there has been a clear shift in Germany toward trucks with better emission standards, partly the result of subsidies for the purchase of low-pollution vehicles.” (ibid) This trend towards a fleet change has led to a decrease in vehicle emissions. In order to avoid the toll fee, marketing campaigns from truck manufacturers promoted lighter trucks less than 12 tons. The annual number of sold vehicles between 10 and 12 tons doubled after the tolls were introduced. (ibid) Finally, the expected modal shift of freight from road to more environmentally friendly railway transportation did not hold due to rail capacity constraints.

With regard to revenue, the responsible Toll Agency (Toll Collect) collected 2.86 billion euro in 2005, which increased in 2006 to 3.08 billion euro. The collected levies should be spent in 2006 as follows: 1.08 billion euro for road building and maintenance, 820 billion euro for upgrading the federal railway network and lastly 260 billion euro for inland waterways. (ibid)

The assessment of impacts on energy savings by the toll charges have also been analyzed by Prognos and results have been included in the 3rd NEEAP and the Article 7 notification. The results are summarized in the following table:

Table 18: Assessment of energy savings by heavy goods vehicle toll charges

Heavy goods vehicle toll charges	3 rd NEEAP/Article 7 notification			Prognos (2012)						
	2014-2020	Intermediate milestone (31.12.2017)	Early Action (2009-2013)	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020
Final Energy (PJ)										
Yearly savings	-	-	-	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0	3.0
Commulative savings	21	12.1	-	3.0	6.1	9.1	12	15	18	21

Source: Website Odyssee - MURE

1.2.3.4 FISCAL ALLOWANCES FOR WORK-RELATED TRAVEL EXPENSES

a) General information

The German tax regulation allows for fiscal allowances in the case of expenses for travelling from home to work and back. These expenses can be, according to the German income tax law (EStG), deducted from the income tax base, resulting in a reduction of the overall income tax burden of the commuter. The fiscal allowance for work-related travel expenses has first been manifested in 1920 and has been subject to several changes in the past decades. Problems occurred for example in the case of persons with multiple residences or regarding the means of transportation eligible for the allowance, and have been tackled in several court decisions.

b) Type of policy instrument

The instrument reduces the income tax burden of the eligible persons and thus is a financial policy / economic instrument.

c) Objectives

The objective of the regulation is to account for expenses due to travelling to and from their workplace by reducing the tax burden of the respective commuters.

d) Target groups

Eligible are all employees and self-employed persons that have to travel to their workplace. Eligible are all means of transport but airplanes and taxis (according to EStG), thus most parts of the transportation sector are concerned by the regulation.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

According to the EStG, commuters can deduct 0,30 € per kilometer driven, independent from which of the eligible means of transport has been used and independent from the actual cost of commuting. The tax allowance is voluntary and has to be applied for by the tax payers. Experts argue, that the allowance offers incentives to commute to work instead of living next to the workplace (see e.g. Donges et al. 2008).

f) Implementation network

A fiscal allowance for travel expenses has been implemented by the government explicitly in the EStG of 1920. Nowadays, local tax authorities in each federal state and the supervision authority of the respective state are responsible for the tax allowance in Germany.

g) Outcomes

The Federal Environment Agency states that the tax allowance for travel-related expenses supports the growth in overall traffic volume in Germany, especially the growth in individual motorised transport, causing an increase in CO₂ emissions (UBA 2010). Abolishing the tax allowance might thus result in CO₂ emission mitigation. The agency estimates potential mitigations of 2.6 Mio. ton of CO₂ per year (UBA 2008).

Additionally, experts argue that the tax allowance supports a potential trend towards longer commuting distances and along with that a so-called “urban sprawl”, while others neglect those interdependencies (UBA 2010, Donges et al. 2008).

1.2.3.5 REGIONALIZATION ACT**a) General information**

The regionalization act stipulates that in return for guaranteeing public local passenger transport in consequence of assuming responsibility for local passenger rail transport, the federal states receive a share of the federal government’s petroleum tax receipts. The idea is to use these additional public funds to finance the local passenger rail transport, which might not be profitable to operate otherwise. Regionalisation funding in the order of around 6.7 billion euro for the federal states was appropriated in the year 2008, and this will increase by 1.5 % annually from the year 2009 (BMWi 2011). The act has first been implemented in 1993.

b) Type of policy instrument

The regionalization act provides financial transfers and incentives between the different levels of public authorities and can thus be considered as financial policy / economic instruments.

c) Objectives

The predominant objective of the statutory provisions is to achieve a behavioral change in favor of local public transport (IEA 2015). To achieve this, the acts help to provide sufficient rail infrastructures and railway services for the German population as part of the so-called public service (“Daseinsvorsorge”).

d) Target groups

The regionalization act targets public transport, especially rail based transport. It is restricted to local and regional rail transport.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

By providing public funds for the local passenger rail transport, the regionalization act provides incentives to improve local public transport.

f) Implementation network

The funds of the regionalization act are provided by the federal government, while it is the responsibility of the federal states to implement sufficient public rail transport on a regional and a municipal level respectively. They will do so with public tenderings and procurement procedures for railway companies and by funding investments into public transport infrastructure.

g) Outcomes

From 1996, when the regionalization act funds were allocated for the first time, until 2013 the number of passengers in local public rail transport increased by 60%, while the number of passenger kilometres increased by 31,9% from 2000 until 2013 (Allianz pro Schiene, 2014). The act can thus be considered successful in promoting local passenger rail transport. Assuming that some passengers

might otherwise have chosen individual motorized transport, one can conclude that the act helped mitigating CO₂ emissions.

1.2.3.6 LEVY ON AIR TRAFFIC AT THE NATIONAL LEVEL FOR ALL FLIGHTS FROM GERMAN AIRPORTS (GERMAN: LUFTVERKEHRSABGABE)

a) General information

The “Luftverkehrsabgabe” is an ecological levy that applies for all departures of passenger flights from 01.01.2011 starting from a German airport. The amount of this “ecological departure tax” depends on the destination country and is divided into three categories of 7.50€, 23.43€ and 42.18€ per flight and passenger. The tax is then added to the ticket prices of the passengers by the aviation companies (Deutscher Bundestag 2012).

b) Type of policy instrument

The levy on air traffic is a tax and can thus be characterized as a financial policy / economic instrument.

c) Objective

The two objectives of the levy on air traffic are to: 1. Generate additional revenue for the federal government, 2. Reduce the tax advantages of the air traffic sector, which do not have to pay fuel taxes (Deutscher Bundestag 2012).

d) Target group

The levy on air traffic is targeted at the passenger air traffic sector in Germany (Deutscher Bundestag 2012).

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

There are exemptions for the freight transport sector, as well as medical and military flights, private planes and amateur flyers. Moreover, the tax is not imposed on children under 2, as well as airplane personnel (Deutscher Bundestag 2012).

f) Implementation network

The levy on air traffic was implemented as part of an austerity package by the German government in 2010.

g) Outcomes

The levy on air traffic put high additional cost on the aviation industry, reaching 983 Mio.€ of tax revenue in 2014 (Statistisches Bundesamt 2015). This made passenger flights less affordable. The additional tax burden might have caused a dampening of demand of around 2 Mio. passengers which equals 1,1% of the yearly passenger traffic from and to Germany. The German government suspects that due to the dampening of air transport demand, pollutant emissions have been mitigated by a similar percentage (Deutscher Bundestag 2012).

1.2.4 INFORMATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS

The provision of information can increase the awareness of alternative modes, leading to a modal shift to public transport, walking or cycling. Information and training can help to improve driver behaviour, resulting in reduced fuel consumption. Finally, information on the energy efficiency of new vehicles can influence purchase decisions (UBA 2010).

1.2.4.1 PASSENGER CAR LABELLING

a) General information

The Fuel Efficiency Labelling of Passenger Cars Regulations, which was implemented on 1st December 2011, require new cars to be equipped with fuel economy labels. These labels shall indicate the vehicle’s CO₂ emissions for consumers. By adopting this law, the EU Directive 1999/94/EC on appropriate “information relating to the fuel economy and CO₂ emissions of new passenger cars offered for sale or lease in the Community” (Directive 1999/94/EC) has been implemented into national law. Thus, car labelling aims to ensure a transparent access of information to the consumer. Apart from emphasising the absolute consumption, the Fuel Efficiency Labelling of Passenger Cars Regulations reveals a colour-coded CO₂ efficiency scale that compares the vehicle’s CO₂ to other models. It ranges from very efficient “A+” to rather in efficient “G”.

Figure 3: Exemplary Fuel Efficiency Labelling of Passenger Cars

b) Type of policy instrument

This policy measure belongs to an information and awareness instrument as it encourages transparency and adequate information on the impact of the vehicle on the environment.

c) Objective

The Fuel Efficiency Labelling was designed to provide the consumer with visible and clear information on the greenhouse gas emissions of a new car. Besides, the fuel economy label is designed to hold electricity consumption data as well in order to take account of the growing popularity of electric vehicles (BMVI 2014).

d) Target group

The fuel economy label particularly addresses the users of vehicles.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The label provides information about

- the CO₂-energy efficiency category the vehicle belongs to (from A+ very efficient to G less efficient),
- the annual motor vehicle tax (which is based on CO₂-emissions)
- the annual costs for energy (fuel or electricity) based on 20,000 kilometers and averaged fuel costs

The classification into a category for energy consumption and CO₂ emissions are related to the weight of the car. It has to be noted that the cars' weight has too much influence on the classification, because heavy passenger cars get a green label more often than lighter passenger cars even if their CO₂ emissions are higher. Thus, the label is only partly suited to differentiate between efficient and inefficient cars.

f) Implementation network

Car salesmen are obliged to visibly label every car offered to buy or to lease.

g) Outcomes

Up to now, there is no evaluation of the impact of the energy consumption labelling of new vehicles. Even analysing the development of the sale figures of vehicles does not provide necessary information, because no evaluation has been carried out yet in order to examine in how far the energy labelling of new cars influences the purchase decision.

1.2.4.2 MOBILITY MANAGEMENT**a) General information**

Mobility Management (MM) is defined in many different ways and is also changing over time. Referring to the MAX-project it can be defined as follows: "Mobility Management (MM) is a concept to promote sustainable transport and manage the demand for car use by changing travellers' attitudes and behaviour. At the core of Mobility Management are "soft" measures like information and communication, organising services and coordinating activities of different partners. "Soft" measures most often enhance the effectiveness of "hard" measures within urban transport (e.g., new tram lines, new roads and new bike lanes. Mobility Management measures (in comparison to "hard" measures) do not necessarily require large financial investments and may have a high benefit-cost ratio" (European Platform on Mobility Management).

There are different initiatives in Germany to promote mobility management, e.g. the action programme "Mobility Management" of the German Energy Agency (dena), which is promoted by the German Federal Environment Ministry. The programme was established in 2008 with 15 model regions being selected.

b) Type of policy instrument

Information and awareness instrument

c) Objectives

The Action Programme Mobility Management aims at coordinating the supply and demand of private, public and industrial mobility. It transfers mobility to more efficient modes of transport and aims at improving mobility communication.

d) Target groups

Enterprises, public administrations, hospitals, universities, local authorities etc.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The target groups (see above) are supported by regional coordinators and information events, initial-advice, information material and a web portal. Within the programme, local actors are consulted by a substantial on-site evaluation of the current situation and the development of a concept plus giving assistance implementing and launching the concept

f) Implementation network

The action programme consists of seven modules:

- regionalization
- initial consultations
- competitions
- national network
- communication
- masterplan
- programme management

g) Outcomes

A first evaluation after two years shows the following outcomes and possible impacts: 100 initial-consultations have been conducted and 85 concepts for company mobility management schemes have been worked out. The total reduction potential is estimated and it adds up to an average of 248 tCO₂ per year for each site. The impact of the whole action programme is quantified to be generating savings of about 23 kt CO₂ per year (www.effizient-mobil.de).

1.2.4.3 INITIATIVE “ME AND MY CAR. DRIVING SMART, SAVING GAS”

a) General information

The initiative started in 2008 and focused on car drivers training for fuel-saving driving techniques and the promotion of low-viscosity engine oil and low rolling resistance-optimised tyres.

b) Type of policy instrument

Information and awareness instrument

c) Objectives

Identifying efficiency potentials in regard to car driving and developing consumer tips.

d) Target groups

Car drivers

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

A compilation of tips, tricks and background information has been developed and merged into a wealth of information and guidance materials. These information materials are distributed at the point-of-sale as well as by extensive media relations work

f) Implementation network

The initiative has been developed by the German Energy Agency (DENA) and is funded by the Federal Ministry for Environment. The German Federation for Motor Trades and Repairs (ZDK) supports the initiative as a partner and multiplier. The German Traffic Safety Association (DVR) takes part in the advisory board and supports the initiative with professional expertise. The automobil club in Germany (ADAC) also supports the initiative with professional expertise, especially in the field “driving behaviour”.

g) Outcomes

After being surveyed, the majority of the German car drivers have already changed their user behaviour and driveability. Furthermore the demand for energy-efficient tyres and low-viscosity engine oils could be stimulated (Website Odysee - MURE).

1.2.4.4 FEDERAL PROCUREMENT INITIATIVE FOR ELECTRIC MOBILITY**a) General information**

In order to support a strong deployment of electrical drives on the motor vehicles, the federal government has started an initiative to promote electric mobility by federal procurement. A guide about electric mobility has been developed by an expert group. Furthermore, the federal “Joint office of electric mobility” had already executed an informational event, namely “Procurement Day” on the similar theme in 2014.

b) Type of policy instrument

It is a combination of an information instruments and economic incentives.

c) Objectives

The federal government has set in its government programme electric mobility, the goal of having 10 % of all newly purchased or leased vehicles by the federal government and its subordinate authorities the emission value will not be allowed to exceed 50 g CO₂/km.

d) Target groups

Federal government and its subordinate authorities

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Cost will be incurred when the differential cost of acquisition between the conventional vehicles and the newly procured/leased vehicle with lowest emission value is funded and this investment cost in return is not compensated by monetary savings during the vehicle operation or by increase the purchase price of the new vehicle

f) Implementation network

Coordinated with the federal states, the Federal Government has launched the procurement campaign in 2015.

g) Outcomes

Presently, impact assessment in terms of savings has not been quantified. The current measures are in actual leading to savings rather they are setting examples of pioneering the role of state of electric mobility (Website Odysee - MURE).

1.2.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

On the national level, there are several research and development programmes in order to support research and development in the field of alternative fuels and propulsion technologies. Main focus lays on the increasing distribution of electric mobility.

1.2.5.1 GOVERNMENT PROGRAMME ON ELECTRIC MOBILITY

a) General information

The Government Programme on Electric Mobility 2011 was implemented in order to react on the results of the second report of the National Platform for Electromobility. Therefore, this programme follows the recommendations of the report. According to this report, electric mobility is key for a climate-friendly mobility. "It is an opportunity, and a challenge, to further consolidate Germany as a cutting-edge location for industry, business, science and technology" (National Platform for Electromobility n.d.). The Government Programme seeks to support R&D measures by creating regional showcases and technical flagship projects in order to encourage an increased synergy effect within this mobility sector (Website Germany Trade & Invest).

b) Type of policy instrument

This programme can be assessed as a policy instrument with the focus on the promotion of research and development measures in the electromobility sector.

c) Objectives

The Government Programme on Electric Mobility aims to push Germany into a lead provider of and a lead market for electric mobility by 2020. Therefore, this plan should pave the way to exploit Germany's opportunities to create a significant contribution to employment and developing Germany to a role model with regard to electric mobility relatively to competing countries.

d) Target groups

Electric mobility target groups are particularly addressed "on the basis of clustering focused needs and interests and on strategic prioritization and cascading" (National Platform for Electromobility n.d.).

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The regional showcase projects will act as a "shop window" for innovative cross-industry partnerships in the country's different federal states. This means making German technological expertise visible in a small number of large projects in which public and private partners pool their joint competences and resources (Website Germany Trade & Invest).

f) Implementation network

The Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi) and the Federal Ministry of Transport, Building and Urban Development (BMVBS) adopted the Government Programme on Electric Mobility in May 2011 as a reaction on results of the second report of the National Platform for Electric Mobility.

g) Outcomes

According to the Second Report of the National Platform for Electric Mobility, by exploiting all the opportunities there will be a potential to create around 30,000 additional jobs over the period to 2020 (National Platform for Electromobility n.d.). This can only be achieved with the investment in research and development.

1.2.5.2 FUNDING FOR ELECTRIC MOBILITY IN MODEL REGIONS (“ELECTRIC MOBILITY MODEL REGIONS” AND “SHOW CASE REGIONS”)

a) General information

The "Electric Mobility Model Regions" funding programme is a cross sectional cooperation of industry, science and the public sector to further promote the electric mobility sector until 2020. Several modal regions were created, which are applying different approaches and strategies. Moreover, seven supra-regional platforms facilitate the exchange of experiences and interlinking over the longer term.

b) Type of policy instrument

The Funding Programme for electric mobility in modal regions is based on a policy instrument to promote of research and development.

c) Objectives

The funding programme "Electric Mobility Model Regions" aims to advance the development of electric mobility infrastructure and and to integrate electric mobility in everyday life. (Website National Organisation Hydrogen and Fuel Cell Technology)

d) Target groups

This funding programme for electric mobility is particularly relevant to the selected modal regions in order to implement the different approaches and strategies. Additionally, the electric mobility industry and scientific institutions are addressed.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Measures are implemented in several model regions.

f) Implementation network

The Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure (BMVI) is responsible for the implementation of the funding programme "Electric Mobility Model Regions". However, on behalf of the Federal Government the NOW GmbH National Organisation Hydrogen and Fuel Cell Technology coordinates these tasks.

g) Outcomes

Within the framework of the "Model Regions" the programme has already achieved the first successes due to the provision of around 300 public charging stations. Therefore, in particular in this area regional project funding has proven itself to be a successful approach, because there are still major differences of electric mobility infrastructure between the pilot regions. Success is further developed by strong regional partnerships.

1.2.5.3 NATIONAL INNOVATION PROGRAMME FOR HYDROGEN AND FUEL CELL TECHNOLOGY (NIP)

a) General information

Hydrogen and fuel cell technology will play an essential role in the future of mobility and energy supply. In order to guarantee the further development of these technologies, in 2006 government, industry and science began a strategic alliance called the National Innovation Programme for Hydrogen and Fuel Cell Technology (NIP).

b) Type of policy instrument

Research and development as well as a funding instrument.

c) Objectives

NIP is intended to speed up the process of market penetration of products based on hydrogen and fuel cell technology.

d) Target groups

Industry

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The total budget of NIP invested over a period of ten years (2006-2016) amounts to 1.4 billion EUR. The Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure (BMVI) and the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs (BMWi) provide half of this sum, while the balance is funded by participating industry.

f) Implementation network

Besides large-scale demonstration projects, NIP also focuses on research and development projects. The demonstration projects are grouped into comprehensive lighthouse projects and take place under real conditions. Project partners thus work together and more efficiently on issues and challenges, which they otherwise would have to face alone, and with considerable individual effort.

NIP is divided into four programme areas in order to advance in equal measure, numerous hydrogen and fuel cell technology product and application option, and to be able to address in a targeted way the market-specific challenges of market penetration. The particular programme areas are:

- transport and hydrogen infrastructure
- hydrogen provision
- stationary energy supply
- special markets

With an eye to series production of components, the explicit focus in all programme areas is on the strengthening of the supply industry.

g) Outcomes

No data available.

1.2.6 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR IN GERMANY

Table 19: Summary table for the German transport sector

Summary table: Transport					
	Short list of implemented policies and measures	Objective ²⁷ (improve system, travel or vehicle efficiency)	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Implementation network
Planning instruments	Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan	System and travel efficiency	All transport users	1. financial resources for maintenance; 2. Remaining financial resources are distributed among the three transport carriers, 3. Project proposals are classified into urgency categories by benefit-cost-ratio	Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure, Federal States, railway infrastructure provider, associations, initiatives
	National Cycling Plan	System and travel efficiency	Federal government, federal states, municipalities	Motivation	Federal government, federal states, local authorities
	Mobility and fuel strategy	Vehicle efficiency			
Regulatory policy instruments	Law on electric mobility	Vehicle efficiency	Municipalities	Motivation	German parliament
	Voluntary	Vehicle efficiency	German National Railways	Motivation	German National Railways

²⁷ Energy efficiency in the transport sector can be divided into system efficiency (reduce or avoid travel or the need to travel), travel efficiency (shift to more energy efficient modes) and vehicle efficiency (improve the efficiency through vehicle technology).

Summary table: Transport					
	Short list of implemented policies and measures	Objective²⁷ (improve system, travel or vehicle efficiency)	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Implementation network
	agreement with German National Railways		and its subsidiaries		
Financial policy instruments	CO ₂ -related motor vehicle tax	Vehicle efficiency	Car owner	Motivation or punish non-compliance	German parliament, federal finance administration
	Ecological tax reform	System efficiency, travel efficiency, vehicle efficiency	Car drivers	Motivation or punish non-compliance	Federal Ministry of Finance and local customs offices
	Heavy goods vehicle toll charges	System efficiency, travel efficiency, vehicle efficiency	Logistic and service companies	Motivation or punish non-compliance; "User pays" principle	Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure, Toll collect
	Fiscal allowances for work-related travel expenses	Travel efficiency	Employees and self-employed persons	Motivation	Local tax authorities and the supervision authority of the respective state
	Regionalisation act	Travel efficiency	Public transport	Providing funds for local passenger rail transport.	Federal government, federal states
	Levy on air traffic	Travel efficiency	Passenger of air traffic		German government
Dissemination and awareness instruments	Passenger car labelling	Vehicle efficiency	Car drivers	Motivation	Car salesmen
	Mobility management action programme	System and travel efficiency	Enterprises, public administrations, hospitals, universities, local authorities etc.	Motivation	German Energy Agency (dena), Federal Ministry for Environment
	"me and my car"	Vehicle efficiency	Car drivers	Motivation	German Energy Agency (dena),

Summary table: Transport					
	Short list of implemented policies and measures	Objective²⁷ (improve system, travel or vehicle efficiency)	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Implementation network
	campaign				Federal Ministry for Environment, German Federation for Motor Trades and Repairs, German Traffic Safety Association, automobil club (ADAC)
	Federal procurement initiative for electric mobility	Vehicle efficiency	Federal government and its subordinate authorities	Motivation	Federal government and federal states
Policy instruments for Research and Development	Government electro mobility programme	Vehicle efficiency		motivation	Federal Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy, Federal Ministry of Transport, Building and Urban Development
	Funding programme for electro mobility in model regions	Vehicle efficiency	Model regions, electric mobility industry, scientific institutions	motivation	Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure, National Organisation Hydrogen and Fuel Cell Technology
	National innovation programme for hydrogen and fuel cell technology	Vehicle efficiency	Industry	motivation	Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure, Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs, participating industry

2. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE REGIONAL / LOCAL LEVEL

The interaction between the different levels (national, regional, local) in energy efficiency policy making has already been covered in D.1.1. Next to national energy efficiency policies, many regions and cities have implemented own climate action plans, energy efficiency action plans, or are part of the Covenant of Mayors. Describing all existing policy instruments or energy efficiency measures, would be too much and is not possible in the framework of this project. Therefore, in this deliverable, specific policy instruments on the regional / local level are exemplarily covered by a case study.

2.1 PRESENTATION OF THE CASE STUDY: THE CLIMATE ACTION PLAN OF THE CITY OF HAMBURG, GERMANY

Hamburg is located in the north of Germany and is Germany's second biggest city with a population of about 1.7 million inhabitants. Hamburg has one of the most important ports in Europe and is also a centre for various industries like, for example, aerospace and media. The great importance of the industry for Hamburg's local economy is apparent in its greenhouse gas inventory: In 2012, the CO₂-emissions of Hamburg's industry amounted to 5.9 million tons. The transport sector was responsible for emissions of 4.2 million tons, the residential sector contributed 4.3 million and the tertiary sector 3.9 million tons. In total, Hamburg's CO₂-emissions added up to 18.4 million tons in 2012²⁸. One peculiarity of Germany's political system makes Hamburg and its climate and energy (efficiency) policy an interesting example. Hamburg is both a city and a state. With respect to the competencies and functions of the different levels in the German multi-level system, Hamburg fulfills both the functions of a state and a city. This means that Hamburg has more options to implement policies and measures and access to a higher budget than the "usual" city.

2.1.1 OVERVIEW OF THE ENERGY EFFICIENCY ACTIONS OF THE CITY OF HAMBURG: THE CITY ACTION PLAN 2007-2012

In 2007, the city of Hamburg developed a climate action plan, which aimed to reduce CO₂ emissions by 2 million metric tons by 2012 compared to 2007 levels. The action plan contains various measures and policies in the following fields of action: building sector, transport sector, industry and plant sector, national and international cooperation, climate impact management and adaptation, research and evaluation and monitoring. Almost 350 measures and policies were implemented within the city's boundaries between 2007 and 2012. A budget of more than 115 million Euros was earmarked for the implementation of Hamburg's climate action plan.

²⁸ Data available online: http://www.statistik-nord.de/fileadmin/Dokumente/Sonderveroeffentlichungen/Energie-und_CO2-Bilanz_Hamburg/EB_CO2_HH_2012.pdf.

Figure 4: Hamburg's climate action plan: Number of measures and share in total funding by field of activity

The measures in Hamburg's climate action plan vary not only with respect to the field of action, but also with respect to scope and, accordingly, impact. **Figure 4** shows the number of measures by field of activity. Within (almost all) these fields of activity, there exist measures and policies which aim to improve energy efficiency. What kind of measures belong to the different fields of activities will be discussed in more detail below. Roughly half of all measures belong to the fields energy, building and transport sector. Looking at the share of total funding allotted to the fields of activities, energy, buildings and transport sector represent almost 70 percent.

Most of the measures in the field energy were designed to support and increase the use of renewable energies in Hamburg. Nevertheless, many measures in this field were energy-efficiency-related as well. For instance, one of the energy efficiency measures with the highest impact belongs to this field of activity. This measure has helped to reduce electricity consumption of public buildings, especially outside of office hours, by retrofitting lighting, ventilation and IT systems.

The majority of projects and measures in the building sector were aimed at improving the energy efficiency of the built environment. With a number of 76 measures, it is obvious that the scope of these is quite diverse. This field of activity comprises funding schemes for energy efficiency refurbishments together with several individual residential building projects, projects for the refurbishment of public buildings and the introduction of an energy label, the so-called *Hamburger Energiepass*. The *Hamburger Energiepass* includes recommendations for energy efficiency improvements and is a prerequisite for being eligible for funds from the funding schemes (see further discussion below). Another important example, which also underlines Hamburg as a special case, is the *Hamburger Klimaschutzverordnung*, the Climate Action Ordinance of Hamburg. In 2007 the legislature of Hamburg passed a bill which imposed stricter minimum energy performance standards for buildings than the respective federal decree²⁹. Hamburg had this option only because it is both a city and a state. The "usual" German city does not have the power to legislate.

For the transport sector, many measures were developed to increase walking and bike use, improve public transportation and to make the port and airport more climate-friendly. Important measures which directly address the energy efficiency of transportation are a substantial refurbishment of street lighting, the development and adoption of hybrid-electric busses and setting efficiency

²⁹ The federal decree for minimum energy performance standards for newly built and refurbished buildings has been tightened in 2009 and thereby superseded the *Hamburger Klimaschutzverordnung* as the most strict decree becomes binding. Hamburg's legislature has not imposed stricter energy performance standards since the *Hamburger Klimaschutzverordnung* in 2007.

standards for the public car pool. The refurbishment of the street lighting is also an example for the city of Hamburg using funding by the federal state to implement a local energy efficiency measure. This is one of few examples of an interaction between national and local actions. With respect to scope and impact, the implementation of a strategy to increase bike use has been the most important measure and will be described in detail below.

The field “Industry and plant technology” contains one of the most important and successful measures of Hamburg’s climate action plan when it comes to energy efficiency. The programme “Unternehmen für Ressourcenschutz” (Companies for Resource Efficiency) financially supports investments by small and medium enterprises in energy and resource efficiency. Examples of specific measures supported are the installation of cogeneration units, the acquisition of new, more energy efficient engines or the refurbishment of lightning, cooling and heating systems. Funding is granted per ton of avoided CO₂-emissions. Other measures also comprised specific energy efficiency improvements, like the refurbishment of the ventilation system of a sewage treatment plant and the improvement of the IT system of the port authority to limit their electricity consumption.

Obviously, the field “climate adaptation” does not contain measures which aim to improve energy efficiency. For instance, the measures in this field are dealing with improvements of flood protection or help to increase the number of trees in the city.

With the measures in the field “Raising awareness” the city of Hamburg wants to reduce energy consumption by increasing awareness for the importance of individual actions and decisions for total energy demand. Typical examples are educating pupils about ways to limit energy use and exhibitions about the dangers of climate change and options for climate protection. The measures in the field “Research and development” span various research and development projects, including projects aimed at developing new energy efficiency technology. Under the caption “National and international cooperation” the city of Hamburg subsumes various activities, like the organization of international conferences and networking. The field “Monitoring and evaluation” contains all activities and measures dealing with monitoring the effects and impacts of the climate action plan and devising ways to increase its impact.

Subsequently, the measures in the buildings and transport sector will be described in more detail.

2.1.2 ENERGY EFFICIENCY INSTRUMENTS: EXAMPLES FOR THE BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT SECTOR

Since the funding schemes are the most important building block with which the city of Hamburg helps to improve the energy efficiency of buildings in Hamburg, the section will concentrate on these. All of the programmes discussed below are administered by the Hamburgische Investitions- und Förderbank (IFB), a public bank owned by the city of Hamburg.

Hamburger Energiepass (Hamburg Energy Certificate)

The Hamburg Energy Certificate is a document that contains an energy performance rating and names specific options for a refurbishment of the building and associated energy saving potentials. The Hamburg Energy Certificate is issued by certified consultants. An examination of the building and its heating system takes place on site and the consultant afterwards discusses options for refurbishment with the building owner(s). As federal law makes an energy performance certification obligatory in some cases, the compilation of the Hamburg Energy Certificate is often coupled to the compilation of the less detailed energy performance certificate required by federal legislation.

The costs for the Hamburg Energy Certificate depend on the building size and range from 880€ for a single family home to 2,000€ for a building with 100 or more dwelling units.

The IFB, a public bank owned by the city of Hamburg, subsidises the compilation of the Hamburg Energy Certificate with 40 to 60% of the total costs if at least three dwelling units in the building are available for rent. In certain cases, i.e. if the building owner uses funding from one of the other funding schemes for energy efficiency refurbishments, the subsidy may even be higher. The Hamburg Energy Certificate is a prerequisite to be eligible for some of the IFB's subsidy programmes.

Wärmeschutz im Gebäudebestand (Energy-saving in existing houses)

This subsidy programme is only available for homeowners, who live in their own house, and landlords with two or less dwelling units available for rent. With this programme the IFB both subsidises individual measures on certain parts of the building (e.g. windows, roof) and extensive refurbishments of the whole building. The amount of subsidies differs between cases, in which individual measures are supported, and complete refurbishments. If individual measures are to be financially supported, the Hamburg energy certificate is no prerequisite. Table 1 shows the amount of grants for individual measures.

Table 20: Subsidies available for individual measures

Thermal insulation of exterior walls	20.00 € / m ²
Thermal insulation of interior walls (only for listed buildings)	15.00 € / m ²
Insulation of double-leaf walls	3.00 € / m ²
Thermal insulation of the basement ceiling	5.00 € / m ²
Thermal insulation of the upper floor ceiling	7.50 € / m ²
Thermal insulation of steep roofs and dormers	30.00 € / m ²
Thermal insulation of flat roofs	15.00 € / m ²
Installation of insulated glazing	60.00 € / m ²
Installation of insulated glazing (roof windows)	120.00 € / m ²
Installation of insulated glazed doors	90.00 € / m ²

Extensive refurbishments of the whole building are funded differently. The amount of subsidies depends on the level of ambition of the refurbishment. The higher the energy performance standard, the higher the subsidy. **Table 21** shows this.

Table 21: Subsidies available for extensive refurbishments

Energy demand for heating after refurbishment	Subsidy
Between 55 and 70 kWh/m ² *a	0.25 € for every kWh saved
Between 40 and 55 kWh/m ² *a	0.30 € for every kWh saved
Less than 40 kWh/m ² *a	0.35 € for every kWh saved

The Hamburg Energy Certificate is a prerequisite for being eligible for funding out of this programme. A combination with other sources of funding (e.g. with funds from the national programmes of the KfW Bank) is generally possible.

Energetische Modernisierung A (Energy Efficiency Refurbishments A)

This funding programme provides funds for energy efficiency refurbishments of multi-family residential buildings with at least three dwellings available for rent. A prerequisite for funding is the Hamburg Energy Certificate and the supervision of the refurbishment through a certified expert. Generally, the subsidy increases with the energy performance standard after the refurbishment and the extent of energy savings. As an element of social policy, the subsidies are higher if the building owner commits himself to limit the increase of the rent after refurbishment. These values are in brackets.

Table 22: Subsidies available in the programme Energetische Modernisierung A

<p>Level 1 – Final energy demand ≤ 90 kWh/m²a</p> <p>Annual energy demand for heating: 0.224 € (0.337 €) for every kWh saved Annual final energy demand: 0.224 € (0.337 €) for every kWh saved</p>
<p>Level 2 – Energy performance equivalent to the minimum energy performance standard required for newly constructed buildings and a final energy demand ≤ 75 kWh/m²a</p> <p>Annual energy demand for heating: 0.245 € (0.367 €) for every kWh saved Annual final energy demand: 0.245 € (0.367 €) for every kWh saved</p>
<p>Level 3 – IFB-Efficiency House 70</p> <p>Annual energy demand for heating: 0.281 € (0.423 €) for every kWh saved Annual final energy demand: 0.281 € (0.423 €) for every kWh saved</p>
<p>Level 4 – IFB-Efficiency House 40</p> <p>245 € (367 €) per m² of floor area</p>
<p>Level 5 – IFB-Passive House</p> <p>245 € (367 €) per m² of floor area</p>
<p>Level 6 – IFB-Ultra Low Energy House</p> <p>265 € (398 €) per m² of floor area</p>
<p>Level 7 – IFB-Plus Energy Building</p> <p>275 € (408 €) per m² of floor area</p>

Additional subsidies are available for the installation of a ventilation system and for the preservation of clinker facades. All subsidies may be cumulated with funding by the KfW bank.

The measure with the widest scope and highest impact for the transport sector was the so called “Radverkehrsstrategie”, a strategy to increase bicycle use. Concrete steps undertaken by the city of Hamburg are the expansion of the bicycle infrastructure, like constructing bicycle lanes and bikeways, and creating more opportunities for bicycle parking. Further elements of the strategy were easing mixed-mode commuting by establishing bicycle parking stations at public transportation stations and motivating the public to more often use their bike.

2.1.3 INTERACTION BETWEEN NATIONAL AND LOCAL POLICIES

There are several interactions between national policies and the funding programmes of the IFB Hamburg, which have already been hinted at. Federal legislation demands energy performance certificates in certain cases. The Hamburger Energiepass is both more detailed and gets subsidised if the building owner is a landlord. Insofar the local policy is both supporting and supplementing the national policy. During the compilation of the Hamburger Energiepass the energy performance certificate according to national legislation can be easily issued. At the same time, the Hamburger Energiepass has a higher standard.

Similar arguments are valid for the IFB's funding schemes. The federal government is supporting the refurbishment of residential buildings to an energy performance standard higher than the minimum standard set by federal legislation through soft loans granted by the Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau (KfW), a public bank owned by the federal state. The IFB's funding schemes are both complementary and supplementary. They are complementary because building owners may both apply for a loan by the KfW and subsidies by the IFB and combine these two sources of funding. They are supplementary because they are grants and thereby constitute a bigger incentive with interest rates as low as currently.

The interaction between national and local policies in the transport sector is less important. Most of the measures implemented within the Radverkehrsstrategie concern urban planning and urban infrastructure, which are inherently municipal competencies. The federal government may support these actions financially but is otherwise not involved in planning municipal bicycle infrastructure.

2.1.4 DISCUSSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Altogether, the climate action plan of Hamburg has been among the most ambitious and successful in Germany. The local measures in the climate action plan have avoided about half a million tons of annual CO₂-emissions, which has been attested in an evaluation of the climate action plan³⁰. This has helped to keep 2012 CO₂-emissions on 2007 levels despite a marked increase in population and industrial activity. Many of the policies are exemplary, particularly those for the buildings sector. The Hamburger Energiepass and the IFB's subsidy programmes are good practices for providing incentives for a refurbishment of the existing building stock while at the same time guaranteeing a high standard. The elements of the subsidy programme, which help to preserve the cityscape (e.g. by subsidising the preservation of clinker facades) are also recommendable for other German and European cities. Other measures in the climate action plan have been proven to be good practice as well. The programme „Unternehmen für Ressourcenschutz“ has been a great success in helping small and medium enterprises to increase their energy efficiency. Hamburg has also wisely used funding available from the federal government. Many public buildings have been refurbished with federal money and the street lightning is one of the most energy efficient and modern in Germany thanks to subsidies from the national level. This wise and extensive use of national funding is an approach which can and should be copied by other municipalities in Germany. The strategy to increase bike use is another element of the climate action plan which may act as a model to other municipalities in Germany and Europe. Nevertheless, one should not fail to mention the most important barrier when it comes to other municipalities copying the successful elements of Hamburg's climate action plan. The most successful programmes (IFB's subsidies for refurbishments and „Unternehmen für Ressourcenschutz“) are quite expensive. As a state Hamburg has access to sources of funding most

³⁰ The goal of two million tons of avoided CO₂-emissions mentioned before refers to the sum of the impacts of local and national policies, technological progress and autonomous energy efficiency improvements by the industry.

municipalities have not. Therefore many municipalities in Germany do not have the (financial) means to implement comparable programmes.

When it comes to the energy and climate policy of Hamburg itself, the city has already learned from the biggest weakness in the climate action plan 2007-2012. The big number of measures, which were very different in scope, cost and impact, made the 2007 climate action plan quite convoluted. With the completion of the climate action plan in 2012, Hamburg has passed a masterplan for climate protection, which is covering the period until 2020. In this masterplan, the city of Hamburg has drastically reduced the number of measures. Right now, the city is concentrating on the most successful policies and strategies, many of which have been continued from the climate action plan. This streamlining of Hamburg's energy and climate policy would have been advisable if it had not been implemented yet.

2.1.5 FURTHER INFORMATION

The city of Hamburg's homepage contains many information on Hamburg's climate action plan and the masterplan – some of it even in English. The masterplan is available in English (<https://www.hamburg.de/contentblob/4316146/data/master-plan-for-climate-protection.pdf>), while the final report on the climate action plan is only available in German (<https://www.hamburg.de/contentblob/4052736/data/klimaschutzkonzept-abschlussbericht.pdf>). The homepage of the city administration's department responsible for climate protection is: <http://www.hamburg.de/klima/>.

Further questions may be directed to Mrs. Ursel Lünsmann-Pielke³¹ (ursel.luensmann-pielke@bsu.hamburg.de).

³¹ Since the Wuppertal Institute was involved in the evaluation of Hamburg's climate action plan, an interview was not necessary to gather the information compiled here.

REFERENCES

[NEEAP] National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (2011).

[NEEAP] National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (2014)

ADB – Asian Development Bank (2009): Changing Course. A new Paradigm for Sustainable Urban Transport. ADB, Manila.

Allianz pro Schiene (Hrsg.) (2014): Stadt, Land, Schiene – 15 Beispiele erfolgreicher Bahnen im Nahverkehr. Allianz pro Schiene e.V., Berlin. Available online: <http://www.allianz-pro-schiene.de/publikationen/stadt-land-schiene/stadt-land-schiene-4-auflage-2014.pdf> (retrieved 14.08.2015).

Antinucci, Marcello (2008): Inspections of Boilers and Air Conditioners. http://www.epbd-ca.org/Medias/Pdf/CA_Annex_2_Inspections.pdf

Arbeitsgemeinschaft Altersunabhängiges Lernen (2015a): Umschulung zum Energieberater/zur Energieberaterin. <http://ratgeber-umschulung.de/dienstleistung/energieberater/>

Arbeitsgemeinschaft Altersunabhängiges Lernen (2015b): Umschulung durch das Arbeitsamt/Arbeitsagentur. <http://ratgeber-umschulung.de/kostentraeger/arbeitsagentur/>

Arbeitsgemeinschaft für Sparsamen und Umweltfreundlichen Energieverbrauch (ASUE) (2009): Die EnergieEinsparverordnung EnEV 2009. http://asue.de/cms/upload/inhalte/aktuelles_presse/broschuere/asue-enev2009.pdf

BMVI (2015d): HGV tolling scheme – Federal Trunk Road Toll Act. Retrieved from <http://www.bmvi.de/SharedDocs/EN/Artikel/G/hgv-tolling-scheme-federal-trunk-road-toll-act-19-july-2011.html> (retrieved 14.08.2015).

BMWi (2011): 2nd. National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP) of the Federal Republic of Germany. Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Technologie, Berlin.

Broaddus & Gertz.(2008). Tolling Heavy Goods Vehicles – Overview of European Practice and Lessons from German Experience. Retrieved from <http://andreabroaddus.com/wp-content/uploads/2013/11/Broaddus-Gertz-Germany-HGV-Toll-TRR-2008.pdf> (retrieved 14.08.2015).

Bundesagentur für Arbeit (2013): was? wie viel? wer? Finanzielle Hilfen auf einen Blick. <http://www.arbeitsagentur.de/web/wcm/idc/groups/public/documents/webdatei/mdaw/mdk1/~edisp/l6019022dstbai378431.pdf>

Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle (BAFA) (2014a): Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie Richtlinie über die Förderung der Energieberatung in Wohngebäuden vor Ort – Vor-Ort-Beratung – Vom 29. Oktober 2014. http://www.bafa.de/bafa/de/energie/energiesparberatung/vorschriften/vob_richtlinie_2014.pdf

Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle (BAFA) (2015a): Heizen mit Erneuerbaren Energien. http://www.bafa.de/bafa/de/energie/erneuerbare_energien/index.html

Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle (BAFA) (2015b): Bericht 2014/2015 – Außenwirtschaft, Wirtschaftsförderung, Energie und Klimaschutz. http://www.bafa.de/bafa/de/das_bafa/publikationen/das_bafa_bericht_2014_2015.pdf

Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle (BAFA) (2015c): Energieberatung im Mittelstand. http://www.bafa.de/bafa/de/energie/energieberatung_mittelstand/

Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle (BAFA) (2015d): Förderung von Energiemanagementsystemen.

<http://www.bafa.de/bafa/de/energie/energiemanagementsysteme/index.html>

Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle (BAFA) (2015e): Energiemanagementsysteme – Merkblatt als Hilfestellung für Anträge nach der Richtlinie für die Förderung von Energiemanagementsystemen (ab 1. Mai 2015).

http://www.bafa.de/bafa/de/energie/energiemanagementsysteme/publikationen/merkblatt_energiemanagementsysteme.pdf

Bundesamt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle (BAFA) (2015f): Förderung von Querschnittstechnologien. <http://www.bafa.de/bafa/de/energie/querschnittstechnologien/>

Bundesanstalt für Wirtschaft und Ausfuhrkontrolle (BAFA) (2014): Kriterienkatalog für die Weiterbildung für die Eintragung in die Energieeffizienz-Expertenliste für Förderprogramme des Bundes. https://www.energie-effizienz-experten.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Qualifizierte_Expertenliste_Landingpage/Leistungskatalog_WB.pdf

Bundesinstitut für Bau-, Stadt- und Raumforschung (BBSR) & Fraunhofer Institute (2015): Effizienzhaus Plus. <http://www.forschungsinitiative.de/effizienzhaus-plus/>

Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz und Reaktorsicherheit (BMUB) (ND): Wege zum Effizienzhaus Plus.

http://www.bmub.bund.de/fileadmin/Daten_BMU/Pool/Broschueren/effizienzhaus_plus_broschue_re_bf.pdf

Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz und Reaktorsicherheit (BMUB) (2014): Zukunft Bauen – Forschungsinitiative Zukunft Bau 2014.

http://www.forschungsinitiative.de/fileadmin/user_upload/publikationen/Downloads/zb_2014_magazin_web.pdf

Bundesministerium für Umwelt, Naturschutz und Reaktorsicherheit (BMUB) (2015): Zukunft Bauen – Forschungsinitiative Zukunft Bau 2014. <http://www.forschungsinitiative.de/forschung/>

Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie (BMWi) (2011): Forschung für eine umweltschonende, zuverlässige und bezahlbare Energieversorgung. Das 6. Energieforschungsprogramm der Bundesregierung. <http://www.bmwi.de/BMWi/Redaktion/PDF/E/6-energieforschungsprogramm-der-bundesregierung,property=pdf,bereich=bmwi2012,sprache=de,rwb=true.pdf>

Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie (BMWi) (2014): Nationaler Aktionsplan Energieeffizienz. <http://www.bmwi.de/BMWi/Redaktion/PDF/M-O/nationaler-aktionsplan-energieeffizienz-nape,property=pdf,bereich=bmwi2012,sprache=de,rwb=true.pdf>

Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie (BMWi) (2015): Klimaschonende Produktionsprozesse. <http://www.bmwi.de/DE/Themen/Industrie/Industrie-und-Umwelt/klimaschonende-produktionsprozesse.html>

Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie (BMWi) (2015a): Förderung von Energiemanagementsystemen. <http://www.bmwi.de/BMWi/Redaktion/PDF/Publikationen/foerderung-von-energiemanagementsystemen,property=pdf,bereich=bmwi2012,sprache=de,rwb=true.pdf>

Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie (BMWi) (2015b): Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie Richtlinie für die Förderung von Energiemanagementsystemen Vom 18. März 2015.

<http://www.bmwi.de/BMWi/Redaktion/PDF/P-R/richtlinie-energiemanagementsysteme.pdf>

Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie (BMWi) (2015d): Energy Consulting and Funding. <http://bmwi.de/EN/Topics/Energy/Energy-Efficiency/energy-consulting-and-funding,did=687122.html>

Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie (BMWi) (2015c): 6. Energieforschungsprogramm der Bundesregierung. <http://www.bmwi.de/DE/Themen/Energie/Energieforschung-und-Innovationen/6-energieforschungsprogramm>

Caritas (ND): Stromspar-Check. <http://www.caritas-bochum.de/87113.html>

Clean Energy Ministerial (2014): GSEP Helps Mexico Identify Significant Energy and Emissions Savings from Cool Roofs. <http://www.cleanenergyministerial.org/news/gsep-helps-mexico-identify-significant-energy-and-emissions-savings-from-cool-roofs--1527>

co2online (2015): BAFA – Förderung und Zuschuss. <http://www.co2online.de/foerdermittel/bafa-foerderung/>

Deutsche Energie-Agentur (dena) (2010): Das dena-Gütesiegel Effizienzhaus. Energieeffiziente Wohnhäuser auf den ersten Blick erkennen.

Dalkmann, H. and Brannigan, C. (2007): Sourcebook Module 5e: Transport and Climate Change. GTZ, Eschborn.

de Haan, P., Mueller, M.G., Peters, A. (2007): Anreizsysteme beim Neuwagenkauf: Wirkungsarten, Wirksamkeit und Wirkungseffizienz. Bericht zum Schweizer Autokaufverhalten Nr. 14, ETH Zürich.

Deutsche Bahn (2015): Climate protection at Deutsche Bahn. Available online: http://www.deutschebahn.com/en/sustainability/environmental_pioneer/db_and_climate_protection.html (retrieved 14.08.2015).

Deutsche Energie-Agentur (dena) (n.d.): Zukunft Haus. Energie sparen. Wert gewinnen. - Effizienzhäuser. <https://effizienzhaus.zukunft-haus.info/effizienzhaeuser/> (2015-08-15)

Deutsche Energie-Agentur (dena) (2005): dena-Modellvorhaben "Niedrigenergiehaus im Bestand". <http://www.dena.de/presse-medien/pressearchiv/dena-modellvorhaben-niedrigenergiehaus-im-bestand.html>

Deutsche Energie-Agentur (dena) (2008): Modellvorhaben „Niedrigenergiehaus im Bestand“: Verlängerung der Antragsfrist für Ein- und Zweifamilienhäuser bis zum 30. September 2008!. <http://www.zukunft-haus.info/newsletter/archiv/newsletter-0308/modellvorhaben-niedrigenergiehaus-im-bestand-verlaengerung-der-antragsfrist-fuer-ein-und-zweifamilienhaeuser-bis-zum-30-september-2008.html>

Deutsche Energie-Agentur (dena) (2009): Modellvorhaben „Niedrigenergiehaus im Bestand für Schulen und andere Nicht- wohngebäude“. <http://energieagentur-oberfranken.de/energie/images/stories/dena%20-%20teilnahmebedingungen%20nichtwohngebaeude%202.pp.pdf>

Deutsche Energie-Agentur (dena) (2013): Das dena-Gütesiegel Effizienzhaus. Regelheft mit Stand vom 02.07.2013

Deutsche Energie-Agentur (dena) (2014): Energieeffiziente Gebäude. Kompetenzzentrum Contracting für Gebäude. http://www.dena.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Publikationen/Gebaeude/Dokumente/FS_Kompetenzzentrum_Contracting_Gebaeude_2014-08.pdf

Deutsche Energie-Agentur (dena) (2014b): Regelheft für die Eintragung als Energieeffizienz-Experte für Förderprogramme des Bundes. <https://www.energie-effizienz->

experten.de/fileadmin/user_upload/Qualifizierte_Expertenliste_Landingpage/2014_06_01_Regelheft_Expertenliste.pdf

Deutsche Energie-Agentur (dena) (2015): dena Efficient House Quality Mark.

<http://www.dena.de/en/projects/building/dena-efficient-house-quality-mark.html>

Deutsche Energie-Agentur (dena) (2015a): Energieeinsparverordnung 2014. [http://www.zukunft-](http://www.zukunft-haus.info/gesetze-studien-verordnungen/enev-enev-historie/enev-2014.html)

[haus.info/gesetze-studien-verordnungen/enev-enev-historie/enev-2014.html](http://www.zukunft-haus.info/gesetze-studien-verordnungen/enev-enev-historie/enev-2014.html)

Deutsche Energie-Agentur (dena) (2015b): Die Energiewende voranbringen.

<http://www.kompetenzzentrum-contracting.de/startseite/>

Deutsche Energie-Agentur (dena) (2015c): Die Energieeffizienz-Experten für Förderprogramme des Bundes.

<https://www.energie-effizienz-experten.de/energieeffizienz-experten-fuer-foerderprogramme-des-bundes/>

Deutsche Energie-Agentur (dena) (2015d): Der Dena-Gebäudereport 2015. Statistiken und Analysen zur Energieeffizienz im Gebäudebestand.

Deutsche Energie-Agentur (dena) (2015e): dena-Gütesiegel Effizienzhaus. Wo Effizienzhaus drauf steht, ist Energieeffizienz drin. <http://www.dena.de/projekte/gebaeude/dena-guetesiegel-effizienzhaus.html>

Deutscher Bundestag (2012): Bericht an den Deutschen Bundestag über die Auswirkungen der Einführung des Luftverkehrssteuergesetzes auf den Luftverkehrssektor und die Entwicklung der Steuereinnahmen aus der Luftverkehrssteuer. Drucksache 17/10225 vom 29.06.2012. Deutscher Bundestag, Berlin. Available online: <http://dip21.bundestag.de/dip21/btd/17/102/1710225.pdf> (retrieved 14.08.2015).

Deutscher Bundestag (2014): Schriftliche Fragen mit den in der Woche vom 13. Oktober 2014 eingegangenen Antworten der Bundesregierung.

<http://dipbt.bundestag.de/doc/btd/18/029/1802930.pdf>

Diefenbach, Nikolaus (2014): Monitoring der KfW-Programme „Energieeffizient Sanieren“ und

„Energieeffizient Bauen“ 2013. [https://www.kfw.de/PDF/Download-](https://www.kfw.de/PDF/Download-Center/Konzernthemen/Research/PDF-Dokumente-alle-Evaluationen/Monitoringbericht_2013_05-12-2014.pdf)

[Center/Konzernthemen/Research/PDF-Dokumente-alle-Evaluationen/Monitoringbericht_2013_05-12-2014.pdf](https://www.kfw.de/PDF/Download-Center/Konzernthemen/Research/PDF-Dokumente-alle-Evaluationen/Monitoringbericht_2013_05-12-2014.pdf)

DIW (2010): Die Ökosteuern haben zu geringerer Umweltbelastung des Verkehrs beigetragen. In: Wochenbericht 13-14/2010, Deutsches Institut für Wirtschaftsforschung (DIW), Berlin. Available online: http://www.diw.de/documents/publikationen/73/diw_01.c.354607.de/10-13.pdf (retrieved 10.08.2015).

DIW Berlin (2011): The Effectiveness of Energy Performance Certificates – Evidence from Germany.

Donges, Jürgen B.; Eekhoff, Johann; Franz, Wolfgang; Fuest, Clemens; Möschel, Wernhard; Neumann, Manfred (2008): Gegen die Neubelebung der Entfernungspauschale. In: Argumente zu Marktwirtschaft und Politik. Stiftung Marktwirtschaft, Nr. 102, 2008. Available online:

http://www.stiftung-marktwirtschaft.de/uploads/tx_ttproducts/datasheet/Argument_102_Entfernungspauschale.pdf (retrieved 13.08.2015).

Energy Agency NRW (2015): Kompetenzzentrum Contracting für Gebäude berät Bund, Länder und Kommunen beim Energiesparen.

<http://www.energieagentur.nrw.de/contracting/kompetenzzentrum-contracting-fuer-gebaeude-beraet-bund-laender-und-kommunen-beim-energiesparen-15532.asp>

Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi) (2014): Making more out of energy. National Action Plan on Energy Efficiency. 2014. Online available <http://www.bmwi.de/English/Redaktion/Pdf/nape-national-action-plan-on-energy-efficiency,property=pdf,bereich=bmwi2012,sprache=en,rwb=true.pdf> (retrieved 14.08.2015)

Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (BMWi) (2015a): Marktanzreizprogramm. <http://www.bmwi.de/DE/Themen/Energie/Energiewende-im-Gebaeudebereich/marktanreizprogramm-map.html>

Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (BMUB) (2014): The German Government's Climate Action Programme 2020. Cabinet decision of 3 December 2014. 2014. Online available: http://www.bmub.bund.de/fileadmin/Daten_BMU/Pool/Broschueren/aktionsprogramm_klimaschutz_2020_broschuere_en_bf.pdf (retrieved 14.08.2015)

Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure (BMVI) (2015b): 2015 Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan. Retrieved from <http://www.bmvi.de/SharedDocs/EN/Artikel/G/federal-transport-infrastructure-plan-2015.html> (retrieved 14.08.2015).

Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure (BMVI) (2003): Laying the foundations for the future of mobility in Germany – Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan 2003. Retrieved from http://www.bmvi.de/SharedDocs/EN/Anlagen/federal-transport-infrastructure-plan-2003.pdf?__blob=publicationFile (retrieved 14.08.2015).

Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure (BMVI) (2015c): National Cycling Plan 2020. Retrieved from <http://www.nationaler-radverkehrsplan.de/en/eu-bund-laender/bund/> (retrieved 14.08.2015).

Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure (BMVI) (2015a): Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan. Retrieved from http://www.bmvi.de/EN/TransportAndMobility/TransportPolicy/FederalTransportInfrastructurePlan/federal-transport-infrastructure-plan_node.html (retrieved 14.08.2015).

Federal Ministry of Transport, Building and Urban Development (BMBVS) (2013): Mobility and Fuel Strategy (MFS). New pathways for energy. Online available: http://www.bmvi.de/SharedDocs/EN/Anlagen/UI-MKS/mfs-strategy-final-en.pdf?__blob=publicationFile (retrieved 14.08.2015)

Fraunhofer ISI (ND): 30 Pilotnetzwerke. <http://www.energie-effizienz-netzwerke.de/een-wAssets/docs/Abschlussbroschuere-30-Pilot-Netzwerke.pdf>

German Federal Government (2012): Communication from the German Federal Government to the European Commission pursuant to Article 7 of Directive 2012/27/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on energy efficiency

German Federal Government (2012): Mitteilung der Bundesregierung der Bundesrepublik Deutschland an die Europäische Kommission gemäß Artikel 7 der Richtlinie des Europäischen Parlaments und des Rates vom 25. Oktober 2012 zur Energieeffizienz (2012/27/EU). https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/article7_de_germany.pdf

Händel, Claus (2008): Energetische Inspektionen von Klimaanlage. http://www.ikz.de/uploads/media/IKZH_200809_1530_Klimatechnik.pdf

IEA (2015): Policies and Measures - Municipal Transport Financing Act (GVFG) and Regionalisation Act (RegG). Available online: <http://www.iea.org/policiesandmeasures/pams/germany/name-31423-en.php> (retrieved 13.08.2015).

IFEU, Institut für Energie- und Umweltforschung (2008): Evaluation des Förderprogramms "Energieeinsparungen vor Ort" – Schlussbericht Kurzfassung. URL: http://www.bafa.de/bafa/de/energie/energiesparberatung/publikationen/sonstiges/energie_vob_ifeu_evaluation_schlussbericht_kurzfassung_06.pdf (2015-08-15)

International Panel on Energy Efficiency Cooperation (2015): About IPEEC. <http://www.ipeec.org/aboutipeec.html>

Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau (KfW) (2015a): Energieeffizient Bauen – Für Bau oder Ersterwerb eines neuen KfW-Effizienzhauses. [https://www.kfw.de/inlandsfoerderung/Privatpersonen/Neubau/Finanzierungsangebote/Energieeffizient-Bauen-\(153\)/#1](https://www.kfw.de/inlandsfoerderung/Privatpersonen/Neubau/Finanzierungsangebote/Energieeffizient-Bauen-(153)/#1)

Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau (KfW) (2015b): Energieeffizient Bauen. [https://www.kfw.de/Download-Center/Foerderprogramme-\(Inlandsfoerderung\)/Arbeitshilfen-Präsentationen/Präsentationen/Energieeffizient-Bauen-3_2013.pdf](https://www.kfw.de/Download-Center/Foerderprogramme-(Inlandsfoerderung)/Arbeitshilfen-Präsentationen/Präsentationen/Energieeffizient-Bauen-3_2013.pdf)

Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau (KfW) (2015c): Energieeffizient Sanieren – Kredit. [https://www.kfw.de/inlandsfoerderung/Privatpersonen/Bestandsimmobilien/Finanzierungsangebote/Energieeffizient-Sanieren-Kredit-\(151-152\)/#1](https://www.kfw.de/inlandsfoerderung/Privatpersonen/Bestandsimmobilien/Finanzierungsangebote/Energieeffizient-Sanieren-Kredit-(151-152)/#1)

Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau (KfW) (2015d): Energieeffizient Sanieren – Investitionszuschuss. [https://www.kfw.de/inlandsfoerderung/Privatpersonen/Bestandsimmobilien/Finanzierungsangebote/Energieeffizient-Sanieren-Zuschuss-\(430\)/#1](https://www.kfw.de/inlandsfoerderung/Privatpersonen/Bestandsimmobilien/Finanzierungsangebote/Energieeffizient-Sanieren-Zuschuss-(430)/#1)

Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau (KfW) (2015e): Energieeffizientes Sanieren – Baubegleitung. <https://www.kfw.de/KfW-Konzern/Service/Download-Center/F%C3%B6rderprogramme-%28Inlandsf.%29-%28D-EN%29/Barrierefreie-Dokumente/Energieeffizient-Sanieren-Baubegleitung-%28431%29-Merkblatt-06-2014/#>

Landtag Nordrhein-Westfalen (2015): Kleine Anfrage 3199 - des Abgeordneten Henning Höne FDP - Wie ernst nimmt die Landesregierung den Beitrag der Heizkostenverordnung zum Klimaschutz? <http://www.landtag.nrw.de/portal/WWW/dokumentenarchiv/Dokument/MMD16-8068.pdf>

Löschel, Andreas et al. (2014): Stellungnahme zum ersten Fortschrittsbericht der Bundesregierung für das Berichtsjahr 2013. <http://www.bmwi.de/BMWi/Redaktion/PDF/M-O/monitoringbericht-energie-der-zukunft-stellungnahme-2013,property=pdf,bereich=bmwi2012,sprache=de,rwb=true.pdf>

Mc Kinsey (2014): Evolution – Electric vehicles in Europe: gearing up for a new phase? (2014) Online: http://www.mckinsey.com/~media/McKinsey_Offices/Netherlands/Latest_thinking/PDFs/Electric-Vehicle-Report-EN_AS_FINAL.ashx (retrieved 14.08.2015)

MURE (2014): Ecological Tax Reform (Energy and Electricity Tax) (Ökologische Steuerreform – Energie und Stromsteuer). http://www.measures-odyssee-mure.eu/public/mure_pdf/household/GER28.PDF

National Platform for Electromobility (NPE) (n.d.): Second Report of the National Platform for Electromobility. Online: http://www.bmub.bund.de/fileadmin/bmu-import/files/english/pdf/application/pdf/bericht_emob_2_en_bf.pdf (retrieved 14.08.2015)

Öko-Institut, IFE-STE, DIW, Fraunhofer ISI, Ziesing (2009): Politikszenerien für den Klimaschutz V – auf dem Weg zum Strukturwandel. Treibhausgas-Emissionsszenarien bis zum Jahr 2030. On behalf of the Environmental Protection Agency (UBA). Climate Change 16/2009. Dessau-Roßlau. Online available: http://www.umweltbundesamt.de/uba-info-medien/mysql_medien.php (retrieved 14.08.2015).

Prognos (2013): Endenergieeinsparziel gem. Art. 7 EED und Abschätzung der durch politische Maßnahmen erreichbaren Energieeinsparungen. <https://www.bmwi.de/BMWi/Redaktion/PDF/Publikationen/Studien/endenergieeinsparziel->

[abschaetzung-der-durch-politische-massnahmen-erreichbaren-energieeinsparungen,property=pdf,bereich=bmwi2012,sprache=de,rwb=true.pdf](#)

Richtlinie über die Förderung von Energieberatungen im Mittelstand vom 28. Oktober 2014

Schettler-Köhler, Horst (2008): Implementation of the EPBD in Germany – Status and Future Planning. [http://www.epbd-](http://www.epbd-ca.org/Medias/Pdf/country_reports_15_08_2011/Germany_BuPLa_Country_reports.pdf)

[ca.org/Medias/Pdf/country_reports_15_08_2011/Germany_BuPLa_Country_reports.pdf](http://www.epbd-ca.org/Medias/Pdf/country_reports_15_08_2011/Germany_BuPLa_Country_reports.pdf)

Schipper, L.; Marie-Liliu (1999): Transportation and CO₂-Emissions: Flexing the link. A Strategy for the World Bank. Washington

Schröder, Mark et al. (2011): The KfW Experience in the Reduction of Energy Use and CO₂ Emissions in from Buildings – Operations, Impacts and Lessons for the UK.

<http://sticerd.lse.ac.uk/dps/case/cp/KfWFullReport.pdf>

Statista (2015): Heizungsmarkt in Deutschland – Statista Dossier.

<http://de.statista.com/statistik/studie/id/25528/dokument/heizungsmarkt-in-deutschland-statista-dossier/>

Statistisches Bundesamt (2015): 983 Millionen Euro Luftverkehrsteuer im Jahr 2014 angemeldet. Statistisches Bundesamt, Wiesbaden. Available online: https://www.destatis.de/DE/PresseService/Presse/Pressemitteilungen/zdw/2015/PD15_016_p002pdf.pdf?__blob=publicationFile (retrieved 14.08.2015).

Stromsparcheck.de (2013): 100.000mal Energie gespart! Press release <http://www.stromsparcheck.de/presse/pressemitteilungen/datum/2013/09/05/100000mal-energie-gespart.html>

Stuible, Achim et al. (2014): Evaluierung von Einzelmaßnahmen zur Nutzung erneuerbarer Energien im Wärmemarkt (Marktanreizprogramm) für den Zeitraum 2012 bis 2014. https://www.erneuerbare-energien.de/EE/Redaktion/DE/Downloads/Berichte/evaluierung-marktanreizprogramm.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=4

Timilsina G.R. and Dulal H.B. (2009): Regulatory instruments to control environmental externalities from the transport sector. In: European Transport/Trasporti Europei n. 41 (2009): 80-112.

UBA (2008): Politikszenerarien für den Klimaschutz IV - Szenarien bis 2030, UBA-Texte 01/08, Umweltbundesamt (UBA), Dessau.

UBA (2010): Umweltschädliche Subventionen in Deutschland 2010 - Aktualisierte Ausgabe 2010. Umweltbundesamt (UBA), Dessau. Available online: <http://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/publikation/long/4048.pdf> (retrieved 13.08.2015).

Umweltbundesamt (2012): Energiemanagementsysteme in der Praxis.

<https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/publikation/long/3959.pdf>

Website Effizient Mobil online: www.effizient-mobil.de (retrieved 14.08.2015)

Website Federal Ministry for the Environment, Nature Conservation, Building and Nuclear Safety (BMUB): Gesetzentwurf der Bundesregierung- Entwurf eines Gesetzes zur Bevorrechtigung der Verwendung elektrisch betriebener Fahrzeuge (Elektromobilitätsgesetz EmoG) (n.d.) Online: http://www.bmub.bund.de/fileadmin/Daten_BMU/Download_PDF/Verkehr/emog_gesetzentwurf_bf.pdf (retrieved 14.08.2015)

Website Germany Trade & Invest (n.d.): Government Program Electromobility. Online: <http://www.gtai.de/GTAI/Navigation/EN/Invest/Industries/Smarter-business/Smart-mobility/government-program-electromobility,t=electromobility-showcase-projects,did=324554.html> (retrieved 14.08.2015)

Website National Organisation Hydrogen and Fuel Cell Technology (n.d.): Electromobility model regions. Online: <http://www.now-gmbh.de/en/mobility/mobility-of-tomorrow/electromobility-model-regions.html> (retrieved 14.08.2015)

Website Odysee-MURE: GER2 Heavy goods vehicle toll charges. Online: http://www.measures-odysee-mure.eu/public/mure_pdf/transport/GER2.PDF (retrieved 14.08.2015)

Website Odysee-MURE: GER28 Campaign „ich und mein auto. Clever fahren, Sprit sparen“ („me and my car. Driving smart, Saving gas“). Online: http://www.measures-odysee-mure.eu/public/mure_pdf/transport/GER2.PDF (retrieved 14.08.2015)

Website Odysee-MURE: GER41 Federal-procurement initiative for Electro-mobility. Online: http://www.measures-odysee-mure.eu/public/mure_pdf/transport/GER41.PDF (retrieved 14.08.2015)

Wuppertal Institute (2012): Progress Toward Low-Carbon Transport: Experiences from Germany. Wuppertal Institute (WI), Wuppertal/Berlin.

HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D1.2

STATUS-QUO ANALYSIS OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICIES IN 8 EU COUNTRIES

D 1.2.

**PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT**

Partner: *Energy Policy & Development Centre – National & Kapodistrian University of Athens*

NATIONAL REPORT

HELLAS, AUGUST 2015

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

OXFORD
BROOKES
UNIVERSITY

Universiteit
Antwerpen

Wuppertal Institute
for Climate, Environment
and Energy

SEI

STOCKHOLM
ENVIRONMENT
INSTITUTE

Institution: Energy Policy & Development Centre – National & Kapodistrian University of Athens

Steering Committee member ⁽¹⁾: Prof. Dimitrios MAVRAKIS

Prepared by: Dr. Popi KONIDARI, Eleni-Danai MAVRAKI, Anna FLESSA, Aliko-Nefeli MAVRAKI

⁽¹⁾ ***The Steering Committee member has the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the report.***

HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACRONYMS	5
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL	8
1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE BUILDINGS SECTOR	8
1.1.1 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	8
1.1.2 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS / INFORMATIVE POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	23
1.1.3 ECONOMIC POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	28
1.1.4 CAPACITY BUILDING AND NETWORKING.....	32
1.1.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR THE PROMOTION OF ENERGY SERVICES.....	33
1.1.6 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT AND BEST AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGY (BAT) PROMOTION	34
1.1.7 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR IN HELLAS	35
1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR	37
1.2.1 PLANNING INSTRUMENTS.....	37
1.2.2 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	39
1.2.3 FINANCIAL POLICY INSTRUMENTS	43
1.2.4 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS	48
1.2.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT	50
1.2.6 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR IN HELLAS.....	51
2. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE REGIONAL / LOCAL LEVEL	53
2.1 PRESENTATION OF THE CASE STUDY FOR THE MUNICIPALITY OF ILIOUPOLIS	53
ANNEX I	61
ANNEX II	62
REFERENCES	63

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Location of the municipality of Ilioupolis (source: Google maps).	54
--	-----------

Table of Tables

Table 1: Penalties for provider/seller not in compliance with energy labelling requirements.	9
Table 2: Proposed categories of energy audits in buildings.	11
Table 3: Fees for energy auditors.	18
Table 4: Information about energy audits for boilers and cooling installations.	19
Table 5: Definition of energy classes.	24
Table 6: Special taxation on energy consumption.	29
Table 7: Revenues due to the implementation of the special taxation for consumption.	29
Table 8: Grant amounts per category.	32
Table 9: History and levels of Euro standards for passenger cars.	41

Table 10: New registrations of passenger electrically charged vehicles in Hellas for time period 2013-2014.	45
Table 11: Revenues from the circulation taxes for cars.	46
Table 12: EE and RES measures for the Municipality of Ilioupoli.....	55
Table 13: SEAP actions for the building sector of the Ilioupolis municipality.	56
Table 14: SEAP actions for the transport sector of the Ilioupolis municipality.	58

ACRONYMS

ACEA	European Automobile Manufacturers Association
BAT	Best Available Technology
BEV	Battery Electric Vehicles
BEMS	Building Energy Management System
BPIE	Buildings Performance Institute Europe
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CRES	Center for Renewable Energy Sources and Saving
EC	European Commission
EE	Energy Efficiency
EES	Energy Efficiency Service
ELOT	Hellenic Organization for Standardization
ELSTAT	Hellenic Statistical Authority
EMAS	Eco-Management and Audit Scheme
EMS	Energy Management Systems
EPB	Energy Performance of Buildings
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
E-REV	Extended Range Electric Vehicles
ESCO	Energy Services Company
EU	European Union
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GPP	Green Public Procurement
HEDNO	Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator
IEA	International Energy Agency
IISD	International Institute for Sustainable Development
IREA	Research Institute of Applied Economics
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
KENAK	Greek abbreviation for Regulation for the Energy Efficiency of Buildings
LA	Local Authorities
LED	Light-Emitting Diode
LPG	Liquefied Petroleum Gas
MEECC	Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change
MREPB	Minimum Requirements of Energy Performance for Buildings
MEIST	Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism
NEEAP	National Energy Efficiency Action Plan
NKUA	National and Kapodistrian University of Athens
NZEB	Nearly Zero Energy Building
NSRF	National Strategic Reference Framework

OBD	On-Board Diagnostic
OPE	Operational Programme for Energy
PHEV	Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles
PPCs	Public Passenger Cars
PPP	Public – Private – Partnership
R&D	Research and Development
RAE	Regulatory Energy Authority
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
RRC	Rolling Resistance Coefficient
RUE	Rational Use of Energy
SEAP	Sustainable Energy Action Plan
TCG	Technical Chamber of Greece
TRIP	Transport Research and Innovation Portal
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
VAT	Value Added Tax
YPEKA	(Greek interpretation) Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The majority of the Hellenic policy instruments for the promotion of Energy Efficiency (EE) concerns the transposition of EU Directives. There are more regulatory policy instruments compared to those in other categories. The policy instruments for the building sector are more and described in details compared to those of the transport sector. The outcomes of these national policy instruments in terms of energy savings are rarely available.

Particularly, concerning the buildings sector, the majority of the policy instruments are targeting to the final energy consumers. These policy instruments include:

- Regulatory policy instruments (Energy labeling, energy audits, Regulation for Energy Performance of Buildings – Minimum requirements of energy performance for buildings, metering, energy auditors, eco-design requirements, energy management systems);
- Dissemination and awareness instruments/informative policy instruments (energy performance certificate; Green Public Procurements, Voluntary agreements);
- Economic policy instruments (taxation on energy products and electricity, Green Fund-subsidies, financial incentives (subsidies, financial exemptions), financial incentives for replacement of devices/systems);
- Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services (ESCO market promotion).

The same situation is observed for the transport sector. Its policy instruments include:

- Planning policy instruments (Cycling and pedestrianism in the city, improvement of infrastructure for electric vehicles);
- Regulatory policy instruments (Emission standards (Euro 5 and Euro 6), Establishment of Permanent Committee on Green Transport; Energy labeling for transport);
- Financial policy instruments (taxation on energy products and electricity, Registration and circulation tax exemption for electric and hybrid vehicles, incentives to replace old technology cars and motorcycles (subsidies, tax exemptions));
- Dissemination and awareness instruments (Consumer information fuel economy and CO₂ emissions of new passenger cars, eco-driving; Green Public Procurements for the transport sector).

There are no policy instruments for any of the two sectors under the categories: Network and capacity building instruments, policy instruments for R&D and BAT promotion.

Finally, a case study about the Municipality of Ilioupolis was included for presenting the application of multi-level policy processes.

1. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE BUILDINGS SECTOR

1.1.1 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS

The implemented policy instruments of this category include: Energy labeling, energy audits, Regulation for Energy Performance of Buildings – Minimum requirements of energy performance for buildings, metering, energy auditors, eco-design requirements, energy management systems

1.1.1.1 Energy labelling

General Information: Energy labelling was introduced at national level with the issuance of Presidential Decree 180/1994¹, which set out the general legislative framework for implementing of energy labelling on household appliances. Then a series of joint ministerial decisions were issued on the implementation of energy labelling in several categories of household appliances² transposing the relevant EU Directives (Directives 1998/11/EC, 1999/9/EC, 2002/31/EC, 2002/40/EC, 2003/66/EC, 2010/30/EC – Commission Regulation No. 626/2011 (supplementing Directive)). More specifically this policy instrument concerns household lamps and dishwashers, air-conditioners, electric ovens, electric refrigerators, freezers and their combinations, labelling and standard product information of the consumption of energy and other resources by energy-related products.

The most recent Ministerial Decision that is in force is 12400/1108/29 of year 2011 (Government Gazette 2301 B, 14.10.2011³). This Decision incorporates into national legislation Directive 2010/30/EC⁴ “on the indication by labelling and standard product information of the consumption of energy and other resources by energy-related products”.

Objectives: Its objectives are to: i) enable customers (end-users) to proceed with informed decisions about the energy performance of a product and ii) increase the interest of manufacturers and intermediary actors in raising the sustainability performance of their products (Benigna Boza – Kiss et al., 2013; CRES, 2013). It also contributes to the reduction of the amount of money that consumers pay for electricity (CRES, 2013).

For the Hellenic case, the Ministerial Decision 12400/1108/29 (Government Gazette 2301 B, 14.10.2011) defines as objective to enact a framework for: i) providing information to the end-users through the labeling and ii) quoting uniform information regarding the product (energy consumption

¹ The year is 1994

² http://www.cres.gr/energy_saving/Ktiria/electrikes_syskeves_simansi.htm

³

http://www.google.gr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&frm=1&source=web&cd=2&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0CCkQFjABahUKEwjxv_GOz5HHAhUJORQKHdKrAX8&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.ydmed.gov.gr%2Fwp-content%2Fuploads%2F2011_09_10_diminiaio.doc&ei=4tXBVfHGEonyUNLXhvgH&usg=AFQjCNFSqq8d5JaYRHWaeMdvBaHCMGeA8Q&bvm=bv.99261572,d.d24 and http://www.et.gr/idocs-nph/search/pdfViewerForm.html?args=5C7QrtC22wFYAFdDx4L2G3dtvSoClrL8zS83ZvoDVVQtiDow6HITE-JInJ48_97uHrMts-zFzeyCiBSQOpYnTy36MacmUFCx2ppFvBej56Mmc8Qdb8ZfRjQznsIAdk8Lv_e6czmhEmbNmZCMxLMtZqO3PZEMz4PAm4MxQaM4YkkPuOjFktnSxOGKTOsdy

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/list_of_enege_labelling_measures.pdf - https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/list_of_enege_labelling_measures.pdf

and occasionally other basic resources during usage) and supplementary information about products related with energy. The aim is the end-users to be able to select more efficient products.

Type of policy instrument: According to UNEP it is a Regulatory – informative policy instrument (Benigna Boza – Kiss et al., 2013). It is mandatory from the point of the manufacturers, but informative and voluntary from the point of the end-users.

Target groups: End-users in households and producers of the respective products. The energy labeling is applied to those products that have a significant direct or indirect effect on energy consumption and depending on the case of other resources during their use. It is not applied to: i) second hand products; ii) to transportation means of persons or merchandise; iii) on the indicative signal or the equivalent label for security reasons that is attached on the product.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: The energy label has seven (7) scales ranging from “A” to “G” (old) or from “A+++” until “D” (new) depending on the type of the device (CRES, 2013). “A” or “A+++” means that the device is the most energy efficient one, while “G” or “D” the less energy efficient one (CRES, 2013). The three additional classes in the new form of the label⁵ (“A+”, “A++” and “A+++”) take into account that new, innovative products, appeared on the market, while the higher rate of the former label is “A” (BIO Intelligence Service, 2013).

Table 1: Penalties for provider/seller not in compliance with energy labelling requirements.

Amount of penalty (in EUR)	Reason for non-compliance of the provider/seller
500 – 2.000	During the first level check/audit - products were found with no label
500 – 1.000	During the first level check/audit - products were with label, brochures, technical material that was not in Hellenic language
3.000 – 30.000	During the second level check/audit - products were found without label and without the foreseen technical envelop
3.000 – 40.000	During the second level check/audit - products were found with label, but and without the foreseen technical envelop
3.000 – 30.000	During the second level check/audit - products were found with label, that was inconsistent with the information of the technical envelop
3.000 – 30.000	During the second level check/audit - products were found with label or technical envelop, but with false or inaccurate information.

(Source: Ministerial Decision 12400/1108/29 of year 2011).

The Ministerial Decision has provisions about: i) the non-compliance of manufacturers, providers and owners of shops that provide and sell the products respectively; ii) the reporting every four years from the pertinent authority to the European Commission regarding implementation and compliance towards this policy instrument; iii) information quoted on the label (energy consumption (whether electricity or other form of energy, noise) and the material that accompanies the product (technical advertising material, manufacturers brochures) wherever it is sold (store, internet, telemarket etc); iv) obligations of the providers/sellers of the product (provision of label, bulletin, complete technical envelop, informative material etc; accuracy of information); v) first⁶, second⁷ and third⁸ level inspections/audits.

⁵ In 2013, the same label was used in all twenty seven (27) Member States and provided information on the noise level of the appliances more visibly (BIO Intelligence Service, 2013).

⁶ The inspection is for checking if the product has the required labels and any other necessary document (Ministerial Decision 12400/1108/29 of year 2011)

Non - compliance

If the pertinent authority decides on a non-compliance case then: i) it imposes to the natural or legal person a penalty that may be up to 50.000 EUR (see Table 1).

In case that the offender is found in relapse then he/she is punished with double amount of penalty. The penalties are imposed with a justified decision of the relevant Directorate. The offender has to pay within 30 days from the day receiving the justified decision. The pertinent authority can also decide to withdraw the product from the market. In case that the offender withdraws the product without informing the authority, then there is a penalty up to 10.000EUR.

Implementation network: The pertinent authority for the implementation of the provisions of the Ministerial Decision of year 2011 was the 4th Directorate of Sectoral Industrial Policy of the General Secretariat of the former Ministry of Economy, Competitiveness and Shipping. Today, due to changes in the structure of the government, the General Secretariat of Industry at the Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy (former Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change (MEECC⁹)) is responsible for implementing it. The Public Economic Services, the Service of Special Audits of the Ministry of Finance, Hellenic Police, Chambers and Regions will also contribute for the market monitoring if the pertinent authority decides their involvement.

Outcomes: The range of the applied penalties in case of manufacturers' or retailers' non-compliance (in 2008) was 2.000 to 15.000EUR (BIO Intelligence Service, 2013).

In 2009 the general compliance level of the Hellenic manufacturers towards the Energy Labelling Directive was assessed as high (Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research, 2009). There were reported only one or two complaints annually regarding the existence or about the content of the labels or fiches for household appliances (Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research, 2009). There were no details about the origin of the manufacturers for whom the complaints were. The overall compliance of the country (for all appliances) based on a survey of 52 samples was 34% - correctly labeled; 29% - mislabeled and 37% - not labeled (Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research, 2009).

In 2012, Greece reported that due to the easier display of the new energy label (new label was coming into one piece) the level of compliance increased (BIO Intelligence Service, 2013). It was also reported that there was a decline in the degree of tolerance in testing results as a result of the transposition of the 2010 Energy Labelling Directive (BIO Intelligence Service, 2013).

1.1.1.2 Energy audits

General information: Energy audits¹⁰ were introduced under Law 3661/2008¹¹ (Government Gazette 89 A, 19.05.2008), but more details were provided with Law 3885/2010 (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.06.2010¹²) which transposes EU Directive 2006/32/EC¹³ "on energy end-use efficiency and energy services and repealing Council Directive 93/76/EEC". Provisions particularly about the energy audits for the thermal and cooling systems are included in Law 4122/2013 (Government Gazette 42 A,

⁷ The inspection is for checking the availability, the completeness, the validity of the content for each document referring to the product (Ministerial Decision 12400/1108/29 of year 2011)

⁸ It is for verifying the content of labels and documents of product (same Ministerial Decision with footnote 6)

⁹ http://www.cres.gr/kape/calendar/progr_ypapen_8_6_15.pdf

¹⁰ Information about energy audits can be found at the relevant web-page of the Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy (former MEECC) at: <http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=338>

¹¹ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=yJy1TVyRqoo%3D>

¹² <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=AxgQsUVAUjA%3d&tabid=506>

¹³ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32006L0032>

19.02.2013¹⁴). Directive 2012/27/EC is still under public consultation¹⁵, but the draft law has relevant provisions.

Objectives: It aims to enhance the cost-effective improvement of energy end-use efficiency (Directive 2006/32/EC) by: i) providing indicative targets¹⁶, mechanisms, incentives and institutional, financial and legal frameworks to remove existing market barriers and imperfections impeding the efficient end use of energy; ii) creating the conditions for development and promotion of a market for energy services and for delivery of other EE improvement measures to final consumers.

Type of policy instrument: Regulatory policy instrument.

Target groups: The policy instrument is imposed to (Directive 2006/32/EC)¹⁷: i) providers of energy efficiency improvement measures, energy distributors, distribution system operators and retail energy sales companies; ii) final customers. The fields at which it is applied are: Buildings – thermal and cooling installations.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: Energy audits concern as aforementioned buildings, thermal and cooling installations. The rules for these objects are presented in more details under the policy instrument of energy auditors, since they are the same with this policy instrument. Energy audits are conducted by Energy Service Companies (ESCOs) and energy auditors according to provision of Law 3661/2008. The rules for the followed procedures for energy audits at the building sector are under the provision of Article 3 of Law 3661/2008 and the KENAK that was approved with decision Δ6/Β/οικ5825/9.4.2010 (Government Gazette 407 Β, 9.04.2010¹⁸). Energy audits are conducted also under the framework of voluntary agreements (these are presented in session 1.1.2.3 of this report).

Energy audits may be conducted for those market entities that have high transaction costs and no complicated installations as those of the industrial sector, by using other accepted means (ie questionnaires, electronic programmes - available through internet or by post (Law 3855/2010)).

According to the draft law that will transpose Directive 2012/27/EC there will be three categories of energy audits for buildings (see Table 2).

Table 2: Proposed categories of energy audits in buildings.

<i>Types of buildings</i>	<i>Category</i>		
	<i>A</i>	<i>B</i>	<i>C</i>
Household buildings, office buildings	<2.000 m ²	>2.000m ²	no
Commercial shops	<2.000m ²	>2.000m ²	no
Building of the tertiary sector (schools, hotels, hospitals etc)	no	yes	no
Industrial and commercial systems	No	<1.000kw	>1.000kw
Professional labs			
<i>with installed power</i>	<22kw		no
<i>With thermal</i>	<50kw		no

(Source: Draft Law for Directive 2012/27/EC)

¹⁴ https://www.buildingcert.gr/N4122_2013.pdf

¹⁵ <http://www.opengov.gr/minenv/?p=6683>

¹⁶ There are no indicative targets for energy audits in Greece.

¹⁷ the armed forces, only to the extent that its application does not cause any conflict with the nature and primary aim of their activities and with the exception of material used exclusively for military purposes.

¹⁸ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=u2VM2IzaXlc%3D&tabid=508>

Reports of energy audits

The report contains information about (Law 4122/2013): i) the outcomes of the energy audit; ii) recommendations for cost effective improvement of the inspected heating or cooling installation or its replacement; iii) the registration number of the energy auditor that performed the audit and signs the Energy Performance certificate (EPC) (see session 1.1.1.2 of this report for more details).

Reports are registered electronically by the energy auditors at the Archive of Energy Audits for Buildings (Law 4122/2013). The withdrawal or replacement of a report –as in the case of an EPC - is done with the approval of the Special Service of the Energy Auditors of the MEECC upon the relevant request by the energy auditor. The request contains the reasons for such an act and the modifications of the report. The Special Service of the Energy Auditors of the MEECC may request additional documentation or refuse the withdrawal/replacement due to inadequate justification.

Non-compliance

If the withdrawal/replacement procedure is not executed as foreseen by the provisions of Law 4122/2013 then sanctions are imposed. Also sanctions are foreseen in case that there are requests for withdrawal/replacements for reports that are exceeding the 5% of the total number of the reports that the energy auditor has submitted for thermal or cooling installations.

If a report or audit is found in infringement due to the energy auditor then it is withdrawn and the owner can receive compensation from the Green Fund for replacing it (Law 4122/2013).

Implementation network: The Special Service of the Energy Auditors¹⁹ of the MEECC is the supervising pertinent authority. Its mission is to check and monitor the: i) fulfillment of the national targets of energy savings and improving energy efficiency; ii) implementation of the measures that lead to reduction of energy consumption in buildings. It is also the control mechanism for the correct implementation of the policy instruments that are presented in Law 3661/2008. More specifically, it is responsible for energy audits, energy auditors, issuance of EPCs, the registry for energy auditors and energy audits in buildings. It also ensures the effectiveness of the energy audits.

Outcomes: There are no available results regarding the implementation of the energy audits on the relevant web-site of the Ministry²⁰. On the specific web-site for energy audits²¹, the public cannot enter without being a registered user so as to get more information on outcomes.

1.1.1.3 Energy performance of Buildings through Regulation for Energy performance of Buildings and Minimum requirements

General information: These policy instruments were set into force initially with Law 3661/2008²² (Government Gazette 89 A, 19.05.2008). Amendments followed with Law 3855/2010 (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.06.2010²³) and Law 4122/2013 (Government Gazette 42 A, 19.02.2013²⁴). The last Law transposes into national legislation the Directive 2010/31/EC²⁵ of the European Parliament and Commission of the 19th May 2010 about “*Energy Performance of Buildings*”.

¹⁹ <http://www.ypeka.gr/?tabid=339>

²⁰ <http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=400&language=el-GR>

²¹ <https://www.buildingcert.gr/info.html>

²² <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=yJy1TVyRqoo%3D>

²³ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=AxgQsUVAUjA%3d&tabid=506>

²⁴ https://www.buildingcert.gr/N4122_2013.pdf

²⁵ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:153:0013:0035:EN:PDF>

Objectives: There are provisions under Law 3661/2008 that refer to the Regulation for the Energy Performance of Buildings (in Greek language the abbreviation is KENAK). Under the Joint Ministerial Decision No.Δ6/Β/οικ.5825 (Government Gazette 407 Β, 9.04.2010²⁶) KENAK was approved. The objectives are: reduction of energy consumption for heating, cooling, lighting, production and use of hot water with the simultaneous ensuring of comfort conditions for the indoor spaces of the buildings.

The national Law 4122/2013 is in agreement with the aforementioned transposing Directive. The objective is to promote the improvement of the energy performance of buildings in Greece, considering: i) outdoor climatic and local conditions and ii) indoor climate requirements and cost-effectiveness.

Type of policy instrument: Regulatory policy instrument²⁷ – Technological standards. It sets the KENAK. Simultaneously it defines the minimum requirements of energy performance for buildings, which fall under the type of performance standards, one of the categories of regulatory policy instruments. The two policy instruments are linked since the minimum requirements of Energy Performance of Buildings (EPB) are defined with the use of the KENAK.

Target groups: The following categories of buildings were foreseen under Laws 3661/2008 and 4122/2013: Households of different types such as detached houses, apartments and apartment complexes; Multi-apartment buildings; Offices; Educational buildings; Hospitals; Hotels and restaurants; Sports facilities; Buildings for Wholesale and retail trade services; Any other category of buildings that are consuming energy.

There are exemptions such as:

- monuments, buildings used as worship places, industrial installations, manufactories, workshops;
- Buildings characterized as protected either as part of specific environment or due to their unique architecture or historical value (ie preserved and located in traditional settlements) are exempted up to the degree that compliance to specific minimum requirements of EPB would alter in an unacceptable manner their character or appearance.
- Buildings of temporary use which based on their planning(the duration of their use will not exceed the period of two years), industrial installations, laboratories, buildings for agricultural use – not residences - with low energy requirements and similar buildings that are used under a relevant national agreement that concerns the EPB (Law 3661/2008, Presidential Decree 100/2010; Law 4122/2013).
- buildings with a total useful floor of less than 50 square meters only the minimum requirements of energy performance about the building elements of the building are set (not for the technical characteristics of the installations).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: There are provisions for KENAK, the methodology for the EPB, the determination of minimum requirements of the energy performance of buildings, buildings with nearly zero energy consumption. More specifically:

KENAK

The Regulation (energy performance building code) contains information and details about:

- The methodology of calculating the Energy Performance of the Buildings (EPB) and the respective Minimum requirements of EPB;

²⁶ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=u2VM2IzaXlc%3D&tabid=508>

²⁷ <http://www.iea.org/aboutus/faqs/energyefficiency/>

- The type and the content of the study for the energy performance of buildings or building blocks and the pertinent persons for conducting it;
- The procedure and the frequency of performing energy audits in buildings, boilers, heating and cooling systems and installations;
- Details about the Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) (type, content, issuing procedure, cost (and its procedure of calculation), monitoring procedure for it and for energy audits, pertinent for these actions bodies);
- Possible forecast for incentives regarding the implementation of additional measures for the improvement of EPB and any other specific issue or necessary detail.

Under KENAK, the values for parameters used in the calculation of the economic feasibility of renovations in existing buildings and technical systems; the technical specifications and the minimum requirements for energy performance for nearly zero energy buildings are determined. Also, the principles of bioclimatic design for buildings need to be considered (Hellenic Republic, MEECC, 2010).

Methodology for calculating the energy performance of the buildings

There are provisions for the “Methodology for calculating the energy performance of the buildings”. The EPB is determined by using the estimated or actual annual consumption of energy needs for its use²⁸ (office, apartment, shop etc). This methodology includes at least (Laws 3661/2008, 4122/2013):

- The thermal characteristics of the building elements (ie heat capacity, insulation, thermal bridges, internal loads);
- The installation of cooling, heating and hot water including their insulation characteristics;
- ventilation and natural ventilation including airtightness;
- the incorporated buildings lighting installation of other uses, except of the residence;
- the design, location and orientation of buildings, including outdoor climatic conditions;
- the passive and hybrid solar systems according to the General Construction Regulation²⁹ and the solar protection;
- the prevailing indoor climatic conditions, including the intended ones.

The following factors with positive influence are also considered during the calculation of the EPB (Law 3661/2008): energetic solar systems according to the General Construction Regulation and other heating systems, cooling and electricity production, that are based on RES; electric energy produced by CHP; heating and cooling systems of regional scale or used by the building block (tele-heating, tele-cooling) and natural lighting.

Determination/Setting n of Minimum requirements of energy performance for buildings

The Minimum Requirements of Energy Performance for Buildings (MREPB) determined by KENAK concern the: i) building elements of the building envelope and ii) technical systems, since both affect significantly the EPB. Optimal levels of cost-effectiveness and factors such as the requirements of indoor conditions for avoiding negative impacts (ie inadequate ventilation), local conditions, foreseen use and the building age are also considered. There is a distinction for the determination of MREPB between: i) new and existing buildings and ii) the different categories of building use.

²⁸ energy needs for heating, cooling, ventilation and lighting in order to achieve indoor conditions of thermal and visual comfort, along with needs for hot water use

²⁹ (new Regulation) Government Gazette 79 A, 9.04.2012, available at:
<http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=5nRUKLGL8E%3D&tabid=506&language=el-GR>

MREPB are reviewed at regular intervals, which are not more than 5 years and if necessary they are updated to reflect the technical progress in the building sector (Laws 4122/2013; 3661/2008).

There are provisions that describe the: i) procedure of how new and existing buildings need to fulfil the MREPB obligations; ii) methodology for calculating the cost effectiveness³⁰ of MREPB.

Buildings with nearly zero energy consumption

From 1.01.2019 all new buildings that host public services must be Nearly Zero Energy Buildings (NZEBs). From 1.01.2021 all new buildings must be NZEBs. There are exemptions for buildings whose analysis of the ratio cost-benefit was negative for the economic lifecycle of the particular building.

The MEECC decided to approve a National Action Plan for NZEBs that will include: i) determination of the technical characteristics of NZEBs considering national, regional and local conditions and the consumption of primary energy in kWh/m²; ii) the intermediary targets for EPB until year 2015; iii) information about policies and measures for NZEB and RES in new and existing buildings.

Financial incentives

For works that aim to the improvement of EPB and the use of RES, there may be funding from the Program of Public Investments after considering the social cost and benefits that EE investments will have. Programs will be also launched for the same purpose.

Non-compliance

There is none for KENAK and MREPB (Law 4122/2013). There are penalties for energy audits, energy auditors and the EPCs. According to Directive 2010/31/EC Member States need to set penalties that are applicable to infringements of the national provisions adopted pursuant to this Directive and to undertake measures necessary to ensure that they are implemented. The penalties provided for must be effective, proportionate and dissuasive.

Implementation network: MEECC, CRES.

Outcomes: There are no available data.

1.1.1.4 Metering

General information: As a part of the EE package this policy instrument was included under law 3855/2010 (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.06.2010). Provisions for the meters and the information on the bills for the electricity consumers are under the Regulation of supply for electric energy (Ministerial Decision Δ5-ΗΛ/Β/Φ1.20/οικ.6262/20.03.2013 – Government Gazette 832 Β, 9.04.2013³¹). Provisions are included in draft Law for Directive 2012/27/EC³².

Objectives: The main objective by promoting the use of metering systems is to: i) provide final customers with information on actual time about their energy use and ii) ensure that the objectives of energy efficiency and benefits for final customers are fully taken into account when establishing the minimum functionalities of the meters and the obligations imposed on market participants (Directive 2012/27/EC).

³⁰ The cost effectiveness calculations include: i) the ratio cost-benefit for the whole estimated economic life cycle (which needs to be positive) and ii) the social costs and benefits (Law 4122/2013).

³¹ <http://www.e-forologia.gr/lawbank/document.aspx?digest=9B9CADC96C3C5000.1D031AEA53&version=2013/04/09>

³² <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32012L0027&from=EN>

Type of policy instrument: Regulatory – informative policy instrument. It is regulatory from the point of the market participants and informative from the point of the end-users. By metering and feedback (e.g. informative billing) the end-users have more detailed, comparable and comprehensible information on their energy use³³.

Target groups: Energy distributors, managers of network distribution of energy and of retail sales energy companies that are obliged to install, operate and maintain meters of electric energy, natural gas, tele-heating, tele-cooling, hot water for household use.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: The target groups are obliged to: i) provide their end-users with individual meters that show their actual energy consumption and provide information in real time use, as long as that is financial feasible and according to the potential energy saving and the available technological options in metering; ii) provide the individual meters in a competitive price within one year after the Law is set in force. For the following cases: i) new connection for new building or after radical renovation of old buildings according to Law 3661/2008; ii) replacement of old meter; iii) any new connection due to the construction of electrical lighting network for public communal spaces or the radical renovation of existing electrical lighting networks of such spaces.

The bills that the end-users will receive need to contain the following information: i) real energy consumption and the corresponding real price; ii) comparative data of the end-user consumption during the time period that the bill concerns and the same period last year.

By 31 December 2016, individual consumption meters will have to be installed in multi-apartment buildings for measuring the consumption of heat or cooling or hot water for each unit where that is technically feasible and cost efficient, while billing information from 1 January 2015 needs to be accurate and based on actual consumption (European Council of Real Estate Professions, 2013).

Non-compliance

There is no such provision. However, Member States were required to lay down rules on effective, proportionate and dissuasive penalties applicable in case of non-compliance with the national provisions adopted pursuant to the transposed Directive (European Commission, 2013a).

Implementation network: The companies that installed the meters check for the smooth functioning. The HEDNO S.A. (Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator S.A.³⁴) is responsible in conducting audits about the installed meters for electric energy. The method of estimation upon consumption is conducted by HEDNO S.A. in accordance with the existing legislation on the liberalized market of electricity (Law 2773/1999, etc.) and particularly with article 16 of the “Manual for the Management of Meter Readings and Periodic Settlement for Providers of the Grid” of RAE issued in Government Gazette 2612/31.12.2009³⁵ and Government Gazette 1463 B, 17.06.2013 (RAE Decision No.182/2013³⁶). The Regulatory Authority for Energy (RAE) is consulted³⁷ if there are violations from the point of the energy distributors.

Outcomes: There are no available data.

³³ <http://mechanisms.energychange.info/backgrounds/11>

³⁴ <http://www.deddie.gr/en/i-etaireia/profil>

³⁵ <http://www.deddie.gr/en/xrisimes-plirofories-sxetika-me-tin-katametrisi/vasei-poiwn-diataksewn-akoloutheitai-i-parapanw-diadikasia>

³⁶ <http://www.aia.gr/userfiles/85ab214c-4e7b-4639-83ca-a1fb2a24fc19/egdiamepepd.pdf>

³⁷ http://www.google.gr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&frm=1&source=web&cd=12&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0CCgQFjABOApqFQoTCPmHsLmdocCFcE8Ggod8gUOXw&url=http%3A%2F%2Fenergypress.gr%2Fsites%2Fdefault%2Ffiles%2Fmedia%2F%25CE%25A1%25CE%2591%25CE%2595%2520%25CE%25B1%25CF%2580%25CF%258C%25CF%2586%25CE%25B1%25CF%2583%25CE%25B7.doc&ei=SQXKvbm_G8H5aPKLuPgF&usq=AFQjCNHQAVWWWA5LtcAi-P06FL1dL4Dgrw&bvm=bv.99804247,d.d2s

1.1.1.5 Energy inspectors for energy performance of buildings - Energy audits

General information: The Presidential Decree 100/2010 (Government Gazette 177 A, 6.10.2010) is the most recent document presenting in details the energy auditors (inspectors) and is linked with the provisions of: i) Law 3661/2008 (Government Gazette 89 A, 19.5.2008) about “*measures for reducing the energy consumption in buildings and other provisions*” and ii) Law 3851/2010 about “*Accelerating the development of Renewable Energy Sources for confronting climate change and other provisions about issues under the responsibility of the MEECC*”.

The provisions of Law 3661/2008 about the energy auditors provided the framework and the necessary actions to establish this type of inspectors. Within a period of six (6) months after the enforcement of this Law, details had to be defined by the Ministry for the energy auditors (qualifications, rules for conducting their work etc).

In 2012, with the legislative act published in Government Gazette 237 A, 5.12.2012, there were amendments to the Presidential Decree 100/2010. In 2013, there was an amendment to the Presidential Decree with Law 4111/2013 (Government Gazette 18 A, 25.01.2013).

Objectives: Audits for boilers and cooling installations aim to reduce energy consumption and GHG emissions (Law 3661/2008). With the aim to reinforce the implementation of measures under Law 3661/2008 for the reduction of energy consumption in buildings, the concept of energy inspectors/auditors for the EPB was set into force with Presidential Decree 100/2010 (Government Gazette 177 A, 6.10.2010).

The purpose of this Presidential Decree was to define: i) the qualifications of energy auditors; rules and principles that govern the performance of their work, of the respective institutes and the duration of their training, the means and the procedure of their evaluation and the granting of the certificate after exams; ii) bodies, procedure and requirements of granting a permission/certificate for performing energy audits, the different levels of certificates and the issues for being accepted at the registry of the energy auditors; the conditions, the procedure and the requirements for granting temporary certificates/permissions; iii) the fees for the energy auditors, the properties that are not consistent with their work, the administrative sanctions and the financial penalties that will be imposed, the bodies, the procedure and the conditions under which sanctions and penalties are imposed, their level and scales and the criteria of measuring them, the administrative recourses against sanctions, the deadlines for complying and about any other relevant matter.

Type of policy instrument: It is a Regulatory/Administrative policy instrument that is linked with the implementation network of the policy instrument of “Energy audits”.

Target groups: Individuals that intend to be granted the property of an energy auditor.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: Law 3661/2008 had one article that referred to the energy auditors and was describing briefly the foreseen actions for implementing the policy instrument. The Presidential Decree contains all the necessary details about:

- i) the qualifications that a person needs to fulfill for becoming an energy auditor (registration at the Energy Auditors Registry³⁸ at the MEECC); types of diplomas (area: Mechanics); attendance of a special training programme defined in relevant provision of the Presidential Decree; successful completion of examination procedures; experience.
- ii) The certificates/permissions that energy auditors hold are for three categories: buildings, boilers, heating and cooling systems. The certificates are of two levels: Level B (higher, all types); Level A (lower, restrictions). Certificates of both levels have duration of 10 years and

³⁸ <https://www.buildingcert.gr/>

- an auditor of Level A is upgraded to Level B after proven experience in conducting energy audits for a 4 year period;
- iii) Responsibilities of energy auditors (reports for energy audits, EPC) and conditions under which they are not allowed to conduct the audit;
 - iv) Rules about the Registry³⁹ (conditions for quoting; type of information; necessary documentation for being registered; registration fees; updating (penalties, retirements, deaths));
 - v) Temporary certificates (duration, conditions of granting, documentation);
 - vi) Sanctions and penalties. If certain conditions are verified (inaccurate data and documentation by the energy auditor, poor performance, etc) the Special Service of the Energy Auditors of the Ministry imposes administrative and financial penalties after listening to the offender. These are: financial penalties from 500 EUR to 20.000EUR; exclusion from conducting audits from 1 to three years, permanent deletion from the registry. The sanction is recorded in the registry. Additional sanctions (administrative, removal of certificate) are also possible;
 - vii) Training of energy auditors. Provisions concern duration of training seminar (per category of certificate); content, institutes allowed to organize such training, the exam procedure (the supervising committee, frequency of exams, announcement of results), fees for the exam;
 - viii) Fees (Tables 3 and 4). VAT is not included in these figures;

Table 3: Fees for energy auditors.

Subject of audit	Surface	Fees
For buildings or parts of buildings (all types of uses) apart from residence	<1.000 m ²	2,5 EUR for each m ² of the building and cannot be less than 3.000EUR
	>1.000 m ²	2,5 EUR for each m ² of the building and for the first 1.000 m ² and 1,5EUR for the remaining m ²
For buildings or parts of buildings (horizontal or vertical ownerships) used as residence	Buildings of many ownerships and audit for the whole building	1,0 EUR for each m ² of the building surface and can not be less than 200 EUR
	Buildings of many ownerships and audit only for a part of the building (separate ownership)	2,0 EUR for each m ² of the building surface and cannot be less than 150 EUR
	Detached house	1,5 EUR for each m ² of the building surface and cannot be less than 200 EUR

(Source: Presidential Decree 100/2010).

- ix) The Advisory Committee of Energy Auditors (established within the Special Secretariat of Environmental and Energy Audits of MEECC). It is a seven member committee with the Special Secretary of Environmental and Energy Audits of the MEECC as chairman and representatives from the Special Service of Energy Audits, CRES, Technical Chamber of Greece, Scientific Association of Mechanical Technological Education and two experts on energy audits issues from universities or research centers. Rules are about incumbency of the members, its responsibilities, frequency of meetings.

³⁹ <http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=341&language=el-GR>

Table 4: Information about energy audits for boilers and cooling installations.

Total thermal power (capacity) ⁴⁰ (kW)	Sequence of conducting audit	Cost for audit (EUR)
20-100	At least every 5 years	150
>100	At least every 2 years (in case of gas fuel – every 4 years)	250
Installations of thermal capacity >20kW and older than 15 years	One time according to KENAK	20% increase per category
Total cooling capacity (kW)	Sequence of conducting audit	Cost for audit (EUR)
12-100	At least every 5 years	300
>100	At least every 5 years	500

Note: Law 4122/2013 for the cooling installations quotes only one case, that of more than 12kW (Source: Law 3661/2008, Presidential Decree 100/2010; Joint Ministerial Decision No.Δ6/B/οικ.5825/2010).

Law 4122/2013 and 4111/2013 provided modifications for provisions of the Presidential Decree 100/2010 – mostly corrections that were more detailed and accurate without changing the set framework. There was a new article about the incompatible of the energy auditors.

Implementation network: The Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy (former MEECC) is responsible for providing the necessary means for informing users and owners of buildings about methods and practices that improve EPB (Law 3661/2008). The Special Service of the Energy Auditors of the Ministry⁴¹ is responsible for checking, maintaining and managing the Registry of the Energy Auditors and of the Building Audits; the Technical Chamber of Greece is responsible for conducting twice a year the exams under the supervision of MEECC.

Outcomes: The implementation of the recast EPBD resulted in the introduction of a mandatory examination for qualified experts (e.g. France since 2012, Belgium-Flanders since 2013 and Greece since 2014) (BPIE, 2014).

Until 9 January 2014, 10.221 Greek energy auditors⁴² were assigned with the right of performing energy audits at buildings (out of which 4.690 were temporary ones), 1.763 energy auditors for performing audits at heating installations (out of which 978 are again temporary ones) and 1.347 energy auditors for performing audits at cooling installation systems (out of which 755⁴³ were temporary ones).

Until October 6th, 2013 (deadline for registry of temporary energy auditors), there were 8.468⁴⁴ temporary energy auditors for buildings, 5.858 and 5.671 for heating and cooling installations respectively. The majority of the registered energy auditors in the final registry was by 87⁴⁵% science graduates engineers and specialized in civil engineering (41%). The majority of temporary energy auditors were specialized in civil engineering by 40%, while 92% were science graduates engineers.

Until January 9th, 2014, 8.399⁴⁶ energy auditors (59,5%) issued from 1 up to 100 EPCs, 39 issued from 500 to 1.100 while 12 issued more than 1.100 EPCs. 4.317 energy auditors issued no EPCs.

⁴⁰ Effective nominal rated power

⁴¹ ΕΥΕΠΕΝ – abbreviation in Greek language

⁴² Statement of Deputy Minister of the Environment, Energy and Climate Change, Mr. Stavros Kalafatis about the three years of implementing energy audits – statistical data and qualitative elements, date: 16.01.2014. <http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=785&snr=5B524%5D=2910>

⁴³ same as footnote 39 and 42

⁴⁴ same as footnote 39 and 42

⁴⁵ same as footnote 39 and 42

⁴⁶ same as footnote 39 and 42

The majority of the registered energy auditors (53,86%)⁴⁷ at the final registry are located in Attiki (34,75%) and Central Macedonia (19,11%). Energy auditors are allowed to conduct audits in any region of the country regardless from the base they have declared.

1.1.1.6 Ecodesign requirements

General information: The Presidential Decree 7/2011 (Government Gazette 14 A, 11.02.2011⁴⁸) is: i) transposing into national law the Directive 2009/125/EC⁴⁹ about “*establishing a framework for the setting of ecodesign requirements for energy-related products (recast)*” and ii) an amendment of the Presidential Decree 32/2010 (Government Gazette 70 A, 14.05.2010⁵⁰).

There are regulations about several energy-related products⁵¹. The Ecodesign Directive provides a coherent and integrated framework which allows setting mandatory ecodesign requirements⁵² for some products. These requirements concern household washers, refrigerating appliances, televisions, washing machines; glandless circulators (standalone and integrated in products; electric motors; no-load condition power consumption and average active efficiency of external supplies, non-directional household lamps, fluorescent lamps without integrated ballast, high intensity discharge lamps, ballasts and luminaires able to operate such lamps; simple set-top boxes, standby and off mode electric power consumption of household and office equipment; energy efficiency requirements for ballasts for fluorescent lighting.

Objectives: Its objectives are to: i) secure the free market circulation of energy related products so that they contribute to sustainable development, improve energy efficiency and the protection level of the environment, with the simultaneous increase of the security of energy supply. Additionally, the functionality or the safety of a product must not be lowered by the ecodesign requirements (EC, 2012). Also, ecodesign requirements should not have a negative impact on its affordability or consumers’ health (EC, 2012).

Type of policy instrument: Regulatory – technological standards (mandatory ecodesign requirements) (Voluntary approaches for end-users). The Ecodesign Directive by itself does not provide binding requirements for specific products. It is through the provided framework that conditions and criteria are determined for setting product specific implementing measures that introduce mandatory requirements for the covered products (BIO Intelligence Service, 2013).

Target groups: It concerns manufacturers and retailers whose products consume energy (Presidential Decree 32/2010). Consumers are also included in the target groups. More specifically the Directive 2009/125/EC defines:

- energy-using products: products which use, generate, transfer or measure energy (e.g. electricity, gas, other fossil fuel), including consumer goods such as boilers, computers, TVs, washing machines, light bulbs and industrial products such as transformers, industrial fans, industrial furnaces (EC, 2012).

⁴⁷ same as footnote 39

⁴⁸ http://www.et.gr/idocs-nph/search/pdfViewerForm.html?args=5C7QrtC22wFYAFdDx4L2G3dtvSoClrL8XHaH_MviECXtlI9LGdkF53UIxSx942CdyqxSQYnuqAGCF0IfB9HI6qSYtMQEkEHLwnFqmgJSA5WIsluV-nRwO1oKqSe4BIOTSpEWYhszF8P8UqWb_zFijKtkGptvczwJkti7EOCKEEXInHeFrNBbQCc70-IZG4JS

⁴⁹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009L0125&from=EN>

⁵⁰ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=kXxhRo5sK4s%3D&...>

⁵¹ https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/list_of_ecodesign_measures.pdf

⁵² An indicative example of ecodesign requirements is the following: many domestic electrical and electronic products (i.e. washing machines, TV or personal computers) must not consume – as ecodesign requirement - more than 0.5W in off mode (stand by) as of year 2013 (EC, 2012).

- other energy related products (ERPs): products which do not necessarily use energy, but have an impact on energy consumption (direct or indirect) and can therefore contribute to saving energy, such as windows, insulation material or bathroom devices (e.g. shower heads, taps) (EC, 2012).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: Each product that consumes energy and falls under “Eco-labelling” needs to have a compliance marking “CE”. The “CE” mark ensures that the product is in compliance with the eco-design requirements; is placed on the product and has a minimum height of 5mm. If it can not be placed on the product then it needs to be placed on the package or the papers that accompany the product.

There are two types of mandatory product requirements (EC, 2012): i) Specific requirements for limit values (maximum energy consumption, minimum quantities of recycled material, etc.); ii) Generic requirements that do not set limit values, but require that: product is "energy efficient" or "recyclable"; provided information for use and maintenance shows how to minimise environmental impact; performed lifecycle analysis of the product identifies alternative design options and solutions for improvement (EC, 2012).

There are provisions for the:

- a) pertinent authorities (titles of Directorates and Services) and their tasks;
- b) free or ban market availability of product;
- c) safeguard and confidentiality clauses;
- d) procedures for assessing compliance (internal check of the eco-design of the product) with Annexes providing more details;
- e) Parameters for eco-design (selection and usage of raw materials; construction; package, transfer and distribution; installation and maintenance; usage; end of life-cycle; foreseen consumption of materials, energy and other resources like water; foreseen emissions in air, water and ground; foreseen pollution through natural phenomena like noise, vibrations, radiation, electromagnetic fields; foreseen production of waste; possibilities of re-use, recycling and recovery of materials or/end energy taking into consideration Directive 2002/96/EC).
- f) Requirements: i) about provided information; ii) for the manufacturer;
- g) Method for defining the special requirements for eco-design.

Non-compliance

There is a financial penalty ranging from 1.000 up to 50.000 EUR depending on the offense severity and considering the level of non-compliance and the number of pieces of non-complying products that were available in the market (for breaching the provisions of eco-design requirements regarding products that fall under such requirements). The penalty or/and the ban or withdrawal of the product from the market are imposed by the relevant Ministry. The Ministry needs to notify the offender in written (fax or registered letter) justifying its decision.

Implementation network: Similarly as in the case of energy labelling. Today the General Secretariat of Industry⁵³ at the Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy (former MEECC⁵⁴) is responsible for the implementation of this policy instrument. For the conduction of checks (audits) in the market, the pertinent authority – whenever that is characterized as needed –

⁵³There is also a General Secretariat under the Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism, at: <http://www.mindev.gov.gr/el/index.php/υπουργείο/γενικές-ειδικές-γραμματείες> and <http://ggb.gr/>

⁵⁴http://www.cres.gr/kape/calendar/progr_ypapen_8_6_15.pdf

will ask the contribution of other public services (ie Public Economic Services, Service of Special Audits of the Ministry of Economy, Customs, Hellenic Police, Chambers, services of the Regions (second level of local authorities) etc) provided that confidentiality is respected for the collection of the necessary material or/and the supply of the staff for the in situ audit of the business or person.

The Hellenic Organization for Standardization (ELOT⁵⁵) monitors also the implementation of this policy instrument (Presidential Decree 7/2011).

There is no responsible institution for prosecution and application of sanctions (BIO Intelligence Service, 2013).

Outcomes: No available information.

1.1.1.7 Energy management systems

General information: “Energy Management System” (EMS) is a set of interrelated or interacting elements of a plan which sets an energy efficiency objective and a strategy to achieve that objective (European Commission, 2013b). Provisions about the energy management systems are included in draft law for the transposition of Directive 2012/27/EC into national legislation. Directive 2012/27/EC is still under public consultation⁵⁶. They are strongly linked with energy audits, since the result of an energy audit may be among others (ie recommendation for window replacement in a household or insulation of piping in a factory) the setting up of a comprehensive EMS in commercial buildings (European Commission, 2013b).

Objectives: When EMS is in place, a continuous energy review process is carried out to control and reduce energy use for the target group. This results in the identification of opportunities for energy saving which are equivalent to those of discrete, regular energy audits (European Commission, 2013b).

Type of policy instrument: Regulatory policy instrument.

Target groups: Owners of buildings and ESCOs.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: EMS complying with relevant European and International Standards can be the alternative option to audit obligation for large enterprises (European Commission, 2013b). An EMS may be supported by separate energy audits (with the same scope as the EMS or with a narrower scope e.g. covering individual sites, buildings or processes) (European Commission, 2013b). So, enterprises that are implementing an energy or environmental management system are certified by an independent body according to the relevant European and International Standards. If they are considered to satisfy the energy audit requirement of the provisions in terms of, they are exempted from this obligation (European Commission, 2013b).

Head of regions and Mayors are obliged for the buildings falling under their responsibility to establish EMSs (draft Law for Directive 2012/27/EC) which will include energy audits in the frame of a plan for EE. Under the Draft Law for Directive 2012/27/EC buildings with EMSs will receive priority for financial incentives and programmes for improving EE in public buildings.

European companies and organizations (of the building or the transport sector) that are registered to EMAS need to do minor changes and additions when applying for an ISO 50001 certification. This is due to the fact that the energy management standard ISO 50001⁵⁷ represents the latest best practice in energy management (European Commission, 2013c). It assists companies to adopt a policy,

⁵⁵ <http://www.elot.gr/>

⁵⁶ <http://www.opengov.gr/minenv/?p=6683>

⁵⁷ <http://certificationeurope.com/iso-50001-energy-management-systems-certification/>

identify areas of energy consumption and target reductions by establishing a systematic Energy Management System (European Commission, 2013c). Because of their already used EMAS most of the formal and content requirements of an Energy Management System are fulfilled with minor actions to be undertaken (European Commission, 2013c).

Non-compliance

No information.

Implementation network: ESCOs can provide consultancy about the energy management system that is needed (European Council of Real Estate Professions, 2013).

Outcomes: No available information.

1.1.2 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS / INFORMATIVE POLICY INSTRUMENTS

The policy instruments of this category include: Energy Performance Certificate (Regulatory – informative), Green Public Procurement (voluntary approach) and voluntary agreements.

1.1.2.1 Energy performance of Buildings – Energy Performance Certificate

General information: Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) was set into force initially with Law 3661/2008⁵⁸ (Government Gazette 89 A, 19.05.2008). Amendments followed with Law 3855/2010 (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.06.2010⁵⁹) and Law 4122/2013 (Government Gazette 42 A, 19.02.2013⁶⁰). The last Law transposes into national legislation the Directive 2010/31/EC⁶¹ of the European parliament and Commission of the 19th May 2010 about “Energy Performance of Buildings”.

Objectives: Reduction of energy consumption of buildings.

Type of policy instrument: Regulatory – informative policy instrument (Mandatory)⁶² (UNEP, 2007). It is characterized as the European mandatory energy label for buildings⁶³. This explains why it is a regulatory policy instrument. Simultaneously, they are characterized as an information instrument because they contain information for owners of new buildings, prospective home owners and home tenants about the energy performance of the building (Markandya A. et al., 2014; CORPUS, 2011). They are also used for the same reason for public buildings and buildings used for public services (CORPUS, 2011).

Target groups: Owners of buildings – categories such as in the KENAK case. The cost for receiving an EPC burdens the owner or the joint owners of the building based on their ownership rate/percentage. Responsible for the issuing of the EPC of the buildings of their competence are: Services of the Public sector, General Secretaries of Ministries, Secretary General of Decentralized Administration Authorities, Heads of the Regions, Mayors, and managing Authorities of the public sector.

⁵⁸ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=yJy1TVyRqoo%3D>

⁵⁹ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=AxgQsUVAUjA%3d&tabid=506>

⁶⁰ https://www.buildingcert.gr/N4122_2013.pdf

⁶¹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:153:0013:0035:EN:PDF>

⁶² <http://www.euroace.org/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=T6QCt9mBlcg%3D&tabid=181>

⁶³ <http://www.iea.org/aboutus/faqs/energyefficiency/>

Rules and influencing mechanisms: The EPC is issued after the completion of: i) the construction of a new building; ii) the radical renovation of an existing one. The owner is obliged to request the issuance of the EPC. During the sale or the rental of the building the EPC is provided from the owner to the buyer or to the renter. Buildings with total surface more than 500 m² that are- used by the public sector and are visited by the public, need to have an EPC. After 9.07.2015 the minimum limit is lowered to 250 m² (Law 4122/2013). EPC is also issued for a building with total usable surface less than 50 m² after 1.01.2016 (Law 4122/2013).

Energy auditors issue the EPC, following KENAK requirements, and with duration of 10 years. If there is radical renovation or an addition to its area affecting its energy performance then the EPC expires by the time the renovation or the addition is completed, before the end of the 10 year period. The EPC contains also information about:

- i. reference values (legal requirements that are in force and criteria for comparative evaluation so that the consumers can compare and evaluate the EPB);
- ii. recommendations for improving the EPB along with the cost implied. These recommendations need to be: a) cost efficient (Law 4122/2013); b) technically feasible for the particular building and to allow the estimation of the payback periods or the ratio cost-benefit for the whole economic life-cycle (Law 4122/2013).
- iii. The index of energy performance (Law 4122/2013).
- iv. The registration number of the energy auditor performing the inspection and signing EPC.

The EPC for public buildings is placed in a clear visible position and does not contain recommendations only information for actual energy consumptions.

EPCs are registered electronically by the energy auditors at the Archive of Energy Audits for Buildings (Law 4122/2013) and hence its validity is checked through the informatics system of the Registry for Audits in Building of MEECC (at: www.buildingcert.gr). The withdrawal or replacement of an EPC is done with the approval of the Special Service of the Energy Auditors of the MEECC on the relevant request by the energy auditor that contains the reasons for such an act and the modifications of the EPC. The Special Service of the Energy Auditors of the MEECC may request additional documentation or refuse the withdrawal/replacement due to inadequate justification.

The classification of buildings is done through 9 scales (Table 5).

Table 5: Definition of energy classes.

Category	Limits
A+	$EP \leq 0,33 R_R$
A	$0,33 R_R \leq EP \leq 0,50 R_R$
B+	$0,50 R_R \leq EP \leq 0,75 R_R$
B	$0,75 R_R \leq EP \leq 1,00 R_R$
Γ	$1,00 R_R \leq EP \leq 1,41 R_R$
Δ	$1,41 R_R \leq EP \leq 1,82 R_R$
E	$1,82 R_R \leq EP \leq 2,27 R_R$
Z	$2,27 R_R \leq EP \leq 2,73 R_R$
H	$2,73 R_R < EP$

Note: EP - calculated primary energy consumption of the examined building, R_R - calculated primary energy consumption of the reference building (Source: Joint Ministerial Decision No.Δ6/Β/οικ.5825 (Government Gazette 407 Β, 9.04.2010⁶⁴) CRES, 2011).

⁶⁴ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=u2VM2IzaXlc%3D&tabid=508>

Non-compliance

Sanctions for not issuing an EPC are defined under a joint Ministerial Decision (Law 3855/2010).

The public target groups that do not comply with the EPC requirements will be excluded from funding resources (programmes and incentives) for interventions in their buildings (Law 4122/2013).

If the withdrawal/replacement procedure is not executed as foreseen (provisions of Law 4122/2013) then sanctions are imposed. Also sanctions are foreseen in case that these requests for withdrawal/replacements of EPCs that are exceeding the 5% of the total number of the EPCs that the energy auditor has submitted. The percentage can change with a decision of the Minister of Environment, Energy and Climate Change. The solemn statement of the owner of the building or the building unit is required if the EPC is valid and used in rental or purchase contract.

If there is violation of the provision for issuing an EPC then a financial penalty (from 1.000 EUR to 10.000 EUR) is imposed to the person characterized as obliged. Penalties are imposed considering the total surface and the use of the building, the size of its installations, the degree of fault and any recurrence of the person liable. The same amount of financial penalties is imposed in any obstruction in the monitoring of the Special Service of the Energy Auditors of the Ministry. Again the final amount depends on the severity of the examined case, the demerit of actions and the impact in the monitoring/check outcome.

If an EPC is found in infringement due to the energy auditor then it is withdrawn and the owner can receive compensation from the Green Fund for replacing it (Law 4122/2013).

Implementation Network: The Special Service of the Energy Auditors of the MEECC is responsible for: i) Controlling and monitoring the procedures and the quality - correctness of the EPCs, the reports for energy audits, Creating a database for all public buildings that will have an issued EPC. The database will be accessible through the web-site of MEECC⁶⁵. The service may be assisted by independent experts (Law 4122/2013).

Outcomes: In Greece the system is still in the early stages of implementation (BPIE, 2014). Access to the outcomes is offered by using the EPC identification number (known only to the building's owner) (BPIE, 2014). Only aggregated results are made publicly available (BPIE, 2014).

The total number of issued EPCs is so far: 60.640 - year 2011; 219.804 - year 2012; 226.077 - year 2013, while up to 9 January 2014, the number was 2.501⁶⁶. These issued EPCs concerned mainly (by 79%) buildings constructed during the period 1950-2009⁶⁷. The majority of the issued EPCs concerned buildings (mainly apartments) that were going to be rent. Also, the number of requested EPCs mentioning as a reasoning "First Energy Audit" for the programme "EXOIKONOMO KAT'OIKON" was increased in 2013 compared to that of the previous years. A significant share of buildings is characterized as "H" because of being without thermal insulation and with old and non-efficient systems for heating and cooling. Detached houses, multi-apartment buildings, offices and shops cover the majority (85%) of the buildings for which the EPCs were issued, while those for the tertiary sectors are much less⁶⁸.

Most EPCs were issued by the prefecture of Athens (30,77%), the county of Thessaloniki (12%), the Prefecture of Piraeus (4,7%) and the Prefecture of eastern Attiki (4,3%)⁶⁹.

⁶⁵ <http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=341&language=el-GR>

⁶⁶ Statement of Deputy Minister of the Environment, Energy and Climate Change, Mr. Stavros Kalafatis about the three years of implementing energy audits – statistical data and qualitative elemats, date: 16.01.2014. <http://www.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=785&snr%5B524%5D=2910>

⁶⁷ same as footnote 62

⁶⁸ same as footnote 62

⁶⁹ same as footnote 62

1.1.2.2 Green Public Procurements

General information: For complying with the EU legislation, the concept of “Green Public Procurements⁷⁰” (GPP) was introduced under Law 3855/2010. The draft Law⁷¹ about the transposition of Directive 2012/27/EC has also provisions for this policy instrument. GPP are considered as a category of Public Private Procurements (PPPs) which were described in details in Law 3389/2005 (Government Gazette 232 A, 22.09.2005⁷²).

Objectives: Promotion of EE in the public sector through agreements between public and private entities. The purpose of the EU Green Public Procurement (GPP) policy instrument is to use the purchasing power of the EU Member States governments to stimulate the markets for goods and services with lower impacts on the environment (BIO Intelligence Service, 2013).

Type of policy instrument: It is a policy instrument of voluntary approach that promotes EE technologies and practices.

Target groups: Public⁷³ and private entities that sign contracts covering: Energy efficient computers, Office furniture from sustainable timber, Low energy buildings, Recycled paper, Cleaning services using environmentally friendly cleaning products, Electric, hybrid or low-emission vehicles, Electricity from renewable energy sources (European Commission and ICLEI – Local governments for Sustainability, 2011).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: Under the common decision of MEECC and MEIST⁷⁴: i) a catalogue will be compiled about EE specifications for vehicles, using also - depending on the case – the methodology of minimizing the cost of the life cycle or similar methods for ensuring the cost efficiency; ii) a percentage will be defined about clean vehicles (electric and hybrid cars, cars using natural gas, biofuel and hydrogen) used by the public services; iii) the procedure of replacing old (middle or heavy) vehicles of the public sector more than 3.5tn and with age more than a decade or transforming their motors to natural gas ones; iv) the vehicle procurement process using the fuel economy label as criterion; v) the terms and the criteria for training programmes regarding the promotion of eco-driving principles for the drivers of vehicles that are used by the public sector.

Rules for the Inter-ministerial Committee

Detailed rules, responsibilities, tasks, procedures, conditions for agreements between public and private entities are described in Law 3389/2005 (Government Gazette 232 A, 22.09.2005⁷⁵). More specifically, there are rules about: its synthesis (indicatively: 3 persons from MEECC and their replacements; 2 from MEIST⁷⁶ etc); selection of its members; working groups that support its work; its responsibilities; participation of other ministries, bodies or institutes; programme and time of meetings and fees.

⁷⁰ Green Public Procurement (GPP) is "a process whereby public authorities seek to procure goods, services and works with a reduced environmental impact throughout their life-cycle when compared to goods, services and works with the same primary function that would otherwise be procured." - http://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/faq_en.htm

⁷¹ <http://www.opengov.gr/minenv/?p=6692>

⁷² http://www.epdm.gr/Uploads/Files/files_for_content/n3389.pdf

⁷³ Public sector, first and second level of local authorities, companies whose stock share belongs to the public sector or local authorities - Public transport sector

⁷⁴ Law 3855/2010

⁷⁵ http://www.epdm.gr/Uploads/Files/files_for_content/n3389.pdf

⁷⁶ Its Members are: The Minister of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (Head of Committee); The Minister of Finance; The Minister of Productive Reconstruction, Environment and Energy; The Minister(s) who supervise(s) each of the Public Bodies that are examining the implementation of PPP projects, under their competencies.

In Greece all offers under a PPP are examined by the Inter-Ministerial Committee for Public-Private Partnerships⁷⁷. This collective governmental body sets the general policy for PPPs and approves projects that should proceed for implementation through the PPP framework. Its responsibilities include: i) approval of inclusion of PPP projects to the framework depicted in Law 3389, but also cancelation of such approvals; ii) decision for the provision of any contractual consideration to the private partner in the Public Investments Programme; iii) decision about the level of the public sector's participation in the financing of a PPP project.

Eco-labels

Eco-labels are one of the key policy instruments that are used in combination with GPP. On the one hand, specifications or criteria are developed and on the other there are verifications of compliance of products and services with these standards so as to proceed with the GPP⁷⁸.

Implementation Network: The MEECC was assigned as the authority responsible to design the National Policy and drawing of a National Action Plan for promoting the Green Public Procurements (Law 3855/2010). MEECC will need to cooperate with other Ministries and bodies of the public and private sector for proceeding with the necessary legislative settings and measure for implementing the "Green Public Procurements". For the better coordination of these efforts an eleven member Interministerial Committee was established.

Outcomes: The outcomes of a survey regarding the implementation of the Green Public procurement in the EU27, showed that Greece had a below 20% GPP uptake performance (Centre for European Policy Studies and the College of Europe, 2012).

1.1.2.3 Voluntary agreements

General information: Voluntary agreements or market schemes such as white certificates are foreseen under Law 3885/2010 (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.6.2010⁷⁹).

Objectives: For improving the energy efficiency of end-user sectors.

Type of policy instrument: Voluntary approach.

Target groups: These agreements are between private entities or between them and public entities.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: Voluntary agreements are submitted for evaluation to the MEECC, which supervises them. Supervision is conducted through the submission of regular reports regarding the achievement of the target or for any reviewed measures or for additional ones when the targets were not be achieved or are not expected to be achieved. The content of the voluntary agreements is published on a specific web-site before their implementation. The published material is subjected to the protection of personal data and market-sensitive information. There is also an invitation to the interested entities for submitting observations.

Implementation network: MEECC and private entities.

Outcomes: No information.

⁷⁷ <http://www.sdit.mnec.gr/en/information/PPP/interministerial-committee>

⁷⁸ http://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/eco_labels.htm

⁷⁹ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=AxgQsUVAUjA%3d&tabid=506>

1.1.3 ECONOMIC POLICY INSTRUMENTS

The policy instruments of this category are: taxation on energy products and electricity, Green Fund-subsidies, financial incentives (subsidies, financial exemptions), financial incentives for replacement of devices/systems).

1.1.3.1 Taxation of energy products and electricity (mentioned also as fuel tax)

General information: The Law 3336/2005 (Government Gazette 96 A, 20.01.2005⁸⁰) transposed Directive 2003/96/EC⁸¹ “on restructuring the Community framework for the taxation of energy products and electricity” and introduced the special tax for consumption of energy products, electricity, alcohol, alcoholic beverages and tobacco products. A minimum of taxation was determined for energy products. Directive 2003/96/EC⁸², named also as Energy Taxation Directive, was amended by Directive 2004/75/EC⁸³. Updates of these minimum figures of taxation were presented in Laws 3828/2010 (Government Gazette 31 A, 25.02.2010⁸⁴), 3833/2010 (Government Gazette 40 A, 15.03.2010⁸⁵); 3845/2010 (Government Gazette 65 A, 6.05.2010⁸⁶) and 4092/2012 (Government Gazette 220 A, 8.11.2012⁸⁷).

Objectives: Revenues for the public sector and achievement of energy savings.

Type of policy instrument: Financial policy instrument.

Target groups: Buildings with diesel heating or cooling installations (Households, office buildings) and vehicles.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: A winter period has been determined. Oil for internal combustion as heating fuel is sold during the period 15 October up to 30 April. Biodiesel is taxed like oil (Foundation for Economic and Industrial Research, 2012). Businesses are obliged to use oil for mobility as if it is for heating (Foundation for Economic and Industrial Research, 2012).

Oil for internal combustion as heating fuel is released for consumption, handled and sold by traders who fall into the Registry of Dealers for Fuel heating. There is an exemption for the case of the Armed Forces for which there is no obligation for their integration in the Registry.

The members of this registry are obliged to insert and quote with accuracy within 14 days at the Monitoring Informatics system for Heating Fuel that is under the supervision of the General Secretariat of Information System and Administrative Support of Ministry of Finance⁸⁸, all the transactions for the Oil for internal combustion (DIESEL) as heating fuel, for all stages (from the deposition to the Customs Authority of the Special tax for Consumption up to final consumption).

Implementation network: MEECC (details for the Ministry are in report D.1.1).

⁸⁰ https://www.mou.gr/elibrary/N3336_200405_fek96.pdf

⁸¹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2003:283:0051:0070:EN:PDF>

⁸² On 20 April 2012 the European Parliament voted against the draft Energy Taxation Directive. In June 2014, the EU countries discussed on revising the Energy Taxation Directive, but did not reach an agreement yet. (Source: http://www.inforse.org/europe/eu_e-tax.htm and http://europa.eu/rapid/press-release_MEMO-11-238_en.htm?locale=en)

⁸³ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32004L0075&from=EN>

⁸⁴ http://www.e-forosimv.gr/docs/fek_a_31_2010.pdf

⁸⁵ http://www.epdm.gr/Uploads/Files/nomoi_kya/N_3833_2010.pdf

⁸⁶ http://www.ktpae.gr/pdf/D_7_N_3845_2010.pdf

⁸⁷ http://www.hfsf.gr/files/legal/13.L4092_am10.pdf

⁸⁸ <http://www.mnec.gr/?q=en/content/general-special-secretaries>

Outcomes: The tax revenues are presented in Table 7.

Table 6: Special taxation on energy consumption.

Year	Amount of tax (in EUR) per type of fuel (in 1.000 lit)		
	Type of fuel (in 1.000 lit) Metric unit (in lit)		
	Oil for internal combustion (DIESEL) for: 1) motor fuel; 2) heating fuel; 3) a use different than 1) and 2).	Paraffin oil (kerosene) for: 1) motor fuel; 2) heating fuel; 3) a use different than 1) and 2).	Biodiesel with methyl esters of fatty acids for motor fuel as it is or in mixture with oil for internal combustion (DIESEL)
2005	245	245	-
2010*	352	380	352
2010	382	410	382
2010	412	412	412
2012**	330	330	330

Note: 2005 prices are from Law 3336 - Government Gazette 96 A, 20.1.2005 (Directive 2003/96/EC)

*2010 prices from Law 3828 - Government Gazette 31 A, 25.02.2010, Law 3833 - Government Gazette 40 A, 15.3.2010 and Law 3845 - Government Gazette 65 A, 6.5.2010

**2012 prices from Law 4092/2012 - Government Gazette 220 A, 8.11.2012.

Table 7: Revenues due to the implementation of the special taxation for consumption.

Year	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013
Implicit tax rate on energy (in EUR per tonne of oil equivalent)	128,67	135,48	131,28	140,70	215,25	223,82	238,55	257,19

Note: The figures are presented in connection with the relevant Directives 2003/96/EC and 2004/74/EC⁸⁹ - The index is the ratio of the revenues in EUR (deflated) and the final energy consumption as toe (tonne of oil equivalent). (Source of data: Eurostat 2015⁹⁰)

1.1.3.2 Green Fund - Subsidies

General information: Green Fund⁹¹ was described as a programme in D.1.1., but due to the fact that it is linked with grants and subsidies it is also presented in this session. It was established with law 3889/2010 (Government Gazette 182 A, 14.10.2010⁹²).

Objectives: A fund is set up with the objective of contributing support through a Programme or Programmes to several financial instruments (subsidies, grants, soft loans etc). The body implementing these financial instruments through the fund of funds is considered the only beneficiary (European Commission and European Investment Bank, 2014).

The objective of setting up the Green Fund was to reinforce development through environmental protection by assigning to the fund the managerial, economic, technical and financial support of

⁸⁹ http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/tsdcc360_esmsip.htm#stat_pres1429535622816.

⁹⁰ <http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/tgm/table.do?tab=table&plugin=1&language=en&pcode=tsdcc360>

⁹¹ <http://www.prasinotameio.gr/index.php/el/>

⁹² <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=h1wqDS%2FNDHg%3D>

programmes, measures and interventions for environmental restoration and enhancement and confronting climate change (Law 3889/2010).

Type of policy instrument: Green Fund is not a policy instrument, but an established entity - public corporation - that supervises the implementation of programs. Its establishment so as to expand the implementation network and to facilitate the flux of resources for EE purposes falls under the category of Regulatory policy instruments. Since it concerns the establishment of a funding mechanism for facilitating the implementation of the EE policy, this action falls under this category of policy instruments. Also, under Directive 2006/32/EC⁹³, the examples for financial policy instruments⁹⁴ for energy savings include funds. There is no information about which sectors these programs concern. The Green Fund is considered as a financial recourse for EE actions in the buildings sector. However, these actions depend on the submitted proposals by the public authorities and the open calls. For the Hellenic case the Green Funds Scheme clearly shows also that a form of public-private collaboration can take place through sponsorships.

Target groups: The type of target groups depends on the type of grant supported by the Green Fund.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: Law 3899/2010 has provisions about the responsibilities of the Green Fund, its Board of Directors and its financial resources⁹⁵. The Green Fund finances programmes (grants, subsidies) that are announced by the MEECC, other Ministries, local authorities, other entities of the public sector⁹⁶. Law 3899/2010 has provisions about the procedure of approving, announcing and organizing such programmes and the criteria which depend on the type of grand that is announced by the Green Fund. There have been announcements that concern EE as well.

Implementation network: MEECC, Green Fund.

Outcomes: No project for EE is in the list of approved projects published by Green Fund on its website⁹⁷.

1.1.3.3 Financial incentives (subsidies, financial exemptions)

General information: This policy instrument was introduced under Law 3851/2010 (Government Gazette 85 A, 4.6.2010⁹⁸) (transposing Directive 2010/31/EC⁹⁹) and concerns the funding of programmes for promoting EE. Financial incentives have been used as part of programmes presented in D.1.1. Some of these programmes are completed and will not open again, others were completed, but are expected to re-open and others are still operational.

Objectives: It aims at the promotion of works for the improvement of EE and the use of RES in households through financial incentives.

⁹³ - <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32006L0032&from=EN>

⁹⁴ financial instruments for energy savings' are by definition: funds, subsidies, tax rebates, loans, third-party financing, energy performance contracting, guarantee of energy savings contracts, energy outsourcing and other related contracts that are available to the market by public or private bodies so as to cover partly or totally the initial project cost for implementing EE improvement measures (Source: Directive 2006/32/EC).

⁹⁵ These resources are sponsorships, donations, inheritances, bequests, revenues from penalties and fines about environmental violations, contributions from energy distributors, managers of network distribution and retail trade energy companies (according to Law 3855/2010).

⁹⁶ <http://www.prasinotameio.gr/index.php/el/programmata-kai-dikaioxoi>

⁹⁷ <http://www.prasinotameio.gr/index.php/el/programmata-kai-dikaioxoi>

⁹⁸ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=pnhppGnURds%3d&tabid=506>

⁹⁹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:153:0013:0035:EN:PDF>

Type of policy instrument: Financial policy instruments (Subsidies through programmes that promote EE, exemptions of paying charges).

Target groups: Owners of buildings, apartments.

Rules and Influencing mechanisms: there are provisions about the types of programmes that will fund such actions and the procedures that will be adopted (types of financial incentives, maximum amount to be given, eligible types of interventions, works etc).

Target groups that proceed with EE works in buildings (interventions etc) are exempted from the charges for the municipalities at which the building is located.

Implementation network: MEECC or authority that is assigned for monitoring the implementation of the policy instrument.

Outcomes: Statistical data of such programmes are not available¹⁰⁰. The estimation for outcomes for the programme “EXOIKONOMO KAT’ OIKON” was energy savings of approximately 1 billion KWh per year¹⁰¹.

The number of applications for participation at the programme “EXOIKONOMO KAT’ OIKON” was more than 1.500 per week (data for September 2012) (Hellenic Parliament, 2013). Up to June 2013, the number of applications for loan approval by banks was 143.981 out of which half were approved (Hellenic Parliament, 2013). 13.597 projects – for the same time period – were fully financed, while 5.390 had received deposit (Hellenic Parliament, 2013). The total available amount for the programme was 207,88 million EUR out of which 145,28 million EUR were from the programme resources and 62,6 million EUR were from the participating banks (see report of D.1.1) (Hellenic Parliament, 2013).

The public expenditure for the whole programme was estimated at 396 million EUR coming mainly from two Operational Programmes “Competitiveness and Entrepreneurship” and “Environment and Sustainable Development (Hellenic Parliament, 2013). 241 million EUR are from the fund for the “EXOIKONOMO KAT’ OIKON” programme and 155 million EUR from the programme “Direct reinforcement” that covers grants (Hellenic Parliament, 2013). Finally, the total public expenditure reached the 470,6 million EUR and additional resources were sought (Hellenic Parliament, 2013). Considering also the financial resources that Banks will also use for the programme, the total budget will be at 650 million EUR (Hellenic Parliament, 2013).

The implementation of EE actions under the “EXOIKONOMO for local authorities I” was approved for 106 local authorities (based on the Ministerial Decision Φ.B1/E5.4/338/6/09.01.2012) with total budget 83,4 million EUR and subsidy percentage at 70% (Hellenic Parliament, 2013). Up to June 2013, 102 proposals were participating with total budget of 80,49 million EUR (Hellenic Parliament, 2013).

For “EXOIKONOMO for local authorities II” the respective figures were 139 proposals with total budget at 50,96 million EUR (Hellenic Parliament, 2013).

The “ALLAZO KLIMATISTIKO” programme (replacement and recycling of old air-conditions) resulted to the introduction of 138.000 new devices with a total budget of 45,16 million EUR (Hellenic Parliament, 2013).

1.1.3.4 Financial incentives for replacement of devices/systems

General information: Ministerial Decision Φ.14/02/19398/2927 (Government Gazette 3071 B, 14.11.2014¹⁰²). The replacement of oil heating systems with natural gas ones was financed by the

¹⁰⁰ <http://www.etean.com.gr/publicpages/ProgramStatistics4.aspx>

¹⁰¹ <http://exoikonomisi.ypeka.gr/Default.aspx?tabid=698&language=el-GR>

¹⁰² https://drive.google.com/file/d/0B7Jb_n_W6q6bR1INNE92THd3c1E/view?usp=sharing&pli=1

National Strategic Reference Framework (NSRF) ESPA – for the period 2007-2013¹⁰³. The deadline was 15 April 2015.

Objectives: Reduction of GHG emissions through energy efficient thermal and cooling systems.

Type of policy instrument: Financial – subsidy.

Target groups: Household buildings (detached or multi-apartment buildings).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: The Ministerial Decision describes in details the: i) conditions and documentation that the owners of the household buildings need to fulfil for receiving the grant/subsidy; ii) obligations of the beneficiaries; iii) procedures for receiving the grant; iv) rules-responsibilities for the supervising authority (see implementation network); v) templates of the necessary documentation relevant to the grant. The grant is up to 60% of the total eligible cost for the internal installation for natural gas in the household for replacing the existing oil heating system (central or individual).

Table 8: Grant amounts per category.

Installed boiler capacity (1. existing without change of boiler; 2. New in case of boiler change) (in kcal/h)	Maximum grant amount (in EUR) (VAT included)	
	without changing boiler	With boiler change
0-35.000	1.000 for conventional boiler systems, 1.150 for condensation systems	
35.001 – 120.000	1.500	2.000
120.001 – 170.000	2.300	3.000
170.001-200.000	3.300	4.000
>200.000	4.700	5.500

(Source: Ministerial Decision Φ.14/02/19398/2927 (Government Gazette 3071 B /14.11.2014).

Implementation network: The pertinent authority for monitoring this policy instrument is the Special Service for Coordination and Implementation for Energy, Natural Wealth and Climate Change of the MEECC (Law 3614/2007 – Government Gazette 267 A, 3.12.2007¹⁰⁴). Also, Regions (second level of local authorities – see report D.1.1) and relevant companies such as companies providing natural gas (EPA are involved with contracts with MEECC).

Outcomes: No information.

1.1.4 CAPACITY BUILDING AND NETWORKING

None.

¹⁰³ <https://www.espa.gr/en/Pages/Default.aspx>

¹⁰⁴ http://www.mou.gr/elibrary/N3614_031207_fek267.pdf

1.1.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR THE PROMOTION OF ENERGY SERVICES

1.1.5.1 ESCO Market Promotion¹⁰⁵ (Other policy instruments)

General information: The concept of Energy Services Companies (ESCOs) was introduced with Law 3855/2010 (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.06.2010¹⁰⁶) which was transposing Directive 2006/32/EC¹⁰⁷ (dated 5.04.2006) of the European Parliament and European Commission about the “energy efficiency of the end-user and the energy services and the abolishment of Directive 93/76/EC”.

Objectives: For transposing Directive 2006/32/EC, the following objectives were set: a) determination of national targets for EE; establishment of the necessary national institutional and legal framework and forecast about the necessary financial means for achieving these objectives; provision of the necessary motives and forecast for the necessary mechanisms for EE so as to overcome barriers and market imperfections; b) creation of conditions allowing development and promotion of the market for energy services and other measures improving the EE of the end-user.

Type of policy instrument: Other policy instruments¹⁰⁸. Promotion of Energy Efficiency Services (EES)

Target groups: It is imposed to the: i) providers of energy services and other measures of EE; ii) distributors of energy; iii) distribution network operators; energy companies of retail sales; iv) end-users¹⁰⁹; v) national Armed Forces as long as this policy instrument is not in contrary with the type and main aim of their activities.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: A Registry for ESCOs is established (Law 3885/2010). There are provisions about the pertinent authority (under the MEECC) that will be responsible for the maintenance of the registry, the procedure, the criteria, the necessary documentation for registration; issues regarding dissemination, deletion and modification for the registrations; the management manner and exploitation of the registry data and for any other specialized issue.

The criteria for allowing an ESCO to register are its technical and financial adequacy and its experience in projects for improving energy efficiency.

Contract of Energy Services (CES)

It is a contract signed between the end-user and ESCO. It has the typical elements of a contract as foreseen in Law 2251/1994 (Government Gazette 191 A, 1994) for the protection of consumers. In the CES there can be a third participant ie bank or a funding entity for covering the cost of the offered services. The CES regulates: i) planning - management of the offered energy service and the energy work; ii) methodology used for estimating energy savings and overall financial benefit; iii) purchase, installation and placing of the necessary energy equipment (electro-mechanical and electronic machinery, building material) that improve energy performance for end-use; iv) management, functionality and maintenance of the equipment; v) total cost of the work (ie costs for supply, installation, operation, maintenance of the equipment and funding cost) and the fee for

¹⁰⁵ The title of this policy instrument is according to UNEP categorization –

<http://www.unep.org/sustainablebuildingpolicies/pdfs/SPoD-final-Chap%203.10.pdf>

¹⁰⁶ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=AxgQsUVAUjA%3D&...>

¹⁰⁷ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32006L0032&from=EN>

¹⁰⁸ These policy instruments do not fall in any of the other categories.

¹⁰⁹ The law contains the following definition for “end-user”: Public sector and every natural or legal person that consumes energy for its own final use and to which/who are offered energy services.

ESCO; v) procedure of estimating the energy benefit; vi) manner and period of payback (Law 3855/2010).

The end-user has to pay to the ESCO or to the third contract participant the financial exchange¹¹⁰ for the offered service. In case that the financial benefit due to energy savings is:

- Less than the conventionally defined one, the ESCO is obliged to pay to the end-user the difference or the end-user will pay the reduced amount under the condition that the end-user was using the energy equipment according to the terms of the contract;
- More than the conventionally defined one, the end-user enjoys the exaggerated amount, unless it is agreed differently.

Non-compliance

Distributors of energy, distribution network operators, energy companies of retail sales are obliged to provide annually to the MEECC statistical data and information for their end-users facilitating the planning of programmes regarding EE. They are also obliged to offer competitive prices for energy services, energy audits or measures for improving EE to their end-users (Law 3855/2010). In case of non-compliance to these actions they will have to pay a penalty ranging from 5.000 EUR to 250.000EUR. The final amount depends on the severity of the offense, the impacts due to it, the degree of responsibility and any recurrence of the offender (Law 3855/2010).

Implementation network: The Green Fund can be used as financial resource for EES (mentioned in the relevant Laws), independent energy consultants, Distributors of energy, distribution network operators, energy companies of retail sales and end-users.

For promoting the market of energy services the MEECC has created the registry (Ministerial Decision Δ6/B/13280/2011 - Government Gazette 1228 B, 14.06.2011¹¹¹), which is located at: <http://www.escoregistry.gr/>

Outcomes: This policy instrument is still in early implementation and there are so far no available outcomes. There are 30 registrations of ESCOs based in the whole country.

1.1.6 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT AND BEST AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGY (BAT) PROMOTION

None.

¹¹⁰ It is a percentage of the financial benefit that will result due to energy savings from end-use.

¹¹¹ <http://www.escoregistry.gr/YA.pdf>

1.1.7 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR IN HELLAS

Summary table: Buildings					
Policy instruments	Short list of implemented policies and measures	Objective	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Implementation network
Regulatory policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy labelling, • KENAK, • Minimum energy performance requirements for buildings, • energy audits, • energy auditors, • Energy management systems • Eco-design requirements 	Promotion of energy efficiency	Final energy consumers and producers/manufacturers of energy efficient technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Registry • Penalties • Sanctions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General Secretariat of Industry at MEECC; • Ministry of Finance; • Chambers; • Regions (second level local authorities)
Dissemination and awareness instruments/Informative policy instruments	Energy Performance Certificate	Promotion of energy efficiency	Owners of buildings, apartments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Penalties • Sanctions 	Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy
	Green Public Procurements, Voluntary agreements	Promotion of energy efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Public sector • Local authorities Private entities that can provide EE services and technologies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not mentioned 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Finance; • Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy
Economic policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subsidies from Green Fund, 	Promotion of energy efficiency; reduction of GHG	Owners of buildings, apartments	Not mentioned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MEECC; • Green Fund;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tax 	emissions;			
Capacity building and networking	None				
Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services	ESCOs market promotion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of an market for energy efficiency actions • Promotion of energy efficiency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providers of energy services and other measures of EE; • Distributors of energy; • Distribution network operators; energy companies of retail sales; • End-users 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Registry • Penalties • Sanctions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy; • Green Fund
Policy instruments for Research and Development and BAT promotion	None	-	-	-	-

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

1.2.1 PLANNING INSTRUMENTS

1.2.1.1 Cycling and pedestrianism in the city

General information: This policy instrument continues to be in force with the Joint Ministerial Decision No. 1397/13.01.2015¹¹² for the “Integrated Plan of Urban Intervention for the city center of Athens” (Government Gazette 64/B 16.01.2015) following the Ministerial Decision 33523/7564/10-6-2002¹¹³. According to the “Integrated Plan of Urban Intervention for the city center of Athens”, new pedestrian zones and network of cycle paths are expected to be developed. Sustainable transport will be also enhanced with the upgrade of the public transport management system.

There was also a pilot action that allowed cycling in certain bus-lanes in the city of Athens from 20.06.2011 until 18.09.2011 in order to determine its impact on the operation of the bus-lanes¹¹⁴.

Type of policy instrument: It does not fall only in one of the categories of policy instruments. It is a planning policy instrument, but also a dissemination – awareness one. It has also voluntary character.

Policy instruments for the transport sector are divided into (Skinner I. et al., 2010): Regulatory policy instruments; Economic instruments; Infrastructure and spatial policy, speed and traffic management; Information to raise awareness; and other instruments to stimulate innovation and development. The categories “infrastructure and spatial policy” and “speed and traffic management” form the planning instruments since they are linked with the planning process (TRIP, 2013). More specifically, sustainable transport planning includes: i) the management of transport demand and ii) the provision of services that enhance the overall urban system and surroundings (Transport Research and Innovation Portal (TRIP, 2013)).

A definition provided by European Commission – Directorate General for Energy and Transport about “Traffic management” quotes that it is the “planning, monitoring and control or influencing of traffic¹¹⁵” (European Commission – Directorate General for Energy and Transport, 2009). Traffic management falls under the planning process and can be further improved through integration and interoperability of the transport networks (TRIP, 2013). One of these actions to achieve this purpose is the integration of cycling with sustainable mobility management schemes¹¹⁶.

Simultaneously, this policy instrument is part of the EU awareness-raising campaigns that promote: i) multimodality (such as the “European Mobility Week”; the “Do The Right Mix campaign”) and ii) physical activity and participation in sport at all levels (such as the “European Week of Sport”)¹¹⁷.

¹¹²http://www.et.gr/idoocs-nph/search/pdfViewerForm.html?args=5C7QrtC22wE4q6ggiv8WTXdtvSoClrL8BI7vRxXKg8ztll9LGdkF52dKwsMi1xmmyqxSQYNUqAGCF0IfB9HI6qSYtMQEkeHLwnFqmgJSA5WIsluV-nRwO1oKqSe4BIOTSpEWYhszF8P8UqWb_zFijBpy4_VMSQ2ZdnTHMCmYCCfAixDHA-ThsbH1lbrEvS7e

¹¹³<http://www.hellenicparliament.gr/Praktika/Synedriaseis-Olomeleias?sessionRecord=e7696f4c-a10c-4222-a036-aa69e43b97ff>

¹¹⁴ <http://www.yme.gr/?aid=3010>

¹¹⁵ This is expected to be achieved by: i) maximizing the effectiveness of the use of existing infrastructure; ii) ensuring reliable and safe operation of transport; iii) addressing environmental goals; and iv) ensuring fair allocation of infrastructure space (road space, rail slots, etc.) among competing users (European Commission – Directorate General for Energy and Transport, 2009).

¹¹⁶ <http://www.cyclecities.eu/>

¹¹⁷ http://ec.europa.eu/transport/themes/urban/urban_mobility/urban_mobility_actions/cycling-walking_en.htm

Objectives: Promotion of sustainable transport (walking, cycling) in the city center of Athens.

Target groups: End-users (citizens of Athens, tourists, etc.)

Rules and influencing mechanisms: Measures that concern the determination of cycling-lanes are set into force with local/regional level (municipalities) decision making according to Law 3542/2007 (Government Gazette 50 A, 02.03.2007¹¹⁸).

Also, STASY SA¹¹⁹ permitted carrying bikes on trams, metro and the electric railway in Athens, so as to contribute to the combined transportation of the citizens¹²⁰.

Non-compliance

There are provisions that concern the driving behavior of the bike owner. If the bike does not have the appropriate lighting, brake system or other parts the driver is charged with a fine of 40 EUR (Law 3542/2007).

Implementation network: Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy, Ministry of Culture, Education and Religious Affairs, Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (former Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport and Networks), Municipality of Athens, OASA (Transport for Athens), Region of Attica, Unification of Archaeological Sites and Redevelopment SA. More details about the Ministries are available in the national report of D.1.1.

Outcomes: No outcomes have been generated yet.

1.2.1.2 Improvement of infrastructure for electric vehicles

General information: This policy instrument is in force with the: Joint Ministerial Decision 71287/6443¹²¹ (Government Gazette 50/B 15.01.2015), Law 4233/2014¹²² (Government Gazette 22 A, 29.01.2014), Law 4070/2012¹²³ (Government Gazette 82 A, 10.04.2012).

The Law 4070/2012 introduced a new definition for “*Fuel and Energy Supply stations*” and gave them the permission to provide the passing vehicles with bioethanol, biodiesel, electric energy and hydrogen, apart from the conventional fuels. This part of the Law was amended by the article 15 of Law 4233/2014. The Joint Ministerial Decision 71287/6443 set the terms, preconditions and technical specifications of the charging devices of electric vehicles’ batteries for their installation in existing or under licensing indoor and outdoor car parks, in existing or under licensing service garage for cars, mopeds and motorcycles, and existing or under licensing public or private Roadworthiness Test Centers/MOT Centers. Plug-in Hybrid Electric Vehicles (PHEV), Extended Range Electric Vehicles (E-REV) and Battery Electric Vehicles (BEV) are considered as electric vehicles.

Type of policy instrument: It is a planning – regulatory policy instrument. It is a planning policy instrument because it concerns transport networks (see also the “type of policy instrument” of the previous policy instrument). For this case it is the support of small networks for recharging vehicles (IREA, 2012). The need to support such recharging networks will reduce the “range anxiety” of the

¹¹⁸

http://www.google.gr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&frm=1&source=web&cd=1&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0CCQQFjAAahUKEwj20b7H5aPHAhUEtRoKHQ1sAl0&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.yme.gr%2Fgetfile.php%3Fid%3D2342&ei=VV3LVbbTNYTqao3YiegF&usq=AFQjCNFdM3SvgrVLYo6HIDpofJI_8NxnQ&bvm=bv.99804247,d.d2s

¹¹⁹ See for more details national report of D.1.1

¹²⁰ <http://www.stasy.gr/?id=42>

¹²¹ <http://www.taxheaven.gr/laws/circular/view/id/20359>

¹²² http://www.depa.gr/uploads/files/fek/N%204233_CNG_29%201%2014.pdf

¹²³ http://gnto.gov.gr/sites/default/files/N_4070_2012.pdf

vehicle owners (ie the fear of not reaching a charging point before the battery dies)(IREA, 2012). It is characterized as a regulatory policy instrument because it sets the framework of operation about the supply stations for electric cars.

Objectives: The objective was the establishment of installation licensing for the charging devices of electric vehicles' and the promotion of electric and hybrid vehicles. By reducing the "range anxiety" of these vehicle owners a significant barrier to the introduction of the electric vehicle, is overcome (IREA, 2012).

Target groups: Vehicle owners, existing or under licensing indoor and outdoor car parks, existing or under licensing service garage for cars, mopeds and motorcycles, & existing or under licensing public or private Roadworthiness Test Centers¹²⁴/MOT¹²⁵ Centers (road).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: The Joint Ministerial Decision 71287/6443 set the obligation for the development of a study on the spatial position of the battery charging equipment meeting minimum inner safety distance. This study will be conducted by a certified engineer and will be submitted to the relevant regional office of Transport and Communications. Also, securing license for the installation of charging points requires the submission of the relevant documentation (designs, technical study, and certification).

Implementation network: Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (former Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport and Networks), Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy (former Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change (MEECC), Regional Offices of Transport and Communications. More details on the Ministries are available in the national report of D.1.1.

Outcomes: The network "Fortizo" includes 14 charging points in Athens by July 2015, which own different entities (car parks, stations, etc.)¹²⁶. Since 2011, EKO-ELPEDISON (company of ELPE-Hellenic Petroleum) installed the first 3 public recharging stations for electrical vehicles in Greece in 3 EKO fuel stations in the area of Athens¹²⁷. Also, the Public Power Corporation (DEI SA) implemented a pilot project for the installation of fifteen (15) charging points (eight in Kozani and seven in Athens) in the frame work of Green e-motion project (FP7).

The small number of charging points can be attributed to the following: There are less than five models of electric cars available in Greece. The cost is preventive since a car of 57hp costs 42.000 EUR (Energy Agency of Aegean, 2011).

1.2.2 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS

1.2.2.1 Emission standards (Euro 5 and Euro 6)

General information: In 1998 the European Automobile Manufacturers Association (ACEA¹²⁸) and the European Commission concluded with the voluntary agreement to limit the amount of carbon

¹²⁴ The Greek abbreviation that is commonly used is KTEO

¹²⁵ Ministry of Transport test (usually abbreviated to MOT test)

¹²⁶ <http://user.fortizo.gr/>

¹²⁷ <https://www.google.gr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&cad=rja&uact=8&ved=0CB8QFjAAahUKewjglzXpKHHAhWHiRoKHehrD1U&url=http%3A%2F%2Femobilityworks.com%2Fro%2Fdesc%25C4%2583rc%25C4%2583ri%2Fcategory%2F1-national-factsheet.html%3Fdownload%3D4%3Afact-sheet-greece&ei=3gzKVeCtMoeTaujXvagF&usg=AFQjCNH-Ro7WnNyMFEYRd2L4TYocU6dCBQ&bvm=bv.99804247,d.d2s>

¹²⁸ ACEA's members are BMW Group, DAF Trucks, Daimler, Fiat Chrysler Automobiles, Ford of Europe, Hyundai Motor Europe, IVECO, Jaguar Land Rover, Opel Group, PSA Peugeot Citroën, Renault Group, Toyota Motor

dioxide (CO₂) emitted by passenger cars sold in Europe. In February 2007, the Commission acknowledged the failure of the voluntary agreement and introduced the EC regulation No. 715/2007¹²⁹. This EU Regulation was adopted by the MEIST.

There is no relevant information about EC Regulation No. 692/2008¹³⁰ (dated 18 July 2008) for “implementing and amending Regulation (EC) No. 715/2007” on type-approval of motor vehicles with respect to emissions from light passenger and commercial vehicles (Euro 5 and Euro 6) and on access to vehicle repair and maintenance information”.

The EC Regulation No. 443/2009¹³¹ “*setting emission performance standards for new passenger cars as part of the Community’s integrated approach to reduce CO₂ emissions from light-duty vehicles*” followed and introduced common requirements for emissions from motor vehicles and their specific replacement parts (standards Euro 5 and Euro 6). It also laid down measures, allowing improved access to information on vehicle repairs and promoting the rapid production of vehicles in compliance with the provisions of the Regulation. The Draft Law about the transposition of Directive 2012/27/EC - mentioned in previous sessions - considers this EU regulation for the determination of the national EE targets.

Objectives: The purpose is to limit pollution caused by road vehicles and support emission reduction actions in transport by introducing stricter limits on polluting emissions. These limits are applicable to light road vehicles, particularly for emissions of particles and nitrogen oxides.

Type of policy instrument: Regulatory policy instrument – Technological standards.

Target groups: Manufacturers need to demonstrate the compliance with the Regulation and its implementing measures of: i) all new vehicles (sold, registered or put into service in EC) ; ii) all new replacement pollution control devices requiring type approval (sold or put into service in the EC).

The Regulation covers vehicles¹³² of categories¹³³ M1, M2, N1 and N2, with reference mass not exceeding 2.610 kg¹³⁴. Apart from these vehicles (falling de facto within the scope of the Regulation), manufacturers may request the coverage of vehicles intended for the carriage of passengers or goods with a reference mass of 2.610 kg to 2.840 kg.

In order to limit as much as possible the negative impact of road vehicles on the environment and health, the Regulation covers a wide range of pollutant emissions: carbon monoxide (CO), non-methane hydrocarbons and total hydrocarbons, oxides of nitrogen (NO_x) and particulates (PM). These include emissions of tailpipe, evaporative emissions and crankcase emissions.

Rules and influencing mechanisms:¹³⁵ There are emission limits for each category of pollutant emissions and for the different types of vehicle listed above; these limit values are listed in Annex I of the Regulation (Annex II of this report).

Europe, Volkswagen Group, Volvo Cars, Volvo Group. (Source: <http://www.acea.be/press-releases/article/european-auto-industry-calls-on-europe-to-rebalance-co2-policy-in-the-inter>

¹²⁹ <http://www.yme.gr/index.php?tid=837>

¹³⁰ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32008R0692&from=EN>

¹³¹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EL/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32009R0443>

¹³² passenger vehicles, vans and commercial vehicles intended for the carriage of passengers or goods or certain other specific uses (for example ambulances), provided that the vehicles are equipped with engine-spark ignition (gasoline engines, engines with natural gas or Liquefied Petroleum Gas - LPG) or compression ignition (diesel engines).

¹³³ <http://www.dft.gov.uk/vca/vehicletype/definition-of-vehicle-categories.asp>

¹³⁴ defined in Annex II to Directive 70/156/EEC

¹³⁵ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EL/TXT/?uri=URISERV:l28186>

Since the implementation of Euro 5 and Euro 6, the approval, registration, sale or entry to any service of vehicles which do not comply with these emission limits, must be refused. For goods transport vehicles (category N1 class II and III, and category N2) and vehicles designed to fulfill specific social needs, provided for each additional period of one year. The schedule is as below:

- Euro 5 standard was launched on September 1, 2009 regarding the approval and was implemented on January 1, 2011 regarding the registration and sale of new types of vehicles;
- Euro 6 standard was launched on September 1, 2014 regarding the approval and from September 1, 2015 regarding the registration and sale of new types of vehicles. However, spark ignition engines with direct injection engines benefit from less restrictive thresholds on the number of particles, for an additional period of 3 years.
- Tax incentives granted by Member States to encourage compliance with the new limits will be authorized if:
 - valid for all new vehicles sold in one Member State and fulfill in advance, the requirements of this Regulation;
 - end on the date of the new limits;
 - the amounts do not exceed the additional cost of the technical measures provided to ensure compliance with the values established, and their installation on vehicles.

Non compliance

According to provisions of EC Regulation 715/2007, the Member States shall lay down the provisions on penalties “applicable for infringement by manufacturers” according to their obligations under the Regulation. The respective penalties must be effective, proportionate and dissuasive.

Offences subject to a penalty include: a) making false declarations during the approval procedures or procedures leading to a recall; b) falsifying test results for type approval or in-service conformity; c) withholding data or technical specifications which could lead to recall or withdrawal of type approval; d) use of defeat devices; and e) refusal to provide access to information.

Table 9: History and levels of Euro standards for passenger cars.

Euro standard	Introduction dates		Petrol		Diesel		Petrol & Diesel
	New approvals	All new registrations	NOx (gr/km)	Mass of particles (gr/km)	NOx (gr/km)	Mass of particles (gr/km)	Number of ultra-fine particle per km
Euro 1	1 July 1992	31 December 1992	0,97 ⁽¹⁾	-	0,97 ⁽¹⁾	0,14	
Euro 2	1 January 1996	1 January 1997	0,50 ⁽¹⁾	-	0,90 ⁽¹⁾	0,10	
Euro 3	1 January 2000	1 January 2001	0,15	-	0,50	0,05	
Euro 4	1 January 2005	1 January 2006	0,08	-	0,25	0,025	
Euro 5	1 September 2009	1 January 2011	0,06	0,0045 ⁽²⁾	0,18	0,0045	6 x 10 ¹¹⁽³⁾
Euro 6	1 September 2014	1 September 2015	0,06	0,0045 ⁽²⁾	0,08	0,0045	6 x 10 ¹¹⁽⁴⁾

Note: (1) Expressed as HC+NO_x; (2) Applicable to direct injection engines; (3) Applicable to diesel engines only; (4) Limit of 6x 10¹² in case of direct injection petrol engines - Common limit of 6x10¹¹ for direct injection petrol engines and diesel engines from September 2017/September 2018 (Source: <http://www.acea.be/industry-topics/tag/category/euro-standards>)

Implementation network: Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism.

Outcomes: There were reductions as shown in table 9. For the Hellenic case there are no available data.

1.2.2.2 Establishment of Permanent Committee on Green Transportation

General information: This policy instrument was set in force with Law 3710/2008¹³⁶ (Government Gazette 216 A, 23.10.2008). According to this Law, a nine-member committee is established on issues of "green" transportation. The Committee's task is to propose and implement measures for the promotion of cleaner and more environmentally friendly transport ("green" transportation).

Type: Regulatory policy instrument.

Objectives: Promotion of clean and environmental-friendly transportation ("green transportation").

Target groups: Transport sector (road, rail, navigation, aviation).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: With the decision of the Minister of Transport and Communications (now Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism), the chairman (prestigious expert), the members of the committee and the secretary as well as his/her deputy are appointed.

Implementation network: Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (former Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport and Networks). More details on the Ministries are available in the national report of D.1.1.

Outcomes: No available information.

1.2.2.3 Energy labelling for tyres in transport

General information: There is energy labeling for tyres. The latest EU regulation in force is 1235/2011/EE¹³⁷ which is amending Regulation (EC) No 1222/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council with regard to the wet grip grading of tyres, the measurement of rolling resistance and the verification procedure. Both concern passenger and light professional vehicles. It is in force since November 2012 in Greece (BUY SMART+, 2012).

Objective: The purpose is to increase the safety and the economic and environmental efficiency of road transport by promoting fuel-efficient and safe tyres with low noise levels (Regulation No. 1222/2009¹³⁸).

Type of policy instrument: Regulatory – informative policy instrument (see energy labeling for buildings).

Target groups: Owners of passenger and light professional vehicles.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: The fuel efficiency class must be determined on the basis of the Rolling Resistance Coefficient (RRC) according to the "A" to "G" scale. The difference between the maximum "A" and minimum "G" coefficient corresponds up to 7,5% reduction in fuel consumption. So, if the end-user selects tyres with coefficient "A" instead of those with "G" it may save more than 6 lit of fuel for every 1.000km. Calculations with an average price of gasoline at approximately 1,5

¹³⁶ <https://nomoi.info/%CE%A6%CE%95%CE%9A-%CE%91-216-2008-%CF%83%CE%B5%CE%BB-1.html>

¹³⁷ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32011R1235&from=EN>

¹³⁸ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:342:0046:0058:en:PDF>

EUR, there can be a credit of 300 EUR through the whole life cycle of the tyres¹³⁹. The tyre categories are: C1, C2, C3.

Implementation network: Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (see details at national report of D.1.1).

Outcomes: No available data.

1.2.3 FINANCIAL POLICY INSTRUMENTS

1.2.3.1 Taxation of energy products and electricity (applies for gas oil (diesel), biodiesel and kerosene for transport)

General information: The description of this policy instrument is covered in the previous section for “Building Sector”. The energy products related to taxation are: Leaded & unleaded petrol, avgas, jet fuel, diesel, mazut fuel oil, kerosene, LPG, natural gas for transport, coal, lignite, coke, benzene, white spirit.

Taxation of energy products and electricity was implemented by: Law 4092/2012 (Government Gazette 220 A, 8.11.2012), Law 3986/2011 (Government Gazette 152 A, 1.07.2011), Law 3845/2010 (Government Gazette 65 A, 6.05.2010), Law 3833/2010 (Government Gazette 40 A, 15.3.2010), Law 3828/2010 (Government Gazette 31 A, 25.02.2010), Law 3336/2005 (Government Gazette 96 A, 20.04.2005)¹⁴⁰. These Laws were transposing the EU Directives: 2003/96/EC, 2004/74/EC, 2004/75/EC, 2003/17/EC.

Objectives: Reduction of GHG emissions, promotion of RES, EE.

Type of policy instrument: Financial policy instrument.

Target groups: Road, rail, navigation, aviation.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: Same in previous session for buildings.

Implementation network: Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism.

Outcomes: See previous section for “Building Sector”.

1.2.3.2 Registration tax exemption for electric and hybrid vehicles

General information: This policy instrument was set in force with the following EU Directives/Regulations: EC Regulations 566/2011¹⁴¹, 692/2008¹⁴² and 715/2007¹⁴³ and Directives 1998/69/EC and 1994/12/EC¹⁴⁴.

¹³⁹ The calculations are based on the data for a mean consumption of 8lit/100km, fuel price of 1,5 EUR/lit and an average performance of the tyres of 35.000km (Source: http://www.goodyear.eu/gr_el/goodyear-quality/eu-tire-label/)

¹⁴⁰ https://www.mou.gr/elibrary/N3336_200405_fek96.pdf

¹⁴¹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32011R0566>

¹⁴² <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32008R0692>

¹⁴³ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32007R0715>

¹⁴⁴ http://ec.europa.eu/enterprise/sectors/automotive/documents/directives/motor-vehicles/index_en.htm

The EC Regulation 715/2007 (dated 20 June 2007) establishes common technical requirements for the type approval of motor vehicles and replacement parts with regard to their emissions and lays down rules for in-service conformity, durability of pollution control devices, On-Board Diagnostic (OBD) systems, measurement of fuel consumption and accessibility of vehicle repair and maintenance information. The EC Regulation 692/2008 (dated 18 July 2008) implemented and amended the EC Regulation 715/2007 by setting the requirements for the type-approval of Euro 5 and 6 vehicles. The EC Regulation 566/2011 (dated 8 June 2011) amended EC Regulations 715/2007 and 692/2008 regarding the access to vehicle repair and maintenance information. These Regulations targeted to the vehicle manufacturers.

The Directive 98/69/EC (13 October 1998) and the Directive 94/12/EC (23 March 1994) are related to measures against air pollution by emissions from motor vehicles and amend the Directive 70/220/EEC.

These EU regulations and Directives were transposed into national legislation with: Law 2052/92¹⁴⁵ (Government Gazette 94 A, 05.06.1992), Law 2682/99¹⁴⁶ (Government Gazette 16 A, 08.02.1999), Law 2960/2001¹⁴⁷ "National Customs Code" (Government Gazette 265 A, 22.11.2001), Law 3156/2003¹⁴⁸ (Government Gazette 157 A, 25.06.2003).

Objectives: Promotion of electric and hybrid vehicles.

Type of policy instrument: Financial policy instrument.

Target groups: Vehicle buyers and sellers (road).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: The procedures and the necessary supporting documents for the characterization of the vehicles as antipollution technology vehicles are determined by common decisions of the Minister of Finance, the Minister of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy and the Minister of Infrastructure, Transport and Networks.

The Laws 2960/2001 and 3156/2003 concerned customs provisions. According to the Law 2960/2001, hybrid and electric cars, which have engines with emissions (that comply with the provision of Directive 94/12/EC or newer for antipollution technologies), are exempted from registration taxes for private vehicles. The aforementioned exception was amended by Law 3156/2003 and according its article 27, the electric trucks are also exempted from registration tax.

Implementation network: Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (former Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport and Networks), Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy and Ministry of Finance. More details on the Ministries are available in the national report of D.1.1.

Outcomes: According to statistics provided from ACEA (European Automobile Manufacturers Association), the following table presents the new registrations of passenger electrically charged vehicles¹⁴⁹ in Hellas for the time period 2010-2014:

¹⁴⁵ <http://www.espa.gr/el/pages/elibraryFS.aspx?item=199>

¹⁴⁶ http://www.elinyae.gr/el/item_details.jsp?cat_id=878&item_id=3412

¹⁴⁷ <http://www.enekta.gr/%CE%B4%CE%B9%CE%B1%CF%81%CE%BA%CE%AE%CF%82-%CF%80%CE%BB%CE%B7%CF%81%CE%BF%CF%86%CF%8C%CF%81%CE%B7%CF%83%CE%B7-%CF%85%CF%80%CE%BF%CF%83%CF%84%CE%AE%CF%81%CE%B9%CE%BE%CE%B7/%CE%B5%CE%B8%CE%BD%CE%B9%CE%BA%CF%8C%CF%82-%CF%84%CE%B5%CE%BB%CF%89%CE%BD%CE%B5%CE%B9%CE%B1%CE%BA%CF%8C%CF%82-%CE%BA%CF%8E%CE%B4%CE%B9%CE%BA%CE%B1%CF%82%CE%BD-29602001/>

¹⁴⁸ http://www.dpa.gr/pls/portal/docs/PAGE/APDPX/THEMATIKES_ENOTITES/N%203156_2003.PDF

¹⁴⁹ Total Electrically Charged Vehicles = Pure Electric Vehicles + Extended-Range Electric Vehicles + Plug-In Hybrid Electric Vehicles

Table 10: New registrations of passenger electrically charged vehicles in Hellas for time period 2013-2014¹⁵⁰.

Year	New passenger electrically charged vehicle registrations in Hellas
2013	4
2014	64

(Source: ACEA, 2015)

1.2.3.3 Circulation tax exemption for electric and hybrid vehicles

General information: This policy instrument was set in force with the following EU Directives/Regulations: EC Regulations 715/2007¹⁵¹ (Euro 5-6), Directive 1999/96/EC¹⁵² (Euro 3 and Euro 4), Directive 91/542/EEC¹⁵³ (Euro 2 and Euro 1) (European emission standards).

These Directives and Regulations were transposed into national legislation with: Law 4093/2012¹⁵⁴ (Government Gazette 222 A, 12.11.2012), Law 3986/2011¹⁵⁵ (Government Gazette 152 A, 1.07.2011), Law 3831/2010¹⁵⁶ (Government Gazette 34 A, 25.02.2010), Legislative Act (Government Gazette 181 A, 16.09.2009)¹⁵⁷.

Objectives: Promotion of electric and hybrid vehicles.

Type of policy instrument: Financial policy instrument.

Target groups: Private vehicle owners, taxi drivers (road).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: For vehicles with circulation tax exemption, a special badge of 5 EUR cost is provided. The exemptions are for (Law 3986/2011): i) hybrid cars of private and public use (taxis) with engines over 1929 cc that are registered for the first time in Greece until 31.10.2010 and ii) hybrid motorcycles with engines over 1929 cc. For this second category of exemptions the circulation tax is half of the tax set for the respective conventional ones. iii) electric and hydrogen cars of private and public use that are registered for the first time in Greece before 31.10.2010. iv) electric and hydrogen motorcycles.

Concerning the hybrid cars of private and public use, the electric and hydrogen vehicles that are registered for the first time in Greece after 01.11.2010, the circulation fees are determined based on carbon dioxide emissions depending on whether these are of private or public use. The Law 4093/2012 concerns the circulation taxes from 2013 and later on.

Implementation network: Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (former Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport and Networks), Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy, Ministry of Finance. More details on the Ministries are available in the national report of D.1.1.

Outcomes: The revenues from the circulation taxes for cars are presented in Table 11.

¹⁵⁰http://www.acea.be/uploads/press_releases_files/ACEA_Electric_Vehicle_registrations_Q4_14-13.pdf

¹⁵¹<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32007R0715>

¹⁵²<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2000:044:0001:0155:EN:PDF>

¹⁵³<http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:31991L0542&from=en>

¹⁵⁴<http://www.taxheaven.gr/laws/law/index/law/474>

¹⁵⁵http://www.mnec.gr/sites/default/files/law_files/N.3986.pdf

¹⁵⁶http://www.dsnet.gr/Epikairothta/Nomothesia/n3831_10.htm

¹⁵⁷http://www.dsnet.gr/Epikairothta/Nomothesia/pnp16_9_2009_1_09.htm

Table 11: Revenues from the circulation taxes for cars.

Years	2010	2011	2012	2013
Circulation tax revenues (in million EUR)	1.591	1.117	1.305	1.1183

(Source: Bank of Greece, 2014)

1.2.3.4 Incentives to replace old technology cars and motorcycles (subsidies, tax exemptions)

General information: This policy instrument was set in force with: Law 4316/2014¹⁵⁸ (Government Gazette 270 A, 24.12.2014), Law 4223/2013¹⁵⁹ (Government Gazette 287 A, 31.12.2013), Law 4110/2013¹⁶⁰ (Government Gazette 17 A, 23.01.2013), Law 3943/2011¹⁶¹ (Government Gazette 66 A 31.03.2011), Decision No. 5006718EΞ2001¹⁶² (Government Gazette 246 B, 11.02.2011), Law 3899/2010¹⁶³ (Government Gazette 212 A, 17.12.2010), Legislative Act (Government Gazette 181 A, 16.09.2009)¹⁶⁴, Law 3333/2005 (Government Gazette 91 A, 12.04.2005), Law 3245/2004¹⁶⁵ (Government Gazette 110 A, 16.06.2004), Law 3109/2003¹⁶⁶ (Government Gazette 38 A, 19.02.2003).

Law 3109/2003 concerned the owners of vehicles of public use (taxi) and for supporting the replacement of old cars of public use (mainly taxis), the amount of sixty million (60.000.000) EUR as subsidies was available from the Ministry of Transport and Communications.

Law 3245/2004 concerned incentives for the renewal of circulated two-wheel motorcycles (registration tax exemption) and was amended by Law 3333/2005. The registration taxes were returned to the beneficiaries if they replaced motorcycles registered in Hellas until 1994 or motopeds registered until 1996 with new two-wheel motorcycles or motopeds of new technology. The first should have been withdrawn and destructed. The new two-wheel motorcycles were also exempted from circulation taxes if their engines were of up to 300cc (for over 300 cc, the tax exemption was applied for 5 years). The motopeds of new technology were exempted from all kind of taxes.

Objectives: GHG reduction and promotion of EE in transport sector.

Type of policy instrument: Financial policy instrument.

Target groups: Owners of private- and public-use vehicles, motorcycle owners (road transport).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: Under Law 3109/2003, the subsidies were available for all those that replaced their cars with new ones registered for the first time until 30.04.2004. Also, joint

¹⁵⁸ <https://nomoi.info/%CE%A6%CE%95%CE%9A-%CE%91-270-2014-%CF%83%CE%B5%CE%BB-1.html> or http://www.seedde.gr/sites/default/files/nomoi/%20270%20%CE%91%20%CE%9D%CE%9F%CE%9C%CE%9F%CE%A3%204316_24-12-2014%20%CE%95%CE%9A%CE%A0%CE%A4%CE%A9%CE%A3%CE%97%20%CE%95%CE%9D%CE%A6%CE%99%CE%91%20%CE%93%CE%99%CE%91%20%CE%A4%CE%9F%CE%A5%CE%A1%CE%99%CE%A3%CE%A4%CE%99%CE%9A%CE%91%20%CE%9A%CE%91%CE%A4%CE%91%CE%9B%CE%A5%CE%9C%CE%91%CE%A4%CE%91_L.pdf

¹⁵⁹ <http://www.taxheaven.gr/laws/law/index/law/570>

¹⁶⁰ <http://www.taxheaven.gr/laws/law/index/law/492>

¹⁶¹ <https://nomoi.info/%CE%A6%CE%95%CE%9A-%CE%91-66-2011-%CF%83%CE%B5%CE%BB-1.html> or http://www.mnec.gr/sites/default/files/law_files/document.pdf

¹⁶² <http://hellastax.com/HTML/2011-n/defk-5006718-ex2011.htm>

¹⁶³ <https://nomoi.info/%CE%A6%CE%95%CE%9A-%CE%91-212-2010-%CF%83%CE%B5%CE%BB-1.html> or <http://www.kepea.gr/uplds1/File/ergasiakos3899.pdf>

¹⁶⁴ http://www.dsnet.gr/Epikairothta/Nomothesia/pnp16_9_2009_1_09.htm

¹⁶⁵ http://www.dsnet.gr/Epikairothta/Nomothesia/n3245_04.htm

¹⁶⁶ <https://nomoi.info/%CE%A6%CE%95%CE%9A-%CE%91-38-2003-%CF%83%CE%B5%CE%BB-1.html>

companies with fleet of at least 300 cars with installed automated fleet management system were eligible for subsidy. Under a common decision of the Minister of Finance and the Minister of Transport and Communications, the rules, the requirements, the documentation, the way of determination of beneficiaries and the amount of subsidy were determined. Also, the maximum number of years that those cars could be in circulation was determined¹⁶⁷. Afterwards, they have to be withdrawn and replaced by new ones or used by two years the most.

Under Law 3333/2005, the first year for the non-payment of taxes was considered to be the year of the circulation license issuance of the new motorcycle/motoped. New technology motopedes or motorcycles were considered to be those compliant with Directive 2002/51/EC. The reception of the withdrawn motorcycles/motoped - accompanied by the necessary documentation - was done by the Management Agency of Public Material (ODDY SA), the municipalities and the police stations. They were. Withdrawal and circulation should had been done by 31.12.2009.

Decision No. 5006718EΞ2001 (Government Gazette 246 B, 11.02.2011) concerned: i) procedures of old cars withdrawal and new cars reception and ii) details for implementing Law 3899/2010. More specifically, it included the reception of new cars of private use (up to 2000 cc) as replacement of old technology (circulation license until 31.12.1998). There was registration tax exemption for new cars of private use (up to 2000 cc), compliant with provisions of Directive 98/69/EC, for replacing old ones that were withdrawn and destructed (circulation license until 31.12.1998) (Law 3899/2010). More specifically for cars:

- a) up to 900 cc (taxable value up to 6.000 EUR) - Full registration tax exemption .
- b) from 901 cc to 1400 cc (taxable value up to 8.000 EUR) - Full registration tax exemption , but under Law 3943/2011, tax exemption became 60%.
- c) from 1401 cc to 1600 cc (taxable value up to 11.000 EUR) - Full registration tax exemption but under Law 3943/2011 tax exemption became 60% from 65% under Law 3899/2010.
- d) from 1601 cc to 2000 cc (taxable value up to 14.000 EUR)- 50% registration tax exemption and it remained so under Law 3943/2011
- e) from 2001 cc to 3500 cc - 40% registration tax exemption (included under Law 3943/2011).

The Laws 4110/2013, 4223/2013 and 4316/2014 extended gradually the date for withdrawal of old cars until 20.12.2015. The recent Law gave the opportunity of the replacement of newer cars with registered circulation license until 31.12.2001.

Non compliance

There are no relevant provisions.

Implementation network: Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (former Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport and Networks), Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy (former Ministry of Development), Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Interior and Administrative Reconstruction, Management Agency of Public Material (ODDY SA), police stations. More details on the Ministries are available in the national report of D.1.1.

Outcomes: On 2013, 62.575 cars were withdrawn and were replaced by 46.761 new ones. On 2012, 60.851 cars were withdrawn and were replaced by 37.690 new ones¹⁶⁸.

¹⁶⁷ 10-12 years for Athens, Piraeus, their suburbs and Thessaloniki, while 16 years for other areas

¹⁶⁸ <http://www.kathimerini.gr/506116/article/oikonomia/ellhnikh-oikonomia/se-isxy-kai-to-2014-h-aposyrsh-ews-2800-eyrw-to-ofelos>

1.2.4 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS

1.2.4.1 Consumer information on fuel economy and CO₂ emissions of new passenger cars (eco-labelling for cars)

General information: This policy instrument was set in force with EU Directives/Regulations: Directives 1999/94/EC & 2003/73, Regulations 1882/2003 & 1137/2008.

It was transposed into national legislation with: Ministerial Decision 11762/654¹⁶⁹ (Government Gazette 327 B, 17.03.2006) (transposing Directive 2003/73/EC), Joint Ministerial Decision 90364/2002 “Programme for raising awareness and providing information to consumers on fuel economy and CO₂ emissions in respect of the marketing of new passenger cars” (Government Gazette 110 B, 31.01.2002) (transposing Directive 1999/94/EC).

According to the Joint Ministerial Decision 90364/2002 “Clients information programme about fuel efficiency and CO₂, emissions of new passenger cars”, information on fuel economy and CO₂ emissions need to be available to consumers, regarding the marketing of new passenger cars, so as to make their choices in purchases of new cars fully informed and updated. The Ministerial Decision 11762/654 amended Annex III of the Joint Ministerial Decision 90364/2002 and replaced it with a new one on the description of the post/table/screen at the cars exhibitions concerning the minimum requirements for information.

Objectives: Promotion of energy efficiency and emission reduction in transport sector.

Type of policy instrument: Regulatory, Dissemination and awareness (as eco-labelling in previous section).

Target groups: end – users/car owners, car suppliers.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: The Annex of Article 2 of Ministerial Decision 11762/654 set the following minimum requirements: Minimum dimensions 70cm X 50cm; Readable information; For electronic screen, minimum dimensions 25cm X 32cm (17”) with capability of scrolling; Grouping and listing of passenger cars according to fuel type and consumption, posing the less fuel consuming car at the top of the list; Information on the brand, the numerical value of official fuel consumption in lt/100 km and the numerical value of official CO₂ emissions in gr/km.

Implementation network: Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (former Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport and Networks), Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy (former Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change)¹⁷⁰. There is no clear assignment of responsibilities.

Outcomes: The measure hasn’t worked as anticipated due to the inappropriate promotion of the responsible vehicle sellers at car exhibitions. Nonetheless, many car companies highlight the label with the minimum requirements of the Directive (3rd Hellenic National EE Action Plan, 2014).

1.2.4.2 Eco-driving

General information: This policy instrument was set in force with: Ministerial Decision No. 76568/1197¹⁷¹ (Government Gazette 81 B, 19.01.2015), Ministerial Decision A3/50984/7947¹⁷²

¹⁶⁹ http://www.elinyae.gr/el/lib_file_upload/b327_06.1144056313149.pdf

¹⁷⁰ More details on the Ministries are available in the national report of D.1.1.

¹⁷¹ <http://www.odigostoupoliti.eu/adia-odigisis-ekpedefsi-ke-exetasi-ipopsifion-odigon-motopodilaton-motosikleton-ke-aftokiniton/>

¹⁷² http://drivingschool.gr/nomothesia/upourgikes/ya_a3-50984-7947-2013.pdf

(Government Gazette 3056 B, 02.11.2013, article 19), Ministerial Decision 552/88¹⁷³ (Government Gazette 4 B, 07.01.2013), Law 3855/2010¹⁷⁴ (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.06.2010, article 8), Presidential Decree 74/2008¹⁷⁵ (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.06.2010), Ministerial Decision 72048/9666/08¹⁷⁶ (Government Gazette 216 B, 09.02.2009).

According to the Law 3855/2010 on the measures for the energy efficiency improvement, it was announced that the conditions and the criteria for the implementation of educational programs on the promotion of eco-driving principles to vehicle-drivers of government agencies and the broader public sector, were to be set. There were eco-driving training programs¹⁷⁷ for the drivers of the companies ETHEL SA (thermal buses) and ILPAP S.A. (trolley buses) (now they are merged to "ODIKES SYGKOINONIES S.A."¹⁷⁸ with the distinctive title "OSY"¹⁷⁹).

Under, the Ministerial Decisions A3/50984/7947 and 552/88, the theoretical education for the trainee-drivers includes the eco-driving principles and during the examination procedure for the possession of driving license, the candidate is tested on those principles, such as driving at a constant speed, avoiding unnecessary braking, observation and forecast traffic conditions. The Ministerial Decision No. 76568/1197 amends the aforementioned one. The training procedure for professional drivers (buses, etc.) also includes eco-driving concepts (Ministerial Decision 72048/9666/08).

Objectives: Promotion of EE, familiarization of the public with energy efficient practices.

Type of policy instrument: Dissemination – Awareness – Educational, Regulatory.

Target groups: New drivers, driving license schools, vehicle-drivers of governmental agencies and the broader public sector, professional drivers (road).

Rules and influencing mechanisms: No available information.

Implementation network: Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism (former Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport and Networks), Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy (former MEECC). More details on the Ministries are available in the national report of D.1.1.

Outcomes: No available information.

1.2.4.3 Green Public Procurements for Transport

General information: With Law 3982/2011 (Government Gazette 143 A, 17.06.2011¹⁸⁰), Directive 2009/33/EC¹⁸¹ "on the promotion of clean and energy-efficient road transport vehicles" was transposed into national legislation. One of the provisions of Law 3855/2010 (Government Gazette 95 A, 23.06.2010) that was mentioned in the policy instruments for the "Building sector" of this report concerns the Green Public Procurements for the Public Sector and particularly for the needs in vehicles.

Objectives: Green public procurements in the transport sector aim at: i) promoting and stimulating the market for clean and energy-efficient vehicles and ii) improving the contribution of the transport sector to the environment, climate and energy policies of the Community.

¹⁷³ <http://www.yme.gr/index.php?tid=884>

¹⁷⁴ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=AxgQsUVAUjA%3D&...>

¹⁷⁵ <http://www.yme.gr/index.php?getwhat=1&oid=1453&id=&tid=1590>

¹⁷⁶ <http://www.yme.gr/index.php?tid=1590>

¹⁷⁷ www.yme.gr/getfile.php?id=1730

¹⁷⁸ <http://www.oasa.gr/content.php?id=eo>

¹⁷⁹ <http://www.osy.gr/ethelsite/pages/identity.php>

¹⁸⁰ http://www.startupgreece.gov.gr/sites/default/files/%20CE%91%20143_%CE%9D3982_17062011_1.PDF

¹⁸¹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009L0033&from=EN>

Type of policy instrument: Same as for the case of the GPP in t buildings.

Target groups: The Law requires contracting authorities, contracting entities and certain operators to consider lifetime energy and environmental impacts, including energy consumption and emissions of CO₂ and of certain pollutants, when purchasing road transport vehicles.

It does not cover special purpose vehicles. Exemptions concern: i) vehicles that are designed and constructed for use at construction sites, quarries, port or airport facilities or by the Armed Forces, civil defense, fire service and forces responsible for maintaining public order; ii) mobile machinery for the exempted vehicles.

Rules and influencing mechanisms: Whenever, the target groups proceed with the purchase of vehicles they need to consider the operational lifetime energy and environmental impacts (ie energy consumption, CO₂ emissions, NO_x, NMHC and particulate matter or other environmental impacts in addition to the previous ones). These requirements are fulfilled by: i) setting technical specifications for energy and environmental performance in the documentation for the purchase of road transport vehicles on each of the impacts considered, as well as any additional environmental impacts; ii) including energy and environmental impacts in the purchasing decision. The last option can occur by using these impacts as award criteria or by monetising the impacts so as to be included in the purchasing decision using the methodology for the calculation of operational lifetime costs that is described in the provision of the Law.

Implementation network: As for the case of the buildings.

Outcomes: Greece delayed to implement the Directive compared to other EU Member States. Finally, all options were allowed because the effectiveness was not shown yet and the market should follow it. There were no estimates undertaken of the anticipated impacts of the options nor any assessments were undertaken about the actual application and the impacts of the options (Ricardo-Aea, 2012).

1.2.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

None.

1.2.6 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR IN HELLAS

Summary table: Transport					
	Short list of implemented policies and measures	Objective ¹⁸² (improve system, travel or vehicle efficiency)	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Implementation network
Planning instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cycling and pedestrianism in the city • Improvement of infrastructure for electric vehicles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve transport infrastructure • Support traffic management • Promotion of energy efficient technologies and practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vehicle owners • End-users 	Penalties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Finance; • Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism; • Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy; • Region of Attica; • Municipality of Athens
Regulatory policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emission standards (Euro 5 and 6) • Energy labelling • Establishment of Permanent Committee on Green Transportation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achievement of energy savings; • reduction of GHG emissions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manufacturers • Owners of passenger and light professional vehicles 	Tax exemptions, Penalties	Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism
Financial policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taxation on energy products and electricity, • Registration and Circulation tax 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Achievement of energy savings; • reduction of 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vehicle owners • Road, rail, navigation, 	Not mentioned	Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism

¹⁸² Energy efficiency in the transport sector can be divided into system efficiency (reduce or avoid travel or the need to travel), travel efficiency (shift to more energy efficient modes) and vehicle efficiency (improve the efficiency through vehicle technology).

	exemption for electric and hybrid vehicles; <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incentives to replace old technology cars and motorcycles (subsidies, tax exemptions) 	GHG emissions	aviation sub-sectors		
Dissemination and awareness instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consumer information fuel economy and CO₂ emissions of new passenger cars • Eco-driving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promotion of energy efficiency; • familiarization of the public with energy efficient practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • End users/drivers; • Car suppliers • Driving license schools • Vehicle drivers of governmental agencies and the broader public sector, professional drivers 	No available information	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Economy, Infrastructure, Shipping and Tourism • Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy
	Green Public Procurement	Promotion of EE		Not mentioned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Public sector</u> • Local authorities
Policy instruments for Research and Development	None	-	-	-	-

2. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE REGIONAL / LOCAL LEVEL

The interaction between the different levels (national, regional, local) in energy efficiency policy making has already been covered in D.1.1. Next to national energy efficiency policies, many regions and cities have implemented own climate action plans, energy efficiency action plans, or are part of the Covenant of Mayors. Describing all existing policy instruments or energy efficiency measures, would be too much and is not possible in the framework of this project. Therefore, in this deliverable, specific policy instruments on the regional / local level are exemplarily covered by a case study.

2.1 PRESENTATION OF THE CASE STUDY FOR THE MUNICIPALITY OF ILIOUPOLIS

Selection of the municipality

The municipality of Ilioupolis, Attica – Hellas was selected because of:

- its participation in the European initiative of Covenant of Mayors. It is an early participation since: The Covenant of Mayors¹⁸³ was launched in 2008, while thirteen (13) Greek municipalities submitted two years later in 2010 their Sustainable Energy Action Plan (SEAP); no one in 2011 and sixteen (16) in 2012¹⁸⁴.
- its Sustainable Energy Action Plan (SEAP) is now accepted and monitored. It is one of the 77 submitted SEAPs and one of the 45 SEAPs that are accepted¹⁸⁵. One out of the four that are monitored.
- its “benchmark” activities on energy efficiency (mainly in the building sector). This is mentioned at the web-site of the Covenant of Mayors¹⁸⁶;
- the questionnaire survey on the behavior of citizens towards energy consumption in the residential and tertiary sector. This survey was included in the SEAP of Ilioupolis.
- its location (part of the metropolitan area of Athens). This proximity would facilitate cooperation between the municipality and the NKUA-KEPA¹⁸⁷ (facilitation of visit exchanges, less time to move from one place to another);
- the availability of information compared to other SEAPs in which the NKUA-KEPA team looked into.

Brief description of the SEAP

Ilioupolis is a suburban municipality that is located southeast of Athens. It is part of the metropolitan area of Athens. According to the Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT), the actual population of the municipality is 75.904 inhabitants (2011 census) and its area is 1.299 hectares (SEAP Ilioupolis, 2012).

¹⁸³ http://www.covenantofmayors.eu/about/covenant-of-mayors_en.html

¹⁸⁴ http://www.covenantofmayors.eu/actions/sustainable-energy-action-plans_en.html?city=&country_seap=gr&co2=&date_of_approval=&accepted=&start=2

¹⁸⁵ http://www.covenantofmayors.eu/actions/sustainable-energy-action-plans_en.html?city=Search+for+a+Sustainable+Energy+Action+Plan...&country_seap=gr&co2=&date_of_approval=&accepted=1

¹⁸⁶ http://www.simfonodimarxon.eu/about/covenant-supporters_el.html?structure_id=263&benchmarks=284

¹⁸⁷ NKUA-KEPA or UoA-KEPA ist he abbreviation fort he HERON Coordinator

Figure 1: Location of the municipality of Ilioupolis (source: Google maps).

The Municipality of Ilioupolis has signed the Covenant of Mayors on 28 April 2011, with the aim to introduce sustainable energy policies at the local community level. On 30 October 2012, the municipality submitted its own Sustainable Energy Action Plan which was, then accepted. The CO₂ emission reduction target was set at 20,36% (78.759 tons of CO₂) by year 2020, compared to the reference annual value 386.796 tons (2009) (SEAP Ilioupolis, 2012).

For this reason, the relevant SEAP includes energy efficiency and RES measures in the various sectors within the limits of the municipality. More specifically:

Table 12: EE and RES measures for the Municipality of Ilioupoli.

Sector	Mitigation policy	Measures	Sectoral targets by 2020
Public (buildings, fleet, open areas)	Energy savings and efficiency	Energy certification, upgrading, installation of BEMS, green roofs in buildings; Information and awareness-raising of users (employees & citizens); Use of low-energy bulbs in municipal lighting; Installation of LED & management systems for road lighting; Implementation of energy criteria in public procurements; Fuel switch to alternative fuels for municipal fleet; Training in eco-driving.	38% CO ₂ emission reduction
	RES	Promotion of renewable energy, mainly photovoltaics, geothermal energy and biomass; Information campaigns on RES and the national programme "PV on roofs".	17% RES electricity consumption
Residential & Tertiary	Energy savings and efficiency	Information and awareness-raising campaigns; Distribution of energy-saving lamps; Promotion campaigns for national programmes "EXOIKONOMO KAT' OIKON" & "BUILDING THE FUTURE".	18% CO ₂ emission reduction
Transport/ Mobility	Energy savings and efficiency	Information campaigns on energy efficiency in transport; Development of Urban Mobility Study; Promotion of Eco-driving.	23% CO ₂ emission reduction

Source: SEAP Ilioupolis, 2012

The budget for the aforementioned interventions is estimated at 19.908.585,25 EUR. The municipality raises funds from national and European funding programmes and from own sources (SEAP Ilioupolis, 2012).

Building sector (public, residential, tertiary)

The SEAP includes the actions presented in Table 13. The selected measure of the building sector is the **"Energy efficiency interventions through participation in the programme "SAVE" (EXOIKONOMO) 2009-2015"** for the municipal buildings (including schools).

General Information: The Municipality of Ilioupolis prepared an integrated action plan in the framework of programme "SAVE". Under Decision No. ΦB1/E5.5/9479/440/12 of Ministry of Reconstruction of Production, Environment and Energy (former MEECC), the Municipality of Ilioupolis participated in the programme "SAVE" and received funding by 70% for EE interventions in existing municipal buildings, fleet and open areas (total budget 993.136,73€)¹⁸⁸.

¹⁸⁸<https://www.google.gr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&source=web&cd=1&ved=0CB8QFjAAahUKEwiBh5qZnabHAhVFPRoKHenBAxQ&url=http%3A%2F%2Fwww.ilioupoli.gr%2FLibraries%2Fdocuments%2FDrasiDimou2013.sflb.ashx&ei=HKTMYGJKcX6aOmDj6AB&usg=AFQjCNHwuZJiOqN07v6STIUafGGz-qFhA&cad=rja>

Table 13: SEAP actions for the building sector of the Ilioupolis municipality.

Sub-sector	Measure	Expected energy savings
Municipal buildings, including schools	Energy inspection, certification and study for EE interventions in 75 buildings.	-
	EE interventions - participation in programme "SAVE" (EXOIKONOMO) 2009-2015.	2.148.845 kWh/year
	EE interventions in 101 buildings, such as: fuel switch (oil to natural gas boilers, thermal insulation, installation of low-energy lighting systems & solar thermal systems, etc.	Electricity: 586.685 kWh/year Thermal energy: 2.000.664 kWh/year
	Installation of Building Energy Management Systems (BEMS) and energy meters; Upgrade of air-conditioning system in city hall.	347.058 kWh/year
	Installation of electricity and thermal energy meters in 100 buildings; Tele-metering and development of energy consumption database.	250.549 kWh/year
	Installation of green roofs in 3 schools and the municipal swimming pool participation in Operational Programme "Environment & Sustainable Development".	7.186 kWh/year
	Awareness-raising campaigns for the promotion of EE in municipal buildings.	Electricity: 3.600.000 kWh/year Thermal energy: 3.600.000 kWh/year
	Information on Green procurements for the municipal personnel and networking with other municipalities.	-
Residential and Tertiary	Use of environmental standards for energy-consuming products.	91.900 kWh/year
	Creation of forum with the participation of municipal actors with aim to inform the citizens on the activities of the municipality in the framework of Covenant of Mayors (awareness-raising).	-
	Information campaigns for the replacement of high energy-consuming lamps and distribution of at least 12.000 low-energy lamps.	720.000 kWh/year
	Information campaigns and promotion of the programmes "EE at Household buildings" (with target 1000 households) and "Building the Future".	-
Residential	Exploration of the possibilities for rewarding within the national legal framework (overcoming certain non-technical barriers).	-
	Information campaigns (brochures, posters, guides) on energy efficiency solutions and behavioral change on energy consumption.	Electricity: 10.368.000 kWh/year Thermal energy: 41.472.000 kWh/year
Tertiary	Information campaigns (brochures, posters, guides) on energy efficiency solutions and behavioral change on energy consumption.	Electricity: 8.400.000 kWh/year Thermal energy: 2.400.000 kWh/year

(Source: SEAP Ilioupolis, 2012)

The relevant EE interventions in the building sector include: Replacement of boilers, Thermal insulation, Replacement of exterior windows, Upgrade of heating systems, Installation of brightness sensors, Green roof on municipal swimming pool, Information campaigns on EE.

The selected buildings are those with low thermal insulation and energy inefficient electromechanical systems.

Type: Financial

Objectives: Energy savings in public sector (municipal buildings and fleet, open areas)

Target Groups: Municipal buildings such as swimming pool, public schools

Outcomes: -

Transport (public, private)

Concerning the transport sector, the SEAP includes the actions presented in Table 14.

The selected measure of the transport sector is the ***“Training programmes and material on eco-driving for the municipal servants (drivers)”***.

General Information: The implementation period was set at 2013-2020. The municipality proceeds to the implementation of eco-driving rules (applying principles for energy efficient driving), the training of the relevant municipal personnel and the creation of promotional and informative material on the eco-driving techniques, such as proper use of gearbox, avoiding excess weight, etc. (SEAP Ilioupolis, 2012).

For this purpose, there were three (3) eco-driving seminars. The following material was prepared:

- Educational material (6-page brochures) for "eco-driving" seminars
- Posters and notices about three (3) "eco-driving" seminars and distribution at selected points
- 3-folded page brochures for the Technical Department

Type: Dissemination - Awareness

Objectives: Energy savings in transport

Target Groups: Municipal drivers and servants (mobility office, maintenance service, technical department)

Outcomes: -

Table 14: SEAP actions for the transport sector of the Ilioupolis municipality.

Sub-sector	Measure	Expected outcome		
Municipal fleet	Conversion of diesel vehicles with the use of bio-diesel mix (18 heavy trucks).	65.016 kWh/year		
	Replacement of 10 heavy trucks (diesel) to others with natural gas engines after the end of their lifetime.	-		
	Training programmes and material on eco-driving for the municipal servants (drivers).	Diesel:	231.301	kWh/year
		Gasoline:	22.283	kWh/year
	Improvement of the fleet management	Diesel:	266.000	kWh/year
Gasoline:		26.348	kWh/year	
	Replacement of 18 gasoline vehicles with hybrid or electric ones after the end of their lifetime.	-		
Vehicles of public & private use	Information and awareness-raising campaigns on alternative fuels and energy efficiency in transport.	Diesel:	4.536.000	
		Gasoline:	4.752.000	
	Development of urban mobility plan and implementation of the relevant actions (such as pedestrian and cycling zones, promotion of public transport).	Gasoline:	788.591.396	
	Supplementary infrastructure to the extension of metro (such as pedestrian and cycling zones, municipal transport).	Gasoline:	8.157.430	
	Promotion of biofuels in the framework of the national policy (target of 6,5% biodiesel mix) and Directives 2009/28/EC & 2009/30/EC.	-		

Interaction between national and local policies

Under the EXOIKONOMO the two levels of the Hellenic multi-level governance cooperated sufficiently leading to concrete outcomes. The pertinent Ministry organized the conditions under which the municipalities were allowed to participate in the EXOIKONOMO programme. On the other hand, the municipalities had to be aware of the energy efficient needs of their area, design their EE actions and be in a position to monitor them so as to have the necessary outcomes. The key factor in implementing the EE actions was the involvement of the citizens. Simultaneously, the Municipality managed to create cooperation bonds with the Municipality of Macarena (Spain) through the project “Green Twinning”¹⁸⁹.

Entities in the national and the local level managed to interact positively in achieving their *objectives* which coincided (reduction of energy consumption and of GHG emissions) so as to contribute at the: i) national target and ii) the SEAP’s target.

¹⁸⁹ http://green-twinning.eu/wp-content/uploads/2013/06/Ilioupoli_Public-Awareness-Campaign.pdf

One year after the interventions that improved the energy efficiency of the natatorium of the municipality the results were: 201tn avoided CO₂ emissions, saved cost of 81.000 EUR that allowed a 20% reduction in the subscription of the natatorium members and energy savings of 1.026 MWh (SIEMENS, 2014; Municipality of Ilioupolis, 2013).

Two years later, under EXOIKONOMO and for the Priority Axis "Infrastructures of the Municipality", the coverage of the pool at the Natatorium of the Ilioupolis municipality resulted to: annual energy savings of 1.900MWh (percentage of 42%), with energy saving cost 46,96 KWh/Euro (Zarkadoulia M., 2015). The payback period was 5-6 months and the total cost of this intervention was 62.238 EUR (Zarkadoulia M., 2015).

Interaction for *target groups* was also positive since the Ilioupolis municipality due to closer proximity had more opportunities to organize successful awareness campaigns and engage the end-users actively. More specifically, the municipality of Ilioupolis undertook fourteen (14) organisational informational and educational public awareness actions (GREEN-TWINNING, 2013). These were: Internet communication channels, a Public Campaign named "Bike day", Travelling school exhibitions, Energy efficiency seminars, Printed material (production and distribution), A local market campaign named "Business Meetings", local forum named " Energy Savings and Environmental Protection", public campaign named "Energy Days", Information kiosks, Energy savings competitions (GREEN-TWINNING, 2013).

Under the *implementation network* all entities seem to have cooperated well (Ministry and local authority). The Ilioupolis municipality has concluded in a SEAP that was manageable for their resources (skills of technical staff, financial resources, citizens' awareness).

An important factor is the monitoring procedures that the municipality has planned and adopted. These are described in the SEAP. For each action there are indexes that will be used for evaluation of the progress. This activity is conducted by the municipality services. An Energy Office under the supervision of the municipality is foreseen.

The municipality was receiving the needed funds from the Ministry. The MEECC approved for the project "*Green roof at the 7th Primary School of the Municipality*" the amount of 234.944,69 EUR¹⁹⁰.

Using again the financial resources of EXOIKONOMO, but for another policy instrument and for the transport sector this time, the Ilioupolis municipality promoted the eco-driving. Municipal professional drivers, municipal employees and engineers, teachers and general public were encouraged to be familiarized with eco-driving principles. The estimated cost was 20.080 EUR for 3 "eco-driving" seminars (GREEN-TWINNING, 2013).

Discussion/Recommendations (barriers, benefits, recommendations for improvement, etc.)

In order to implement successfully the SEAP actions, the Municipality of Ilioupolis developed a Public Awareness Plan. Also, it participated in the Intelligent Energy Europe project "Green Twinning" and in the framework of this project, the Public Awareness Plan was elaborated. For this purpose, a questionnaire survey was carried out on the energy behavior of the end users in the residential and tertiary sector¹⁹¹ (GREEN-TWINNING, 2013). The survey outcomes showed that citizens and companies of the Municipality are aware of EE and zero cost measures that lead to considerable financial savings on their energy bills. However, they consider that the application of these measures (in the meaning of energy behaviour) is deficient. This indicates that more efforts for improvement can be exerted in relation to energy savings and the CO₂ abatement potential (GREEN-TWINNING, 2013).

¹⁹⁰ <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=lqGsD2Wrxds%3D&tabid=785&language=el-GR>

¹⁹¹ http://green-twinning.eu/wp-content/uploads/2013/06/Ilioupoli_Public-Awareness-Campaign.pdf

The citizens and the professionals of the Municipality of Ilioupolis show generally positive attitude towards the implementation of EE actions, mainly motivated by the potential reduction of operating expenses of their buildings. It is expected that there will be reluctance towards the medium- and high-cost investments on EE interventions, due to the economic recession. The survey concluded that, in a greater extent compared to the residential sector, the tertiary sector requires energy efficiency actions that should be linked with financial incentives, particularly for medium- and high cost investments (SEAP Ilioupolis, 2012). For the aforementioned reasons, in the SEAP the Municipality highlighted its efforts to promote and inform the citizens and professional especially about zero and low cost energy efficiency solutions.

Since the outcomes of the monitoring procedure are not yet available, there are no further recommendations.

Further Information

Further available information on the case of Ilioupolis can be found in the following links:

<http://www.ilioupoli.gr/index.aspx>

http://www.covenantofmayors.eu/about/signatories_en.html?city_id=2772&overview

The contact person for the monitoring of the SEAP of Ilioupolis is:

Mrs. Harikleia CHRISTOFILAKI, Head of Department of Programming and European Programmes

Address: Municipality of Ilioupolis, Sof. Venizelou & Protopappa str., 16310 Ilioupolis, Attica – Greece

Tel.: (+30) 210 9970164, 210 9970000

Fax: (+30) 210 9945848

E - Mail: info@ilioupoli.gr

ANNEX I

Justification for the type of policy instrument for GPP

PPP as a generic term has been used to describe structures that facilitate the participation of the private sector in the provision of public infrastructure and services (IISD, 2011). Its definition is continuously changing since it responds to institutional, legal, investment and public procurement setting of different jurisdictions, and refers to the contextual nature of individual agreements (IISD, 2011). This justifies why there is neither a common PPP definition nor a specific model implemented in Europe (European Policy Centre, 2012). They present different forms and have different characteristics according to country and sector (European Policy Centre, 2012).

However, PPPs are considered as a policy instrument that is similar to negotiated agreements, voluntary commitments because they bring government agencies and businesses together (Steurer R. et al., 2012). In many cases they can serve as an appropriate instrument for the realization of public investments (Centrum für Europäische, 2010). They are structured around a public contract or as work or service concessions which are subject to the provisions of the public procurement directives¹⁹² if their value exceeds the EU Community thresholds¹⁹³ (Commission of the European Communities, 2009 - COM(2009) 615 final). The use of GPP in the EU has been encouraged by the Commission since its 2003 Communication on Integrated Product Policy (Ricardo-Aea, 2012). After extensive modifications in 2004, the public procurement Directives introduced the use of environmental criteria in public procurement since this practice was clarified from the legal perspective (Ricardo-Aea, 2012). So, EU public procurement legislation provided for a range of procedures that contracting authorities can employ when awarding contracts (Commission of the European Communities, 2009 - COM(2009) 615 final).

In this context, GPP is a voluntary policy instrument, since Member States and public authorities can determine individually the extent to which they implement it. It can be applied to contracts both above and below the threshold for application of the EU Procurement Directives (BIO Intelligence Service, 2013; European Commission and ICLEI – Local governments for Sustainability, 2011).

¹⁹² EU legislation makes a clear distinction between two types of PPP: i) The concession model and the ii) public procurement model (European Policy Centre, 2012).

¹⁹³ For public contracts or works concessions below the thresholds, Treaty principles apply (transparency, equal treatment, non-discrimination).

ANNEX II

Emission limits for Euro 5 and Euro 6

Standard Euro 5	Standard Euro 6
<p>Emissions from diesel vehicles:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon monoxide: 500 mg / km • particulates: 5 mg / km (ie reduction of emissions by 80% compared to the standard Euro 4) • Nitrogen oxides (NOx): 180 mg / km (ie reducing emissions by more than 20% compared to the standard Euro 4) • combined emissions of hydrocarbons and nitrogen oxides: 230 mg / km. <p>Emissions from petrol vehicles or those running on natural gas or LPG:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Carbon monoxide: 1.000 mg / km • non-methane hydrocarbons: 68 mg / km • total hydrocarbons: 100 mg / km • Nitrogen oxides (NOx): 60 mg / km (ie 25% reduction in emissions compared to the standard Euro 4) • Particles (only for petrol vehicles with direct-injection lean burn mode): 5 mg / km (introduction of a limit that did not exist in the standard Euro 4). <p>Regarding vans and other light commercial vehicles intended for goods transport, the Regulation includes three categories of emission limits, depending on the vehicle reference mass below 1.305 kg, from 1.305kg to 1.760kg, more than 1.760kg.</p> <p>The limits applicable to the last three categories also apply to goods transport vehicles (category N2).</p>	<p>For all vehicles equipped with a diesel engine will be required to substantially reduce emissions of nitrogen oxides from the entry into force of the standard Euro 6.</p> <p>For example, emissions from cars and other vehicles intended for transport to apply maximum limit of 80 mg / km (i.e. additional reduction by more than 50% compared to the standard Euro 5).</p> <p>The combined emissions of hydrocarbons and nitrogen oxides from diesel vehicles will also be reduced so as to be capped, eg 170 mg / km for passenger cars and other vehicles.</p>

Source: EC 715/2007¹⁹⁴

¹⁹⁴ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EL/TXT/?uri=URISERV:l28186>

REFERENCES

Bank of Greece, 2014. The report of the Director for year 2013. Available at: <http://www.bankofgreece.gr/BogEkdoseis/ekthdkth2013.pdf> (Accessed: August 2015).

Benigna Boza – Kiss, Sergi Moles – Grueso & Ksenia Petrichenko, 2013. Handbook of Sustainable Building Policies. Composing Building Blocks. Eds: Tatiana de Feraudy, Tess Cieus. United Nations Environment Programme. Available at: <http://www.unep.org/sustainablebuildingpolicies/pdfs/SPoD-Handbook%20final-Full.pdf> (Accessed: August 2015).

BIO Intelligence Service (2013), Implications of the new Energy Labelling Directive (2010/30/EU) and the Ecodesign of energy-related products (Ecodesign) Directive (2009/125/EC) on market surveillance activities, ATLETE II: Second Work Package prepared for. ADEME. Available at: <http://www.atlete.eu/2/doc/Report%20on%20implementation%20and%20national%20legislation> (Accessed: August 2015).

BUY SMART+, 2012. Green Public Procurements in Europe – Contracts and Climate Protection – Guide for Contracts about vehicles. Available at: http://www.buy-smart.info/media/file/2371.%CE%9F%CE%94%CE%97%CE%93%CE%9F%CE%A3_Buy_Smart+_%CE%B3%CE%B9_%CE%B1_%CE%BF%CF%87%CE%AE%CE%BC%CE%B1%CF%84%CE%B1.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

Buildings Performance institute Europe (BPIE), 2014. Energy performance Certificates Across the EU – A mapping of national approaches. Authors: Aleksandra Arcipowska (lead author), Filippos Anagnostopoulos, Francesco Mariottini, Sara Kunkel. Available at: http://bpie.eu/uploads/lib/document/attachment/81/BPIE_Energy_Performance_Certificates_EU_mapping_-_2014.pdf (Accessed: August 2015)

Centre for European Policy Studies and the College of Europe, 2012. The uptake of Green Public Procurement in the EU27. Submitted to the European Commission – DG Environment. Authors: Andrea Renda, Jacques Pelkmans, Christian Egenhofer, Lorna Schrefler, Giacomo Luchetta, Can Selçuki (CEPS), Jesus Ballesteros, Anne-Claire Zirnhelt. Available at: <http://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/pdf/CEPS-CoE-GPP%20MAIN%20REPORT.pdf> (Accessed: August 2015).

Centrum für Europäische, 2010. EU Communication – Developing Public Private Partnerships. Available at: http://www.cep.eu/Analysen_KOM/KOM_2009_615_Oeffentlich-private_Partnerschaften/cepPolicyBrief_KOM_2009_615_PPP.pdf (Accessed: August 2015)

Commission of the European Communities, 2009. Communication from the Commission to the European parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions – Mobilizing private and public investment for recovery and long term structural change: developing Public Private Partnerships, Brussels 19.11.2009, COM(2009) 615 final. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/economy_finance/events/2010/20101213-epcc/com_2009_615_en.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

CORPUS, 2011. Energy performance certificates of buildings. Author: David McKinnon. Available at: <http://www.scp-knowledge.eu/sites/default/files/McKinnon%202011%20Energy%20performance%20certificates%20of%20buildings.pdf> (Accessed: August 2015)

CRES, 2013. Energy labeling of air-conditioning devices. Available at: <http://www.come-on-labels.eu/download/training-manual-on-the-new-energy-labelling-of-air-conditioning-systems-in-greek-language-published> (Available in Greek language) (Accessed: August 2015)

CRES, 2011. Implementation of EPBD in Greece. Status in November 2010. Authors: Markogiannakis G., Giannakidis G., Lampropoulou L. Available at: http://www.epbd-ca.org/Medias/Pdf/country_reports_14-04-2011/Greece.pdf

Energy Agency of Aegean, 2011. Electric cars. Author: George Emmanouilidis. Available at: http://www.aegean-energy.gr/gr/academy2013/pdf/AEA_electric_cars.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

European Commission and European Investment Bank, 2014. Ex-ante assessment methodology for financial instruments in the 2014-2020 programming period – Financial instruments for urban and territorial development, Volume V. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy/sources/thefunds/fin_inst/pdf/ex_ante_vol5.pdf (Assessed: August 2015).

European Commission and ICLEI – Local governments for Sustainability, 2011. Buying green! A handbook on green public procurement, 2nd edition. ISBN: 978-92-79-19930-1, doi: 10.2779/74936. Available at: <http://ec.europa.eu/environment/gpp/pdf/handbook.pdf> (Accessed: August 2015)

European Commission, 2013a. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council - Implementing the Energy Efficiency Directive – Commission Guidance, COM(2013) 762 final. Available at: http://www.nezeh.eu/assets/media/PDF/EED_CommunicationEC47.pdf (Accessed: August 2015)

European Commission, 2013b. Commission Staff Working Document - Guidance note on Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency, amending Directives 2009/125/EC and 2010/30/EC, and repealing Directives 2004/8/EC and 2006/32/EC - Article 8: Energy audits and energy management systems. SWD(2013) 447 final. Available at: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52013SC0447&from=EN> (Accessed: July 2015).

European Commission, 2013c. EMAS and energy management. Available at: http://ec.europa.eu/environment/emas/pdf/factsheet/EMAS_Energy_Management.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

European Commission, 2012. Ecodesign your future - How Ecodesign can help the environment by making products smarter. Available at: http://www.google.gr/url?sa=t&rct=j&q=&esrc=s&frm=1&source=web&cd=1&ved=0CCQQFjAAahUKEwjmi8m6s5rHAhXMuhQKHS2LDyo&url=http%3A%2F%2Fec.europa.eu%2FDocsRoom%2Fdocuments%2F5187%2Fattachments%2F1%2Ftranslations%2Fen%2Frenditions%2Fnative&ei=13DGVabEFsz1Uq2WvtAC&usq=AFQjCNFy8B_3wIHVka6iP6PelsZQQ_YHXQ (Accessed: August 2015).

European Commission – Directorate General for Energy and Transport, 2009. Transport Traffic management for Land transport - Research to increase the capacity, efficiency, sustainability and safety of road, rail and urban transport networks. Available at: http://www.transport-research.info/Upload/Documents/200909/20090915_180031_11989_TRKC%20Traffic%20Management%20for%20Land%20Transport.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

European Council of Real Estate Professions, 2013. A Guide to the Energy Efficiency Directive. Available at: <http://www.cepi-cei.eu/index.php?mact=Profile,cntnt01,downloadfile,0&cntnt01returnid=400&cntnt01uid=5213258e1b6cd&cntnt01showtemplate=false&hl=fr> (Accessed: August 2015)

European Policy Centre, 2012. Can Public Private Partnerships (PPPs) lever investment to get Europe out of economic crisis? EPC ISSUE PAPER NO.71. Authors: Claire Dhéret, Hans Martens and Fabian Zuleeg. Final report of a European Policy Centre (EPC) project with support from the European Investment Bank (EIB) Available at: http://www.epc.eu/documents/uploads/pub_3066_can_public_private_partnerships_lever_investment_to_get_europe_out_of_economic_crisis.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

Foundation for Economic and Industrial Research, 2012. The equation for the spectral tax on consumption for oil used in heating and mobility. Authors: karavitis Nikos, Maniatis Giorgos and Dandtsev Svetoslav. Available at <http://www.seepe.gr/site/files/%CE%9C%CE%B5%CE%BB%CE%AD%CF%84%CE%B7%20%CE%99%CE%9F%CE%92%CE%95%20%CE%B3%CE%B9%CE%B1%20%CE%B5%CE%BE%CE%AF%CF%83%CF%89%CF%83%CE%B7%20%CE%95%CE%A6%CE%9A.pdf> (Accessed: August 2015).

Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research, 2009. Survey of Compliance Directive 92/75/EEC (Energy Labelling), Final Report for the European Commission, Directorate-General Energy and Transport - Project Reference No. TREN/D3/238-2006, OJEU 2007/S 124-150987 of 30/06/2007. Available at: http://www.eceee.org/ecodesign/Energy_labelling_directive/Report_energy_labelling (Accessed: August 2015).

GREEN-TWINNING, 2013. Available at: http://green-twinning.eu/wp-content/uploads/2013/06/Ilioupoli_Public-Awareness-Campaign.pdf

Hellenic Parliament, 2013. Report of the Special Permanent Committee for the Protection of the Environment – Period 15, First Meeting. Available at: <http://www.hellenicparliament.gr/UserFiles/510129c4-d278-40e7-8009-e77fc230adef/%CE%95%CE%9A%CE%98%CE%95%CE%A3%CE%97%20%CE%95%CE%A0%CE%99%CE%A4%CE%A1%CE%9F%CE%A0%CE%97%CE%A3%20%CE%A0%CE%95%CE%A1%CE%99%CE%92%CE%91%CE%9B%CE%9B%CE%9F%CE%9D%CE%A4%CE%9F%CE%A3.pdf> (Available in Greek language)(Accessed: August 2015).

Hellenic Republic, Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change, 2010. Special Service of Energy Auditors – Implementation of KENAK, 4.10.2010. Available at: https://www.buildingcert.gr/nomiko_plaisio/egkyklios_kenak_1.pdf (Accessed: August 2015)

Hellenic Republic, Special Service of the Energy Auditors of the MEECC. Frequently Asked Questions for EPCs. Available at: <http://www.ypeka.gr/LinkClick.aspx?fileticket=e6ZYgIszjc8%3D&tabid=340> (Accessed: August 2015). (Date was not mentioned)

International Institute for Sustainable Development, 2011. Policy Brief – Sustainable Development: Is there a role for public-private partnerships? A summary of an IISD preliminary investigation. Authors: Samuel Colverson and Oshani Perera. Available at: http://www.iisd.org/pdf/2011/sust_markets_PB_PPP.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

Markandya Anil, Labandeira Xavier, Ramos Ana, 2014. Policy Instruments to Foster Energy Efficiency. Economics for Energy – Working Paper 01/2014. Available at: <http://eforenergy.org/docpublicaciones/documentos-de-trabajo/WP01-2014.pdf> (Accessed: August 2015).

Municipality of Ilioupolis, 2013. The activity of the municipality. Available at: <http://www.ilioupoli.gr/Libraries/documents/DrasiDimou2013.sflb.ashx>, available in Greek language. (Accessed: August 2015).

Research Institute of Applied Economics (IREA), 2012. Policy options for the promotion of electric vehicles: a review. Working paper. Authors: Jordi Perdiguer and Juan Luis Jiménez. Available at: http://www.ub.edu/irea/working_papers/2012/201208.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

Ricardo-Aea, 2012. Monitoring Report of the Directive 2009/33/EC on the promotion of clean and energy efficient road transport vehicles – Final Report. Authors: Charlotte Brannigan, James Harries, Agnieszka Griffin (Ricardo-AEA) and Ian Skinner (TEPR). Available at: <http://ec.europa.eu/transport/themes/urban/studies/doc/2012-monitoring-report.pdf> (Accessed: August 2015).

SEAP Ilioupolis, 2012. “Sustainable Energy Action Plan of the municipality of Ilioupolis”. Available at: http://www.covenantofmayors.eu/about/signatories_en.html?city_id=2772&seap. (Accessed: August 2015).

SIEMENS, 2014. Upgrading the Presenter: Boultaidakis <http://www.ashrae.gr/perch/resources/presentation07boultaidakis.pdf>

Skinner Ian, Essen van Huib, Smokers Richard, Hill Nikolas, 2010. EU Transport GHG: Routest to 2050? Towards the decarbonisation of the EU's transport sector by 2050. Available at: <http://www.eutransportghg2050.eu/cms/assets/EU-Transport-GHG-2050-Final-Report-22-06-10.pdf> (Accessed: August 2015).

Steurer R., Margula S. & Martinuzzi A., 2012. Public Policies on CSR in Europe: Themes, Instruments, and Regional Differences, in: Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management, 19, 206-227. Available at: https://www.wiso.boku.ac.at/fileadmin/data/H03000/H73000/H73200/InFER_Discussion_Papers/InFER_DP_1_2_2_Regional_differences.pdf (Accessed: July 2015)

Third Hellenic National Energy Efficiency Action Plan, 2014. – Pursuant to Article 24(2) of Directive 2012/27/EU. Prepared by the Centre for Renewable Energy Sources in Athens, December 2014. (Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/EL_NEEAP_en%20version.pdf). Accessed on August 2015.

Transport Research and Innovation Portal (TRIP), 2013. Innovation in urban mobility – Policy making and planning. The TRIP consortium prepared this report on behalf of the European Commission's Directorate-General for Mobility and Transport (DG MOVE) the report. Available at: <http://www.transport->

research.info/Upload/Documents/201304/20130417_132707_15935_PB03ENWEB.pdf (Accessed: August 2015).

UNEP, 2007. Assessment of policy instruments for reducing greenhouse gas emissions from buildings - Summary and Recommendations. Available at: <http://www.unep.org/pdf/policytoolbox.pdf> (Accessed: August 2015)

Zarkadoulia Maria, 2015. The Programme EXOIKONOMO. Presentation at the Workshop titled Designing the transfer towards energy efficient cities – Energy savings at the municipality level. Available at: http://anemosananeosis.gr/greek/wp-content/uploads/2015/06/EnergyEfficiency_11.06.15_%CE%96%CE%91%CE%A1%CE%9A%CE%91%CE%94%CE%9F%CE%A5%CE%9B%CE%91.pdf (Accessed: August 2015)

HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.1.2

STATUS-QUO ANALYSIS OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICIES IN 8 EU COUNTRIES

D 1.2.

**PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT**

NATIONAL REPORT FOR ITALY

DATE

Partner: “Università Commerciale Luigi Bocconi”

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

OXFORD
BROOKES
UNIVERSITY

Wuppertal Institute
for Climate, Environment
and Energy

SEI

STOCKHOLM
ENVIRONMENT
INSTITUTE

Institution: Università Commerciale Luigi Bocconi

Steering Committee member ⁽¹⁾: Edoardo Croci

Prepared by: Edoardo Croci, Denis Grasso, Tania Molteni, Alessandro Palma, Università Commerciale Luigi Bocconi - UB - IEFE.

(1) The Steering Committee member has the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the report.

HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	5
GLOSSARY	6
ACRONYMS	7
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	9
1. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL	10
1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE BUILDINGS SECTOR	10
1.1.1 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	10
1.1.2 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS/ INFORMATIVE POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	12
1.1.3 ECONOMIC POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	16
1.1.4 CAPACITY BUILDING AND NETWORKING.....	25
1.1.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR THE PROMOTION OF ENERGY SERVICES.....	27
1.1.6 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT AND BEST AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGY (BAT) PROMOTION	29
1.1.7 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR IN ITALY	32
1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR	34
1.2.1 PLANNING INSTRUMENTS.....	34
1.2.2 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	36
1.2.3 FINANCIAL POLICY INSTRUMENTS	39
1.2.4 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS	42
1.2.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT	44
1.2.6 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR IN ITALY	46
2. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE REGIONAL / LOCAL LEVEL	48
2.1 PRESENTATION OF THE CASE STUDY: METROPOLITAN CITY OF MILAN	48
ANNEXES	54
REFERENCES	55

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Comparison among smart meters projects in 3 European countries 14
Figure 2: Final annual energy savings achieved since the launch of the scheme and expected savings (Mtoe)19
Figure 3: Expected annual final energy savings from the Thermal Account (Mtoe)..... 21
Figure 4: Expected annual final energy savings under the White Certificates mechanism (Mtoe)..... 23
Figure 5: Past and forecast annual primary energy savings under the White Certificates scheme 24
Figure 6: Homepage of ENEA energy efficiency training platform 26
Figure 7: Annual Italian biofuels objectives 2006-2012 38
Figure 8: Covenant of Mayors – Signatories in Lombardy Region (2013) (table and figure)..... 52

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

GLOSSARY

ACRONYMS

AEEG: Italian Regulatory Authority for Electricity Gas and Water.

AMAT: Agenzia Mobilità Ambiente Territorio (Agency for Mobility Environment Territory).

ASSTRA: Associazione Trasporti (Transport Association).

BEEM: Building Energy Management System.

CEER: Catasto Energetico Edifici Regionale (Regional Energy Cadastre of Buildings).

CEI: Comitato Termoelettrico Italiano (Italian Electrotechnical Committee).

CoM: Covenant of Mayors.

CNR: Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (National Research Council).

CURIT: Catasto Unico Regionale Impianti Termici (Unique Regional Cadastre of Heating Plants).

D.I.: Decreto Interministeriale (Inter-ministerial Decree).

D.L.: Decreto Legge (Law Decree).

Dlgs: Decreto Legislativo (Legislative Decree).

D.M.: Decreto Ministeriale (Ministerial Decree).

D.P.R.: Decreto del Presidente della Repubblica (Decree of the President of the Republic).

DSO: Distributors System Operators

EIB: European Investment Bank.

ELENA: European Local ENergy Assistance.

EME: Energy Management Expert.

ENEA: Agenzia nazionale per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e lo sviluppo economico sostenibile (Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development)

EPBD: Energy Performance of Buildings Directive.

EPC: Energy Performance Contracting.

ESCO: Energy Service Company

EU: European Union.

GME: Gestore dei Mercati Energetici (Energy Market operator)

GPP: Green Public Procurement.

GSE: Gestore dei Servizi Energetici (Energy Service Operator).

IEA: International Energy Agency.

IRPEF: Personal income tax

IRES: Corporate income tax

ITS: Intelligent Transport System

L.: National Law.

LEED: Leadership in Energy & Environmental Design.

LPG: Liquefied Petroleum Gas.

MATTM: Italian Ministry for the Environment and the Protection of Land and Sea.

MISE: Italian Ministry of Economic Development.

MIT: Italian Ministry of Infrastructures and Transport.

NEEAP: National Energy Efficiency Action Plan

PAE: Piano d'Azione per l'Energia (Energy Action Plan).

PEAR: Programma Energetico Ambientale Regionale (Energy and Environmental Regional Programme).

PIDEE: Piano integrato di diffusione dell'efficienza energetica (Integrated plan for the uptake of energy efficiency).

PNIRE: Piano Nazionale Infrastrutturale per la ricarica dei veicoli alimentati ad energia elettrica (National infrastructure plan to set up electric vehicle charging points).

RSE: Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico (Research on the Energy System).

R&D: Research and Development.

SEAP: Sustainable Energy Action Plan.

SME: Small and Medium-sized Enterprise.

SUMP: Sustainable Urban Mobility Plan.

TOE: Tonnes of equivalent oil.

UNI: Ente Italiano di Normazione (Italian Organization for Standardization).

Please note that throughout the report, "SEN, 2013" is used to refer to the following reference: Ministry of Economic Development. (2013). National Energy Strategy 2013. Available at: http://www.encharter.org/fileadmin/user_upload/Energy_policies_and_legislation/Italy_2013_National_Energy_Strategy_ENG.pdf

Please note that throughout the report, "NEEAP, 2014" is used to refer to the following reference: Ministry of Economic Development. (2014a). Italian Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2014. Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/2014_neeap_en_italy.pdf

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Italy has a wide and comprehensive set of energy efficiency policies in place, both in the buildings and transport sectors. In the present report, the most relevant Italian energy efficiency policies are analysed. The selection of these policies, both for buildings and transport sectors, are based on the relevance given to the policy in the national NEEAPs and on the expert assessment of Bocconi University-IEFE research team.

For the **building sector**, the following 10 most relevant policies are analysed:

- **Regulatory policy instruments:** set of national laws on the energy performance in buildings;
- **Dissemination and awareness instruments:** Electric Smart Meters and ENEA website “Obiettivo efficienza energetica” (Target: Energy Efficiency);
- **Economic Policy Instruments:** Tax deductions for improving the energy efficiency of buildings, Thermal Account, White Certificates and Kyoto Fund;
- **Capacity Building and Networking:** ENEA training platform and e-learning courses for experts on energy efficiency in buildings;
- **Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services:** Voluntary national certification scheme for ESCOs;
- **Policy Instruments for Research and Development and Best available Technology (BAT) Promotion:** National Electric System Research.

For the **transport sector**, the following 5 most relevant policies are analysed:

- **Planning Instruments:** National infrastructural plan to set up electric vehicle charging points;
- **Regulatory Policy Instruments:** Obligation to input into consumption biofuels;
- **Financial Policy Instruments:** Government subsidies for the purchase of low emission vehicles and funds related to the “Five-year bus fleet renewal plan”;
- **Dissemination and awareness instruments:** National Logistic Platform UIRNET;
- **Policy Instruments for Research and Development:** National Electric System Research.

Where available, quantitative data on the energy efficiency/energy saving results obtained by the policy instruments are provided.

1. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE BUILDINGS SECTOR

Based on the relevance given in the national NEEAPs and on the expert assessment of Bocconi University-IEFE research team, 10 key policy instruments among those in force for energy efficiency in the buildings sector have been selected for a deeper description and analysis.

They are presented in the following paragraphs divided according to policy type (regulatory policy instruments, dissemination and awareness, economic policy instruments, capacity building, Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services, Research and Development and BAT promotion).

1.1.1 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

Italy has several regulatory policy instruments related to the buildings sector. The main regulatory policy instruments in the building sector are:

- Energy performance in buildings. Transposition of EPBD and EPBD recast EU directives (Dlgs. 19 August 2005, n. 192, modified with Dlgs. 30 May 2008, n. 115; L. 3 August 2013, n. 90);
- Transposition of the Energy Efficiency Directive 2012/27/EU (Dlgs. 4 July 2014, n. 102);
- Rules for implementing the national energy plan in the field of rational use of energy, energy saving and development of renewable energy sources (L. 9 January 1991, n. 10);
- Regulation on Accreditation of Italian Energy Certifiers (D.P.R. 16 April 2013, n. 75);
- Green Public Procurement. Minimum Environmental Criteria for several appliances related to buildings, in particular public lighting and energy services for buildings (D.M. 25 February 2011, D.M. 25 July 2011, D.M. 7 March 2012);
- Energy labelling of households appliances (Dlgs. 28 June 2012, n. 104);
- Simplification/exemption of authorization procedures for some energy efficiency measures (municipal level);
- Regional Regulatory Schemes on energy efficiency in buildings (regional level);
- Municipal buildings regulations (municipal level).

All the Italian regulatory standards on buildings, based on NEEAP 2014 prevision data, are foreseen to produce a total final energy savings in 2020 of 5.23 Mtoe/year.

1.1.1.1 Energy performance in buildings (Dlgs. 19 August 2005, n. 192 and consecutive updating)

a) General information

The national legislative framework for increasing the energy efficiency in the buildings sector is quite varied (NEEAP, 2014) as during the years several national laws determined a large amount of amendments. One of the main critical aspects in the implementation of the European directive on Energy performance in buildings in Italy was related to the relevant delay in the adoption of EU legislation. In fact Directive 2002/91/EC (EPBD) was implemented in Italy by Dlgs. 19 August 2005, n. 192¹, three years after the adoption of the EU Directive. Directive 2010/31/EU (EPBD recast) was transposed in Italy by D.L. 4 June 2013, n. 63², converted into law by L. 3 August 2013, n. 90³, also in this case three years after the adoption of the EU Directive. For these reasons, the European Commission asked Italy to take action and ensure that the Energy efficiency in buildings directive is fully transposed into national law (DG Energy)⁴.

b) Type of policy instrument

The set of laws on “Energy performance in buildings” belongs to the policy type “Regulatory policy instruments”. It defines energy efficiency compulsory targets for new and existing buildings.

c) Objectives

In line with the EU Directives, the objectives of the set of laws on “Energy performance in buildings” are to promote the construction of new and retrofitted nearly-zero energy buildings by 2020 (2018 in the case of Public buildings), and the application of a cost-optimal methodology for setting minimum requirements for both the envelope and the technical systems.

d) Target group

Target groups of the set of laws on “Energy performance in buildings” are buildings owned both by private citizens and public authorities.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The “Energy performance in buildings” legislative framework in Italy foresees a clear different competence repartition among the national and regional levels. In particular the main functions of the national level in the buildings sector are:

- Defining the overall energy efficiency objectives and strategies;
- Defining energy efficiency technical regulation;
- Monitoring the results of policies and measures;

Instead, the main roles of Italian Regions in the buildings energy efficiency legislative framework are:

- Technical definition and monitoring of regional energy efficiency certification schemes;

¹ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2005-08-19;192!vig=>

² <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legge:2013-06-04;63!vig=>

³ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2013-08-03;90!vig=>

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/april-2015-energy-efficiency-buildings-commission-asks-italy-netherlands-and-poland-comply-eu-rules>

- Training and accreditation of operators realizing energy efficiency certifications;
- Monitoring and control (through inspections) of buildings energy efficiency certifications and qualified energy efficiency operators.

f) Implementation network

The implementation network of the energy performance in buildings legislation in Italy is very complex. In fact in Italy energy issues are governed under a system of “concurrent legislative powers”. This means that the Regions have legislative powers over energy matters, except for the fundamental principles, which are determined by central Government. The application of this constitutional provision has caused considerable difficulty in terms of harmonizing legislation on energy efficiency in buildings among different Regions.

g) Outcomes

Based on NEEAP 2014 data, the Italian energy performance in buildings scheme achieved in the period 2005-2012 a final energy saving of 2.32 Mtoe/y.

Forecast of final energy savings according to the NEEAP:

Programme	Savings 2005-2012	Savings total 2014-2020
On-site energy consultation	2.16 Mtoe/y	Not available

1.1.2 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS/ INFORMATIVE POLICY INSTRUMENTS

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

Italy has several dissemination and awareness instruments/informative policy instruments related to the buildings sector. The main national dissemination and informative policy instruments in the building sector are:

- Pilot Projects on multi service smart metering (Deliberation 19 September 2013, 393/2013/R/gas of the AEEG)⁵;
- Transparent billing methods (Deliberation 18 November 2008 – ARG/com 164/08 of the AEEG)⁶;
- National Green Procurement Plan (“Piano d’Azione Nazionale per il GPP”) (D.M. 11 April 2008⁷, updated with D.M. 10 April 2013⁸);

⁵ <http://www.autorita.energia.it/allegati/docs/13/393-13.pdf>

⁶ <http://www.autorita.energia.it/allegati/docs/08/164-08arg.pdf>

⁷ http://www.minambiente.it/sites/default/files/archivio/allegati/GPP/all.to_3_DI_135_11.04.08_PAN.pdf

- ENEA website “Obiettivo efficienza energetica” (Target: energy efficiency)⁹;
- Several dissemination/awareness campaigns on specific energy efficiency themes (all experiences are mapped in the NEEAP – National Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2014);
- Buildings energy efficiency voluntary certification schemes and environmental voluntary certification schemes (Casa Clima¹⁰, Protocollo Itaca¹¹, LEED...);
- Sustainable Energy Action Plans (SEAPs) (municipal level).

1.1.2.1 Electric Smart Meters

a) General information

In Italy, the replacement of the traditional electricity meters with a wide national smart metering infrastructure started in 2001. Italy (NEEAP, 2014) launched the adoption of smart metering in electricity sector on a voluntary basis, driven by the initiative of national Distribution Service Operators (DSOs), in particular “ENEL Distribuzione” (an Italian state-controlled power provider). The replacement of the traditional electricity meters later became mandatory under a Decision of the Electricity, Gas and Water Authority (AEEG). The Smart Meters national infrastructure was completed on the initiative of “ENEL Distribuzione” which implemented a plan for the installation of about 36.7 million meters between 2001 and 2011 (NEEAP, 2014), well in advance of the mandatory regime. For all these reasons Italy is today a pioneer country at World level in digital electricity metering (ENEL)¹². These efforts have driven to install electric smart meters in more than 90% of Italian households (Reuters, 2013).

b) Type of policy instrument

The “Electric Smart Meters” measure belongs to the policy type “Dissemination and Awareness instruments”. In fact electric smart meters system aim “to provide households with a user-friendly tool that improves awareness of energy behaviour in homes, enabling better management via the visualization of consumption and persuasive tailored information on domestic electricity use” (NEEAP, 2014).

c) Objectives

The “Electric Smart Meters” measure objective is to add functions to electricity and gas meters that can help distributors and sellers to improve their energy services and users to use supply data to improve management of off takes, in line with the “Smart Grid” paradigm. The final objective is to substitute all the Italian electric meters with a smart one (NEEAP, 2014).

d) Target group

⁸ http://www.sviluppoeconomico.gov.it/images/stories/normativa/decreto_ministeriale_10aprile2013.pdf

⁹ <http://www.energiaenergetica.enea.it/>

¹⁰ <http://www.agenziacasaclima.it/it/casaclima/1-0.html>

¹¹ <http://www.itaca.org/index.asp>

¹² https://www.enel.it/it-IT/eventi_news/news/la-rivoluzione-dei-contatori-elettronici/p/090027d981930477

The “Electric Smart Meters” measure targets groups, within the building sector, are both the final energy users and the Italian Distribution Service Operators (DSOs).

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Italian DSOs used their own financial resources for implementing such a system, with remuneration from network tariffs introduced at a later stage. In Italy the tariff system for metering (introduced in 2004) has enabled full recovery of DSOs investments (NEEAP, 2014).

f) Implementation network

The adoption of electric Smart Meters started on a voluntary basis and it was conducted by national DSOs. In a second moment, due to an AEEG decision, smart electric meters became a mandatory roll-out.

g) Outcomes

A study conducted in 2013 on smart meters’ impacts on Italian citizens, found that energy related persuasive communication provided by Italian Smart Meters is effective in reducing electricity consumption in dwellings on average by –18% and up to –57% (D’Oca S., Corgnati S., Buso T., 2013). Moreover, with more than 36 million of installed smart meters in the country (NEEAP, 2014), Italy is the leading European country in this field.

Figure 1: Comparison among smart meters projects in 3 European countries

MS already completed roll-out	Metering points in the Country		Roll-out period Start Date	Roll-out period End Date	Penetration rate by 2020 (%)	SM lifetime (years)
Finland	3 300 000		2009	2013	97%	15 - 25
Italy	36 700 000		2001	2011	99%	15
Sweden	5 200 000		2003	2009	100%	10
MS already completed roll-out	Investment (CAPEX + OPEX, € mn)	Total Benefit (€ mn)	Consumers' benefit (%)	Energy savings	Peak Load shifting	Discount rate used
Finland	692	NA	NA	1-2%	2.0%	NA
Italy	3359	6398	NA	NA	NA	4.5%
Sweden	1500*	1677	19.7%	1 - 3%	NA	NA

Source: NEEAP, 2014

Data on “electric smart meters” final energy savings are not available.

1.1.2.2 ENEA website “Obiettivo efficienza energetica”

a) General information

The ENEA website “Obiettivo efficienza energetica” (Target: Energy Efficiency)¹³ was created by ENEA in June 2015 in order to gather all the different thematic webpages created during the years by ENEA in relation to the different energy efficiency policies and measures.

b) Type of policy instrument

The ENEA website “Obiettivo efficienza energetica” belongs to the policy type “Dissemination and awareness instruments”. It provides to final users (both private and public authorities) all the required information and links to the main Italian energy efficiency laws and economic supporting schemes.

c) Objectives

The ENEA website “Obiettivo efficienza energetica” objective is to collect in a single website several Italian and European energy efficiency thematic websites. Moreover ENEA website intends to improve the widespread of an energy efficiency culture among different private and public subjects.

d) Target group

The ENEA website “Obiettivo efficienza energetica” target groups are private citizens, business operators and public authorities. In order to target in a more efficient way the different website information, three specific thematic areas were created. Each thematic area has a specific focus based on the needs of the selected target groups.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The ENEA website “Obiettivo efficienza energetica” brings together these thematic ENEA websites:

- Website dedicated to the 65% fiscal deduction for energy efficiency interventions;
- White Certificate Blog;
- Youtube Channel dedicated to energy efficiency in buildings;
- Website for the promotion of energy efficiency in buildings envelopes;
- Website “Obiettivo Efficienza”, a general ENEA energy efficiency information webpage.

A specific section is dedicated to energy efficiency news and to the dissemination of thematic contents developed in European and national energy efficiency research projects.

f) Implementation network

The website is fully financed and managed by ENEA. In particular ENEA manages this website through their dedicated energy efficiency information office “Energy Efficiency National Agency” (Agenzia Nazionale Efficienza Energetica)¹⁴. Public and private energy efficiency subjects participate to the platform sharing their specific news and disseminating their activities and thematic publications.

g) Outcomes

No data on final energy savings related to ENEA website “Obiettivo efficienza energetica” are available.

¹³ <http://www.energiaenergetica.enea.it/>

¹⁴ <http://www.agenziaefficienzaenergetica.it/>

1.1.3 ECONOMIC POLICY INSTRUMENTS

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

Italy has several economic policy instruments related to the buildings sector. The main national economic policies in the building sector are:

- Thermal Account (D.M. 28 December 2012¹⁵);
- Tax deductions (introduced with L. 27 December 2006, n. 296, namely the Budget Law 2007¹⁶ – “Legge finanziaria 2007”, and renewed several times with modifications);
- White Certificates (or Energy Efficiency Certificates) scheme and Obligation for national energy distributors (D.M. 20 July 2004¹⁷);
- Kyoto Fund (introduced with L. 27 December 2006, n. 296, namely the Budget Law 2007 – “Legge finanziaria 2007”, and implemented through following acts);
- National Fund for Energy Efficiency (“Fondo Nazionale per l’Efficienza Energetica”) (Dlgs. 4 July 2014, n. 102¹⁸);
- Measures for the energy efficiency in schools (“Misure per l’efficientamento energetico degli edifici scolastici”) (D.I. 14 April 2015, n. 66¹⁹);
- Fund for home purchase and/or renovation (“Plafond Casa”)(Cassa Depositi e Prestiti) (D.L. 31 August 2013, n. 102²⁰, converted into L. 28 October 2013, n. 124²¹).

1.1.3.1 Tax deductions for improving the energy efficiency of buildings

a) General information

Tax deductions for improving the energy efficiency of buildings were introduced in Italy by the Budget Law 2007 (L. 27 December 2006, n. 296²²) and are still in force since 2007. As tax deductions are not a permanent policy but need annual Parliament approval, their general functioning schemes

¹⁵ http://www.gse.it/Conto%20Termico/GSE_Documenti/_DM_28_DICEMBRE_2012_CONTO_TERMICO.PDF

¹⁶ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2006-12-27;296!vig=>

¹⁷ http://www.autorita.energia.it/docs/riferimenti/decreto_040720fr.htm

¹⁸ <http://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2014/07/18/14G00113/sg>

¹⁹ <http://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2015/05/13/15A03601/sg>

²⁰ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto-legge:2013-08-31;102>

²¹ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2013-10-28;124>

²² <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2006-12-27;296>

have changed several times. As evidenced in the Italian NEEAP 2014, “the Government and Parliament have extended the action through 2015 (up to June 2016 for actions on the common parts of buildings) and have raised the tax deduction rate to 65% but have already decided to revise the scheme, with a view to rationalising expenditure, so as to transform the scheme into a structural incentive”.

b) Type of policy instrument

“Tax deductions” belong to the policy type “Economic policy instruments”. It is a policy recognising specific fiscal and tax benefits to all taxpayers implementing one of the energy efficiency action supported by national Laws.

c) Objectives

The tax deductions scheme aims to provide financial and economic support to families and companies improving energy efficiency of their existing buildings. In particular the Tax deductions scheme supports the following energy efficiency investments (NEEAP, 2014):

- Reduce heating demand by means of overall upgrading of the building’s energy performance;
- Improve the building’s thermal insulation (replacement of windows, including blinds or shutters, and insulation of roofs, walls and floors);
- Install solar thermal panels;
- Replace winter heating systems (with condensing boilers or heat pumps);
- Replace electrical water heaters with heat pump water heaters.

d) Target group

Target groups are all the Italian taxpayers, including natural persons, professionals, companies undertaking incurring costs for implementing energy efficiency actions in their existing buildings. Both commercial and residential buildings are granted.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The tax deductions scheme (which are granted for both residential and commercial buildings) consists in a reductions of IRPEF (personal income tax) and IRES (corporate income tax) for subjects investing in actions aimed to improve the energy efficiency of an existing buildings. The access to the incentives is limited to those buildings provided with an energy certification. The 2015 tax deductions schemes define the following supporting measures:

- A **65% tax deduction (Ecobonus)** (to be repaid in 10 annual rates) for energy upgrading of existing buildings. It was 55% tax deduction until the end of 2013;
- A **Tax bonus** consisting of a further deduction of 50% for a maximum cost of € 10,000, for the purchase of furniture and appliances with high efficiency, but only for the furnishing of properties subject to deduction of 50% for restructuring.

Since 1 January 2016 tax benefits will be lowered to 36%²³, in line with the spending review process launched at national levels in the last years.

The monitoring system and sanctionary regime are managed by the Italian Revenue Agency²⁴, which other than guaranteeing the reliability of the applicant documentation, performs randomly-distributed controls and applies monetary fees to non-compliant subjects.

²³<http://www.agenziaentrate.gov.it/wps/content/Nsilib/Nsi/Home/CosaDeviFare/Richiedere/Agevolazioni/Detrazione+riqualificazione+energetica+55/Scheda+informativa+riqualificazione+55/>

f) Implementation network

Several national institutions are involved in the tax deductions implementation network. As the tax deductions scheme is not a permanent policy, each year the national Parliament has to agree the continuation of this program and the amount of dedicated money. The savings reported in the application for tax deductions are checked for congruity by ENEA. On its part, the Revenue Agency (Agenzia delle Entrate) performs tax spot-checks to verify the correctness of the tax deductions claimed against invoiced expenses (NEEAP, 2014).

g) Outcomes

Tax deductions have been the key drivers of energy efficiency improvements in the housing sector in Italy (NEEAP, 2014). The total number of actions implemented has generated final energy savings of an average 0.86 Mtoe/year, corresponding to more than 2 million tonne/year of avoided CO₂ emissions.

Forecast of final energy savings according to the NEEAP are:

Programme	Savings 2005-2012	Savings total 2014-2020
Tax deduction	3.61 Mtoe (data available only for the 2007-2012 period)	10.4 Mtoe

²⁴ For further information, see:

http://www.agenziaentrate.gov.it/wps/file/Nsilib/Nsi/Agenzia/Agenzia+comunica/Prodotti+editoriali/Guide+Fiscali/Agenzia+informa/pdf+guide+agenzia+informa/Guida_Le_sanzioni_tributarie_e_penali.pdf

Figure 2: Final annual energy savings achieved since the launch of the scheme and expected savings (Mtoe)

Legend:
■ Achieved
■ Expected
▲ Total

Source: Ministry of Economic Development, 2014b

1.1.3.2 Thermal Account

a) General information

The Thermal Account, introduced by D.M. 28 December 2012, is the first nationwide direct incentive scheme for the generation of renewable thermal energy. Moreover it is the first scheme encouraging public authorities to implement energy efficiency actions in their buildings (NEEAP, 2014). The Thermal Account became operational in July 2013. The decree Dlgs. 4 July 2014, n. 102, established a cap of 65% of the capital costs as a maximum subsidy.

b) Type of policy instrument

The Thermal Account belongs to the policy type “Economic policy instruments”. It is a policy providing economic incentives to private and public subjects producing and using renewable thermal energy.

c) Objectives

The Thermal Account aims to provide subsidies for the installation of renewable heating and cooling systems, as well as for energy efficiency refurbishments. The Thermal Account intends to support the following energy efficiency actions:

- Thermal insulation of walls;
- Replacement of transparent vertical structures (windows);
- Installation of screening and shading systems;
- Replacement of heating systems with condensing boilers;
- Replacement of heat generators with electrical and gas heat pumps, including heat pumps for the production of sanitary hot water;

- Replacement of heat generators with biomass-fed heat generators, heating fireplaces and stoves;
- Installation of solar thermal collectors and solar cooling systems.

d) Target group

The Thermal Account target groups are public authorities and non-industrial private parties like individuals, condominiums, business and farms (NEEAP, 2014).

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Two categories of projects are eligible to benefit from the scheme: energy efficiency improvements in existing buildings and small-scale projects concerning systems producing thermal energy from renewable and high-efficiency systems. For the first Thermal Account Government plan, a budget of € 7 million was available for public entities and € 23 million for private ones. The maximum power limit in order to qualify for the incentive is 1,000 thermal kW or 1,000 gross m² of surface area for thermal solar systems. In the case of energy efficiency actions, an expenditure ceiling has been set for each type of action. The incentive covers part of the costs incurred and is paid out in annual instalments for a period from 2 to 5 years according to the actions implemented. The cap of the incentive scheme was set at €200 million for public entities and at €700 million for private persons. Once the cap is reached, this funding level will be reassessed (NEEAP, 2014). Penalties (monetary fees) are imposed on the obligated parties in cases of non-compliance, as envisaged in the art. 23(3) of the Dlgs n. 28/2011. The GSE manages the monitoring regime, together to several sub-entities which act in belief of the GSE. In case of non-compliance, the GSE reports the violations to the local authorities which apply specific sanctionary measures.

f) Implementation network

Several national institutions are involved in the Thermal Account implementation network. **GSE** (Italy Energy Service Operator) is in charge of implementing and managing the scheme. It also awards, disburses and revokes incentives and it is in charge of monitoring and checks. **ENEA** (Italian Energy Agency) assists GSE in preparing the technical rules for implementing the measure and takes part in the verifications and checks. It also provides specialist assistance to GSE in monitoring activities and, in cooperation with GSE, draws up an annual report. The **Authority for Electricity and Gas** (AEEG) prepares the model contract between GSE and the beneficiaries and defines the manner whereby the funding for the incentives will be drawn from the income from natural gas tariffs (NEEAP, 2014).

g) Outcomes

As evidenced in NEEAP 2014, “several simulations quantify the expected savings in a cumulative value of about 5.88 Mtoe of end-use energy over the period 2014-2020. In greater detail, the 1.47 Mtoe/y total savings to 2020 will come mainly from the services sector (0.93 Mtoe/y), while the remaining 0.54 Mtoe/y will come from the residential sector” (NEEAP, 2014).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the NEEAP:

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
On-site energy consultation	(Thermal Account started in 2013)	5.88 Mtoe

Figure 3: Expected annual final energy savings from the Thermal Account (Mtoe)

Source: NEEAP, 2014

1.1.3.3 White Certificates (Energy Efficiency Certificates)

a) General information

The White Certificates system was introduced in the Italian legislation by ministerial decrees D.M. 20 July 2004. It foresees that distributors of electricity and natural gas annually reach specific quantitative goals of primary energy savings, expressed in tonnes of equivalent oil saved (TOE). A certificate is equivalent to saving one ton of oil equivalent.

The White Certificates scheme was amended several times during the years²⁵. The characteristics of obliged actors were reviewed, the energy efficiency targets were made more stringent, the implementation times were extended and the so-called “large projects” were introduced. Large Projects are energy efficiency projects concerning relevant infrastructures, industrial processes, or linked to interventions in the transport sector, which generate, in a year, savings of no less than 35,000 toe and which have a technical life exceeding 20 years. For these projects a specific financial treatment was introduced.

b) Type of policy instrument

The White Certificates system belongs to the policy type “Economic policy instruments”. It is a policy combining a regulatory/obligation policy with the generation of economic resources to be used to financially support energy efficiency projects.

c) Objectives

The White Certificates scheme aims to promote end-use energy savings both in residential and industrial sectors.

²⁵ See for a complete framework of all the changes IEA Energy Efficiency. Policies and Measures databases. Italy. <http://www.iea.org/policiesandmeasures/energyefficiency/?country=Italy>

d) Target group

Target groups are Italian electricity and gas distributors. Italian electricity and gas distributors with at least 50,000 end-user customers are the obligated parties. Voluntary participants are distributors with less than 50 000 customers, energy services companies, entities required to appoint an energy manager, entities which have voluntarily appointed an energy manager, entities that have implemented an energy management system conforming with ISO 50001 (NEEAP, 2014).

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Electricity and gas distributors may fulfil their energy efficiency national obligation by implementing energy efficiency projects entitled to White Certificates or by buying White Certificates from other parties in the Energy Efficiency Certificates Market that is organised by GME. Energy service providers, subsidiaries of electricity and gas distributors and distributors themselves will all sell energy efficiency certificates each representing primary energy savings. Distribution companies must meet specified energy savings targets, either by implementing energy conservation projects that benefit their customers, which will earn them White Certificates, or through the purchase of White Certificates produced by energy conservation projects undertaken by others.

The White Certificates represent marketable documents issued by the Energy Market Administrator (GME) testifying the energy saved by the energy distribution companies - as well as by their controlled partnerships - and by the ESCOs. A simplified methodology, by "technical cards"²⁶, is used to determine the quantification of primary energy savings. Savings achieved under the scheme must be additional to measures that would be normally implemented, including those implemented to meet new legal requirements. Reference conditions are thus continuously updated to account for regulatory and market changes. The White Certificates can be exchanged by means of bilateral contracts, or in the frame of a specific market ruled by GME.

Three types of white certificates can be produced and traded. Type I certificates are for savings achieved in the electricity sector, Type II certificates for those achieved in the gas sector, and Type III for those in neither sector (from other fuels). Penalties are imposed on the obligated parties in cases of non-compliance (NEEAP, 2014).

In particular, the monitoring system of the White Certificates scheme in Italy is not executed on the entire applicants population, but relies on randomly-distributed checks. The checks are performed by the GSE through several sub-entities which are responsible for verifying the accuracy and reliability of the requested documents as specified in the Dlgs. 3 March 2011, n. 28. Once the check is concluded, such entities report to GSE the final response which allows for receiving the incentives. When control subjects, which include also local authorities such as the Municipal Police, report non-compliant actions (such as falsification of documents, information or infringement of local building regulations), a sanctionary system also applies. The GSE, through the local authorities, is allowed to impose monetary sanctions to non-compliant applicants and, in case of repeated violations, it can also suspend the incentive scheme up to six months.

f) Implementation network

Several national institutions are involved in the White Certificates implementation network. **GSE** (Energy Service Operator) is in charge of implementing, assessing and certifying the savings. On May of each year GSE verifies whether the obligated parties have achieved their target. The **Ministry for Economic Development**, in agreement with **the Ministry for the Environment**, sets periodically the

²⁶<http://www.gse.it/it/CertificatiBianchi/Modalit%C3%A0%20di%20realizzazione%20dei%20progetti/Schede%20tecniche/Pagine/default.aspx>

national energy efficiency targets to be achieved by the obligated parties. The applications for the White Certificates undergo technical and administrative assessment by **ENEA** (National Energy Agency) or **RSE** (a GSE technical office). **GME** (the energy markets' operator) issues the certificates after completing the assessment and manages the certificates trading mechanisms.

g) Outcomes

The NEEAP 2014 shows the predicted annual savings, yielding a cumulative value of about 16.03 Mtoe of final energy. The 4.3 Mtoe/y achievable by 2020 through projects implemented in the period 2014-2020 are increased by the sum of 1.2 Mtoe/y savings from the projects implemented over the period 2011-2013. Thus, the total expected savings by 2020 from actions over the period 2011-2020 comes to 5.45 Mtoe/y.

Forecast of final energy savings according to the NEEAP:

Programme	Savings 2005-2012	Savings total 2014-2020
On-site energy consultation	22.4 Mtoe	16.03 Mtoe

Figure 4: Expected annual final energy savings under the White Certificates mechanism (Mtoe)

Source, NEEAP, 2014

Figure 5: Past and forecast annual primary energy savings under the White Certificates scheme

Legend:

- Savings achieved (Mtoe)
- Saving targets (Mtoe)
- Targets for the coming period (Mtoe)

Source: Ministry of Economic Development, 2014b

1.1.3.4 Kyoto Fund

a) General information

The Kyoto Fund is a revolving fund supporting GHG emission reduction projects, managed by “Cassa Depositi e Prestiti” (Deposit and Loan Fund). The Kyoto Fund was activated in 2012. In 2014 the Kyoto Fund was ended and the residual economic resources were directed to a “National Fund for youth employment in the Green Economy Sector”²⁷.

b) Type of policy instrument

The Kyoto Fund belongs to the policy type “Economic policy instruments”. It provides discounted loans to public and private subjects interested in financing GHG emission reduction projects.

c) Objectives

The Kyoto Fund aimed to provide discounted loans to public and private subjects interested in financing GHG emission reduction projects in accordance to the Kyoto Protocol. In particular the Kyoto Fund intended to support investments in the following energy efficiency technologies:

- Micro-cogeneration;
- Renewables;

²⁷ http://www.nextville.it/Archivio_Incentivi_e_agevolazioni/960/Archivio_Fondo_rotativo_per_Kyoto

- Electric motors;
- Energy reduction in end-use;
- “Nitrous oxide measures”.

d) Target group

Kyoto Fund target groups are Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), ESCOs, national and local public authorities, condominiums and individuals with a legal entity (Cassa Depositi e Prestiti, 2012).

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The Kyoto Fund had a total budget of € 600 million, to be paid out in three one-year cycles of € 200 million each. The subsidised projects obtained loans with a duration of 3 to 6 years (3 to 15 for public authorities) with six-monthly instalments at a fixed annual interest rate of 0.5%.

f) Implementation network

The Kyoto Fund was managed by “Cassa Depositi e Prestiti” (Deposit and Loan Fund), the joint-stock company under public control (Italian government holding 80.1% and a broad group of bank foundations holding 18.4%, the remaining 1.5% in treasury shares). The economic resources to be allocated were decided by the Central Government. The Kyoto Fund economic resources were allocated through the national bank system.

g) Outcomes

No final energy savings related to Kyoto Fund are documented in Italian NEEAPs.²⁸

1.1.4 CAPACITY BUILDING AND NETWORKING

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

Italy has several capacity building and networking instruments related to the buildings sector. The main national capacity building and networking instruments policy in the building sector are:

- Integrated plan for the uptake of energy efficiency (“Piano integrato di diffusione dell’efficienza energetica”, PIDEE)(Dlgs. 4 July 2014, n. 102²⁹);
- General conference on Energy Efficiency (“Stati Generali Efficienza Energetica”³⁰)(ENEA);
- ENEA training platform and e-learning courses for experts on energy efficiency in buildings³¹.

²⁸ The demand for these funds has been very limited (ENEA, 2014), especially for local micro-cogeneration and electric motors. For this reason the fund was interrupted in 2013.

²⁹ <http://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2014/07/18/14G00113/sg>

³⁰ <http://www.statigeneralefficienzaenergetica.it/>

³¹ <http://www.formazione.enea.it/>

1.1.4.1 ENEA training platform and e-learning courses for experts on energy efficiency in buildings.

a) General information

“ENEA e-learn” platform³² is an online repository of thematic courses on energy efficiency and renewable energy. These courses were thought both for energy efficiency experts (technician, installers, etc.) and for national and local public authorities working on these themes.

Figure 6: Homepage of ENEA energy efficiency training platform

b) Type of policy instrument

³² <http://www.formazione.enea.it/>

“ENEA e-learn” platform belongs to capacity building policies. In fact “ENEA e-learn” platform provides training materials and thematic courses aimed to increase the technical skills of private and public subjects operating in buildings energy efficiency sector.

c) Objectives

The “ENEA e-learn” platform objective is to improve the energy efficiency skills of professionals and regional and local public authorities, both in Italy and abroad.

d) Target group

The “ENEA e-learn” platform target groups are both energy efficiency experts (technician, installers, etc.) and national and local public authorities working on energy efficiency themes.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The “ENEA e-learn” platform provides energy efficiency and renewable energy thematic courses. These courses are both:

- E-learning courses;
- Traditional lessons.

The platform was so successful that ENEA was committed to provide specific training courses to Italian regions and provinces using the materials contained in this e-learning platform. All the experts attending these courses were rewarded with a specific certification.

f) Implementation network

“ENEA e-learn” platform is fully managed and financed by ENEA through their “Training and technology knowledge transfer service” (Servizio Formazione e Informazione dell’Unità Trasferimento Tecnologico).

g) Outcomes

Over 200 online courses and 300 video lectures are available for free on the “ENEA e-learn” platform³³. No data on final energy savings related to this measure are available.

1.1.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR THE PROMOTION OF ENERGY SERVICES

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

Italy has only few policies related to the promotion of energy services. The most important policy in energy services promotion is:

- Definition of ESCOs and set-up of a voluntary national certification scheme for ESCOs (Dlgs. 30 May 2008, n. 115³⁴).

³³ http://www.formazione.enea.it/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=3&Itemid=105

³⁴ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2008-05-30;115~art11!vig=>

1.1.5.1 Voluntary national certification scheme for ESCOs

a) General information

The first Italian definition of Energy Service Companies (ESCOs) was detailed in the legislative decree Dlgs. 30 May 2008, n. 115. This definition represents the first fundamental step for the full development of the ESCOs market in Italy. Later, in 2011, AEEG launched a voluntary accreditation scheme for ESCOs. Today this voluntary accreditation scheme is based on the ESCOs technical quality requirements defined in UNI CEI 11352:2014 (Energy management - Energy services companies (ESCO) - General requirements, checklist for verification of organization requirements and service offer contents)³⁵.

b) Type of policy instrument

The “Voluntary national ESCOs certification scheme” belongs to policy instruments for the promotion of energy services. It defines an accreditation system certifying the managerial and economic quality of an ESCO operating in Italy.

c) Objectives

The “Voluntary national certification scheme for ESCOs” objective is to check and assess the quality of an ESCO operating in Italy, both from the managerial and economic point of view.

d) Target group

The “Voluntary national ESCOs certification scheme” target groups are all the Energy Service Companies operating in Italy.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The voluntary ESCOs accreditation is based on the technical norms defined by UNI CEI 11352:2014. This standard “defines general requirements and a checklist for their verification in an energy service company (ESCO) providing to its customers energy efficiency services compliant to UNI CEI EN 15900, with guarantee of results. Especially, it defines general requirements and capacities (organizational, diagnostic, designing, managing, economic and financial) that an ESCO shall demonstrate to have in order to offer energy efficiency services and other specific activities, here described too, to its own final customer. Moreover it gives a check list to be used for the verification of ESCO's capacities and the minimum content of the contractual offer of an energy efficiency improvement service supplied by an ESCO, and guidance for the management of a second and third party audit for certification scope” (UNI CEI, 2014)³⁶.

Under national legislation, the ESCO's organisational chart must include a manager with appropriate skills in the management of energy and the energy markets and a technician with appropriate design competence in the project areas (NEEAP, 2014). Consequently, it is advisable for ESCOs to have one or more managers fulfilling the profile of the Energy Manager and at least one certified EME (Energy Management Expert).

f) Implementation network

The Italian ESCOs accreditation system is managed by GSE (earlier these activities were in charge to AEEG) through an online accreditation platform³⁷. The Technical requirements were defined by UNI -

³⁵ <http://store.uni.com/magento-1.4.0.1/index.php/uni-cei-11352-2014.html>

³⁶ http://store.uni.com/magento-1.4.0.1/index.php/uni-cei-11352-2014.html?_store=en&_from_store=it

³⁷ <http://www.gse.it/it/CertificatiBianchi/Accreditamento%20Operatori/Pagine/default.aspx#2>

Italian Organization for Standardization (Ente Italiano di Normazione)³⁸, a private association responsible for the definition of technical voluntary norms in Italy.

g) Outcomes

As evidenced in NEEAP 2014, “the ESCO sector in Italy is quite diverse, with 1,900 units registered with AEEG in 2011. But the companies operating routinely in the sector (in particular within the White Certificates scheme) are just 15% of the total, about 390 operators”. There aren’t available data on final energy savings related to this policy.

1.1.6 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT AND BEST AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGY (BAT) PROMOTION

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

Italy has several research and development and best available technology promotion instruments related to the buildings sector. The main national research and development and best available technology promotion instruments in the building sector are:

- National Electric System Research (ENEA³⁹, CNR⁴⁰ and RSE⁴¹ carry out R&D activities on urgent and strategic issues which have results for the benefit of the national electric system users as a whole);
- National “Smart Cities and Communities and Social Innovation” funds (2012 and 2013) (Director Decree 5 July 2012, N.391/Ric)⁴²;
- National prize for energy efficiency measures (GSE’s “Premio Efficienza Energetica”);
- ENEA reports on energy efficiency best available technologies.

1.1.6.1 National Electric System Research

a) General information

Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development (ENEA), National Research Council (CNR) and Research centre on energy system (RSE) carry out R&D activities on urgent and strategic issues, which have results for the benefit of the national electric

³⁸ <http://www.uni.com/>

³⁹ Italian National Agency for New Technologies, Energy and Sustainable Economic Development. URL: http://www.enea.it/en/home?set_language=en&cl=en

⁴⁰ National Research Council. URL: <http://www.cnr.it/sitocnr/Englishversion/Englishversion.html>

⁴¹ Ricerca sul Sistema Energetico S.p.a. URL: <http://www.rse-web.it/Missione.page?country=eng>

⁴² <http://attiministeriali.miur.it/anno-2012/luglio/dd-05072012.aspx>

system users as a whole (IEA, 2015). In order to support these R&D activities, the Italian central government allocates specific economic resources. Moreover, it defines a three year plan in order to coordinate the different research activities carried out by these national research offices.

b) Type of policy instrument

The National Electric System Research belongs to the policy type “Policy instruments for research and development and best available technology promotion”. It set up economic resources to finance energy R&D activities at national level.

c) Objectives

The National Electric System Research objective is to finance research activities aimed to supporting national and regional local authorities in taking/defining the most effective energy efficiency policies based on real data and research activities.

d) Target group

The National Electric System Research target groups are national authorities (in particular Ministries with specific competencies on energy efficiency and government authorities which often consult these national technical authorities before launching a new legislative proposal) and regional public authorities.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

At national level, there are three main technical organizations with a key role in Italian buildings energy efficiency policies and measures definition. These key national technical organizations are:

- **Organization for New Technologies, Energy and the Environment (ENEA)** is the national energy agency. ENEA performs research activities and provides agency services in support to public administrations, public and private enterprises, and citizens. Specifically, ENEA is concerned with energy efficiency, renewable energy sources, nuclear energy;
- **National Research Council (CNR)**. CNR is the largest public research institution in Italy, the only one under the Research Ministry performing multidisciplinary activities . Its role is to promote innovation and competitiveness of the national industrial system, to promote the internationalization of the national research system, to provide technologies and solutions to emerging public and private needs.
- **Electric Systems Research (RSE)**. RSE is a joint stock company, whose unique shareholder is GSE SpA, which develops research in electro-energy, with a particular focus on the strategic national projects of general public interest, financed by the Italian Electricity System Research Fund (Fondo per la Ricerca di Sistema) of the Italian Economic Development Ministry. RSE's activity topics concern electricity system innovation, its technological development and topics of general interest such as efficiency, economics and material, process and device experimentation.

The Decree of the Ministry of Economic Development D.M. 19 March 2009 set a floor of € 210 million on available funds for the 2009-2011 triennium, subdivided into: a) management and development of the national electric system (€ 79mill); b) electricity production and environmental protection (€ 56mill); c) rationalization and saving of electricity use (€ 75 mill). The Ministry of Economic

Development issued a new decree approving a three-year plan to finance research activities in the field of electricity system (D.M. 9 November 2012)⁴³(IEA, 2015).

f) Implementation network

The Central government, in accordance with the Ministry of Economic Development, set up funds to be allocated to national R&D activities. ENEA, CNR and RSE have their own elected administrative bodies managing these funds and define the specific implementation activities to be launched.

g) Outcomes

No data on final energy savings related to this measure are available in national NEEAPs.

⁴³ <http://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2013/01/30/13A00674/sg>

1.1.7 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR IN ITALY

Summary table: Buildings					
Policy instruments	Short list of implemented policies and measures	Objective	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Implementation network
Regulatory policy instruments	Energy Performance in buildings	Improve energy performance of new and existing buildings	Private house owners and public authorities	Compulsory buildings energy efficiency targets.	National government; Regional Authorities
Dissemination and awareness instruments/Informative policy instruments	Electric Smart Meters	Improve awareness of households behaviours	Final energy users and Distribution Service Operators (DSOs)	Voluntary action of Italian DSOs	DSOs and AEEG
	ENEA Website "Obiettivo Efficienza Energetica"	Widespread energy efficiency culture	Citizens, business operators and public authorities	ENEA initiative	ENEA
Economic policy instruments	Tax deductions	Provide financial and economic support for energy efficiency projects	Citizens and companies	65% tax deduction + Tax bonus for energy efficient furniture and appliances	National Government, ENEA, Revenue Agency (Agenzie delle Entrate)
	Thermal Account	Subsidies for installation of renewable heating and cooling systems	Public authorities and non-industrial private parties	Economic incentive covering a part of the total costs (spread from 2 to 5 years according to project type)	GSE, ENEA, AEEG.
	White Certificate	Promote end-use energy savings in residential and industrial sectors	Italian electricity and gas distributors; ESCOs; entities requiring an energy manager; voluntary participants.	Tradable energy savings certificates (1 certificate =1 TOE)	GSE; GME; ENEA; RSE; Minister for Economic Development
	Kyoto Fund	Provide discounted	Small and medium	Revolving fund with a total	Cassa Depositi e Prestiti; Central

		loans to GHG emissionis reduction projects	enterprises; public authorities; individuals with legal entities	budget of € 600 billion	Government.
Capacity building and networking	ENEA training platform and e-learning courses	Improve energy efficiency skills and disseminate energy efficiency information	Energy Efficiency experts; national and regional public authorities	Thematic training courses for experts	ENEA
Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services	Voluntary national certification scheme for ESCOs	Certificate the quality of ESCOs operating in Italy	ESCOs operating in Italy	Certification of ESCOs quality based on UNI CEI 11352:2014	GSE; AEEG
Policy instruments for Research and Development and BAT promotion	National Electric System Research	Promote energy R&D efficiency activities	National and regional public authorities	Research and consultancy activities	Ministry of Economic Development; National Government

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

Based on the relevance given in the national NEEAPs and on the expert assessment of Bocconi University-IEFE research team, 5 key policy instruments among those in force for the energy efficiency in the transport sector have been selected for a deeper description and analysis.

They are presented in the following paragraphs divided according to policy type (planning instruments, regulatory instruments, economic instruments, information and awareness instruments, Policy instruments for Research and Development).

1.2.1 PLANNING INSTRUMENTS

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

Italy has several planning instruments related to the transport sector. The main national transport planning instruments are:

- Italy's National Plan for Logistics 2011/2020 (Piano Nazionale della Logistica 2011-2020) (Ministry of Transport note prot. 567/CGA 30 may 2012⁴⁴);
- National Strategic Plan for Ports and Logistic (Piano Strategico Nazionale della Portualità e della Logistica⁴⁵) (Ministry of Transport 2015);
- National infrastructure plan to set up electric vehicle charging points (Piano Nazionale Infrastrutturale per la ricarica dei veicoli alimentati ad energia elettrica, PNIRE) (L. 7 August 2012, n.134⁴⁶);
- National Action Plan for Intelligent Transport System (Piano di Azione Nazionale sui Sistemi Intelligenti di Trasporto) (D.M. 12 February 2014, n.44⁴⁷);
- Promotion of use of biomethane in transports. (Dlgs. 3 March 2011, N.28, Article 8⁴⁸);
- Five years bus fleet renewal plan (Piano quinquennale per il rinnovo del parco mezzi del trasporto passeggeri su gomma) (L. 27 December 2014, N.147⁴⁹);
- Contract for the development of the national rail infrastructures (Contratto di Programma 2012-2016. Parte Investimenti) (Report to Italian Senate 3 February 2015 n.21⁵⁰);

⁴⁴ http://www.mit.gov.it/mit/mop_all.php?p_id=12968

⁴⁵ http://www.mit.gov.it/mit/mop_all.php?p_id=23291

⁴⁶ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2012;134>

⁴⁷ http://www.mit.gov.it/mit/mop_all.php?p_id=17744

⁴⁸ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2011-03-03;28>

⁴⁹ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2013-12-27;147>

⁵⁰ http://serviziparlamentari.com/index.php?option=com_mtree&task=att_download&link_id=1166&cf_id=72

- Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans, SUMP (Piani Urbani per la Mobilità Sostenibile);
- National Green Procurement Plan (Piano d’Azione Nazionale per il GPP) (D.M. 11 April 2008, updated with D.M. 10 April 2013⁵¹);
- Sustainable Energy Action Plan, SEAPs (Piani d’Azione per l’Energia Sostenibile).

Among all these planning instruments, the “National infrastructure plan to set up electric vehicle charging points” (PNIRE) has been chosen for a deeper analysis as it is expected to have a big impact on the spread of electric vehicles in Italy.

1.2.1.1 National infrastructural plan to set up electric vehicle charging points

a) General information

In 2013 the Italian Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport, with Law 134/2012 (L. 7 August 2012, n.134)⁵², set up a "National infrastructure plan for installing electric vehicles charging points" (PNIRE)⁵³ to ensure an uniform spreading of electric charging points across the national territory to 2020.

b) Type of policy instrument

The “National infrastructural plan to set up electric vehicle charging points” belongs to the policy type “Planning instruments”. It set up a national strategy to 2020 for the construction of a widespread national electric charging points network.

c) Objectives

PNIRE main objective is to develop a national wide electric charging points network with common technical and operational standards. More specifically, in the short term (1-2 years), an infrastructure network will be set up with charging points in urban and metropolitan areas. In the medium and long term (3-5 years) charging points will also be set up in non-urban areas and along the motorways (PNIRE, 2013).

d) Target group

“National infrastructure plan for installing electric vehicles charging points” main target groups are Regions and local authorities. Moreover it involves the main national energy distributors interested in the construction and operation of the charging points (for example the Italian energy distributors ENEL, A2A, etc.).

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The PNIRE foresees two main phases for a full development of an Italian wide electric charging points network:

⁵¹ http://www.sviluppoeconomico.gov.it/images/stories/normativa/decreto_ministeriale_10aprile2013.pdf

⁵² <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2012-08-07;134>

⁵³ For further information, see <http://www.mit.gov.it/mit/site.php?p=cm&o=vd&id=2983>

- Phase 1 (2013-2016) dedicated to the definition and development of electric charging points common operational and construction standards. Moreover PNIRE phase 1 is dedicated to the definition, development and implementation of the required national policies able to contribute to the development of an electric mobility in Italy;
- Phase 2 (2017-2020) dedicated to the consolidation of the Phase 1 results and to the construction of the national charging infrastructures.

One of the key aspects of PNIRE is related to the definition of national standard electric charging protocols in line with the main international and European standards. In particular 4 main typologies of charging points protocols were developed (PNIRE, 2013):

- Mode 1. Slow charging from a household-type socket-outlet;
- Mode 2. Slow charging from a household-type socket-outlet with an in-cable protection device;
- Mode 3. Slow or fast charging using a specific EV socket-outlet with control and protection function installed;
- Mode 4. Fast charging using an external charger.

In order to implement the plan, the Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport has provided for the establishment of an ad-hoc fund with a budget of EUR 20 million for 2013 and EUR 15 million for each of the years 2014 and 2015. In July 2013 the Ministry issued a "Call in favour of the Regions to fund a network of electric vehicle charging points" (NEEAP, 2014).

f) Implementation network

There are several public and private subjects participating in the PNIRE implementation network. In fact the charging points will be both public and private, in a ratio of 1 to 8. The main PNIRE coordination actions are in the hand of Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport, which defined the general framework. For the regulatory and standardization aspects, both national technical offices (AEEG and ENEA) and national and international standardization associations like ISO and CEI were involved. Moreover the construction and realization of the charging infrastructures are entrusted to Regions and to interested energy distributors (Enel S.p.A, A2A S.p.A, etc.).

g) Outcomes

As PNIRE has a 2020 prospective, no data on outcomes are yet available.

1.2.2 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

Italy has several regulatory policy instruments related to the transport sector. The main national transport regulatory policy instruments are:

- Vehicle Certification. Vehicle CO₂ emissions standards (several national laws compliant with European policies on theme);

- Renewable energy in transport sector. (Dlgs. 3 March 2011, N.28⁵⁴);
- Urban Traffic Plans (Piano Urbano del Traffico) (Dlgs. 30 April 1992, N.285⁵⁵);
- Obligation for national fuel producers to input into consumption 1% of biofuels of total traditional fuel. (L.11 March 2006, n. 81⁵⁶);
- National quality standards for biofuels (AEEG Resolution 160/2012/R/GAS⁵⁷);
- Minimum Environmental Criteria for the acquisition of vehicles for road transport (Criteri Minimi Ambientali per l'acquisizione dei veicoli adibiti al trasporto su strada) (D.M. 8 May 2012⁵⁸);
- Limits to polluting vehicles (Regional legislations).

Among these regulatory policy instruments, "Obligation to input into consumption biofuels" was chosen for a deeper analysis as it had a relevant impact on innovation of transport fuel markets in Italy.

1.2.2.1 Obligation to input into consumption biofuels

a) General information

With Legislative Decree 128/2005 (Dlgs. 30 May 2005, n. 128⁵⁹), Italy adopted the EU Directive 2003/30/EC (Biofuels Directive) on the promotion of biofuels in the transport sector. The decree, in accordance with the EU Directive objectives, defines annually obligatory biofuels targets (in percentage) to be inputted into traditional fuels national markets. The obligatory biofuels percentages to be inputted each year on the national market are calculated on the basis of energy content of the fuel and apply to petrol and diesel fuel for transport purposes placed on the national market. Italy set as mandatory for national suppliers of petrol and diesel (obligated parties) to annually input in the national territory ("release for consumption") a minimum quantity of biofuel. These obligatory biofuels input quotas are defined year by year (GSE, 2013).

b) Type of policy instrument

The "obligation to input into consumption biofuels" belongs to the policy type "Regulatory Policy Instruments". In fact this policy sets annually compulsory objectives to be reached with sanctions for the national fuels suppliers not attending their obligations.

c) Objectives

⁵⁴ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto-legislativo:2011-03-03;28>

⁵⁵ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto-legislativo:1992-04-30;285>

⁵⁶ <https://www.politicheagricole.it/flex/cm/pages/ServeBLOB.php/L/IT/IDPagina/3457>

⁵⁷ <http://www.autorita.energia.it/allegati/docs/12/160-12.pdf>

⁵⁸ http://www.minambiente.it/sites/default/files/archivio/allegati/GPP/gu_128_dm.pdf

⁵⁹ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto-legislativo:2005-05-30;128>

The “Obligation to input into consumption biofuels” objectives are to support the growing of national biofuels production and supply chains⁶⁰ and to increase the use of biofuels among final consumers.

Figure 7: Annual Italian biofuels objectives 2006-2012

Anno di riferimento	Quota minima	Riferimento legislativo
2006	1%	Art. 2-quater, comma 2 Legge 11 marzo 2006, n. 81
2007	1%	Art. 1, comma 368 Legge 27 dicembre 2006, n. 296
2008	2%	
2009	3%	Art. 139 Legge 24 dicembre 2007, n. 244
2010	3,50%	Decreto MiSE 25 gennaio 2010
2011	4%	
2012	4,50%	

Source: GSE, 2013

d) Target group

The “Obligation to input into consumption biofuels” target groups are both the producers of biofuels and the traditional fuel sellers.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The Italian government has defined annually obligatory biofuels targets (in percentage) to be inputted into traditional fuels national markets. The share of biofuels to be inputted into consumption is calculated based on the total calorific value of gasoline and diesel fuel supplied in the previous year (GSE, 2013). As a tool for monitoring the compliance of obliged subjects with the national targets, a “Certificate of Release for consumption” (Certificati di Immissione in Consumo) was created. This certificate issued by the Ministry of Economy with the technical assistance of GSE, proves the input into the market of 10 Gcal of biofuels. In order to carry out its obligation, the obliged parties can purchase the Certificates by those who have them in excess. The Government (with D.M. 23 April 2008, n. 100⁶¹) defined fines for the subjects not attending the minimum biofuels input.

f) Implementation network

Since 2013⁶², all the management and technical competencies on biofuels were entrusted to GSE (earlier these competencies were in charge to the Ministry of Economic Development). An important role, from the regulatory point of view, in the implementation national network is fulfilled by AEEG. AEEG, in 2012, defined the biofuels sustainable minimum criteria, in accordance with EU Directive

⁶⁰ <http://www.gse.it/it/EnergiaFacile/guide/Trasporti/Biocarburanti/Pages/default.aspx>

⁶¹ http://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/atto/serie_generale/caricaDettaglioAtto/originario?atto.dataPubblicazioneGazzetta=2008-06-06&atto.codiceRedazionale=008G0120&elenco30giorni=false

⁶² <http://www.gse.it/it/Qualifiche%20e%20certificati/Biocarburanti/Pagine/default.aspx>

2009/28/EC⁶³ and 2009/30/EC⁶⁴ (“Fuel Quality Directive”). Only biofuels compliant with AEEG sustainable requirements could access the national biofuels incentives.

g) Outcomes

This measure is not analysed in the Italian NEEAPs. No data on final energy savings are available.

1.2.3 FINANCIAL POLICY INSTRUMENTS

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

Italy has several financial policy instruments related to the transport sector. The main national transport financial policy instruments are:

- Government subsidies for the purchase of low-emission vehicles (D.L. 10 February 2009, n. 5, converted into law by L. 9 April 2009, n.33⁶⁵; L. 7 August 2012, n.134⁶⁶);
- Incentives for the promotion of biofuels in transport sector (Dlgs. 3 March 2011, n.28⁶⁷);
- Ad-hoc fund of Ministry of Infrastructure and Transport on PNIRE implementation 2013-2015 (L. 7 August 2012, n.134);
- Ministry call in favour of the Regions to fund a network of electric vehicle charging points (L. 7 August 2012, n. 134);
- National electric car sharing project in cities (co-financed by the Ministry of Environment);
- National funds for the development of underground railways (Defined in annual Italian Budget Laws);
- Funds related to the “Five years bus fleet renewal plan” (L. 27 December 2013, N.147⁶⁸);
- Structural fund on thematic area “sustainable movement of people and goods” (EU 2014-2020 Structural Funds);
- Road tax (tax exemption for electric vehicles and discount on car assurance) and regional schemes for tax exemption for LPG and methane vehicles. (Regional legislations);
- National funds for local public transports (indirect effects for example in fleets renewal, etc.). (Defined in annual Italian Budget Laws);
- Funding for energy efficiency, renewable energy and bike-sharing (L. 24 December 2007, n.244⁶⁹).

⁶³ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32009L0028&from=EN>

⁶⁴ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:140:0088:0113:EN:PDF>

⁶⁵ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legge:2009-02-10;5!vig=2015-09-21

⁶⁶ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2012-08-07;134!vig=2015-09-21

⁶⁷ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2011-03-03;28>

⁶⁸ www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2013-12-27;147!vig=

1.2.3.1 Government subsidies for the purchase of low emission vehicles

a) General information

In February 2009, as part of measures aimed to support industrial sectors in crisis (IEA, 2015), the Italian Council of Ministers launched a temporary incentive scheme for consumers to replace their old vehicles with new ones meeting certain environmental criteria (D.L. 10 February 2009, n. 5). The temporary incentive ended at the end of 2009. A second incentive scheme aimed to replace old vehicles was launched with Law No 134/2012 (L. 7 August 2012, n.134) (Article 17-decies). It introduced incentives for the purchase of low CO₂ emission vehicles in the period from the January ,1st 2012 and December, 31st 2015.

b) Type of policy instrument

“Government subsidies for the purchase of low emission vehicles” belongs to the policy type of “Financial Policy Instruments”. It provides incentive to privates substituting their old car with a more environmentally friendly one.

c) Objectives

The “Government subsidies for the purchase of low emission vehicles” objective is to provide an economic support to the renewal of Italian private cars, motorcycles and light commercial vehicles fleets.

d) Target group

The “Government subsidies for the purchase of low emission vehicles” target groups are people intending to substitute their car with a more environmentally friendly one.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The 2009 incentives scheme applies to cars, light commercial vehicles, as well as motorcycles and scooters. The incentives are provided in the form of a discount obtained by consumers directly from the dealers, who in turn receive this as a tax credit. There were several typologies of incentives (ODYSEE-MURE, 2014):

- A bonus of € 1500 was provided when a car older than 9 years meeting Euro 0, 1 or 2 standards was exchanged for a new vehicle meeting Euro 4 or 5 standards and emitting a maximum of 130gCO₂/km for diesel cars or 140gCO₂/km for others;
- Additional incentives for green and high performance vehicles (purchase incentive of € 1500 for new vehicles running on electricity, hydrogen or methane. This purchase incentive increased to € 3000 if the vehicle emitted 120gCO₂/km, and to € 3500 if it emitted less than that);
- Purchase incentive for liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) vehicles. This incentive amounted to €1500 (€ 2000 if the vehicle emitted less than 120gCO₂/km);
- Lightweight commercial vehicles (a bonus of € 2500 was provided for scrapping a vehicle meeting Euro 0, 1 or 2 standards and registered before 31 December 1999, and purchasing a

⁶⁹ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2007-12-24:244!vig=>

new one. In addition, € 4000 were provided for the purchase of a new "innovative vehicle", running on gas, LPG, hydrogen);

- For motorcycles, scooters and other two-wheel vehicles, a € 500 bonus was provided when purchasing a new 400cc Euro 3 vehicle when combined with the scrapping of a Euro 0 or 1 category vehicle;
- Incentives were also provided for converting existing cars to run on LPG (€ 500) and methane (€ 600).

The 2012 national incentives scheme, instead, was paid out through an ad-hoc fund with a budget of € 50 million for 2013 and € 45 million respectively for 2014 and 2015, mainly targeting the purchase of company and public-use vehicles. Subsequently, the "Stability Law 2013" of 24 December 2012 reduced the overall budget for the three-year period to € 120 million. In compliance with this Decree, the Ministry of Economic Development issued an "Implementing Decree concerning the incentives for the purchase of low emission vehicles" (February 2013), which detailed the procedure for requesting the incentives and the allocation of resources for 2013 (NEEAP, 2014).

f) Implementation network

Both incentives schemes were defined by the National Government. The technical aspects were defined by the Ministry of Economic Development. Finally, also car sellers were involved as they applied the discount on cars sales.

g) Outcomes

Based on NEEAP 2014 data, at January 2014, 2,584 vehicles had been registered, of which 535 electric and 541 hybrid. Most of the vehicles that benefited from the incentives (about 1,820) have CO₂ emissions between 50 and 95 gCO₂/km. No data about final energy savings are provided in Italian NEEAP.

1.2.3.2 Funds related to the “Five-year bus fleet renewal plan”

a) General information

The Stability Law 2014 (L. 27 December 2013, n. 147⁷⁰) has earmarked € 500 million for the purchase of new public transport vehicles, including € 200 million for renewing the railway cars and € 300 million for renewing the bus fleets. These funds are related to a long-standing and multi-year national investments strategy on improvements of local public transport services.

b) Type of policy instrument

The funds related to the “Five-year bus fleet renewal plan” belong to the policy type “Financial Policy Instruments” as they provided economic resources to regional authorities involved in the renewal of their local public transport fleets.

c) Objectives

The funds related to the “Five-year bus fleet renewal plan” objective is to provide funds for a complete renewal over the next five years of the national bus fleet both public and private (NEEAP, 2014) which has an average age of 12 years.

⁷⁰ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2013-12-27:147>

d) Target group

The funds related to the “Five-year bus fleet renewal plan” target groups are Regional authorities. In fact the Italian normative framework entrusted to regional authorities the management of the local public transport services.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The feasibility of launching a 5-year financing plan to renew the bus fleets (around 50 000 vehicles) is currently being assessed and alternative incentive schemes for the private sector are being considered (NEEAP, 2014).

f) Implementation network

The funds are set up by the national Government in its annual Stability Law. These funds will be managed by regional authorities which are in charge of local transport services provision.

g) Outcomes

Based on ASSTRA analysis (ASSTRA, 2014), 7,500 old buses will be substituted by 2019 (the Italian total public bus fleet is about 40,000 buses). According to the NEEAP 2014, this should generate an energy saving of 0.04 Mtoe/year. Total savings in the period 2014-2020 are not available.

Forecast of final energy savings according to the NEEAP:

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
On-site energy consultation	/	/

1.2.4 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

Italy has several dissemination and awareness instruments related to the transport sector. The main national transport regulatory policy instruments are:

- Guide to fuel saving and decreasing CO₂ emission by cars (Guida sul risparmio di carburanti e sulle emissioni di anidride carbonica delle autovetture⁷¹) (Published by MATTM, MIT and MISE);
- National Logistics Platform UIRNET⁷² (Sistema Nazionale della Logistica Integrata e Intermodalità) (D.M. 20 June 2005, n.18T)⁷³;
- Events and initiatives within the European Sustainable Mobility Week;
- National observatory on local public transports policies Osservatorio nazionale sulle politiche per il trasporto pubblico locale (L. 24 December 2007, n.244⁷⁴).

⁷¹ http://www.sviluppoeconomico.gov.it/images/stories/documenti/Guida_Co2_2013_rev_small.pdf

⁷² <https://www.uirnet.it/uirnet/>

⁷³ https://www.uirnet.it/uirnet/resources/cms/documents/Decreto_Ministeriale_18T_del_20.06.2005.pdf

1.2.4.1 National Logistic Platform UIRNET

a) General information

The National Logistic Platform UIRNET, driven by the Ministry of Transport, is a complex web-based system that intends to manage all the movements of freights on road, railroad and on Italian sea. The Platform intends to coordinate at a national level all the logistic activities carried out by the different logistic operators, in order to guarantee a more efficient delivery of Italian freights. Moreover, the UIRNET platform intends to promote inter-mobility and to optimize the interactions among trucks, trains and cargo ships. The National Logistics Platform falls under the broader context of the National Action Plan for Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS), launched in February 2014 by the Ministry of Transport in accordance with Directive 2010/40/EU⁷⁵ (NEEAP, 2014).

b) Type of policy instrument

The National Logistic Platform UIRNET belongs to the policy type “Dissemination and awareness instruments”. It creates a national online platform where logistic operators and public authorities can share data on their freights delivery services and increase their awareness on inefficiency in the freights delivery services.

c) Objectives

The National Logistic Platform UIRNET main objective is to improve the overall efficiency level of national freights delivery services.

d) Target group

The National Logistic Platform UIRNET main target groups are logistic operators. Moreover also national and local public authorities are involved.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The National Logistic Platform UIRNET focuses “on the realization of a localized hardware and software platform which is open and modular and capable of integrating service providers and freights suppliers directed towards logistics process management and freight transport, with the aim of providing various services through the interaction of the various players involved” (UIRNET)⁷⁶. On 28th of December 2006, UIRNet SpA signed an agreement with the Ministry of Transport in order to identify a subject responsible to manage the platform during the years. The UIRNET platform started its operations with a commissioning cost of € 14 million and an annual operating budget of € 2 million for the first three years (NEEAP, 2014). After the start-up phase, the UIRNET platform should not require any further public funding (NEEAP, 2014).

f) Implementation network

The National Logistic Platform UIRNET was launched by the Italian Ministry of Transport. In January 2014 UIRnet S.p.A. launched an European call in project-financing mode to select a private operator able to manage the platform.

⁷⁴ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:legge:2007-12-24;244!vig=2015-09-18>

⁷⁵ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:207:0001:0013:EN:PDF>

⁷⁶ <https://www.uirnet.it/uirnet/>

g) Outcomes

The UIRNET platform, based on NEEAP 2014 data, should have 25,000 users and 8 logistics nodes in the starting phase and in a few years the number of actual users will rise to 250 000 actual users. Thanks to the UIRNET platform, a € 40 billion saving in the entire transport system will be possible (Milano Finanza, 2013). The pilot phase, implemented in 2013, involved more than 800 transport companies and around 10,000 trucks (UIRNET Data). If plan estimates are confirmed, the energy savings achievable in the national road transport would be in the range of 0.5 Mtoe/year. Total savings in the period 2014-2020 are not available.

Forecast of final energy savings according to the NEEAP:

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
On-site energy consultation	/	/

1.2.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

Italy has several instruments for research and development in the transport sector. The main national policy instruments for research and development are:

- Design and implementation of a Green Wheel bicycle (Initiative of Ministry of Environment);
- National “Smart Cities and Communities and Social Innovation” funds 2012 and 2013 (Director Decree 5 July 2012, N.391/Ric⁷⁷);
- National technological maritime platform (Piattaforma Tecnologica Nazionale Marittima) (Dlgs. 21 November 2005, N.284⁷⁸).

1.2.5.1 Design and implementation of a Green Wheel bicycle

a) General information

The Copenhagen Wheel is an international project unveiled on December 2009 at the COP15 United Nations Climate Conference. The project was conceived and developed by the SENSEable City Lab. The prototype bikes were realized with the help of technical partner “Ducati Energia” and funding from the Italian Ministry for the Environment.

⁷⁷ <http://attiministeriali.miur.it/anno-2012/luglio/dd-05072012.aspx>

⁷⁸ <http://www.normattiva.it/uri-res/N2Ls?urn:nir:stato:decreto.legislativo:2005-11-21;284>

b) Type of policy instrument

The Green Wheel bicycle project belongs to the policy type supporting research and development activities.

c) Objectives

The Green Wheel bicycle project objective is developing an electric bike for municipalities able to elaborate traffic data for urban planning activities.

d) Target group

Green Wheel bicycle project's target group are municipalities. These bikes in fact could map pollution levels, traffic congestion and road conditions in real-time in order to provide data for the municipalities transport planning activities.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The prototype bikes were realized with the help of technical partner Ducati Energia and funding from the Ministry for the Environment.

f) Implementation network

The project was conceived and developed by the SENSEable City Lab for the Kobenhavns Kommune. The prototype bikes were realized with the help of technical partner Ducati Energia and funding from the Italian Ministry for the Environment.

g) Outcomes

No data available.

1.2.6 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR IN ITALY

Summary table: Transport					
	Short list of implemented policies and measures	Objective ⁷⁹ (improve system, travel or vehicle efficiency)	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Implementation network
Planning instruments	National infrastructural plan to set up electric vehicles charging points	Develop a national wide electric charging points network	Regions; Italian energy distributors	Dedicated funds and definition of policy and technical standards	Ministry of Infrastructure; Regions; Electric distributors
Regulatory policy instruments	Obligation to input into consumptions biofuels	Supporting national biofuels production and supply chains	Biofuels producers and traditional fuels seller	Obligation to input a quota of biofuels into market	GSE; AEEG
Financial policy instruments	Government subsidies for the purchase of low emissions vehicles	Provide economic support to the renewal of vehicles fleets	Private car owners	Economic support to purchase a new car	National Government; Car sellers
	Funds related to "Five Years bus fleets renewal plan	Complete the renewal of national bus fleets	Regional public authorities	Economic incentives for the purchasing of green buses	National Government; Regional public authorities

⁷⁹ Energy efficiency in the transport sector can be divided into system efficiency (reduce or avoid travel or the need to travel), travel efficiency (shift to more energy efficient modes) and vehicle efficiency (improve the efficiency through vehicle technology).

Dissemination and awareness instruments	National Logistic Platform UIRNET	Sharing data and information among Italian logistic operators	Logistic operators operating in Italy	Share of data and information	Ministry of Transport
Policy instruments for Research and Development	Design and implementation of a Green Wheel bicycle	Developing an electric bike for municipalities able to elaborate traffic data for urban planning activities.	Municipalities	Support from a technical partner and funding from the Ministry for the Environment.	SENSEable City Lab; Ducati Energy; Ministry for the Environment

2. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE REGIONAL / LOCAL LEVEL

The interaction between the different levels (national, regional, local) in energy efficiency policy making has already been covered in D.1.1. Next to national energy efficiency policies, many regions and cities have implemented own climate action plans, energy efficiency action plans, or are part of the Covenant of Mayors. Describing all existing policy instruments or energy efficiency measures, would be too much and is not possible in the framework of this project. Therefore, in this deliverable, specific policy instruments on the regional / local level are exemplarily covered by a case study.

2.1 PRESENTATION OF THE CASE STUDY: METROPOLITAN CITY OF MILAN

- **City / Region:**

Metropolitan City of Milan (until 2014 named: Province of Milan).

The Metropolitan City of Milan is an autonomous territorial entity located in Lombardy (Northern Italy) comprising 134 municipalities, covering 1.575 km² and totalling 3,2 million inhabitants. It has been established through L. 7 April 2014, n. 56⁸⁰, substituting the entity of the Province of Milan.

- **Energy Efficiency Policy / Action:**

In 2006, the Province of Milan adopted the **Provincial Energy Efficiency Programme** (“Programma Provinciale di Efficienza Energetica”, deliberation 739/2006⁸¹ of 23/10/2006), updating the 1996 provincial energy plan. The Programme established a 35.000 toe/year energy saving target (130 kton/CO₂/year) to be accomplished by 2010 targeting the civil and industrial sector. The programme included an **Action Plan** that defined the operative instruments to concretely implement these targets, reducing energy use from fossil fuels and promoting renewable energy, with the aim also to tackle air quality problems.

The Action Plan identified five strategic sectors (Information, Buildings, SMEs, Public Administration, Mobility and Transport) focusing on three pillars:

1. Adoption of a set of rules for the civil sector;
2. Provision of financial incentives to renovate buildings and heating systems;
3. Diffusion of information, communication and education.

The main activities of the Metropolitan City of Milan regarding energy efficiency regard the building sector and are the following:

⁸⁰ <http://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/2014/04/07/14G00069/sg>

⁸¹ http://www.cittametropolitana.mi.it/export/export_14032014/n_energia_dgp_739_2006_allegato_1_programma_a_efficienza_energetica.pdf

Elaboration and dissemination of Guidelines for energy-efficiency oriented Building Regulations⁸²

This activity aims at providing municipalities with common orientations for updating their municipal building regulations taking into account high energy efficiency and environmental quality criteria. The guidelines have been updated in 2014 and they set requirements which go beyond national and regional regulations in force, looking at sustainability criteria and environmental certification protocols.

Management of info-desks (Infoenergia)

Founded in 2006 by the Province of Milan, Infoenergia is an in-house company (public limited liability consortium) currently joined also by the Province of Monza Brianza and 65 municipalities. The company acts through a network of info-desks located in the municipalities (60 municipal info-desks for citizens, 4 info-desks for technicians), carrying out the following functions:

- providing support to technical departments of municipal and provincial authorities regarding energy and environmental issues;
- promoting information and awareness raising towards citizens regarding renewable energy, energy saving and energy efficiency (i.a. the “CalorEfficienza” communication campaign, aimed at diffusing compliance with normative rules regarding heating plants);
- controlling thermal plants in small municipalities (< 40.000 inhabitants).

Infoenergia also provides technical assistance to municipalities in the elaboration of their Sustainable Energy Action plans within the Covenant of Mayors initiative. To date 23 SEAPs regarding 447.564 citizens have been elaborated, also with the financial support of the banking foundation Fondazione Cariplo. The estimated emission reductions from these plans are 327 kton CO₂ (source: Infoenergia website⁸³).

- **Energy Efficiency instruments / measures per sector:**

An interesting measure launched by the Province of Milan to promote energy efficiency in the building sector is the “**Programme for the energy refurbishment of public buildings owned by Municipalities of the Province of Milan**”. This measure concerns the energy refurbishment of public buildings, mainly schools, owned by Municipalities that adhered to the Covenant of Mayors with the support of the Province of Milan. The measure aimed to overcome the problem of the limited capacity of municipalities to finance investments in energy renovation in their properties. A pilot project based on the involvement of third-party financiers (Energy Service Companies - ESCOs) was designed and submitted to the European Investment Bank (EIB). The project was based on a wide database of data obtained through a previous energy auditing activity (700 audited buildings), financed by the banking foundation Fondazione Cariplo.

After the assessment of the application, the EIB approved in 2009 the province investment programme (90 million €) and authorized the use of up to 65 million € as loan to ESCOs, to be selected through public tenders, for the realization of refurbishment activities on public buildings

⁸² Available at:

http://www.cittametropolitana.mi.it/export/sites/default/ambiente/doc/doc_energia_infoenergia_linee_guida_regolamento_edilizio_2014.pdf

⁸³ <http://www.infoenergia.net/bkjoomla/joomla/index.php/notizie/paes>

through the activation of Energy Performance Contracts (EPC) with Guarantee of Result in favour of the Municipalities (each tender corresponds to a grouping of municipalities); the remaining part should be covered by the ESCOs through equity (Zabot, Di Santo, 2013). Energy Performance Contracting is a contract form explicitly aimed to improve the energy performances of building-heating systems through energy renovation⁸⁴. In EPC, the future energy savings deriving from the energy renovation interventions are guaranteed by the contract and they are used to finance the interventions; the remuneration of the ESCO is based on the results effectively achieved (Zabot, Di Santo, 2013). In the investment programme of the Province of Milan, the EPC form enables to repay the EIB's loan through the obtained energy savings. The municipalities will pay a fee to the ESCO calculated each year based on actual performance. Municipalities will benefit since the beginning from a percentage of the savings; in case of underperformance, the fee paid by the municipalities to the ESCO will be lowered, in case of overperformance, the additional savings will be shared by the municipality and the ESCO (Micale et al., 2014). The supply of fuel and electricity is excluded from the Concession. This is the first case of "pure" EPC applied to energy retrofits in the public sector in Italy, since - in the country - energy-saving services are usually bundled with fuel supply in the energy service contracts (Micale et al., 2014).

The programme benefitted also from a technical assistance support through ELENA (European Local ENergy Assistance)⁸⁵. The ELENA grant was used to set up the investment programme support unit; assess existing audits; draw the Terms of Reference; prepare the tender documents, the contracts, negotiate with suppliers and banks; handle any litigation; monitor the results, disseminate and transfer the know-how.

The programme is currently being implemented involving 48 Municipalities with less than 30.000 inhabitants and the Municipality of Milan. The first tender (13 Mln.€) has been awarded, regarding 98 buildings in 16 Municipalities, with interventions such as envelope insulations, Micro-Cogeneration, Heat Pumps, condensation boilers, Solar Thermal, Lighting sensors, BEMS, etc.... Guaranteed Savings are 35%, with a shared saving for Municipalities of 5% and a concession duration of 15 years.

The second tender (two lots, 187 buildings in 31 Municipalities) and the third tender (dedicated to the Municipality of Milan and regarding 38 schools) are in progress.

The implementation of the investment programme has seen delays due to the tendering processes for the selection of the consultants (technical, financial and legal) and for the identification of the financial intermediary, which in the end was identified through a direct negotiation (Micale et al., 2014).

Within an interview with representatives of the Metropolitan City of Milan (energy department), the following lessons learnt have been highlighted:

- This investment programme has engendered a positive relation between the Province of Milan and the single Municipalities and has offered the opportunity of putting Energy Efficiency to the core of their interests;

⁸⁴ EPC is defined as a "contractual arrangement between the beneficiary and the provider (normally an ESCO) of an energy efficiency improvement measure, where investments in that measure are paid for in relation to a contractually agreed level of energy efficiency improvement" (art. 3, comma j, Directive 2006/32/EC).

⁸⁵ ELENA is a grant facility managed by EIB funded by EU budget (CIP/IEE programme) (<http://www.eib.org/products/advising/elena/index.htm>). For the Province of Milan the ELENA support had a 2.16 Mln.€ total budget, of which 1.94 Mln.€ from EIB and 10% of Province of Milan contribution.

- ELENA Technical Assistance has proven to be essential for the development of an innovative tender documentation, the Energy Supply Contracting being yet largely predominant over Energy Performance Contracting in Italy;
- Scarce financial autonomy of Municipalities due to the “Stability Pact” together with a lack of legal and technical knowledge of EPC have represented major barriers to the implementation of this EIB Investment Programme, hence without the ELENA fund and the Province of Milan acting as Support Structure this initiative would have not taken place;
- EIB should directly release the line of credit to the winning ESCOs, because banks are reluctant to assume the risk and thus apply high interest rates. Finding the Intermediary Financial Institution has proven to be very challenging and time consuming.
- Time and costs needed to train the personnel of the Municipalities involved is often underestimated as well as the time required to run the administrative procedures.

- **Interaction between national and local policies:**

Energy efficiency of buildings is a cross-cutting topic among national, regional and local policies. The policy framework at **national level** has been described in the previous chapters, and reflects the transposition of European directives on the topic.

The policy framework at **regional level** is complex, since in Italy energy issues are governed under a system of “concurrent legislative powers”, with the regions having legislative powers in the framework of key principles determined by the central government. Each region has therefore its set of laws and schemes for energy efficiency in the building sector.

The **Lombardy Region**, in which the Metropolitan City of Milan is localized, is considered among the best performers in Italy on energy efficiency⁸⁶. The Region has implemented several policy instruments to address energy efficiency in buildings:

- a set of **regional laws** regarding regional energy and air quality policy and specific regulations regarding energy efficiency and energy certification of buildings⁸⁷;
- an **Energy Action Plan**, in place since 2007 (PAE) and an **Energy and Environmental Regional Programme** (PEAR), which is currently being elaborated, both targeting the buildings sector;
- a series of **energy cadastres**, in place since 2007, which represent relevant sources of information for energy efficiency policies and that display data also in Opendata format; these include the Regional Energy Cadastre of Buildings (CEER - Catasto Energetico Edifici Regionale⁸⁸); and the Unique Regional Cadastre of Heating Plants (CURIT - Catasto Unico Regionale Impianti Termici⁸⁹);
- an **information system on Sustainable Energy Policies** (SIRENA20⁹⁰), developed with the support of the EU-funded project LIFE+ “Factor 20”, which enables the planning and monitoring of GHG reduction, energy saving and renewable energy policies in the region; the system includes a set of operational tools for municipalities and provinces participating in the Covenant of Mayors.

⁸⁶ <http://www.efficientaenergetica.enea.it/l-efficienza-energetica-nelle-regioni/lombardia/politiche-regionali-in-materia-di-efficienza-energetica.aspx>

⁸⁷ A complete list can be found at: http://www.cened.it/normativa_regionale.

⁸⁸ <http://www.cened.it/ceer>

⁸⁹ <http://www.curit.it/>

⁹⁰ <http://www.energielombardia.eu/sirena20>

Looking at the **local level**, in January 2013 622 municipalities on 1546 of the Lombardy Region had adhered to the Covenant of Mayors, of which 415 with a SEAP submitted to the European Commission (elaboration by Factor 20 project on CoM data⁹¹).

Figure 8: Covenant of Mayors – Signatories in Lombardy Region (2013) (table and figure)

	N. of municipalities	Inhabitants	Municipalities with signed adhesion	Municipalities with signed adhesion and submitted SEAP	Total Municipalities	Municipalities coordinated by the province
Bergamo	244	1.075.582	71	143	214	182
Brescia	206	1.230.159	14	85	99	
Como	162	584.762	5	2	7	
Cremona	115	360.223	12	8	20	
Lecco	90	335.420	4	27	31	4
Lodi	61	223.639	3	9	12	
Mantova	70	409.775	19	14	33	8
Milano	134	3.096.997	20	75	95	94
Monza e Brianza	55	833.348	11	19	30	10
Pavia	190	539.238	21	3	24	
Sondrio	78	182.084	1	19	20	
Varese	141	871.448	26	11	37	
Lombardy Region	1546	9.742.675	207	415	622	298

Source: Factor 20 project, elaboration of CoM data 2013

As shown in the graph, the province of Bergamo, Brescia and Milan are those with the highest number of signatories.

The capital city of Milan, in particular, joined the CoM in 2008 and is currently completing a participative process in which the SEAP proposal has been presented. Public and private buildings are

⁹¹ http://www.factor20.it/PattoDeiSindaci_ComuniLombardi

key strategic sectors of Milan's SEAP, accounting, respectively, for 5% and 55% of total expected emission reductions by 2020 (Comune di Milano, AMAT, 2015).

Among the several policy instruments foreseen in Milan's SEAP, in October 2014 Milan adopted its new Municipal Buildings Regulations, which foresee high energy efficiency mandatory targets for new buildings (A class) and renovations, as well as an incentive system (volumetric incentive) based on increasing levels of sustainability in buildings.

- **Discussion / Recommendations:**

The case study of the Metropolitan City of Milan shows how in Italy energy efficiency in the building sector is a cross-cutting issue being targeted by policies at the national, regional and local level. In the Lombardy region, several supporting instruments are in place to guide municipalities in their sustainable energy planning efforts, both from the Regional Authority, the provincial authority (now Metropolitan City) and from other subjects of the territory, such as the banking foundation Fondazione Cariplo. The availability of data and monitoring (such as the cadastre of energy performance certificates and heating plants) represents a key excellence of the region and a valid source of information to plan, implement and monitor effective policies on the topic.

Looking in particular at the refurbishment programme on public buildings promoted by the Metropolitan City of Milan, the case is particularly interesting since it has seen the collaboration of a wider metropolitan authority with single municipalities of its territory, bundling projects that otherwise would not have had enough size to be brought forward. Furthermore, the experience is innovative in Italy since it promotes Energy Performance Contracting instead of Energy Supply Contracting which is currently more diffused. The experience is currently in progress and it is not possible to measure its actual energy impacts. Nonetheless, the lessons learnt show that some barriers exist in the implementation of Energy Performance Contracting in Italy (such as long times of procedures and bureaucracy; lack of legal and technical knowledge on EPC; scarce will of financial institutions to assume risks when energy efficiency projects are considered), as well as opportunities (energy efficiency potential of the building sector; supporting role of technical assistance in preparing tenders and related documentation).

After Milan, also other Italian provinces have launched EPC schemes, including the Provinces of Modena, Chieti and Padova.

- **Further information:**

<http://www.cittametropolitana.mi.it/ambiente/energia/index.html>

ANNEXES

REFERENCES

ASSTRA (2014). Legge di stabilità, arriva la svolta per rinnovare gli autobus. *Press release*.

URL: http://www.asstra.it/stampa/visualizza_comunicato_stampa/archivio-2014/legge-di-stabilita-arriva-la-svolta-per--rinnovare-gli-autobus-.html

Cassa Depositi e Prestiti (2012), Il Fondo Kyoto per la riduzione delle emissioni di gas serra.

URL: <http://www.cdp.it/static/upload/kyo/kyoto.pdf>

Comune di Milano, AMAT (2015), Proposta di PAES Piano di Azione per l’Energia Sostenibile e il Clima. Pianificare e programmare per ridurre le emissioni di gas serra. *Presentation*.

URL:

<http://mediagallery.comune.milano.it/cdm/objects/changeme:32101/datastreams/dataStream7742621732586123/content>

D’Oca S., Corgnati S., Buso T., (2013), Smart meters and energy savings in Italy: Determining the effectiveness of persuasive communication in dwellings, *Energy Research & Social Science*, Volume 3, September 2014, Pages 131–142.

ENEA (2014), Rapporto Annuale Efficienza Energetica 2014.

ENEA (2015), Rapporto Annuale Efficienza Energetica 2015 (RAEE 2015).

URL: <http://www.enea.it/it/produzione-scientifica/pdf-volumi/raee-2015.pdf>

Energy Strategy Group (2013), Energy Efficiency Report. L’efficienza energetica in Italia: soluzioni tecnologiche ed opportunità di business nell’industria, terziario e la Pubblica Amministrazione.

GSE (2013), Obbligo di immissione in consumo e accreditamento degli impianti di produzione di biocarburanti premiali. Procedura applicativa.

URL:

http://www.gse.it/it/Qualifiche%20e%20certificati/GSE_Documenti/Biocarburanti/Procedura%20Soggetti%20Obbligati%20e%20Produttori.pdf

IEA, (2015). IEA Energy Efficiency. Policies and Measures databases. Italy.

URL: <http://www.iea.org/policiesandmeasures/energyefficiency/?country=Italy>

Micale V., Deason J., Hervé-Mignucci M. (2014), Early Lessons on Introducing Energy Performance Contracts in Italy: Milan’s Energy Efficiency Program. *San Giorgio Group Brief*.

URL: <http://climatepolicyinitiative.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/09/SGG-Brief-Early-Lessons-on-Introducing-Energy-Performance-Contracts-in-Italy-Milans-Energy-Efficiency-Program.pdf>

Milano Finanza (2013). The logistic revolution. *Article*.

URL: <https://www.uirnet.it/uirnet/en/uirnetnewviewer.wp?contentId=NEW1102>

Ministry of Economic Development. (2013). National Energy Strategy 2013 (SEN).

URL:

http://www.encharter.org/fileadmin/user_upload/Energy_policies_and_legislation/Italy_2013_National_Energy_Strategy_ENG.pdf

Ministry of Economic Development. (2014a). Italian Energy Efficiency Action Plan 2014 (NEEAP).

URL:

https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/2014_neeap_en_italy.pdf

Ministry of Economic Development (2014b), Application of article 7 of directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency obligation scheme. Notification of methodology.

URL: https://ec.europa.eu/energy/sites/ener/files/documents/article7_en_italy.pdf

ODYSEE-MURE (2014). Database-query.

URL: http://www.measures-odyssee-mure.eu/output1A_mr.asp

Reuters (2013), Europe to follow Italy's lead on smart meters. *Article*.

URL: <http://www.reuters.com/article/2013/05/30/energy-efficiency-smartmeters-italy-idUSL5N0EA3HL20130530>

Zabot, S., Di Santo D. (2013), Guida ai Contratti di Prestazione Energetica negli Edifici Pubblici. *Ente per le nuove tecnologie, l'energia e l'ambiente and Federazione Italiana per l'uso Razionale dell'Energia*.

URL: http://www.tazioborges.it/Documenti/Guida_agli_EPC.pdf

Websites (last visit: July 2015)

<https://ec.europa.eu/energy/en/april-2015-energy-efficiency-buildings-commission-asks-italy-netherlands-and-poland-comply-eu-rules>

<http://www.energiaefficienza.enea.it/>

<http://www.energiaefficienza.enea.it/politiche-e-strategie-1/politiche-e-strategie-in-italia/paee/paee-2014.aspx>

https://www.enel.it/it-IT/eventi_news/news/la-rivoluzione-dei-contatori-elettronici/p/090027d981930477

<http://www.energiaefficienza.enea.it/>

<http://www.agenziaefficienzaenergetica.it/>

<http://www.agenziaentrate.gov.it/wps/content/Nsilib/Nsi/Home/CosaDeviFare/Richiedere/Agevolazioni/Detrazione+riqualificazione+energetica+55/Scheda+informativa+riqualificazione+55/>

<http://www.iea.org/policiesandmeasures/energyefficiency/?country=Italy>

<http://www.gse.it/it/CertificatiBianchi/Modalit%C3%A0%20di%20realizzazione%20dei%20progetti/Schede%20tecniche/Pagine/default.aspx>

http://www.nextville.it/Archivio_Incentivi_e_agevolazioni/960/Archivio_Fondo_rotativo_per_Kyoto

http://www.formazione.enea.it/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=3&Itemid=105

<http://store.uni.com/magento-1.4.0.1/index.php/uni-cei-11352-2014.html>

http://store.uni.com/magento-1.4.0.1/index.php/uni-cei-11352-2014.html?_store=en&_from_store=it

<http://www.gse.it/it/CertificatiBianchi/Accreditamento%20Operatori/Pagine/default.aspx#2>

http://www.mit.gov.it/mit/mop_all.php?p_id=14588

<http://www.gse.it/it/EnergiaFacile/guide/Trasporti/Biocarburanti/Pages/default.aspx>

<http://www.ilsole24ore.com/art/norme-e-tributi/2014-10-22/manovrapiano-rinnovo-parco-autobus-170458.shtml?uuid=ABHZki5B>

<https://www.uirnet.it/uirnet/>

<https://www.uirnet.it/uirnet/en/uirnetnewviewer.wp?contentId=NEW1102>

Websites - Case study (last visit: July 2015)

<http://www.cened.it>

<http://www.cened.it/ceer>

http://www.cened.it/normativa_regionale

<http://www.cittametropolitana.mi.it/ambiente/energia/>

<http://www.curit.it/>

<http://www.efficienzaenergetica.enea.it/l-efficienza-energetica-nelle-regioni/lombardia/politiche-regionali-in-materia-di-efficienza-energetica.aspx>

<http://www.energielombardia.eu/sirena20>

http://www.factor20.it/PattoDeiSindaci_ComuniLombardi

<http://www.infoenergia.net>

<http://www.infoenergia.net/bkjoomla/joomlaa/index.php/notizie/paes>

HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.1.2

STATUS-QUO ANALYSIS OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICIES IN 8 EU COUNTRIES

**PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT**

NATIONAL REPORT FOR SERBIA

30.07.2015.

Partner: Centre for Energy, University of Belgrade – Faculty of Mining and Geology

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

OXFORD
BROOKES
UNIVERSITY

Wuppertal Institute
for Climate, Environment
and Energy

SEI

STOCKHOLM
ENVIRONMENT
INSTITUTE

Institution: University of Belgrade – Faculty of Mining and Geology

Steering Committee member ⁽¹⁾: Prof. Dejan Ivezić

Prepared by: Prof. Dejan Ivezić, Dr. Marija Živković, Assoc. Prof. Miloš Tanasijević, Miodrag Gluščević, Aleksandar Madžarević

⁽¹⁾ *The Steering Committee member has the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the report.*

HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme, under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors’ views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACRONYMS	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
1. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL	7
1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE BUILDINGS SECTOR	7
1.1.1 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS	7
1.1.2 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS/INFORMATIVE POLICY INSTRUMENTS	13
1.1.3 ECONOMIC POLICY INSTRUMENTS	14
1.1.4 . CAPACITY BUILDING AND NETWORKING	16
1.1.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR THE PROMOTION OF ENERGY SERVICES	19
1.1.6 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT AND BEST AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGY (BAT) PROMOTION.....	20
1.1.7 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR IN SERBIA	22
1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR	24
1.2.1 PLANNING INSTRUMENTS	25
1.2.2 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS	28
1.2.3 FINANCIAL POLICY INSTRUMENTS	30
1.2.4 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS.....	30
1.2.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT	30
1.2.6 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR IN #COUNTRY#	31
2. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE REGIONAL / LOCAL LEVEL	33
2.1 PRESENTATION OF THE CASE STUDY CITY OF NIŠ	33
REFERENCES	39

List of Tables

Table 1: Estimation of final energy savings according the second EEAP	9
Table 2: Estimation of final energy savings according the second EEAP	11
Table 3: Projection of final energy savings as a result of introduction of energy management system	13
Table 4: Projection of final energy savings (The Second EEAP)	14
Table 5: Projection of final energy savings according to the second EEAP	20
Table 6: Achieved and forecast of final energy savings (The Second EEAP)	30
Table 7: Main elements of the measure: Education and behavioral change of the buildings users in objects owned by the City of Niš (SEAP)	36
Table 8: Main elements of the measure: System for Centralized Management of Traffic on the territory of City of Niš (SEAP)	37
Table 9: Projections of energy consumption and CO2 emissions till 2020 of the buildings sector per scenarios	37
Table 10: Projections of energy consumption and CO2 emissions till 2020 of the transport sector per scenarios	38

ACRONYMS

ECTS	European Credit Transfer System
EEAP	Energy Efficiency Action Plan
ESCO	Energy Service Company
IEE	International Energy Agency
IRAP	International Road Assessment Programme
MIFF	Multiannual Indicative Financial Framework
Mtoe	Million Tons of Oil Equivalent
NPI	National Plan for Integration with the EU
RSD	Republic of Serbia Dinar
SAA	Stabilization and Association Agreement
SEAP	Sustainable Energy Action Plan
SEC	Swedish Export Credit Corporation
UN	United Nations
UNECE	United Nations Economic Commission for Europe

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Republic of Serbia has adopted the Law on Efficient Use of Energy (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013a) and The Second Energy Efficiency Action Plan (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b), and made a significant step towards the transposition of the energy efficiency acquis. However, more needs to be done in the near future for full implementation of the energy efficiency acquis (Energy Community, 2015).

Also, The Republic of Serbia has recently adopted several regulations that promote energy efficiency in the buildings sector. These regulations are in accordance with the Law on Planning and Construction (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2009, 2014a). This Law was the first legal act that introduced energy efficiency principals in Serbia's buildings sector. Next set of adopted regulations and rulebooks are based on the legal framework provided by the Law on Efficient Use of Energy. Together, these documents make the legal basis for policy instruments related to energy efficiency in buildings.

These policy instruments include regulatory, economic and financial instruments, as well as capacity building and networking. The main policy instruments in the buildings sector are: Minimum energy performance requirements for new or reconstructed buildings, Energy audit (mandatory), Energy management system in buildings, Energy labeling, Subsidy, Education and Training for energy managers, Education and training for energy efficiency in buildings, Model of Energy Service Agreement for Public buildings, Funding for research in energy efficiency.

Compared to the buildings sector, policy instruments for improvement of energy efficiency in the transport sector are less developed. Planning instruments are developed based on the Law on Road Traffic Safety: Improvements of bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure, Traffic calming, and Traffic management systems.

Regulatory policy instruments related to energy efficiency in transport are based on mixture of regulations related to energy sector, but also to trade, market regulation, environment, etc.: Fuel economy standards/vehicle CO₂-emission standards, Fuel quality standards. Currently, there are no specific financial policy instruments dedicated to support improvement of energy efficiency in the transport sector in Serbia.

As an example for implementation of energy efficiency measures at local level the case of the city of Niš is explained. According to the Ordinance on establishing an unified list of Regions and Local Self-governments per Level of Development for 2014¹ Niš belongs to the first, most developed group of municipalities in Serbia. In terms of dealing with local energy issues the City of Niš is one of the better performing in Serbian context. The City of Niš signed Covenant of Mayors Charter in July 2011 and submitted Sustainable Energy Action Plan (SEAP) in December 2014². SEAP is covering period till year 2020 and sets indicative target for CO₂ emissions to 21% compared to baseline levels of 2010.

According to the SEAP, the buildings sector is the most important in terms of reduction of CO₂ emissions for the upcoming period till 2020. Therefore, majority of measures, 25 of them, belong to the buildings sector. Most of the measures are energy efficiency related, but there are some that promote utilization of renewables. All measures in the buildings sector are divided in five subgroups: general measures, promotional, informational and educational measures and activities, measures in

¹ [Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia", No. 104/2014, 2014;](#)

<http://www.regionalnirazvoj.gov.rs/Lat/ShowNARRFolder.aspx?mi=171> (30.07.2015)

² http://www.covenantofmayors.eu/about/signatories_en.html?city_id=2996&seap (30.07.2015)

residential and public buildings owned by the City, measures in residential sector including collective and individual housing and measures in commercial and service buildings.

SEAP defines 17 measures to reduce CO₂ emissions from the transport sector in the City of Niš, which are divided into 5 categories: legislative and planning measures, promotion, information and education measures and activities, specific measures and activities for private and commercial vehicles, specific measures and activities for the vehicles owned by the City, specific measures and activities for the public transport.

Regarding improvement of energy efficiency of buildings, general measure in the buildings sector - Education and behavioral change of the buildings users in objects owned by the City of Niš is described, while for the transport sector the System for Centralized Management of Traffic on the territory of City of Niš is presented.

1. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL

The Republic of Serbia has adopted the Law on Efficient Use of Energy (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013a) and the Second Energy Efficiency Action Plan (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b), and made a significant step towards the transposition of the energy efficiency acquis. However, more needs be done in the near future for full implementation of the energy efficiency acquis (Energy Community, 2015). Development and adoption of a comprehensive set of secondary legislation based on the Law on Efficient Use of Energy is necessary precondition for implementation of comprehensive set of policy instruments. Therefore, set of current and here presented policy instruments is relatively modest.

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE BUILDINGS SECTOR

The Republic of Serbia has recently adopted several regulations which deal with and promote energy efficiency in the buildings sector. These regulations are in accordance with the Law on Planning and Construction (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2009, 2014a). This Law was the first legal act which introduced energy efficiency principals in legal framework of Serbia. Another set of regulations and rulebooks follow the Law on Efficient Use of Energy and tackle the issue of energy efficiency in buildings more or less directly. They address the buildings sector in terms of regulation, but also financing and capacity building. While the Law on Planning and Construction is completely covered by secondary legislations, this is still not the case with the Law on Efficient Use of Energy.

Serbia proclaimed several measures, to improve efficiency in buildings, through the EEAPs and back them up as policy instruments with regulations and rulebooks. These policy instruments include regulatory, economic and financial instruments, as well as capacity building and networking. The main policy instruments in the buildings sector are related to:

- Minimum requirements for energy performance in buildings,
- Energy audit (mandatory),
- Energy management system in buildings,
- Energy labeling,
- Subsidy,
- Education and training for energy managers,
- Education and training for energy efficiency in buildings,
- Model of Energy Service Agreement for Public Buildings,
- Funding for research in energy efficiency.

1.1.1 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS

Three regulatory policy instruments are recognized within this class of existing instruments targeting the buildings sector. The Law on Planning and Construction (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013a) has established minimum requirements for energy performance of buildings and it is fully implemented. Energy audit (mandatory) and energy management system in buildings are instruments established by the Law on Efficient Use of Energy, and their implementation is on very beginning.

1.1.1.1 Minimum requirements for energy performance for new and reconstructed buildings

a) General information

This policy instrument is related to the Serbian transposition of relevant provisions of Directive 2010/31/EU. Legal base are the Law on Construction and Planning, the Law on Efficient Use of Energy, the Rulebook on Energy Efficiency of Buildings (Ministry of Environment, Mining and Spatial Planning, 2011a) and the Rulebook on Conditions, Content and Manner of Issuance of Certificates of Energy Performance of Buildings (Ministry of Environment, Mining and Spatial Planning, 2011b). These regulations that govern energy efficiency in the buildings sector, prescribe the energy performance of buildings, the manner of calculating the thermal properties of buildings, energy requirements for new and existing buildings, as well as conditions, content and manner of issuing certificates for the energy performance of buildings. Furthermore, the rulebooks stipulate obligation of making the study on energy efficiency of a building, which should be enclosed with documentation for issuing of a building permit. Finally they define that energy certificate should be enclosed within the request for occupancy permit.

b) Type of policy instrument

This policy instrument principally belongs to regulatory policy instruments, but also have awareness raising and informative purpose.

c) Objectives

Objective of this policy initiative is to ensure improvement of quality of design, used materials and building technology, in order to achieve improvement of energy performance of buildings. Furthermore, it is aimed to guaranty and provide document of certain level of energy performance for all types of buildings. The objective is to save a total of 9.98 PJ of energy by 2018.

d) Target group

Target groups are owners, users and investors in public, commercial and residential buildings.

Energy certificate is not requested for following buildings:

- 1) Existing buildings for selling, renting, reconstructed or rehabilitated with a net surface area of less than 50 m²;
- 2) Buildings with planned life time of two years or less;
- 3) Buildings of a temporary purpose (for example accommodation of people and building materials during construction);
- 4) Workshops, production halls, industrial buildings and other commercial buildings which in accordance with their purpose, must be held open for more than half of working time, if not equipped with air curtain;
- 5) Buildings for religious rites;
- 6) Existing buildings which are sold, or ownership right is transferred in bankruptcy procedure in the case of forced sale or enforcement;
- 7) Buildings that are under a protection and in which fulfillment of energy efficiency requirements would conflict with protection requirements;
- 8) Buildings which are not heated, or are heated to a temperature up to + 12 ° C.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Minimal requirements in terms of energy performance of the buildings stipulated in two mentioned rulebooks are for newly built buildings class "C" and for renovated existing buildings improvement of at least one energy class.

f) Implementation network

The most significant role in implementation of this policy instrument has the Ministry of construction, transport and infrastructure, Department of energy efficiency and construction products³ that oversees and regulates the processes, and the Chamber of Engineers which is in charge for training energy auditors and organizations licensed for issuing energy certificates for buildings.

Conduct procedures regarding obtaining energy certificate is as follows:

First step is preparation of the Elaborate of energy efficiency of the building (whether existing or in design phase). The Elaborate can be issued only by licensed energy efficiency engineer for buildings. The aforementioned study serves as a mandatory document for obtaining construction permits for objects that are only planned for construction.

After preparing the Study, the authorized legal entity - organizations licensed for issuing energy certificates for buildings (with minimum 3 responsible energy efficiency engineers for buildings with appropriate licenses) prepares and issues the building energy certificate.

g) Outcomes

Calculations made during the determination of national typology of residential buildings in Serbia (Jovanović et al., 2012) created in accordance with IEE Tabula project,⁴ have shown that the first level of energy recovery (in accordance with this policy instrument) can provide savings of a minimum 25% of the energy needed for heating. The second EEAP quoted potential for energy saving of this particular policy instrument for the period 2012-2018 of 0,0848 Mtoe in residential sector and 0,0535 Mtoe in public and commercial sector.

Forecast of final energy savings according to the second EEAP is presented in Table 1. Data about cost-effectiveness are not available.

Table 1: Estimation of final energy savings according the second EEAP

Policy instrument	Savings 2010-2012	Savings total 2012-2018
Minimum energy performance requirements for new or reconstructed buildings		9.98 PJ

1.1.1.2 Energy audit (mandatory)

a) General information

The Law on Efficient Use of Energy introduced energy audit as mandatory information instrument. According to the Law, energy audit has been defined as “systematic procedure for collecting

³ <http://www.mgsi.gov.rs/cir/odsek/odsek-za-energetsku-efikasnost-i-gradjevinske-proizvode>

⁴ www.building-typology.eu

necessary information and knowledge about existing level and manner of production, transport, distribution and use of energy in building, manufacturing process, private and public service, with the purpose to define and to quantify possibilities for economically feasible and efficient energy use". The Law prescribes general content of Report on conducted energy audit. This document should contain (in the case of buildings):

- Energy balance of the building;
- Evaluation of the existing level of energy efficiency of the building;
- Proposed measures for increasing energy efficiency of the building that is a subject of examination;
- Assessment of achievable energy savings and reduction of CO₂ emissions for each of the proposed measures, and estimation of total achievable energy savings and overall reduction of CO₂ emissions in the case of simultaneous introduction of energy efficiency measures, including economic and financial analysis;
- The final expert opinion with the proposal of measures for effective energy use to be implemented;
- All other information relevant to evaluation of energy efficiency and proposed measures for efficient use of energy.

Authorized energy advisor shall perform energy audit. Authorized energy advisor is natural or legal person, evidenced in the registry of authorized energy advisors.

This instrument is still not in force, as secondary legislation necessary for its conduction is still not developed. The only document adopted so far is the Rulebook on conditions in terms of personnel, equipment and facilities of the organization that conducted the training for energy managers and authorized energy advisors (Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2015a).

b) Type of policy instrument

Energy audit according to Law on Efficient Use of Energy is classified as a regulatory policy instrument, as it is mandatory. However, this is the policy instrument that combines obligation with information, motivation and advice.

c) Objectives

Energy audit should define and quantify possibilities for economically feasible and efficient energy use in buildings. Energy audit shall be used for identification and understanding options for energy savings, and their prioritizing in accordance to conducted economic analysis.

d) Target group

According to the Law on Efficient Use of Energy, the obligation to perform energy audit refers to:

- 1) Facilities and buildings used by public administration bodies and other bodies of the Republic of Serbia, autonomous provinces, local government authorities with more than 20,000 inhabitants, as well as other public services that use facilities in public ownership, with an usable area of more than 500 m²;
- 2) Buildings or parts of buildings which are classified into one of the energy classes (as defined by the Rulebook on Conditions, Content and Manner of Issuance of Certificates of Energy Performance of Buildings (Ministry of Environment, Mining and Spatial Planning, 2011b));
- 3) Buildings and parts of buildings in case of change of purpose, change of the owner, or if they are intended for renting.

Owners of buildings or parts of buildings mentioned above are obliged to perform an energy audit at least once every 10 years.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Rules and influencing mechanisms are still not prescribed.

f) Implementation network

Ministry of Mining and Energy (Department for energy efficiency and renewable energy)⁵ has prescribed conditions in terms of personnel, equipment and facilities for the organizations which conduct the training for energy managers and authorized energy advisors. Department for energy efficiency and renewable energy within Ministry of Mining and Energy is responsible for the register of authorized energy advisors, while responsible Minister issues appropriate licenses. The same Ministry is in charge for the database with conducted energy audits. Ministry should prescribe data that will be collected, methodology and terms and manner for collecting, as well as forms to be filled in with collected data.

g) Outcomes

According to the Second EEAP this policy instrument is closely connected to proposed financial instruments (credit lines, subsidies, loans) and introduction of Energy Efficiency Fund. Estimated potential for energy savings according to the second EEAP, as a result of synergy of these instruments for the period 2010-2018 is 0.0436 Mtoe in residential sector and 0.0170 Mtoe in public and commercial sector (Table 2). Data about cost-effectiveness are not available.

Table 2: Estimation of final energy savings according the second EEAP

Policy instrument	Savings 2010-2012	Savings total 2012-2018
Energy audit (mandatory)	-	8.94 PJ

1.1.1.3 Energy management system in buildings**a) General information**

The Law on Efficient Use of Energy has created a legal base for establishing the system of energy management. Introduction and implementation of energy management system should help the public administration bodies, autonomous province, local self-governments with more than 20,000 inhabitants, and other public services using the facilities in the public property, as well as consumers of energy in the service sector, which consume energy above the limit (to be determined by the Government through adequate regulation), to reduce energy consumption in accordance with the requirements defined in the same regulation (this regulation is in the process of preparation).

This instrument is still not in force, as secondary legislation necessary for its conduction is still not issued. The only documents are those concerning training of energy managers: the Rulebook on conditions in terms of personnel, equipment and facilities of the organization that conducted the training for energy managers and authorized energy advisors (Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2015a) and the Rulebook on the manner of implementation and content of training program for energy managers, expenditures for attending the training courses, and detailed conditions, curriculum, and taking of the examination for energy managers (Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2015b).

⁵ <http://mre.gov.rs/energetska-efikasnost.php>

b) Type of policy instrument

Energy management system belongs to regulatory policy instruments, but also has awareness raising and informative purpose. Implementation in municipalities' and government's buildings is especially important, because public sector should be an example of good practice, in implementation energy efficiency policy.

c) Objectives

The main objective of introducing energy management system in buildings is reduction of energy consumption in public and commercial buildings. The designated organizations define targets for energy consumption reduction and prepare energy efficiency plans and programs in order achieve proposed targets in the most convenient manner - through organization and investment. The objective is to save a total of 1.87 PJ of energy by 2018.

d) Target group

Target groups for energy management system's implementation in buildings are bodies of public administration and other authorities of the Republic of Serbia, authorities of the autonomous province, authorities and bodies of local self-governments with a population exceeding 20,000, and other public services using buildings in public ownership, as well as companies whose core activity is in the sector of trading and services (if they consume more energy than prescribed by the Government) and companies whose core activity is in the manufacturing sector and posses facilities which jointly (in manufacturing and trading and services) consume more energy than prescribed.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Designated organizations will be required to appoint an energy manager, with the appropriate license, who will be responsible for monitoring and analyzing energy consumption data, planning and implementing the energy efficiency measures.

The designated organization prepares energy efficiency plans and programs, and informs Ministry of Mining and Energy (Department for energy efficiency and renewable energy) on achieved results of their implementation annually. Designated organizations from public and commercial sectors are required to conduct energy audits at least once every 10 years.

Rules and influencing mechanisms are still not prescribed by appropriate rulebooks.

f) Implementation network

Ministry of Mining and Energy (Department for energy efficiency and renewable energy) prescribed conditions in terms of personnel, equipment and facilities of the organization that conducted the training for energy managers and authorized energy advisors. This Ministry is responsible for the register of authorized energy advisors, and responsible Minister issues appropriate licenses. The same Ministry is in charge for the database with conducted energy audits. Ministry should prescribe data that shall be collected, methodology and terms and manner for collecting, as well as forms to be filled in with collected data.

g) Outcomes

According to the second EEAP, in order to establish a system of energy management, Ministry of Mining and energy has provided grants from Japan and the UNDP. The Japanese project will help to establish a training program for energy managers, prepare bylaws, establish a training center for energy managers and energy advisors, as well as databases and integrated platform for the collection and analysis of data submitted by designated organizations. UNDP will donate a database for energy management at the local level. The EEAP envisages that the first saving can be achieved in 2015, and gives projection of final energy savings (Table 3). Data about cost-effectiveness are not available.

Table 3: Projection of final energy savings as a result of introduction of energy management system

Policy instrument	Savings 2010-2012	Savings total 2012-2018
Energy management system	-	1.87 PJ

1.1.2 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS/INFORMATIVE POLICY INSTRUMENTS

Energy Labeling is the only policy instrument that is classified in this category. Activities related to energy labeling in Serbia begun in 2005/06 when Energy Efficiency Agency of the Republic of Serbia (ceased to exist in 2012) conducted a promotion and raising awareness campaign for usage of energy-efficient household appliances. The campaign included video on household appliances` energy labeling, and distribution of 996,000 leaflets related to energy labeling of appliances (The Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b). The effect of this measure wasn't directly measurable, but it coincides with the period when all major retailers begin to label home appliances, although it was not mandatory at the time.

1.1.2.1 Energy Labeling

a) General information

With the enforcement of the Law on Efficient Use of Energy in 2013, the energy labeling of household appliances became mandatory. By adoption of the regulation (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013c) and rulebooks (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014a-g) on the labeling of energy-related products in 2013 and 2014 full transposition of Directive 2010/30/EU and Delegated Acts is achieved.

b) Type of policy instrument

Energy labeling belongs to the policy type "Energy information and advice". It combines information, motivation and advice.

c) Objectives

The objective of energy labeling is to reduce electricity consumption by introducing more energy-efficient household appliances (refrigerators, stoves, washing machines, dishwashers, air conditioners, electrical lamps and luminaires, etc.). The objective is to save a total of 0.5 PJ of energy by 2018.

d) Target group

Target group for energy savings is residential sector, i.e. households. Obligations of labeling have suppliers and vendors of products.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The Regulation (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013c) prescribes that, based on Rulebooks (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014a-g) the following products shall be labeled regarding energy consumption, and/or energy efficiency: household refrigerating devices, TVs,

household washing machines, household dishwashers, electric ovens, air-conditioning devices and electrical lamps and luminaires. The Regulation likewise regulates: the obligations of suppliers and vendors regarding products being labeled, the contents of the energy efficiency label, the energy efficiency classes, obligations regarding the data sheet and technical documentation of the product, methodology for determination of energy efficiency class, obligations during the remote sale of products, as well as inspection supervision.

f) Implementation network

Ministry of Mining and Energy and market inspection are directly responsible for conducting this policy instrument. Also, the role of NGOs and consumers associations in the cases of regulations violation is very important.

g) Outcomes

The second EEAP analysed results of implementation energy labelling in period of implementation of the first EEAP when it was voluntary, and found that the energy saving was 0.00228 Mtoe. For the interior lighting, according to the first EEAP, the expected target of savings was almost reached, while for household appliances saving wasn't determined. Table 4 presents projection of final energy savings according to the second EEAP. Data about cost-effectiveness are not available.

Table 4: Projection of final energy savings (The Second EEAP)

Policy instrument	Savings 2010-2012	Savings total 2012-2018
Energy Labeling	0.095 PJ	0.5 PJ

1.1.3 ECONOMIC POLICY INSTRUMENTS

The second EEAP envisaged different economic policy instruments for supporting activities and measures related to energy efficiency. However, the only implemented instrument is subsidizing from the Budget Fund for energy efficiency.

1.1.3.1 Subsidy

a) General information

The Law on Efficient Use of Energy provided the framework for establishment of the Budget Fund for energy efficiency, with an aim to provide funds, to finance or co-finance projects, programs and activities directed to increase efficiency of energy use. The Budget Fund was established in 2013 (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013d). Financing or co-financing from the Budget Fund shall be governed in accordance with the annual program for financing activities and measures for improving energy efficiency. Regulation on establishing the program for financing activities and measures for improving energy efficiency in 2014 (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment 2014h) was the first Program for financing that was adopted.

b) Type of policy instrument

Subsidy is an economic policy instrument.

c) Objectives

The main objective is financial supporting of measures and mechanisms directed to energy efficiency improvement, envisaged by the Law, the Action Plan and other strategic documents of the energy sector. It shall contribute in achieving following objectives: energy saving and rational use by introduction of modern technologies and products with economically justified implementations and usages; use of renewable energy for own needs; greater employment of business entities; protection of the environment by reduced emissions of greenhouse gases; increasing public awareness of the importance and effects of energy efficiency.

d) Target group

One of the major target groups is the buildings sector. Regulation (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment 2014h) specifies activities that shall be supported: improvement of energy efficiency in buildings (refurbishment, renovation, replacement or installation of new energy efficient equipment in systems for heating and/or cooling, replacement/modernization of interior lighting, introduction of a system for automatic control etc.); connection of new consumers to existing district heating systems; connection of consumers, who use electricity for direct heating or inefficient boilers/stoves for heating to existing gas distribution network; installation of heat pumps with low nominal power and high coefficient of performance; installation of biomass boilers; installation of solar collectors for heating domestic hot water; promotion of energy efficient appliances in households; raising awareness of the importance of energy efficiency.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

For the realization of the Program, the Budget Fund provided the total amount of 300 million of dinars (approximately 2.5 million of Euro) in 2014. Additional funding should be provided by donations. For the household sector total amount of 100 million of dinars (approximately 825,000 Euro) is allocated. Fund's beneficiaries shall be commercial banks while loan beneficiaries shall be individuals and associations of homeowners.

For the public sector the total amount of 180 million of dinars (approximately 1.48 million of Euro) is allocated. Beneficiaries of the funds shall be local authorities. Financing of projects should be carried out in accordance with the Regulation that defines conditions and manners for allocation and use of funds, as well as methods of monitoring, contractual commitments and obligations.

The Rulebook on the conditions for allocation and use of the Budget Fund for improving energy efficiency of the Republic of Serbia and criteria for exemption from the obligation of performing an energy audit (Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2014h) in more detail regulates necessary documentation that shall be submitted, criteria for the selection and ranking of projects, as well as maximal participation in costs, provided by the Fund.

f) Implementation network

Implementation of this policy instrument shall be carried out by Ministry of Energy and Mining, local authorities and commercial banks.

g) Outcomes

The Rulebook on the conditions for allocation and use of the Budget Fund, defines as the first criteria for ranking the expected energy savings in kWh/RSD. Although, for the first open call, projects that shall be financed are selected (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2014i), (Ministry of Energy, Development, 2014j), expected energy savings are still not presented. So far eleven projects got financing from the Budget Fund.

1.1.4. CAPACITY BUILDING AND NETWORKING

Instruments related to capacity building, are new, adopted in 2015, and can be classified in two sections: education and training for energy managers (under jurisdiction of Ministry in charge for energy) and education and training for engineers to be specialized in area of energy efficiency of buildings (under jurisdiction of Ministry in charge for construction).

1.1.4.1 Education and training for energy managers

a) General information

In accordance with the Law on Efficient Use of Energy (Government of the Republic of Serbia, (2013a)⁶, The Rulebook on the manner of implementation and content of training program for energy managers, expenditures for attending the training courses, and detailed conditions, curriculum, and taking of the examination for energy managers (Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2015b) prescribes the manner in which training shall be delivered, the content of theoretical and practical training for energy managers, the amount and manner of payment of costs related to energy manager training, and detailed conditions, the curriculum and taking of the examination for energy managers.

b) Type of policy instrument

This policy instrument is classified as a capacity building policy instrument.

c) Objectives

Objectives of this policy instrument, in order to contribute to capacity building, are to prescribe curriculums of different trainings for energy managers, depending on target group, the conditions to be met by candidates who shall attend training, training and examination procedure, as well as related costs.

d) Target group

Person who can attend training shall have: higher education of the first degree academic studies in the field of technical or technological sciences with the extent of 180 ECTS (European Credit Transfer

⁶ http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/A_01_Zakon_o_efikasnom_korisecnju_energije.pdf (28.07.2015)

System) or higher education of the second degree of academic study at master academic studies in educational and scientific fields of mechanical engineering, electrical engineering or technology.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The curriculums of training programs are different depending on energy management system obligors:

- 1) The training for energy managers for energy management systems with predominant activity in the manufacturing sector, which includes public enterprises, referred to as energy managers in the field of industrial energy;
- 2) The training for energy managers for systems with predominant activity in the sector of trade and services, as well as government authorities and other authorities of the Republic of Serbia, autonomous province, as well as public services and public companies which do not conduct the activity in the manufacturing sector- referred to as energy managers for the buildings sector;
- 3) The training for energy managers for system of local self-governments with more 20,000 inhabitants (energy managers in the field of municipal energy).

The Organization in charge for training appoints mentors who supervise the trainees. The number of participants in the training sessions for the use of specialized software can be up to 20. The number of participants in the classes of practical training cannot be more than ten.

f) Implementation network

Training for energy managers shall be carried out by the Organization that meets the requirements regarding human resources, equipment and premises for delivering training for energy managers and authorized energy advisors. Rulebook on conditions regarding human resources, equipment and premises of organizations delivering training for energy managers and authorized energy advisors (Ministry of Mining and Energy, 2015a) prescribes relevant details.

g) Outcomes

The person who attends the training and passes the examination for the appropriate type of energy manager is trained to: collect and analyze data on use of energy provided by energy management obligors, prepare plans and programs of energy efficiency for energy management obligors, prepare annual reports on the program's objectives and plan of energy efficiency, undertake other actions and measures prescribed by the Law regulating the efficient use of energy. Although, there were no appropriate legislative in the time of training, it has been estimated that approximately 1,700 energy advisors have been trained in Serbia so far (GIZ, 2015).

According to the second EEAP, expected savings due to introduction of energy management system are 1.87 PJ until 2018. Education and training for energy managers is a precondition for that achievement. Data about cost-effectiveness are not available.

1.1.4.2 Education and training for energy efficiency in buildings

a) General information

In accordance with the Law on planning and construction⁷, The Rulebook on licensing exams in the field of spatial and urban planning, design of technical documentation, construction and energy efficiency and on issuing and revocation of licenses for the authorized urban planner, designer, contractor and responsible planner (Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure, 2015) regulates the conditions, program and manner of taking professional exams in the field of spatial and urban planning, the design documentation, construction and energy efficiency, and the conditions and procedures for granting and revoking licenses of authorized urban planner, designer, contractor and responsible planners.

b) Type of policy instrument

This policy instrument is classified as a capacity building policy instrument.

c) Objectives

The aim of this policy instrument is to train engineers for implementation of The Rulebook on Energy Efficiency of Buildings (Ministry of Environment, Mining and Spatial Planning, 2011a) and the Rulebook on Conditions, Content and Manner of Issuance of Certificates of Energy Performance of Buildings (Ministry of Environment, Mining and Spatial Planning, 2011b), in order to guaranty and document certain level in energy performance of all types of buildings.

d) Target group

Persons with acquired education at the master academic studies or bachelor studies as well as education on vocational studies (basic vocational studies, specialized professional studies) and secondary education in construction, architecture, mechanical engineering, electrical engineering, technology or other appropriate can participate in training.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Requirement for taking professional exam for responsible energy efficiency engineer for buildings and for obtaining appropriate license is that a person has at least four years of professional experience and completed training in the field of energy efficiency in buildings, according to the program.

f) Implementation network

Serbian Chamber of engineers⁸ carries out training and examination for energy efficiency in buildings.

⁷ http://www.ingkomora.org.rs/zakoni/zakon_o_planiranju_i_izgradnji2014.pdf (28.07.2015)

⁸ <http://www.ingkomora.org.rs>

g) Outcomes

Person educated for energy efficiency in buildings, according to the program, shall have knowledge about all aspects of energy consumption in buildings, influential parameters, possibilities for energy efficiency improvement, as well as related economic aspects.

According to the Second EEAP, savings due to introduction of Minimum energy performance requirements for new or reconstructed buildings are 9.98 PJ until 2018. Education and training for energy efficiency in buildings is a precondition for that achievement. Data about cost-effectiveness are not available.

1.1.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR THE PROMOTION OF ENERGY SERVICES

1.1.5.1 Model of Energy Service Agreement for Public Buildings

a) General information

The Law on Efficient Use of Energy for the first time in Serbia introduced and defined terms: energy service and energy service company (ESCO). The law stipulates that the provision of energy services shall be governed by an Energy Services Agreement concluded between ESCO and the relevant energy consumer. The law also, defines mandatory elements of this agreement (efficiency criteria, measures for increasing energy efficiency, manner of financing of the project, energy consumption within the reference period, fees for the provided energy services, etc.). The Rulebook on Model Energy Service Contracts for the Implementation of Energy Efficiency when Users are from Public Sector (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2015c) was developed to help public entities, as well ECCOs in preparation of an Energy Service Agreement. Two models for contracts are provided, one for public buildings and another for public lighting.

b) Type of policy instrument

This policy instrument is created to promote implementation of energy services in buildings sector.

c) Objectives

This instrument allows establishment of public-private partnerships between the relevant public partner (e.g. a municipality, a public company, a State) and the relevant private partner (i.e. ESCO company) on a long-term basis wherein the installation and management of the undertaken energy efficiency measures by a private partner shall be financed from the savings achieved. For overall bankability of ESCO projects in Serbia it is important to note that this instrument allows the receivables attributed to a private partner from the savings, to be further transferable to third parties.

d) Target group

Relevant public partner (e.g. a municipality, a public company, a State) and the relevant private partner (i.e. ESCO company) are the target groups for this instrument.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The model agreement set out by this policy instrument envisages three main periods of the ESCO agreement. The Preparatory Period mainly consists of planning and design activities. The second - Implementation Period consists of activities related to the implementation of the respective energy savings measures by a private partner in cooperation with a public partner. The Guarantee Period is the period of utilizing the energy savings potentials of the contracted facility. In this period energy savings, i.e. financial savings are achieved as a result of the implemented measures. The model agreement further contains amply sophisticated provisions related to collateral packages, warranties regarding the performance, the insurance of the project, the force majeure clauses and detailed rules regarding the aforesaid three main contractual periods. It also contains a comprehensive set of appendices where necessary details relevant for a particular project shall be set, such as details of the contracted facility, the instructions for achieving energy savings, as well as the guidelines for verification of the quality of maintenance and performance levels (Petrikić & Partneri AOD, 2015).

g) Outcomes

This policy instrument has been introduced in 2015, so results and outcomes are expected to be visible in the future. The second EEAP considers implementation of this policy instrument in energy efficiency improvement measures in public and commercial buildings. Total energy saving potential of this measure is 0.0169 Mtoe (0.71 PJ), up to 2018, but the share of ESCO projects in it was not determined. In table 5 projection of final energy savings according to the second EEAP is presented. Data about cost-effectiveness are not available.

Table 5: Projection of final energy savings according to the second EEAP

Policy instrument	Savings 2010-2012	Savings total 2012-2018
Energy Labeling	-	0.71 PJ*

* Total saving potential of energy efficiency improvement measures in public and commercial buildings (partly will be financed by ESCO)

1.1.6 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT AND BEST AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGY (BAT) PROMOTION

1.1.6.1 Funding for research in energy efficiency

a) General information

The Strategy of science and technological development of the Republic of Serbia for the period 2010-2015 (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2010a) identified “Energy and Energy Efficiency” as one of the top priorities in the domain of science and technology in Serbia. This priority is supported partly through the co-funding of integral and interdisciplinary research in “energy efficiency of production, distribution and use of energy, with a special attention to improvement of energy efficiency in buildings” and partly through funding of projects in the Program of technological

development (Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, 2010). Currently, different research projects are financed, and they have been selected through public call from 2010.

b) Type of policy instrument

This policy instrument is created to support research and development related to energy efficiency.

c) Objectives

General objectives of this instrument is to improve capacities of Serbian economy by securing energy supply, rationalizing consumption, reducing of dependency on imports and expanding production of energy equipment and equipment for the protection of the environment, contributing to the reduction of unemployment rate (Stojiljkovic et al., 2012). Within topics of energy, mining and energy efficiency, energy efficiency in the buildings sector is emphasized. Objectives are achieved by different research projects that are financing or co-financing by the State budget.

d) Target group

Relevant scientific institutions (e.g. Universities, research institutes, etc.), and relevant public (e.g. a municipality, a public company, a State) or commercial partners (owner of buildings) are target groups for this instrument.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

The Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development⁹ regularly announces public calls for funding research in the Program of technological development (topic: Energy, mining and energy efficiency) and for co-funding of integral and interdisciplinary research (topic: Energy and energy efficiency, sub-topic: Energy efficiency of production, distribution and use of energy, with a special attention to improvement of energy efficiency in buildings). Researches in Program of technological development are 100% financed from the budget of Ministry of Education and Science, while integral and interdisciplinary researches are partly financed by public or private partners. Funding includes salaries of researchers and research equipment.

f) Implementation network

The Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development - Department for Technological Development, Technology Transfer and Innovative Systems¹⁰ and Department for Science¹¹ announce public calls for funding and co-funding of research and development projects related to energy efficiency in buildings. The same Ministry is responsible for selecting projects to be funded, and monitoring of their implementation, as well as for the supervision of achieved results.

g) Outcomes

Total budget of the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development for project in energy field is approximately 4 million euro per year. However, there is no publicly available data about the outcomes of ongoing and realized projects, and their effects on energy efficiency in buildings.

⁹ <http://www.mpn.gov.rs/?lang=sr-YU>

¹⁰ <http://www.mpn.gov.rs/nauka/tehnoloski-razvoj>

¹¹ <http://mpn.gov.rs/nauka/integralna-i-interdisciplinarna-istrazivanja>

1.1.7 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR IN SERBIA

Summary table: Buildings					
Policy instruments	Short list of implemented policies and measures	Objective	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Implementation network
Regulatory policy instruments	Minimum energy performance requirements for new or reconstructed buildings Energy audit (mandatory) Energy management system in buildings	Reduction of energy consumption in buildings for heating and cooling	Target group: Owners, users and investors in public, commercial and residential buildings. Targeted objects: Residential, commercial and public buildings	Punish non-compliance	Ministry of Mining and Energy Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure Chamber of Engineers
Dissemination and awareness instruments/Informative policy instruments	Energy Labeling	Reduction of electricity consumption for operation of different appliances in buildings	Target group: Households, suppliers and vendors of products Targeted objects: Households appliances	Punish non-compliance	Ministry of Mining and Energy
Economic policy instruments	Subsidy	Financing of activities and measures directed to improve energy efficiency in buildings	Target group: Owners and investors in public, commercial and residential buildings. Targeted objects: Residential, commercial and public buildings	Motivation	Ministry of Mining and Energy

<p>Capacity building and networking</p>	<p>Education and training for energy managers Education and training for energy efficiency in buildings</p>	<p>Training and education for implementation proposed regulatory policy instruments</p>	<p>Target group: Persons with acquired education at the master academic studies or bachelor studies as well as education on vocational studies (basic vocational studies, specialized professional studies) and secondary education in construction, architecture, mechanical engineering, electrical engineering, technology or other appropriate. Targeted objects: Commercial and public buildings</p>	<p>Motivation</p>	<p>Ministry of Mining and Energy</p>
<p>Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services</p>	<p>Model of Energy Service Agreement for Public Buildings</p>	<p>Financing of activities and measures directed to improve energy efficiency in buildings</p>	<p>Target group: public institutions (e.g. a municipality, a public company, a State), ESCO companies Targeted objects: Public buildings</p>	<p>Motivation</p>	<p>Ministry of Mining and Energy</p>
<p>Policy instruments for Research and Development and BAT promotion</p>	<p>Funding for research in energy efficiency</p>	<p>Scientific research and development of technologies for improvement of energy efficiency in buildings</p>	<p>Target group: Scientific institutions (e.g. Universities, research institutes, etc.), public institutions (e.g. a municipality, a public company, a State), owners of the buildings Targeted objects: Residential, commercial and public buildings</p>	<p>Motivation</p>	<p>Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development</p>

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

Compared to the buildings sector, policy instruments for increasing energy efficiency in the transport sector are less developed. Planning instruments are developed based on the Law on Road Traffic Safety (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2009a)¹² are:

- Improvements of bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure,
- Traffic calming, and
- Traffic management systems.

Regulatory policy instruments related to energy efficiency in transport are based on mixture of regulations related to energy sector, but also to trade, market regulation, environment, etc.:

- Fuel economy standards/vehicle CO₂-emission standards,
- Fuel quality standards.

Currently, there is no specific financial policy instruments dedicated to energy efficiency in transport sector in Serbia. In previous period (2010-2012) the Government of Republic of Serbia passed regulations on the conditions and manner of subsidized acquisition of vehicles manufactured in the Republic of Serbia in accordance with the old-for-new policy, with an idea to encourage the replacement of old vehicles equipped with engines that do not meet even Euro 3 standard, with new domestically produced vehicles equipped with Euro 5 engines (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013c). Also, in 2011 the Fund for Environmental Protection had the programs for subsidizing purchasing vehicles with low emissions of CO₂ (in 2011) and adopted the Decision on the awarding of grants to automotive companies aimed at encouraging the purchase of environmentally friendly vehicles, i.e. vehicles with CO₂ emissions lower than 100 g/km (in 2012). This Fund ceased to operate in 2012.

Dissemination and awareness instruments in transport sector are mostly related to transport safety. Promotion of eco-driving and car sharing scheme are proposed as information measures, but appropriate instruments for supporting are still not developed.

Research and development in the area of energy efficiency in transport sector is not recognized as a priority in relevant strategy (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2010a) and there are no specific policy instruments which are targeting this sector.

¹² <http://en.abs.gov.rs/regulations>

1.2.1 PLANNING INSTRUMENTS

1.2.1.1 Improvements of bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure

a) General information

The Law on Road Traffic Safety (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2009a) regulates issues related to bicycle traffic. Improvements of bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure are under jurisdiction of local self-governments, and shall be regulated in spatial and urban plans (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2014a). In large cities there are initiatives for improvements of bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure, often financially and organizationally supported by international institutions and organizations¹³.

b) Type of policy instrument

Improvements of bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure is planning policy instrument.

c) Objectives

Improvements of bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure should increase the share of biking and walking in passenger transport and consequently reduce fuel consumption.

d) Target group

Passengers in city transport are the main target group.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Introduction of bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure in local spatial and urban plans is the precondition for their construction. Improvements of bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure should motivate people to use these modes of transport. However, in Serbian regulations and practice still there are no sanctions for using non-efficient modes of transport.

f) Implementation network

Local administrations are responsible for spatial and urban plans development.

g) Outcomes

There is no officially available document about energy savings achieved by this policy instrument.

1.2.1.2 Traffic calming

a) General information

This policy instrument was developed with an aim to reduce and slow down the intensity of traffic. It is directly related to the relevant international documents, UN Improving Global Road Safety (United Nations Secretary, 2013) and International Road Assessment Programme¹⁴, which have very

¹³ http://www.rs.undp.org/content/serbia/en/home/operations/projects/environment_and_energy/support-to-sustainable-transport-in-the-city-of-belgrade.html (30.07.2015)

¹⁴ International Road Assessment Programme, iRAP Report Serbia, 2009., available at <http://www.irap.net/about-irap-3/assessment-reports?download=66:irap-serbia-results> (30.07.2015)

important role in creating legal base for application of measures for traffic calming at international level. Legal base for this policy instrument are the Law on road traffic safety (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2009) and the Rulebook of the technical measures for slowing road traffic (Ministry of Transport, 2013).

b) Type of policy instrument

This is planning policy instrument.

c) Objectives

Objective of this policy instrument is to ensure an increase of quality of transport intensity and safety by changes in road geometry and placement of proper traffic equipment, pavement markings and traffic signs. Traffic calming measures are developed to ensure reduction of vehicle speed. This would lead to an increase of energy efficiency and caused by decrease fuel consumption.

d) Target group

Target groups are users (public and private companies), drivers, pedestrians, public and private companies that maintain the roads and railways, investors, equipment producers etc.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

No rules and influencing mechanisms are defined.

f) Implementation network

Most important role in terms of application of the policy instrument has primarily the Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure Department for road transport, roads and safety, Group for road safety¹⁵. To support this measure Ministry developed the Rulebook on technical tools for slowing road traffic (Ministry of construction, transport and infrastructure, 2014). In the case when roads are under jurisdiction of local authority, each local self-government shall adopt Rulebook on the criteria for the installation of technical traffic calming tools¹⁶ in order to specify locations where road slowing tools shall be introduced. Sector for traffic police with in the Ministry of interior¹⁷ is involved in managing traffic safety and monitoring and improvement of legislation in road safety.

The Road Traffic Safety Agency¹⁸ continuously coordinates and performs different tasks: cooperation and coordination with regional and local road traffic safety bodies, offering professional help to the bodies in order to improve traffic safety, creating professional instructions, manuals and guides for improving the work of the local bodies, following international experiences and accomplishments in the field of road traffic safety.

¹⁵ <http://www.mgsi.gov.rs/cir/odsek/grupa-za-unapređenje-bezbednosti-saobraćaja-na-putevima>

¹⁶ <http://www.tsgserbia.com/file/SRBIA%20Podzakonski%20akti/Pravilnik%20o%20kriterijumima%20za%20ugradnju%20tehničkih%20sredstava....pdf>

¹⁷ <http://prezentacije.mup.gov.rs/usp/Poslovi/Poslovi.html>

¹⁸ <http://en.abs.gov.rs/>

g) Outcomes

The Rulebook of the technical measures for slowing road traffic has contributed to an increase in infrastructure investments in transport sector (Road Traffic Safety Agency, 2015). Although this instrument affects fuel consumption, data about achieved savings are not available.

1.2.1.3 Traffic management system

a) General information

This policy instrument is primarily targeting the problem of traffic organization and transport infrastructure. It should contribute in establishing extended, improved and safe transport network. Traffic management system is a complex system that combines infrastructure, traffic regulations and adequate enforcement. Implementation of traffic management system in the Republic of Serbia coincided with initiatives of Introduction and Benefits of Intelligent Transport Systems (Public Enterprise "Roads of Serbia, 2009). The legal base for implementation of traffic management system is the Strategy of the Railway, Road, Inland Waterway, Air and Intermodal Transport Development in the Republic of Serbia (2008-2015) (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2007)¹⁹. Traffic management system as policy instrument can be used in traffic control, incident management, travel demand management, operation and maintenance, environmental conditions monitoring, automated dynamic warning and enforcement and non-vehicular road user safety.

b) Type of policy instrument

Traffic management system represent principally planning policy instrument, but purpose of it is also informative.

c) Objectives

The main objective of this policy instrument is to increase safety and efficiency of transport (including energy efficiency).

d) Target group

This instrument is targeting all transport modes. Target groups are owners, users and investors in public, private and commercial companies, Governmental agencies, transport operators and environmental organisation.

e) Rules and influencing mechanisms

Rules and influencing mechanisms are still not prescribed.

f) Implementation network

Ministry of construction, transport and infrastructure - Department for transport, Group for intelligent transport systems²⁰, promotes and defines the traffic signalization, equipment, devices

¹⁹ http://www.putevi-srbije.rs/strategijapdf/Strategijatransport_lat.pdf

²⁰ <http://www.mgsi.gov.rs/cir/odsek/grupa-za-intelligentne-transportne-sistemee>

and systems for managing and controlling traffic, as well as intelligent systems for roads and vehicles. Legal base for implementation traffic management systems represents Strategy for planning, development and intelligent transport systems application on roads of the Republic of Serbia²¹

g) Outcomes

The good practice show that, after implementation of different measures of this policy instrument increase of traffic flow is up to 25% and travel time reduction is up to 25%. Reduction of energy consumption achieves almost 30% (Public Enterprise "Roads of Serbia, 2009).

1.2.2 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS

1.2.2.1 Fuel Quality Standards

a. General information

The Rulebook on technical and other requirements for petroleum-derived liquid fuels (Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, 2013a) prescribes the required quality of petrol and liquid fuels. This Rulebook is adopted on the basis of the Law on Technical Requirements for Products and Conformity Assessment (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2009b). The Directive 98/70/EC on the quality of petrol and diesel fuels is partially transposed to the Rulebook (European Integration Office, 2014). Implementation of this policy instrument is further support by the Regulation on marking of oil products (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013e).

b. Type of policy instrument:

A fuel standard is regulatory and mandatory policy instrument.

c. Objectives:

Application of this policy instrument directly affects increasing of liquid fuel quality and reducing consumption. Consequently this leads to improvement of energy efficiency in transport sector.

d. Target groups:

This policy instrument is related to unleaded petrol, aviation gasoline, jet fuel and diesel. Therefore, higher-quality liquid fuels are targeting energy efficiency in all transport sectors.

e. Rules and influencing mechanisms

This policy instrument prescribes technical and other requirements to be met by petroleum based liquid fuels that are used in internal combustion engines that are as fuels placed on the market of the Republic of Serbia. It also defines method for assessment of compliance (of selected fuel) with standards. Prescribed method of sampling is in accordance with SRPS EN ISO 3170 and SRPS EN ISO 3171 standards. Penalties for placing fuels with lower quality than specified are prescribed by

²¹ <http://www.putevi-srbije.rs/strategijapdf/itsrezime.pdf>

regulation related to control and monitoring of petroleum fuels on the market (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013e).

f. Implementation network:

The appointed and accredited institutions are responsible for assessment of specific fuel compliance with standards. Appointed procedure is conducted in accordance with Regulation on method of appointment and authorization of the body for assessment of compliance (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2009c), while the appropriate accreditation procedure is the responsibility of Accreditation body of Serbia²². Inspection and monitoring of fuel quality and fuel marking are the responsibility of the Ministry of Trade, Tourism and Telecommunications – Department for Market Inspection.

g. Outcomes:

There are no official data on increasing energy efficiency related to quality of fuels used in transport sector.

1.2.2.2 Fuel economy standards/vehicle CO₂ - emission standards

a. General information

This policy instrument was introduced by the Law on Ratification of the Agreement on the adoption of unified technical regulations for wheeled vehicles, equipment and parts which can be fitted and/or used on vehicles with wheels and conditions for reciprocal recognition of approvals awarded in line with these regulations (National Assembly of the Republic of Serbia, 2011). Approval of vehicles according to United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) regulations include determination and verification that the vehicle's characteristics meet the requirements related to the active safety, passive safety, environmental protection and energy saving (fuel consumption), control of the conformity of series production, a unique method of application and acceptance by all contracting parties. The Stabilization and Association Agreement of the Republic of Serbia²³ stipulates the obligation of acceptance and implementation of EU legislation in the field of approval of road vehicles. The level of harmonization between UNECE regulations and EU regulations is very high, as they have the same technical requirements and procedures for testing. Hence, the Republic of Serbia performs controls of the conformity of imported vehicles, both on the basis of UNECE regulations, and on the relevant EU regulations (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b).

b. Type of policy instrument:

This is regulatory and mandatory policy instrument.

c. Objectives:

The key problem in terms of energy efficiency, environmental pollution and safety in Serbian road transport sector is the age of the vehicle fleet (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b). Using newer vehicles, with stricter emission and consumption standards should increase energy efficiency in the transport sector. The objective is to save 2.43 PJ of energy in period 2012-2018 (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b)

²² <http://www.ats.rs> (30.07.2015)

²³ http://ec.europa.eu/enlargement/pdf/serbia/key_document/saa_en.pdf (30.07.2015)

d. Target groups:

Importers and car dealers are the target group for this policy instrument.

e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:

Currently all new imported vehicles must be equipped with engines that meet at least Euro 5 standard (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2013b), while for the import of used vehicles minimum Euro 3 standard is required (Government of the Republic of Serbia, 2010b). Customs Administration makes inspection of compliance of imported vehicle with proposed vehicle standards by inspection of vehicle, insight into accompanying documents and comparing of vehicle and accompanying documents with technical specification for selected vehicle type. If Customs Administration is unable to define compliance of vehicle with Euro 3 standard, further inspection is carried out in accordance with conditions provided by Road Traffic Safety Agency.

f. Implementation network:

Implementation of this policy instrument is responsibility of Road Traffic Safety Agency and the Ministry of Interior, while institutions in charge of monitoring are Road Traffic Safety Agency, Customs Administration and Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure.

g. Outcomes:

Implementation of this policy instrument and corresponding UNECE regulations and EU legislation is very important for the fleet modernization in the Republic of Serbia, but also for the reduction of fuel consumption in the transport sector. Achieved and expected savings in transport sector related to this policy instrument are elaborated in the second EEAP (Table 6).

Table 6: Achieved and forecast of final energy savings (The Second EEAP)

Policy instrument	Savings 2010-2012	Savings total 2012-2018
Vehicle standards	0.02 PJ	2.43 PJ

1.2.3 FINANCIAL POLICY INSTRUMENTS

N/A

1.2.4 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS

N/A

1.2.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

N/A

1.2.6 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR IN #COUNTRY#

Summary table: Transport					
	Short list of implemented policies and measures	Objective ²⁴ (improve system, travel or vehicle efficiency)	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Implementation network
Planning instrument	Improvements of bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure	System efficiency	Target groups: Passengers in the city transport Target sector: Road transport	Motivation	Local self-governments
Planning instrument	Traffic calming	System efficiency	Target groups: All participants in road transport, public and private companies that maintain the roads and railway, equipment producers Target sector: Road transport	Motivation	Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure Ministry of Interior Road traffic safety Agency
Planning instrument	Traffic management systems	System efficiency	Target groups: All participants in road transport Target sector: Road transport	Motivation	Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure

²⁴ Energy efficiency in the transport sector can be divided into system efficiency (reduce or avoid travel or the need to travel), travel efficiency (shift to more energy efficient modes) and vehicle efficiency (improve the efficiency through vehicle technology).

Regulatory policy instruments	Fuel economy standards/vehicle CO2-emission standards	Travel efficiency	Target sector: Road transport	Punish non-compliance	Road Traffic Safety Agency Ministry of Interior Customs Administration
Regulatory policy instruments	Fuel quality standards	Vehicle efficiency	Target sector: All transport sectors	Punish non-compliance	Accredited and Appointed and institutions for fuel inspection Market Inspection
Financial policy instruments	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Dissemination and awareness instruments	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Policy instruments for Research and Development	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

2. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE REGIONAL / LOCAL LEVEL

2.1 PRESENTATION OF THE CASE STUDY CITY OF NIŠ

City / Region:

The City of Niš is located in the south-eastern part of Serbia and it is the third largest city in the country, with 260,237 inhabitants according to census of 2011 (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2011a). It covers area 596 km² out of which 63.1% is agricultural land (Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, 2011b). According to the Ordinance on establishing an unified list of Regions and Local Self-governments per Level of Development for 2014²⁵ Niš belongs to the first, most developed group of municipalities in Serbia.

In terms of dealing with local energy issues the City of Niš is one of the better performing in Serbian context. Within local administration it has Directorate for Communal Services, Energy and Transport which again consists of several smaller administrative units. One of them is the Department for Energy with five highly educated staff. Until this department was established energy issues in the City of Niš haven't been tackled in organized and systematic manner. In the very beginning activities of the Department included the preparation and adoption of the documents that shape the legal framework for dealing with energy at the local level with a particular focus on district heating (Tariff System, Decision on conditions and manner of heat supply²⁶ and accompanying ordinances). Activities also included defining the conditions for development of the gas network infrastructure in the City, the intensification of activities related to the participation of the City in the international association "Energy Cities". Furthermore the City of Niš with the support of the Swedish Export Credit Corporation (SEK) implemented the project of preparing the analysis of the potential for heating the city of Nis (excluding district heating). In the initial period employees of the Department have been trained to prepare the energy balance, upon which regular collection of data regarding energy consumption in the public sector started.

Also, after establishing the Department the City of Niš signed the Covenant of Mayors Charter in July 2011 and submitted Sustainable Energy Action Plan (SEAP) in December of 2014²⁷. The SEAP is covering period till year 2020 and sets indicative target for CO₂ emissions to 21% compared to baseline levels of 2010, which is equivalent of 842.093,07 t of CO₂. This plan suggests and foresees 50 measures and actions in five different sectors: buildings, transport, public lighting, water provision and waste management. Measures include:

- **Energy Efficiency Policy / Action**

Implementation of energy efficiency measures in organized manner started in 2008 when trilateral agreement on the use of KfW Development Bank funds within the programme "Rehabilitation of the District Heating Systems in Serbia - Phase III" was signed between the Republic of Serbia, the City of Niš and local district heating provider (Public Utility Company "Gradska toplana"). With this credit arrangement equipment and services were procured for the rehabilitation and modernization of district heating system. In following period with growing understanding of importance of the energy management system, several projects were implemented including one in sector of the public

²⁵ [Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia", No. 104/2014, 2014;](#)

<http://www.regionalnirazvoj.gov.rs/Lat/ShowNARRFolder.aspx?mi=171> (30.07.2015)

²⁶ http://www.nitoplana.co.rs/index.php?seo_name=downloads&next_downloads=1 (30.07.2015)

²⁷ http://www.covenantofmayors.eu/about/signatories_en.html?city_id=2996&seap (30.07.2015)

buildings - restoration and renovation of the envelope of one of city's administrative buildings (24, Nikola Pasic Street).

According to the SEAP, the buildings sector is the most important in terms of CO₂ emissions reduction for the upcoming period, till 2020. Therefore, majority of measures, 25 of them, belong to the buildings sector. Most of the measures are energy efficiency related but there are some that belong to utilization of renewables. All the measures in the buildings sector are divided in five subgroups: (1) General measures; (2) Promotional, informational and educational measures and activities; (3) Measures in residential and public buildings owned by the City; (4) Measures in residential sector including collective and individual housing; and (5) Measures in commercial and service buildings.

The category of General measures includes activities related to entire building stock in the City of Niš and can be divided into two subgroups: measures to remove obstacles to the monitoring and control of energy consumption in the buildings sector and schemes for co-financing implementation of identified energy efficiency measures in all subsectors. Group of general measures is considered to be very important and a bases for all others, because on one hand, without collecting data and relevant energy indicators it is impossible to monitor the actual change in energy consumption and corresponding reduction in CO₂ emissions from the buildings sector, and on the other, experiences show that without co-financing mechanisms action plans remain just a wish lists.

Subcategory promotional, informational and educational measures include following: opening of the info-corner on energy efficiency; implementation of the "Engage" campaign on energy efficiency and putting up posters and billboards; continuous informing consumers about ways of energy savings and current energy issues on the back of the energy bill; implementation of thematic promotional and information campaigns to raise awareness of energy efficiency in buildings; organization of conferences to promote the rational use of energy and reduction of CO₂ emissions; educational campaigns on the design, construction and use of buildings in a sustainable way to target groups like architects, contractors and planners; education and introduction of energy efficient principles in public procurement.

Energy efficiency measures for buildings owned by the City can be divided into three groups: Preparatory activities, Operational projects, and Legislative measures. A set of preparatory activities include the following measures and activities: introduction of the Information system of energy management in buildings owned the City; Introduction of energy passports for public buildings, development of a plan of reconstruction of public facilities based on the currently available data on energy consumption and other information on objects (with the possibility of change the plan annually when information system becomes operational) and Introduction of a scheme 50-50 [%] according to which the achieved energy savings, i.e. avoided energy costs are evenly shared between the city administration as operators and users. Overview of specific projects planned in the City of Nis is very long, and here are presented just most potent ones: reconstruction of heating systems in public buildings, introduction of automation and process control and conversion to more efficient energy sources including renewable; installation of solar systems for hot water preparation in education, cultural, sports and administrative buildings owned by the city; installation of thermostatic valve sets on the radiators in buildings owned by the City in which there are multiple users; introduction of efficient indoor lighting in all public buildings; Thermal insulation of envelopes and roofs of buildings public buildings; Installing a high-efficiency power windows in buildings owned by the city; installation of solar photovoltaic systems on the roofs of all public buildings. Legislative-administrative measures on the city level that can result in considerable reduction in CO₂ emissions are as follows: introduction of energy efficiency criteria in public procurement under the Law on Efficient Use of Energy for all the equipment and services buildings owned City; decision of the City Assembly, according to which all new buildings owned by the City should use at least one renewable energy source (Photovoltaic systems, solar collectors, heat pumps); installation of central cooling

systems for new buildings owned by the City; decisions on local tax reduction for construction of low energy and passive buildings.

Energy efficiency measures in the residential sub-sector can be divided into measures for new and for existing buildings. Measures in new buildings will be most effectively achieved by adopting legislation that will limit consumption. Measures of energy efficiency for existing residential buildings include two categories: preparatory activities; and performing projects. Preparatory activities like in the case of the sub-sector public buildings will not have a direct impact on reduction of energy consumption but they would set the necessary preconditions for the successful implementation of the energy efficiency projects. Residential sector is the largest consumer of energy and thus there is the biggest potentials for savings and reduction of CO₂ emissions. Therefore related preparatory activities are of great importance. In addition to these activities following ones have the potential for reduction in energy consumption: co-financing of the reconstruction of facades and roofs of buildings on the principles of sustainable construction; co-financing installation of solar systems for hot water; replacement of existing windows with high efficiency ones; conversion of boilers to renewables; conversion of electric water heaters to a central water heating system.

Energy efficiency measures for the sub-sector commercial and service buildings can be divided into new and existing buildings. Proposed measures for existing buildings include the following activities: use of renewable energy sources; use of energy efficient electrical appliances; installation of energy saving light bulbs. Proposal of measures for new commercial buildings includes: employment of high energy standards in planning and construction; and Installment of efficient equipment and utilization of renewable energy sources.

The SEAP prescribes altogether 17 measures to reduce CO₂ emissions from the transport sector in the City of Nis which are divided into following 5 categories: legislative and planning measures; promotion, information and education measures and activities; specific measures and activities for private and commercial vehicles; specific measures and activities for the vehicles owned by the City; specific measures and activities for the public transport. Legislative and planning measures include activities that arise from legal obligations as well as those related to projects aiming to improve traffic infrastructure, and regulation. Implementation of the planning measures will create necessary preconditions for improvement of the transport sector but also determine investment costs of specific measures. Preparatory activities also include preparation of following studies: study on the development and implementation of information system for monitoring and route traffic in the city; feasibility study on using a light rail traffic in City; feasibility study of application and use of measures to improve public transport in the City; investment studies for the improvement of bicycle transportation in the City; transport study of the city of Nis; study for parking; study of public transport; study of improving traffic safety; study of improving regulation and traffic management; project for zones of slow traffic; project on rent a bike system; project for introduction of new subsystems transport (minibus, midi bus).

- **Energy Efficiency instruments / measures per sector**

For the purpose of this case study a general measure in buildings sector - education and behavioral change of the buildings users in objects owned by the City of Niš will be described. General measure (by its nature) does not require excessive external funding, implementation can start immediately and it corresponds to the measure PC4 from the second Energy Efficiency Action Plan – Introduction of energy management system in public and commercial sector.

The measure includes a range of educational activities on the regular basis: organization of educational workshops on ways to save energy; preparation and distribution of educational materials (flyers, brochures, posters, and the like.); and Organization of forums for different actors. There is also possibility of reducing the costs for measure implementation if multipliers of knowledge are engaged (employees of the city administration) who would be prepared to conduct trainings for

users of the buildings. Their involvement would be significantly cheaper, with minimal investment in equipment, especially if local center for energy efficiency would be establish. In addition to educational activities under this measure it is necessary to introduce an incentive scheme for savings within which the financial resources of energy savings remains available to the institution in which the savings was achieved. It is recommended that this measure be linked with the training for the representatives of the buildings users on the use of software for data on energy consumption database. Also it is proposed to link this measure with membership in an international network of cities "Euronet 50-50"²⁸ that are dedicated to mechanism of retaining parts of the revenue generated from savings with the users. Estimating energy savings achieved by implementation of measures aimed at awareness raising and education of buildings users is not easy. According to the experience of other European cities, it was assumed that continuous educational, promotional and informative activities can realize savings of heat and electric power of 9%. For the reference consumption of heat and electricity in year 2010 in buildings owned by the City of Niš was 39,769.80 MWh and 18,799.58 MWh respectively. Following table shows main elements in terms of costs and savings of the measure.

Table 7: Main elements of the measure: Education and behavioral change of the buildings users in objects owned by the City of Niš (SEAP)

Stakeholder carrying out the measure	City of Nis
Start / end of realization (years)	from 2014 until 2020
Estimated costs (unit / total)	Yearly 6,500.00 € Total 45,500.00 €
Assessment savings [MWh]	3,579.28 [MWh] heat 1,691.96 [MWh] electricity
Assessment of emission reductions [t CO ₂]	Heat 1,353.57 Electricity 998.93 Total 2,352.50
Costs for reducing the emissions [€ / t CO ₂]	19.34
Source of funds for implementation	City budget Funds (IPA, IEE, etc.).

Example measure in the transport sector is the System for Centralized Management of Traffic on the territory of the City of Niš. The savings in energy consumption by using this measure should occur by ensuring priority of passage for public transport vehicles in the traffic system of the City including optimization of traffic lights, priority lanes, horizontal signalization, junctions, etc. Within this measure the percentage of savings apply to the total daily traffic in all subsectors including public transport, emergency vehicles, private vehicles and commercial vehicles. It is assumed that successful implementation of this measure would result in total savings of 2% of energy consumption. Expected effects of the measure, besides energy saving, are the reduction of time spent in traffic, increased traffic exploitation rate and enabling of priority for public transportation and emergence vehicles at intersections. Table 8 shows main elements in terms of costs and savings of the measure.

²⁸ <http://www.euronet50-50.eu>

Table 8: Main elements of the measure: System for Centralized Management of Traffic on the territory of City of Niš (SEAP)

Stakeholder carrying out the measure	City of Nis
Start / end of realization (years)	2014 – 2015
Estimated costs (unit / total)	1 st phase 663,300 € 2 nd phase 850,000 € 3 rd Phase 1,167,500 € Total: 2,680,800 €
Assessment savings ([MWh],liter fuel)	Fuel all together 659,224 liters Petrol 5,193.10 MWh Diesel 6,321.36 MWh TNG 1,503.12 MWh
Assessment of emission reductions [t CO ₂]	3,320.70
Costs for reducing the emissions [€ / t CO ₂]	807.30
Source of funds for implementation	City budget Council for safety of the traffic IEE program National EE Fund

- **Interaction between national and local policies**

Serbia has recently adopted several regulations and strategic documents that deal with and promote energy efficiency in the buildings and transport sectors. Most important documents in this respect are the Law on Planning and Construction, the Law on Efficient Use of Energy and Energy Law with accompanying by-laws, and the First and the Second Energy Efficiency Action Plan.

When it comes to the policy instruments in the buildings and transport sectors Serbia proclaimed several of them predominantly through National Action Plans for Energy Efficiency and back them up with mentioned laws and accompanying regulations. These policy instruments spread over areas of regulation, and financial instruments, capacity building and networking and are presented in separate section preceding case study.

The SEAP of the City of Niš in its chapter 9 on Energy Management makes references to priorities and measures in both buildings and transport sectors arising from mentioned laws and strategic documents, thus making top down integration of national policies and goals to local policy. Furthermore chapter 10 of the SEAP - Action Plan, by listing, describing and quantifying number of measures in the buildings and transport sectors contributes to reaching of national goals set in the second Energy Efficiency Action Plan. Cumulative contribution of proposed measures in the SEAP for buildings and transport sectors in terms of reduction of energy consumption and related CO₂ emissions showing bottom up integration of policies are given in tables 8 and 9.

Table 9: Projections of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions till 2020 of the buildings sector per scenarios

Scenarios	Energy Consumption [MWh]		Compared to 2010 in %	Emissions [t/CO ₂]		Compared to 2010 in %
	2010	2020		2010	2020	
Without Measures	1,414,734.73	1,583,033.22	11.90	850,963.91	991,045.39	16.46
With Measures	1,414,734.73	1,020,445.31	-27.87	850,963.91	645,314.54	-24.17

Table 10: Projections of energy consumption and CO2 emissions till 2020 of the transport sector per scenarios

Scenarios	Energy Consumption [MWh]		Compared to 2010 in %	Emissions [t/CO ₂]		Compared to 2010 in %
	2010	2020		2010	2020	
Without Measures	707,148.62	905,455.80	28.04	180,937.44	231,661.41	28.03
With Measures	707,148.62	662,389.45	-6.33	180,937.44	167,329.50	-7.52

It should be emphasized that in Serbian context the City of Niš is one of better performing local authorities in energy field and their SEAP is one of the best documents of its kind.

- **Discussion / Recommendations**

There are several barriers for successful implementation of the City of Niš SEAP and thus active contribution to realization of national policies and goals. They can be described as the lack of political support, lack of financial or economical instruments and lack of administrative capacities in public sector. Fortunately all of mentioned barriers are tackled in the SEAP which gives different solutions and approaches to financing and realizing foreseen measures.

The data acquisition on public sector energy consumption in the City of Nis is an example of administrative capacity barrier. This activity is being performed since 2009, but still it doesn't produce satisfactory results. The quality of the provided data on energy consumption is not on the satisfactory level because the employees from various public institutions that should submit the data find difficult to understand which information is relevant and data processing takes too long. In this case intensive education and capacity building of users in public buildings and public servants on energy consumption and data collection is needed.

- **Further information**

Contact person: Mr. Bojan Gajić, Senior Associate, Administration for communal Services, Energy and Transport of the City of Niš, Department of Energy, bojan.gajic@gu.ni.rs.

<http://www.ni.rs/gradska-uprava/uprave-i-sluzbe/ukdes/odsek-za-energetiku/>

http://www.covenantofmayors.eu/about/signatories_en.html?city_id=2996&seap

REFERENCES

- Energy Community, (2015), Energy Community Portal - Energy Efficiency in Serbia, https://www.energy-community.org/portal/page/portal/ENC_HOME/AREAS_OF_WORK/Implementation/Serbia/Energy_Efficiency (28.07.2015)
- European Integration Office, (2014), National Programme for the adoption of the EU acquis, 2014, url: http://www.seio.gov.rs/upload/documents/nacionalna_dokumenta/npaa/npaa_eng_2014_2018.pdf (28.07.2015)
- GIZ - Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit GmbH, (2015), Advisory service for energy efficiency, 2015, <https://www.giz.de/en/worldwide/21212.html> (28.07.2015)
- Government of the Republic of Serbia - Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure (2007), Strategy of the Railway, Road, Inland Waterway, Air and Intermodal Transport Development in the Republic of Serbia (2008-2015), 2007, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia No. 101/07, url: http://www.putevi-srbije.rs/strategijapdf/Strategijatransport_eng.pdf (29.07.2015)
- Government of the Republic of Serbia, (2009a), Law on Road Traffic Safety, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 41/2009, 2009, URL: <http://en.abs.gov.rs/regulations> (28.07.2015)
- Government of the Republic of Serbia, (2009b), Law on Technical Requirements for Products and Conformity Assessment, Official Gazette of the RS No. 36/09, 2009, url: <http://www.tehnis.privreda.gov.rs/sw4i/download/files/article/Law%20on%20Technical%20Requirements.pdf?id=37> (28.07.2015)
- Government of the Republic of Serbia, (2009c), Regulation on method of appointment and authorization of the body for assessment of compliance, Official Gazette of the RS No. 98/09, 2009, url: <http://www.tehnis.privreda.gov.rs/bezbednost-proizvoda/imenovanje-tela-za-ocenjivanje-usaglasenosti.html> (28.07.2015)
- Government of the Republic of Serbia, (2010a), Strategy of Science and Technology Development in the Republic of Serbia for the period from 2010 up to 2015, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 13/2010, 2010, <http://mpn.gov.rs/dokumenta-i-propisi/podzakonski-propisi/nauka-i-tehnoloski-razvoj/94-strateski-i-programski-dokumenti> (28.07.2015)
- Government of the Republic of Serbia, (2010b), Regulation on motor vehicle import, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia No.23/2010, 2010, url: <http://www.abs.gov.rs/odluke-i-uredbe> (28.07.2015)
- Government of the Republic of Serbia, (2013a), Law on Efficient Use of Energy, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 25/2013, 2013, URL: http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/A_01_Zakon_o_efikasnom_koriscenju_energije.pdf (28.07.2015)
- Government of the Republic of Serbia, (2013b), The Second Energy Efficiency Action Plan of the Republic of Serbia for the period from 2013 to 2015, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 98/2013, 2013, http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/B_01_Drugi_akcioni_plan_za_energetsku_efikasnost_za_Republiku_Srbiju_za_period_od_2013_do_2015_godine.pdf?uri=CELEX:32009L0028 (28.07.2015)
- Government of the Republic of Serbia, (2013c), Regulation on types of products that affect the consumption of energy and require labelling of consumption of energy and other resources, 2013, Official Gazette of the RS, No 92/2013

http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/D_01_Uredba_o_vrstama_proizvoda_koji_uticu_na_potrosnju_energije_za_koje_je_neophodno_oznacavanje_potrosnje_energije_i_drugih_resursa.pdf (28.07.2015)

Government of the Republic of Serbia, (2013d), Decision on the establishing the Budget Fund for the promotions of efficient use of energy in the Republic of Serbia, RS Official Gazette, No. 92/13

Government of the Republic of Serbia, (2013e), Regulation on marking of oil products, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 46/2013, 2013, url: [http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/nafta-i-gas/B02%20Uredba%20o%20obelezavanju%20\(markiranju\)%20derivata%20nafte.pdf](http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/nafta-i-gas/B02%20Uredba%20o%20obelezavanju%20(markiranju)%20derivata%20nafte.pdf) (28.07.2015)

Government of the Republic of Serbia, (2014a), Law on Construction and Planning, Official Gazette of RS, 72/2009 145/2014, http://www.ingkomora.org.rs/zakoni/zakon_o_planiranju_i_izgradnji2014.pdf (28.07.2015)

IRAP Serbia, Report The International Road Assessment Programme, 2009, url: <http://www.irap.net/about-irap-3/assessment-reports?download=66:irap-serbia-results> (29.07.2015)

Jovanović Popović M. et al., (2012), National Typology of Residential Buildings in Serbia, University of Belgrade - Faculty of Architecture, GIZ - Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit, Belgrade

Ministry of Construction, Transport and Infrastructure (2015), Rulebook on licensing exams in the field of spatial and urban planning, preparation of technical documentation, construction and energy efficiency and on issuing and revocation of licenses for the authorized urban planner, designer, contractor and responsible planner, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, 27/2015 http://www.ingkomora.rs/zakoni/pravilnici/59713_Pravilnik_o_polaganju_strucnog_ispita.pdf

Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, (2010), Program of Basic Research, Program of Research in the Field of Technological Development, Program of Co-financing of integral and Interdisciplinary Research and Program for Provision of Equipment and Facilities for R&D activities in Period 2011-2014, Official Document No. 451-01-967/2010-01, 2010, http://mpn.gov.rs/images/content/strategije/program_23052010.pdf (28.07.2015)

Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, (2013a), Rulebook on technical and other requirements for petroleum-derived liquid fuels, Official Gazette of the RS No. 75/2013, 2013, url: <http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/nafta-i-gas/izmena/C12%20Pravilnik%20o%20tehnickim%20i%20drugim%20zahtevima%20za%20tecna%20goriva%20naftnog%20porekla.pdf> (28.07.2015)

Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, (2014a), Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of household refrigerating appliances, Official Gazette of the RS, No. 17/14, url: http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/D_06_Pravilnik_o_ozacavanju_energetske_efikasnosti_rashladnih_uredjaja_za_domacinstvo.pdf (28.07.2015)

Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, (2014b), Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of household washing machines (Official Gazette of the RS, No 24/14);

http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/D_02_Pravilnik_o_ozacavanju_energetske_efikasnosti_masina_za_pranje_vesa_u_domacinstvu.pdf (28.07.2015)

Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, (2014c), Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of household dishwashers (Official Gazette of the RS, No 24/14);

http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/D_03_Pravilnik_o_ozacavanju_energetske_efikasnosti_masina_za_pranje_sudova_u_domacinstvu.pdf (28.07.2015)

Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, (2014d), Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of electric ovens (Official Gazette of the RS, No 24/14);

http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/D_04_Pravilnik_o_ozacavanju_energetske_efikasnosti_elektricnih_pecnica.pdf (28.07.2015)

Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, (2014e), Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of electric bulbs and lamps (Official Gazette of the RS, No 24/14);

http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/D_05_Pravilnik_o_ozacavanju_energetske_efikasnosti_elektricnih%20sijalica_i_svet_iljki.pdf (28.07.2015)

Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, (2014f), Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of TVs (Official Gazette of the RS, No 24/14); http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/D_07_Pravilnik_o_ozacavanju_energetske_efikasnosti_televizora.pdf (28.07.2015)

Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment, (2014g), Rulebook on the labelling of energy efficiency of air-conditioning devices, Official Gazette of the RS, No 24/14,

http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/D_08_Pravilnik_o_ozacavanju_energetske_efikasnosti_uredjaja_za_klimatizaciju.pdf (28.07.2015) (28.07.2015)

Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment (2014h), Rulebook on the conditions for allocation and use of the Budget Fund for improving energy efficiency of the Republic of Serbia and criteria for exemption from the obligation of performing an energy audit, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia 8/2014, http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/C_02_Pravilnik_o_uslovima_za_raspodelu_i_koriscenje_sredstava_Budzetskog_fonda_za_unapredenje_energetske_efikasnosti.pdf (28.7.2015)

Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment (2014i): Decisions on the allocation of funds from the Budget Fund, the first open call http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/efikasnost/C_04_Odluka_o_dodeli_sredstava_po_prvom_javnom_pozivu_iz_Budzetskog_fonda.pdf (28.7.2015)

Ministry of Energy, Development and Environment (2014j): Decisions on the allocation of funds from the Budget Fund, <http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/Odluka%20o%20dodeli%20sredstava%20iz%20Budzetskog%20fonda.PDF> (28.7.2015)

Ministry of Mining and Energy, (2015a), Rulebook on conditions in terms of personnel, equipment and facilities of the organization that conducted the training for energy managers and authorized energy advisors, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 12/2015,

<http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/Pravilnik%20o%20uslovima%20u%20pogledu%20kadrova.pdf?uri=CELEX:32009L0028>
(28.07.2015)

Ministry of Mining and Energy, (2015b), The Rulebook on the manner of implementation and content of training program for energy managers, expenditures for attending the training courses, and detailed conditions, curriculum, and taking of the examination for energy managers, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 12/2015, <http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/Pravilnik%20o%20nacinu%20sprovodjenja%20obuke.pdf?uri=CELEX:32009L0028> (28.07.2015)

Ministry of Mining and Energy, (2015c), Rulebook on Model Energy Service Contracts for the Implementation of Energy Efficiency when Users are from Public Sector (Official Gazette of the RS, No 41/2015), <http://www.mre.gov.rs/doc/efikasnost-izvori/00%20-%20Pravilnik.pdf> (28.07.2015)

Petrikić & Partneri AOD (2015), ESCO - A new opportunity for the Serbian Energy Market, CMS Reich-Rohrwig Hainz, 2015, url: http://www.cms-rrh.com/Hubbard.FileSystem/files/Publication/e6d5b25f-e6f0-464d-b764-707057932f71/Presentation/PublicationAttachment/b5394b07-0070-4fd3-abf0-70db0f255551/CMS_ESCO_brochure.pdf (28.07.2015)

Ministry of Environment, Mining and Spatial Planning, (2011a), Rulebook on Energy Efficiency of Buildings, Official Gazette of the RS, No. 61/11, 2011 a, http://www.ingkomora.org.rs/strucniispiti/download/ee/PRAVILNIK_O_EEZ_za%20obuku.pdf
(28.07.2015)

Ministry of Environment, Mining and Spatial Planning, (2011b) Rulebook on Conditions, Content and Manner of Issuance of Certificates of Energy Performance of Buildings (Official Gazette of the RS, No. 61/11) <http://www.kombeg.org.rs/Slike/UdrGradjevinarstvo/Statika/Informacije-zakoni/EnergetskaEfik.pdf>
(28.07.2015)

Ministry of Transport, Rulebook of the technical measures for slowing road traffic, 2013, Official Gazette of the Republic of Serbia, No. 149/2013, <http://slglasnik.info/sr/9-30-01-2014/22305-pravilnik-o-tehnickim-sredstvima-za-usporavanje-saobraćaja-na-putu.html> (29.07.2015)

National Assembly of the Republic of Serbia, (2011), Law on Ratification of the Agreement on the adoption of unified technical regulations for wheeled vehicles, equipment and parts which can be fitted and/or used on vehicles with wheels and conditions for reciprocal recognition of approvals awarded in line with these regulations, Official Gazette of the RS - International agreements, No. 11/2011, url: http://demo.paragraf.rs/combined/Old/t/t2011_12/t12_0360.htm (28.07.2015)

Public Enterprise - Roads of Serbia, Introduction and Benefits of Intelligent Transport Systems, 2009, ITS Mini - Workshop Belgrade, <http://www.putevi-srbije.rs/strategijapdf/itsuvodeng.pdf> (29.07.2015)

Road Traffic Safety Agency, (2015), Road accidents data in the Republic of Serbia in the past decades, 2015, url: <http://en.abs.gov.rs/road-accidents-data-in-the-republic-of-serbia-in-the-past-decades>
(30.07.2015)

Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, (2011a): Municipalities and Regions in Republic of Serbia, Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, Belgrade, URL: <http://webrzs.stat.gov.rs/WebSite/Public/PublicationView.aspx?pKey=41&pubType=1> (30.07.2015)

Statistical Office of the Republic of Serbia, (2011b): Census, <http://webrzs.stat.gov.rs/WebSite/Public/SiteSearchResult.aspx?searchKey=popis>

Stojiljkovic D., Komatina M., Stefanovic P., Kutlaca Dj., Djukic Z., Sataric D., National background report on Energy for Republic of Serbia, 2012, url: http://wbc-inco.net/object/document/9828/attach/0_National_Background_Report_Energy_Serbia_2012.pdf

Ministry of construction, transport and infrastructure, (2014): Rulebook on technical tools for slowing road traffic, http://www.putevi-srbije.rs/pdf/regulativa/pravilnik_o_tehnickim_sredstvima_za_usporavanje_saobracaja_na_putu.pdf (10.09.2015)

HERON (No: 649690): Deliverable D.1.2

STATUS-QUO ANALYSIS OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICIES IN 8 EU COUNTRIES

D 1.2.

**PART OF WORK PACKAGE 1: MAPPING OF ENERGY EFFICIENCY POLICY INSTRUMENTS AND
AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGIES IN BUILDINGS AND TRANSPORT**

DATE 05 AUGUST 2015

Partner: "Oxford Brookes University"

Università Commerciale
Luigi Bocconi

OXFORD
BROOKES
UNIVERSITY

Universiteit
Antwerpen

Wuppertal Institute
for Climate, Environment
and Energy

SEI

STOCKHOLM
ENVIRONMENT
INSTITUTE

Institution: Oxford Brookes University, UK

Steering Committee member ⁽¹⁾: Prof Rajat Gupta

Prepared by: Prof Rajat Gupta, Mariam Kapsali, Matt Gregg, Laura Barnfield, Adorkor Bruce-Konuah, Low Carbon Building Group, Oxford Institute for Sustainable Development, Oxford Brookes University, UK

⁽¹⁾ The Steering Committee member has the responsibility for ensuring the quality of the report.

HERON: Forward – looking socio-economic research on Energy Efficiency in EU countries

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Contents

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	5
GLOSSARY	6
ACRONYMS	7
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	10
1. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL	11
1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE BUILDINGS SECTOR	11
1.1.1 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	11
1.1.2 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS / INFORMATIVE POLICY INSTRUMENTS	18
1.1.3 ECONOMIC POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	28
1.1.4 CAPACITY BUILDING AND NETWORKING.....	35
1.1.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR THE PROMOTION OF ENERGY SERVICES	38
1.1.6 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT AND BEST AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGY (BAT) PROMOTION	43
1.1.7 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR IN THE UNITED KINGDOM	48
1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR	65
1.2.1 PLANNING INSTRUMENTS.....	65
1.2.2 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS.....	68
1.2.3 FINANCIAL POLICY INSTRUMENTS	74
1.2.4 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS	79
1.2.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT	82
1.2.6 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR IN THE UNITED KINGDOM	85
2. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE REGIONAL / LOCAL LEVEL	101
2.1 PRESENTATION OF THE CASE STUDY: LONDON	101
ANNEXES	107
REFERENCES	108

Table of Figures

No table of figures entries found.

Table of Tables

Table 1. Final energy savings from Building Regulations	14
Table 2. Final energy savings from the Energy Company Obligation (ECO)	16
Table 3. Final energy savings from the Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS)	18
Table 4. Final energy savings from the Smart Metering Implementation Programme	25
Table 5. Final energy savings from Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs)	27
Table 6. Final energy savings from the Green Open Homes Network initiative	28
Table 7. Final energy savings from the Green Deal Programme	30

Table 8. Final energy savings from the Salix Finance Public Sector Loan Scheme.....	32
Table 9. Final energy savings from the Electricity Demand Reduction (EDR) Pilot Scheme.....	35
Table 10. Final energy savings from the Big Energy Saving Network	36
Table 11. Final energy savings from the Energy Management for non-specialists training programme	37
Table 12. Final energy savings from the Community Energy Peer Mentoring Programme	38
Table 13. Final Energy Savings from Licence Lite (SLC 11.3)	40
Table 14. Final energy savings from the Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU).....	41
Table 15. Final energy savings from the Rural Community Energy Fund (RCEF) and the Urban Community Energy Fund (UCEF).....	43
Table 16. Final energy savings from the Technology Strategy Board (TSB)/InnovateUK	45
Table 16. Final energy savings from the Code for Sustainable Homes	46
Table 17. Final energy savings from the Energy Technology Institute (ETI).....	47
Table 18. Summary table for the building sector in the UK	48
Table 19. Final energy savings from the Plug-in Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy.....	66
Table 20. Final energy savings from the Eco-towns planning policy.....	68
Table 21. Final energy savings from the Vehicle Excise Duty (VED).....	70
Table 22. Final energy savings from the Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation	72
Table 23. Final energy saving from the Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS) - transport	74
Table 24. Final energy savings from the Cycle to Work Scheme	76
Table 25. Final energy savings from the Plug-in Car and Van Grants	78
Table 26. Final energy savings from the Low Emission Bus Scheme (LEBS)	78
Table 27. Final energy savings from Fuel Economy labels for cars	80
Table 28. Final energy savings from the National Standard for cycle training	81
Table 29. Final energy savings from the Eco-driving/FuelGood driver training schemes	82
Table 30. Final energy savings from the Research Council's Energy Programme (RCEP).....	83
Table 31. Final energy savings from the Technology Strategy Board (TSB)/Innovate UK.....	84
Table 32. Summary table for the transport sector in the UK	85
Table 33. Overview of activities in London regarding energy efficiency in the building and transport sectors (GLA, 2011)	102

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 649690. The content of this document reflects only the authors' views and the EASME is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

GLOSSARY

If any, please include. If not, please leave blank.

ACRONYMS

BAT	best available technologies
BESN	Big Energy Saving Network
BIS	Department for Business Innovation and Skills
CARES	Community Renewable Energy Scheme
CCA	Climate Change Agreements
CCL	Climate Change Levy
CCS	Carbon Capture and Storage
CERT	Carbon Emission Reduction Target
CESP	Community Energy Saving Programme
CHP	Combined Heat and Power
CSCO	Carbon Saving Community Obligation
CSE	Centre for Sustainable Energy
CSH	Code for Sustainable Homes
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
DCLG	Department for Communities and Local Government
DEC	Display Energy Certificates
DECC	Department of Energy and Climate Change
Defra	Department for Environment, Food & Rural Affairs
DfT	Department for Transport
DH	Department of Health
DNO	District network operators
ECA	Enhanced Capital Allowances
ECO	Energy Company Obligation
EDR	Electricity Demand Reduction
EE	Energy Efficiency
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EPC	Energy Performance Certificate
EPSRC	Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council
ESCO	Energy service company
ESME	Energy system modelling environment

ESOS	Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme
EST	Energy Saving Trust
ETI	Energy Technology Institute
EU	European Union
EV	Electric Vehicles
FiT	Feed-in Tariff
FYRs	First Year Rates
GD ORB	Green Deal Oversight and Registration Body
GGC	Greening Government Commitments
GHG	Green House Gas
GLA	Greater London Authority
HEaT	Household Efficiency and Thermal improvement Programme (NI)
HEEPS	Home Energy Efficiency Programmes for Scotland
HGV	heavy goods vehicles
HNDU	Heat Networks Delivery Unit
ICE	Incentive on Connections Engagement
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPEEC	International Partnership for Energy Efficiency Cooperation
ITOs	instructor training organisations
LEBS	Low Emission Bus Scheme
LESA	Landlords Energy Saving Allowance
MEPS	Minimum energy performance standards
NI	Northern Ireland
NIEA	Northern Ireland Environment Agency
NISEP	Northern Ireland Sustainable Energy Programme
NRMM	Non-road mobile machinery
NRW	Natural Resources Wales
Ofgem	Office of Gas and Electricity Markets
OLEV	Office for Low Emission Vehicles
PHEV	plug-in hybrid electric vehicles
PICG	Plug-In Car Grant
PiP	Plugged-In Places programme
RCEF	Rural Community Energy Fund
RCEP	Research Councils Energy Programme

RHI	Renewable Heat Incentive
RTFO	Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation
SAFED	Safe and Fuel Efficient Driving
SBRI	Small Business Research Initiative
SEPA	Scottish Environment Protection Agency
SME	Small Medium Enterprises
SOGE	Sustainable Operations on the Government Estate
SR	Standard Rates
TSB	Technology Strategy Board
TWh	terawatt-hours
UK	United Kingdom
ULEV	Ultra-Low Emissions Vehicles
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UREF	Urban Community Energy Fund
VED	Vehicle Excise Duty
VERA	Vehicle and Registration Act
VCA	Vehicle Certification Agency
ZCH	Zero Carbon Hub

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report outlines the energy efficiency policy instruments and measures implemented in the United Kingdom at national and local levels. The first section provides details on regulatory, dissemination and awareness, economic, capacity building and networking, promotion of energy services and research and development policy instruments in use in the UK. It outlines specific policy measures used in terms of their objectives, target groups, rules and influencing mechanisms, implementation network, and outcomes (quantitative energy savings where available).

The second part of the report uses the case study of London to describe the multi-level policy processes between the national, regional (federal state, province etc.) and local level. The focus lies on the vertical integration of local actions into the national energy efficiency framework and vice versa.

1. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE NATIONAL LEVEL

In comparison to Report D 1.1 where policy packages are in the focus of analysis, this chapter presents single energy efficiency policy instruments implemented in the eight considered countries. Additionally, case studies for eight provinces or cities, focussing on the vertical integration of local actions into the national energy efficiency framework and vice versa, will be presented.

1.1 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE BUILDINGS SECTOR

1.1.1 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

The United Kingdom has a very comprehensive number of policies, which focus on regulation. These include minimum energy performance standards (MEPs), energy audits and energy management. The main policy instruments that are described below are:

- Building regulations
- Energy company obligations
- Mandatory energy assessment schemes

1.1.1.1 Building Regulations

- General information:** The legislative framework of the Building Regulations is principally made up of The Building (Approved Inspectors etc) Regulations 2010 (SI 2010/2215) and the Building Regulations Legislation 2010 (SI 2010/2214)¹. 'Approved Documents' support the fourteen technical 'Parts' of the Building Regulations, and Regulation 7 (workmanship and materials) and aim to provide supporting guidance to show builders how compliance with building regulations may be achieved. First implemented in the 1980s, fabric energy efficiency is enforced through Approved Document Part L of the UK Building Regulations² and has been progressively tightening over time to make buildings more energy efficient, e.g. towards the approach of the Zero Carbon Homes Standard in 2016 (DECC, 2014c). As of this year however, progression toward the 2016 Standard is no longer part of the Government's plan (HM Treasury, 2015). Building Regulations are devolved across the four UK administrations but energy standards are broadly comparable in content, scope and in the levels of improvement delivered (DECC, 2014c). Amendments are too numerous to list here but most notably the Part L split into four Approved Documents from 2006 to encompass New dwellings (L1A), Existing Dwellings (L1B), New Buildings other than Dwellings (L2A) and Existing Buildings other than dwellings (L2B) (BRAC & DCLG, 2015).
- Type of policy instrument:** Regulatory, it is required that all new buildings and additions meet or exceed specified fabric energy efficiency target.
- Objectives:** The primary objective of Part L of the Building Regulations is to guide the design process to arrive at or progress beyond a required fabric energy efficiency target.

¹<http://www.planningportal.gov.uk/buildingregulations/buildingpolicyandlegislation/currentlegislation/buildingregulations/>

² <http://www.planningportal.gov.uk/buildingregulations/approveddocuments/partl/>

d. Target groups: Anyone responsible for dwelling and non-dwelling building work (e.g., designer, builder, installer) must ensure that the construction and design work complies with all applicable requirements of the Building Regulations. The Building Regulations are made up of procedural and technical provisions. Some works are exempt from the whole of the Regulations, whilst others are only exempt from certain aspects. In relation to technical requirements, exemptions are judged by two approaches (depending on which Approved Document):

- Parts A to K, M, N and P are judged against seven classes set out in Schedule 2 of the Building Regulations³;
 - Class 1 (Buildings controlled under other legislation) e.g. building in which explosives are manufactured or stored under a licence granted through the Manufacture and Storage of Explosives Regulation 2005.
 - Class 2 (Buildings not frequented by people)
 - Class 3 (Greenhouses)
 - Class 3 (Agricultural buildings)
 - Class 4 (Temporary buildings)
 - Class 5 (Ancillary buildings)
 - Class 6 (Small detached buildings) e.g. detached, single storey building, with floor area less than 30m², with no sleeping accommodation and has no point less than one metre from the boundary of its curtilage or, which is constructed substantially of non-combustible material
 - Class 7 (Extensions) e.g. ground level conservatory, porch, covered yard/way or carport (open on at least two sides) where the floor area does not exceed 30m², provided that, where applicable, the glazing satisfies the requirements of Part N of Schedule 1.
- Part L is judged against criteria set out in Regulation 21[a1] of the Building Regulations. Regulation 9⁴ provides further detail on exemptions.

Generally, the Part L requirements apply to buildings, or extensions of such buildings (except Class 7: extensions type), or the carrying out of any work to, or in connection of any such building or extension where the building is a) a roofed construction with walls, and uses energy to condition the indoor climate. Part L requirements do not apply to buildings that fall into the following categories:

- Certain buildings which are listed, in conservation areas or are included in the Schedule of Monuments; where compliance with the energy efficiency requirements would unacceptably alter their character or appearance.
- Buildings which are used primarily or solely as places of worship.
- Temporary buildings with a planned time of use of 2 years or less, with low energy demand.

³ <http://www.planningportal.gov.uk/permission/responsibilities/buildingregulations/approvalneeded/exemptions>

⁴ <http://www.planningportal.gov.uk/permission/responsibilities/buildingregulations/approvalneeded/exemptions/bcexemptreg9>

- Industrial sites, workshops and non-residential agricultural buildings with low energy demand.
- Stand-alone buildings other than dwellings with a total useful floor area of less than 50m².

e. Rules and influencing mechanisms: Prosecution and enforcement notices are applicable if there is a failure to comply with the Building Regulations⁵, in terms of:

- Not following the building control procedures set out for handling building work, or;
- Building work is carried out which does not comply with the requirements contained in the Building Regulations.

In terms of prosecution, the local authority (LA) has a general duty to enforce Building Regulations in its area. If informal enforcement does not achieve compliance, the LA has two formal enforcement powers:

- **Prosecution:** if a person carrying out building work contravenes the Building Regulations, the LA may prosecute them in the Magistrate's Court. An unlimited fine may be imposed (sections 35 and 35A of the Building Act 1984). Prosecution is possible for up to two years after the completion of the offending work, and will usually be taken against the person carrying out the work (builder, installer, main contractor).
- **Enforcement notice:** the LA may serve an enforcement notice instead of, or in addition to prosecution. The notice is served on the building owner and requires the alteration or removal of work which contravenes the regulations (section 36 of the 1984 Act). If the owner does not comply with the notice, the LA can undertake the work itself and recover the costs from the owner. A Section 36 enforcement notice must be served after the expiration of 12 months from the date of completion of the building work. An LA cannot take enforcement action under section 36 if the work is carried out in accordance with the full plans application which the LA either approved, or failed to reject.

Where an approved inspector is providing the Building Control Service, the responsibility for checking that the Building Regulations are complied with during the building works lies with that inspector. However, approved inspectors do not have formal enforcement powers. If the building work is considered, by the Building Inspector, to not comply with Building Regulations and there is a refusal to bring it into compliance, the inspector will cancel the initial notice. If no other approved inspector takes on the work, the building control function will be taken on automatically by the LA.

f. Implementation network: The Secretary of State approves any amendments to the Building Regulations 2010 (SI 2010/2214), following guidance from relevant Government departments such as the Department for Communities and Local Government (DCLG) and advisory non-departmental public bodies such as the Building Regulations Advisory Committee (BRAC), as well as industry members. The DCLG provide ongoing practical actions and support to provide effective building regulations including publishing supporting guidance known as Approved Documents, overseeing and supporting building control organizations, publishing research to provide a scientific basis to underpin regulations and providing the secretariat for the Building

⁵ <http://www.planningportal.gov.uk/permission/responsibilities/buildingregulations/failure>

Regulations Advisory Committee for England (BRAC), which advises the Secretary of State. In terms of ensuring the Building Regulations are enforced, the LAs are responsible for building works (except those which are exempt) in their local area, and for ensuring compliance. All building works subject to Building Regulations are checked by Local Authority Building Control or a private Approved Inspector, or carried out by a 'Competent Person', and with Local Authorities enforcing compliance. In Scotland, where such work requires a building warrant, verification of building work is the responsibility of local authorities alone. (DECC, 2014c; BRAC & DCLG, 2015).

- g. Outcomes:** (i) Estimate of observed and projected energy savings (dwellings and non-dwellings) up to end of 2012: 13.3 TWh; Estimated energy consumption savings (dwellings and non-dwellings): 7.1 TWh in 2014; 14.2 TWh in 2015 (DECC, 2014c); beyond 2015 estimates are no longer relevant following the recent policy shift away from Zero Carbon Standards (HM Treasury, 2015). (ii) Changes to Part L, 2013: best estimate total cost £1,109m (DCLG, 2013).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 1. Final energy savings from Building Regulations

Programme	Savings up to end of 2012	Savings total 2014-2020
Building Regulations	47.88PJ	475.2PJ (domestic) 234PJ (non-domestic)

1.1.1.2 Energy Company Obligation (ECO)

- a. General information:** The legislative framework for the Energy Company Obligation is the Energy Act 2011 and the Electricity and Gas (Energy Companies Obligation) Order 2014 (2012 No.3219)⁶ and the following subsequent amendments:

- The Electricity and Gas (Energy Companies Obligation) (Amendment) Order 2014 (2014 No. 1131)⁷
- The Electricity and Gas (Energy Companies Obligation) (Determination of Savings) (Amendment) Order 2014 (2014 No. 2897)⁸
- The Electricity and Gas (Energy Companies Obligation) (Amendment) (No. 2) Order 2014 (2014 No. 3231)⁹

Previously, it was covered by the Electricity and Gas (Energy Companies Obligation) Order 2012 (2012 No. 3018)¹⁰. Under the Energy Act 2011¹¹, the 'energy company obligations provisions' means:

⁶http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2014/3219/pdfs/uksi_20143219_en.pdf

⁷ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2014/1131/pdfs/uksi_20141131_en.pdf

⁸ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2014/2897/pdfs/uksi_20142897_en.pdf

⁹ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2014/3231/pdfs/uksi_20143231_en.pdf

¹⁰ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/3018/pdfs/uksi_20123018_en.pdf

¹¹ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2011/16/pdfs/ukpga_20110016_en.pdf

- sections 33BC and 33BD of the Gas Act 1986 and sections 41A and 41B of the Electricity Act 1989 (promotion of reductions in carbon emissions and home-heating costs),
- sections 103 and 103A of the Utilities Act 2000 (overall carbon emissions and home-heating cost reduction targets), and
- section 103B of the Utilities Act 2000 (Secretary of State's power to require information about carbon emissions and home-heating cost reduction targets).

The latest Energy Company Obligation (ECO2) was launched on 1st April 2015 (running until 31st March 2017) to reduce the UK's energy consumption and support people living in fuel poverty by funding energy efficiency improvements in homes. It extended the original scheme, which ended on 31st March 2015. The larger energy companies are set obligations to install insulation and heating measures in order to achieve reductions in energy usage and heating costs. ECO works alongside the Green Deal as a way of supporting the installation of energy efficiency measures in low-income households and areas, and in properties that are harder to treat. The ECO replaced two previous schemes, the Carbon Emissions Reduction Target (CERT) and the Community Energy Saving Programme (CESP). There are 3 obligations under the ECO. *Carbon Emissions Reduction Obligation*: provides solid wall, cavity wall and loft insulation measures, and connections to district heating systems, alongside secondary measures including double glazing and draught proofing. *Carbon Saving Community Obligation (CSCO)*: provides insulation measures and connections to district heating systems to households in specified low income areas. Suppliers must meet 15% of their obligation by installing measures in rural areas. Ofgem has published a tool to assist installers and customers to identify eligible CSCO and CSCO rural areas. *Affordable Warmth Obligation*: provides heating and insulation measures to consumers living in private tenure properties that receive particular means-tested benefits. This obligation supports low income consumers that are vulnerable to the impact of living in cold homes (DECC, 2012c).

- Type of policy instrument:** Regulatory: ECO places legal obligations on the larger energy suppliers to deliver energy efficiency measures to domestic energy users (DECC, 2012c).
- Objectives:** ECO and Green Deal aim to help reduce carbon emissions from Britain's domestic building stock, which is an essential part of the UK's plan to meet its statutory domestic carbon emission reduction targets by 2050 (DECC, 2012c).
- Target groups:** Energy suppliers in relation to their end-users, particularly low income, fuel poor, hard to treat homes. The Green Deal and ECO do not cover Northern Ireland. (DECC, 2012c).
- Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Suppliers with a customer base of less than 250,000 customer accounts will be exempt from the ECO (DECC, 2012c). Penalty for non-compliance: unspecified financial penalty, if financial penalty is not paid, licenses may be revoked (Ofgem, 2014).
- Implementation network:** ECO is administered by the Office for Gas and Electricity Markets (Ofgem) (DECC, 2012c), alongside the Warm Home Discount (WHD), through the Energy Efficiency and Social Programmes team, that is part of Ofgem's Environmental Programmes team. Until March 2015, Ofgem E-Serve (on behalf of the Gas and Electricity Markets Authority) was the Administrator for ECO.
- Outcomes:** (i) The actual total carbon target runs between January 2013 to March 2015 and is 27.8MtCO₂ (DECC, 2012a). Estimated energy consumption savings: 0.7 TWh in 2013; 1.4 TWh in 2014; 2.1 TWh in 2015 (DECC, 2014c). (ii) Best estimate total cost £17.3bn (ECO and Green Deal

combined) (iii) Expected benefits to wider society from improved air quality (£1.2bn to £1.6bn), non-traded carbon savings (£3.0bn to £4.8bn) and traded carbon allowance savings (£1.4bn to £1.5bn). Jobs are likely to be created in the solid wall insulation market where demand is expected to rise steeply. Industry responses to the consultation have suggested that the reduction in basic insulation measures (CWI and LI) may induce loss of jobs and closure of manufacturing capacity, given that skills and resources could not be expected to be redeployed in the SWI sector. However, support for hard to treat CWI and SWI which are more labour intensive than easy to treat CWI and LI, is expected to compensate for any reductions in capacity and to increase the number of jobs in the insulation sector to around 39,000-60,000 by 2015 (DECC, 2012c). ECO measures – provisional figures show there were 1,456,891 measures installed under ECO up to the end of April 2015 (DECC, 2015a).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 2. Final energy savings from the Energy Company Obligation (ECO)

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Energy Company Obligation (ECO)	2.52PJ	90.36PJ

1.1.1.3 Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS)

- a. **General information:** Introduced June 2014, ESOS is a mandatory energy assessment scheme for large organisations in the UK. It was established by the UK Government in order to implement Article 8 (4-6) of the EU Energy Efficiency Directive (2012/27/EU)¹². The ESOS Regulations 2014¹³ give effect to the scheme. Organisations that qualify for ESOS must carry out ESOS assessments every 4 years. These assessments are audits of the energy used by their buildings, industrial processes and transport to identify cost-effective energy saving measures (Environment Agency, 2015).
- b. **Type of policy instrument:** Regulatory; ESOS is a mandatory scheme (Environment Agency, 2015).
- c. **Objectives:** To target a gap in the existing policy landscape and help them to cut their energy costs, by providing targeted cost-effective recommendations to improve their energy efficiency. It will stimulate demand amongst UK businesses for energy efficiency measures, by making clear in the assessments what savings could be made. The assessments will review the organisations' entire energy consumption including buildings, industrial processes and transport activities (DECC, 2014c).
- d. **Target groups:** ESOS applies to large UK undertakings (UK company that either employs 250 or more people, or has an annual turnover in excess of 50m euro, and an annual balance sheet total in excess of 43m euro; or an overseas company with a UK registered establishment which has 250 or more employees paying income tax to the UK) and their corporate groups. It mainly

¹² <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2012:315:0001:0056:EN:PDF>

¹³ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2014/1643/pdfs/uksi_20141643_en.pdf

affects businesses but can also apply to not-for-profit bodies and any other non-public sector undertakings that are large enough to meet the qualification criteria. Corporate groups qualify if at least one UK group member meets the ESOS definition of a large undertaking (Environment Agency, 2015).

- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The environmental regulator is responsible for compliance and enforcement activities. The regulator may issue civil sanctions including financial penalties (ranging from £5k-50k if an organisation does not meet the scheme's obligations (Environment Agency, 2015).
- f. Implementation network:** Overall, the Environment Agency is responsible for administering the scheme across the UK, and holding the UK register. A registered office or principal place of activity (in the absence of a registered office) determines the regulator, in terms of compliance and enforcement activities (Environment Agency, 2015):
- The Environment Agency (England)
 - Northern Ireland Environment Agency (Northern Ireland)
 - Scottish Environment Protection Agency (Scotland)
 - Natural Resources Wales (Wales)
 - DECC Offshore Oil & Gas Environment and Decommissioning (offshore).

In relation to undertaking an ESOS assessment, a corporate group demonstrates compliance using either:

- An ISO 50001 energy management system certified by an accredited certification body (United Kingdom Accreditation Service (UKAS) accredited, a body accredited by another EU member state's national accreditation body or a body accredited by a body which is a member of the International Accreditation Forum), and covers all their energy use (for the whole corporate group in the UK),
- Display Energy Certificates (DECs), which are defined by the Energy Performance of Buildings Regulations 2008 (Northern Ireland) and the Energy Performance of Buildings Regulations 2012 (as amended) (England and Wales). DECs form part of the implementation in England and Wales of the European Directives 2002/91/EC and 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings. DECs are undertaken by qualified assessors.
- Green Deal Assessments (GDAs), can be part of an ESOS compliant energy assessment for the types of energy consumption they cover, if they qualify as per regulation 7 of the Green Deal Framework Regulations 2012¹⁴
- ESOS compliant energy audits. All such energy audits must be reviewed by an ESOS lead assessor. An register of approved lead assessors is available online via the UK Government's ESOS webpage¹⁵. An assessor can be an employee of the business, or a third party. The assessor is not held responsible for compliance by the regulators; therefore it is recommended that a member of the corporate group/organisation who

¹⁴ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/2079/contents/made>

¹⁵ <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/energy-savings-opportunity-scheme-esos>

understands the ESOS requirements, and works with the lead assessor to ensure the overall approach taken is compliant with ESOS.

The Environment Agency, and the other regulators do not provide standard templates for ESOS related data/activities and/or presentation of findings. Only the data to evidence that 90% of the total energy consumption is compliant via ESOS audits or other alternative routes to compliance, is required to be undertaken and recorded. This is to reduce the administrative burden on organisations that have existing data management procedures and tools.

- g. Outcomes:** (i) Assumptions suggest that ESOS could generate annual savings of around 3.0 TWh per year, of which 2.3TWh from buildings and industrial processes (DECC, 2014b). Current analysis suggests that ESOS has the potential to deliver £1.9 billion of net benefits to the UK and reduce business energy bills by £300 million in its first year (DECC, 2014c). (ii) Best estimate total cost £1,178m (iii) The process of conducting the ESOS assessments themselves will provide employment for auditors and auditing companies. A range of other energy efficiency product and service businesses may also benefit from supporting large enterprises in implementing ESOS assessors' recommendations. The growth in the sector will help the supply side of the market mature, and enable the sector to promote the contribution it can make to a range of enterprises more effectively (DECC, 2014b).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 3. Final energy savings from the Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS)

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS)	unknown	59.4PJ

1.1.2 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS / INFORMATIVE POLICY INSTRUMENTS

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

The UK has a very comprehensive number of policies, which focus on information and awareness. This includes mandatory and voluntary labelling schemes, energy consultation, information campaigns, energy checks and web-based awareness raising programmes. The main policy instruments that are described below are:

- Smart metering
- Energy performance certificates
- Green Open Homes

1.1.2.1 Smart Metering Implementation Programme (including in-home displays)

- a. General information:** The Smart Metering Implementation Programme began its foundation stage in March 2011. The Government's vision is for every home and small business in Great Britain to have smart electricity and gas meters. The programme aims to replace 53 million

meters with smart electricity and gas meters in domestic properties and smart or advanced meters in smaller non-domestic sites, benefitting approximately 30 million premises (DECC, 2014d). Most households will have smart meters installed between 2015 and 2020 (DECC, 2012b).

The energy sector in Great Britain is regulated primarily through the Electricity Act 1989¹⁶ and the Gas Act 1986¹⁷, both of which have amended several times to reflect government policy developments. These Acts ensure the supply of gas and electricity under licence; licence-holders are then required to comply with relevant conditions contained within the licence. Below the licence conditions, a number of industry codes are applicable, and which contain the technical and commercial obligations that govern participation in licensed activities. Changes to the above regulatory framework have been, and are being undertaken to ensure every home, and smaller non-domestic premises have smart metering equipment. These changes include:

- Amendments to existing energy licences and industry codes (e.g. the requirement of suppliers to roll out smart meters), and the consequential changes to legislation, licences and codes,
- The introduction of a new licensable activity relating to communications between suppliers and other parties and smart meters in consumer premises, as well as the appointment of a Data and Communications Company (DCC) to carry out this licensed activity.
- The introduction of a new Smart Energy Code, which sets out the rules, rights and obligations for all parties for the new long-term metering arrangements in Great Britain.

The amendments to the regulatory framework, in relation to smart metering include¹⁸:

- **Tranche 1**¹⁹ (came into effect on 30 Nov 2012): mandated the roll-out of smart meters by energy suppliers and the establishment of a code of practice for the installation of Smart Meters.
- **Tranche 2**²⁰ (came into effect on 4 March 2013): set out energy supplier and energy network licence modifications in relation to consumer engagement, data access, reporting and security risk assessments and audits in the period before DCC provides services.

¹⁶ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1989/29/contents>

¹⁷ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1986/44>

¹⁸ <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/smart-meters-information-for-industry-and-other-stakeholders#regulatory-framework-for-smart-metering>

¹⁹ https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/65646/7107-smart-meters-mod-elc-gas-licences.pdf

²⁰

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/128747/Tranche_2_licence_conditions_Ministerial_sign_off.pdf

- **Tranche 3²¹** (came into effect on 14 July 2013): introduced energy supplier and energy network licence conditions to support the creation of a new industry code called the Smart Energy Code (SEC); placed requirements on energy suppliers to ensure that smart meters make key data available to domestic and micro-business consumers, and that key smart meter functions are switched on.

The introduction of these first three tranches supported the establishment of the enduring commercial and regulatory framework for smart metering. In September 2013 Smart DCC Ltd, a wholly owned subsidiary of Capita PLC, was awarded the licence to provide smart metering communication services (the 'DCC Licence'). This award and commencement of the DCC Licence introduced a new licensed entity into the energy market.

Following the award of the DCC Licence, the Government designated the first stage of the SEC. SEC content is being introduced in stages, so that it is in place when the DCC and users of its services need it. The designated version of the SEC was introduced to deal with matters that were required to support the initial operations of the DCC. Further stages have been introduced together with amendments to industry licences where appropriate.

- **Tranches 4 and 5²²** (various dates for coming into effect, starting on 31 March 2014): included new supply licence conditions to ensure consumer access to data as required by the Energy Efficiency Directive (2012/27/EU) and to support 'Smart Change of Supplier'. They also contained changes to energy supply licence conditions related to the mandated roll-out of smart metering. These tranches also introduced further content to the SEC and amendments to the DCC Licence principally concerning the development and financing of DCC services.
- **Tranche 6²³** (came into effect 31 July 2014): included arrangements for the testing regime that will allow the DCC to demonstrate that all the DCC developed systems work prior to its operational service becoming available, introduces the Smart Meter Key Infrastructure (SMKI) and sets out amendments relating to smart metering system requirements, as well as some minor modifications to the DCC Licences identified which are required to ensure that the original policy and regulatory intent is achieved.
- **Tranches 7 and 8 (not yet introduced)**: predominately includes content that is required in advance of User Integration Testing (UIT) and User Entry.

Secondary Legislation: As part of the tranches of regulation changes described above DECC, using their powers under the Energy Act 2008, made amendments to the Electricity Act 1989

²¹ https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/211216/SMMModifications.pdf

²² https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/297873/ModificationsSmartEnergyCode26March14.pdf

²³ <https://www.gov.uk/government/consultations/new-smart-energy-code-content-stage-3>

and Gas Act 1986 (the 'Acts') to make two new statutory instruments that supported the establishment of the DCC:

- **The Electricity and Gas (Smart Meters Licensable Activity) Order 2012 (SI 2012/2400)²⁴:** this Order introduced a new licensable activity into each of the Electricity Act 1989 and the Gas Act 1986. It is unlawful to undertake that activity without holding a licence. The new activity relates to the provision of a service of communicating with smart energy meters on behalf of all licensed energy suppliers.
- **The Electricity and Gas (Competitive Tenders for Smart Meter Communication Licences) Regulations 2012 (SI 2012/2414)²⁵ (DCC Licence Application Regulations):** these set out the competitive application process to award licences for the provision of a service of communicating with smart energy meters on behalf of all licensed energy suppliers. The process under the Regulations allows for a single person to be granted licences for this activity in respect of both electricity and gas smart meters after competition and to become a monopoly provider of communication services in Great Britain.

The UK Government also introduced a new statutory instrument to support the implementation of the *Smart Energy Code, The Electricity and Gas Appeals (Designation and Exclusion) Order 2013 (SI 2013/2429)²⁶*, which extends the right of appeal to the Competition Commission against certain decisions of the Gas and Energy Markets Authority (GEMA) to include decisions in relation to the Smart Energy Code. This right of appeal is in line with other industry codes.

Smart Metering Equipment Technical Specifications

In addition to the regulatory framework outlined above, energy suppliers are also required to take all reasonable steps to install smart metering equipment which meets the requirements of the smart metering equipment technical specifications (SMETS):

- SMETS 1²⁷ was designated by the Secretary of State in December 2012, with minor amendments made to the specification in March 2014. Equipment installed now must be compliant with SMETS 1 if it is to count towards suppliers' roll-out obligations.
- The UK Government has developed drafts of SMETS 2, the Communications Hub Technical Specification (CHTS), the Great Britain Companion Specification (GBCS) and the Security Characteristics for GB Smart Metering, which set out the requirements for the next generation of metering equipment to be installed. These documents and the associated regulatory requirements were notified to the European Commission, as required by the Technical Standards and Regulations Directive, in July 2014.

²⁴ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukdsi/2012/9780111526545/contents>

²⁵ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/2414/introduction/made>

²⁶ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2013/2429/contents/made>

²⁷ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/smart-metering-implementation-programme-technical-specifications>

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Awareness instrument, regulatory: Installers must provide energy efficiency advice as part of the visit to install smart meters and in-home displays (DECC, 2012b).
- c. Objectives:** Through the In-home Display offered by energy suppliers as part of the rollout, consumers will have near-real time information on their energy consumption to help them control energy use, and avoid wasting energy and money. Smart meters will bring an end to estimated billing, help consumers to budget better, make switching between energy suppliers smoother and faster, and help restore trust in the energy market. New products and services will be supported in a vibrant, competitive, more efficient market in energy and energy management. Energy suppliers will have access to accurate data for billing and to improve their customer service. They will also be able to reduce costs, for example by reducing call centre traffic, removing the need for a site visits to read meters (DECC, 2014d).
- d. Target groups:** The Government is requiring energy companies to install 53 million gas and electricity meters at 30 million domestic and smaller non-domestic properties (DECC, 2012b).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Smart meters will be rolled out as standard across the country by 2020, but there will not be a legal obligation on individuals to have one. Energy companies will be required to install smart meters and take all reasonable steps to reach everyone. However, energy companies are not expected to take legal action to fit a smart meter if they cannot get the householder's co-operation (DECC, 2012b).
- f. Implementation network:** The programme is led by the DECC, with co-operation from interested parties such as the energy industry, Ofgem and consumer groups. DECC is responsible for driving delivery and providing active oversight of progress by all delivery parties. During 2014, industry partners including the Data and Communications Company and its contractors, energy suppliers, network operators and manufacturers have continued to develop the systems that will deliver smart meters to consumers when the main installation phase begins (DECC, 2012b). Ofgem, as electricity and gas industry regulator, will be responsible for ensuring compliance with smart metering rules. DECC's aim is to leave the management and evolution of smart metering to energy industry participants, which will then be governed through the arrangements in the Smart Energy Code, and subject to regulatory oversight by Ofgem. DECC will remain responsible for the Government's 'retail energy policy and for the realisation of the benefits set out in the Programme's business case', and if required, 'will introduce further regulation to protect these benefits, using its powers in the Energy Acts 2008 and 2011'²⁸. DECC has worked with industry to develop a Smart Metering Implementation Programme (SMIP) Transition Governance Model; the role of such groups is to support DECC decision-making through advice and recommendations on a variety of issues including planning, risk and issue management, and change control for design and regulatory documents. The key groups are:
- **Smart Metering Steering Group (SMSG):** a strategic level forum to review overall progress of the GB smart metering programme, discuss key challenges and resolve significant escalated issues. Members include: large energy suppliers; smaller energy suppliers; Energy UK; Energy Networks Association; Citizens Advice; Ofgem; Data and

2828

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/386482/DECC_Ofgem_open_letter_on_smart_metering.pdf

Communications Company Licensee; Smart Energy Code Panel; Smart Energy GB; Critical Friend; DECC Senior Responsibility Owner and DECC Minister.

- **Smart Metering Delivery Group (SMDG):** a senior operational level forum through which DECC can work together with key industry and other delivery partners to monitor and drive the delivery of the overall portfolio of GB smart metering programmes, and agree actions required to mitigate key risks and resolve issues that could impact the delivery of the joint programme plan and planned benefits. Members include: large energy suppliers; smaller energy suppliers; Energy UK; Smart Energy GB; ENA; DCC Licensee; Ofgem; SEC Panel; metering equipment manufacturers (trade association level). In addition Consumer Futures and the DECC SRO will have a standing invitation to attend.
- **Technical and Business Design Group (TBDG):** A working level forum through which DECC can work together with key industry and other delivery partners to pro-actively manage changes to the baseline technical and business design products prior to their inclusion in the SEC, thereby ensuring that the integrity of the end-to-end solution is maintained during transition. Members are expected to be Design Lead/Lead Technical Architect level from their respective organisations, and have a detailed understanding of the technical and business design baseline and the impact of changes. Members include: large energy suppliers; smaller energy suppliers; electricity and gas network operators; Energy UK; DCC Licensee; Ofgem; Smart Energy Code Administrative Secretariat; energy services providers; metering equipment manufacturers; Meter Asset Providers and meter operators (trade association level).
- **Implementation Managers Forum (IMF):** a working level forum through which DECC can work together with key industry and other delivery partners to review progress of the portfolio of individual contributor projects and programmes towards the delivery of planned milestones and benefits. Members are expected to be Programme Manager/Implementation Manager level from their respective organisations, and have a detailed understanding of both their own programme and how it fits into the overall portfolio of smart metering programmes. Members include: large energy suppliers; smaller energy suppliers; Energy UK; Smart Energy GB; electricity and gas network operators; DCC Licensee; Ofgem; SECAS; metering equipment manufacturers (trade association level).
- **Regulatory Group (RG):** a working level forum through which key industry and other delivery partners can pro-actively provide advice and support to DECC with its on-going work on the smart metering regulatory framework. Members are expected to have a detailed understanding of the regulatory framework of the energy market.
- **Transitional Security Expert Group (TSEG):** a working level expert forum through which DECC can work together with key industry and other security experts to pro-actively manage security risks, amend security requirements and to oversee security assurance, thereby ensuring that the security of the end-to-end solution is maintained during transition until the relevant SEC security governance is in place. TSEG members are expected to have a detailed understanding of the smart metering security architecture, security requirements, be experienced in security risk management and have the ability to analyse and impact potential new or changed risks. Initial members include: large energy suppliers; smaller energy suppliers; Energy UK; electricity and gas network

operators; DCC Licensee; Ofgem; SECAS; metering equipment manufacturers (trade association level) with representation from the government's security and intelligence services.

- **Transitional SMKI Policy Management Authority Group (TPMAG):** a senior, DECC led, operational level group focused on managing and governing aspects of the Smart Metering Key Infrastructure (SMKI) until SMKI obligations are implemented into the Smart Energy Code (SEC). The long term governance for SMKI is through the SMKI Policy Management Authority (PMA) which was established as a sub-committee of the SEC Panel from 31 July 2014 with its membership, role and powers defined in SEC Section L. However, the TPMAG will continue to provide governance alongside the PMA for the Subsidiary SMKI Documents that are subject to further consultation before they are implemented into the SEC after which the PMA will become responsible for their governance and TPMAG will be closed. The membership and meetings of TPMAG are aligned with the PMA membership and meetings to ensure consistency in the advice provided by the PMA and by TPMAG to the SEC Panel and the Secretary of State in support of:

- Directive 1999/93/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 1999 on a Community framework for electronic signatures that was published on 19 January 2000; and the subsequent
- UK Electronic Communications Act 2000

TPMAG and PMA members include: two large energy suppliers; one smaller energy supplier; one Network Operator; and one independent PKI Specialist with representatives from the DCC Licensee; Ofgem; DECC; and SECAS.

- **Benefits Monitoring and Review Group (BMRG):** a forum for representatives of all delivery partners and the wider stakeholder group to review evidence provided by DECC and by group members on the performance of the smart metering rollout and the benefits realised. The BMRG has a key role in advising on the quality of the rollout, the optimisation of benefits realised, reviewing research and evaluation outputs, managing threats and exploiting opportunities for benefit realisation, identifying new benefits, sharing lessons learned, and reviewing and responding to the broadest range of evidence available. The BMRG has an overview and advisory role to DECC on benefits realisation, which will include continued engagement in developing the reporting framework for monitoring the progress and benefits of the rollout. Core membership of the BMRG comprises representatives from the following organisations: Age UK, Association of Meter Operators, British Electrotechnical and Allied Manufacturers Association, large energy suppliers, small energy suppliers, District Network Operators, Citizens Advice, Ofgem, Energy UK, Smart Energy GB, Energy Networks Association and Energy Savings Trust. Additional participants will include those who are considered benefit enablers and those who receive benefits of Smart Metering.
- g. **Outcomes:** (i) Estimated energy saving potential to 2020: 8TWh (DECC, 2014c). (ii) This national infrastructure programme is expected to deliver £17.1b of benefits at a cost of £10.9b. (iii) Smart meters are expected to have a positive net impact on consumers' bills (DECC, 2012b).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 4. Final energy savings from the Smart Metering Implementation Programme

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Smart Metering Implementation Programme	unknown	64.8PJ

1.1.2.2 Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs)

- a. General information:** The EU Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (2002/91/EC) and the recast Directive, Energy Performance of Buildings (recast) Directive 2010/31/EU²⁹ require that all properties (homes, commercial and public buildings) must have an Energy Performance Certificate (EPC) when sold, built or rented and larger public buildings over 500m² must display a Display Energy Certificate (DEC). This legislation has been transposed into legislation in England and Wales through the Housing Act 2004, the Energy Performance of Buildings (Certificates and inspections) (England and Wales) Regulations 2007 (SI 2007/991)³⁰, and subsequently the Energy Performance of Buildings (England and Wales) Regulations 2012 (SI 2012/3118)³¹. In Scotland, the EU EPBD has been transposed through Building Standards legislation (EPCs for new buildings and inspection of air-conditioning systems) and the Energy Performance of Buildings (Scotland) Regulations 2008 (EPCs for existing buildings)³². In Northern Ireland, the Energy Performance of Buildings (Certificates and Inspection) (Amendment) Regulations 2014 were published in response to outstanding requirements of the (recast) EU Directive 2010/31/EU. This is due to Scotland and Northern Ireland having separate building standards to England and Wales.
- EPCs are produced by accredited energy assessors using standard methods and assumptions about energy usage (IEA, 2015). An EPC contains: information about a property's energy use and typical energy costs recommendations about how to reduce energy use and save money. An EPC gives a property an energy efficiency rating from A (most efficient) to G (least efficient) and is valid for 10 years (DECC, 2014c). A DEC must clearly show the actual energy use of a building, the Operational Rating (information gathered through the EPC), in order to help the public see the energy efficiency of a building. The requirement for DECs came into effect from 1st October 2008. DECs are valid for 10 years, in buildings with a total useful floor area of 500-1,000m²; but only valid for 12months if the building is over 1,000m².
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Dissemination and awareness instruments: The person selling the house, the landlord or the letting agent must show you the EPC if you're buying or renting - An EPC includes a recommendation report that lists cost-effective and other measures to improve the building's energy rating. DCLG has also developed an EPC Adviser tool to help people assess how much money they can save and carbon they can reduce by making their homes more energy efficient; required domestic energy assessors to increase their skills so that they can provide a

²⁹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:153:0013:0035:EN:PDF>

³⁰ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2007/991/contents/made>

³¹ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/3118/pdfs/uksi_20123118_en.pdf

³² http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ssi/2008/309/pdfs/ssi_20080309_en.pdf

more effective service; improved the training for domestic energy assessors to help them provide an effective service; and opened up access to the EPC register of more than 11 million domestic EPCs by providing online access to individual EPCs and making all EPC data held on the register publicly available. / Regulatory: You can be fined if you don't get an EPC when you need one (DECC, 2014c; GOV.UK, 2015a).

- c. **Objectives:** This means that the energy efficiency of one building can easily be compared with another building of the same type. This allows prospective buyers, tenants, owners, occupiers and purchasers to see information on the energy efficiency and carbon emissions from their building so they can consider energy efficiency and fuel costs as part of their investment (DECC, 2014c).
- d. **Target groups:** Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are needed whenever a property is: built, sold, or rented (with the exception of: places of worship, temporary buildings that will be used for less than 2 years, stand-alone buildings with total useful floor space of less than 50 square metres, industrial sites, workshops and non-residential agricultural buildings that don't use a lot of energy, some buildings that are due to be demolished, holiday accommodation that's rented out for less than 4 months a year or is let under a licence to occupy, listed buildings, residential buildings intended to be used less than 4 months a year) (GOV.UK, 2015a).
- e. **Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The current owner can be fined if an EPC is not in place as required (GOV.UK, 2015a). The enforcement of the regulations is the responsibility of local weights and measures authorities i.e. trading standards. The fine is 12.5% of the rateable value of the building, capped at £5,000 (€6,890) and with a default penalty of £750 where the calculation is not possible. A further fine of £200 (€275) can be issued for failure to provide a copy of the EPC, when requested by an enforcement authority officer within seven days. In terms of DEC's, the penalties are; a £500 (€690) fine for failure to display a DEC at all times in a prominent place, and a £1,000 (€1,380) fine for failure to possess a valid advisory report (GVA, unknown).
- f. **Implementation network:** The Domestic and Non-Domestic Energy Performance Certificate Registers are operated by Landmark Information Group on behalf of the Secretary of State for Communities and Local Government (DCLG); DCLG is responsible for making sure buildings in the UK meet the standards required by the EU Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (DCLG, 2015).
- g. **Outcomes:** (i) Energy savings due to EPCs unknown (ii) Best estimate total cost £13.44m (DCLG, 2015). (iii) A Government study has shown that the benefits of energy efficiency extend beyond lowering the cost of bills and cutting carbon emissions. The study found that having a more energy efficient rating can increase a property's value, demonstrating that house buyers and estate agents are beginning to recognise the value of energy efficiency measures. For an average home in England, improving its Energy Performance Certificate rating from band G to E, or from band D to B, could add more than £16,000 to the sale price of the property. This represents a significant development, particularly in the context of the misaligned financial incentives barrier (DECC, 2014c).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 5. Final energy savings from Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs)

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs)	Unknown	Unknown

1.1.2.3 Green Open Homes (complementary to the Green Deal)

- a. **General information:** In 2013, the Department for Energy and Climate Change (DECC) awarded funding to the Centre for Sustainable Energy (CSE), working in partnership with Bristol Green Doors (a national leader in running local low carbon open homes events) to set up a national Green Open Homes network³³ to stimulate more activity and provide support for low carbon open homes events across the country (CSE, 2014).
- b. **Type of policy instrument:** Dissemination and awareness instruments: approach includes a number of sources and methods for dissemination and outreach: website – searchable directory of open home events; 18 guidance notes for event organisers with free marketing graphics, photos, and templates; roadshow events to share experience and advice and networking opportunities for organisers; network newsletter; funding and expert support – grants worth £500 – 20k (total £180k) (CSE, 2014).
- c. **Objectives:** The aim was to help new open homes events and networks get off the ground all around the country, to increase people’s feeling that making energy saving improvements is ‘normal in my neighbourhood’. For groups who already ran small open homes events, our goal was to help them flourish, to make the events bigger, easier to deliver, and have more impact (CSE, 2014).
- d. **Target groups:** Homeowners seeking more information on energy efficiency upgrades, e.g. those with further questions regarding the Green Deal (CSE, 2014).
- e. **Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Grants cannot be used directly for private profit and a budget breakdown must be provided as part of the application; Grant awards of greater than £1,000 can only be made to legally incorporated organisations; Grants cannot be used directly for private profit and a budget breakdown must be provided as part of the application. Public liability insurance is also required (CSE, 2013).
- f. **Implementation network:** DECC funded, delivered by the Centre for Sustainable Energy and Bristol Green Doors (CSE, 2014).
- g. **Outcomes:** (i) Energy savings due to Green Open Homes unknown (ii) Total funding for events from CSE: £180k (CSE, 2014). Most events cost up to £1,000, with some of the larger events costing up to £10,000. However, size of event didn’t necessarily equate with greater cost. Unpaid volunteer time was unquantified.
(iii) Between September 2013 and September 2014, Green Open Homes Network supported 49 organisations with the running of their events, with an average of 16 homes opening at each event (Newbury et al., 2014).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK’s NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

³³ <http://www.greenopenhomes.net/>

Table 6. Final energy savings from the Green Open Homes Network initiative

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Green Open Homes	Unknown	Unknown

1.1.3 ECONOMIC POLICY INSTRUMENTS

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

The UK has a very comprehensive number of economic policy instruments and measures including subsidies, loans, tax exemptions and reductions, tradable permits and certificates. The following are described in more detail below:

- The Green Deal programme (complementary to ECO, Green Open Homes, domestic RHI)
- The Salix Finance public sector energy efficiency loan scheme
- Electricity Demand Reduction (EDR) scheme

1.1.3.1 The Green Deal programme (complementary to ECO, Green Open Homes, domestic RHI)

a. **General information:** Launched in January 2013, the Green Deal was expected to be the UK Government's 'flagship piece of legislation, which will deliver energy efficiency to homes and buildings across the land.'³⁴ Legislation for the programme was first provided in the Energy Act 2011³⁵ and the implementing Regulations are:

- The Green Deal Framework (Disclosure, Acknowledgment, Redress etc.) Regulations 2012 SI 2012 No. 2079³⁶
- The Green Deal (Energy Efficiency Improvements) Order 2012 SI 2012 No. 2106³⁷
- The Green Deal (Qualifying Energy Improvements) Order 2012 SI 2012 No. 2105³⁸
- The Green Deal (Acknowledgment) Regulations 2012 2012 No. 1660³⁹
- The Green Deal (Disclosure) Regulations 2012 SI 2012 No. 1660⁴⁰

It aimed to provide a framework of accredited market participants, through which people pay for some of the cost of improving their homes and businesses using a type of loan that is paid back with the savings they can expect to make on their fuel bills; a pay-as-you-save scheme. The

³⁴ HC Deb 19 May 2011 c491

³⁵ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2011/16/enacted>

³⁶ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/2079/contents/made>

³⁷ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/2106/contents/made>

³⁸ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/2105/contents/made>

³⁹ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/1661/contents/made>

⁴⁰ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/1660/contents/made>

Green Deal process begins with a household employing a Green Deal assessor to provide an energy efficiency rating as well as recommend improvements that are appropriate for the property and indicate whether they can be expected to pay for themselves through reduced energy bills (IEA, 2015). Householders receive a Green Deal assessment and energy performance certificate (EPC). The customer can then take the assessment to a Green Deal provider, for a quote for the finance and installation of one or more of the recommended measures. The provider and customer then agree a Green Deal Plan, to set out the agreed amount and terms of repayment. One main aim of the Green Deal was to encourage the uptake of energy efficiency measures in buildings through reducing the capital costs required by customers and support households to install energy efficiency measures, including: insulation (loft, cavity or solid wall); draught-proofing; improved heating controls; double glazing; and renewable energy technologies (e.g. solar panels) (DECC, 2014c). Therefore, the financing of the Green Deal was critical. The Green Deal Finance Company (GDFC) was a not-for-profit organisation including local authorities and companies whose role was to set-up, finance and administer Green Deal Plans, as part of the overall Green Deal Programme. The GDFC financed the Green Deal by purchasing Green Deal Plans from Green Deal Providers, once the agreed Green Deal measures had been installed and accepted by the consumer. In addition to the GDFC, the UK Government also provided financial incentives directly to consumers through the Green Deal Cashback and Green Deal Home Improvement Fund.

From July 2015, the UK Government stopped funding the Green Deal Finance Company (GDFC) and future funding releases of the Green Deal Home Improvement Fund (GDHIF) due to concerns around low take-up, industry standards and the administrative complexities of the programme.

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Economic: loan system; dissemination and awareness: The Green Deal has a central role to play in raising consumer awareness of the benefits of installing energy efficiency measures; the Green Deal assessment provides the perfect opportunity for targeted advice to be given to consumers, as required by Article 17(2) (DECC, 2014c).
- c. Objectives:** The objective is to help households and small businesses improve energy efficiency or reduce carbon emissions and ensure that they have access to trusted information about energy efficiency. The Green Deal is intended to encourage undertaking of energy assessments. It offers energy efficiency assessments, financing and the installation of energy efficiency measures through a network of Green Deal approved assessors, installers and providers (DECC, 2014c).
- d. Target groups:** Households (owner-occupied and private rented tenants and landlords) in existing dwellings as well as the owners, landlords and tenants of small non-dwellings. The Green Deal and ECO do not cover Northern Ireland (DECC, 2014c).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The Green Deal, although legislated through DECC, is based in the private sector and seeks to enhance the uptake of physical energy efficiency measures as well as increase assessments and awareness of energy use and efficiency in domestic and small non-domestic properties. The Green Deal framework regulations provide a Code of Practice as well as assessor and provider certification in order to ensure consumer protection. The overall authorisation body is the Green Deal Oversight and Registration Body (GD ORB). In addition, a Green Deal Ombudsman and Investigation Service, run by the Ombudsman Services, has been established. The Ombudsman Services provide independent, impartial and cost-effective dispute resolution outside the courts, and operate under appropriate UK legal and regulatory authority.

The Green Deal also sought to positively influence the conflicting interests of tenants and landlords, and is supported by the first tenants' energy efficiency improvements regulations coming into force by 1 April 2016, and the legislation surrounding EPCs ensuring that by 2018, it will be illegal to rent a property with an EPC rating of E or below. Because it is the bill payer in rented dwellings that benefits from energy efficiency improvements, the Landlords Energy Saving Allowance, a financial incentive, allows landlords of domestic rented property to claim tax relief of up to £1,500 per property for the costs of buying and installing energy-saving products (DECC, 2014c).

- f. Implementation network:** The Green Deal Oversight and Registration Body (GD ORB), on behalf of the Secretary of State, manages the authorisation scheme for participants in the Green Deal and is responsible for a number of functions aimed at providing effective administration and oversight of the scheme. The GD ORB is responsible for maintaining a register of all authorised Green Deal Providers, Certification Bodies, Assessors and Installers; maintaining the Green Deal Code of Practice and controlling the use of the Quality Mark; ongoing monitoring of Green Deal Participants against the Code of Practice; producing an annual Green Deal report; and gathering evidence of non-compliance and referring participants to the Ombudsman or the Secretary of State where appropriate and imposing sanctions when directed (DCLG, DWP & DECC, 2015).
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Estimated energy consumption savings (dwelling and non-dwelling): 0.4 TWh in 2014; 0.7 TWh in 2015 (DECC, 2014c). (ii) Best estimate total cost £17.3bn (Green Deal and ECO combined) (DECC, 2012c). (iii) The Green Deal programme will support the creation of up to 60,000 jobs in the insulation sector alone by 2015. Heating and insulation measures will benefit around 230,000 low-income households each year. By 2020 the Green Deal could reduce UK household and business carbon emissions by 4.5 million tonnes per year (DCLG, DWP & DECC, 2015).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 7. Final energy savings from the Green Deal Programme

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
The Green Deal programme	Unknown	28.8PJ

1.1.3.2 The Salix Finance public sector energy efficiency loan scheme

- a. General information:** The EU Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (2002/91/EC) and the subsequent recast Directive (2010/31/EU) sought to ensure the public sector was given a leading role in promoting energy efficiency. Due to this, UK Government created means of funding energy efficiency measures in buildings in the public sector. One such initiative was the funding of the Salix scheme. In 2004 the Salix Finance public sector energy efficiency loan scheme was established to provide public sector organisations with interest free loans for energy efficiency projects (DECC, 2014c). Salix is an independent, not-for-profit organisation that is publicly funded by the DECC, the Department for Education (DoE), the Welsh Government, the Scottish Government and Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE) and provides two types of funding programmes; the Salix Energy Efficiency Loans Scheme (savings from measures

installed due to loan are used to pay back the interest-free loan, and once the loan has been repaid, the continued savings are used within the specific public sector organisation that installed the measures) and the Recycling Fund (a ring-fenced fund managed by the public sector organisation. In this case, the loan is repaid, through the financial savings delivered by the projects, into the fund and is effectively self-sustaining and enables further funding of other energy efficiency projects).

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Economic and dissemination/awareness: interest free loans for energy efficiency improvements in the public sector (DECC, 2014c). Salix also facilitates knowledge sharing through quarterly regional meetings, technical workshops and project case studies. This enables the sharing of this knowledge between organisations helps support Salix clients in delivering long term, cost effective savings (Salix, 2014).
- c. Objectives:** To provide interest free loans to improve the energy efficiency of hospitals, schools and other public sector buildings (DECC, 2014c) in order to ensure the UK's public sector leads by example in terms of achieving a low-carbon economy.
- d. Target groups:** *'Any public sector body who receive the majority of their income directly from the public sector can apply. Only those projects where the resultant energy savings, over the lifetime of the project, go directly back to the public sector and the public sector gains a direct financial benefit are eligible. An example of an ineligible project would be an outsourced estate management contract in which the outsource supplier paid the energy bills and benefitted from any savings achieved from the project. However, if the energy bill was a pass through under the contract and the public sector benefitted from the energy savings, then the project would be eligible'* (Salix, 2014). All public sector organisations (across their whole estates) in England, Wales and Scotland are eligible to apply for funding. Such organisations include schools, higher and further educational institutions, emergency services, hospitals, leisure centres, local authorities, the NHS. Eligibility is dependent on the installation of technologies on the Salix list of eligible technologies, and the completion of the Salix Programme Compliance Tools (Salix, 2014).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Recipients of funding must apply the basic rules of procurement whenever they spend public money. These rules look to make sure that public funds are spent openly and fairly, and make the most of every budget, while protecting against legal challenges, financial penalties and damage to a recipient's reputation (Salix, 2014). In total, over 120 technologies (e.g. boilers, combined heat and power, LED and lighting upgrades, and heat recovery) fit the Salix funding criteria, and as such can be funded through the Salix finance schemes. However, the list of supported technologies is evolving and public sector organisations can discuss the addition of technologies they feel fit the Salix criteria for funding.
- f. Implementation network:** Salix Finance Ltd is grant funded by DECC, with contributions from the Department for Education (DfE), The Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE) and the Welsh and Scottish governments (Salix, 2014). Salix Finance Ltd ensure the participating public sector organisations provide data to ensure cost-effective and energy/carbon savings are achieved.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Estimated energy consumption savings (dwelling and non-dwelling): 0.2 TWh in 2015; 0.5 TWh in 2016 (DECC, 2014c). All projects are forecast to save 538,146 tonnes of CO₂ annually and 7,422,659 tonnes over the projects' lifetime. This represents £98.5 million of annual financial savings to Salix clients' energy bills and £1.395 billion over the projects' lifetime. The average financial payback from all projects is 3.8 years, based on the value of projects in relation

to the forecast annual financial savings from these projects. (ii) Total funding to Salix to date: £198.7m; The cost of generating 1 tonne of lifetime CO₂ saving across all projects is £50.64 per tonne (Salix, 2014). (iii) Salix has funded over 11,000 projects with 794 public sector bodies, valued at £272.8 million. An additional £18 million was provided for Salix loans in 2012-13, £8m of which was ring-fenced for schools. In December 2013 the Government announced a further £90 million for Salix over the next three years to provide loans to improve the energy efficiency of hospitals, schools, and other public sector buildings, building on the Salix scheme (DECC, 2014c).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 8. Final energy savings from the Salix Finance Public Sector Loan Scheme

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Salix Finance	Unknown	21.6PJ

1.1.3.3 Electricity Demand Reduction (EDR) scheme

- a. General information:** The Energy Act 2013⁴¹ contained provisions for a financial incentive to encourage lasting reductions in electricity demand that can be delivered through the Capacity Market⁴²; part of the UK Government's electricity market reform package which seeks to ensure security of electricity supply, encourage investment required to replace older power stations and provide backup for more intermittent and inflexible low carbon generation sources. The Capacity Market was also designed to support the development of more active demand management in the electricity market. Further regulations relating to the Capacity Market include; Electricity Capacity Regulations (2014)⁴³, the Electricity Capacity (supplier payment etc.) regulations 2014⁴⁴, the Electricity Capacity (amending) Regulations 2015⁴⁵.

"A Capacity Market is being introduced in Great Britain to ensure that consumers continue to receive reliable electricity supplies at an affordable cost at times of very high electricity demand. It will provide regular monthly payments to capacity providers during the delivery year. In return, they must be available to produce electricity or shift demand when demand is close to exceeding supply, or face penalties if they fail to deliver the capacity. At present, the Capacity Market will be open to capacity providers in the form of new and existing power stations, electricity storage providers and those who can shift or switch demand to other times (demand side response). EDR could reduce the level of demand placed on the system and, in turn, lower the amount of other

⁴¹ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2013/32/contents/enacted/data.htm>

⁴² <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/electricity-market-reform-capacity-market>

⁴³ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2014/2043/contents/made>

⁴⁴ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2014/3354/contents/made>

⁴⁵ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2015/875/contents/made>

types of capacity that need to be provided. The diagram below illustrates how different types of resources (electricity generators, electricity demand reduction and demand side response) could provide capacity.

The Capacity Market will operate as an auction, with participants bidding in the amount of capacity they are able to offer and a price at which they are willing to provide it. The first capacity auction will take place in December 2014 for delivery four years ahead. In addition, the Government will run transitional arrangements for demand side response capacity in 2015 and 2016.” (DECC, 2014e)

The Electricity Demand Reduction Scheme (EDR) was used to test this approach. The EDR is a Government pilot providing the chance to be paid for delivering electricity savings at peak times from certain types of efficiency projects in Great Britain. Currently the scheme is in Phase II of the pilot. The EDR Pilot is based around a competitive auction (like the Capacity Market is); the first auction was held on 12th January 2015 for a total of around £10million, the second is scheduled for the following year, and the total budget for the EDR pilot is at least £20million. The EDR Pilot process is as follows:

“The EDR Pilot auction process will first invite participants to submit an Expression of Interest Form, and to subsequently submit an application to qualify for the auction. Expression of Interest and Application Forms will be assessed to ensure that they meet the requirements of the EDR Pilot and are for projects that we expect should be able to deliver the expected capacity savings. If successful, participants will then be invited to submit a bid into the auction on a £.pence per kW basis for the average amount of capacity reduction their project is expected to deliver in the specified winter peak period. A maximum price will be set at £300 per kW. Winning bids will be selected on a £/kW ranking up to the total budget available in the auction.

Winners will be required to sign a Participant Agreement, which will commit the participant to a number of obligations, including installing and reporting Operational Verification for the measures they bid into the auction, measuring and reporting the capacity savings delivered and participating in the evaluation of the EDR Pilot. In exchange for full compliance, DECC will pay participants their winning bid price multiplied by the average capacity savings committed to in their successful application.

The evaluation of the EDR Pilot is intended to provide a robust evidence base so that the Government is able to make such decisions on EDR in the longer term. Learning from the evaluation will underpin the design of any enduring scheme therefore participation in evaluation activities is essential. The evaluation will also be used to fulfil the Department’s obligation to report the outcomes of the EDR Pilot to Parliament.” (DECC, 2014e)

All bids for the Pilot Scheme Phase I had to be received before 10am on 12th January 2015. Following this time, the bids were opened and ranked in merit (price) order from low to high, up to the available budget. This ranking meant that the cheapest projects (on a £/kW basis) were selected first. The auction was run as a ‘pay-as-bid’ auction; the bidders were paid the price they bid, if they were successful. Bids were selected up until the point where the budget was exhausted, and an independent observer oversaw the auction.

Following lessons learnt from Phase I, eligibility has been broadened to explicitly include: the installation of insulation or other thermal envelope improvements in buildings that are electrically heated and the installation of Building Energy Management Systems (including energy IT/software where these actively control electricity use); and bidders can protect from risk of

under-delivery of savings by bidding into the Auction a lower level of savings than are recognised in measurement and verification Documents (DECC, 2015b).

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Economic: grant provided for reduction of electricity demand (DECC, 2015b).
- c. Objectives:** To evaluate and report on an exemplar case of electricity demand reduction during peak times, most likely through the replacement of less efficient equipment with a more efficient version (DECC, 2015b). The EDR pilot has two objectives:
- To examine the viability of electricity demand reduction in the Capacity Market; and
 - To learn lessons for Government and wider stakeholders on the delivery of EDR schemes.
- d. Target groups:** Organisations from all sectors (private, public and voluntary/third-sector) are invited to participate in the EDR Pilot (DECC, 2013a). DECC is excluded. Participants from all geographic locations may apply, as long as they are able to enter into contract with the UK Government. However, project sites must be located within Great Britain and be connected to the Great Britain Electricity Grid (England, Wales and Scotland only; sites in Northern Ireland are excluded as they are connected to the Irish Single Electricity Market).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** There are eligibility rules in place (some described above in target groups) (DECC, 2014e):
- All measures included in an application must deliver reductions in electricity demand through the installation of equipment, including replacement of less efficient measures. Behavioural, new build, generation, load shifting and expansion projects are excluded.
 - The 'payback' of measures included at any single site in a project must have a payback period of two years or more.
 - Measures which are already benefitting or will benefit from specified incentives are not eligible.
 - Measures must deliver capacity savings across the winter peak period (the 83 business days from 1 November 2015 to 29 February 2016).
 - Measures must not have a short replacement cycle (an expected lifespan of less than 16,000 hours), unless included as a component in the installation of an eligible EDR measure.
 - Measures included as part of any one application (one project) must result in an average of at least 100kW of savings throughout the winter peak period (4pm-8pm, business days, 1 November 2015 to 29 February 2016).
 - Measures must be able to be installed and provide Operational Verification by 15 October 2015.
 - Measures must be electricity Grid connected and based in Great Britain (if the site is partially self-supplied, then any onsite generation must be declared).

In addition, there are also eligibility criteria relating to the participant's history of convictions, insolvency, misconduct and/or tax offences (DECC, 2015b).

- f. Implementation network:** Funded, approved, and evaluated by DECC as part of their Energy demand reduction in industry, business and the public sector policy framework (DECC, 2015b). There is a specific EDR project team overseeing and providing administrative and evaluation duties in relation to the pilot scheme.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Total Potential for EDR in 2030 (after impact of existing policy) is 32.2TWh. (ii) Best estimate total cost £0.34bn (DECC, 2013). (iii) In addition to being paid per kW, projects will also

benefit from the ongoing reduction in electricity bills, which includes savings made outside the winter peak period (DECC, 2015b).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 9. Final energy savings from the Electricity Demand Reduction (EDR) Pilot Scheme

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Electricity Demand Reduction (EDR)	Unknown	Unknown

1.1.4 CAPACITY BUILDING AND NETWORKING

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

The UK has a very comprehensive number of capacity building and networking policy instruments and measures including education and training, certification of qualified actors, energy networks. The following are described in more detail below:

- Big Energy Saving Network (BESN)
- Energy Management for Non-specialists training programme
- Community Energy Peer Mentoring Fund

1.1.4.1 Big Energy Saving Network (BESN)

- General information:** The Big Energy Saving Network (BESN)⁴⁶ is a £900,000 programme established in 2014 to support eligible third sector organisations and community groups to deliver an extensive programme of outreach to vulnerable consumers, focussed on helping them to reduce their energy costs through assisted action on tariffs, switching and take-up of energy efficiency offers. Additional funding of £1m will allow us to continue supporting and growing BESN in 2015/16.
- Type of policy instrument:** Capacity building and networking: building capacity in the most vulnerable areas to reduce energy consumption and resultant bills. Also building capacity in community groups in order to reach out to these vulnerable groups.
- Objectives:** Outreach to vulnerable consumers, focussed on helping them to reduce their energy costs through assisted action on tariffs, switching and take-up of energy efficiency offers.
- Target groups:** Third sector organisations and community groups that focus on helping vulnerable energy consumers i.e. those significantly less able than a typical consumer to protect or represent his or her interests in the energy market; and/or; significantly more likely than a typical consumer to suffer detriment, or that detriment is likely to be more substantial.
- Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Mainly socio-economic influences and potential to 'up-skill'. No exemptions, penalties or sanctions.
- Implementation network:** BESN is funded by the Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC), and there is a specific team within DECC that provide an over-seeing role. DECC were

⁴⁶ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/big-energy-saving-network-grant-offer-fund>

successful in appointing a range of delivery organisations that reflected the diverse characteristics of vulnerable consumers that BESN was intended to reach.

- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Based on the £900k allocated to Phase I, the following unit costs were calculated: customers engaged through workshops: £56.25; customers engaged overall: £9.57; customers achieving 'key' outcomes (workshops only): £193.97. (iii) BESN workshops were successful in reaching a range of vulnerable groups including: those aged over 65; households with dependent children, those without access to gas and those without internet access. BESN is estimated to have reached around 16,000 participants via workshops (exceeding the target of 15,000) and a further 78,000 through frontline workers (falling within the target range of 60-90,000). BESN workshops were particularly successful at empowering consumers to get the best energy deal. The majority of those who responded to the survey reported feeling more informed and empowered as a result of their participation (73 per cent) and many went on to take subsequent action - from small-scale changes such as installing new light bulbs (32 per cent) to larger actions; nearly a third of participants (29 per cent) contacted their energy supplier about their tariff, 11 per cent switched supplier, and 5 per cent applied for an ECO assessment following BESN (DECC, 2015c).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 10. Final energy savings from the Big Energy Saving Network

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Big Energy Saving Network	Unknown	Unknown

1.1.4.2 Energy Management for non-specialists training programme

- a. General information:** GAIA Active⁴⁷, funded by the UK Government as part of the UK's 'improving the skills base and supporting take up policy in the UK National Energy Efficiency Strategy (DECC, 2013b) created the 'Energy Management for Non-specialists' training programme in 2013. The programme was created for individuals that have energy management as part of their remit, but are not energy managers. The programme consisted of a one-day workshop and five subject-oriented webinars, as well as homework designed to ensure participants put the learning into practice. Topics covered included understanding energy data and bills, company engagement, and choosing and presenting capital investments. On successful completion of the programme, participants were awarded an EMA Level II certification.
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Capacity building and networking: support from Government to enable energy management skills. / Financial: Grant.
- c. Objectives:** To equip non-specialists with the skills of energy management.
- d. Target groups:** Any individual with the capacity to put into practice energy management; those who are not energy specialists but have (or will have) energy reduction as part of their role.

⁴⁷ <http://gaiaactive.com/energy-management-ema-stage-ii-and-beyond-online/>

- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Information on rules and influencing mechanisms not available. Mainly socio-economic influences and potential to ‘up-skill’. No exemptions, penalties or sanctions.
- f. Implementation network:** GAIA Active⁴⁸, a private company of sustainability specialists was responsible for the design and implementation of the training programme, and the programme itself was funded through the DECC. GAIA now continue to run the programme without funding from DECC.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) No cost details available. (iii) The programme was attended by facilities, property, health and safety, environment, and energy managers. The training was successful in raising the profile of energy management within participants business, and speeding up energy reduction initiatives. Participants reported undertaking new projects in employee engagement, investment in new technologies, and engaging the boardroom to back tough reduction targets. Two participants actually changed jobs to become full time energy reduction specialists. Following success of the first round, GAIA secured funding to offer the programme again the following year (DECC, 2013b).
Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK’s NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 11. Final energy savings from the Energy Management for non-specialists training programme

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Energy management for non-specialists training programme	Unknown	Unknown

1.1.4.3 Community Energy Peer Mentoring Fund (CEPMF)

- a. General information:** The Community Energy Peer Mentoring Fund (CEPMF)⁴⁹ (ran from November 2013 – March 2015) supported community energy projects with grants to receive support and advice to get started with community energy projects. 12 community energy projects received grants totalling £500,000 to help fund projects including a community forum that provides workshops and assistance to communities to generate power using hydro energy and a social enterprise that sets up study visits and seminars for local community groups to help reduce their fossil fuel energy. Currently, community energy groups work on a variety of different projects such as raising funds for solar panels on community buildings to installing energy efficiency measures to help communities save money on their energy bills (SIB, n.d.). The CEPMF was developed in the context of the publication of the UK’s first ever Community Energy Strategy⁵⁰ (2014), which highlighted a number of barriers, including the difficulties facing community groups in relation to accessing the right skills and expertise.

⁴⁸ <http://gaiaactive.com/>

⁴⁹ https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/449831/CEPMF_learning_doc-Final_corrected.pdf

⁵⁰ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/community-energy-strategy>

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Capacity building and networking: support from Government to enable community energy projects. / Financial: Grant.
- c. Objectives:** The funding was designed to help new groups working in the area of energy efficiency and carbon reduction to get off the ground so they can start saving money and generating energy in their community. It also helped existing groups to professionalise, develop business plans and scale up their work and to show how social action can help people reduce their energy bills.
- d. Target groups:** Community-level organisations and groups (both existing and new) who undertake energy-related projects and activities.
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Information on rules and influencing mechanisms not available. Mainly socio-economic influences and potential to 'up-skill'. No exemptions, penalties or sanctions.
- f. Implementation network:** The Community Energy Peer Mentoring Fund was funded by Cabinet Office's Centre for Social Action and the Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC). EDF Energy were also part of the CEPMF through pro bono supporting to the 12 grant recipients; senior staff from EDF Energy volunteered to act as mentors, depending on the expertise and their geographical locations, and provided ongoing business support as and where needed.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) £500k total in grants awarded. (iii) Examples of projects developed with funding: Training volunteers to carry out home energy audits and simple energy saving installations such as draught proofing for Sutton's vulnerable and low income households; Marches Energy Agency, Beat the Cold, Keele University and Middleport Environment Centre are working together to support volunteers in designing and delivering activities and events to raise awareness about energy efficiency in the home. Based in Shrewsbury and Silverdale (Newcastle under Lyme), the project will run until March 2015 (SIB, n.d.)

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 12. Final energy savings from the Community Energy Peer Mentoring Programme

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Community energy peer mentoring programme	Unknown	Unknown

1.1.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR THE PROMOTION OF ENERGY SERVICES

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

The UK has a number of policy instruments for the promotion of energy services. The following are described in more detail below:

- LicenseLite
- Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU)
- Rural Community Energy Fund (RCEF) & Urban Community Energy Fund (UCEF)

1.1.5.1 Licence Lite (Standard Licence Condition (SLC) 11.3)

- a. General information:** In 2009 the UK Government recognised the importance of encouraging smaller-scale, distributed generation. The Electricity Act 1989⁵¹ provides the overall regulatory framework for the supply of electricity in the UK. The Act provides Ofgem, as the regulator of the gas and electricity industries in Great Britain powers and duties relating to the protection of the interests of existing and future consumers, by *“promoting effective competition between persons engaged in, or in commercial activities connected with...the generation, transmission, distribution or supply of electricity or the provision or use of electricity interconnectors.”*⁵² As part of this Act, certain activities concerning electricity may only be carried out with a licence (or under a relevant exemption or exception). Ofgem published licence modification proposals and guidance which allows for exemption from certain licence conditions as long as alternative arrangements are made with another fully licensed supplier. Licence Lite⁵³ (or Standard Licence Condition (SLC) 11.3) is a Licence Condition implemented in 2009, with associated guidance that helps new suppliers to enter the electricity supply market by providing a way to apply for a licence to supply electricity and get a direction that will relieve the obligation to directly fulfil the Standard Licence Condition (SLC) 11.2⁵⁴. If Licence Lite is proven to operate successfully, the UK Government would be supportive of greater levels of uptake amongst community energy projects and low- and zero-carbon decentralised energy projects generally, including for the electricity element of heat networks supplied by combined heat and power (CHP) systems (DECC, 2014a).
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Promotion of energy services: providing an easier way to licence small scale energy suppliers (DECC, 2014a).
- c. Objectives:** To enable communities to sell electricity locally, at a ‘local price’ as a way for all members of the community to benefit from a community energy project. Further community energy projects may wish to sell electricity beyond their local community, which ultimately has the potential to increase competition in the retail market and increase access for consumers to the sector (DECC, 2014a).
- d. Target groups:** Owners and operators of distributed energy schemes, electricity suppliers, distribution network operators, consumer groups, local authorities, property developers, and manufacturers and any other interested parties, in particular, small scale energy suppliers and community energy organisations (DECC, 2014a).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Licence Lite relieves the applicant of their obligation to be a direct party to a number of industry codes. The regulatory costs incurred by complying with these codes are disproportionately high for smaller suppliers. Licence Lite lets a new supplier partner with an existing supplier (third party fully licensed supplier (TPLS)) to be responsible for some of the more costly and technically challenging parts of a supply licence. License suppliers that handle domestic and/or small-business customers are required to be members of the

⁵¹ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1989/29/contents>

⁵² <https://www.ofgem.gov.uk/ofgem-publications/58104/definalproposals.pdf>

⁵³ https://www.ofgem.gov.uk/sites/default/files/docs/2009/02/de_final_proposals_0.pdf

⁵⁴ <https://epr.ofgem.gov.uk/Content/Documents/Electricity%20Supply%20Standard%20Licence%20Conditions%20Consolidated%20-%20Current%20Version.pdf>

Ombudsman scheme, and comply with complaints handling regulations. Customers have the right to take certain complaints to the Energy Ombudsman, if the supplier fails to resolve the problem. If either the Licence Lite supplier or the TPLS does not meet its commercial obligations as set out in the supplier services agreement, it is expected that parties seek redress via the commercial agreement. If a Licence Lite supplier is found to have breached its licence conditions there are a number of enforcement actions Ofgem may take, including imposition of penalties, consumer redress, and orders (Ofgem, 2015). In terms of setting the amount of any financial penalty and/or payment under a consumer redress order, the amount in each case must not exceed 10% of the regulated person's turnover. Ofgem have enforcement powers under the following legislation:

- the Gas Act 1986 (the Gas Act)
- the Electricity Act 1989 (the Electricity Act)
- the Utilities Act 2000
- the Competition Act 1998 (the Competition Act)
- the Enterprise Act 2002 (the Enterprise Act)
- the Unfair Terms in Consumer Contracts Regulations 1999 (UTCCRs)
- the Business Protection from Misleading Marketing Regulations 2008 (the BPMMRs).

- f. Implementation network:** Ofgem; The UK Government wants to see Licence Lite work for community groups and will actively work with Ofgem to support this (DECC, 2014a).
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) No cost details available. (iii) This arrangement, which has become known as 'Licence Lite', has been taken forward by the Greater London Authority (GLA) which has made application for a Licence Lite licence on behalf of the Mayor of London. The GLA application is a welcome development which will help clarify the need for any further guidance in this area. Clearly this would be an important step for Licence Lite, and would provide others with a route to learn from (DECC, 2014).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 13. Final Energy Savings from Licence Lite (SLC 11.3)

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Licence Lite (SLC 11.3)	Unknown	Unknown

1.1.5.2 Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU)

- a. General information:** Recognising the capacity and capability challenges which local authorities identified as barriers to heat network deployment in the UK, the Heat Network Delivery Unit (HNDU)⁵⁵ was established by the Department of Energy and Climate Change in September 2013 to provide grant funding and guidance to local authorities in England and Wales (the Scottish Parliament has set its own Heat Map and Vision for Heat). This honoured a commitment in 'The future of heating: meeting the challenge' (published in March 2013) to support local authorities

⁵⁵https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/394509/DECC_Energy_Investment_Report_WEB.pdf

exploring heat network opportunities. In the first round of the programme, 31 local authorities will be receiving £1.95m.

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Promotion of energy services: the intent is to support heat network programmes / Capacity building: the purpose is to provide support and guidance for capacity building with regard to heat networks / Financial: funding is allotted to local authorities
- c. Objectives:** HNDU aims to transform district heating in the UK, providing financial support, guidance and expertise for local authorities, especially in the crucial early stage of developing a heat network.
- d. Target groups:** Local authorities
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Local authorities apply for HNDU support through bidding rounds. Successful applicants are published on the Heat Network Delivery Funding page. All bids are reviewed by a panel of engineering, financial and commercial experts with significant experience in heat networks development. Grant funding of no more than 67% of eligible costs is provided to successful local authorities under section 31 of the Local Government Act. Eligible costs are defined as externally commissioned consultancy costs for heat network development work. If successful, each local authority is assigned an HNDU staff member as 'Project Lead' and their work together is supported through an online collaboration site and face to face meetings.
- f. Implementation network:** HNDU is a unit within DECC and is staffed by experts, who have gained experience developing heat networks outside the civil service working on technical or commercial aspects of heat networks for consultancies or local authorities.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Budget of £6.9m (iii) Since inception the Unit has awarded support to 180 unique projects across 115 local authorities including £9.7 million of grant funding. The Unit is currently scheduled to run until March 2016. As set out in Delivering UK Energy Investment: Networks released in January 2015, DECC analysis suggests the portfolio of HNDU projects alone could represent between £400 million to £800 million of capital investment opportunity over the next 10 years (on an assumption of 25% to 50% of current projects coming to fruition) (GOV.UK, 2015b).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 14. Final energy savings from the Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU)

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU)	Unknown	Unknown

1.1.5.3 Rural Community Energy Fund (RCEF) & Urban Community Energy Fund (UCEF)

- a. General information:** In June 2013 DECC and Defra launched the £15m Rural Community Energy Fund (RCEF) to provide finance for rural communities in England to explore the feasibility of, and planning for, electricity and heat projects. This fund was also complemented by the £10m Urban Community Energy Fund (UCEF). Communities in Wales can already access similar financial support through the Ynni'r Fro scheme, while in Scotland the Community and Renewable Energy Scheme (CARES) includes a preplanning loan scheme. Evaluation of the schemes will look at the impact of community energy group involvement in Green Deal Communities schemes (DECC,

2014a). A legal structure is needed in order for applications for the majority of grants and loans, such as; community benefit society, co-operative society, community interest companies (supervised by the CIC Regulator), charities (regulated by the Charity Commission), joint ventures.

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Promotion of energy services: the intent is to support community energy programmes / Capacity building: the purpose is to provide support and guidance for capacity building with regard to community energy projects / Financial: funding is allotted to community groups
- c. Objectives:** RCEF and UCEF funds are offered to be used as source of early stage finance for community heat projects. Through these funds, community groups can receive grants for technical feasibility studies, and loans for the later, more complex stages of project development. This funding will help groups overcome the riskier stages of renewable development and attract commercial finance, or raise money through a community share offer. The RCEF and UCEF aim to contribute to the UK Government's target for renewable energy and community-owned renewable schemes (DECC, 2014a).
- d. Target groups:** Rural and urban communities interested in renewable energy and community-owned renewable schemes. Local authorities become eligible for RCEF and UCEF if working with an applicant community group. (DECC, 2014a).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Local authorities become eligible for RCEF and UCEF if working with an applicant community group. Loans issued to groups are repaid, enabling the fund to self-sustain, recycling funds to support more community groups (DECC, 2014a). The Rural Community Energy Fund (RCEF) is available to rural communities in England that:
 - represent a rural community of:
 - fewer than 10,000 residents; or
 - more than 10,000 residents but within a local authority area which is classified by the Office of National Statistics as 'predominantly rural'.
 - form a legal entity in order to receive public funds
 - demonstrate the support of the wider community

and are planning a renewable energy project which:

- will provide a legacy for the future benefit of the community
- use a proven renewable technology

In terms of the UCEF, the following are eligible to apply:

- Groups that:
 - are developing a project in an urban area
 - incorporated as a legal form that we can give money to
 - answer a series of other eligibility criteria
- In addition, any of the following groups are eligible to apply for the fund:
 - Registered Company (including CICs)
 - Charitable Incorporated Organisation
 - Registered Societies (formerly known as IPS)
 - Parish and Town Councils

- Local Authorities, businesses and Housing Associations can apply in partnership with the local community.

f. Implementation network: DECC/DEFRA-funded; monitoring and evaluation will be carried out on the UCEF and RCEF by DECC Community Energy Unit (DECC, 2015d). Waste and Resources Action Programme (WRAP) and Centre for Sustainable Energy (CSE) provide advice and support relating to the application and undertaking of RCEF and UCEF-funded projects. WRAP⁵⁶ are the UCEF scheme administrators and CSE⁵⁷ have been contracted the management of the UCEF fund, in partnership with Pure Leapfrog, a business-led charity⁵⁸.

g. Outcomes: (i) The potential generation of all the approved RCEF and UCEF projects is already up to 60MW and growing (DECC, 2015d). (ii) £15m total funds to distributed under RCEF / £10m total funds to distributed under UCEF (iii) RCEF distributed £450k to 25 electricity generation projects in 2014. RCEF passes £1m distributed to 48 projects in February 2015 and projecting £800k for 25 electricity generation projects over the course of the year (DECC, 2015d).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 15. Final energy savings from the Rural Community Energy Fund (RCEF) and the Urban Community Energy Fund (UCEF)

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Rural Community Energy Fund (RCEF) & Urban Community Energy Fund (UCEF)	Unknown	Unknown

1.1.6 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT AND BEST AVAILABLE TECHNOLOGY (BAT) PROMOTION

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

The UK has a very comprehensive number of policy instruments and measures for research and development and the promotion of best available technology (BAT) including funding for research and development and demonstration projects, competitions and awards. The following are described in more detail below:

- Technology Strategy Board (TSB) / Innovate UK
- Energy Technology Institute (ETI)

1.1.6.1 Technology Strategy Board (TSB) / Innovate UK

a. General information: The Technology Strategy Board was first established in 2004 as an advisory body within the former UK Department of Trade and Industry (DTI). As the primary channel

⁵⁶ <http://www.wrap.org.uk/content/rural-community-energy-fund>

⁵⁷ <https://www.cse.org.uk/>

⁵⁸ <http://www.pureleapfrog.org/page.jsp?id=2>

through which the Government encourages innovation, the Technology Strategy Board (TSB), now called Innovate UK, is the UK's innovation agency. Many of the priority areas Innovate UK focus on are also reflected in the 'Eight Great Technologies' identified by Science and Universities Minister David Willetts. One of Innovate UK's main tools is collaborative R&D funding; running competitions in a broad range of growth creating areas, from transport to biosciences and from construction to nanoscale technologies. Innovate UK have developed Catalysts are run in partnership with the research councils, offering businesses and researchers a clear and progressive route for development, so that successful early-stage projects can easily find support for the next stage on their innovation journey; and Catapult centres: A Catapult is a technology and innovation centre where the very best of the UK's businesses, scientists and engineers can work side by side on research and development – transforming ideas into new products and services to generate economic growth. Catapults add an important new dimension to complement our existing research and development programmes, helping businesses to adopt, develop and exploit innovative products and technologies. They offer concentrated expertise in areas such as manufacturing processes, test facilities, type approval and accreditation or supply chain development. Many provide access to cutting-edge equipment and specialist facilities to develop and test ideas in reality (TSB, 2014). Previous TSB projects funded include: Retrofit for the Future: funding innovate technology and methods in retrofitted dwellings; Building Performance Evaluation: funding two year evaluation of sustainable new build dwellings and non-dwellings; and Design for Future Climate: funding research of the impact of climate change on energy efficiency and technology in buildings and innovative responses to the problem (Innovate UK, 2015).

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Policy instruments for R&D and best available technologies (BAT) promotion.
- c. Objectives:** The focus of Innovate UK is on innovation, working with business to stimulate and support innovation and accelerate economic growth
- d. Target groups:** Business and research
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The responsibilities of Innovate UK are to: provide new support for innovative small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with high-growth potential; make sure that government initiatives such as SBRI (Small Business Research Initiative) attract innovative UK businesses and give companies access to important customers in the public sector; identify and invest in the sectors that have the greatest potential for innovation to speed up economic growth; and help innovative companies work with their backers so their ideas can be developed commercially
- f. Implementation network:** Innovate UK is an executive non-departmental public body, sponsored by the Department for Business, Innovation & Skills.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Gross grant expenditure for built environment 2012-2013: £15m; 2013-2014: £32.7m (iii) Aside from job creation as a result of funding Innovate UK has increased full-time employment from 196 to 257 employees from 2013-2014. Millions of £ invested in R&D resulting in numerous outcomes directly befitting business and the public.
Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 16. Final energy savings from the Technology Strategy Board (TSB)/InnovateUK

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Technology Strategy Board (TSB) / InnovateUK	Unknown	Unknown

1.1.6.2 Code for Sustainable Homes (CSH)

- a. **General information:** The code for sustainable homes is the national standard for the sustainable design and construction of new homes. The Code was launched by the Department for Communities and Local Government (DCLG) in December 2006. The CSH technical guidance came into effect in April 2007, and it became possible to assess new homes built in England from this date. It can take, on average, 18 months to two years to design and build a Code home. As a result the first homes built to the Code standard were not awarded a certificate until 2008. The code provides nine measures of sustainable design: energy/CO₂; water; materials; surface water runoff (flooding and flood prevention); waste; pollution; health and well-being; management; and ecology. It uses a 1 to 6 star system to rate the overall sustainability performance of a new home against these nine categories (DCLG, 2010a). Following the December 2009 consultation, a number of revisions were made to the Code in 2010 (DCLG, 2010b).
- b. **Type of policy instrument:** Policy instruments for R&D and best available technologies (BAT) promotion: As a result of pushing the limit on new home design to meet more stringent standards the CSH inspires R&D and promotes and demonstrates the integration of BAT.
- c. **Objectives:** The Code for Sustainable Homes is a vital tool for improving environmental performance and reducing CO₂ emissions from new homes. The extensive framework provided by the Code sets challenging targets in a range of categories; from energy use and CO₂ emissions, to water consumption, to site ecology. It aims to reduce carbon emissions and promote higher standards of sustainable design above the current minimum standards set out by the building regulations.
- d. **Target groups:** Designers, builders and owners of new dwellings.
- e. **Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The code is voluntary and should not be confused with zero-carbon policy or the 2016 zero-carbon target. The only circumstances where the code can be enforced are where: local councils require developers to comply with the code by including a requirement in their planning policy; affordable housing is funded by the Homes and Community Agency that requires homes to be built to code level 3; the level 3 energy standard is now incorporated in the building regulations. The code applies in England, Wales and Northern Ireland. Within England it replaces the EcoHomes scheme, developed by the Building Research Establishment. Assessments are carried out in two phases: An initial assessment is carried out at the design stage. This is based on detailed documentary evidence and commitments which results in an interim certificate of compliance. Final assessment and certification is carried out at the post construction stage. Based on the design stage review, this includes a confirmation of compliance, including site records and visual inspection, and results in a final certificate of compliance.
- f. **Implementation network:** Launched and managed by DCLG.

- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Best estimate total cost £67.6m (DCLG, 2010b) (iii) Between April 2007 and the end of December 2014, 151,262 dwellings have received a three star rating at post-construction stage and 42,017 dwellings have received a four star rating. A total of 76% of those at post-construction stage have been awarded at Code level 3 since April 2007 (DCLG, 2015).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 17. Final energy savings from the Code for Sustainable Homes

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Code for Sustainable Homes Standard	Unknown	Unknown

1.1.6.3 Energy Technology Institute (ETI)

- a. General information:** The ETI is a public-private partnership between global energy and engineering companies and the UK government established by the UK government in 2007. ETI makes targeted commercial investments in nine technology programmes across heat, power, transport and the infrastructure that links them. Investment must meet UK 2020 and 2050 energy climate change targets cost effectively (ETI, 2015). Example project: £100 million, 5 year Smart Systems and Heat Programme to investigate what drives heat demand and the potential for technical innovations to meet this demand more efficiently (DECC, 2014c).
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Policy instruments for R&D and best available technologies (BAT) promotion: ETI brings together engineering projects that develop affordable, secure and sustainable technologies to help the UK address its long term emissions reductions targets as well as delivering nearer term benefits (ETI, 2015).
- c. Objectives:** The primary objective is to act as a conduit between academia, industry and the government to accelerate the development of low carbon technologies. ETI brings together engineering projects that develop affordable, secure and sustainable technologies to help the UK address its long term emissions reductions targets as well as delivering nearer term benefits (ETI, 2015).
- d. Target groups:** Academia and industry as well as government bodies and departments with energy efficiency-related policies within their remit (ETI, 2015).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** All officers and employees of the ETI must avoid conflicts of interest with their ETI responsibilities. Any such conflict, actual or potential, must be declared immediately as it arises to enable the ETI to take appropriate action. ETI establishes processes that identify, assess and manage risks and carries out regular internal audits to ensure full compliance throughout. All business transactions on behalf of the ETI will be reflected accurately and fairly in the accounts, in accordance with established procedures, and will be subject to audit and disclosure. ETI respects the strict need for confidentiality when dealing with the intellectual property assets of both member organisations and other organisations with ETI conducts business. ETI respects all applicable laws and regulations of the countries in which ETI operates and shall seek to operate within the framework of applicable competition laws including any EC

rules and regulations relating to State Aid. ETI expressly forbids the direct or indirect offer, payment, solicitation or acceptance of bribes or any form of payments which seek to create an unfair advantage or exert undue influence over an individual or organisation. Gifts and hospitality in excess of £30 will be declared (ETI, 2015).

- f. Implementation network:** The ETI is a public-private partnership between global energy and engineering companies and the UK government.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) No cost details available. (iii) No other impact details available.

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 18. Final energy savings from the Energy Technology Institute (ETI)

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Energy Technology Institute (ETI)	Unknown	Unknown

1.1.7 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE BUILDINGS SECTOR IN THE UNITED KINGDOM

Table 19. Summary table for the building sector in the UK

Summary table: Buildings					
Policy instruments	Short list of implemented policies and measures	Objective	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Implementation network
Regulatory policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Building regulations 	To guide the design process to arrive at or progress beyond a required fabric energy efficiency target	<p>Anyone responsible for dwelling and non-dwelling building work (e.g., designer, builder, installer) must ensure that the construction and design work complies with all applicable requirements of the Building Regulations. The Building Regulations are made up of procedural and technical provisions. Some works are exempt from the whole of the Regulations, whilst others are only exempt from certain aspects.</p> <p>Generally, the Part L requirements apply to buildings, or extensions of such buildings (except Class 7: extensions type), or the carrying out of any work to, or in connection of any such building or extension where the building is a) a roofed construction with walls, and uses energy to condition the indoor climate. Part L requirements do not apply to buildings that fall into the following categories:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Certain buildings which 	<p>Prosecution and enforcement notices are applicable if there is a failure to comply with the Building Regulations, in terms of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Not following the building control procedures set out for handling building work, or; Building work is carried out which does not comply with the requirements contained in the Building Regulations. <p>In terms of prosecution, the local authority (LA) has a general duty to enforce Building Regulations in its area. If informal enforcement does not achieve compliance, the LA has two formal enforcement powers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prosecution: if a person carrying out building work contravenes the Building Regulations, the LA may prosecute them in the Magistrate's Court. An unlimited fine may be imposed (sections 35 and 35A of the Building Act 1984). Prosecution is possible for up to two years after the completion of the offending work, and will usually be taken against 	The Secretary of State approves any amendments to the Building Regulations 2010 (SI 2010/2214), following guidance from relevant Government departments such as the Department for Communities and Local Government (DCLG) and advisory non-departmental public bodies such as the Building Regulations Advisory Committee (BRAC), as well as industry members. The DCLG provide ongoing practical actions and support to provide effective building regulations including publishing supporting guidance known as Approved Documents, overseeing and supporting building control organizations, publishing research to provide a scientific basis to underpin regulations and providing the secretariat for the Building Regulations Advisory Committee for England (BRAC), which advises the Secretary of State. In terms of ensuring the Building Regulations are enforced, the LAs are responsible for building works (except those which are exempt) in their local area, and for

			<p>are listed, in conservation areas or are included in the Schedule of Monuments; where compliance with the energy efficiency requirements would unacceptably alter their character or appearance.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Buildings which are used primarily or solely as places of worship. • Temporary buildings with a planned time of use of 2 years or less, with low energy demand. • Industrial sites, workshops and non-residential agricultural buildings with low energy demand. • Stand-alone buildings other than dwellings with a total useful floor area of less than 50m². 	<p>the person carrying out the work (builder, installer, main contractor).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enforcement notice: the LA may serve an enforcement notice instead of, or in addition to prosecution. The notice is served on the building owner and requires the alteration or removal of work which contravenes the regulations (section 36 of the 1984 Act). If the owner does not comply with the notice, the LA can undertake the work itself and recover the costs from the owner. A Section 36 enforcement notice must be served after the expiration of 12 months from the date of completion of the building work. An LA cannot take enforcement action under section 36 if the work is carried out in accordance with the full plans application which the LA either approved, or failed to reject. <p>Where an approved inspector is providing the Building Control Service, the responsibility for checking that the Building Regulations are complied with during the building works lies with that inspector. However, approved inspectors do not have formal enforcement powers. If the building work is considered, by the Building Inspector, to not comply with Building Regulations and there is a refusal to bring it into compliance, the inspector will cancel the initial notice. If no other approved inspector takes on the work, the building control function</p>	<p>ensuring compliance. All building works subject to Building Regulations are checked by Local Authority Building Control or a private Approved Inspector, or carried out by a 'Competent Person', and with Local Authorities enforcing compliance. In Scotland, where such work requires a building warrant, verification of building work is the responsibility of local authorities alone. (DECC, 2014c; BRAC & DCLG, 2015).</p>
--	--	--	---	---	--

				will be taken on automatically by the LA.	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy company obligations 	Reduce carbon emissions from Britain’s domestic building stock, combat fuel poverty and encourage uptake and awareness of energy efficiency measures	Energy suppliers in relation to their end-users, particularly low income, fuel poor, hard to treat homes. The Green Deal and ECO do not cover Northern Ireland. (DECC, 2012c).	Suppliers with a customer base of less than 250,000 customer accounts will be exempt from the ECO. Penalty for non-compliance: unspecified financial penalty, if financial penalty is not paid, licenses may be revoked.	ECO is administered by the Office for Gas and Electricity Markets (Ofgem) (DECC, 2012c), alongside the Warm Home Discount (WHD), through the Energy Efficiency and Social Programmes team, that is part of Ofgem’s Environmental Programmes team. Until March 2015, Ofgem E-Serve (on behalf of the Gas and Electricity Markets Authority) was the Administrator for ECO.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mandatory energy assessment schemes (Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS)) 	To target a gap in the existing policy landscape and help them to cut their energy costs, by providing targeted cost-effective recommendations to improve their energy efficiency. It will stimulate demand amongst UK businesses for energy efficiency measures, by making clear in the assessments what savings could be made. The assessments will review the organisations’ entire energy consumption including buildings, industrial processes and transport activities	ESOS applies to large UK undertakings and their corporate groups. It mainly affects businesses but can also apply to not-for-profit bodies and any other non-public sector undertakings that are large enough to meet the qualification criteria. Corporate groups qualify if at least one UK group member meets the ESOS definition of a large undertaking.	The environmental regulator is responsible for compliance and enforcement activities. The regulator may issue civil sanctions including financial penalties (ranging from £5k-50k if an organisation does not meet the scheme’s obligations (Environment Agency, 2015).	Overall, the Environment Agency is responsible for administering the scheme across the UK, and holding the UK register. A registered office or principal place of activity (in the absence of a registered office) determines the regulator, in terms of compliance and enforcement activities (Environment Agency, 2015): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Environment Agency (England) Northern Ireland Environment Agency (Northern Ireland) Scottish Environment Protection Agency (Scotland) Natural Resources Wales (Wales) DECC Offshore Oil & Gas Environment and Decommissioning (offshore).

					<p>In relation to undertaking an ESOS assessment, a corporate group demonstrates compliance using either:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An ISO 50001 energy management system certified by an accredited certification body . • Display Energy Certificates (DECs). • Green Deal Assessments (GDAs), can be part of an ESOS compliant energy assessment for the types of energy consumption they cover, if they qualify as per regulation 7 of the Green Deal Framework Regulations 2012) • ESOS compliant energy audits. All such energy audits must be reviewed by an ESOS lead assessor. An register of approved lead assessors is available online via the UK Government’s ESOS webpage . An assessor can be an employee of the business, or a third party. The assessor is not held responsible for compliance by the regulators; therefore it is recommended that a member of the corporate group/organisation who understands the ESOS requirements, and works with the lead assessor to ensure the overall approach taken is compliant with ESOS. <p>The Environment Agency, and the other regulators do not provide standard templates for ESOS related data/activities and/or</p>
--	--	--	--	--	---

					presentation of findings. Only the data to evidence that 90% of the total energy consumption is compliant via ESOS audits or other alternative routes to compliance, is required to be undertaken and recorded. This is to reduce the administrative burden on organisations that have existing data management procedures and tools.
Dissemination and awareness instruments/ Informative policy instruments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Smart Metering Implementation Programme 	To increase awareness of energy use in consumers to help them control energy use and reduce energy wastage. Provide accurate billing and improved customer service as well as reduce administration costs, for example by reducing call centre traffic, removing the need for a site visits to read meters	The Government is requiring energy companies to install 53 million gas and electricity meters at 30 million domestic and smaller non-domestic properties (DECC, 2012b).	No legal obligation on individuals to have one. Energy companies will be required to install smart meters and take all reasonable steps to reach everyone. However, energy companies are not expected to take legal action to fit a smart meter if they cannot get the householder's co-operation	The programme is led by the DECC, with co-operation from interested parties such as the energy industry, Ofgem and consumer groups. DECC is responsible for driving delivery and providing active oversight of progress by all delivery parties. During 2014, industry partners including the Data and Communications Company and its contractors, energy suppliers, network operators and manufacturers have continued to develop the systems that will deliver smart meters to consumers when the main installation phase begins (DECC, 2012b). Ofgem, as electricity and gas industry regulator, will be responsible for ensuring compliance with smart metering rules. DECC's aim is to leave the management and evolution of smart metering to energy industry participants, which will then be governed through the arrangements in the Smart Energy Code, and subject to regulatory oversight by Ofgem. DECC will remain responsible for the

					Government’s ‘retail energy policy and for the realisation of the benefits set out in the Programme’s business case’, and if required, ‘will introduce further regulation to protect these benefits, using its powers in the Energy Acts 2008 and 2011’ . DECC has worked with industry to develop a Smart Metering Implementation Programme (SMIP) Transition Governance Model; the role of such groups is to support DECC decision-making through advice and recommendations on a variety of issues including planning, risk and issue management, and change control for design and regulatory documents.
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy performance certificates 	Provide energy efficiency information on, and comparison of energy efficiency of one building with another building of the same type; encourage energy efficiency and fuel costs to be considered as part of investment.	Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are needed whenever a property is: built, sold, or rented (with the exception of: places of worship, temporary buildings that will be used for less than 2 years, stand-alone buildings with total useful floor space of less than 50 square metres, industrial sites, workshops and non-residential agricultural buildings that don’t use a lot of energy, some buildings that are due to be demolished, holiday accommodation that’s rented out for less than 4 months a year or is let under a licence to occupy, listed buildings, residential buildings intended to be used less than 4 months a year) (GOV.UK, 2015a).	The current owner can be fined if an EPC is not in place as required (GOV.UK, 2015a). The enforcement of the regulations is the responsibility of local weights and measures authorities i.e. trading standards. The fine is 12.5% of the rateable value of the building, capped at £5,000 (€6,890) and with a default penalty of £750 where the calculation is not possible. A further fine of £200 (€275) can be issued for failure to provide a copy of the EPC, when requested by an enforcement authority officer within seven days. In terms of DECs, the penalties are; a £500 (€690) fine for failure to display a DEC at all times in a prominent place, and a £1,000 (€1,380) fine for failure to possess a valid	The Domestic and Non-Domestic Energy Performance Certificate Registers are operated by Landmark Information Group on behalf of the Secretary of State for Communities and Local Government (DCLG); DCLG is responsible for making sure buildings in the UK meet the standards required by the EU Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (DCLG, 2015).

				advisory report (GVA, unknown).	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Green Open Homes 	<p>The aim was to help new open homes events and networks get off the ground all around the country, to increase people’s feeling that making energy saving improvements is ‘normal in my neighbourhood’.</p>	<p>Homeowners seeking more information on energy efficiency upgrades, e.g. those with further questions regarding the Green Deal (CSE, 2014).</p>	<p>Grants cannot be used directly for private profit and a budget breakdown must be provided as part of the application; Grant awards of greater than £1,000 can only be made to legally incorporated organisations; Grants cannot be used directly for private profit and a budget breakdown must be provided as part of the application. Public liability insurance is also required (CSE, 2013).</p>	<p>DECC funded, delivered by the Centre for Sustainable Energy and Bristol Green Doors (CSE, 2014).</p>
<p>Economic policy instruments</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Green Deal programme 	<p>To help households and small businesses improve energy efficiency and/or reduce carbon emissions and ensure that they have access to trusted information about energy efficiency. The Green Deal is intended to encourage undertaking of energy assessments.</p>	<p>Households (owner-occupied and private rented tenants and landlords) in existing dwellings as well as the owners, landlords and tenants of small non-dwellings. The Green Deal and ECO do not cover Northern Ireland (DECC, 2014c).</p>	<p>The Green Deal, although legislated through DECC, is based in the private sector and seeks to enhance the uptake of physical energy efficiency measures as well as increase assessments and awareness of energy use and efficiency in domestic and small non-domestic properties. The Green Deal framework regulations provide a Code of Practice as well as assessor and provider certification in order to ensure consumer protection. The overall authorisation body is the Green Deal Oversight and Registration Body (GD ORB). In addition, a Green Deal Ombudsman and Investigation Service, run by the Ombudsman Services, has been established. The Ombudsman Services provide independent, impartial and cost-effective dispute resolution outside the courts, and</p>	<p>The Green Deal Oversight and Registration Body (GD ORB), on behalf of the Secretary of State, manages the authorisation scheme for participants in the Green Deal and is responsible for a number of functions aimed at providing effective administration and oversight of the scheme. The GD ORB is responsible for maintaining a register of all authorised Green Deal Providers, Certification Bodies, Assessors and Installers; maintaining the Green Deal Code of Practice and controlling the use of the Quality Mark; ongoing monitoring of Green Deal Participants against the Code of Practice; producing an annual Green Deal report; and gathering evidence of non-compliance and referring participants to the Ombudsman or the Secretary of State where appropriate and</p>

				operate under appropriate UK legal and regulatory authority. The Green Deal also sought to positively influence the conflicting interests of tenants and landlords, and is supported by the first tenants' energy efficiency improvements regulations coming into force by 1 April 2016, and the legislation surrounding EPCs ensuring that by 2018, it will be illegal to rent a property with an EPC rating of E or below. Because it is the bill payer in rented dwellings that benefits from energy efficiency improvements, the Landlords Energy Saving Allowance, a financial incentive, allows landlords of domestic rented property to claim tax relief of up to £1,500 per property for the costs of buying and installing energy-saving products (DECC, 2014c).	imposing sanctions when directed (DCLG, DWP & DECC, 2015).
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Salix Finance public sector energy efficiency loan scheme 	To provide interest free loans to improve the energy efficiency of hospitals, schools and other public sector buildings	'Any public sector body who receive the majority of their income directly from the public sector can apply. Only those projects where the resultant energy savings, over the lifetime of the project, go directly back to the public sector and the public sector gains a direct financial benefit are eligible. An example of an ineligible project would be an outsourced estate management contract in which the outsource supplier paid the energy bills and benefitted from any savings achieved from the project. However, if the energy bill was a pass through under the	Recipients of funding must apply the basic rules of procurement whenever they spend public money. These rules look to make sure that public funds are spent openly and fairly, and make the most of every budget, while protecting against legal challenges, financial penalties and damage to a recipient's reputation (Salix, 2014). In total, over 120 technologies (e.g. boilers, combined heat and power, LED and lighting upgrades, and heat recovery) fit the Salix funding criteria, and as such can be funded through the Salix finance schemes. However, the list of supported technologies is evolving and public	Salix Finance Ltd is grant funded by DECC, with contributions from the Department for Education (DfE), The Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE) and the Welsh and Scottish governments (Salix, 2014). Salix Finance Ltd ensure the participating public sector organisations provide data to ensure cost-effective and energy/carbon savings are achieved.

			<p>contract and the public sector benefitted from the energy savings, then the project would be eligible' (Salix, 2014). All public sector organisations (across their whole estates) in England, Wales and Scotland are eligible to apply for funding. Such organisations include schools, higher and further educational institutions, emergency services, hospitals, leisure centres, local authorities, the NHS. Eligibility is dependent on the installation of technologies on the Salix list of eligible technologies, and the completion of the Salix Programme Compliance Tools (Salix, 2014).</p>	<p>sector organisations can discuss the addition of technologies they feel fit the Salix criteria for funding.</p>	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electricity Demand Reduction (EDR) scheme 	<p>To evaluate and report on an exemplar case of electricity demand reduction during peak times, most likely through the replacement of less efficient equipment with a more efficient version (DECC, 2015b). The EDR pilot has two objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> To examine the viability of electricity demand reduction in the Capacity Market; and To learn lessons for Government and wider stakeholders on the delivery of EDR schemes. 	<p>Organisations from all sectors (private, public and voluntary/third-sector) are invited to participate in the EDR Pilot (DECC, 2013a). DECC is excluded. Participants from all geographic locations may apply, as long as they are able to enter into contract with the UK Government. However, project sites must be located within Great Britain and be connected to the Great Britain Electricity Grid (England, Wales and Scotland only; sites in Northern Ireland are excluded as they are connected to the Irish Single Electricity Market).</p>	<p>There are eligibility rules in place (some described above in target groups) (DECC, 2014e):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> All measures included in an application must deliver reductions in electricity demand through the installation of equipment, including replacement of less efficient measures. Behavioural, new build, generation, load shifting and expansion projects are excluded. The 'payback' of measures included at any single site in a project must have a payback period of two years or more. Measures which are 	<p>Funded, approved, and evaluated by DECC as part of their Energy demand reduction in industry, business and the public sector policy framework (DECC, 2015b). There is a specific EDR project team overseeing and providing administrative and evaluation duties in relation to the pilot scheme.</p>

				<p>already benefitting or will benefit from specified incentives are not eligible.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Measures must deliver capacity savings across the winter peak period (the 83 business days from 1 November 2015 to 29 February 2016). Measures must not have a short replacement cycle (an expected lifespan of less than 16,000 hours), unless included as a component in the installation of an eligible EDR measure. Measures included as part of any one application (one project) must result in an average of at least 100kW of savings throughout the winter peak period (4pm-8pm, business days, 1 November 2015 to 29 February 2016). Measures must be able to be installed and provide Operational Verification by 15 October 2015. Measures must be electricity Grid connected and based in Great Britain (if the site is partially self-supplied, then any onsite generation must be declared). <p>In addition, there are also eligibility criteria relating to the participant's history of convictions, insolvency, misconduct and/or tax offences (DECC, 2015b).</p>	
--	--	--	--	--	--

Capacity building and networking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Big Energy Saving Network (BESN) 	<p>Outreach to vulnerable consumers, focussed on helping them to reduce their energy costs through assisted action on tariffs, switching and take-up of energy efficiency offers</p>	<p>Third sector organisations and community groups that focus on helping vulnerable energy consumers i.e. those significantly less able than a typical consumer to protect or represent his or her interests in the energy market; and/or; significantly more likely than a typical consumer to suffer detriment, or that detriment is likely to be more substantial.</p>	<p>Mainly socio-economic influences and potential to 'up-skill'. No exemptions, penalties or sanctions.</p>	<p>BESN is funded by the Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC); DECC were successful in appointing a range of delivery organisations that reflected the diverse characteristics of vulnerable consumers that BESN was intended to reach.</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Energy Management for Non-specialists training programme 	<p>To equip non-specialists with the skills of energy management</p>	<p>Any individual with the capacity to put into practice energy management; those who are not energy specialists but have (or will have) energy reduction as part of their role.</p>	<p>Mainly socio-economic influences and potential to 'up-skill'. No exemptions, penalties or sanctions.</p>	<p>GAIA Active, a private company of sustainability specialists was responsible for the design and implementation of the training programme, and the programme itself was funded through the DECC. GAIA now continue to run the programme without funding from DECC.</p>
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community Energy Peer Mentoring Fund 	<p>The funding was designed to help new groups working in the area of energy efficiency and carbon reduction to get off the ground so they can start saving money and generating energy in their community. It also helped existing groups to professionalise, develop business plans and scale up their work and to show how social action can help people reduce their energy bills.</p>	<p>Community-level organisations and groups (both existing and new) who undertake energy-related projects and activities.</p>	<p>Mainly socio-economic influences and potential to 'up-skill'. No exemptions, penalties or sanctions.</p>	<p>The Community Energy Peer Mentoring Fund was funded by Cabinet Office's Centre for Social Action and the Department of Energy and Climate Change (DECC). EDF Energy were also part of the CEPMF through pro bono supporting to the 12 grant recipients; senior staff from EDF Energy volunteered to act as mentors, depending on the expertise and their geographical locations, and provided ongoing business support as and where needed.</p>

<p>Policy instruments for the promotion of energy services</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Licence Lite 	<p>To enable communities to sell electricity locally, at a 'local price' as a way for all members of the community to benefit from a community energy project. Further community energy projects may wish to sell electricity beyond their local community, which ultimately has the potential to increase competition in the retail market and increase access for consumers to the sector</p>	<p>Owners and operators of distributed energy schemes, electricity suppliers, distribution network operators, consumer groups, local authorities, property developers, and manufacturers and any other interested parties, in particular, small scale energy suppliers and community energy organisations (DECC, 2014a).</p>	<p>Licence Lite relieves the applicant of their obligation to be a direct party to a number of industry codes. The regulatory costs incurred by complying with these codes are disproportionately high for smaller suppliers. Licence Lite lets a new supplier partner with an existing supplier (third party fully licensed supplier (TPLS)) to be responsible for some of the more costly and technically challenging parts of a supply licence. License suppliers that handle domestic and/or small-business customers are required to be members of the Ombudsman scheme, and comply with complaints handling regulations. Customers have the right to take certain complaints to the Energy Ombudsman, if the supplier fails to resolve the problem. If either the Licence Lite supplier or the TPLS does not meet its commercial obligations as set out in the supplier services agreement, it is expected that parties seek redress via the commercial agreement. If a Licence Lite supplier is found to have breached its licence conditions there are a number of enforcement actions Ofgem may take, including imposition of penalties, consumer redress, and orders (Ofgem, 2015). In terms of setting the amount of any financial penalty and/or payment under a consumer redress order, the amount in each case must not exceed 10% of the regulated person's turnover. Ofgem</p>	<p>Ofgem; a non-ministerial department of the UK Government. The UK Government wants to see Licence Lite work for community groups and will actively work with Ofgem to support this (DECC, 2014a).</p>
---	--	---	--	--	---

				<p>have enforcement powers under the following legislation:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the Gas Act 1986 (the Gas Act) the Electricity Act 1989 (the Electricity Act) the Utilities Act 2000 the Competition Act 1998 (the Competition Act) the Enterprise Act 2002 (the Enterprise Act) the Unfair Terms in Consumer Contracts Regulations 1999 (UTCCRs) the Business Protection from Misleading Marketing Regulations 2008 (the BPMMRs). 	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Heat Networks Delivery Unit (HNDU) 	<p>HNDU aims to transform district heating in the UK, providing financial support, guidance and expertise for local authorities, especially in the crucial early stage of developing a heat network.</p>	<p>Local authorities</p>	<p>Local authorities apply for HNDU support through bidding rounds. Successful applicants are published on the Heat Network Delivery Funding page. All bids are reviewed by a panel of engineering, financial and commercial experts with significant experience in heat networks development. Grant funding of no more than 67% of eligible costs is provided to successful local authorities under section 31 of the Local Government Act. Eligible costs are defined as externally commissioned consultancy costs for heat network development work. If successful, each local authority is assigned an HNDU staff member as 'Project</p>	<p>HNDU is a unit within DECC and is staffed by experts, who have gained experience developing heat networks outside the civil service working on technical or commercial aspects of heat networks for consultancies or local authorities.</p>	

				Lead' and their work together is supported through an online collaboration site and face to face meetings.	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rural Community Energy Fund (RCEF) & Urban Community Energy Fund (UCEF) 	<p>RCEF and UCEF funds are offered to be used as source of early stage finance for community heat projects. Through these funds, community groups can receive grants for technical feasibility studies, and loans for the later, more complex stages of project development. This funding will help groups overcome the riskier stages of renewable development and attract commercial finance, or raise money through a community share offer. The RCEF and UCEF aim to contribute to the UK Government's target for renewable energy and community-owned renewable schemes (DECC, 2014a).</p>	<p>Rural and urban communities interested in renewable energy and community-owned renewable schemes (DECC, 2014a). Local authorities become eligible for RCEF and UCEF if working with an applicant community group.</p>	<p>Local authorities become eligible for RCEF and UCEF if working with an applicant community group. Loans issued to groups are repaid, enabling the fund to self-sustain, recycling funds to support more community groups (DECC, 2014a). The Rural Community Energy Fund (RCEF) is available to rural communities in England that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> represent a rural community of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> fewer than 10,000 residents; or more than 10,000 residents but within a local authority area which is classified by the Office of National Statistics as 'predominantly rural'. form a legal entity in order to receive public funds demonstrate the support of the wider community <p>and are planning a renewable energy project which:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> will provide a legacy for the future benefit of the community use a proven renewable technology <p>In terms of the UCEF, the following</p>	<p>DECC/DEFRA-funded; monitoring and evaluation will be carried out on the UCEF and RCEF by DECC Community Energy Unit (DECC, 2015d). Waste and Resources Action Programme (WRAP) and Centre for Sustainable Energy (CSE) provide advice and support relating to the application and undertaking of RCEF and UCEF-funded projects. WRAP are the UCEF scheme administrators and CSE have been contracted the management of the UCEF fund, in partnership with Pure Leapfrog, a business-led charity .</p>

				<p>are eligible to apply:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Groups that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o are developing a project in an urban area o incorporated as a legal form that we can give money to o answer a series of other eligibility criteria •In addition, any of the following groups are eligible to apply for the fund: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Registered Company (including CICs) o Charitable Incorporated Organisation o Registered Societies (formerly known as IPS) o Parish and Town Councils o Local Authorities, businesses and Housing Associations can apply in partnership with the local community. 	
<p>Policy instruments for Research and Development and BAT promotion</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology Strategy Board (TSB) / Innovate UK 	<p>The focus of Innovate UK is on innovation, working with business to stimulate and support innovation and accelerate economic growth</p>	<p>Business and research</p>	<p>The responsibilities of Innovate UK are to: provide new support for innovative small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with high-growth potential; make sure that government initiatives such as SBRI (Small Business Research Initiative) attract innovative UK businesses and give companies access to important customers in the public sector; identify and invest in the sectors that have the greatest</p>	<p>Innovate UK is an executive non-departmental public body, sponsored by the Department for Business, Innovation & Skills</p>

				potential for innovation to speed up economic growth; and help innovative companies work with their backers so their ideas can be developed commercially	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Code for Sustainable Homes 	<p>The Code for Sustainable Homes is a vital tool for improving environmental performance and reducing CO2 emissions from new homes. The extensive framework provided by the Code sets challenging targets in a range of categories; from energy use and CO2 emissions, to water consumption, to site ecology. It aims to reduce carbon emissions and promote higher standards of sustainable design above the current minimum standards set out by the building regulations.</p>	<p>Designers, builders and owners of new dwellings.</p>	<p>The code is voluntary and should not be confused with zero-carbon policy or the 2016 zero-carbon target. The only circumstances where the code can be enforced are where: local councils require developers to comply with the code by including a requirement in their planning policy; affordable housing is funded by the Homes and Community Agency that requires homes to be built to code level 3; the level 3 energy standard is now incorporated in the building regulations. The code applies in England, Wales and Northern Ireland. Within England it replaces the EcoHomes scheme, developed by the Building Research Establishment. Assessments are carried out in two phases: An initial assessment is carried out at the design stage. This is based on detailed documentary evidence and commitments which results in an interim certificate of compliance. Final assessment and certification is carried out at the post construction stage. Based on the design stage review, this</p>	<p>Launched and managed by DCLG.</p>

				includes a confirmation of compliance, including site records and visual inspection, and results in a final certificate of compliance.	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Energy Technology Institute (ETI) 	<p>The primary objective is to act as a conduit between academia, industry and the government to accelerate the development of low carbon technologies. ETI brings together engineering projects that develop affordable, secure and sustainable technologies to help the UK address its long term emissions reductions targets as well as delivering nearer term benefits</p>	<p>Academia, industry and government</p>	<p>All officers and employees of the ETI must avoid conflicts of interest with their ETI responsibilities. Any such conflict, actual or potential, must be declared immediately as it arises to enable the ETI to take appropriate action. ETI establishes processes that identify, assess and manage risks and carries out regular internal audits to ensure full compliance throughout. All business transactions on behalf of the ETI will be reflected accurately and fairly in the accounts, in accordance with established procedures, and will be subject to audit and disclosure. ETI respects the strict need for confidentiality when dealing with the intellectual property assets of both member organisations and other organisations with ETI conducts business. ETI respects all applicable laws and regulations of the countries in which ETI operates and shall seek to operate within the framework of applicable competition laws including any EC rules and regulations relating to State Aid.</p>	<p>The ETI is a public-private partnership between global energy and engineering companies and the UK government.</p>

1.2 POLICY INSTRUMENTS IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR

1.2.1 PLANNING INSTRUMENTS

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

The UK has a very comprehensive number of planning policy instruments and measures for research and development and the promotion of best available technology (BAT) including smart spatial planning, improvements to bicycle, pedestrian, public and rail infrastructure, traffic calming and management systems as well as improvements in logistic. The following are described in more detail below:

- Plug-in Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy
- Eco-towns Planning Policy

1.2.1.1 Plug-in Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy

- General information:** The Plugged-In Places (PiP) programme is the key mechanism for commencing the roll-out of recharging infrastructure in the UK and providing learning to inform the future development of a national network. The PiP is part of the key transport actions held within the UK Governments Carbon Plan 2011⁵⁹. The Government provided up to £30m in matched funding in 2010-2013 to support the installation and trialling of recharging infrastructure in eight places across the country (8,500 charge points). These are led by local consortia including private and public sector organisations, local utilities and businesses to secure investment in plug-in vehicle infrastructure for their areas (OLEV, 2011). The PiP programme is supported by a legislative framework based on European new car CO₂ targets (Regulation (EC) No. 443/2009⁶⁰), EU Framework Directive 2007/46/EC⁶¹ as well as the Renewable Energy Directive (RED) 2009/28/EC⁶² as well as the UK's National Planning Policy Framework (DCLG, 2012).
- Type of policy instrument:** Planning instrument: The Strategy is focused on improving the infrastructure for electric vehicle ownership through planning.
- Objectives:** In addition to making plug-in vehicles more affordable and stimulating technological innovation, having the right infrastructure in place to support plug-in vehicle owners is the other critical component in maintaining the UK's favourable market position. By providing clarity of approach and removing barriers for those wishing to invest in, provide or benefit from such

⁵⁹ https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/47613/3702-the-carbon-plan-delivering-our-low-carbon-future.pdf

⁶⁰ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32009R0443>

⁶¹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX:32007L0046>

⁶² <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:140:0016:0062:EN:PDF>

infrastructure, the Strategy aims to stimulate and accommodate the growth in the plug-in vehicle market that we expect to see up to 2020.

- d. Target groups:** The PiP aims to encourage local authorities to adopt plug-in vehicle recharging infrastructure within their local planning policies, as well as encourage research and development in electric vehicles within the transport industry, and improve the economic viability of plug-in vehicle infrastructure for installation contractors, charge-point manufacturers and operators as well as local authorities and owners of publicly accessible car parks. In addition, a secondary target group is the end user/consumer (both domestic and business).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** As a strategy, there are no specific rules. However, it is combined with numerous policies and financial incentives in relation to increasing the uptake of plug-in vehicles (hybrid and/or full electric) such as the Plug-in Car and Van Grant incentives, favourable tax regimes (plug-in vehicles receive VED and Company Car Tax exemptions, as well as Enhanced Capital Allowances). Furthermore, businesses monitored under the Carbon Reduction Commitment (CRC) are able to discount electricity used to charge plug-in vehicles from their total electricity consumption. Planning-related incentives include the establishment of a Permitted Development Right for landowners to install charge-points without the need for planning permission.
- f. Implementation network:** Office for Low Emission Vehicles (OLEV). Implementation strategy includes: using the Plugged-In Places trials as a central mechanism to inform the development of commercial models for plug-in vehicle infrastructure; removing barriers to the market, such as the requirement for planning permission for public recharging infrastructure, and working to enable charge point operators to charge the market rate for electricity; producing a conducive environment for private investment, by encouraging infrastructure through planning policies, supporting the move to standardisation and, if raising finance proves a barrier, the potential for targeted financial solutions through the Green Investment Bank; and helping the consumer by enabling all public infrastructure to be interoperable and improving the provision of information about public charge points (OLEV, 2011).
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Total grant funding £30m. (iii) Following a qualitative research review of the PiP programme, public charging infrastructure was considered to be important by 40% of respondents in influencing their decision to purchase EVs. Though EV drivers used the charge points there was very little awareness of the PiP programme provided the infrastructure. Lack of compatibility between different charge point providers was confusing and frustrating for EV purchasers and users (TRL, 2013).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 20. Final energy savings from the Plug-in Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Plug-in Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy	Unknown	Unknown

1.2.1.2 Eco-towns Planning Policy

- a. General information:** In 2009 DCLG set out how eco-towns should be defined as part of the overall planning policy. Among many issues such as setting out that dwellings should be zero carbon and planning for biodiversity. With regard to transportation specifically: It is important to ensure that eco-towns are genuine mixed-use communities and that unsustainable commuter trips are kept to a minimum. Travel in eco-towns should support people's desire for mobility whilst achieving the goal of low carbon living. The town should be designed so that access to it and through it gives priority to options such as walking, cycling, public transport and other sustainable options, thereby reducing residents' reliance on private cars, including techniques such as filtered permeability. To achieve this, homes should be within ten minutes' walk of (a) frequent public transport and (b) neighbourhood services. The provision of services within the eco-town may be co-located to reduce the need for individuals to travel by private car and encourage the efficient use of the sustainable transport options available (DCLG, 2009b). *The eco-towns planning policy supplement was cancelled in its current form from 5th March 2015.*
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Planning instrument: sets out planning rules for eco-towns
- c. Objectives:** To minimize energy consumption and to make healthy living easier.
- d. Target groups:** Developers, designers, infrastructure and building industries.
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Planning applications should include travel plans which demonstrate: (a) how the town's design will enable at least 50 per cent of trips originating in eco-towns to be made by non-car means, with the potential for this to increase over time to at least 60 per cent (b) good design principles, drawing from Manual for Streets, Building for Life, and community travel planning principles (c) how transport choice messages, infrastructure and services will be provided from 'day one' of residential occupation, and (d) how the carbon impact of transport in the eco-town will be monitored, as part of embedding a long term low-carbon approach to travel within plans for community governance. Where eco-town plans intend to incorporate ultra-low carbon vehicle options, including electric car schemes to help achieve a sustainable transport system, planning applications should demonstrate that: (a) there will be sufficient energy headroom to meet the higher demand for electricity, and (b) the scheme will not add so many additional private vehicles to the local road network that these will cause congestion. The policies set out in the Planning Policy Strategy should be taken into account by regional planning bodies in the preparation of revisions to regional spatial strategies, by the Mayor of London in relation to the spatial development strategy for London, and by local planning authorities in the preparation of local development documents (DCLG, 2009b).
- f. Implementation network:** The UK Government ministerial department, DCLG,⁶³ sets out national planning policy guidance, strategy and rules. The DCLG has the following responsibilities:
- supporting local government by giving them the power to act for their community - without interference from central government.
 - helping communities and neighbourhoods to solve their own problems so neighbourhoods are strong, attractive and thriving.
 - working with local enterprise partnerships and enterprise zones to help the private sector grow.

⁶³ <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/department-for-communities-and-local-government>

- making the planning system work more efficiently and effectively.
- supporting local fire and rescue authorities so that they're able to respond to emergencies and reduce the number and impact of fires.

There are corresponding departments in the Welsh Government, Scottish Government and the Northern Ireland Executive, and which are responsible for policy relating to communities and local government within their localities. In terms of planning, England and Wales follow the same planning policies, whilst Scotland and Northern Ireland have their own separate local planning policy frameworks. Within the DCLG, the executive agency, the Planning Inspectorate, deals with "planning appeals, national infrastructure planning applications, examinations of local plans and other planning-related and specialist casework in England and Wales."⁶⁴ Eco-towns will need to be monitored through regional and local monitoring frameworks. Regional Planning Bodies and Local Planning Authorities will be required to monitor the implementation of their spatial policies as set out in the RSS and in development plan documents at the local level. Regional Planning Bodies and Local Planning Authorities should set out in their Annual Monitoring Reports indicators for monitoring the sustainability of eco-towns in their region/district. Arrangements should be put in place for the long-term monitoring of the standards set out for eco-towns as part of the requirements for community governance.

- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Total estimated implementation cost £700-1400m (DCLG, 2009a) (iii) Three Ecotowns have progressed since 2007: Cornwall (St. Austell), Oxfordshire (Bicester) and Hampshire (Bordon). The UK government appears to have misunderstood both how long it takes to bring such large schemes together from scratch (and ignoring a lengthy recession) and what institutional support is needed to ensure delivery. Spring 2015 the UK Government indicated that it would remove the policy guidance (PPS1 supplement) involving eco-towns from the National Planning Policy Framework (along with requirements for zero carbon homes by 2016) (Parker, 2015).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 21. Final energy savings from the Eco-towns planning policy

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Eco-towns Planning Policy	Unknown	Unknown

1.2.2 REGULATORY POLICY INSTRUMENTS

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

The UK has a very comprehensive number of regulatory policy instruments and measures including fuel economy/vehicle CO₂ emission standards, speed restrictions, low emission zones, rules for energy-efficient public procurement and voluntary agreements. The following are described in more detail below:

- Vehicle Excise Duty (VED): fuel type and CO₂ emission vehicle bands

⁶⁴ <https://www.gov.uk/government/organisations/planning-inspectorate>

- Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (RTFO)
- Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS)

1.2.2.1 Vehicle Excise Duty (VED): fuel type and CO₂ emission vehicle bands

- a. General information:** Section 1 of the Vehicle and Registration Act (VERA) 1994 provides for the charging of VED. Section 2 of VERA provides that VED in respect of a vehicle of any description is chargeable by reference to the applicable rate specified in schedule 1 of VERA. Part 1A of Schedule 1 to VERA sets out the VED rates for cars registered on or after 1 March 2001, as amended by successive Finance Acts (HM R&C, 2015).
Policy set forth in the 2015 Summer Budget (July): Vehicle Excise Duty (VED) for cars first registered from 1 April 2017 onwards. First Year Rates (FYRs) of VED will vary according to the carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions of the vehicle. A flat Standard Rate (SR) of £140 will apply in all subsequent years, except for zero-emission cars for which the SR will be £0. Cars with a list price above £40,000 will attract a supplement of £310 on their SR for the first 5 years in which a SR is paid. All cars first registered before 1 April 2017 will remain in the current VED system, which will not change (HM R&C, 2015).
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Regulatory: VED and SR are required by all vehicle owners.
- c. Objectives:** The reformed VED system retains and strengthens the CO₂-based FYRs to incentivise uptake of the very cleanest cars whilst moving to a flat SR in order to make the tax fairer, simpler and sustainable (HM R&C, 2015).
- d. Target groups:** All vehicle owners.
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** To ensure those who can afford the most expensive cars make a fair contribution, a supplement of £310 will be applied to the SR of cars with a list price (not including VED) over £40,000, for the first 5 years in which a SR is paid. Section 1 of the Vehicle and Registration Act (VERA) 1994 provides for the charging of VED. Section 2 of VERA provides that VED in respect of a vehicle of any description is chargeable by reference to the applicable rate specified in schedule 1 of VERA. Part 1A of Schedule 1 to VERA sets out the VED rates for cars registered on or after 1 March 2001, as amended by successive Finance Acts (HM R&C, 2015).
- f. Implementation network:** Tax set forth by HM Revenue & Customs. The measure is monitored through the DVLA vehicle licensing data (HM R&C, 2015).
- g. Outcomes:** (i) This measure supports the development and manufacture of zero and Ultra Low Emission Vehicles (ULEVs) in the United Kingdom by providing preferential tax treatment of these cars over conventionally fuelled cars. The very cleanest zero-emission vehicles are particularly incentivised as they continue to be pay a £0 of VED. - Carbon emissions: by strengthening the incentive to purchase zero-emission cars and ULEVs over conventionally fuelled cars this measure is expected to contribute to the UKs carbon emissions targets. (ii) No cost details available. (iii) The current VED structure based on CO₂ bands was introduced in 2001 when average UK new car emissions were 178 gCO₂/km. The Band A threshold of 100 gCO₂/km below which cars pay no VED was introduced in 2003 when average new car emissions were 173 gCO₂/km. Since then, to meet EU emissions targets average new car emissions have fallen to 125 gCO₂/km. This means that an increasingly large number of ordinary cars now fall into the zero- or lower-rated VED bands, creating a sustainability challenge and weakening the environmental

signal in VED. This is set to continue as manufacturers meet further EU targets of 95 gCO₂/km set for 2020. Additionally, the system results in significant unfairness as owners of newer cars pay little or no VED while owners of older cars generally pay higher rates. This measure is expected to have a small positive effect on inflation but is not expected to have any significant macroeconomic impacts. The costing includes a behavioural response to account for an increase in vehicle purchases in the period between the measure being announced and it being implemented (HM R&C, 2015).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 22. Final energy savings from the Vehicle Excise Duty (VED)

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Vehicle Excise Duty (VED)	Unknown	Unknown

1.2.2.2 Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (RTFO)

a. General information: The Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (RTFO)⁶⁵ supports the government's policy on reducing greenhouse gas emissions (GHG) from vehicles by encouraging the production of biofuels that don't damage the environment. Under the RTFO suppliers of transport and non-road mobile machinery (NRMM) fuel in the UK must be able to show that a percentage of the fuel they supply comes from renewable and sustainable sources. Fuel suppliers who supply at least 450,000 litres of fuel a year are affected. This includes suppliers of biofuels as well as suppliers of fossil fuel. The RTFO only covers biofuels used in the transport and NRMM sectors (DfT, 2012).

The Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation Order 2007⁶⁶ was amended in December 2011⁶⁷ to transpose the transport elements of the EU Renewable Energy Directive (RED) 2009/28/EC, and was amended again in 2013⁶⁸ to implement the closely related requirements of articles 7a-e of the EU Fuel Quality Directive 2009/30/EC⁶⁹. It has also undergone amendments in 2009⁷⁰ and 2015⁷¹. The RTFO scheme is closely aligned to reporting requirements placed on suppliers under the Motor Fuel (Road Vehicle and Mobile Machinery) Greenhouse Gas Emissions Regulations

⁶⁵ <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/renewable-transport-fuels-obligation>

⁶⁶ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2007/3072/contents/made>

⁶⁷ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2011/2937/contents/made>

⁶⁸ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2013/816/contents/made>

⁶⁹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:140:0088:0113:EN:PDF>

⁷⁰ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2009/843/contents/made>

⁷¹ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2015/534/contents/made>

2012⁷², which also form part of the UK's transposition of the EU Fuel Quality Directive 2009/30/EC.

Other related UK legislation includes:

- The Energy Act 2004 (Part 2, Chapter 5 outlines)⁷³
- The Climate Change Act 2008⁷⁴
- The Biodiesel Duty Regulations 2010⁷⁵
- HM Revenue and Customs note on the extension of the duty differential for biodiesel from used cooking oil⁷⁶
- The Biodiesel and Bioblend Regulations 2002⁷⁷
- The Hydrocarbon Oil Duties Act 1979⁷⁸

Relevant EU legislation about biofuels includes:

- The Renewable Energy Directive (RED)⁷⁹
- The Fuel Quality Directive (FQD)⁸⁰
- Regulation 510/2011 of the European Parliament and of the council of 11 May 2011 setting emission performance standards for new light commercial vehicles as part of the Union's integrated approach to reduce CO₂ emissions from light-duty vehicles.⁸¹

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Regulatory: suppliers of transport and non-road mobile machinery (NRMM) fuel in the UK must be able to show that a percentage of the fuel they supply comes from renewable and sustainable sources.
- c. Objectives:** Reducing transport related GHG while supporting production of biofuels.
- d. Target groups:** Obligatory for companies own and supply 450,000 litres or more of any road transport or NRMM fuel for use in the UK. Open to any company.
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** A company must register under the RTFO if it owns and supplies 450,000 litres or more of any road transport or NRMM fuel for use in the UK during the course of an obligation year (15 April to 14 April). The 450,000 litre figure includes all fossil fuels

⁷² <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2012/3030/contents/made>

⁷³ <http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/+/http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2004/20/contents>

⁷⁴ <http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20120202155346/http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2008/27/contents>

⁷⁵ <http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20110131070443/http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2010/984/contents/made>

⁷⁶ <http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20110202215457/http://www.hmrc.gov.uk/pbr2009/pbrn31.htm>

⁷⁷ <http://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20101218152931/http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2002/1928/contents/made>

⁷⁸ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1979/5/contents>

⁷⁹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:140:0016:0062:EN:PDF>

⁸⁰ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2009:140:0088:0113:EN:PDF>

⁸¹ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=CONSLEG:2011R0510:20120313:EN:PDF>

and biofuels. If a company supplies less than 450,000 litres a year in the UK, it can still register to claim Renewable Transport Fuel Certificates (RTFCs). Any company that supplies sustainable biofuel for use in road transport or NRMM in the UK can claim RTFCs. Companies can trade RTFCs or sell them to companies that need them to meet their obligations under the RTFO. Suppliers covered by the RTFO must provide data on the volumes and source of biofuel brought to market in the UK (DfT, 2012). In terms of non-compliance; *“The Administrator has powers to impose civil penalties in certain cases of noncompliance with the requirements of the RTFO including: failure to register with the Administrator if obligated; failure to meet the obligation through either the redemption of RTFCs or the payment of the buy-out price; or the fraudulent application for, or gaining of RTFCs. The Administrator may also apply interest to, and will collect, overdue civil penalties and buy-out payments”* (DfT, 2014b).

- f. Implementation network:** The Administrator of the RTFO is the Secretary of State; however, the daily administration including registration and compliance of the RTFO is managed by the RTFO Unit in the Department for Transport (DfT). In addition to the practical administration of the RTFO, the RTFO Unit run regular stakeholder events, publish a monthly newsletter with updates on important developments and has developed guidance to help suppliers and verifiers meet the requirements in the RTFO legislation. The unit also has an expert advisory group which provides technical advice, input and expertise on issues around carbon and sustainability of biofuel.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Estimated total net GHG savings in mtCO₂e/yr (not including indirect land use change effects): 1.6 in year 1; 2.0 in year 2; 2.1 in year 3; 2.4 in year 4; 2.0 in year 5. (ii) Best estimate total cost £2,215m (iii) Benefits which have not explicitly monetised in this cost benefit analysis include development of a UK biofuels industry (capital investment and jobs), increased agricultural production, diversification of the fuel supply, increased production of protein rich animal feed (as a co-product of bioethanol production). It was estimated that a 100 million litre biodiesel processing plant would create/sustain 200 jobs in farming and 62 jobs at the plant itself. If the plants were supplied entirely by feedstock produced in the UK, this would equate to 2,200 farming jobs and 682 jobs at the plants (DfT, 2014a).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK’s NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 23. Final energy savings from the Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation	Unknown	Unknown

1.2.2.3 Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS)

- a. General information:** Introduced June 2014, ESOS is a mandatory energy assessment scheme for large organisations in the UK. It was established by the UK Government in order to implement Article 8 (4-6) of the EU Energy Efficiency Directive (2012/27/EU)⁸². The ESOS Regulations 2014⁸³

⁸² <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2012:315:0001:0056:EN:PDF>

⁸³ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/uksi/2014/1643/pdfs/uksi_20141643_en.pdf

give effect to the scheme. Organisations that qualify for ESOS must carry out ESOS assessments every 4 years. These assessments are audits of the energy used by their buildings, industrial processes and transport to identify cost-effective energy saving measures (Environment Agency, 2015).

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Regulatory; ESOS is a mandatory scheme (Environment Agency, 2015).
- c. Objectives:** To target a gap in the existing policy landscape and help them to cut their energy costs, by providing targeted cost-effective recommendations to improve their energy efficiency. It will stimulate demand amongst UK businesses for energy efficiency measures, by making clear in the assessments what savings could be made. The assessments will review the organisations' entire energy consumption including buildings, industrial processes and transport activities (DECC, 2014c).
- d. Target groups:** ESOS applies to large UK undertakings (UK company that either employs 250 or more people, or has an annual turnover in excess of 50m euro, and an annual balance sheet total in excess of 43m euro; or an overseas company with a UK registered establishment which has 250 or more employees paying income tax to the UK) and their corporate groups. It mainly affects businesses but can also apply to not-for-profit bodies and any other non-public sector undertakings that are large enough to meet the qualification criteria. Corporate groups qualify if at least one UK group member meets the ESOS definition of a large undertaking (Environment Agency, 2015).
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The environmental regulator is responsible for compliance and enforcement activities. The regulator may issue civil sanctions including financial penalties (ranging from £5k-50k if an organisation does not meet the scheme's obligations (Environment Agency, 2015).
- f. Implementation network:** Overall, the Environment Agency is responsible for administering the scheme across the UK, and holding the UK register. A registered office or principal place of activity (in the absence of a registered office) determines the regulator, in terms of compliance and enforcement activities (Environment Agency, 2015):
 - The Environment Agency (England)
 - Northern Ireland Environment Agency (Northern Ireland)
 - Scottish Environment Protection Agency (Scotland)
 - Natural Resources Wales (Wales)
 - DECC Offshore Oil & Gas Environment and Decommissioning (offshore).

In relation to undertaking an ESOS assessment, a corporate group demonstrates compliance using either:

- An ISO 50001 energy management system certified by an accredited certification body (United Kingdom Accreditation Service (UKAS) accredited, a body accredited by another EU member state's national accreditation body or a body accredited by a body which is a member of the International Accreditation Forum), and covers all their energy use (for the whole corporate group in the UK),
- Display Energy Certificates (DECs), which are defined by the Energy Performance of Buildings Regulations 2008 (Northern Ireland) and the Energy Performance of Buildings Regulations 2012 (as amended) (England and Wales). DECs form part of the

implementation in England and Wales of the European Directives 2002/91/EC and 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings. DECs are undertaken by qualified assessors.

- Green Deal Assessments (GDAs), can be part of an ESOS compliant energy assessment for the types of energy consumption they cover, if they qualify as per regulation 7 of the Green Deal Framework Regulations 2012⁸⁴)
- ESOS compliant energy audits. All such energy audits must be reviewed by an ESOS lead assessor. An register of approved lead assessors is available online via the UK Government's ESOS webpage⁸⁵. An assessor can be an employee of the business, or a third party. The assessor is not held responsible for compliance by the regulators; therefore it is recommended that a member of the corporate group/organisation who understands the ESOS requirements, and works with the lead assessor to ensure the overall approach taken is compliant with ESOS.

The Environment Agency, and the other regulators do not provide standard templates for ESOS related data/activities and/or presentation of findings. Only the data to evidence that 90% of the total energy consumption is compliant via ESOS audits or other alternative routes to compliance, is required to be undertaken and recorded. This is to reduce the administrative burden on organisations that have existing data management procedures and tools.

- g. Outcomes:** (i) Assumptions suggest that ESOS could generate annual savings of around 3.0 TWh per year, of which 0.7TWh from transport (DECC, 2014b). Current analysis suggests that ESOS has the potential to deliver £1.9 billion of net benefits to the UK and reduce business energy bills by £300 million in its first year (DECC, 2014c). (ii) Best estimate total cost £1,178m (iii) The process of conducting the ESOS assessments themselves will provide employment for auditors and auditing companies. A range of other energy efficiency product and service businesses may also benefit from supporting large enterprises in implementing ESOS assessors' recommendations. The growth in the sector will help the supply side of the market mature, and enable the sector to promote the contribution it can make to a range of enterprises more effectively (DECC, 2014b).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 24. Final energy saving from the Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS) - transport

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS)	Unknown	12.6PJ

1.2.3 FINANCIAL POLICY INSTRUMENTS

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

⁸⁴ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukxi/2012/2079/contents/made>

⁸⁵ <https://www.gov.uk/guidance/energy-savings-opportunity-scheme-esos>

The UK has a very comprehensive number of financial policy instruments and measures including incentives, subsidies, tax exemptions, congestion charges and road tolls. The following are described in more detail below:

- Cycle to Work Scheme
- Plug-in Car and Van Grants
- Low Emission Bus Scheme

1.2.3.1 Cycle to Work Scheme

- a. General information:** To promote healthier journeys to work and to reduce environmental pollution, the 1999 Finance Act⁸⁶ introduced an annual tax exemption, which allows employers to loan cycles and cyclists' safety equipment to employees as a tax-free benefit. The exemption was one of a series of measures introduced under the Government's Green Transport Plan (DfT, 2011).
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Financial: tax-free benefit.
- c. Objectives:** The Cycle to Work tax efficient scheme is a part of a series of measures to promote healthier journeys to work and to reduce environmental pollution by making cycling more attractive.
- d. Target groups:** Employers of all sizes across the public, private and voluntary sectors can implement a tax exempt loan scheme for their employees.
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** To qualify for the tax exemption, the cycles and cyclists' safety equipment loaned by the employer under the scheme must be available to employees generally with no groups of employees excluded. There is no limit on the total value of the equipment including the cycle, e.g. it is possible to loan two cycles to one employee. The tax exemption only applies when an employee mainly uses the cycle and cyclists' safety equipment for qualifying journeys. A qualifying journey for an employee means a journey, or part of a journey; between his or her home and workplace, or between one workplace and another, in connection with the performance of their duties of employment. So, for example, cycling to and from the station to get to work would qualify. In this case, 'mainly' means that more than 50% of use of the cycle and safety equipment must involve a qualifying journey. Employees are not expected to keep mileage logs but employers should make clear to them that if they do not use the cycle mainly for qualifying journeys, they may lose the benefit of the tax exemption. In that event the employer would have to report the benefit in kind on form P11D, and account for Class 1A NICs, in the normal way. The employee would be liable for the tax due on the benefit in kind.
- f. Implementation network:** Scheme was first put forth by the DfT and is implemented by employers, under the guidance and regulation of HMRC, OFT/FCA and through approved cycle to work scheme providers. In addition, in order to gain the tax exemption, bicycles must be purchased through a retailer that is affiliated to a cycle to work scheme. The HMRC have published guidance and clarifications relating to the scheme; in 2010 the HMRC clarified that the bicycles needed to be sold at fair market value, to prevent the scheme becoming a tax loophole. Until March 2014, the scheme was regulated by the Office of Fair Trading (OFT; now no longer in existence), after which the Financial Conduct Agency (FCA) provided regulation relating to the

⁸⁶ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/1999/16/contents>

Cycle to Work scheme as it regulates the consumer credit market, overall, and other regulated financial services activities. Within the FCA Handbook, PERG 2.11.3⁸⁷ outlines the specific exemption for Cycle to Work schemes. In terms of how the scheme is implemented in practice; *“Normally, hire payments are sacrificed from your employees' gross monthly salary, these payments are not subject to income tax and National Insurance Contributions (NICs). At the end of the hire period, as the employer, you may choose to give employees the option to purchase the equipment. If your employee chooses to purchase your bike the cycle to work scheme provider will put in place a transfer of ownership process based on a Market Value payment set by HMRC. The scheme operates under a group consumer credit licence, which has an upper limit of £1,000. This allows employees to obtain cycles and related cycling safety equipment up to the limit of £1,000 including VAT. The Office of Fair Trading has agreed to adjust the consumer credit licence limit of £1,000 per person in the event someone has a specific need such as a disability. A higher limit can be applied if an employer has a separate company specific consumer credit licence thereby enabling employees to obtain cycles and equipment for an amount above the £1,000 limit covered by the group licence.”* (Cycletoworkalliance.org.uk, 2015)

- g. Outcomes:** (i) Scheme users are cycling a total of 13.2m miles per week. 67% of participants would commute to work by car if they did not cycle to work. These commuters are saving 112,210 tonnes of CO2 per annum in reduced carbon emissions. (ii) No cost details available. (iii) Employees who participate in schemes run by Alliance members save up to 40% of the total cost of a new bike. To date over 550,000 people have taken advantage of the scheme, which involves over 2,220 bike retailers and 32,000 employers. There is a direct health benefit from the scheme, with 87% of participants noticing their health improving, 84% of users rating the scheme as an important and easy way to keep fit and 97% of businesses thinking the scheme is an important way to encourage a healthy workforce. The scheme plays an important role in helping new cyclists get started. 54% of people did not cycle to work before joining the scheme. Furthermore, 40% of those who classed themselves as novice cyclists before joining the scheme, now class themselves as enthusiast cyclists – demonstrating the role of the scheme in delivering behavioural change and driving cycling up-take (CtWA, n.d.).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 25. Final energy savings from the Cycle to Work Scheme

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Cycle to Work Scheme	Unknown	Unknown

1.2.3.2 Plug-in Car and Van Grants

- a) General information:** The Plug-In Car Grant⁸⁸ (PICG) and the Plug-in Van Grant⁸⁹ (PiVG) were launched in January 2011 and reduce the cost of plugin vehicles for consumers by cutting the

⁸⁷ <https://www.handbook.fca.org.uk/handbook/PERG/2/11.html>

⁸⁸ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/plug-in-car-grant/plug-in-car-grant-eligibility-guidance>

cost of eligible vehicles by 25% up to £5,000 and 20% off the cost of a van, up to a maximum of £8,000. A consumer can get a grant towards the cost of each new electric (plug-in) car or van if it meets certain conditions (OLEV, 2011). The Home charge point grant is set as a 75% contribution to the cost of one charge point and its installation and the grant cap is set at £700 (including VAT) per eligible vehicle (OLEV, 2015a). The grants, offered by the UK Government, aim to encourage more consumers to purchase and drive ultra-low emission vehicles, as part of the UK's Carbon Plan 2011 and the framework and targets established in through the Climate Change Act 2008⁹⁰. The grants use EU Directives ((EC) 2007/46/EC) to specify eligible vehicles.

- b) Type of policy instrument:** Financial: grants.
- c) Objectives:** To encourage uptake of electric (plug-in) vehicles. Combined with tax benefits (such as VED and Company Car Tax exemptions) and selected local benefits, these measures aim to make ultra-low emission vehicles a more attractive proposition to consumers in terms of cost – one of the key barriers to the uptake of new technology (OLEV, 2011).
- d) Target groups:** Auto consumers
- e) Rules and influencing mechanisms:** A new vehicle is likely to be eligible if it is one of the following: electric vehicles (EVs) – these run completely on batteries and are plugged into the mains to be recharged plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs) – these use a petrol or diesel engine combined with a battery that plugs into the mains hydrogen fuel cell vehicles and other technologies. Vehicles must emit less than 75 grams of carbon dioxide (CO₂) per kilometre driven. Electric vehicles must be able to travel a minimum of 70 miles between charges. Plug-in hybrid electric vehicles must have a minimum electric range of 10 miles. Vehicles must be able to reach a speed of 60 miles per hour or more (OLEV, 2011). Customers must provide evidence of keepership, lease, or be named as the primary user of an eligible electric vehicle in order to be able to qualify for the home charge grant (OLEV, 2015a).
- f) Implementation network:** DfT through OLEV supplies the grants. Auto dealerships will manage all paperwork with regard to the grants. It is a requirement of the Plug-In Car Grant that manufacturers of eligible vehicles set out how they will engage with purchasers to ensure safe recharging of their vehicles; and the Institution of Engineering and Technology, the standards body responsible for electrical safety, is producing a Code of Practice to advise electricians how to ensure safe plug-in vehicle recharging installations (OLEV, 2011).
- g) Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) The Spending Review made provision of over £300m over the life of this Parliament for the Plug-In Car Grant to reduce the upfront cost of eligible vehicles to consumers and businesses (OLEV, 2011). (iii) A total of 9,046 ultra-low emission vehicles were registered in the first quarter of 2015 – a rise of 366% from the same period in 2014. As announced in the 2015 Summer Budget the government is investing £500 million over the next 5 years in making ULEVs more accessible to families and businesses across the country (DfT, 2015).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

⁸⁹ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/plug-in-van-grant/plug-in-van-grant-vehicles-list-and-eligibility-guidance>

⁹⁰ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2008/27/contents>

Table 26. Final energy savings from the Plug-in Car and Van Grants

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Plug-in Car and Van Grants	Unknown	Unknown

1.2.3.3 Low Emission Bus Scheme (LEBS)

- a. General information:** The LEBS was announced by OLEV in 2015 as a low emissions vehicle impact for local areas. The scheme will be run as a competition, with £30m made available for local authorities and operators in England and Wales through a competitive bidding process for the purchase of low mission buses and the infrastructure to support them between April 2016 and March 2019. The scheme builds on the success of the Green Bus Fund which ran from 2009-2013 (OLEV, 2015b). The grants, offered by the UK Government, aim to encourage more consumers to purchase and drive ultra-low emission vehicles, as part of the UK's Carbon Plan 2011 and the framework and targets established in through the Climate Change Act 2008⁹¹.
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Financial: Central government funding for local authorities.
- c. Objectives:** Increase the uptake of low and ultralow emission buses, speeding up the full transition to an ultralow emission bus fleet in England and Wales, and reducing the need for subsidy support; support the improvement of local air quality; and support OLEV's commitment of attracting investment to the UK (OLEV, 2015b).
- d. Target groups:** Any English or Welsh local authority or bus operator can apply for funding.
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The Department will contribute a maximum of 90% of the cost difference between the low emission bus and the standard diesel equivalent of the same total passenger capacity. Under the new testing procedure, in order to qualify as a LEB, a bus will need to: produce at least 15% less greenhouse gas emissions than the average conventional Euro V equivalent diesel bus of the same total passenger capacity; and meet or exceed Euro VI emissions regulations (OLEV, 2015b).
- f. Implementation network:** This is an OLEV funded scheme which will be administered by the Department for Transport. The Office for Low Emission Vehicles (OLEV) is a cross Government, industry endorsed team combining policy and funding streams to simplify policy development and delivery for ultra low emission vehicles. OLEV currently comprises people and funding from the Departments for Transport (DfT), Business, Innovation and Skills (BIS), and Energy and Climate Change (DECC). Its core purpose is to support the early market for electric and other ultra low emission vehicles (ULEVs).
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Total of £30m available in funds. (iii) The Green Bus Fund delivered around 1,250 low emission buses onto England's roads (OLEV, 2015b). Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 27. Final energy savings from the Low Emission Bus Scheme (LEBS)

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
-----------	-------------------	----------------------------

⁹¹ <http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2008/27/contents>

Low Emission Bus Scheme (LEBS)	Unknown	Unknown
--------------------------------	---------	---------

1.2.4 DISSEMINATION AND AWARENESS INSTRUMENTS

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

The UK has a very comprehensive number of dissemination and awareness policy instruments and measures including mobility advice for transport users, information and image campaigns for sustainable transport, vehicle labelling, gear shift indicators, training for eco-driving. The following are described in more detail below:

- Fuel Economy labels for cars
- The National Standard for cycle training
- Eco-driving training / FuelGood driver training

1.2.4.1 Fuel Economy labels for cars

- General information:** Regulations came into force on 21 November 2001⁹². These regulations were further amended by Statutory Instrument 2013 No 65⁹³, which took effect 11 February 2013 (VCA, 2013).
- Type of policy instrument:** Dissemination and awareness instruments: the primary purpose is to create more awareness with regard to emissions. / Regulatory: the labels are required for all vehicles.
- Objectives:** To give consumers more information about the fuel consumption and CO2 emissions characteristics of new cars (VCA, 2013).
- Target groups:** Dealers, suppliers and manufacturers of vehicles that are displayed for sale or lease.
- Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The Regulations specify the Secretary of State as an enforcement authority (England, Wales and Scotland). The Vehicle Certification Agency (VCA) are officials of the Secretary of State for Transport and have responsibility for reviewing the content of promotional literature to ensure that the mandatory data is included and accurate. Local weights and measures authorities will enforce all other aspects of the regulations in England, Wales, and Scotland e.g. checking posters, labels, and availability of guidebooks. Since weights and measures authorities will be visiting dealers' premises to conduct their enforcement duties, they also have responsibility for checking that promotional literature available on site contains fuel consumption and CO2 data. However, if there are queries regarding the accuracy of the data in the literature, the matter should be referred to the VCA. As part of their enforcement responsibility, weights and measures authorities have the authority to take action against dealers and suppliers if information is incorrect or not supplied to dealers. In Northern Ireland the Department of Enterprise, Trade and Investment will hold enforcement responsibility for all aspects of the Regulations. Enforcement action should be in the form of helping and encouraging

⁹² <http://www.dft.gov.uk/vca/additional/files/fcb--co2/enforcement-on-advertising/vca061.pdf>

⁹³ http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukxi/2013/65/pdfs/ukxiem_20130065_en.pdf

dealers and manufacturers to comply with the requirements of the Regulations, and prosecutions only to be brought in cases of persistent non-compliance (VCA, 2013).

- f. Implementation network:** Overseen by the Department for Transport, and administered by the VCA, with local weights and measures authorities enforcing all aspects of the regulations, except for the review of promotional literature content, which is the responsibility of the VCA.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) No cost details available. (iii) No other impact details available.

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 28. Final energy savings from Fuel Economy labels for cars

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Fuel Economy labels for cars	Unknown	Unknown

1.2.4.2 The National Standard for cycle training

- a. General information:** The National Standard for cycle training is built upon similar principles to training for motorcycle riders and car drivers, teaching the importance of assessing the likely risks faced by road users. Launched in 2005, the National Standard was developed by over 20 organisations and is maintained by the Department for Transport (DfT). There are three levels and a series of progressive outcomes within each level which can be used in training to take the complete beginner all the way to being able to ride on any road where cycling is permitted. In 2012, following consultation with stakeholders, the National Standard was revised and re-launched alongside a new quality assurance framework (DfT, 2015).
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Dissemination and awareness instruments: the primary purpose of the scheme is to equip people with cycling skills.
- c. Objectives:** The primary purpose of the National Standard is to get more people cycling, more often and with less risk. It helps break down some of the biggest barriers to cycling, opening up opportunities for people to get on their bikes and enabling cycling to become a normal everyday activity.
- d. Target groups:** The National Standard for cycling is designed to encourage and empower people of all ages to make independent cycle journeys in a wide range of road conditions.
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** National Standard/Bikeability training may only be delivered by National Standard Instructors (NSIs), who have successfully completed a DfT recognised instructor training course. From 1 January 2011, instructor training organisations (ITOs) are the only bodies recognised by government as providers of training for National Standard instructor trainers, instructors and assistant instructors. All NSIs are issued with an NSI number. The National Standard instructor database contains a record of every instructor holding an NSI number.
- f. Implementation network:** The DfT promotes the National Standard through the Bikeability award scheme in England. Any cycle training organisation wishing to use the Bikeability branding and issue the Bikeability award materials to trainees must first register a scheme. Bikeability is organised and delivered locally by registered bikeability providers. Scheme registration is part of

a quality assurance process to help ensure organisations are delivering good practice cycle training. The NSI database is managed by Steer Davies Gleave on behalf of the Department for Transport.

- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) No cost details available. (iii) Bikeability training addresses cycling safety concerns, equipping children with the necessary skills to respond to these dangers. Children who have taken part in the scheme feel safer and more confident when riding on the road (86%) and their parents feel more confident in allowing them to do so (87%). Children who have participated also feel more confident about riding their bike more often (87%) and, attested to by their parents, report an increased frequency in cycling having taken part in Bikeability (51% of children say they ride more having taken part in Bikeability and 49% of parents report an increase in the frequency with which their child rides). Participation also seems to encourage children to make new types of journeys using their bike, with children who have taken part more likely to cycle to get to places and more likely to say that they always or sometimes cycle on the road than those who have not. In light of these positive outcomes, it is perhaps unsurprising that Bikeability training itself is rated very highly by both parents (97% say that they are very/quite satisfied with the training) and children (95% describe it as fairly/very good), and children who have taken part say that they would recommend it to friends (91%). Indeed, children who have not yet participated (and their parents) are keen that they should do so, indicating a high level of latent demand for the scheme (DfT, 2015).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 29. Final energy savings from the National Standard for cycle training

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
National Standard for cycle training	Unknown	Unknown

1.2.4.3 Eco-driving training / FuelGood driver training

- a. General information:** Eco-driving training as offered through the FuelGood driver training from Energy Saving Trust (EST) trains employees to be more fuel efficient. Training is free and is also offered for electricity vehicles (EST, 2014).
- b. Type of policy instrument:** Dissemination and awareness instruments: the primary purpose of the scheme is to equip people with efficient driving skills.
- c. Objectives:** To increase the efficiency of driving; reducing emissions.
- d. Target groups:** Employees who drive for companies.
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Mainly socio-economic influences and potential to 'up-skill'. No exemptions, penalties or sanctions.
- f. Implementation network:** Delivered by the Energy Saving Trust (EST); training is delivered in 2-hour, one-to-one driving sessions.
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) No cost details available. (iii) Based on 8,700 miles per year, typical annual savings of up to £235 per car driver (more for van drivers) should all the tips given in the training be followed. Other expected benefits include: reduced wear and tear on tyres, brakes and clutches; reduced carbon footprint; and less accidents. Over 200 organisations have trained in the Energy Saving Trust's driver training programme including

FTSE 100 companies Carillion and Mitie as well as 25 Scottish Local Authorities, five NHS Trusts and more than 10 universities and colleges. The training is projected to increase a driver's MPG by up to 15%, helping organisations save on fuel costs and carbon emissions. 15% is the average MPG improvement seen on the day of training. Studies suggest that a typical driver will maintain savings of 1-6%, or £20-£120, across the entire year.

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 30. Final energy savings from the Eco-driving/FuelGood driver training schemes

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Eco-Driving training/FuelGood driver training	Unknown	Unknown

1.2.5 POLICY INSTRUMENTS FOR RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT

General description of the different policies that are described in this chapter

The UK has a very comprehensive number of research and development policy instruments and measures including funding of alternative fuels, and low emission vehicles, freight and passenger transport. The following are described in more detail below:

- Research Councils Energy Programme (RCEP)
- Technology Strategy Board (TSB) / Innovate UK

1.2.5.1 Research Councils Energy Programme (RCEP)

- General information:** Led by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC), the Energy Programme brings together the work of EPSRC and that of the Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC), the Economic and Social Research Council (ESRC), the Natural Environment Research Council (NERC), and the Science and Technology Facilities Council (STFC). The Energy Programme is investing more than £625 million in research and skills to pioneer a low carbon future. This builds on an investment of £839 million over the past eight years (RCUK, 2014).
- Type of policy instrument:** Dissemination and awareness instrument: The research Councils Energy Programme focusses on R&D and prioritises dissemination of findings.
- Objectives:** The Research Councils UK Energy Programme aims to position the UK to meet its energy and environmental targets and policy goals through world-class research and training. The objectives are to support a full spectrum of energy research to help the UK meet the objectives and targets set out in the 2007 Energy White Paper; to work in partnership to contribute to the research and postgraduate training needs of energy-related businesses and other key stakeholders; to increase the international visibility and level of international collaboration within the UK energy research portfolio; and to expand UK research capacity in energy-related areas (RCUK, 2014).
- Target groups:** Academia, business, government.
- Rules and influencing mechanisms:** Priorities for the Energy Programme include continuing support for a broad research portfolio in power generation and supply and to grow the portfolio in demand reduction, transport, security of supply, research capacity building and international

engagement. It includes investments in large research consortia, “whole-system” research, strategic partnerships with leading companies and support for the UK Energy Research Centre (UKERC), as well as support for fundamental science based energy research through investigator-led projects (HM Government, 2013).

- f. Implementation network:** RCEP is the largest public funder of the Energy Technologies Institute (ETI) – a public-private partnership of up to £1 billion to accelerate the deployment of new energy technologies. RCEP is also working with the Living with Environmental Change Programme (LWEC) to ensure a whole systems response to climate change (RCUK, 2014).
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Over the period 2011-15 expenditure under the Programme will exceed £540 million (HM Government, 2013). (iii) Funding has led to breakthroughs in hydrogen use for the future of car fuels and a second generation in biofuels (RCUK, 2014).

Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK’s NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 31. Final energy savings from the Research Council’s Energy Programme (RCEP)

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Research Council’s Energy Programme (RCEP)	Unknown	Unknown

1.2.5.2 Technology Strategy Board (TSB) / Innovate UK

- a. General information:** The Technology Strategy Board was first established in 2004 as an advisory body within the former UK Department of Trade and Industry (DTI). As the primary channel through which the Government encourages innovation, the Technology Strategy Board (TSB), now called Innovate UK, is the UK’s innovation agency. Many of the priority areas Innovate UK focus on are also reflected in the ‘Eight Great Technologies’ identified by Science and Universities Minister David Willetts. One of Innovate UK’s main tools is collaborative R&D funding; running competitions in a broad range of growth creating areas, from transport to biosciences and from construction to nanoscale technologies. Innovate UK have developed Catalysts are run in partnership with the research councils, offering businesses and researchers a clear and progressive route for development, so that successful early-stage projects can easily find support for the next stage on their innovation journey; and Catapult centres: A Catapult is a technology and innovation centre where the very best of the UK’s businesses, scientists and engineers can work side by side on research and development – transforming ideas into new products and services to generate economic growth. Catapults add an important new dimension to complement our existing research and development programmes, helping businesses to adopt, develop and exploit innovative products and technologies. They offer concentrated expertise in areas such as manufacturing processes, test facilities, type approval and accreditation or supply chain development. Many provide access to cutting-edge equipment and specialist facilities to develop and test ideas in reality (TSB, 2014). Previous TSB projects funded include: Low carbon truck trial; Batteries for Low Carbon Vehicles: Recycling and Re-Use; Marine Vessel Efficiency (Innovate UK, 2015).

- b. Type of policy instrument:** Policy instruments for R&D and best available technologies (BAT) promotion
- c. Objectives:** The focus of Innovate UK is on innovation, working with business to stimulate and support innovation and accelerate economic growth
- d. Target groups:** Business and research
- e. Rules and influencing mechanisms:** The responsibilities of Innovate UK are to: provide new support for innovative small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with high-growth potential; make sure that government initiatives such as SBRI (Small Business Research Initiative) attract innovative UK businesses and give companies access to important customers in the public sector; identify and invest in the sectors that have the greatest potential for innovation to speed up economic growth; and help innovative companies work with their backers so their ideas can be developed commercially
- f. Implementation network:** Innovate UK is an executive non-departmental public body, sponsored by the Department for Business, Innovation & Skills. Innovate UK's responsibilities are to:
- determine which science and technology developments will drive future economic growth
 - meet UK innovators with great ideas in the fields we're focused on
 - fund the strongest opportunities
 - connect innovators with the right partners they need to succeed
 - help our innovators launch, build and grow successful businesses
- g. Outcomes:** (i) Energy impact data is not available. (ii) Gross grant expenditure for transport sector 2012-2013: £23.3m; 2013-2014: £30.8m (iii) Aside from job creation as a result of funding Innovate UK has increased full-time employment from 196 to 257 employees from 2013-2014. Millions of £ invested in R&D resulting in numerous outcomes directly befitting business and the public.
Forecast of final energy savings according to the UK's NEEAP (DECC, 2014c):

Table 32. Final energy savings from the Technology Strategy Board (TSB)/Innovate UK

Programme	Savings 2009-2013	Savings total 2014-2020
Technology Strategy Board (TSB)/Innovate UK	Unknown	Unknown

1.2.6 SUMMARY TABLE FOR THE TRANSPORT SECTOR IN THE UNITED KINGDOM

Table 33. Summary table for the transport sector in the UK

Summary table: Transport					
	Short list of implemented policies and measures	Objective ⁹⁴ (improve system, travel or vehicle efficiency)	Target group and targeted objects	Rules and influencing mechanism (motivation or punish non-compliance)	Implementation network
Planning instruments	Plug-in Vehicle Infrastructure Strategy (Plug-in Infrastructure Programme, PiP)	<i>Travel efficiency</i> ; In addition to making plug-in vehicles more affordable and stimulating technological innovation, having the right infrastructure in place to support plug-in vehicle owners is the other critical component in maintaining the UK's favourable market position. By providing clarity of approach and removing barriers for those wishing to invest in, provide or benefit from such	The PiP aims to encourage local authorities to adopt plug-in vehicle recharging infrastructure within their local planning policies, as well as encourage research and development in electric vehicles within the transport industry, and improve the economic viability of plug-in vehicle infrastructure for installation contractors, charge-point manufacturers and operators as well as local	As a strategy, there are no specific rules. However, it is combined with numerous policies and financial incentives in relation to increasing the uptake of plug-in vehicles (hybrid and/or full electric) such as the Plug-in Car and Van Grant incentives, favourable tax regimes (plug-in vehicles receive VED and Company Car Tax exemptions, as well as Enhanced Capital Allowances). Furthermore,	Office for Low Emission Vehicles (OLEV). Implementation strategy includes: using the Plugged-In Places trials as a central mechanism to inform the development of commercial models for plug-in vehicle infrastructure; removing barriers to the market, such as the requirement for planning permission for public recharging infrastructure, and working to enable charge point

⁹⁴ Energy efficiency in the transport sector can be divided into system efficiency (reduce or avoid travel or the need to travel), travel efficiency (shift to more energy efficient modes) and vehicle efficiency (improve the efficiency through vehicle technology).

		<p>infrastructure, the Strategy aims to stimulate and accommodate the growth in the plug-in vehicle market that we expect to see up to 2020.</p>	<p>authorities and owners of publicly accessible car parks. In addition, a secondary target group is the end user/consumer (both domestic and business).</p>	<p>businesses monitored under the Carbon Reduction Commitment (CRC) are able to discount electricity used to charge plug-in vehicles from their total electricity consumption. Planning-related incentives include the establishment of a Permitted Development Right for landowners to install charge-points without the need for planning permission.</p>	<p>operators to charge the market rate for electricity; producing a conducive environment for private investment, by encouraging infrastructure through planning policies, supporting the move to standardisation and, if raising finance proves a barrier, the potential for targeted financial solutions through the Green Investment Bank; and helping the consumer by enabling all public infrastructure to be interoperable and improving the provision of information about public charge points (OLEV, 2011).</p>
	<p>Eco-towns Planning Policy (<i>cancelled in current form from 5th March 2015</i>)</p>	<p><i>System efficiency</i>; To minimize energy consumption and to make healthy living easier.</p>	<p>Developers, designers, infrastructure and building industries</p>	<p>Planning applications should include travel plans which demonstrate: (a) how the town’s design will enable at least 50 per cent of trips originating in eco-towns to be made by non-car means, with the potential for this to increase over time to at least 60 per cent (b) good design principles, drawing from Manual for Streets, Building for Life, and community travel planning principles (c) how transport choice messages, infrastructure and services will be provided from ‘day one’ of residential occupation, and (d)</p>	<p>The UK Government ministerial department, DCLG, sets out national planning policy guidance, strategy and rules. The DCLG has the following responsibilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • supporting local government by giving them the power to act for their community - without interference from central government. • helping communities and neighbourhoods to solve their own problems so neighbourhoods are strong, attractive and thriving.

				<p>how the carbon impact of transport in the eco-town will be monitored, as part of embedding a long term low-carbon approach to travel within plans for community governance. Where eco-town plans intend to incorporate ultra-low carbon vehicle options, including electric car schemes to help achieve a sustainable transport system, planning applications should demonstrate that: (a) there will be sufficient energy headroom to meet the higher demand for electricity, and (b) the scheme will not add so many additional private vehicles to the local road network that these will cause congestion. The policies set out in the Planning Policy Strategy should be taken into account by regional planning bodies in the preparation of revisions to regional spatial strategies, by the Mayor of London in relation to the spatial development strategy for London, and by local planning authorities in the preparation of local development documents (DCLG, 2009b).</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • working with local enterprise partnerships and enterprise zones to help the private sector grow. • making the planning system work more efficiently and effectively. • supporting local fire and rescue authorities so that they're able to respond to emergencies and reduce the number and impact of fires. <p>There are corresponding departments in the Welsh Government, Scottish Government and the Northern Ireland Executive, and which are responsible for policy relating to communities and local government within their localities. In terms of planning, England and Wales follow the same planning policies, whilst Scotland and Northern Ireland have their own separate local planning policy frameworks. Within the DCLG, the executive agency, the Planning Inspectorate, deals with "planning appeals, national infrastructure planning applications, examinations of local plans and other planning-related and specialist casework in England and Wales." Eco-</p>
--	--	--	--	---	--

					towns will need to be monitored through regional and local monitoring frameworks. Regional Planning Bodies and Local Planning Authorities will be required to monitor the implementation of their spatial policies as set out in the RSS and in development plan documents at the local level. Regional Planning Bodies and Local Planning Authorities should set out in their Annual Monitoring Reports indicators for monitoring the sustainability of eco-towns in their region/district. Arrangements should be put in place for the long-term monitoring of the standards set out for eco-towns as part of the requirements for community governance.
Regulatory policy instruments	Vehicle Excise Duty (VED): fuel type and CO2 emission vehicle bands	<i>Travel and vehicle efficiency;</i> The reformed VED system retains and strengthens the CO2-based First Year Rates (FYRs) to incentivise uptake of the very cleanest cars whilst moving to a flat Standard Rate (SR) in order to make the tax fairer, simpler and sustainable	All vehicle owners.	To ensure those who can afford the most expensive cars make a fair contribution, a supplement of £310 will be applied to the SR of cars with a list price (not including VED) over £40,000, for the first 5 years in which a SR is paid. Section 1 of the Vehicle and Registration Act (VERA) 1994 provides for the charging of VED. Section 2 of VERA provides that VED in respect of	Tax set forth by HM Revenue & Customs. The measure is monitored through the DVLA vehicle licensing data (HM R&C, 2015).

				a vehicle of any description is chargeable by reference to the applicable rate specified in schedule 1 of VERA. Part 1A of Schedule 1 to VERA sets out the VED rates for cars registered on or after 1 March 2001, as amended by successive Finance Acts (HM R&C, 2015).	
Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation (RTFO)	<i>Travel and vehicle efficiency;</i> Reducing transport related GHG while supporting production of biofuels.	Obligatory for companies own and supply 450,000 litres or more of any road transport or NRMM fuel for use in the UK. Open to any company.	A company must register under the RTFO if it owns and supplies 450,000 litres or more of any road transport or NRMM fuel for use in the UK during the course of an obligation year (15 April to 14 April). The 450,000 litre figure includes all fossil fuels and biofuels. If a company supplies less than 450,000 litres a year in the UK, it can still register to claim Renewable Transport Fuel Certificates (RTFCs). Any company that supplies sustainable biofuel for use in road transport or NRMM in the UK can claim RTFCs. Companies can trade RTFCs or sell them to companies that need them to meet their obligations under the RTFO. Suppliers covered by the RTFO must provide data on the volumes and source of biofuel brought to market in the UK	The Administrator of the RTFO is the Secretary of State; however, the daily administration including registration and compliance of the RTFO is managed by the RTFO Unit in the Department for Transport (DfT). In addition to the practical administration of the RTFO, the RTFO Unit run regular stakeholder events, publish a monthly newsletter with updates on important developments and has developed guidance to help suppliers and verifiers meet the requirements in the RTFO legislation. The unit also has an expert advisory group which provides technical advice, input and expertise on issues around carbon and sustainability of biofuel.	

				(DfT, 2012). In terms of non-compliance; “The Administrator has powers to impose civil penalties in certain cases of noncompliance with the requirements of the RTFO including: failure to register with the Administrator if obligated; failure to meet the obligation through either the redemption of RTFCs or the payment of the buy-out price; or the fraudulent application for, or gaining of RTFCs. The Administrator may also apply interest to, and will collect, overdue civil penalties and buy-out payments” (DfT, 2014b).	
Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme (ESOS)	<i>System and travel efficiency;</i> To target a gap in the existing policy landscape and help them to cut their energy costs, by providing targeted cost-effective recommendations to improve their energy efficiency. It will stimulate demand amongst UK businesses for energy efficiency measures, by making clear in the assessments what savings could be made. The assessments will review the organisations’ entire energy consumption including buildings, industrial processes	ESOS applies to large UK undertakings (UK company that either employs 250 or more people, or has an annual turnover in excess of 50m euro, and an annual balance sheet total in excess of 43m euro; or an overseas company with a UK registered establishment which has 250 or more employees paying income tax to the UK) and their corporate groups. It mainly affects businesses but can also apply to not-for-profit bodies and any other non-public sector undertakings that are	The environmental regulator is responsible for compliance and enforcement activities. The regulator may issue civil sanctions including financial penalties (ranging from £5k-50k if an organisation does not meet the scheme’s obligations (Environment Agency, 2015).	Overall, the Environment Agency is responsible for administering the scheme across the UK, and holding the UK register. A registered office or principal place of activity (in the absence of a registered office) determines the regulator, in terms of compliance and enforcement activities (Environment Agency, 2015): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Environment Agency (England) • Northern Ireland Environment Agency (Northern 	

		<p>and transport activities (DECC, 2014c).</p>	<p>large enough to meet the qualification criteria. Corporate groups qualify if at least one UK group member meets the ESOS definition of a large undertaking (Environment Agency, 2015).</p>		<p>Ireland)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scottish Environment Protection Agency (Scotland) • Natural Resources Wales (Wales) • DECC Offshore Oil & Gas Environment and Decommissioning (offshore). <p>In relation to undertaking an ESOS assessment, a corporate group demonstrates compliance using either:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • An ISO 50001 energy management system certified by an accredited certification body (United Kingdom Accreditation Service (UKAS) accredited, a body accredited by another EU member state’s national accreditation body or a body accredited by a body which is a member of the International Accreditation Forum), and covers all their energy use (for the whole corporate group in the UK), • Display Energy Certificates (DECs), which are defined by the Energy Performance of Buildings Regulations 2008 (Northern Ireland) and the Energy Performance of Buildings Regulations 2012 (as
--	--	--	---	--	---

					<p>amended) (England and Wales). DECs form part of the implementation in England and Wales of the European Directives 2002/91/EC and 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings. DECs are undertaken by qualified assessors.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green Deal Assessments (GDAs), can be part of an ESOS compliant energy assessment for the types of energy consumption they cover, if they qualify as per regulation 7 of the Green Deal Framework Regulations 2012) • ESOS compliant energy audits. All such energy audits must be reviewed by an ESOS lead assessor. An register of approved lead assessors is available online via the UK Government’s ESOS webpage . An assessor can be an employee of the business, or a third party. The assessor is not held responsible for compliance by the regulators; therefore it is recommended that a member of the corporate group/organisation who understands the ESOS requirements, and works with the lead assessor to ensure the
--	--	--	--	--	--

					<p>overall approach taken is compliant with ESOS.</p> <p>The Environment Agency, and the other regulators do not provide standard templates for ESOS related data/activities and/or presentation of findings. Only the data to evidence that 90% of the total energy consumption is compliant via ESOS audits or other alternative routes to compliance, is required to be undertaken and recorded. This is to reduce the administrative burden on organisations that have existing data management procedures and tools.</p>
<p>Financial policy instruments</p>	<p>Cycle to Work Scheme</p>	<p><i>Travel efficiency</i>; aims to promote healthier journeys to work and to reduce environmental pollution by making cycling more attractive.</p>	<p>Employers of all sizes across the public, private and voluntary sectors can implement a tax exempt loan scheme for their employees.</p>	<p>To qualify for the tax exemption, the cycles and cyclists' safety equipment loaned by the employer under the scheme must be available to employees generally with no groups of employees excluded. There is no limit on the total value of the equipment including the cycle, e.g. it is possible to loan two cycles to one employee. The tax exemption only applies when an employee mainly uses the cycle and cyclists' safety equipment for qualifying journeys. A qualifying journey</p>	<p>Scheme was first put forth by the DfT and is implemented by employers, under the guidance and regulation of HMRC, OFT/FCA and through approved cycle to work scheme providers. In addition, in order to gain the tax exemption, bicycles must be purchased through a retailer that is affiliated to a cycle to work scheme. The HMRC have published guidance and clarifications relating to the scheme; in 2010 the HMRC clarified that the bicycles needed to be sold at fair</p>

				<p>for an employee means a journey, or part of a journey; between his or her home and workplace, or between one workplace and another, in connection with the performance of their duties of employment. So, for example, cycling to and from the station to get to work would qualify. In this case, 'mainly' means that more than 50% of use of the cycle and safety equipment must involve a qualifying journey. Employees are not expected to keep mileage logs but employers should make clear to them that if they do not use the cycle mainly for qualifying journeys, they may lose the benefit of the tax exemption. In that event the employer would have to report the benefit in kind on form P11D, and account for Class 1A NICs, in the normal way. The employee would be liable for the tax due on the benefit in kind.</p>	<p>market value, to prevent the scheme becoming a tax loophole. Until March 2014, the scheme was regulated by the Office of Fair Trading (OFT; now no longer in existence), after which the Financial Conduct Agency (FCA) provided regulation relating to the Cycle to Work scheme as it regulates the consumer credit market, overall, and other regulated financial services activities. Within the FCA Handbook, PERG 2.11.3 outlines the specific exemption for Cycle to Work schemes. In terms of how the scheme is implemented in practice; "Normally, hire payments are sacrificed from your employees' gross monthly salary, these payments are not subject to income tax and National Insurance Contributions (NICs). At the end of the hire period, as the employer, you may choose to give employees the option to purchase the equipment. If your employee chooses to purchase your bike the cycle to work scheme provider will put in place a transfer of ownership process based on a Market Value payment set by HMRC. The scheme operates</p>
--	--	--	--	--	--

					<p>under a group consumer credit licence, which has an upper limit of £1,000. This allows employees to obtain cycles and related cycling safety equipment up to the limit of £1,000 including VAT. The Office of Fair Trading has agreed to adjust the consumer credit licence limit of £1,000 per person in the event someone has a specific need such as a disability. A higher limit can be applied if an employer has a separate company specific consumer credit licence thereby enabling employees to obtain cycles and equipment for an amount above the £1,000 limit covered by the group licence.” (Cycletoworkalliance.org.uk, 2015)</p>
	<p>Plug-in Car and Van Grants</p>	<p><i>Travel and vehicle efficiency;</i> To encourage uptake of electric (plug-in) vehicles. Combined with tax benefits (such as VED and Company Car Tax exemptions) and selected local benefits, these measures aim to make ultra-low emission vehicles a more attractive proposition to consumers in terms of cost – one of the key barriers to the uptake of new technology</p>	<p>Auto consumers</p>	<p>A new vehicle is likely to be eligible if it is one of the following: electric vehicles (EVs) – these run completely on batteries and are plugged into the mains to be recharged plug-in hybrid electric vehicles (PHEVs) – these use a petrol or diesel engine combined with a battery that plugs into the mains hydrogen fuel cell vehicles and other technologies. Vehicles must</p>	<p>DfT through OLEV supplies the grants. Auto dealerships will manage all paperwork with regard to the grants. It is a requirement of the Plug-In Car Grant that manufacturers of eligible vehicles set out how they will engage with purchasers to ensure safe recharging of their vehicles; and the Institution of Engineering and Technology, the standards body responsible</p>

		(OLEV, 2011).		emit less than 75 grams of carbon dioxide (CO ₂) per kilometre driven. Electric vehicles must be able to travel a minimum of 70 miles between charges. Plug-in hybrid electric vehicles must have a minimum electric range of 10 miles. Vehicles must be able to reach a speed of 60 miles per hour or more (OLEV, 2011). Customers must provide evidence of keepership, lease, or be named as the primary user of an eligible electric vehicle in order to be able to qualify for the home charge grant (OLEV, 2015a).	for electrical safety, is producing a Code of Practice to advise electricians how to ensure safe plug-in vehicle recharging installations (OLEV, 2011).
Low Emission Bus Scheme	<i>Travel and vehicle efficiency;</i> Increase the uptake of low and ultralow emission buses, speeding up the full transition to an ultralow emission bus fleet in England and Wales, and reducing the need for subsidy support; support the improvement of local air quality; and support OLEV’s commitment of attracting investment to the UK (OLEV, 2015b).	Any English or Welsh local authority or bus operator can apply for funding.	The Department will contribute a maximum of 90% of the cost difference between the low emission bus and the standard diesel equivalent of the same total passenger capacity. Under the new testing procedure, in order to qualify as a LEB, a bus will need to: produce at least 15% less greenhouse gas emissions than the average conventional Euro V equivalent diesel bus of the same total passenger capacity; and meet or exceed Euro VI emissions regulations (OLEV, 2015b).	This is an OLEV funded scheme which will be administered by the Department for Transport. The Office for Low Emission Vehicles (OLEV) is a cross Government, industry endorsed team combining policy and funding streams to simplify policy development and delivery for ultra low emission vehicles. OLEV currently comprises people and funding from the Departments for Transport (DfT), Business, Innovation and Skills (BIS), and Energy and Climate Change (DECC). Its core purpose is to support the	

					early market for electric and other ultra low emission vehicles (ULEVs).
Dissemination and awareness instruments	Fuel Economy labels for cars	<i>Travel and vehicle efficiency;</i> To give consumers more information about the fuel consumption and CO2 emissions characteristics of new cars (VCA, 2013).	Dealers, suppliers and manufacturers of vehicles that are displayed for sale or lease.	The Regulations specify the Secretary of State as an enforcement authority (England, Wales and Scotland). The Vehicle Certification Agency (VCA) are officials of the Secretary of State for Transport and have responsibility for reviewing the content of promotional literature to ensure that the mandatory data is included and accurate. Local weights and measures authorities will enforce all other aspects of the regulations in England, Wales, and Scotland e.g. checking posters, labels, and availability of guidebooks. Since weights and measures authorities will be visiting dealers' premises to conduct their enforcement duties, they also have responsibility for checking that promotional literature available on site contains fuel consumption and CO2 data. However, if there are queries regarding the accuracy of the data in the literature, the matter should be referred to the VCA. As part of their enforcement responsibility,	Overseen by the Department for Transport, and administered by the VCA, with local weights and measures authorities enforcing all aspects of the regulations, except for the review of promotional literature content, which is the responsibility of the VCA.

				weights and measures authorities have the authority to take action against dealers and suppliers if information is incorrect or not supplied to dealers. In Northern Ireland the Department of Enterprise, Trade and Investment will hold enforcement responsibility for all aspects of the Regulations. Enforcement action should be in the form of helping and encouraging dealers and manufacturers to comply with the requirements of the Regulations, and prosecutions only to be brought in cases of persistent non-compliance (VCA, 2013).	
	National Standard for cycle training	<i>Travel efficiency</i> ; To get more people cycling, more often and with less risk.	The National Standard for cycling is designed to encourage and empower people of all ages to make independent cycle journeys in a wide range of road conditions.	National Standard/Bikeability training may only be delivered by National Standard Instructors (NSIs), who have successfully completed a DfT recognised instructor training course. From 1 January 2011, instructor training organisations (ITOs) are the only bodies recognised by government as providers of training for National Standard instructor trainers, instructors and assistant instructors. All NSIs are issued with an NSI number. The National Standard instructor database	The DfT promotes the National Standard through the Bikeability award scheme in England. Any cycle training organisation wishing to use the Bikeability branding and issue the Bikeability award materials to trainees must first register a scheme. Bikeability is organised and delivered locally by registered bikeability providers. Scheme registration is part of a quality assurance process to help ensure organisations are delivering good practice cycle training. The NSI database is managed

				contains a record of every instructor holding an NSI number.	by Steer Davies Gleave on behalf of the Department for Transport.
	Eco-Driving / FuelGood training	<i>Travel efficiency</i> ; To increase the efficiency of driving; reducing emissions.	Employees who drive for companies.	Mainly socio-economic influences and potential to ‘up-skill’. No exemptions, penalties or sanctions.	Delivered by the Energy Saving Trust (EST); training is delivered in 2-hour, one-to-one driving sessions.
Policy instruments for Research and Development	Research Council’s Energy Programme (RCEP)	<i>System, travel and vehicle efficiency</i> ; Aims to enable the UK to meet its energy and environmental targets and policy goals through world-class research and training; support a full spectrum of energy research to help the UK meet the objectives and targets set out in the 2007 Energy White Paper; to work in partnership to contribute to the research and postgraduate training needs of energy-related businesses and other key stakeholders; to increase the international visibility and level of international collaboration within the UK energy research portfolio; and to expand UK research capacity in energy-related areas	Academia, business, government	Priorities for the Energy Programme include continuing support for a broad research portfolio in power generation and supply and to grow the portfolio in demand reduction, transport, security of supply, research capacity building and international engagement. It includes investments in large research consortia, “whole-system” research, strategic partnerships with leading companies and support for the UK Energy Research Centre (UKERC), as well as support for fundamental science based energy research through investigator-led projects.	RCEP is the largest public funder of the Energy Technologies Institute (ETI) – a public-private partnership of up to £1 billion to accelerate the deployment of new energy technologies. RCEP is also working with the Living with Environmental Change Programme (LWEC) to ensure a whole systems response to climate change.
	Technology Strategy Board / InnovateUK	<i>System, travel and vehicle efficiency</i> ; The focus of Innovate UK is on innovation, working with business to stimulate and support innovation and accelerate	Business and research	The responsibilities of Innovate UK are to: provide new support for innovative small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with high-growth potential; make sure that	Innovate UK is an executive non-departmental public body, sponsored by the Department for Business, Innovation & Skills. Innovate UK’s

		<p>economic growth</p>		<p>government initiatives such as SBRI (Small Business Research Initiative) attract innovative UK businesses and give companies access to important customers in the public sector; identify and invest in the sectors that have the greatest potential for innovation to speed up economic growth; and help innovative companies work with their backers so their ideas can be developed commercially</p>	<p>responsibilities are to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • determine which science and technology developments will drive future economic growth • meet UK innovators with great ideas in the fields we're focused on • fund the strongest opportunities • connect innovators with the right partners they need to succeed • help our innovators launch, build and grow successful businesses
--	--	------------------------	--	--	--

2. POLICY INSTRUMENTS ON THE REGIONAL / LOCAL LEVEL

The interaction between the different levels (national, regional, local) in energy efficiency policy making has already been covered in D.1.1. Next to national energy efficiency policies, many regions and cities have implemented own climate action plans, energy efficiency action plans, or are part of the Covenant of Mayors. Describing all existing policy instruments or energy efficiency measures, would be too much and is not possible in the framework of this project. Therefore, in this deliverable, specific policy instruments on the regional / local level are exemplarily covered by a case study.

2.1 PRESENTATION OF THE CASE STUDY: LONDON

The case study describes the multi-level policy processes between the national, regional and local level. The focus lies on the vertical integration of local actions into the national energy efficiency framework and vice versa.

City / Region: London

Local government in London is structured over two administrative tiers;

- City-wide strategic tier (co-ordinated by the Greater London Authority (GLA))
- Local tier (33 local authorities)

The GLA has two elected parts; the Mayor of London and the London Assembly. It is responsible for strategic planning, policing, fire services and most transport and economic development aspects⁹⁵.

The local authorities consist of 32 London borough councils and the City of London Corporation. They are responsible for local services including local planning, schools, social services, local roads and refuse collection.

In 2011, the GLA launched Mayor's Climate Change Mitigation and Energy Strategy to deliver London's Energy Future, through collaboration with the local authorities, and in line with EU and UK national energy policies (GLA, 2011). The main objectives for the strategy were:

- To reduce London's CO₂ emissions to mitigate climate change. The target is to reduce London's emissions by 60% of 1990 levels by 2025 and 80% by 2050. The 60% reduction in emissions will be achieved through energy supply reductions and energy efficiency improvements from homes, workplaces and transport.
- To maximise economic opportunities from the transition to a low carbon capital.
- To ensure a secure and reliable energy supply for London.
- To meet, and where possible exceed, national climate change and energy objectives

The strategy is built on three main policies in the fields of buildings, the environment and transport. The programmes that underpin these pillars are aimed at delivering targeted improvements to make public services more efficient and less of a burden on tax payers, whilst delivering wider environmental benefits such as conserving water, saving energy or reducing waste.

The current Mayor is putting unprecedented levels of funding into a variety of Climate Change Mitigation and Energy Strategy programmes; that operate at both the strategic and local levels.

⁹⁵ Health services in London are managed by the UK national Government, but controlled and administered in London by one strategic health authority; NHS London.

Several sources of funds are being, and have been used to fund climate change programmes since 2011. This includes £100million London Green Fund (LGF) and independently managed Urban Development Funds which invests in energy efficiency, waste and decentralised energy at the local authority level. In addition to this, the programmes also aim to attract national funding streams (past and current) such as CERT, CESP, Warm Front, FiTs, RHI, Green Deal and Green Investment Bank. A further £100million of private sector funding is also expected. The aim is that as the LGF demonstrates to investors its ability to make a return on investments, it will stimulate further funding from other sources such as public sources, development banks and infrastructure funds to achieve over £500 million (GLA, 2011).

Energy Efficiency Policy / Action

Table 1 provides an overview of activities in London in terms of implementing the city's energy efficiency plans.

Table 34. Overview of activities in London regarding energy efficiency in the building and transport sectors (GLA, 2011)

Action	Description
Retrofitting London	<p>London's existing buildings are responsible for nearly 80% of London's CO₂ emissions. Retrofitting London's existing buildings is crucial in order to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reduce energy and water use • deliver new jobs and skills • save businesses and household energy bills <p>The programmes planned to tackle the major building sectors by retrofit with energy efficient and energy supply measures are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RE:CONNECT – low carbon zones signed-up to deliver a 20.12% reduction in CO₂ emissions by 2012 by taking novel approaches to community engagement aiming to increase the uptake of energy efficiency and energy supply programmes in homes and workplaces by concentrating activity at a neighbourhood level. • RE:NEW – retrofit 1.2million homes by 2015, the largest programme of its kind in London. Demonstrations from this programme showed that households could save over £150 per year through retrofitting actions • RE:FIT – retrofitting London's public sector buildings. This programme has secured energy savings of £1m per year for the GLA group from 42 pilot buildings. <i>DECC has committed to rolling out the RE:FIT scheme established by the GLA throughout England (as part of the UK National Energy Efficiency Action Plan)</i> • Decentralised energy programme – deploying new low carbon energy supply infrastructure in London. The London Waste and Recycling Board is investing in the development of waste-to-energy infrastructure that can generate renewable heat and power, helping London to reduce its carbon footprint of its waste.
Cleaner air for London	<p>Actions being taken to improve air quality (but also enable improved energy efficiency) include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introducing age limits for black cabs

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • tougher standards for the Low Emission Zones • new cleaner hybrid and hydrogen buses • retrofit older buses with equipment such as filters to curb pollution • introduce more EV on London streets • delivering a cycling revolution in London <p>Emissions from transport account for approximately 22% of London's total CO₂ emissions. The programmes planned to deliver a reduction in emissions from transport are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Electric vehicle rollout – the plans include new charging infrastructure to support the introduction of 100,000 EVs on London's streets. This ambitious plan is aimed at making London the EV capital in Europe. • Further use of ultra-low carbon vehicles – with the introduction of low carbon buses, hybrid buses, new buses for London which have fuel consumption with an expected 40% improvement in fuel consumption compared to a conventional diesel double decker bus. In July 2015, the Mayor of London released further plans to help the capital become the ultra-low emission vehicle capital of Europe. The plan sets a direction for London to support the expected increase in the number of ULEV • Moving to more carbon-efficient modes of transport – measures to support travel by public transport, unprecedented levels of walking and cycling investment and energy efficiency measures on the London Underground.
--	--

Energy Efficiency instruments / measures:

The following section outlines energy efficiency instruments / measures used in London in both the building and transport sectors.

Building sector: RE:FIT

RE:FIT is an award winning scheme that uses an Energy Service Company (ESCO) to implement energy efficiency measures which allows the public sector to improve the energy performance of their buildings through cutting energy consumption and carbon emissions and reducing the running costs (GLA, 2015b). The RE:FIT programme has flexible funding options. The finance sources include the London Energy Efficiency Fund, the Energy Service Company, self-funding or third parties.

The programme is used for a range of measures to improve the energy performance and reduce carbon emissions from the buildings. These measures include insulation, building fabric improvements, replacement or upgrading of mechanical and electrical services equipment and the installation of bespoke measures such as CHP and voltage optimisation equipment

To test and demonstrate the concept of RE:FIT, pilot projects were delivered on a number of public sector buildings including those owned by Transport for London and the Metropolitan Police Service.

In these projects, energy efficiency measures were retrofitted, delivering over 7000 tonnes of carbon emission reduction and 28% of energy consumption reduction (RE:FIT, 2015a).

The RE:FIT model is available to every public sector organisation in London and 199 public sector organisations have already shown interest, including the NHS, central government, museums and education organisations. To date, 31 out of the 33 London boroughs are participating in RE:FIT. Over 450 buildings have been retrofitted, generating carbon savings of approximately 33,000 tonnes per year. Greater London Authority is aiming for 600 buildings to be refitted. This will generate carbon savings of approximately 45,000 tonnes of CO₂ emissions by 2015 (REFIT, 2015b)

Transport sector: Support for Ultra-Low Emission Vehicles (ULEVs)

To minimise CO₂ emissions from transport, the Mayor, through Transport for London and working with London boroughs and other partners, has plans to invest in, incentivise and encourage the development and use of low carbon vehicles, including EVs, hydrogen-fuelled vehicles and low carbon buses. This includes delivering the infrastructure required for the distribution of alternative transport fuel sources. In 2009, the then Mayor launched the Electric Vehicle Delivery Plan for London which included aims to achieve 100,000 electric vehicles on London's streets as soon as possible (Mayor of London, 2009). In July 2015, the Mayor revealed further plans to help London become the ULEV capital of Europe. Transport for London, the world's largest green bus fleet, is expanding with the introduction of two new all-electric routes as part of its commitment for 300 single deck buses in central London to be zero emission by 2020 (TFL, 2015). This is a significant step towards delivering London's plans to be the ULEV capital of Europe. This will also help London meet its air quality challenge as well as provide economic benefits across the UK through investments and creating job opportunities.

The ULEV delivery plan sets out additional actions to support the uptake of electric and ULEVs. These include (GLA, 2015a):

- A commitment to ultra-low emission discount for the congestion charge
- Working with boroughs across London to develop preferential access, parking or charging in new area-based schemes, including a £2million low emission neighbourhood programme
- A £65million programme of Zero Emission capable London taxi top-up grants and decommissioning grants for taxis older than 10 years
- A trial of inductive wireless charging in the bus fleet by 2016

Interaction between national and local policies:

From the success of the programmes, the Mayor is working to share expertise with other regions in the UK to support the delivery of the retrofitting programmes.

The UK Government is planning the initial England-wide rollout of the RE:FIT programme which has been pioneered by the Greater London Authority through its Climate Change Mitigation and Energy Strategy programme. This was presented in the UK National Energy Efficiency Action Plan published in April 2014 (DECC, 2014c). The DECC has committed to the rolling out of this scheme and the initial funding for this nation-wide scheme will be delivered through local partnerships, supporting 50

public sector energy efficiency projects. As of December 2013, 60 projects had registered funding and the DECC anticipates that the RE:FIT roll out will be self-financing.

There has been a confirmed provision of over £500million to support the development of the UK's ULEVs market (DECC, 2014c). The Government has also committed to mandate a national charging network with the announcement of a £37million package of measures and grants for the installation on both private (at home) and public (in public spaces such as train stations and on-street) charging points. The Government's plans and policies set out for low carbon transport programmes included a grant of up to £5,000 to facilitate the purchase of ULEVs (DECC, 2011a). It is the Government's aspiration that by 2050 almost every car and van in the UK will be an ULEV. The Mayor's Electric Vehicle Delivery Plan for London both supports and enhances the national policy in relation to ULEVs.

Discussion / Recommendations:

Benefits

- The city can establish itself as a global leader of low carbon transition
- Increasing investments through the demonstration of the success of programmes and schemes
- Positive economic benefits from creation of jobs
- Rollout of successful programmes and schemes across the nation as the city pioneers and demonstrates the success of its plans
- Large scale programmes and schemes result in multiple benefits such as reducing fuel poverty and reducing inequalities and increases community pride and responsibilities as residents begin to see and feel the improvements in their neighbourhood
- Opportunities for research, development and innovation by involving the education sector and the business sector.
- Knowledge exchange as lessons are learnt from the city's plans and programmes

Barriers

- Uncertainty around government policy and changes in policies can be a barrier to delivering schemes and programmes aimed at reducing carbon emissions and energy consumption
- Cost and funding – the London Energy Future programmes require some private sector funding, e.g. projects in the RE:FIT need to be separately self-financed
- Some of the future funding streams have recently been closed, e.g. Warm Front (Warm Front, 2014) or cancelled, e.g. Green Deal (Green Deal, 2015)
- Barriers between landlords and tenants in commercial buildings can impact on the uptake on measures which reduce emissions and energy consumption in buildings
- High upfront cost of technologies such as the low emission vehicles is a barrier to its uptake
- Limited infrastructure such as EV charging point is a barrier to its uptake. This is being tackled with plans to increase the network of charging points across the city.
- Limited public awareness of the technologies and lack of public confidence about the variety of electric and ultra-low emission vehicles

Recommendations

- More work can be done to include all the boroughs in London through community and neighbour engagement activities. This will increase the uptake of the programmes as well as tackle any inequality issues
- Funding options should be made more accessible through the use of a mixture
- The most appropriate retrofit measures should be investigated and implemented to ensure maximum benefits.
- Evaluation and monitoring measures should be conducted.

Further information: <https://www.london.gov.uk/sites/default/files/Energy-future-oct11.pdf>

ANNEXES

REFERENCES

- BRAC & DCLG (2015). Policy paper: 2010-2015 government policy: building regulation, [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/2010-to-2015-government-policy-building-regulation/2010-to-2015-government-policy-building-regulation>
- CoM. (2015). *Covenant of Mayors*. [Online]. Available: http://www.covenantofmayors.eu/participation/covenant_map_en.html.
- CSE (2013). Green Open Homes. Available: <http://www.greenopenhomes.net/support-for-organisers>
- CSE (2014). Green Open Homes. Available: [http://www.greenopenhomes.net/downloads/file/GOH_end_of_project_summary\(2\).pdf](http://www.greenopenhomes.net/downloads/file/GOH_end_of_project_summary(2).pdf)
- Cycle to Work Alliance (CtWA). (2015). *Cycle to work* [Online]. Available: <http://www.cycletoworkalliance.org.uk/home.html>.
- DCLG (2009a). Impact assessment. Planning policy statement: eco-towns. Available: http://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukia/2009/171/pdfs/ukia_20090171_en.pdf
- DCLG (2009b). Planning Policy Statement: eco-towns. A supplement to Planning Policy Statement 1. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/7773/pps-ecotowns.pdf
- DCLG (2010a). Code for sustainable homes: a cost review. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/7810/1501290.pdf
- DCLG (2010b). Revisions to the code for sustainable homes: impact assessment. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/8558/1766290.pdf
- DCLG (2012). National Planning Policy Framework. London: Department for Communities and Local Government. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/6077/2116950.pdf
- DCLG (2013). Changes to Part L of the Building Regulations 2013: Impact Assessment. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/226965/Part_L_2013_IA.pdf
- DCLG, D., DECC,. (2015). 2010 to 2015 government policy: household energy.
- DECC (2011a). The Carbon Plan: Delivering our Low Carbon Future. Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/47613/3702-the-carbon-plan-delivering-our-low-carbon-future.pdf
- DECC (2011b). UK Report on Articles 4 and 14 of the EU End-use Efficiency and Energy Services Directive (ESD). Available:

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/48144/2289-uk-report-eu-enduse-esd.pdf

DECC (2012a). The Energy Efficiency Strategy: The Energy Efficiency Opportunity in the UK.

Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available:

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/65602/6927-energy-efficiency-strategy--the-energy-efficiency.pdf

DECC (2012b). Smart Metering Implementation Programme. Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available:

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/245736/smart_meters_domestic_leaflet.pdf

DECC (2012c). Final Stage Impact Assessment for the Green Deal and Energy Company Obligation (IA No. DECC0072). Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available:

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/42984/5533-final-stage-impact-assessment-for-the-green-deal-a.pdf

DECC (2013a). Electricity Demand Reduction – Amendment to capacity market clauses (IA No: DECC0133). Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available:

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/246126/Impact_Assessment_for_Electricity_Demand_Reduction_Policy_Options_FINAL.pdf

DECC (2013b). Energy Efficiency Strategy: 2013 Update. Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available:

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/266187/2901415_EnergyEfficiencyStrategy_acc.pdf

DECC (2014a). Community Energy Strategy: Full Report. *In*: DECC (ed.). London: Department of Energy and Climate Change

DECC (2014b). Energy Saving Opportunity Scheme. Impact Assessment. London: Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available:

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/323116/ESOS_Impact_Assessment_FINAL.pdf

DECC (2014c). UK National Energy Efficiency Action Plan. London: Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available:

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/307993/uk_national_energy_efficiency_action_plan.pdf

DECC (2014d). Third annual report on the roll-out of Smart Meters. London: Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available:

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/384190/s mip_smart_metering_annual_report_2014.pdf

DECC (2014e). Electricity Demand Reduction Pilot Scheme: Participant Handbook. London: Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available:

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/367394/EDR_participant_handbook.pdf

- DECC (2015a). Domestic Green Deal and Energy Company Obligation in Great Britain, Monthly Report. London: Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/435839/Monthly_Statistical_Release_-_GD_ECO_in_GB_June15_Final.pdf
- DECC (2015b). Electricity Demand Reduction Pilot Scheme Phase II. London: Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/435340/EDR_Participant_Handbook.pdf
- DECC (2015c). Evaluation of the Big Energy Saving Network. London: Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/405800/BE_SN_final_report1.pdf
- DECC (2015d). Community energy Strategy Update. London: Department of Energy and Climate Change. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/414446/CE_SU_FINAL.pdf
- DEFRA. (2012). *Sustainable procurement: the Government Buying Standards (GBS)* [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/collections/sustainable-procurement-the-government-buying-standards-gbs>.
- DfT (2011). Cycle to Work Scheme implementation guidance Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/11305/cycle-to-work-guidance.pdf
- DfT (2012). Guidance: Renewable transport fuels obligation. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/renewable-transport-fuels-obligation>
- DfT (2014a). Renewable Transport Fuel Obligation: Post Implementation Review. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/307437/im pact-assessment-pir.pdf
- DfT (2014b). RTFO Guidance Part One: Process Guidance. London: Department for Transport. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/301072/part-1-process-guidance-yr7.pdf
- DfT (2015). *Bikeability* [Online]. Available: http://bikeability.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/National_Standard_for_Cycle_Training_Level_ONE2.pdf.
- Energy Efficiency Watch (2013). Energy Efficiency in Europe Assessment of Energy Efficiency Action Plans and Policies in EU Member States. Available: http://www.energy-efficiency-watch.org/fileadmin/eew_documents/Documents/EEW2/United_Kingdom.pdf
- Energy Saving Trust. (2014). *FuelGood driver training* [Online]. Available: <http://www.energysavingtrust.org.uk/fuelgood-driver-training>.
- Entranze (2013). Overview of the EU-27 building policies and programs. Factsheets on the nine Entranze target countries Cross-analysis on Member-States' plans to develop their building

regulations towards the nZEB standard. Available:

http://www.entranze.eu/files/downloads/D5_1_3/ENTRANZE_Integration_of_report_D5.1_D5.2_D5.3_v03.pdf

Environment Agency (2015). Complying with the Energy Savings Opportunity Scheme.

London. Available:

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/445205/LIT_10094.pdf

ETI (2015). Energy technologies institute. Available: <http://www.eti.co.uk/>

GLA (2011) [Online] Available from: <https://www.london.gov.uk/sites/default/files/Energy-future-oct11.pdf>

GLA (2015a) Mayor unveils London's Ultra Low Emission Future as Fire Brigade joins electric revolution [Online] Available from: <https://www.london.gov.uk/media/mayor-press-releases/2015/07/mayor-unveils-london-s-ultra-low-emission-future-as-fire-brigade>

GLA (2015b). RE:FIT [Online] Available from:

<https://www.london.gov.uk/priorities/environment/energy/refit-putting-our-energy-reducing-yours> [Accessed 06/08/2015]

GOV.UK (2015a). Energy Performance Certificates [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/buy-sell-your-home/energy-performance-certificates>

GOV.UK (2015b). Heat networks delivery support. [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/heat-networks-delivery-support>

Green Deal (2015) [Online] Available from: <https://www.gov.uk/green-deal-energy-saving-measures/overview>

GVA (unknown). EPC and DEC requirements. London

HM Government (2013). The UK's Sixth National Communication and First Biennial Report under the UNFCCC. *In*: Change, D. o. E. a. C. (ed.). London.

HM Treasury (2015). Fixing the foundations: Creating a more prosperous nation. London. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/443897/Productivity_Plan_print.pdf

HMRC. (2015). *Vehicles Excise Duty* [Online]. Available:

<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/vehicle-excise-duty/vehicle-excise-duty>.

House of Commons (2013). Local Energy, Sixth Report of Session 2013-14. *In*: Committee, E. a. C. C. (ed.). London: The stationery office limited

Hutchins, R., Delmonte, E., Stannard, J., Evans, L. & Bussell, S. (2013). Assessing the role of the Plug-in Car Grant and Plugged-in Places scheme in electric vehicle take-up Department for Transport, Social Research and Evaluation Division

IEA (2012). Energy Policies of IEA Countries. The United Kingdom. *In*: Agency, I. E. (ed.). Available: http://www.iea.org/publications/freepublications/publication/UK2012_free.pdf

IEA (2015). [Online]. Available:

<http://www.iea.org/policiesandmeasures/energyefficiency/?country=United%20Kingdom>

Innovate UK (2015). Innovate UK funded projects between 2004-2015. Available:

<https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/innovate-uk-funded-projects>

Mayor of London (2009) An Electric Vehicle Delivery Plan for London. [Online] Available from:

<http://www.london.gov.uk/sites/default/files/electric-vehicles-plan.pdf> [Accessed 07/08/2015]

Newbery, B. (2014). Green open homes: changing social norms around energy behaviour. Available:

http://behaveconference.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/08/F_Bridget_Newbery_Centre_for_Sustainable_Energy.pdf

Ofgem (2014). Enforcement Guidelines. Available:

https://www.ofgem.gov.uk/sites/default/files/docs/2014/09/enforcement_guidelines_12_september_2014_published_version_1.pdf

Ofgem (2015). Licence Lite: SLC 11.3 operating guidance. Available:

https://www.ofgem.gov.uk/sites/default/files/docs/2015/04/licence_lite_slc_11.3_operating_guidance_0.pdf

Odyssee-Mure (2012). Energy efficiency profile: UK. Energy Efficiency Trends. Available:

<http://www.odyssee-mure.eu/publications/profiles/united-kingdom-efficiency-trends-policies.pdf>

OLEV (2011). Making the connection. The plug-in vehicle infrastructure strategy. Available:

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/3986/plug-in-vehicle-infrastructure-strategy.pdf

OLEV (2015a). Electric Vehicle Homecharge Scheme. Guidance for manufacturers and installers: 13 April 2015. Available:

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/434148/electric-vehicle-homecharge-scheme-guidance-for-manufacturers-and-installers-2015.pdf

OLEV (2015b). Low emission bus scheme. Guidance for participants. Available:

https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/413022/Low_Emission_Bus_Scheme_bidding_guidance.pdf

Parker, G. (2015). Housing, Eco-Towns and Garden Cities in an era of deregulation. Available:

http://www.walker-institute.ac.uk/comment/ECOtowns_Mar2015.htm

RCUK. (2014). *RCUK Energy Programme* [Online]. Available:

<http://www.rcuk.ac.uk/research/xrcprogrammes/energy/>.

Read, S. (2014). Fuel poverty support is ten times bigger in Scotland and Wales than in England.

Independent [Online]. Available: <http://www.independent.co.uk/news/uk/politics/fuel-poverty-support-is-ten-times-bigger-in-scotland-and-wales-than-in-england-9219554.html>.

RE:FIT (2015a) RE:FIT pilot [Online] Available from: <http://refit.org.uk/what-refit/background/>

RE:FIT (2015b) What has RE:FIT achieved so far? [Online] Available from: <http://refit.org.uk/what-refit/refit-achievements/>)

Sib (n.d.). [Online]. Available: <http://www.sibgroup.org.uk/energy/>

Salix(2014). [Online]. Available: <http://www.salixfinance.co.uk/>

TFL (2015) London's first all-electric bus route to be operated by Ariva [Online] Available from: <https://tfl.gov.uk/info-for/media/press-releases/2015/march/london-s-first-all-electric-bus-route-to-be-operated-by-arriva>

TRL (2013). Assessing the role of the Plug-in Car Grant and Plugged-in Places scheme in electric vehicle take-up. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/236748/research-report.pdf

TSB (2014). Annual Report and Accounts 2013-2014. Available: https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/341384/Technology-strategy-board-annual-report-and-accounts_2013-14.pdf

UK Government. (2015). *Buying or selling your home* [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/buy-sell-your-home/energy-performance-certificates>.

VCA (2013). The passenger car (Fuel consumption and CO2 emissions information) regulations. Available: <http://www.dft.gov.uk/vca/additional/files/fcb--co2/enforcement-on-advertising/vca061.pdf>

Warm Front (2014) [Online] Available from: <https://www.gov.uk/warm-front-scheme> [Accessed 07/08/2015]